

**10th Symposium on
High-Performance Marine Vehicles**

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Edited by Volker Bertram

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Welcome to the 10th HIPER Conference

Greetings from Giampiero Soncini, Patron of HIPER 2016

The maritime industry faces great challenges which will require bold and innovative solutions. Today, the informed public and legislative bodies all over the world expect that we contribute to fighting global warming and reduce our carbon footprint. But the focus on energy efficiency lets us often forget that we face many other challenges: preventing spread of invasive species, meeting the ambitious emission targets for SOx and NOx, facing crewing problems, addressing the relatively poor safety record of shipping, to name just a few. Shipping and ships will need to be revolutionized to be fit for the new era of shipping that will come and needs to come.

This simple observation corresponds with the idea of the Conference for High-Performance Marine Vehicles - Technologies for the Ship of the Future. HIPER has and will continue to promote the dialogue between technology leaders in the maritime industries as well as related fields. If the conference had not been initiated 17 years ago, it would be high time to get. As it is, we can build on a proud tradition and expand into the exciting theme of future technologies, where science fiction starts today.

While there are many aspects to tomorrow's shipping, the topic of low-crew/no-crew smart ships is particular to my heart. Advances in telecommunication and intelligent automation come together with progress on maintenance-free engine rooms in fully electric ships and new materials for ship structures. In 1988, I stated how silly it was to have a crew of 40 to 44 men on the ships sailing back then. I spoke about how ships could have the machinery room totally unmanned. I recall very well the smiles, the comments. As 30 years ago, time is on my side, and I am sure that "unmanned" vessels will sail the seas in 10 or 20 years from now.

Collectively, we will manage the progress. SpecTec is proud to sponsor HIPER 2016 and that I can be part of this exciting journey towards the future of ships and shipping – our future.

I wish everyone an inspiring exchange of ideas!

Giampiero Soncini

CEO SpecTec

Index

Giampiero Soncini <i>Homo Maritimus and Homo Informaticus: Can They Co-exist?</i>	7
Volker Bertram <i>Unmanned & Autonomous Shipping – A Technology Review</i>	10
Luigi Mascellaro <i>Monotricat Hull – Innovative High-Speed Platform</i>	25
John Almeter <i>Performance Gains from Longitudinal Concave Camber in Planing Hulls</i>	32
David Andrews <i>Unconventional Ships and Unconventional Design</i>	47
Prasanta K Sahoo, Karthik Avala, Iruthayaraju Andrews, Peña Blanca <i>CFD Analysis of Hydrodynamic Characteristics of High-speed Displacement Hull-forms fitted with Hull Vane[®]</i>	62
Michael R. Riley, Heidi Murphy, Timothy Coats <i>An Integrated Approach for Developing Rough Water Methodologies for Small High-Speed Craft Structure, Equipment, Shock Isolation Seats, and Human Performance At-Sea</i>	77
Valery O. Borusevich, Alexander V. Pustoshny, Andrei V. Sverchkov, Giorgio Trincas <i>Impact of Air Cavity Technology on Ship Drag Reduction: Experience from Research Studies</i>	94
Ruoxin Li, Qing Xiao, Lijun Li, Hao Liu <i>Multi-Body Dynamics Modelling on a Self-Propelled Pufferfish with its Application in AUV</i>	108
Enrico Ravina, Susanna Valenti <i>A Fleet of Sea-Cleaning Autonomous Units Managed by Waste-Recovery Island</i>	115
Volkmar Stenzel, Claus Schreiner, Andreas Brinkmann, Dorothea Stübing <i>Biomimetic Approaches for Ship Drag Reduction – Feasible and Efficient?</i>	131
Darren Halliday, Sam Hill, Simon Pullin <i>Autonomous Shipping – A Concept for an Autonomous Firefighting and Rescue Vessel</i>	141
Jeroen Taen, Mariano Otheguy, Robert Hekkenberg <i>Energy Efficient Maritime Accommodations</i>	152
Mary Etienne, Andrea Romano <i>The Internet of Things for Smarter, Safer, Connected Ships</i>	164
Enrico Ravina, Francesca Bertesago <i>Concept Design of Rudders Using Pneumatic Artificial Muscles</i>	172
Lars-Uve Schrader <i>Drag Reduction for Ships: Drawing Inspiration from Dolphins</i>	187

Burak Zincir, Cengiz Deniz <i>Comparison of Hydrogen Production Methods for Shipboard Usage</i>	193
Jarle A. Kramer, Sverre Steen, Luca Savio <i>Drift Forces – Wingsails vs Flettner Rotors</i>	202
Diego Meseguer Yebra <i>Future Directions towards Low-Friction Hulls</i>	217
Maurits van den Boogaard, Andreas Feys, Mike Overbeek, Joan le Poole, Robert Hekkenberg <i>Control Concepts for Navigation of Autonomous Ships in Ports</i>	225
Noah Silberschmidt, Dominic Tasker, Takis Pappas, Johannes Johannesson <i>Silverstream® System – Air Lubrication Performance Verification and Design Development</i>	236
Sverre Steen, Luca Savio, Ørjan Selvik, Vahid Hassani <i>Experience with Rim-Driven Azimuthing Thrusters on the Research Ship “Gunnerus”</i>	247
Ichiro Kumagai, Yuichi Murai, Yoshiaki Takahashi, Ross Roberts <i>Power-Saving Device for Air Bubble Generation using a Hydrofoil to Reduce Ship Drag</i>	262
Volker Bertram, Anthony Sayers <i>Combine and Conquer – Ships and Shipping of Tomorrow</i>	271
Yasuyuki Toda, Md. Mahbubar Rahman, Shingo Hashimoto, Junpei Mino <i>Development of the Osaka University Squid-Like Underwater Robot</i>	283
Denis Morais, Nick Danese, Mark Waldie <i>Ship Design, Engineering and Construction in 2030 and Beyond</i>	297
Karsten Fach <i>1, 2, 3 – How Many Hulls Should a High-Performance Vessel have?</i>	311
Cornel Thill <i>Air Lubrication Technology – Past, Present and Future</i>	317
Ciro Cannavacciuolo, Gabriel Paternoster <i>A Novel Wind-Assistance Concept – Design by CFD</i>	331
Marcis Eimanis, Janis Auzins <i>Flagella Inspired Propulsion for AUVs</i>	342
Andreas Wulf, Christof Nagel, Markus Brede <i>Concept of Local Hull-Shape Adaptation by Means of Inflatable Flow-Resistors</i>	355
Rogier Eggers <i>Operational Performance of Wind Assisted Ships</i>	366
Taro Kajihama, Yoshihisa Okada, Akinori Okazaki, Kenta Katayama, Takuya Tachikawa <i>Innovative Energy Saving Device Designed by Virtual Prototyping Method</i>	380
Thiago G. Monteiro, Henrique M. Gaspar <i>An Open Source Approach for a Conceptual Ship Design Tools Library</i>	386

Gabriel D. Weymouth <i>Biologically Inspired Force Enhancement for Maritime Propulsion and Maneuvering</i>	401
Elouan Autret, Anna Friebe, Ronny Eriksson, Kjell Dahl, Matias Waller <i>Cable Towing with an Autonomous Sailboat</i>	415
Jurrit M. Bergsma, Max van der Zalm, Jeroen F.J. Pruyn <i>3D-Printing and the Maritime Construction Sector</i>	428
Morgan Behrel, Nedeleg Bigi, Kostia Roncin, Damien Grelon, Frederic Montel, Alain Nême, Jean-Baptiste Leroux, Christian Jochum, Yves Parlier <i>Measured Performance of a 50-m² Kite on a Trawler</i>	443
Sven Albert, Thomas Hildebrandt, Stefan Harries, Matthias Reyer <i>Hydrodynamic Optimization of a Power Boat in the Cloud</i>	458
Julien Sellier <i>Opportunities for Cost Effective Composite Solutions for Future Ships</i>	473
James W. Gose, Kevin Golovin, Julio Barros, Michael Schultz, Anish Tuteja, Steven L. Ceccio, Marc Perlin <i>Biomimetic Super-Hydrophobic Coatings for Friction Reduction</i>	477
Carlo Bertorello, Ermina Begovic <i>From Nuclear Submarine to Sailing Trimaran Record The Globe Circumnavigation, The Ultimate Marine Challenge</i>	491
Florian Beuß, Jan Sender, Jens Meißner, Martin Eggert <i>Efficient and Ergonomic Assembly Processes of Sailing Yachts Based on a Modular Design</i>	504
John Calleya, Santiago Suárez de la Fuente, Rachel Pawling, Tristan Smith <i>Designing Future Ships for Significantly Lower Energy Consumption</i>	510
John Prousalidis, Gregory Grigoropoulos, Dimitrios V. Lyridis, Eleni Aloniati, Chris Bakirtzoglou, Konstantina Fountouli, Dimitra Konstantinou, Dimos Spathis, Stela Spiraj, Aggelos Themelakis, Bill Tsarsitalidis, Socraetes Tzanetos, Theo Kourmpelis <i>Design Considerations for Energy Efficient Electric Powerboats</i>	523
Index of authors	536
Call for Papers for next HIPER	

Homo Maritimus and Homo Informaticus: Can They Co-exist?

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Abstract

Shipping has immensely changed in the last 30 years, going from an almost deregulated environment, to one of the most regulated in the world. In these last 30 years, the working conditions of crews have also changed, and probably not for the best: the phenomena of criminalization of seafarers, the arrival of piracy, the economic crisis, the plethora of new rules and regulations have made their lives difficult. The use of IT can alleviate the burden, but the shipping industry is a very late adopter of advanced IT to manage ships. This paper examines some of the reasons behind this attitude.

1. IT and Shipping

Shipping industry is not fond of information technology (IT). There is resistance at all levels at the introduction of normal IT systems, which are used all over the world in any other industry.

There are many reasons for this, some not very noble, some due to ignorance, some to arrogance, some to laziness, some to personal convenience; the shipping industry suffers a lot from this lack of IT awareness. But the greatest challenge comes when dealing with introducing IT systems to a large number of people within the organization. When it is a small number of people working with IT tools, such as a Research Department, the introduction of a new software or new hardware, even if different from what previously used, is normally welcome. But try to bring something new in IT to the working masses (not to the playing ones... this is a different story) and you will be subject to a barrage of resistance: the resistance to changes.

Many IT projects fail to fulfill initial expectations because managers fail to forecast the resistance to changes and fail to cope with them.

Changing the way we work is difficult, and requires a lot of strength from the management; moreover, resistance to change can come from all levels of the organization.

2. Why people resists

There are many reasons why someone would resist a path to innovation at work:

- Belief that the change initiative is a temporary fake
- Belief that fellow employees or managers are incompetent (Lack of trust in management)
- Loss of authority or control
- Loss of status or social standing
- Lack of faith in their ability to learn new skills
- Feeling of change overload (too much too soon)
- Loss of job security
- Loss of family or personal time
- Feeling that the organization is not entitled to the extra effort

IT is perceived by most as a dangerous change to their own lifestyle. Inside the brain, the following questions will circulate, even if silently (these doubts are not shared with the colleagues):

- Will I be able to learn
- Will I look antiquate
- Will it tell my boss that I am not doing the right job
- Will it keep in memory all my mistakes
- Will it allow younger people to bypass me
- Will it make me redundant

Managing changes require identifying the people who will make it happen and the ones who will try everything to stop changes from happening

- Enthusiasts
- Followers
- Objectors
- Underground

2.1. Enthusiasts

They are fully convinced of the benefits in changes. They agree that the change will be of benefit to the organization, also because they perceive they may receive some personal gain from the change, such as a guarantee of job security, more status or a higher salary. Enthusiasts will use opportunities to broadcast approval for the change and will try to convince others of its merits. They will also model the new behavior early and will volunteer for membership of teams. These early adopters may also make good choices as trainers and coaches during the implementation process.

They are rare.

2.2. Followers

Followers range from those that are generally compliant, wishing to take the path of least resistance, to those that are initially reticent to adapt, but eventually do so once they accept the inevitability of the change. These change recipients will do what is required, but no more.

They are the majority.

2.3. Objectors

Objectors will display their resistance to change whenever the opportunity arises. They may disrupt meetings, find any excuse not to attend training, take leave and refuse to carry out instructions. Objectors will continue to use superseded systems and processes when others are taking up the new ways of doing things. Objectors are not averse to arguing with managers and fellow workers, and will try to convince others to continue with the old ways. They can be present at any level. The higher the level, the higher the probability of failure.

They are few, and can be dangerous, but can be easily identified and isolated or removed

2.4. Underground

Change recipients working for the underground have solid motivations for not making their resistance public. They may fear direct punishment, such as termination or fines, or more personal costs, such as

ridicule or loss of status and authority. Managers, who are against the change but need to be seen to be in support of it, are prime candidates for promoting underground resistance. This style of resistance is, by its nature, always covert and can take many forms. Common among these are falsifying reports, inputting incorrect data, using sarcasm, spreading rumors, amplifying issues, negating evidence.

If undetected, they will ruin every project.

3. Conclusion

When you start an IT project, you have to include in the planning also the management of the expectations of the final users, the people who will have to use the system. Failing to do so will cause heavy resistance at all levels.

Remember: Chains of habit are too light to be felt until they are too heavy to be broken.

Unmanned & Autonomous Shipping – A Technology Review

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Abstract

This paper gives an introduction to autonomous (possibly unmanned) commercial shipping. The aim is to give a rational foundation for speculations on the chances for and nature of future autonomous shipping. A historic review shows that while the vision of unmanned ships is old, it is increasingly discussed in recent years. Key tasks for unmanned shipping are discussed along with potential solutions and their maturity. Nautical tasks, machinery and cargo supervision do not pose significant hurdles for unmanned shipping. Maintenance tasks have been traditional show-stoppers, but should no longer be a major problem with future LNG powered propulsion and electrical drives (batteries or fuel cells). Non-technical hurdles include the traditionally conservative mind-set of the maritime community, legal frameworks at IMO and other regulatory bodies and doubtful economics for first adapters.

1. Introduction

We have self-driving cars, trucks, trains and unmanned planes (drones). In view of these spectacular projects, naturally questions arise concerning unmanned shipping. In fact, unmanned shipping has been the subject of speculation for at least five decades now. But more recent developments in autonomous technology used in other transport industries and related maritime fields (robotics in oil & gas, navies, oceanography and sailbot competitions) have refueled the debate.

An autonomous ship is not the same as an unmanned ship. *Porathe et al. (2013)* explain:

- “An autonomous ship is navigating and making evasive maneuvers based on an automated software system. The system and the ship are under constant monitoring by a Shore Control Center [...]. An autonomous ship does not have to be unmanned but can contain maintenance or service crews, while the bridge and/or the engine control room is unmanned.
- An unmanned ship is a ship with no humans onboard. An unmanned ship does not have to be autonomous; it can be under autonomous control but it can also be under remote control from a [Shore Control Center], or from other places (e.g. a pilot or tug boat, or a mooring supervisor).”

However, most visions for unmanned shipping extensive use of autonomous systems, often supplemented by human remote supervision and control. There are different levels of autonomy, e.g. following the Sheridan model, Table I. At the lowest level, autonomous systems just advise and aid, at the highest level replace or override human decision making and action. Automatic braking systems in cars are an example of such high-level autonomy.

Table I: Sheridan Model

1	Computer offers no assistance and human must do all
2	Computer offers a complete set of action alternatives
3	Computer narrows the selection down to a few
4	Computer suggests a solution
5	Computer executes that suggestion if the human approves
6	Computer allows human some time to veto before automatic execution
7	Computer executes automatically, then necessarily informs the human
8	Computer informs human after execution only if asked
9	Computer acts, and decides if it informs human after
10	Computer decides everything and acts autonomously, ignoring the human

1.2. Maritime autonomous technology

Maritime robotic vehicles are interesting in the context of smart or unmanned shipping, but can at best furnish only partial solutions:

- AUVs (autonomous underwater vehicles), *Caiti et al. (2012)*, *Fjellheim et al. (2015)*, feature some significant differences to ships: Radio signals cannot reach far underneath the water surface. This makes telecommunication in deeply submerged mode impossible. Underwater robots have 6 degrees of freedom (like airplanes); surface ships navigate in 3 degrees of freedom. There is much less risk of collision underwater and IMO's collision regulations do not apply to deeply submerged bodies. Underwater robots are frequently intended for short-term tasks, typically in the order of several hours. Maintenance is then no problem.
- Oceanographic unmanned surface vessels (USVs), *Caiti et al. (2012)*, are generally very slow. This changes options for collision avoidance strategies. Oceanographic USVs without engines and propellers, but often very long times between overhaul, have very different maintenance requirements from envisioned unmanned ships. Swarms of such USVs may support future commercial shipping (manned or unmanned), e.g. in weather observation and data transmission.
- Navy USVs, *Bertram (2008)*, are generally high-speed, short-range craft. Maintenance is then no problem. USVs are "boats" with limited payload and space for sensors and computing power. Some tasks are then shifted to a human supervisor. As navy vessels, they are exempted from IMO regulations. They are generally faster and much more maneuverable than cargo ships. This changes options for collision avoidance strategies.
- Sailing robots (sailbots), *Stelzer and Jafarmadar (2011)*, have become a popular research topic, partially due to several competitions such as MicroTransat challenge, Sailbot and the World Robotic Sailing Championships (WRSC). Sailbots are small and severely limited in payload. At present, they cannot transport sufficient computing power for real-time processing of complex tasks. Due to payload restrictions, standard nautical equipment such as radar is not available. Sailing boats have much more severe restrictions for maneuvering than propeller-driven ships.

One advantage of small autonomous robots is the ability to form swarms. The technology for robots to communicate and cooperate together without a human controller is a key technology for autonomous and unmanned shipping. E.g., computers on different ships in dense traffic could automatically communicate their individual route plans and resolve potential conflicts within fractions of seconds.

2. Visions and developments for unmanned/autonomous commercial shipping

The concept of unmanned or autonomous shipping is by no means new, but has evolved over a long time with variations on the theme:

- In 1898, Nikola Tesla obtained a patent for radio-based remote control of boats. In his autobiography from 1919, Tesla predicts robotic vehicles "... capable of acting as if possessed of their own intelligence and their advent will create a revolution."
- *Schönknecht et al. (1973)* envisioned fleets of unmanned cargo ships, Fig.1: "In this age of rationalisation and automation it would not be difficult to imagine a ship without a crew. [...] It is indeed quite possible that at some distant future date the captain will perform his duties in an office building on shore. In his place he will leave a computer on board ship which will undertake all the tasks of the navigator's art, or [...] controlling the ship, and will in fact perform the task much more effectively."
- During the 1980s, the Japanese "Intelligent Ship Project" aimed "at bringing about 'intelligent ships' that can function without help from the crew". Connected to the "Intelligent Ship Project", the Japan Marine Machinery Development Association formulated its vision: "The use of robot ship fleets may be seen as an advanced, yet highly practical development in international ship-

ping for the 21st century. The concept envisages a fleet consisting of a 'mother' ship, carrying a crew of 20-30, and 4-5 remote-control slave barges.”

Fig.1: Vision of future shipping: master-slave concept of Schönknecht et al. (1973) (left) and Rolls-Royce's Oskar Levander in 2015 (right)

- *Munk (1989)* states that it “is of course possible to remove crew completely”. He continues arguing that mainly for legal reasons unmanned ships were unlikely [in the then foreseeable future]. “It is at the moment impossible to state the absolute minimum number of crew for a ship with unrestricted service, but it seems difficult to get below the number of 6, which has been obtained by the Danish Ministry of Industry in connection with their project on a low-manned ship.”
- (Kai) *Levander (1994)* describes the ‘ship without crew’ for future (short sea) shipping. “A ship with no crew onboard could travel aided by the GPS chain and guided from the traffic stations. Separate lanes would be allocated to unmanned vessels. Pilots could board near the harbour and take the [ship] into port. An automated mooring system secures the [ship] to the quay.” Levander speculates more about the autonomous ship than the unmanned ship, focusing on a smart, low-crew ship: “A ship without a crew is certainly feasible, but is it also economically profitable? [...] It is today more realistic to concentrate on a minimum manning of 4...6 crew onboard and shore based maintenance and support.”
- *Kaeding and Bertram (1996)* present a case study for an unmanned Panmax containership. They conclude that such a ship would be feasible, but - mainly due to maintenance and reliability issues - financially unattractive.
- *Payer (1996)* states: “using the capabilities of automation, data acquisition, telecommunication technology in combination with Artificial Intelligence, we can imagine an unmanned, computer guided ship. [...] Such a system is feasible today [...]”.
- *Bucknall and Freire (2003)* present a concept of an unmanned container feeder, using a predicted shortage of skilled labor as main argument for unmanned shipping. The concept is largely based on remote control from vessel traffic services. The feeder makes shore-based maintenance feasible, as times between ports are relatively short. A fully automated mooring system based on vacuum pad technology replaces the traditionally labor-intensive mooring lines. The electric propulsion configuration lowers failure rates, but increases life-cycle costs.
- *Barnett et al. (2005)* describe a scenario for unmanned shipping: “A ship is taken from its berth to the outer harbour limit by a pilot and other shore-based port personnel. At the fairway buoy, the pilot sets automatic navigation, propulsion and communications parameters and disembarks, leaving the vessel to proceed on its voyage with no one on board. At its destination, a pilot boards and the vessel is navigated to the berth by a pilot and docked with the assistance of tugs and a mooring gang as necessary. The voyage is controlled from pilot to pilot from ashore. All propulsion, cargo care, navigation and fire control systems can be monitored and fully controlled from the shipping company's shore office and/or an ocean control centre.” In a survey, over 80% of the respondents thought that this scenario was feasible within 25 years.
- The MUNIN project, www.unmanned-ship.org, intends to demonstrate the feasibility of unmanned bulk carrier shipping, *Rodseth and Burmeister (2012)*. The project includes autonomous navigation, autonomous engine control, and shore-based remote control with necessary communication links. The project will also investigate the legal implications of autonomous shipping. A

bulk carrier was chosen as it operates typically between only two ports and the cargo does not require much human supervision.

- Oskar Levander (Rols-Royce) reignited the discussion on unmanned ships in presentations and interviews in 2013. “The idea of a remote-controlled ship is not new, it has been around for decades but the difference is the technology now exists,” [Financial Times, 26 Dec 2013].
- In 2014, DNV GL presented a concept for an unmanned container feeder for Norwegian territorial waters, ReVolt, www.dnvgl.com/technology-innovation/revolt/index.html.

Fig.2: Unmanned container ship concepts: left: *Kasai and Bertram (1996)*; right: *Rolls-Royce (2013)*

All proposed unmanned ship concepts can be classified into (combinations) of three main approaches:

- “Shore Captain” concept (remote control via satellite)
The control system is transferred ashore. The ship retains only a largely self-regulating propulsion plant together with the equipment needed for reception, transmission and decoding of the control signals received from the shore and supervision of on-board systems. Ship shore centers would feature crews with different training background and experience, similar to on-board crews, but assigned to several ships at the same time, *Porathe (2014)*. Qualification and certification standards for such ship shore-center operators are yet to be developed and flag states and port states would have to find consensus on sufficient and safe manning requirements for such shore centers.
- “Master/Slave” concept (remote control within line of sight)
One or more unmanned 'slave ships' are remotely controlled from a 'master' escort ship, Fig. 1. Pilot or tug boats may e.g. escort ships in the vicinity of ports.
- “Captain Computer” concept (autonomous ships)
The ship is equipped with sufficient hardware and software to perform all tasks and decisions using 'Artificial Intelligence' (AI).

In practice, a mix of local and remote control will be employed with redundancy for vital systems in case the communication link breaks down or local systems fail.

For unmanned (or even autonomous) shipping, there are technical, legal, economic and emotional barriers to overcome. Let us look first at the technical issues.

3. Gap analysis for technical aspects of unmanned / autonomous ship operation

3.1. Collision & grounding avoidance

While it may be impossible to create a system (human or computer based) that guarantees 100% collision avoidance, autonomous systems for collision avoidance must demonstrate that they are at least as safe as ships under manual control. In classical navigation, the crew on the bridge performs the two key tasks of obstacle detection and collision avoidance (planning and execution).

Autonomous collision avoidance may use the same information sources as used by crews today

(radar, transponders, electronic charts), but would need to compensate for the human vision and hearing of crews on board of manned ships. In classical navigation, human vision is the “last line of defense”. If radar and transponders do not notice an obstacle, human vision is supposed to detect and classify it. However, human vision is poor at night and in bad weather. Similarly, in thick fog, human hearing is of limited value. Detecting distance and often even direction is difficult for humans based on sound which may be diffracted by sea and even fog itself. Noisy environment (own ship and weather) impedes hearing other ships. One option for unmanned ships may be using remote sight and hearing, i.e. using cameras and microphones and remote operators to supply required information for sufficient situation awareness.

Shipping should be based on intelligent use of all sensor approaches with counter-checks. Complementary technologies could augment present detection capabilities. Prime candidates for such complementary technologies are:

- Machine vision - Various machine-vision approaches for marine obstacle avoidance have been proposed, e.g. *Gal (2011)*, *Huntsberger et al. (2011)*, but so far with limited success. *Kumlu (2012)* presents a completely autonomous ship type recognition system based on color images combined with ARPA (Advanced Radar Plotting Aid) to supply distance and course information of the target ship. The obtained accuracy is 93%. However, this system requires a data base of ship types. Machine vision at sea is a particular challenge, due to changes in illumination (night, fog) and sea state (changing/moving environmental pattern). Infra-red cameras in addition to regular cameras may improve detection rates. In general, technologies that improve human vision / situation awareness will also help autonomous systems.
- Laser-based systems - Ladar (a.k.a. Lidar) may detect objects that radar will not, e.g. non-metallic objects. Ladar systems with ranges of up to 2 km even under water are expected by 2020. Ladar may become “a very valuable complementary device to traditional radar-based techniques”, *Jimenez and Seco (2009)*.
- Extended ECDIS - In the future, we may see rapid updates on slowly drifting obstacles such as icebergs. Already, there are internet-based services to track icebergs using ship reports and satellite observation, e.g. www.icebergfinder.com. The information could be automatically imported in ECDIS and guide human as well as autonomous navigation.
- Remote vision – Shore-based operators could access real-time images from cameras on board an unmanned ship and resolve (rare) issues of pattern recognition that require human judgement.

Avoidance path planning involves mainly rule-based reasoning, following IMO’s COLREGs (collision avoidance regulations). In addition, crew members follow intuitively own strategies of when and where to initiate maneuvers. IMO’s COLREGs consist of two types of rules: “Hard” rules are straight-forward to code into a collision avoidance system (e.g. motorized vessels must yield to sailing vessels). Problems may still appear if input is uncertain, e.g. in diagnosing whether another vessel is a sailing vessel. “Soft” rules are open to interpretation and depend on the maneuverability and speed of the ship (e.g. the ship with right of way should initiate “last-minute” evasive maneuver if the target ship fails to give right of way). Here, the collision avoidance system must be equipped with additional rules that mimic qualitative human assessment. Fuzzy logic is an obvious choice to cope with gradual changes from “safe” to “risky”.

Nautical simulators with experienced captains and maneuvering characteristics for a given ship can elucidate “common practice” for maneuvering in situations that are open to interpretation. Expert systems may then incorporate common-practice rules. Typically the development of such an expert system requires several iterations in which the expert system is observed by domain experts (ship masters) and deviations from human decisions point to further rules to be added.

Prototype systems for autonomous collision avoidance date back to the 1990s, *Bertram (2000)*, e.g. the Japanese SuperBridge system, *Kasai and Bertram (1996)*, or the American Shipboard Piloting Expert System (SPES) and the SmartBridge system, *Grabowski (1999)*. As these systems are

company or country specific, the market has yet to develop globally available solutions. Similarly, intelligent traffic management systems have been developed and field-tested since the late 1990s. “These systems have grown from standalone intelligent piloting aids to embedded intelligent systems within a distributed information system, i.e., ship and shore-based information systems. Originally, these decision aids focused on enhancing the performance of individual vessels and pilots in the waterway. Currently, they also coordinate traffic interaction between multiple vessels on the waterway as well as distribute intelligent reasoning which underlies this coordination to all concerned parties on the waterway: to vessels currently on the waterway, to vessel traffic controllers facilitating the flow of traffic, and to vessels planning to be on the waterway in the near future,” *Grabowski (1999)*.

Autonomous collision avoidance systems could relieve ship crews of dull watch tasks which require constant vigilance. Completely autonomous collision & grounding avoidance would require overcoming several barriers, such as identification of obstacles with weak signature, special ship types (such as sailing vessels as long as these are given right of way in COLREG), and regulatory permission to use higher levels of autonomy (execution rather than advice).

3.2. Other navigational and port tasks

While collision and grounding avoidance receives the most attention in the discussion about autonomous ship operation, there are assorted other navigational tasks that need to be considered:

- Voyage planning is already often shore-based. *Walther et al. (2014)* present a route planning concept for unmanned ships, both for strategic and operational route planning.
- Voyage execution involves consideration of environmental loads on ships. Experienced ship masters can “feel” when the ship is subject to excessive loads. On-board stress monitoring or motion analysis systems may then be installed to substitute the human sensory input.
- Berthing is a difficult and complicated operation, even for experienced ship masters. The complexity of the berthing task depends on ship type:
 - Larger ships without special manoeuvring equipment (side thrusters, podded drives, etc.) need tug assistance. Such berthing operations for autonomous ships were tested successfully in computer simulations, *Takai and Ohtsu (1990)*.
 - Smaller ships and highly manoeuvrable ships (e.g. cruise vessels and ferries) usually manage berthing without tug assistance. For such a ship, fully automatic berthing using an optical system was demonstrated in sea trials, *Ohtsu et al. (1991)*. Alternatively, narrow radar beams, *Van Rees et al. (2004)*, differential GPS and suction or electro-magnet systems for final berthing and quay-side attachment may be used.
- Tug assistance in port and in emergency situations (e.g. engine failure) requires establishing communication and physical links. All the required communication infra-structure is already in place. Tug operators should obtain log-in permissions to the towed ships commands if the ship is unmanned. Physical links may be established using cooperative robotics as described in *Bruzzzone et al. (2013)*, *Bibuli et al. (2014)*, Fig.4. The system would require installation of additional equipment on autonomous ships and tugs. If there is sufficient demand and motivation for autonomous ships, this should be no obstacle.

Fig.3: Electro-optical system Fig.4: Concept (left) and field test (right) for robotic tow-link system, for berthing
Bruzzone et al. (2013)

- Emergency response requires quick decisions, often under stressful conditions, based on incomplete information, and sometimes by only moderately experienced officers. Here autonomous systems offer significant progress. Autonomous damage control systems are likely to be accepted readily as there are no emotional barriers to rapid emergency response. (Smarter sprinkler systems are more readily accepted than smarter navigational systems.) Assorted expert systems for emergency response have been developed since the 1980s, *Kaeding and Bertram (1996)*. More advanced systems cross-reference functionalities, e.g. firefighting and ballasting. Future firefighting systems may employ robotic technology to couple diagnostic cognitive skills for fire detection and response planning with mobility in execution of fire-fighting. Examples are:
 - Robotic arms configured with multiple fire suppression agents and infrared imaging, *Ditizio et al. (1995)*.
 - SAFFiR (Shipboard Autonomous Firefighting Robot), a humanoid autonomous robot capable of finding and suppressing shipboard fires and working seamlessly with human firefighters.

Intelligent damage control systems may also reconfigure auxiliary systems (electrical networks, piping networks, data networks, etc.) in response to damaged ship scenarios.

- Communication for ships will increase in any case beyond the now usual ship-to-ship/ship-to-shore communication. For highly automated ship operation, all on-board systems have to be efficiently linked with each other. Data exchange with other ships and with shore stations has to be performed automatically. Transponders communicate already much of the information between ship and Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) automatically, including ship identity, course over ground, heading, position and status. Further information, such as ship type, draft, dangerous cargo, intended routes, etc. could be requested when needed. This information will support collision avoidance systems overcoming current challenges with ship-type identification (for sailing vessels) and target acquisition in poor visibility. Various automatic subsystems, external communication, and sensors will create a flood of data. On each level, data must be screened and condensed, filtering unnecessary data before passing it on to other systems or the main operating system. Such filtering techniques have already been developed, but further work is required as the size of the systems grows. Future systems will have to work on a 'management by exception' basis, i.e. performing most tasks locally and only informing superior systems (with the human being the most superior system) if data indicate the possibility of malfunctions or threats. *Rødseth and Tjora (2014)* present details of the system architecture of unmanned ships. Exponentially growing satellite bandwidth is expected to furnish the required connectivity for future data exchanges, *Laag (2015)*.

3.3. Cargo-related tasks

Cargo needs onboard supervision for reasons of safety (cargo shifting, fires), security (theft, tampering, stowaways) and preserving cargo quality (livestock, refrigerated goods including LNG). The diligence of automated systems may outweigh their disadvantages for cargo related tasks. Depending on ship and cargo type, requirements and ease of automation vary:

- For bulk carriers and tankers, no special considerations appear to be necessary.
- For container vessels, cargo supervision may be required for certain container cargo types, e.g. refrigerated containers under deck. Here failure of refrigeration units may cause concern.
- For multi-purpose vessels, transport of refrigerated cargo below deck is not usual, but the trade of these ships makes them unlikely candidates for low-crew, no-crew shipping.
- For LNG carriers, Japanese researchers have developed and tested systems for automatic fault detection, diagnosis and corrective actions since the 1990s. Such systems have already been installed on a number of LNG carriers.

All cargo documents could be digital with (automated) electronic transmission to ports and other stakeholders. The “Internet of Things” foresees that containers and other unit cargo will have their own chips and near-field communication, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_of_Things, *Etienne and Sayers (2016)*. *Levander (1994)* already predicted this development: “Coded ‘intelligent’ cargo units inform the automated loading cranes of their destination. The cargo units are unloaded directly on road trucks and sent to their final destination [...]” This general trend driven by logistics will also benefit cargo handling as it opens the door for automatic identification and tracking of cargo.

3.4. Machinery operation

Kaeding and Bertram (1996) discussed potential automation for machinery operation and identified maintenance issues for diesel engines as a major show-stopper for unmanned shipping. LNG as a fuel is a major game changer in this context, reducing machinery maintenance drastically. Maintenance requirements will further decrease when switching from diesel generators to fuel cells and batteries. Besides the reduction of maintenance-prone moving parts, the redundancy in electric or hybrid propulsion systems makes unmanned shipping scenarios more realistic. The general trends towards more sensors on board will promote condition-based maintenance schemes avoiding unscheduled repair work, *Rødseth and Mo (2014)*. In summary, with the advent of LNG as fuel, autonomous machinery operation at least for the duration of a complete ship voyage appears feasible. Maintenance issues are no longer a show-stopper.

4. Non-technical challenges

The technology for autonomous shipping is arguably already available. However, there are non-technical issues that stand in the way of unmanned or even more autonomous shipping.

4.1. Economic considerations

Little attention has been paid so far to the economy of unmanned ships. The enthusiasts of unmanned shipping frequently overestimate savings and underestimate costs. “A ship without a crew is certainly technically feasible, but is it also economically profitable? [...] A reduction in the crew cost by investment in sophisticated [technology] both onboard the ship and ashore might add more costs, than what is saved [by] having no crew onboard,” *Levander (1994)*. *Kaeding and Bertram (1996)* come to a similar conclusion for a Panmax containership, finding unmanned operation economically unattractive. However, twenty years later it is worthwhile to have a second look.

Typical discussion points for the economies of autonomous and/or unmanned shipping are:

- Liability & insurance costs - Suppliers of autonomous technology for commercial shipping declare their systems generally as “advisory” to avoid liability issues. With time and experience, more confidence in autonomous systems may overcome liability concerns. But residual risks will remain and suppliers will require additional financial incentives for taking such risks. Although autonomous systems are expected to increase safety, there may be an initial phase with higher insurance fees than for conventional ships. With proven performance, eventually the insurance fees should then be lower, reflecting the higher level of safety.
- Piracy - Currently, pirates take ship, cargo and crew, demanding and receiving ransom for all. Unmanned ships may actually be safer than manned ships in this respect. Unmanned ships may have shut-down mechanisms for main propulsion and maneuvering systems. In this case, pirates would require ocean-going tugs to get ship and cargo into friendly ports. A new concern is cyber-jacking where criminals obtain electronic control of unmanned ships. This is a serious concern also for sea traffic management and largely autonomous, but manned shipping. Awareness of the cyber-security issue starts to spread in the maritime industry and at least partial solutions are on the horizon, *Ervik (2015)*, *Rødseth and Lee (2015)*. In summary, unmanned ships will not eliminate the problem of piracy, but may face similar risk levels as manned ships in this regard.
- Building costs – Win some, lose some. There are savings and additional expenses, e.g.:

- Deckhouses and accommodation
- Life-saving equipment
- + Additional equipment for automation (sensors, communication, computers, software)
- + High-quality equipment for reduced maintenance work or higher reliability
- + Additional equipment to have redundancy in key systems
- + Additional security systems (against terrorism, cyber-jacking or piracy)

Whether the unmanned ship has higher or lower building costs than the manned ship depends then on many assumptions.

- Lower resale value (initially) - The first autonomous ships are likely to operate in territorial waters only. In this case, a national authority may grant permission to operate even though regulations for international ship operation are not fulfilled. With flag state and port state approval limited to one country only, the resale value of such a ship would be very low.
- Crew costs - Crew costs are often cited as motivation in proposal for unmanned ships. If all costs are considered (including fuel costs and depreciation costs) crewing costs are relatively low, e.g. 4% for a 4250 TEU vessel in 2012 [internal DNV GL Maritime Advisory study]. For unmanned ships, more personnel may be needed for remote surveillance and work in harbour, e.g. to keep the maintenance times within the time for loading/discharging. The increased on-shore personnel costs must be included in a realistic cost-benefit assessment. For smart ships with a reduced crew and assorted automated systems, some argue that higher qualified crews will be needed; others argue that on the contrary smart ships will be easier to operate and require less training. The actual costs for training and availability of trained crews will depend on the degree of automation and the degree of user-friendliness of future designs for autonomous systems.
- Crewing problems - Another issue driving “crew friendly” ships may be scarcity of good crews. The crewing market is a free and rather transparent market, where the best ships may attract the best officers. Concerns about shortage of qualified crew and subsequent competition among ship operators for qualified officers were a driving force behind the Japanese “Intelligent Ship Project”. However, *BIMCO (2016)* states a generally balanced job market for seafarers, albeit with some shortages for officers and a surplus in ratings. Whether significant crew shortages will be a recurring issue in the future remains to be seen.

The additional costs make net cost savings for autonomous shipping debatable, especially since future requirements for systems (“you would have these anyhow on board a ship in the future”) and future costs of automation equipment (“prices of sensors, computers and hardware are decreasing rapidly”) are by nature speculative.

4.2. Regulations

The lack of a legal framework for unmanned shipping is a fundamental hurdle. Several issues need to be addressed within the maritime legal framework, foremost IMO regulations, before we may see commercial unmanned shipping. For example, many international maritime conventions are stated to apply to “ships”. Manned ships with some autonomous systems fall clearly under this definition, while small unmanned surface vessels do not. Whether unmanned cargo vessels are treated as “ships”, thus have to follow all international requirements for manned ships, is yet to be formalized. Similarly, it is not clear whether a remote operator in a shore center is the “captain” addressed in current maritime regulations. Flag states and port states will need to agree on the interpretation of the applicability of existing regulations. *Hooydonk (2014)* is recommended for an initial appreciation of the tasks ahead for the maritime legal community.

Of the many issues and details to be addressed, let us look at three frequently raised concerns:

- Minimum manning regulations - Flag states impose lower limits for commercial ship manning. These are binding for international shipping. These regulations are often copied or only slightly modified for shipping in territorial waters governed by national regulations. There is some tacit consensus between port states and flag states on minimum manning, with only small variations

between different flag states. For unmanned ships, future regulations would be guided most likely by an “equivalent safety” approach adopted in many recent additions to maritime regulations, following a goal-based rather than prescriptive legal philosophy. One possibility may be a separate registry for unmanned ships.

- Seafarers in distress - Various international frameworks address the legal and moral obligation of helping persons in distress at sea, most prominently SOLAS. The legal situation of unmanned ships is yet to be defined. If unmanned (tele-operated) ships are obliged to help seafarers in distress, we may need robotic devices to assist seafarers in distress. However, retrieval of seafarers and subsequent (medical and other) care are unsolved problems. One possibility is exempting unmanned autonomous ships (the same as unmanned oceanographic platforms) from the obligation to assist seafarers in distress.
- Evaluation of safety of autonomous systems - Autonomous systems will reduce the number of accidents due to human error. However, decision-making of “intelligent” (machine learning) systems may introduce different risks. New generations of increasingly autonomous systems will require a new approach to safety evaluation of these systems. *Payer (1996)* sees classification societies as the stakeholders for finding such approaches: “Classification societies are taking over the task to assure the reliability of the components and of the system and to ensure the optimum interaction between the automation system and the crew.” Processes for evaluating autonomous systems may resemble the processes for certification of competence applied to human crews: a combination of loosely monitored regular performance combined with simulator testing of dangerous or critical situations.

For international, unmanned cargo shipping, a multitude of IMO regulations will need to be changed:

1. SOLAS (Safety of Life at Sea), requiring e.g. life-saving devices and safe manning
2. GMDSS Manual (Global Maritime Distress and Safety system), requiring on-board personnel qualified for distress and safety communications (linking to SOLAS)
3. ISPS Code (International Ship and Port Facility Security), requiring crew to undertake regular security inspections of ship, cargo and stores
4. ISM Code (International Safety Management), requiring ships to be manned with qualified, certificated and medically fit seafarers
5. STCW Convention (Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping), requiring a watch physically present on the bridge
6. COLREGs (Collision regulations), requiring at all times a proper look-out by sight and hearing (linking to STCW)
7. SAR Convention (Maritime Search and Rescue), requiring assistance in SAR operations including retrieval of seafarers from the sea and subsequent care
8. International Convention on Salvage, requiring assistance to persons in danger of being lost at sea (linked to SAR convention).
9. SUA Convention (Suppression of Unlawful Acts of Violence), requiring consideration of piracy and cyber-jacking in the conception and operation of unmanned ships.
10. CLC Convention (Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage), where liability clauses need to be clarified for autonomous ships, addressing issues of negligence, third-party liability and salvage claims.
11. LLMC Convention (Convention of Limitation of Liability for Marine Claims), similar to CLC
12. ILLC Convention (International Load Line Convention), requiring protection and safe passage of crews. It is unclear whether this would apply to unmanned ships as its main objective is protection of crew on board. It may still be required to explicitly state in the ILLC convention that it does not apply to unmanned ships.

In addition to these IMO regulations, ILO (International Labour Organization) requires adequate accommodation of crews and sufficient manning. At least some clarifying statements are then needed for unmanned ships. Ships that are only occasionally manned (e.g. for maintenance or piloting) will still have to comply with all regulations for crew accommodations and protection at work on ships.

Some of the changes may be small, e.g. adding “or with equivalent safety on unmanned vessels” or “This convention does not apply to ... unmanned vessels”. But even such small changes require international consensus and the usual time-consuming processes. Other convention will require major changes or even new conventions for unmanned shipping. In view of scope and depth of required changes, a time frame of at least 20 years appears likely before we see a solid legal foundation for unmanned shipping. In view of discord on the topic, an even longer time frame may be needed before collective confidence prevails in the maritime industry.

4.3. Ethics and maritime culture

The marine industry views the issue of unmanned ships with much skepticism. Opposition to the vision of unmanned shipping is also based on some “softer” issues connected to the maritime culture. *Barnett et al. (2005)* summarize the findings of a formal study on alternative manning structures on ships: “One major conclusion of the participants was that, although technically feasible, unmanned ships were unlikely to appear in the foreseeable future for commercial and political reasons.” Considerable consensus was found that unmanned ships might be technically feasible by 2030, but “the opinion of the respondents was split on both the desirability and the likelihood of adoption.”

Key issues in this respect are:

- Conservative attitude in maritime industry - Shipping is a conservative industry. There are good reasons for this: “There are many reasons for this [resistance to the introduction of IT systems in the shipping industry], some not very noble, some due to ignorance, some to arrogance, some to laziness, some to personal convenience,” *Soncini (2014)*. There are also good reasons for the conservatism in the industry. Ships represent very expensive assets. High capital investment goes hand in hand with low risk taking.
- Society’s intolerance of machine error - Public opinion plays a key role in driving marine regulations. Being human, we can forgive human error much more easily than technical failure. Our tolerance for human failures and intolerance for technical failure translates into higher liability claims for failing machines than for failing humans. High-profile accidents due to human error may swing the balance in favour of autonomous systems, but even more so accidents due to failures of autonomous systems will impede adoption of new technology.
- Ego problems and emotions - *Schönknecht et al. (1973)* addressed already the problem of emotional barriers: “[...] it is not difficult to imagine an unmanned, remotely controlled ship [...]. Much more difficult would it be to say goodbye to a profession that has inspired the fantasies of adolescents and adults alike: the captain of a ship.” Many members of the maritime industry cannot imagine that computers and telecommunication may replace humans on board ships. Objectively, professional and prudent seafarers have (some) capabilities superior to machines at present, foremost common sense needed in unanticipated situations. A recurrent argument for human crews is the complexity of the ship and the ocean environment, which is compounded by the long duration of sea voyages. Progress in information and communication technologies may narrow or eliminate existing gaps, and machines are certainly superior in speed, reliability, monitoring rare events and many other aspects with relevance to safer shipping. Emotional acceptance of technology comes gradually. Sometimes the process requires a new generation which grew up with a new technology and not only accepts it, but demands it.
- Solidarity with seafarers - Seafarers and trade unions look with concern at ideas which (at least in their perception) implicitly devalue their profession, may threaten employment and degrade working conditions. IMO, several national authorities and non-governmental organizations have voiced concerns regarding low-crew ships with increased work load for remaining crews. Whether this is actually an argument for or against autonomous systems depends on the implementation of these systems. Poorly designed (partial) automation may result in boredom, fatigue and stress, ultimately making the seafarer profession unattractive and shipping less safe. This is detrimental to our goals and values in the maritime industry. Human factors and ergonomics

should play a larger role in the design of autonomous systems to accelerate the process of acceptance in the marine community.

5. Conclusions

A key argument for further automation is the human factor. “Human errors range from misjudgement to ignorance, from folly to mischief. The errors are intensified and more likely in times of excessive stress and panic. [...] Obviously automation, automatic navigation systems and judgment and decision-making by knowledge-based systems can considerably improve this situation,” *Payer (1996)*.

Autonomous systems could perform most of the tasks of present-day crews, although commercially available systems with sufficient maturity have yet to be developed in many cases. In short: The state of the art is there, but not yet state of the industry.

Technical developments and general acceptance (and subsequently legal frameworks) will evolve gradually. At each stage, we will review and learn, before moving on to the next level of autonomy. As with many other technical “revolutions”, we may be disappointed by how little progress is made within a year and we may be surprised how much progress there is in a decade. For now, we should focus on the “smart ship”, a user-friendly and much safer ship which will familiarize a wider maritime community with possibilities of autonomous technology.

Most likely, the first applications of unmanned ship technology will be found in national territorial waters by-passing slow IMO regulations. I see suitable candidates for unmanned ships e.g. in:

- Tugs and fire-fighting boats as proposed by Robert Allan in Canada, Fig. 5. The risky operation and possibly easier operation from a higher vantage point are arguments in favour of unmanned operation.
- Ferries as proposed by *Levander (2016)*. Ferries are among the first ships to adopt fully electric technology, Fig. 6. They also operate on fixed routes where they may be given right of way.

It will then take probably another 20-30 years before we see wider adoption of international (e.g. transpacific) unmanned cargo shipping. Prototype testing with special dispense from IMO regulations for research purposes may appear in half that time.

Fig. 5: RAMORA unmanned tug concept, source: Robert Allan

Fig. 6: All-battery powered ferry *Ampere* in 2015

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Monotricat Hull – Innovative High-Speed Platform

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Abstract

The "Monotricat" hull is the first naval hull energy recovery high hydrodynamic efficiency navigating on a formation of spray self-produced. Its technology, thanks to its innovative architecture, is able to achieve an energy saving of over 20% (certified) and also ensuring safety, navigational stability and comfort. These results were certified by studies in Towing Tank and C.F.D. The reduction of the resistance, as opposed to other solutions which introduce air under pressure below the hull (ASV hulls), is obtained thanks to the particular architecture able to pick up the sprays from the wave formation of the bow. This is therefore a technology able to reduce the viscous friction that limits the speed of the boats, the main cause of the limitation of the speed of the vessels. The Monotricat hull is also patented internationally to cover its innovative technology.

1. Introduction

The need to have naval units ever faster pushed the ship design to design hull shapes with increasingly higher performance thanks to the use of lightweight materials such as aluminum, and more powerful engines, etc., but without substantially modifying the traditional forms of hull. The patented Monotricat hull with its high hydrodynamic efficiency represents an evolution of the traditional hull architectures, <http://www.monotricat.net>. Its shape is adapted to recover wave formation produced at the bow and sprays associated with in order to reduce the resistance making it 20% more efficient than comparable planing hulls. The Monotricat overcomes the distinction between displacement and planing hulls, because it operates both at displacement and at planing speeds with an almost straight resistance curve. The innovative hull design could be seen as a hybrid between a monohull and a catamaran, navigating on self-produced spray. The design has been tested in model tests and sea trials.

2. Innovative hull

The hull shape features a deep-V bow that widens with an increasing angle until it becomes flat towards the stern. In the central part, the central hull is flanked by two small side blades, turning into a trimaran. The stern section is a catamaran with the bottom connecting between the two blades immersed in water. The thin bow creates a waves and spray that are picked up by the side blades and conveyed below the hull, where the kinetic energy of water, forced between the two blades and the bottom of the hull, generates a pressure distribution that lifts the stern. This lift is compensated by an equal hydrodynamic lift of the bow. Sprays, positioning itself between the bottom of the hull and the water, break the "boundary layer" reducing the viscous friction of water.

Fig.1: Monotricat Hull Shape

Fig.2: Spray self-produced - Towing Tank Test CNR-INSEAN 16 kn (left) and 18 kn (right)

Fig.3: Spray self-produced - Towing Tank Test CNR-INSEAN 20 kn (left) and 24 kn (right)

The amount of spray and its distribution between the hull and the water is directly proportional to the speed of the hull, and therefore to the amplitude of the boundary layer detachment. This results in a proportional reduction of the resistance: the greater the amount of spray interposed between the hull and the water, the greater the reduction of the resistance. The hull behaves like an ASV (Air Support Vessel) but without the need of introduce air pressure below the hull, thanks to its particular architecture that allows to capture the spray generated from the bow. This technology can reduce the viscous friction which limits the boat speed, the main cause of the limitation of the speed of the vessels.

3. Sea trials and Experiments

3.1. Tests in open water and in Towing Tank

Several models were made and numerous towing tests and self-propulsion tests conducted, both in calm waters and in rough seas for comfort and navigation tests. Model tests were performed in the towing tanks of the University of Trieste and at INSEAN in Rome. The model tests confirmed a unique, almost straight “resistance curve”.

Fig. 4: Self-propelled model hull navigating on Bolsena Lake

Fig. 5: Resistance curve Monotricat hull from towing tank at Trieste University

Fig. 6: Resistance at different speeds in INSEAN's towing tank

Fig.7: Resistance curve from towing tank at Trieste University 2008

Fig.8: Monotricat hull at INSEAN's towing tank

The model tests confirmed the exceptional hydrodynamic efficiency of this new concept. For comparison, Table I shows data for the "Monotricat" hull and the similar sized Shuttle 28 m of the renowned Ferretti shipyard, demonstrating the significantly higher performance of the Monotricat.

Table I: Monotricat (Insean model tests) and Shuttle 28 (Magazine "Boats", may 2015, p.92)

	Shuttle 28	Monotricat
Length	28.31 m	28.00
Beam	7.00 m	8.77 m
Disp. Max.	106 t	114 t
Engines	2 x 1200 hp MAN	2 x 1200 hp MAN
Speed	15.4 kn	19.5 kn
Range @ 13.5 kn	640 nm	1100 nm

3.2. CFD investigation

Until a few years ago, the complex spray under the Monotricat hull had prevented reliable CFD (computational fluid dynamics) investigations at INSEAN. In 2010, a European research program allowed CFD studies at the High Performance Computing center of the KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm. The simulations allowed demonstrating the "scalability" between the towing tests at INSEAN and the full-scale vessel (24 m long, 7.40 m wide, 70 t displacement).

Fig.9: Volume mesh CFD

Subsequently, the hull was optimized in Italy using a CFD. The optimization shifted volume forward compensating for the aft lift to push the speed beyond 21-22 kn. As a result, we see again an straight resistance curve, maintaining a positive trim between 1° and 2° max.

Fig.10: Trim for original hull v0 and CFD-modified hull v5 (left) and resistance for v5(right)

We also varied the length:beam ratio and the initial trim in the range of $\pm 0.5^\circ$ to see how trim sensitive the design is. This resulted in maximum 10% variations over the speed range, but virtually no change near the design speed of 21 kn, Fig.11.

Fig.11: Effect of variation of initial trim

4. Operational experience

For ten years now, a Monotricat design has operated regularly on Lake Bolsena in Italy, used for underwater research and diving courses. This boat has 7.30 m length, 2.40 m beam, an inboard engine of 180 hp, 4 t displacement and a normal speed of 26 kn, with an excellent hull efficiency ($r/t = 0.126$). Videos of the vessel in operation are stored on www.monotricat.net. The videos show that the hull leans slightly outwards in turns, as is typical for displacement hulls.

5. Results

The large hydrodynamic efficiency of the Monotricat hull, superior to other existing hulls, allows a drastic reduction of fuel costs, ensuring a considerable economic saving. For working vessels or

passenger transporting vessels, the design allows larger beam and thus higher stability without significant fuel penalties. For pleasure craft, the beam is generally chosen based on mooring requirements.

The wave formation confined between the side blades and the wet-deck transforms to lift of the aft region, compensating the hydrodynamic lift of the bow region. This makes the Monotricat rather robust in terms of load variations. The dynamic changes in the pressure distribution also give an inherent roll stability which makes further anti-roll devices unnecessary.

6. Conclusions

The Monotricat hull features unique hydrodynamic performance, compared to other high-speed concepts on the market. It may contribute to a revitalization of the high-speed craft sector.

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Performance Gains from Longitudinal Concave Camber in Planing Hulls

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Abstract

The addition of longitudinal concave camber can significantly reduce drag of planing hulls in some applications. The lift of the concave camber has a comparatively aft center of pressure and this coupled with its additional lift can reduce trim and cause the bow to dig in. Several approaches and design techniques are described in this paper to avoid or at least reduce the issue of the bow digging in. One of the approaches discussed is partial hydrofoil support.

1. Introduction

The traditional mono-hull planing hull has predominantly straight buttocks except forward to accommodate the bow and at the stern to accommodate transom wedges. Almeter and Newman (2014) discuss how a simple concave cambered surface can significantly increase lift and improve the Lift to Drag ratio. This is illustrated in Fig.1 from Wagner (1933) where the concave surface is depicted as having greater lift and a further aft center of pressure than a simple flat planing surface. Fig.1 also shows that a convex planing surface will have reduced lift and a further forward center of pressure. This is not a new concept as discussed in Almeter and Newman (2014). Cambered surfaces are widely used in marine dynamic lift applications such as propellers, stepped hulls, and hydrofoils.

The focus of this paper is how concave camber aft, when properly balanced or controlled, can potentially reduce the drag of a planing hull. Several approaches incorporating concave camber are discussed that show strong potential. However, the introduction of concavity does not always reduce drag, especially for very fast and lightly loaded planing hulls where frictional drag dominates. The concavity reduces pressure drag and unless it is supplemented with a bow foil or used in a planing step it will not reduce frictional drag.

Convexity has to exist forward to accommodate the bow and results in a composite concave / convex cambered hull form referred to as a Wiggle Hull due to the obvious wiggle in the hull shape as illustrated in Fig.2 from Almeter and Newman (2014). The hull shown in Fig.2 is a 1920's seaplane float.

Surface of fluid and forces on several circular curved planing surfaces of infinite width; the forces are comparatively to scale.

Fig.1: Lift of cambered surfaces, Wagner (1933)

Fig.2: Concave / convex seaplane float

The greater lift and aft center of pressure of the concavity reduces drag and can cause the wetted length to increase and this can cause the convex bow to dig in the water. The flow over the convex bow can significantly increase drag and potentially produce dynamic instabilities, *Blount (2014)*. The same situation can occur with a more traditional planing boat lacking concave camber, but is less likely to happen due to its higher running trim and shorter wetted length for the same center of pressure. This paper identifies several approaches to effectively use concave camber without the bow digging in. The paper is focused on monohulls, but the approaches can also be used for multi-hulls.

See *Almeter and Newman (2014)* for a more general discussion of concave and convex camber and a listing of historical model tests. The new results presented in this paper are based on computations. Additional model testing verification is needed.

2. Concave / Camber Planing Concepts

2.1 Trim Tab / Wedge Analogy

The introduction of concave camber is analogous to trim wedges on a traditional hull in that they increase lift, move the center of pressure aft with respect to the dynamic wetted area and increase wetted area. The addition of a wedge introduces concave camber near the transom. The wedge adds additional lift whose center is forward of the transom, but still comparatively aft. At slow to moderate speeds the wedge decreases running trim and reduces drag. At higher speeds the wedge can cause the bow to dig in and increase drag due to increased wetted area and the bow digging in. The bow digging in or burying introduces convex camber which further increases the drag. This is well documented in model tests and *Millward (1976)*, *Yaakob et al. (2004)*, and *Tsai and Hwang (2004)* are a few examples. The speed where the drag starts to increase is dependent on displacement, longitudinal center of gravity, size and angle of the wedges and the overall hull shape. High speed planing craft operators commonly run the trim tabs downward at a high angle to get over hump and may lift them all the way up such that they are out of the flow so that they are no longer producing lift at high speeds.

The drag reduction benefit of a trim tab or wedge is often more due to its hydrodynamic moment impact to the hull than to actual hydrodynamic unloading of the hull. The drag reduction from the concave camber presented in this paper is generally more due to the hydrodynamic unloading of the hull than to the hydrodynamic moment change. A concave camber hull may require a shift aft of the longitudinal center of gravity.

2.2 Wagner's Paper

Wagner (1933) addressed the impact of camber in the equations that follow for a flat plate in pure planing (no buoyant forces) and without aspect ratio correction at small trim angles. The equations also do not address friction, which is accounted for separately using a friction line approach.

$$\text{Lift or Weight (L)} = \frac{1}{2} \pi \rho b (2 f + l \tau) V^2$$

b Wetted Beam

f Camber ratio, camber height divided by wetted length, *l*

l Wetted length

V Velocity

ρ Mass density

τ Trim Angle (in radians)

$$\text{Drag (D)} = \frac{1}{2} \pi \rho b (2 f \tau + l \tau^2) V^2$$

$$\text{R/W or } (1/(L/D)) = (2 f \tau + l \tau^2) / (2 f + l \tau) \text{ (resistance to weight ratio)}$$

R Resistance

$$\text{LCP} / l = (1 (f + 3/4 l \tau) / (2 f + l \tau))$$

LCP Longitudinal Center of Pressure from trailing edge

These are simple equations for a complex problem, but still capture the relative impact of camber on a planing surface. The following conclusions from *Wagner (1933)* are generally supported by testing, more advanced theories and analysis within limits for small amounts of camber. Trim is based on the angle between the wetted leading edge and the trailing edge (transom).

1. Concave camber (positive camber) increases lift for a given trim and wetted length. Convex camber (negative camber) decreases it.
2. The additional lift from the camber is constant and independent of trim angle.
3. The “additional” lift due to the camber is proportional to the camber ratio and does not increase pressure drag at zero trim. In reality the camber pressure drag is small, but not zero as predicted by *Wagner*.
4. The center of pressure of the additional lift is further aft than the center of pressure of the lift induced by trimming the surface.
5. The addition of concave camber results in lower trim and pressure drag for a given lift and wetted length if the aft movement of the center of pressure is possible.

The approach of separately adding the lift and drag of the camber to that caused by inclining the surface together is a classic approach and has been used for hydrofoils and wings for many years. The same approach is used by *Savitsky and Brown (1976)* in the formulation of additional lift and drag of trim tabs. As discussed earlier, adding concavity is analogous to the use of trim tabs and it can be argued that the down trim tab is nothing more than the addition of local concavity near the transom. The additional lift of the trim tab in *Savitsky and Brown (1976)* is also independent of trim as is the camber lift in *Wagner’s* equations.

There are limits. The center of pressure can only be so far aft. Excessive camber can cause the bow to dig in and increase drag. The addition of concave camber can increase the drag of a boat at high speed as discussed in the previous section.

2.2.1 Supporting Model Testing

Almeter and Newman (2014) summarizes model testing of cambered surfaces and hulls. The limited model testing available supports the work presented in this paper and the attributes of cambered planing surfaces, both positive and negative. *Van Dyck (1965)* presents the results of testing a 15° deadrise planing surface with and without positive circular arc camber. The length to beam ratio is three and the camber ratio $f = 0.022$. The same configuration was tested without camber – straight. Figs.3-5 summarize the results. The wetted keel starts at the leading edge. For the same trim, the lift was significantly greater with the camber as shown in Fig.3. The additional lift from the camber was largely independent of trim as discussed in the previous section. The additional lift from the camber was equal to approximately 3.4° of additional trim. The equivalent additional lift predicted by *Wagner (1933)* is equivalent to 2.5° and close to the experimentally derived 3.4°. The Lift to Drag for the same lift coefficient was also greater for the cambered model as shown in Fig.4 as expected from *Wagner (1933)*.

Model testing also shows that negative or convex camber can reduce lift, decrease Lift to Drag and move the dynamic center of pressure forward as predicted by *Wagner’s* equations presented earlier. This is illustrated in *Mottard (1959) and (1960)*. Fig.6 is from *Almeter and Newman (2014)* and presents the convex model data of *Mottard (1959)*. The skin friction has been estimated and deducted. The surface has a flat circular arc. The trailing edge was locked at 5.25° of local slope in this example and the degrees of arc, as used, refers to the wetted length. The “trim” is the angle between the leading edge and the trailing edge. The Lift to Drag of a flat plate in this scenario should be the inverse of the tangent of the trim when frictional drag is deducted, which is also plotted. Please note that the model test values are significantly below this curve due to the inherent poor planing performance of convex planing surfaces as discussed previously. It is also interesting to note that the two curves con-

verge together for low values of arc. This is due to the planing surface approaching a flat (camberless) surface at low values of arc.

Fig.3: Lift coefficient versus trim for straight and cambered surfaces, *Van Dyck (1965)*

Fig.4: L to D vs Lift coefficient for straight and cambered surfaces, *Van Dyck (1965)*

Fig.5: LCP / L_p (chine length) versus trim for camber and straight surfaces, *Van Dyck (1965)*

Fig.6: Convex Planing surface Lift to Drag, *Almeter and Newman (2014)*

Models representative of practical planing hulls with different degrees of camber were tested at Davidson Laboratory and the results given in *Chey (1963)*, *Van Mater (1963)* and *Fridsma (1966)*. The cambered model's lines from *Fridsma (1966)* is shown in Fig.7 for Model 2387. Fig.8 is a magnification of the profile in Fig.7 and includes straight lines from the start of the camber on the centerline to the transoms to illustrate the size and length of the camber.

Fig.7: Cambered Model 2387, *Fridsma (1966)* Fig.8: Detail of camber of model 2387, *Fridsma (1966)*

The camber length is approximately 70 % of the chine length and the camber ratio is 1.7 % for the original camber and 1.0 % for the reduced modified camber. The testing was at LCG / L_p of approximately 43 % from the transom. Model 2387 was originally tested at speeds up to Volumetric Froude Number of 5.0 (50 knots full size). The LCP / L_p is much further forward than what is normally considered optimal for this high speed, especially with camber. At the higher speeds the bow never fully lifted out of the water. With the reduced modified camber the drag was decreased as expected above a Volumetric Froude Number of 3.5 (35 knots full size) as shown in Fig.9. Even with the lower camber the bow was still in the water at the higher speeds as shown in Fig.10 from *Fridsma (1966)* for a Volumetric Froude Number of 5.0.

The cambered models were compared to equivalent round bilge models in *Chey (1963)* and the cambered models were found to have lower resistance and accelerations than their round bilge counterparts over a wide range of speeds, including the lower speeds where round bilge boats are traditionally thought to be better performers. *Van Mater (1963)* compared the performance of the cambered hulls with a more modern planing hull without camber, Model 4876, shown in Fig.11 taken from *Van Mater (1963)*. The cambered models had lower drag and accelerations than the modern straight hull of Model 4876. Fig.9 consolidates test results from these references for a full-size displacement of 25 t. Overall the cambered hulls had the lowest resistance. Only at very high end speeds do the cambered hulls start to lose their advantage in resistance. Fig.9 and the references show that introducing longitudinal camber into a hull can have favorable results, but there are limits, especially at high speeds.

Fig.9: Impact of camber on EHP, *Fridsma (1966)*, *Van Mater (1963)*, *Chey (1963)*

Fig.10: Model 2387 with modified camber at Volu-metric Froude Number of 5, *Fridsma (1966)*

Fig.11: Model 4876 with straight lines, *Van Mater (1963)*

Hellstrom and Blount (1995) presents model testing with localized convex and concave camber in close proximity to the transom. The concave camber had significantly lower dynamic trim than the convex camber. The concave camber had lower drag at the lower speeds than the convex camber but higher drag at higher planing speeds due to increased wetted surface and the bow digging in due to concave camber. *Blount (1995)* indicates that the concave camber can improve seakeeping in some cases.

2.3 Wave Rise

Wave rise is a well-known phenomenon of planing hulls. It is simply a pile-up of the water above the undisturbed water surface in the region of the stagnation line where the still water strikes the hull. In

theory there is a shockless entry scenario where there is no wave rise, but this is not a realistic case for a true planing hull in realistic planing. A practical planing hull with concave camber aft requires a relatively flat planing surface forward of the camber and this surface has to have at least a small positive inclination, local slope or local running trim. This is illustrated in the top part of Fig.12 from the presentation associated with *Almeter and Newman (2014)*. The bottom part of Fig.12 is a depiction of a shockless entry. This is not a realistic scenario. In reality there will be wave rise on the inclined bow as shown in the middle part of Fig.12 that will result in increased drag or the concavity will ventilate resulting in reduced wetted length, loss of lift and aft shift in center of pressure. If the stagnation line is on the highly inclined bow as shown in the middle the pressure drag at this location will be very high. Additionally the flow has to abruptly change direction and flow upward and this will result in an undesirable reduction in pressure. *Almeter and Newman (2014)* incorrectly assumed a situation like that depicted in the lower part of Fig.12 for some cases. As such, some of the concave camber resistance predictions will be low when the wetted lengths approached the end of the inclined bow in *Almeter and Newman (2014)*. Fig.8 is an example of a hull where the camber is properly faired into the hull. The transition to the camber is not abrupt and there is a significant straight area preceding the camber. The model in Fig.8 ran with a few degrees of dynamic trim such that the flat in front of the camber was at a positive slope during steady planing. It is representative of the top portion of Fig.12.

Fig.12: Wave rise on Wiggle Hull

2.4 Introduction of Concave Camber into a Planing Hull

There are an infinite number of possible concave camber shapes. A few examples are shown in Fig.13 from *Johnson (1961)*. The leading edge is on the left and trailing edge is on the right. A modified Johnson 3 Term camber is used in the analysis presented in this paper. *Johnson (1961)* provides the mathematical definition and its derivation.

Fig.13: Concave camber shapes

Concave camber is introduced into a modified Series 62 hull bottom, *Clement and Blount (1962)*, Fig.14 (vertical scale greatly exaggerated for clarity). Forward is to the left and aft is to the right. The

concave camber was rotated aft before being faired into the hull. The start of the camber section moves aft from the centerline. This is to accommodate the craft's deadrise, local buttock shape and the dynamic waterline. Ideally the cambered portion needs to be behind the stagnation line and the stagnation line needs to be on a near flat surface with minimal positive local inclination to minimize drag. However, portions of the stagnation line can be behind the start of the camber if the local slope of the camber is positive due to the craft's dynamic trim. Fig. 15 shows a typical dynamic wetted area. In this example the local camber ratio was kept constant and the local length of the cambered section varied with longitudinal position – becomes shorter as it moves outboard from the centerline. Neither of these choices is mandatory. It may be desirable to have the center of pressure associated with the concavity forward and this will likely dictate a long concave section as shown in Fig.14.

Fig.14: Buttocks of modified Series 62 hull bottom with concave / convex camber - Wiggle

Fig.15: Typical wetted area of modified Series 62 hull during planing

3. Concave / Convex Wiggle Hull Prediction Results

3.1 Prediction Method

The concave / convex Wiggle Hull predictions were made with the Non-Linear Vortex Lattice Method code AUTOWING. AUTOWING is an established code and is described in numerous references including *Kornev et al. (2005)* and *Migotte (2002)*. A different Vortex Lattice Method code was successfully used in *Verengo and Brizzolara (2014)* to predict cambered planing performance. As part of this investigation AUTOWING results were compared to model test results of Model 5328 of Series 65B, *Hadler et al. (1974)*, and Model 4667-1 of Series 62, *Clement and Blount (1962)*. The resistance predictions were consistent with model test results at Volumetric Froude Numbers greater than 3. However, the program tended to underestimate the dynamic trim and underestimate the wetted length for a given displacement and longitudinal center of gravity combination. The AUTOWING predicted impacts of the camber are consistent with the findings of *Almeter and Newman (2014)*.

Seventeen hulls were analyzed in this effort and more than 1000 runs made. Each run being a combination of fixed trim, transom submergence, and speed for a particular hull. Each planing hull bottom consisted of approximately 2000 panels per side with both sides mirrored. Convergence tests confirmed that this density was adequate. Each run required approximately 10 to 20 minutes on the laptop used. A higher order CFD code such as used in *Faison (2014)* for a cambered planing surface was not used because of the large number of runs required for this investigation. The computational requirements of AUTOWING are much less than viscous CFD codes. It was not practical to use new model testing or viscous CFD codes for such a large and broad preliminary investigation for the resources available and the large number of runs made. Unfortunately existing model tests are also insufficient. However, future investigations should consider such approaches for a smaller number of cases.

3.2 Dynamic Force Predictions

Dynamic force (lift, drag and moment) predictions were made for the hull bottom shown in Fig.14 with the camber shown, without camber and with an even higher camber. The results include frictional resistance from solid water (spray not included) at a Reynolds Number of 120,000,000. The craft was run at such a high speed that buoyant forces can be neglected. The chine length was 2.43 m. Overall, the calculated results were consistent with the conclusions from Wagner's paper.

The Lift to Drag, and Longitudinal Center of Pressure divided by chine length, LCP/L_p , are plotted against displacement in Fig.16 for the cambered hull in Fig.14, the same hull with straight buttocks and the same hull with an even heavier camber against the displacement. The dynamic R/W ratio (including friction) is significantly lower for the cambered hulls than for the hull with the straight buttocks for the same displacement. The LCP/L_p with respect to the transom is significantly further aft for the cambered hulls for the same displacement. The cases in Fig.16 have the same hull dimensions and the same dynamic wetted area within a few percent. The dynamic trims were different between the three hulls with the dynamic trim decreasing with decreasing camber for the same displacement.

The lift of the camberless hull is plotted in Fig.17. Also plotted are the additional lift due to the camber and heavy camber that were added to the hull. The total lift of the cambered hull is the sum of the camberless hull and the additional camber lift. The calculated additional lift from the camber does not change significantly as a function of dynamic trim as predicted by *Wagner (1933)*. The R/W (resistance to weight ratio) of the additional lift from the camber is additionally plotted in Fig.17. *Wagner (1933)* predicts that the R/W of the additional lift is equal to the tangent of the dynamic trim which is also plotted in Fig.17. The calculated slope of the R/W of the additional lift of the regular camber is a little higher than the Wagner's curve, and the slope of the heavy camber is even higher. This is consistent with the previous analysis of model test data in *Almeter and Newman (2014)*. The very simple Wagner prediction does a good job for predicting the impact of small amounts of camber. The R/W of the additional lift from the camber at 2.5° of dynamic trim is only 0.06, or a Lift to Drag ratio of 16. This is very attractive and the equal of hydrofoil performance.

Fig.16: Lift to Drag and LCP/L_p vs Displacement for straight and cambered hulls

Fig.17: R/W and lift from camber

The predictions in this section are not radical or revolutionary. There are numerous model tests of simple concave cambered surfaces exemplifying these characteristics dating at least back to *Sottorf (1934)*. *Almeter and Newman (2014)* summarizes and analyzes many of these early model tests.

Introducing concave camber into the hull can significantly increase hydrodynamic lift with little increase in drag in some cases. The obstacle to be addressed is the associated aft center of pressure of the increased camber lift.

4. Use of Concave Camber to Improve Performance

There are several approaches incorporating concave camber that can significantly improve performance in some cases. The following approaches will be discussed.

- Concave camber only with speed and LCG limitations
- Concave camber aft and forward bow foil
- Concave camber with adjustable transom tab
- Dynaplane concept

4.1 Concave Camber only with Speed and LCG Limitations

Concave camber alone can in some cases significantly reduce drag as long as the speed is not too great and the LCG not too far forward. If the speed is too great or the longitudinal center of gravity is too far forward this can cause the dynamic trim to be too low and the wetted length too great and the convex bow will dig in resulting in excessive drag. Craft with low length to beam ratios, which are heavily loaded or have low deadrise are good candidates to benefit from concave camber in the semi-planing speed range where buoyant forces are significant. Proper use of concave camber may require the LCG to be further aft than normal. It may be desirable to have the center of pressure associated with the concavity forward and this will likely dictate a long concave section as shown in Fig.14 and Fig.18. Analysis and / or model testing is required to determine the benefit of concave camber for a particular design. In some cases there may not be any benefit.

Fig.18 depicts a craft bottom with concave camber introduced. Principal characteristics are:

Chine length	7.3 m
Chine beam	2.3 m
Displacement	6000 kg

LCG from transom	3.0 m (no camber)
LCG from transom	2.6 m (with camber)
Hull loading, $A_p/\nabla^{2/3}$	5.3 (A_p projected planing area)

The LCG of the camber variant is significantly aft of the uncambered hull. If the cambered hull's LCG was further forward the bow will start to dig in at a lower speed. The top speed of the results in Fig.19 is already near the point where the bow of the cambered hull is predicted to start getting wet and the drag increases. At the top speed the wetted keel length to chine length ratio is 0.88, significantly greater than the 0.67 ratio predicted for the uncambered hull despite the uncambered hull having a significantly further forward LCG. The R/W of the cambered hull is significantly lower than that of the uncambered variant, Fig.19. The uncambered variant's LCG was selected to minimize resistance in the speed range shown in Fig.19. If the comparison was based on both hulls having the same LCG as the cambered hull, the differences in drag will be even greater in favor of the cambered hull. The predicted dynamic trim of the cambered hull is significantly lower than that of the uncambered variant despite having a further aft LCG. This is due to the higher lift associated with a cambered surface and the reduced dependency on buoyant lift. The analysis was also performed at 4000, 8000 and 10000 kg and the results were similar as was found when run with a variant with even greater camber.

Fig.18: Buttocks of bottom of planing hull with and without camber - Wiggle

Fig.19: R/W of craft with and without concave camber

4.2 Concave Camber Coupled with a Bow Foil

It can be difficult to fair camber into a fine hull, especially with high aft deadrise. Keeping the camber within the dynamic wetted area is a problem due to the large differences between the keel and chine wetted lengths, especially at low running trims. This can cause the cambered section to be short and cause an even further aft center of pressure from the additional camber lift. The camber could potentially become not much more than a cambered transom wedge, which in some cases may still have advantages at lower speeds. But the focus on this paper is on the more general use of camber where the camber supports a significant portion of the craft's weight. The concave camber by itself in the situation just described may have little benefit at higher speeds due to its aft center of pressure. But if a small bow foil is added to the cambered hull the net result could significantly lower the drag in some cases. The improved performance is not solely by the unloading of the hull by the foil or by the foil's low Lift to Drag but also by the significant forward moment that causes the convex bow to lift out of the water. The net center of pressure of the dynamic, hydrostatic and foil forces can result in a very desirable and realistic longitudinal center of gravity.

Fig.20 is a high deadrise and fine hull bottom derived from Series 65B, *Hadler et al. (1964)*, with a concave camber in the after portion of the hull. The concave camber is comparatively aft due to the craft's original geometry; high deadrise aft and fine bow. The principal characteristics follow.

Chine length	23.82 m
Chine beam	4.86 m
Bound projected planing area, A_p	86 m ²
Forward foil area	1.3 m ²
Lift coefficient of foil	0.4
Lift to Drag of foil	16
Center of pressure of foil from transom	22 m
Displacement	112 t
LCG from transom	8.9 m
Hull loading, $A_p/\nabla^{2/3}$	3.7
Slenderness ratio	5.0

Fig.20: Series 65B hull with camber - Wiggle

Fig.21: R/W of Series 65B hull without camber and with camber and fwd foil

Fig.21 shows the predicted R/W ratio of the craft with and without camber and bow foil. The lift and drag of the bow foil is linearly added to the cambered hull performance. This is a simplification of the partial hydrofoil lift problem and if this design was to be continued a more sophisticated analysis or testing is required. The predicted R/W of the cambered hull with the bow foil is significantly lower than the uncambered hull. The bow foil is very small, with an area only 1.5 % of the projected bottom planing area. If the bow foil was moved aft to midship on the cambered hull, the drag reduction in the speed range given would not be achieved because the concave bow will be in the water. The concept of a forward bow foil coupled with an aft camber is not terribly different than other partial hydrofoil

concepts with a forward foil that have been tested, built and shown to have lower drag in some cases. In these concepts there is an additional lift developing device near the transom such as a foil or a trim wedge, *Migeotte (2004)*. The concave camber can be thought of as taking the place of the aft lifting device. As discussed previously, the R/W of the additional lift of the camber is similar to that of a foil and as such the substitution of camber for an aft lifting device in a partial hydrofoil supported planing craft is plausible.

Partial hydrofoil support can also reduce the drag of conventional uncambered planing hulls. *Karafiath (1974)* and *Sherman (1958)* are two example model investigations. Fig.22 is one of the test configurations of *Karafiath (1974)*. Shown on the left is a quartering view of the tested model and to the right is an underwater photograph. The optimal foil location of the uncambered hull is generally going to be significantly aft of the cambered hull optimal foil location. If the foil is too far forward on a conventional uncambered hull the reduced drag benefit may not be achieved. The far forward foil on an uncambered planing hull without an aft lift device can result in increased dynamic trim beyond optimal. The resistance of partial hydrofoil supported cambered and uncambered planing hulls were predicted and compared. The location of the foil was further forward for the cambered concepts. The resistance was lower for the cambered hulls with the forward bow foil than the uncambered hulls with further aft foils, but the analysis was not exhaustive and not all the significant variables were addressed. Variables include displacement, amount and shape of camber, speed, initial longitudinal center of gravity, location of foil, size of foil and angle of attack. Fig.23 is the same as Fig.21 but with the addition of uncambered hulls with a foil at different locations from the transom. The predicted performance advantage of the cambered hull with a bow foil over the uncambered hull with a bow foil is significant, but not dramatic. Please note that the best longitudinal location of the foil for the straight planing hull was substantially aft of the concave cambered hull's foil position.

Besides lower drag there are several additional advantages of a cambered planing surface with a forward bow foil. The dynamic trim can be lower than an uncambered hull and an uncambered hull with a foil. This could improve seakeeping. Additionally the forward location of the bow foil makes it ideal for dynamic trim control and ride control. Obvious disadvantages include the additional cost of the foil and possible a foil retraction system (somewhat negated by its small size) and increased navigational draft. Its potential impact on maneuvering also has to be considered.

Fig.22: Series 65B hull tested with mid foil, *Karafiath (1974)*

Fig.23: R/W of Series 65B hull with and without camber and foil locations

4.3 Concave Camber Coupled with a Trim Tab

As discussed in the paper the bow can dig in at higher speeds when concave camber is introduced into the hull due to its greater lift and its center of lift being aft causing an increase in drag from the partial immersion of the convex bow. This problem can be avoided or reduced by changing the hull shape, and a simple way to do this is with trim tabs or interceptors. The trim tab could be the last few percent of the cambered hull. At the proper speed the trim tab could swing up to allow the flow to separate at the hinge point. The reduction of cambered length, camber ratio, and shifting forward of the aft end of the camber can in some circumstances reduce drag at the higher speeds by a combination of lifting the bow out of the water and reduced wetted area. The trim tab could also help reduce any increased drag at low speeds associated with the further aft LCG used for concave cambered hull design.

4.4 Dynaplane for very High Speeds

As discussed the incorporation of concave camber can reduce the drag of hulls whose drag is dominated by hydrodynamic pressure. If the drag is dominated by frictional drag, the addition of concave camber can actually increase drag. The Dynaplane concept incorporates concave camber and dramatically reduces drag at very high speed by the use of a stepped hull and the associated reduction in wetted area. The stepped hull can have a high percentage of its drag from pressure drag despite its high speed. The pressure drag on the main step is reduced by incorporation of the concave camber in the area of the step.

The Dynaplane was tested and developed by David Taylor Model Basin and Eugene Clements was a principal investigator. One of the tested configurations is shown in Fig.24 from *Almeter and Newman (2014)*. At planing conditions the bulk of the lift is provided on the cambered step and a minority of the lift by a device on the transom, such as a foil. Since the wetted length is so short at the step, the relative aft center of pressure of a cambered surface is not an issue. This results in a cambered hull with high Lift to Drag at high planing speeds. There is renewed interest in this concept. The Dynaplane is not discussed further only because it has already been addressed in many other references, including *Faison (2014)* and *Clement (2005,2006,2007)*.

Fig.24: Dynaplane stepped hull with camber at step

5. Summary

The use of concave camber in a planing hull bottom can in some cases significantly reduce drag. Approaches that can be used to incorporate camber include:

- Concave camber only added to hull bottom
- Concave camber plus a bow foil
- Concave camber plus a trim tab
- Concave camber in a step of a stepped hull - Dynaplane

The addition of concave camber is most effective where there is significant pressure drag, including at the hump condition. Hulls whose drag is predominantly frictional likely will not benefit from the addition of concave camber.

The concave camber can produce so much additional lift that the dynamic trim can become too small and the bow may dig in causing an increase in drag at a high speed. The center of pressure of the additional camber lift is relatively aft. A hull with concave camber may require a further aft center of gravity than an uncambered hull.

For at least the near future, incorporation of longitudinal concave camber into a hull requires analytical analysis and / or testing.

6. Recommended Additional Work

The effort described in this paper is analytical. Model testing or full size testing is needed to further advance this concept. The combining of the foil lift and the planing lift is overly simplistic in this paper and is an area deserving of more thoughtful analysis.

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Unconventional Ships and Unconventional Design

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Abstract

This paper addresses the nature of unconventional ship design. It addresses what it is that makes design unconventional by considering the unconventionality of highly novel marine vehicles and ships. There are seen to be two broad categories of unconventional vessels, those that are effectively fast vehicles and those that have unconventional hull-forms, but may not necessarily be “very fast”. From this, firstly, conventional ship design is considered as a benchmark before the nature of unconventional ship design is explored. Recent proposals to change how ship design in general could be changed are then addressed under the topic of design unconventionality, before conclusions looking towards the future practice of advanced ship design are made.

1. Introduction – Unconventional Ships

The term an unconventional ship usually means one other than the normal monohull, which relies on buoyancy for lift and with propellers for efficient propulsion at a maximum speed given by a Froude “hollow”, see Fig.1. However there have occasionally been monohulls with unconventional arrangements, that ought also to be included in the term “unconventional” as this should not be restricted to just a question of hull form and propulsor system. Nevertheless the term “unconventional” (or sometimes “advanced” (McKesson 2014)) hullform/ship/vessel/marine vehicle is usually used to denote either:

- a. fast vehicles (much faster than most ocean-going ships, which have maximum speeds of well under 30 knots in moderate seaways) using some other form(s) of lift (wholly or partially) than buoyancy and then getting over the wave-making main hump (i.e. Froude Number = 0.54) by most (if not all) of the vessel’s hull being “out of the water”;
- b. not so necessarily fast vessels, which adopt “unconventional hullforms”, usually with multiple hulls of different sizes and configurations in order to achieve certain specialist performance criteria (some of which are discussed further below).

Fig.1: Humps and Hollows in wave-making resistance curve, Rawson and Tupper (1974)

It is the case that the vast majority of sea going vessels remain “conventional” for good economic and risk reduction reasons, the modern (normally diesel and propeller powered) monohull being well optimised for most marine transport systems and almost all service vessel uses. (This is adopting the main distinction between the majority of ships, that are part of a wider transportation system, Erichsen (1998), and those “service” vessels that “go to sea to do something”. Thus the latter consist of a very diverse range of vessels, such as offshore support vessels or some form of naval vessel and is a

useful design distinction, as argued previously, *Andrews (2010)*.) However, it is noticeable that much of the published discussion on new ship designs focuses on the more unconventional, as this is seen to be of particular interest to the ship design profession, see review at *Andrews (2010)*. Furthermore such interest in unconventional ships can be seen to lead on to the specific consideration of “unconventional ship design”, which is the primary focus of this paper.

One might ask why, given they are relatively rare, is it that there remains interest in the unconventional in the maritime sector. In this regard, a relevant insight was provided by the eminent engineering design theorist, Stuart Pugh, when he addressed a marine design audience, *Pugh (1985)*. Pugh observed that he expected, in admitted ignorance, to find that ship design was conceptually “static”, as is the case for cars and aircraft where the choice of engineering solution is very restricted. However, to his surprise, Pugh observed “ships are conceptually dynamic, (*such*) that many differing designs (conceptually) are yet to emerge”. This is precisely why, even with the very small relative number of unconventional ships produced, their engineering aspects and the design processes to produce them is of interest.

Furthermore Pugh went on to say “one should practice as if this (“dynamic conceptual nature”) were the case”. In other words, at least for what this author has defined as “complex ship design”, *Andrews (2016)*, novel (i.e. unconventional) options should be explored as part of the initial (conceptual) design process. This is because a properly divergent concept exploration process may reveal more attractive alternatives than the conventional to meet, what should be, an emerging requirement, *Andrews (2013)*. Furthermore, unconventional options can push the design process and practice to the limits, which is essential if the nascent requirements are to be adequately explored before programme commitment occurs. The latter desirable practice echoes Pugh’s follow up remark just above.

The next section briefly considers the broad nature of conventional ship design as a benchmark, before firstly exploring the natures of the two main categories of unconventional ships/marine vehicles distinguished above. This is followed by consideration of unconventional ship design and largely draws on the author’s distinction of the degree of novelty of any design option driving the appropriateness of the design process adopted for that given design option. The last section, before a brief conclusion, looks at “designing unconventionally” by discussing various recently proposed and, potentially, future developments in ship design.

2. Conventional Ship Design

To better understand why the design of unconventional ships is different to that of the norm, it is necessary to briefly consider conventional ship design, particularly in its early stages, as this is where unconventional design is most distinct. The contrast of commercial ship design with that for those very complex design programmes required, particularly, for most naval vessels, is summarised in the author’s contribution to *Freeth (2015)*. Furthermore, Table 1 categorises ship design in increasing levels of design novelty, as is explained most fully in a recent paper largely addressing naval ship design, *Andrews (2016)*.

Table 1: Types of Ship Design in terms of Design Novelty

Type	Example
Second batch	Batch 2 Type 22 frigate
simple type ship	many naval auxiliary vessels
evolutionary design	a family of designs
simple synthesis	UCL student designs
architectural synthesis	UCL design studies
radical configuration	SWATH, Trimaran
radical technology	US Navy Surface Effect Ship

Most commercial vessels, particularly the ubiquitous transportation vessel (be it a bulkier or container-ship), are designed according to the second category of Table 1, where the fundamental issue, once this category of design has been selected (often by default rather than any systematic selection process), is how far will the new ship design differ from the chosen type ship. Beyond that, the major design decisions will, essentially, be unchanged from those previously incorporated in the chosen type ship. Thus the ship design approach, the use of design tools, the adoption of design criteria etc. will be as for the “type ship”, with the only new (“improved”) features inserted being those warranting a new design. Typically such features will be moderate changes in speed, range, payload or the adoption of some discrete enhanced technology (e.g. a newer version of existing power plant or operational equipment, such as a new radar, or minor changes in crew numbers or supporting facilities). However, when it comes to the initial sizing, which preferably should be a fully architecturally driven synthesis (see further discussion below), this will still require a full iterative process to ensure a naval architectural balance is achievable in the new design as this will be necessitated by the whole ship impact of even moderate changes from the type ship.

This “type ship” design approach could be said to cover that used for most general commercial ship designs, where the approach adopted by the winning shipyard in response to the ship owner’s request for bids is very much to modify the last successful ship design that shipyard produced. However, it may still be necessary to not just achieve a new balanced solution (in weight, buoyancy, stability and powering) but also be necessary to undertake a form parameter investigation, to get the “optimum” hull dimensions and form coefficients for the new performance and “payload” requirements. With a type ship basis, the form parameter investigation is likely to be highly constrained in the extent of design choices, as the new design’s style will follow, in almost all regards, that of the type ship. Thus often the same form parameters will be adopted, with just a slightly different set of dimensions found necessary to meet the improved performance with regards to payload, speed range or, even, seakeeping/manoeuvrability, should those dimensions of the type ship have been found to be inadequate in-service. This broad, type ship modification, approach also applied to pre-World War II Royal Navy vessels, such as destroyers, when a new class was ordered, almost every year. This is no longer the case for modern combatants with new designs often separated by a decade or two and so requiring wholly new designs and approaches with greater novelty. This is suggested by the examples shown in Table 1, if not to the fuller extents of significant unconventionality, suggested by the last two categories of Table 1.

It can be further argued that service vessels (especially naval combatants) are less likely to adopt a type ship approach, because such ship programmes are usually initiated by a new need (i.e. weapon/sensor/role). However naval vessels are not driven by commercial market forces but are heavily constrained by political pressures which, when there is no immediate geopolitical threat, can stretch out timescales to an extraordinary extent in comparison to the commercial sector. It is also the case that new naval vessels are often designed in response to an unpredictable future, rather than an immediate, commercial market need, hence the “wicked nature” of their requirements elucidation, *Andrews (2011)*. With acquisition costs of naval vessels running ahead of inflation, programmes are delayed and stretched, which leads to excessive technical changes between classes. All this means that the concept design phase for such expensive ships is different to that for commercial vessels, leading to the adoption of different concept design methods, *Andrews (2013)*. However this more protracted process then means it is in the concept phase of such vessels that it is worth considering unconventional solutions.

Interestingly, if the two categories of unconventional vessels identified in the paper’s first paragraph are considered, then it is the first of these categories, that of fast vehicles, which is designed in a manner further most from that of conventional ship design. This is so much the case, that they do not follow even the extended ship design practice of naval ships but rather follows practices more akin to those of the aerospace sector (see Table 1), which is consistent with the manufacturing origin of most of fast craft. Most conventional ships, both commercial and naval, are produced in shipyards, in a manner akin to large-scale civil engineering constructions, thus through a bespoke structural manufacturing/fabrication followed by an equipment assembly process. Whereas fast (and hence light-

weight) marine craft are produced in factories much more like aerospace manufacturing assembly lines, even if the numbers produced rarely match those for aircraft, and certainly not those typical of the automotive industry. In contrast the second category of “unconventional vessels” follow much more closely the classical shipbuilding process, which is consistent with most of them being of the same technology as conventionally constructed ships. However, it is true that these unconventional ships have demonstrated that conventional ship design approaches reveal their limitations when being pushed to the greater degrees of novelty inevitable in the unconventional forms, even if the technology is the same as for the conventionally configured ships. One needs to caveat the last statement in that there have been recent examples of significant vessels with “unconventional hull forms” that seek to exploit the moderately fast operating domain in between the fastest monohull displacement ships and the very high-speed forms (i.e. category (a) above). Such examples are certain high-speed ferries (e.g. Seacat Catamarans) and sizable vessels operating well above the nominally 30 knots boundary (e.g. US Navy Trimaran LCS).

Finally, it is worth remarking that while the vast bulk of seagoing shipping is conventional, discussions in the technical conferences and learned journals, with regard to new ship designs and ship design methods, focuses to quite a significant degree on the unconventional. In a review of ship design over the last momentous 150 years, in the oldest naval architectural proceedings, *Andrews (2010)*, it was observed that a large number of papers presented were on novel or even unconventional vessels and craft. This was seen as partly an obvious interest of the profession in the cutting edge but also a way of assessing whether new solutions and technologies could drive the maritime sector forward. It was also noticeable that, with the advances in computer driven technologies occurring in the last third of the period reviewed, many more publications have been produced considering how ships are designed and how this could be better achieved. Hence the theme of bringing together, in the current paper, unconventional “ships” and unconventional ship design.

3. The Nature of Unconventional Ships (and Craft)

Perhaps the easiest statement to make about unconventional ships and craft is that there are very many different types and any means of distinction is open to criticism for lack of coherence. Given that the objective of this paper is to consider the issues in design of non-conventional vessels, the distinction made at the beginning of this paper between (a) fast (marine) vehicles and (b) unconventional hull forms (UHF) is seen to be justified in that the design approaches for these two (broad) categories of unconventionality follow, essentially, the last two distinct categories in Table 1. Thus the design of fast vehicles conforms to the last category, while the design of UHFs fits the penultimate category. Having said that, one immediately has to qualify the statement that fast vehicles and UHFs are distinct, by pointing out that there are some exceptions. This is particularly so when it comes to vehicles adopting hybrid forms of lift (i.e. other than buoyancy alone) where there are clearly “unconventionally hulled fast craft” (the surface effects ship (SES) being the most common and established example).

The traditional manner in which the forms of lift for marine vehicles are delineated is that of the sustentation diagram, although this has been considered inadequate in not including aerodynamic lift (to produce a “sustention pyramid”, *Jewell (1979)*). The latter is then able to accommodate Wing-in-Ground (WIG) or Ground Effect vehicles, which despite both names operate over water at very high speeds even for fast marine craft (i.e. several hundred knots). In the recent book by *McKesson (2014)* on the practical design of “advanced marine vehicles (AMVs)”, which will be discussed further in the next section, McKesson prefers the “sustention cube” as this introduces the distinction between passive and active (mechanical) lift mechanisms:

- i. Passive hydrostatics, hydrodynamics, aerostatics, aerodynamics;
- ii. Active hydrostatics, hydrodynamics, aerostatics, aerodynamics.

McKesson’s Cube can thus distinguish between (say) hydrofoils and WIGs, which are both (“passive”) dynamic lift craft, one hydro- the other aerodynamic. McKesson then compares seven AMVs (i.e. catamaran, trimaran, SWATH, hydrofoil, WIG, air cushion vehicle (ACV) and SES). It is of

note that the last of his AMVs is a hybrid using tow forms of lift and that the first three are multi-hulls, so not really “fast” craft. McKesson’s comparison is done generically for five performance parameters (i.e. sea-kindliness, speed/power, comfort & space, load carrying ability and economics). However the current author prefers to use some nine design aspects to compare, not just McKesson’s seven AMVs but also an extra multihull hybrid, the Hydrodynamic Slender Water-plane Area Ship (HYSWAS), and to do so in comparison with the mono-hull, as is shown in Table 2. However it is important to remark that this latter comparison was for a naval combatant role. Thus some of McKesson’s aspects like comfort, load carrying and economics are considered too role dependant to be sensibly compared generically across such a range of marine vessel types and their possible commercial and naval usages.

Table 2: Qualitative Assessment of Different Hull Forms, *Andrews (2003)*

Ship Types Aspects	Mono-hull	Cata-maran	ACV	SES	Hydro-foil	SWATH	HY-SWAS	WIG	Tri-maran
Speed, Power and Endurance	Good	Good ¹	V Good ²	Good	V Good ²	Good	Good	V Good	Good
Space and lay-out	Good	Good	Ave	Good	Poor	V Good	Poor	Poor	V Good
Structural design and weight	V Good	Ave	Poor	Poor	V Poor	Ave	Poor	V Poor	Good
Stability	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good ³	Good	Good	Poor	V Good
Manoeuvrability	Good	Ave	Poor	Good	Good	Ave	Good	Poor	Good
Noise, Radar & Magnetic Signature	Good	Ave	Good	Good	Good	V Good	Good	Good	V Good
Weapon placement & effectiveness	Good	Ave	Ave	Ave	Poor	Good	Ave	Poor	V Good
Construction costs and build time	V Good	High	V High	High	V High	Good	High	V High	Good
Through life costs	Good	Ave	V High	High	V High	Ave	High	V High	V Good

Notes to Table 2:

1. But poorer in deep ocean seaway.
2. Very fast but limited to hull borne (slow) in seaway and endurance poor (fuel weight).
3. Very good hull borne but foil borne degraded by wave effects in deep ocean.

In considering the first unconventional vessel category, it is clear that the need to go fast which then requires the vehicle to be “lifted out of the water” (by hydrodynamic or aero-static lift) quite alters the concerns for the designer. Whereas the conventional ship designer is concerned with all the engineering issues of speed, seakeeping, stability and strength, plus the wider issues of “style”, *Andrews*

(2012), the design of really fast craft is dominated by the need for lift. Thus the power to weight ratio becomes much more like that of an aircraft where both the need to keep “in the air” and powerful engines for both lift and speed, very significantly change the design focus. Without the “free” facility of buoyancy, such marine craft have to invest in light-weight structures and expensive and fuel guzzling power/propulsion systems. So text books on fast craft (such as *McKesson (2014)* and *Faltinsen (2006)*) concentrate on hydrodynamics, including special propulsive devices, and on lightweight structural materials to meet specific loadings due to supporting the small payloads at speed. This also explains that to date, despite some early post war proposals (*Lavis et al. 1990*), such fast vehicles have remained coastal craft, rather than deep ocean ships, and can only carry expensive light-weight payloads, like people on short ferry routes. There is growing interest in large military ocean transport at genuine high speeds (e.g. about 80 knots – see *Kennell et al. (1998)*). However this US Navy initiative identified that there needs to be considerable investment in developing technologies to deliver large power as well as finding new propulsion systems and new structural materials that can have sufficient stiffness and high strength to weight ratios to support cargoes of more commercial ship like quantities and densities, *Keane (2003)*. So for the near term future the specific design processes appropriate to the current generation of small high-speed craft therefore tend to be more aerospace based than maritime like and these are considered in the next section.

Fig.2: A SWATH Combatant and its Monohull Equivalents, *Kennell et al. (1985)*

The other unconventional ships, in the second category above, are much more like conventional ships as regards the S^5 , *Brown and Andrews (1980)*, engineering issues just spelt out. This is because these vessels are conventional ships in technology (and construction) but merely unconventional in configuration, i.e. they are multi-hulled. In fact in the case of the trimaran (and its pentamaran derivative, *Gee et al. (1997)*) it as been argued they are no more than very slender monohulls with very low displacement outriggers to restore static stability, *Andrews and Hall (1995)*. That and their generally moderate speed means that, for examples like ocean going SWATHs, there is no virtue in adopting really high speeds and hence resorting to advanced propulsion systems and light weight structures if a comparable payload to an equivalent monohull is what is being sought. There are two provisos to this. The first is that if low payloads at speed are required both SWATHs and trimarans (as already is the case with high speed catamaran ferries) can be designed for moderately high speeds (40 to 50 knots) and utilise light weight structures - the significant example of this is the US Navy’s LCS Trimaran class (however this has not been without its problems, *Warship Technology (2016)*).

The second proviso is related to the question as to what is the monohull equivalent of such multi-hulls. This was quite nicely addressed by *Kennell et al. (1985)* for the SWATH, where they compared three solutions to meet the requirement for a naval combatant, which are shown in, the reproduced, Fig.2. The first is the SWATH solution, which has the same payload and speed etc. as the first monohull. However it has greatly superior seakeeping to that monohull and the third design, as a monohull, then has to be considerably bigger (e.g. 28% greater displacement) than the SWATH to achieve the same seakeeping performance. Thus *Kennell et al.* argue the latter, larger monohull is the real equivalent design. This just demonstrates that comparisons of unconventional and conventional design options require clarity in the comparisons being made. This could be said to be a further subtlety in any discussion of unconventional ships and their design process, to which we now turn.

4. Nature of Unconventional Ship Design

From the discussion of conventional ship design together with Table 1, giving a taxonomy of design based on design novelty, unconventional design clearly needs to cover the design of both the last two categories of radical configuration and radical technology. Furthermore this seems to match the two broad types of unconventional ships distinguished at the start of this paper. The design process applicable to each of these is discussed below, however it is the contention of this paper that unconventional ship design also encompasses unconventional ways of designing more conventional vessels. Thus the author's Integrated Synthesis or Architecturally driven approach, encapsulated in the UCL Design Building Block (DBB) approach, *Andrews and Dicks (1997)*, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)* is seen as such an approach to deal with the design of non-conventional complex physical large and complex (PL&C) systems. This term has been used in arguing marine vessels and structures are just one important domain of PL&C systems alongside large chemical and civil engineering facilities and large building complexes, such as Heathrow Terminal 5. These systems have at their heart the "wicked problem", *Rittel and Webber (1974)*, which requires a Requirement Elucidation approach, *Andrews (2011)* to an extended concept phase, *Andrews (2013)* and this is therefore considered more fully in next section, under the heading of "Designing Unconventionally" to distinguish it from the design of unconventional vessels.

Turning first to the design of vessels designed to incorporate radical technology, these craft such ACVs, jetfoils, and semi planing craft are driven by the need to achieve high speeds and hence adopt aerospace type technologies, which are unconventional for the maritime sector. Because of their need to go fast with more aircraft like power weight ratios, to lift such hulls out of the water if they are to achieve speeds impossible with displacement hulls, they have both been produced using the approach of the aerospace industry sector and logically adopt that industry's practice. This is not just in regard to the very light weight structure and propulsive plant but also resorting to full-scale prototypes and re-tooling production lines for each new "model". Thus for an appropriate design approach one needs to look at aerospace design practice, which as has already been remarked has traditionally dealt with design of new craft by constructing full scale prototypes. This is quite unlike the design of PL&C systems, typified by "big ships".

One good summary of aerospace practice, at the most complex end, is given in a paper on the Lockheed Martin "Skunk Works", *Miller (1995)*. This article on the "Principles of the SKUNK Works" largely focuses on the management culture that enabled a relatively small team to bring into US service high performance spy planes and the first stealth fighters (see the list of 14 short Operating Rules, *Miller (1995)*). Thus such high-end aerospace practice is characterised by "simple brief systems specifications", with three critical performance parameters): focus on engineering design; a concurrent engineering approach; and early development of prototypes. Given the size of the product relative to ocean going vessels, full-scale physical prototyping of advanced marine craft is possible and thus de rigueur for such novel technologies. However, the consequence is an extremely high investment in early design development, which has been an anathema in the main marine industries producing large ocean going vessels. (The only exception in the marine sector being naval weapons development (e.g. sensors, command & control and weapon delivery systems), which has much closer links to aerospace practice than the heavy marine industries.) It is thus not surprising that ad-

vanced technological options for even naval vessels have been very rarely pursued beyond the research phase and there are no high speed oceangoing vessels – genuine high speed has so far only been applied to high speed small coastal ferries and small naval craft (e.g. Boeing Jetfoil PHMs and USN ACV LCACs).

As already mentioned there are currently few oceangoing high-speed vessels, however as this paper ought to also consider the future scope of approaches to ship design, it is worth briefly addressing this issue. Furthermore it could be argued some semi high-speed vessels have been produced, the obvious recent example being the, problem riven, US Navy Littoral Combatant Ships (LCS) (in both its fast trimaran and semi-planing mono-hull variants – see *Warship Technology (2016)*). Part of the problem with these vessels could be seen in trying to extrapolate to an ocean going capability technologies only current exploitable in smaller fast coastal vessels. Thus 3,000 tonne designs intended to operate “in the littoral” up to 50 knots, require not just high powered jet engines (gas turbines) and state of the art water jet propulsors but also very thin steel (in the monohull variant) or aluminium (in the trimaran variant). However the latter structure has to resist the classic deep ocean wave loadings of a hull girder bending nature, with a material both lacking sufficient Young’s Modulus and with a fatigue life much less than that of steel. The extent to which there needs to be a major investment in both high speed propulsion and ship appropriate structural material development was starkly spelt out by *Keane (2003)* from the considerable pre-concept research investigations undertaken by the US Navy in its desire to project large land forces “From the Sea” at high speeds over intercontinental distances.

Turning now to the second unconventional ship category (that of radical configurations), but essentially for ocean going vessels having to adopt current ship technologies, the design approaches vary in their specifics with the choice of the particular (largely multihull) configuration. The designs of the various multihulls tend to be driven by a particular issue. Thus catamarans are designed to achieve moderately high speeds and SWATH by much reduced ship motions in a seaway, whereas Trimarans are much more like monohulls, in being good at most aspects, given they are essentially slender monohulls, with bits on, see Table 2). The two cases of SWATH and Trimaran are considered in more detail in the next two sub-sections.

4.1 The Preliminary Design of SWATH Vessels

The initial design procedure for a SWATH vessel is more complicated than for its conventional equivalent, as there are many more variables to be taken into account from the beginning in order to get a first estimate of ship size. This does have the advantage that that the geometry of each separate part, namely box structure, struts and hulls, can to some degree be considered separately, although they must then be sensibly brought together as their final selected dimensions are interactive with each other in achieving a balanced design. The complication is further compounded, as with all novel hull forms, by a basic lack of design data and in particular sufficient parametric guidance.

In initial sizing, individual space balances are required for the box and the struts plus hulls, with the latter usually containing the Tankage, Ballast, deep stores and some of the power and propulsion systems. As regards initial weight estimates, most weight groups can draw on monohull data. The main exception is the structural weight fraction for which the much higher value for, say, a SWATH naval combatant to its deep displacement of 0.45 is a more appropriate start point. This is necessary because of the larger relative area of structural material and the dominant transverse structural prying loads. This guidance obviously can be modified if there are clear reasons, from the beginning of the design, to depart from current SWATH practice, for example if greater loads are predicted or if configurational or material differences are intended or imposed.

Further guidance on the initial synthesis is that it is usually sufficient to initially determine the basic ship dimensions using the main underwater parameters and assume that there will be sufficient volume provided in the box structure above. Typically the proportion of displacement provided by the hulls relative to the submerged portion of the struts will be 0.70 to 0.85. Below this range the struts

become excessive with resistance penalties and degraded seakeeping, and above it there will be insufficient waterplane leading to stability and trim plus sinkage problems. For the hulls the primary parameter is their Prismatic Coefficient (C_p), which is defined in terms of hull length and the average diameter (the latter being particularly necessary to adopt as an average when the hulls have elliptical and varying cross sections). For low to medium speed forms, that is Froude Number ≤ 0.45 then C_p should be 0.60 to 0.70, while for smaller higher speed craft (such as fast ferries operating at $F_n > 0.55$) then $C_p \geq 0.90$. The other very significant early design choice is that of box clearance, which is usually driven by the choice of the significant wave height in the maximum sea state for which slamming is to be avoided.

Beyond the initial sizing, which requires a greater degree of form parameter and dimension selection than in the monohull case to obtain first estimates of size, volume and weight, then the parametric survey consists of a more detailed refinement of the initial form parameter selection. In particular, there needs to be an early check that the stability and trim requirements can be met. In consequence the parametric selection tackles the hulls and struts first before the box dimensions are selected. The latter will be driven by the separation of the struts and, to a lesser degree, by the hulls and struts lengths. Since an excessive overhang of the box structure would have both weight and centroid implications, which the parametric selection would have to take into account, it is important to give particular attention to longitudinal balance from the start. Andrews (2004) lists a series of further design considerations, such as number of struts per hull, strut length and strut separation. All these aspects show the highly interactive nature of SWATH preliminary design, which is more akin to submarine sizing, with the need for care in weight and buoyancy/moment balance not so necessary for monohull ships.

4.2 The Preliminary Design of Trimaran Ships

Although the Trimaran is essentially a slender monohull, modified with the addition of side hulls, to initially size the vessel it is necessary to determine practically all the principal form parameters. This is unlike the case of the conventional monohull, where it is possible to delay full parametric selection, since there is a large historical database and so the designer can be reasonably confident that the initial default hull parameter values adopted to size the option will only need refining beyond the initial sizing.

Essentially the sizing and hull form selection for the Trimaran are in three interrelated parts, namely main hull, side hulls and cross deck structure:

- **Main Hull.** This is slender and so the length to hull beam and hull beam to draught ratios should be selected to be 14 and 2.0, respectively, given by the speed range and the available monohull methodical series data for powering estimation. Initial UCL Frigate studies extrapolated *Taylor-Gertler (1953)* data slightly beyond the range of a typical current frigate form to fit the dimensions and chosen form parameters ($C_m = 0.803$, $C_p = 0.581$). This choice of parent form is appropriate if a twin shaft arrangement is to be adopted. Clearly the more radical adoption of single shaft or even podded propulsion would require further modification to the parent hull form.
- **Side Hulls.** The dimensions and form of the side hulls are essentially governed by overall stability considerations, as their impact on resistance (through their large wetted surface area relative to their displacement) and their contribution to structural weight needs to be minimized. The side hulls provide the major contribution to the transverse righting moment and through them a high GM_T is easily achieved. The critical stability condition for a naval combatant would be the damage case with one side hull damaged with a breach of 0.15 x ship's waterline length, which represented flooding of (say) five adjacent compartments in the closely subdivided side hulls. This extent of flooding implies flooding 50% of the side hull length, which typically means the side hulls' waterline length being just under 40% of the ship's waterline length, whereas in the case of a commercial ship it is unlikely that the side hulls would need to be quite so extensive and demanding in the design. There still remain choices on the side hull form such as whether flat surfaces are adopted, likely to lead to two

sets of knuckle lines. For radar signature reasons a 7° flare was introduced on the outboard side of the side hulls, while a 30° rise of floor was also incorporated to reduce slam-induced pressures on the side hulls. The side hulls can be made symmetrical about their centreline plane. The mid section of the side hulls can be located relative to the main hull with a choice balancing the extent of the length aft of amidships. This position could be further aft as best for reducing resistance at speed, but significantly worse for coping with damage stability. In the end the choice of side hull longitudinal position is also determined by upper deck and internal deck layout preferences, in conjunction with ensuring the cross deck structure remains less exposed to wave action in the forward portion of the hull.

- **Cross Structure.** The first decision on the cross deck structure is in regard its outboard length and whether it should be the same as that of the side hulls. The most significant parameter is that of wet deck clearance, which for a frigate size is suggested to be 3.5 m. based on the early analysis of symmetric motion seakeeping analysis described more fully in *Andrews (2004)*. This choice effectively will drive the depth of the main hull to the upper weather deck, since Depth equals Draught + Wetdeck Clearance + Wetdeck "Double Bottom" structure + Main Deck to Upper Deck. This consideration means the Trimaran is likely to have an overall excess of volume relative to its monohull equivalent. Although it might be considered that this excess volume is a negative feature of Trimaran designs, since it might seem to imply that the designs are not strictly "balanced" solutions, it can be argued that because the excess is in the central portion of the ship high up on the main deck(s), it greatly increases the "real estate" in the prime part of the ship. If additionally a highly adaptable design is required through life, then this objective can be much more readily facilitated in a Trimaran than a monohull.

Should other applications than frigates be pursued using the Trimaran configuration, such as fast ferries, cruise liners or fast feeder route container ships, then the specific nature of this guidance is likely to be less appropriate, although the above sequence is considered to be broadly applicable.

5. Designing Unconventionally

The author has argued for many years, particularly with respect to complex (naval) vessels, that complex ships really ought to be initially designed in a manner similar to the configurationally driven ships, *Andrews (2003)*. Thus the synthesis should commence with a preferred disposition of the primary operational and support spaces of such service ships. This architecturally driven approach, then requires a putative hull (and superstructure) to be "wrapped" around the spaces, which is readily possible with modern CASD systems. This Design Building Block (DBB) approach alters the initial design focus to produce a gradual joint evolution of the inside spatial disposition, weight and displacement, and hull dimensions and form, as is shown in Fig.3 and numerically summarised in Table 3 (actually for a trimaran combatant example and so is very appropriate for the design synthesis of ocean going multi-hulls).

Additionally the DBB approach enables the ship designer to much more readily derive designs exploring design decisions beyond the classical (S^4) issues to address wider "Style" decisions and even use Simulation Based Design (SBD) to explore human factors aspects well before the design dimensions and parameters are essentially fixed. Thus the design exploration in the concept phase can then be used to question many of the major design decisions that are largely ignored (or not even recognised to be considerable so early), but which actually determine the choice of design options being used to produce the selected design solution and the emergent requirement, both of which then go forward to be developed.

The logic underlying the SURFCON tool realisation of the UCL Design Building Block approach was spelt out by *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*. In essence this approach gives a primary focus to ship architecture and ensures that is produced alongside the traditional numerical sizing and naval architectural balance in the initial design synthesis.

Fig.3: Architectural representations of the UCL LCS study showing the design building blocks at each of the concept design stages, *Andrews and Pawling (2008)*

The Design Building Block approach to producing a new ship design is outlined in Fig.4. This diagram summarises a comprehensive set of analysis processes, most of which are unlikely to be used in the initial setting up of the design or even in early iterations around the sequence of selecting and placing Design Building Blocks, hull geometric definition and size balance. In fact several of the inputs shown in Fig.4 are either specific to the naval combatant case, such as topside features, or omit aspects which could be dominant in specialist vessels, such as aircraft carriers or amphibious warfare vessels, where personnel and vehicle flow are likely to dominate the internal ship configuration, rather than, say, topside configuration in a surface combatant.

Table 3 Summary of the UCL LCS design stages shown in Fig.3, *Andrews and Pawling (2008)*

Start of Major Feature Design Stage	(in 11 discrete SBBs and grouped BBs) 2830 tonne; 5300 m ³ ; 126.2 m
End of Major Feature Design Stage	(in 15 discrete SBBs and grouped BBs) 2900 tonne; 24000 m ³ ; 135 m
End of Super Building Block Design Stage	(in 33 discrete SBBs and grouped BBs) 3100 tonne; 22700 m ³ ; 135 m
End of Building Block Design Stages (Design freeze)	(in c. 25 SBBs and 11 grouped BBs) 3210 tonne; 26000 m ³ ; 136.3 m

The SURFCON realisation of the Design Building Block approach to preliminary ship design is described in *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, as is its place as a module within Graphics Research Corporation's PARAMARINE ship design suite, *Munoz and Forrest (2002)*. A feature of SURFCON is the use of the term Master Building Block to denote how the overall aggregated attributes of the Design Building Blocks can be brought together to provide the numerical description of the resultant ship design. The advantage of providing the Design Building Block capability of SURFCON, as an adjunct to the well-established commercial ship design suite of PARAMARINE, is that the audited building block attributes within the Master Building Block can be directly used by PARAMARINE, so the necessary naval architectural calculations can be performed to ascertain the balance or otherwise of the configuration just produced by the designer.

Fig.4: Design building block approach applied to surface ship initial design, *Andrews and Dicks (1997)*

Typical information held in the Master Building Block includes:

- Overall ship requirements: ship speed, seakeeping, stability, signatures (in the case of a naval combatant);
- Ship characteristics: weight, space, centroid;
- Overall margins: weight, space and their locations for both growth and enhancement.

As the design description is built up and modified, all the features of the Design Building Blocks are normally utilised by the system. The geometric definition (shape and location) is used to constantly update the graphical display, while Fig.5 shows the tree structure, graphical description and an analytical window, all of which are described in more detail in *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*. Fig.3 shows the graphical evolution and Table 3 a tabular summary of numerical information for each of the major concept stages for a given design study, *Andrews and Pawling (2008)*.

Fig.5: SURFCON representation showing the three panes for tree structure, graphics (Design Building Blocks) and analysis (weight balance in example)

It has been argued that the DBB approach to preliminary ship design is a significant step towards a complete design sketch philosophy in the earliest stages of ship design, in that it encourages a sketching-like approach of exploration, innovation and understanding in design. However, the full exploitation of highly flexible sketch representations to explore and more fully understand the design space is limited in preliminary ship design. To enable a process more akin to design sketching for preliminary ship design, a flexible, interactive, visually rich CAD system with a flexible configurational model and, vitally, integrated technical analysis is seen to be required.

As noted above, although the flexible, configurationally centred SURFCON implementation of the DBB approach is seen to assist in utilising a sketching approach in preliminary ship design, there are also features that could be enhanced. Future developments could reduce the “gulf of execution” (see *Pawling (2007)*) by reducing the degree of abstraction and duplication needed to represent ship features. Those needs could also be improved by utilising existing and developmental interface technologies, such as graphics tablets, 3-D pens, high-resolution screens, 3D and Virtual Reality. There is considered to be a clear agenda for significant developments in spatially oriented tools for preliminary ship design, provided this can be taken up by the ship design profession and the vendors of their tools.

6. Conclusions

- It is likely there will be more unconventional ships in the future and they need to have appropriate design approaches and methods.
- Unconventional ship design is not just necessary for unconventional ships (and craft) but also for the most complex ships, as examples of Physically Large and Complex systems (PL&C) (where should be the norm).
- With the advent of technologies such as VR then Simulation Based Design (SBD) will also modify approaches to designing unconventionally, especially to incorporate the whole system aspects, such as Human Factors (HF), with an architecturally based preliminary design approach becoming the conventional approach, *Tupper (2014)*.
- It is always good design practice to consider the unconventional, as “Striving for the novel can also enhance the prosaic”.

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CFD Analysis of Hydrodynamic Characteristics of High-speed Displacement Hull-forms fitted with Hull Vane®

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Abstract

The hydrodynamic performance of round bilge high-speed hull forms are of considerable interest in the field of maritime engineering as such vessels could be suitably deployed for a variety of purposes such as naval vessels for shore protection, surveillance, rescue, anti-smuggling, combating piracy, relief operations during natural disasters as well as high-speed coastal transport. The seakeeping performance and resistance prediction of high-speed displacement hull forms fitted with Hull Vane® have been analyzed using Star CCM+, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation tool. However, the resistance prediction was carried out using NUMECA Fine™/Marine. Hull Vane® is a fixed foil located below the waterline, aft of the stern of the vessel. This study was carried out to investigate the heave and pitch responses as well as the resistance characteristics of high-speed displacement hull forms fitted with a Hull Vane®. Selected models of Australian Maritime Engineering Cooperative Research Centre (AMECRC) systematic series hull forms have been used for this investigation. Investigations carried out so far show considerable promise in designing vessels or fitting existing vessels with Hull Vane®.

1. Introduction

Designers of high-speed vessels have been continuously striving to improve the hydrodynamic characteristics. The seakeeping behaviour of fast mono-hulls degrade in higher sea states which affects its operability. Conventional mono-hull designs always focused on optimizing the calm water performance. The world is looking at greener ships with lower carbon emission and better fuel efficiency. In order to make the existing ships more fuel efficient, research endeavour has been to develop to improved hull forms by modifying the forward and aft regions of the hull.

In this study on motions, five models from the AMECRC systematic series were chosen. For resistance prediction, model #13 from the AMECRC systematic series was chosen. The motion responses for head seas in an irregular sea way have been determined at Froude numbers ranging from 0.1 to 1.0. An attempt has also been made to predict the bare hull motion response of the five models using MAXSURF motions and Star CCM+ for validation purposes. Motion transfer function for heave and pitch obtained by both the methods have been validated against experimental results. After validating Star CCM+, a CFD tool, with these results, it was used to predict the motion response of the hull forms with Hull Vane®. The seakeeping and resistance evaluation using Star CCM+ and NUMECA Fine™/Marine have been presented for selected models with and without Hull Vane® respectively. Although it is very difficult to see any significant improvement when fitted with a Hull Vane®, the results nevertheless look quite promising.

2. Background

Numerous studies have been carried out in the past in an attempt to improve the seakeeping behaviour of fast ships. These studies mainly focused on developing new hull forms which resulted in a wide variety of advanced marine vehicles for high-speed transportation. *Fridsma (1969)* carried out extensive research in an attempt to explain the importance of various design parameters on the hydrodynamic behaviour of vessels. *Fridsma (1969)* conducted tests on models with different deadrise angles

in different condition in both regular and irregular waves. *Fridsma's (1969)* research concluded that motions responses were non-linear in nature.

Beukelman and Huijser (1976) studied the influence of various parameters on the seakeeping qualities of systematically varied ships forms in head seas. In their study a series of hull forms were derived from “Todd 60” series. The model parameters such as length-beam (L/B) ratio, length-draft (L/T) ratio and the mid-ship section coefficient were kept constant. Their investigation was based on 44 models developed by varying the block coefficient, the longitudinal centre of buoyancy and the fore body section shape.

Ship Hydromechanics Laboratory of the Delft University of Technology, carried out full-scale trials to study the limiting factors that affect the operation of fast ships in irregular waves. These test results imply that, speed reduction is necessary in order to prevent any potential consecutive impacts from happening, *Rijkens (2016)*. *Fridsma (1969)* noted that increase the running trim from 4° to 6° can result in 50% to 100% higher values in the vertical acceleration on hull with a deadrise angle of 20° moving at constant speed in regular head waves.

In general, trim control can be achieved with the help of hydrodynamic lift generating devices such as interceptors, wedges or transom flaps. Interceptor is a vertically mounted plate extending below the hull, perpendicular to incoming flow. Wedge flap is situated underneath the transom stern, integrated into the hull bottom plating of the ship. Transom flap is a flat plate extending aft of the hull, *Rijkens (2016)*. *Salas et al. (2004)* conducted systematic tests on scaled models, to evaluate the hydrodynamic performance of stern flaps and its effects. The experiments were conducted on towing tanks with six configurations for stern flaps, obtained by changing chord length, span and flap angle. They also tested the bare hull performance to compare these results against the hull forms with stern flaps.

Fig.1a: Transom flaps - *Rijkens (2016)*

Fig.1b: Interceptors - *Rijkens (2016)*

Also, considerable amount of research has been conducted in the past on stern appendages such as trim tabs, stern wedges, stern flaps, interceptors and transom wedges for resistance reduction. All of these have proven to reduce the overall resistance of a vessel by reducing its running trim. In a study conducted on stern wedges by *Karafiath and Fisher (1987)*, it was shown that a reduction of running trim of up to 2.0° could result in a 2% of saving in fuel consumption. *Cusanelli and Cave (1993)* investigated the application of stern flaps as a retrofit on US Navy vessels and found a reduction in power which resulted in reduced fuel consumption and increased top speed. In a later study by *Karafiath and Cusanelli (1997)* on integrated wedge-flap design, a reduction in power of 11.6% was observed, while a wedge-only configuration lead to a power reduction of 6.2%. *Tsai and Hwang (2003)* studied interceptors and found that these can be used to reduce the resistance of planning hulls.

In line with the above research, *van Oossanen (1992)* invented the Hull Vane[®] *Uithof et al. (2014)*, a fixed, resistance-reducing foil situated below the water line, aft of the stern of the ship. *Uithof et al. (2014)* have summarised the various application of Hull Vane[®] on different types of vessels. Extensive research using CFD computations, model tests and sea trials have been conducted and found that the reduction in resistance can be up to 26.5% on ships running at Froude number between 0.2 and 0.7.

3. AMECRC Systematic Series

Australian Marine Engineering Co-operative Research Centre (AMECRC) conducted research on high-speed round-bilge, transom-stern hull forms, to develop a systematic series of hull forms suitable for combatants. AMECRC series hull forms are based on the High Speed Displacement Hull Forms (HSDHF) developed at Maritime Research Institute Netherlands (MARIN) as a result of a 10 year project on combatant-vessel design, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*.

Fig.2: Lines Plan of the Parent Hull Form of AMECRC Series, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*

The parent hull form, Fig.2, of the AMECRC series is similar to the HSDHF series, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*, and Table 1 shows the parameters that are varied in order to obtain the 14 models in the series. In the present study only 5 out of the 14 models of the AMECRC series were chosen, parameters of which are depicted in Table 2. The parameters of the models which are kept constant have been shown in Table 3.

4. Hull Vane®

Table 1: AMECRC Parameter ranges, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*

	Parent model	AMECRC
L/B	8.0	4 – 8
B/T	4.0	2.5 - 4.0
C _B	0.396	0.396 - 0.50

Table 2: Parameters of the five models used for this analysis, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*

Model	L/B	B/T	C _B	Model Disp.(kg)	L/∇ ^{1/3}	WSA (m ²)
3	8	2.5	0.447	11.454	7.098	0.3626
4	8	4	0.447	7.158	8.302	0.3064
8	4	2.5	0.5	51.197	4.308	0.7552
11	4	4	0.5	32.006	5.039	0.6318
13	6	3.25	0.45	15.784	6.379	0.4384

A hull vane is a wing-shaped fixed-foil structure, placed horizontally below the waterline near the stern of the vessel. When the stern wave flows over the hull vane, a hydrodynamic lift is created. The lift created by the Hull Vane[®] can be resolved into two forces, one in x-direction and one in z-direction, Fig.3. Hull Vane[®] has four distinct effects on vessels namely, a thrust force, a trim correction, the reduction of waves, and the reduction of motions in waves, *Uithof et al. (2014)*.

Table 3: Parameters kept constant for the models, *Sahoo et al. (1999)*

C_p	0.626
C_{WP}	0.796
A_T/A_x	0.296
B_T/B_x	0.964
LCB	44.6% L_{PP} from transom

Fig.3: Schematic representation of the forces on the Hull Vane[®], *Uithof et al. (2014)*

5. CFD Tool - Star CCM+

STAR-CCM+ (2014), a CFD tool has the capability to model a wide range of fluid dynamics phenomenon such as incompressible, compressible, laminar and turbulent fluid flow problems and solves conservation equations of mass and momentum. CFD analysis of a problem involves three main steps namely pre-processing, analysis of the problem and post-processing, *Mahmood and Huang (2011)*. Pre-processing involves creating the model geometry and importing into CFD package, creating a domain, generating the required mesh and setting up the boundary conditions. Analysis is carried out by the CFD which is based on the user input. The post processing is comprised of the graphs, results, and values that are fetched once the analysis has been completed.

Fig.4: Wave pattern from CFD computations on the 55 meter supply vessel without Hull Vane[®] (top) and with Hull Vane[®] (bottom) at 20 knots, *Uithof et al. (2014)*

Figs.4 and 5 depict the changes to wave patterns in CFD as well as behind the vessel with and without Hull Vane®.

Fig.5: Comparison of the wave profile of the 55 meter supply vessel without Hull Vane® (left) and with Hull Vane® (right) at 13 knots sea trials, *Uithof et al. (2014)*

6. Model Geometry, Domain and Boundary Condition

The domain around the AMECRC hull has been constructed such that the boundaries do not influence the results. The analysis has been performed in the created domain which also acts as the virtual towing tank where the fluid flow depicts the real world scenario. In general, the size of the domain is usually represented in terms of ships’ length. In this paper the length forward and aft of the hull has been taken as three times and two times ships’ respectively. The width and height of the domain around the hull has been taken as one ships’ length. The domain has been divided into three zones, velocity inlet, and pressure outlet and symmetry plane. AMECRC model along with domain is shown the Fig.7.

7. Mesh generation and Solution setup

Once the domain has been created, Boolean operation has been carried out to subtract the model from the domain, into order to make the whole domain as one single body as recommended by user’s manual of Star CCM+. In order to get greater mesh quality and for obtaining sound results of the marine solution, trimmed cell meshing method has been used for creating a finer mesh around the domain. Figures 8 to 11 have been shown with trimmed cell mesh and volume mesh around model 8 of the AMECRC systematic series. The physics of models used for flow analysis are three dimensional, incompressible, implicit unsteady, Eulerian multiphase, viscous and turbulent flow. Since free surface motion is governed by gravitational forces, gravity has been considered. Volume of fluid (VOF) method is good for modelling free surface flows such as ship motion through open water, filling of tank and sloshing. VOF method has been adopted to solve multiphase flow. For turbulence model, realizable $\kappa - \epsilon$ turbulence model has been used.

Fig.6: Model 13 with Hull Vane® in Star CCM+

Fig.7: Boundary Domain

8. CFD Tool – NUMECA Fine™/Marine

NUMECA Fine™/Marine is an integrated computational fluid dynamics software environment for the simulation of mono-fluid and multi-fluid flows around ships, boats or yachts, including various types

of appendages. It is a commercially available package and is used for generating the unstructured hexahedral mesh and solving the steady flow. The model setup is used for analyzing the bare hull model 13 of the AMECRC series with and without Hull Vane[®] for Froude numbers 0.5, 0.6, 0.7. The hull is free to trim and sink, using the 6° of freedom solver, allowing the hull to surge, sway, heave, pitch, yaw and roll.

The simulation was conducted with zero forward speed after which the speed was gradually increased to the final velocity. The "volume of fluid" method is used to account for the free surface (i.e. both water and air flows are solved). The free stream turbulence quantities were initialized using the reference length and velocity. Wall functions were used to simulate the flow in regions very close to solid walls, reducing the mesh density requirements in the boundary layer.

Fig.8: Trimmed cell mesh of model 8 of the AMECRC systematic series

9. Domain and Boundary Conditions

The domain around the hull is constructed such that the boundaries do not influence the results. Only half of the ship was modelled for computational efficiency. The dimensions of the computational domain around the hull are given in Table 5. In the symmetry plane a mirror boundary condition was applied and on the top and the bottom of the domain the pressure was prescribed. All other domain faces have external/free-flow boundary conditions with a prescribed flow speed of 0 m/s.

Table 5: Limits of Domain

X (longitudinal)	-4.8 m	3.2 m
Y (beam)	0.0 m	3.2 m
Z (height)	-3.2 m	0.8 m

10. Mesh Generation

The domain volume is divided into small cells to generate the mesh. The largest cells on the hull are approximately $\Delta(X, Y, Z) \approx 0.0016$ m in size. In areas with large curvature and small features, cells as small as $\Delta(X, Y, Z) \approx 0.000098$ m were used to ensure that flow features have a good resolution. Extra cells were added perpendicular to the hull surfaces to ensure a good resolution in the boundary layer. The first cell near the wall was set to have a size of about 0.00064 m, such that its non-dimensional distance (y^+) to the wall was approximately 30.5. Cells near the air-water interface were refined to have a size of 0.0016 m in z-direction. Fig.11 shows the mesh on the surface of the hull.

Fig.9: Meshed model - side view

Fig.10: Meshed model showing Hull Vane®

Fig.11: Meshed model - stern view and bow view

11. CFD Validation and Discussion

For validation purposes motion transfer functions were predicted using MAXSURF and Star CCM+, for models 4, 8 and 13 of the AMECRC series at different speeds corresponding to F_n 0.285, 0.57 and 0.856 for which experimental results were available. Figs.13 and 14 compare experimental value and the predicted motions response characteristics of models 4 and 8 of the AMECRC systematic series. From the comparative analysis it can be seen that at lower speed of about F_n 0.285, model 4 showed good agreement between predicted results and experimental values. Model 8 for the same Froude number, showed minor differences. Since the predicted motion results are plotted as a continuous data rather than discrete data and experimental results are plotted as discrete data, a small difference is observed at low Froude numbers for model 8.

12. HYDROS Theory

HYDROS is based on the thin-ship approach. The reader is referred to the work of Doctors (2003), where the method has been detailed. This essentially inviscid analysis can be easily modified in order to account approximately for all of viscosity, surface tension, and surface elasticity (representing surface contaminants). In this paper HYDROS has not been utilized for any computational work.

Fig.12: Volume mesh of model 8 of the AMECRC systematic series

Fig.13: Model 4 Validation results

Fig.14: Model 8 Validation results

13. Resistance prediction – Star CCM+ & NUMECA FineTM/Marine

The resistance to displacement ratio (R_T/Δ) value of the model 13 obtained through Star CCM+ simulations have been compared against the actual experimental value of bare hull. The results have

been presented for three different velocities corresponding to Froude numbers 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7 in Table 6 and Fig.15.

Table 6: Resistance data validation for Model 13

Fn	Fn_∇	(R_T/Δ)_{STARCCM+}	(R_T/Δ)_{EXPT.}	% difference
0.5	1.263	0.06389	0.06531	-2.23%
0.6	1.515	0.08271	0.08789	-6.26%
0.7	1.768	0.10296	0.10263	0.32%

Fig.15: Star CCM+ and Experimental data for bare hull

Table 7 shows the % difference between the experimental and NUMECA CFD results. The error comparison between the NUMECA FineTM/Marine and the experimental data shows an average difference of 5% in R_T/Δ value for the corresponding Froude numbers 0.5, 0.6, 0.7. As can be seen from Tables 6 and 7 the differences between CFD and experimental results lie within $\pm 6\%$ and within the bounds of experimental and computational errors can be considered as reasonable in agreement.

14. Results and Conclusion

Star CCM+ has been used to predict the motion characteristics with and without Hull Vane[®] for models 3, 4, 8, 11 and 13 although only results of models 4 and 8 have been presented in this paper. The simulations were carried out for speed corresponding to Froude number 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 and 1.0. The computed heave and pitch motion characteristics for the five models of the AMECRC series with and without Hull Vane[®] have been depicted in graphical form as transfer functions against non-dimensional wave frequencies. Figures 19 and 20 exhibit the heave and pitch transfer function for the AMECRC models 4 and 8. The results predicted using Star CCM+ and MAXSURF showed reduction in the heave and pitch transfer function of models fitted with Hull Vane[®]. It was obvious from the results obtained through CFD that there are differences in the motion response. Nevertheless the results show considerable promise that Hull Vane[®] may in fact prove to be a helpful device in reducing motions. In this respect Star CCM+ results need to be validated not only against experimental results but also changing the configuration of the vane in terms of its position in stern region and tweaking the angle of attack in order to maximize its effects on motion.

The model 13 of the AMECRC series was run for Froude numbers of 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7 with the Hull Vane[®] attached to it. These results were compared with the bare hull resistance of the model from Star CCM+ simulations and the difference was calculated as a percentage. The comparison between the resistance of the bare hull with and without Hull Vane[®] indicates a reduction in resistance for the model with Hull Vane[®].

Table 7: Resistance data validation for Model 13

Fn	Fn_v	(R_T/Δ)_{NUMECA}	(R_T/Δ)_{EXPT.}	% difference
0.5	1.263	0.06247	0.06531	-4.54%
0.6	1.515	0.08297	0.08789	-5.92%
0.7	1.768	0.09775	0.10263	-5.21%

Fig.16: NUMECA FineTM/Marine and Experimental data for bare hull

Table 8: Resistance data of model 13 with and without Hull Vane[®] using Star CCM+

Fn	Fn_v	(R_T/Δ)_{WITHOUTVANE}	(R_T/Δ)_{WITHVANE}	diff.
0.5	1.263	0.06389	0.06195	-3.126%
0.6	1.515	0.08271	0.08088	-2.269%
0.7	1.768	0.10296	0.09990	-3.061%

Fig.17: Resistance data for the model 13 with and without Hull Vane[®] using Star CCM+

Table 9: Resistance data of model 13 with and without Hull Vane[®] using NUMECA FineTM/Marine

Fn	Fn_v	(R_T/Δ)_{WITHOUTVANE}	(R_T/Δ)_{WITHVANE}	diff.
0.5	1.263	0.06247	0.05465	-14.32%
0.6	1.515	0.08297	0.07507	-10.53%
0.7	1.768	0.09775	0.09028	-8.05%

Fig.18: Resistance data for model 13 with and without Hull Vane[®] using NUMECA FineTM/Marine

Fig.19: Heave and Pitch transfer function for Model 4

Fig.20: Heave and Pitch transfer function for Model 8

The Star CCM+ simulations show an average reduction in resistance of 3% when fitted with a Hull Vane[®] whereas the NUMECA Fine[™]/Marine simulations show percentage reduction in resistance varying from 8% to 14%. The addition of Hull Vane[®] shows a significant reduction in the total resistance of the model. A Hull Vane[®] is optimized for required speed and it is to be noted that a limited number of simulations were carried out to get these results.

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An Integrated Approach for Developing Rough Water Methodologies for Small High-Speed Craft Structure, Equipment, Shock Isolation Seats, and Human Performance At-Sea

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Abstract

This paper presents a new integrated approach to investigating the effects of wave impacts on hull structure, equipment ruggedness, shock isolation seats, and human performance in small high-speed planing craft. Acceleration data recorded during full-scale seakeeping trials are presented to illustrate lessons learned from deterministic studies of individual wave impacts. Example applications are presented to show how use of both statistical and deterministic methodologies address a broader range of design and comparative analysis topics than obtained from a single approach. Implications for further research are also presented.

1. Introduction

For craft that operate beyond calm sea conditions the study of seakeeping is synonymous with the study of wave effects on dynamic stability, structural integrity, effects on equipment, and effects on human comfort, safety, and performance, *Blount (2014)*. The earliest studies of high-speed craft in waves faced major challenges, especially in the field of instrumentation and data acquisition. Even with advances in electronics it was extremely challenging because of limited data processing methods for interpreting the recorded motions. The subsequent introduction of computer hardware and data processing software fostered the development of statistical approaches for hull design and methods for assessing wave impact effects on humans. The following paragraphs provide a broad overview of the statistical approaches used to study hull strength and human ride quality to illustrate the importance of their evolutionary development. But there is sufficient justification now to also pursue a new non-statistical approach. This is especially true in light of advanced data analysis software not widely available 15 years ago.

1.1 Hull Structure Impact Load

The earliest hull design studies focused on underwater pressure, acceleration, and strain data to study wave impact loads during seakeeping trials. Fig.1 shows pressure data and acceleration data recorded during high-speed craft trials of a naval support craft in the mid-1940's. Fig.2 shows pressure, hull strain, and acceleration data recorded in the 1950's, *DuCane (1956)*. Peak amplitudes were determined manually using appropriate scales and values were hand printed on paper plots referred to as strip charts.

Fig.1: Example Craft Data Circa 1944

Fig.2: Craft Data Circa 1956

In rough seas the relationship between the wave impact pressure distribution and the dynamic response of the craft is very complex. Simplifying assumptions were therefore made that assumed the net vertical force at a hull cross-section due to the pressure distribution at any instant in time is directly proportional to the heave acceleration response at that cross-section, *Heller and Jasper (1960)*. The heave acceleration was used as a measure of the wave impact load in units of g. Later developments included publication of the envelope of the maximum vertical acceleration (i.e.; impact load factor) shown in Fig.3. It was used to compute an effective design pressure, *Allen and Jones (1978)*.

Fig. 21 - Impact-Load Factors Derived from Experimental Data

Fig.3: Maximum Vertical Acceleration

The paper by *Allen and Jones (1978)* acknowledged that the most difficult and controversial step in the hull design pressure calculation was selection of the impact load factor (i.e.; the rigid body acceleration value). For planing hulls the paper referenced work by *Savitsky and Brown (1976)* whose significant contributions included an empirical equation for computing the average vertical acceleration (i.e.; A_{AVG} , the average of many impact peak accelerations) at the longitudinal center of gravity (LCG) as a function of wave height, speed, craft deadrise, beam, length, and weight. The empirical fit was based on scale-model data for irregular seas analyzed to determine its statistical distribution, *Fridsma (1971)*. The A1/N approach had the benefit of being able to scale from the A_{AVG} acceleration using the following theoretical equations for the exponentially distributed scale-model data.

$$A_{1/N} = A_{AVG} [1 + \ln(N)] \quad \text{Equation (1-1)}$$

$$A_{1/3} = 2.1 A_{AVG} \quad \text{Equation (1-2)}$$

$$A_{1/10} = 3.3 A_{AVG} \quad \text{Equation (1-3)}$$

$$A_{1/100} = 5.6 A_{AVG} \quad \text{Equation (1-4)}$$

These statistics were referred to as averages of the highest $1/N^{\text{th}}$ peak accelerations from origins in earlier oceanographic studies where wave height distributions were described by averages of the highest $1/N^{\text{th}}$ wave heights, *Munk (1944)*. The same statistical approach was used to develop an empirical

equation for $A_{1/10}$ based on analysis of full-scale seakeeping data, *Hoggard and Jones (1980)*. Ship classification societies continued the statistical paradigm by publishing equations for computing the $A_{1/100}$ parameter as an impact load factor used in equations for the effective pressure to be used in hull design analyses. Some naval architects, not all, argued that the $A_{1/10}$ statistic was more appropriate for hull design, *Koelbel (2001)*.

1.2 Ride Quality

The study of human comfort and performance at sea in high-speed craft was also an important topic during the early 1970's. Approaches to quantifying wave slam exposure were being investigated and shock isolation seats adapted from airplane landing struts and land vehicle designs were in development. Fig.4 shows acceleration data recorded on a Moulton suspension seat in a 31-foot craft operating in rough seas, *Ducane (1971)*. It shows from top to bottom the boat vertical acceleration, seat vertical acceleration, seat relative displacement, and seat relative velocity. Fig.5 shows an early design of an adjustable shock isolation seat for naval gunboats, *Pickford, et al. (1975)*.

Fig.4: Shock Isolation Seat Response

Fig.5: Naval Gunboat Shock Isolation Seat

The successful acquisition of motion data did not however lead to agreement on parameters for quantifying ride quality (or ride roughness) in the marine environment. There was a general dissatisfaction with the lack of valid hard data upon which meaningful comparisons between different craft could be based, and there was no fully satisfactory criterion for judging the ride quality of high-speed craft in rough seas, *Ellsworth (1974)*. The introduction of new computer systems significantly improved signal processing and the computation of statistical parameters. Initially, lessons learned from airline and automobile vibration environment studies influenced marine vehicle researchers who applied the statistical root mean square (RMS) acceleration criteria to compare the motions experienced on displacement hulls, surface effects ships, and hydrofoils with established criteria for motion sickness and

fatigue, NASA (1972) and Stark (1980). The RMS parameter was used to establish criteria for fatigue-decreased proficiency, ISO 2631-1 (1985) and motion sickness. But the RMS value of vertical accelerations in a high-speed craft was known to be much less than the amplitude of the majority of peak accelerations caused by impacts. Other statistical parameters were therefore introduced with 4th-order terms in an attempt to emphasize the larger peaks. For example, the root mean quad (RMQ) and the vibration dose value (VDV) were introduced, Boileau, Turcot, and Scory (1989). The VDV is given by equation (1-5) where $a_w(t)$ is the recorded acceleration signal after being subjected to a band-pass filter (i.e.; frequency weighting) specified for seated or standing positions.

$$VDV = \left[\int_0^T a_w^4(t) dt \right]^{1/4} \quad \text{Equation (1-5)}$$

The VDV is used for quantifying human exposure to whole body vibrations with intermittent shocks, ISO-2631 - 1 (1997). There is also a 6th-power statistical parameter for estimating adverse health effects on the spine of a seated human due to whole body vibrations containing multiple shocks, ISO-2631-5 (2004) and Petersen, et al. (2004).

Another statistical approach initially used by naval craft designers in the 1970's used vertical $A_{1/10}$ values at the LCG to characterize different levels of ride quality in terms of human comfort and performance, Savitsky and Koelbel (1978). Table 1 was published much later to show the $A_{1/10}$ values and descriptions of crew effects in high-speed planing craft, Savitsky and Koelbel (1993).

Table 1: 1993 Crew Comfort and Performance Criteria

$A_{1/10}$ (g) at LCG	Effects on Personnel
1.0	Maximum for military function long term (over 4 hours)
1.5	Maximum for military function short term (1 - 2 hours)
2.0	Tests discontinued
3.0	Extreme discomfort
4.0	
5.0	Physical injury
6.0	Military crew under fire

It was reported that acceleration levels for crew tolerance and structural design are most frequently given as the average of the one-tenth highest accelerations, but there was “no intrinsic reason why this statistic should be used. It probably came about because observers felt that this level best represented, with a single number, their experience of the actual random accelerations in much the same way that oceanographers characterize the random waves of a sea state by the average of the one-third highest”, Savitsky and Koelbel (1993).

1.3 Observations

Interpretation of recorded accelerations like the data shown in Figs.1, 2, and 4 focused on the effects of individual wave impacts, primarily because they were recorded before the introduction of computers. As research continued, however, the literature shows that the study of hull structural strength and human comfort evolved with a reliance on statistical parameters to quantify the wave impact environment. This was a natural evolution dealing with wave height environments best characterized by statistical methods. The evolution of computer data processing in the early 1970's significantly reduced the arduous task of analyzing acceleration records that previously had to be read by hand, Savitsky and Brown (1975). But the development of these methods across diverse communities of interest resulted in different statistical approaches for quantifying wave impact load for different applications. All the statistical methods rely on either full-scale or model-scale acceleration data, but there is no common engineering rationale nor is there consistency in the metrics for quantifying wave impact

load. Some use the average of many peak accelerations, while others use parameters that average entire signals over time with 2nd order, 4th order, or 6th order terms.

Recent studies suggest that future advances in high-speed craft methodologies can benefit from an integrated approach that combines statistical information with a better understanding of the physics of individual wave impacts. Forty-five years ago the study of individual wave impacts could take hours, days, or weeks to analyze. Now the use of desktop computers and new general purpose data analysis software can do similar work in seconds, minutes, or hours. The following paragraphs summarize lessons learned from the study of individual wave impacts, referred to as wave impact determinism.

2. The Deterministic Approach

2.1 Craft Motion Mechanics

In 2005 a research project was initiated to understand why statistical acceleration values documented in historical test reports from different agencies could not be used in craft comparative analyses, *Jacobson et al. (2007)*. Methods to extract peak accelerations were implemented subjectively by different analysts, which invariably led to processed peak accelerations that were not comparable. One of the products of this study was the standardized process for computing $A_{1/N}$ values referred to as StandardG, *Riley et al. (2010a)*. (StandardG is available free of charge by contacting the Branch Head of the United States Naval Academy Hydrodynamics Laboratory. Contact information is available at www.usna.edu/Hydrodynamics/Contact.php.) The research evolved further into a pursuit of a better understanding of craft motion mechanics and the cause-and-effect physical relationships between impact loading and craft responses. Fig.6 shows an unfiltered acceleration time history of three wave impacts. The responses to each impact damp out before the next wave impact. This simple impact and response relationship, observed even in the most flexible craft locations, provides the engineering justification for analyzing responses to wave impacts one at a time. The first step in the analysis (i.e.; separation into its fundamental parts) is to decompose the acceleration signal.

Fig.6: Wave Slam Input and Response Phenomena

(All data plots shown in the paper were created using UERDTools, *Mantz and Costanzo (2009)*.)

2.2 Response Mode Decomposition

Accelerometers measure relative and absolute (i.e.; rigid body) motions simultaneously. In marine craft the relative motions include millimeter deck vibrations caused by propulsion systems, power generation machinery, and forced structural vibrations during and after a wave impact. The absolute motions include heave, surge, and sway. The heave acceleration is the measure relevant to the study of shock (i.e.; wave slam) load transmission within a craft structure, *Riley, Coats, and Murphy (2014a)*. The analysis of wave slam shock effects therefore requires that raw acceleration data be low-pass filtered to attenuate the vibration content in the record, leaving the majority content in the filtered record attributed to rigid body content. Fig.7 illustrates the response mode decomposition process of

separating rigid body and vibration accelerations. The plot on the left shows a time history of the raw vertical acceleration (gray line) and the rigid body heave acceleration (black line) obtained by low-pass filtering. The rigid body heave acceleration is typically that motion about which the local vibrations oscillate. The plot on the right shows the vibration content obtained by high-pass filtering the recorded acceleration. The use of response mode decomposition to remove the seemingly random vibration signals recorded at different locations in different craft led to observations of rigid body motions during wave impacts that provide the foundation for pursuing a new integrated approach to the study of wave slam phenomena.

Fig.7: Rigid Body and Vibration Accelerations

2.3 Individual Wave Slam Observations

The Combatant Craft Division of Naval Surface Warfare Center Carderock Division has conducted full-scale seakeeping trials of many craft since its establishment in 1967. Consistent testing protocols provide a useful data base for observing interesting trends. The lessons learned summarized herein were based on analysis results for craft that weighed approximately 14,000 pounds (6.35 metric tons) to 116,000 pounds (52.6 metric tons) with lengths that varied from 33 feet (10 m) to 82 feet (25 m). Deadrise values varied from 18 to 22°, *Riley et al. (2014b)*.

2.3.1 Sequence of Events

A vertical acceleration time history for one wave impact sequence and the velocity and absolute displacement (i.e.; heave) curves obtained by integration are shown left to right in Fig.8. The curves illustrate the wave impact period and non-impact periods. At time A, the -0.9 g vertical acceleration indicates a condition very close to free fall.

Fig.8: Wave Impact Sequence of Events

The relatively constant -0.9 g from time A to time B and the linear decrease in velocity suggests that the craft is rotating downward with the stern in the water. The drop in height from time A to B is most likely a combination of heave and pitch. At time B, the craft impacts the incident wave, the velocity is

at a minimum, the negative slope changes rapidly to a positive slope, and the force of the wave impact produces a sharp rise in acceleration. From time B to time C, the craft continues to move down in the water, the velocity approaches zero, and the acceleration decreases rapidly. At time C the downward displacement of the craft reaches a maximum, the instantaneous velocity is zero, and the impact event is complete. From time C to D forces due to buoyancy, hydrodynamic lift, and components of thrust and drag combine to produce a net positive acceleration. From time D to E, gravity overcomes the combined forces of buoyancy, hydrodynamic lift, and components of thrust and drag as another wave encounter sequence begins.

The period of time in Fig.8 from point B to point C is the wave impact period, i.e.; the shock pulse. It is this period of time from B to C that is important for understanding and evaluating the effects of wave impact shock. Five parameters are important for characterizing an acceleration shock pulse, including direction, pulse shape, rate of acceleration application (i.e.; jerk), peak amplitude, and pulse duration, *Eiband (1959)*.

2.3.2 Wave Slam Type

The time history responses of individual wave slams tend to follow three characteristic patterns before and after the wave impact phase. The patterns are used to characterize types of wave impacts referred to as Alpha, Bravo, and Charlie wave slams, *Riley et al. (2010)*. The Type Alpha slam is one where the craft is airborne prior to impact. The stern of the craft impacts the water first and this induces bow down pitching just prior to a severe wave impact. The Type Bravo slam is one where the craft may be airborne or the stern stays in the water, and impact occurs with little or no bow down pitching prior to impact. Prior to impact there is typically a temporary loss of forward momentum for Type Alpha and Bravo slams. The Type Charlie slam is one where the craft is in the water, there is no loss of forward momentum. There is little or no bow-down pitching prior to impact and the impact causes rapid bow up pitching. The significance here is that even in what is described as a random seaway in fully developed seas, the response motions observed in craft follow repeatable patterns.

2.3.3 Shock Pulse Shape and Direction

At any measurement point on a craft the direction of the shock pulse during a wave slam can be aligned with coordinate axes X (surge acceleration, positive forward), Y (sway acceleration, positive to port), and Z (heave acceleration, positive up). The shape of the rigid body vertical acceleration when impact forces dominate can be simplified for analytical study as a half-sine pulse, *Riley and Coats (2012)*. Fig.9 illustrates the half-sine representation of the rigid body vertical acceleration pulse for a wave impact where the largest amplitude is A_{max} and the pulse duration is T. While the sequence of wave encounters in terms of wave height and time between impacts is random, the vertical response of the craft to a single wave impact appears to be repeatable in shape with amplitudes that vary primarily with speed, craft weight, wave period, and wave height, *Riley et al. (2014b)*.

Fig.9: Half-sine Pulse Shape

2.3.4 Shock Pulse Duration

Fig.10 plots wave impact duration versus peak acceleration recorded at the LCG in 13 different craft during head-sea trials in rough water, *Riley et al. (2014c)*. All wave impacts with peaks greater than 3 g were analyzed. Lower amplitude pulses were surveyed for trends. The square symbols correspond to six craft that weighed from 22,000 pounds to 38,000 pounds. The circles correspond to six craft that weighed from 14,000 pounds to 18,000 pounds. The triangles were recorded on a craft that displaced 105,000 pounds. The peak acceleration is the rigid body peak acceleration estimated using a 10-Hz low-pass filter. The data indicates that the shortest impact durations regardless of impact severity are on the order of 100 milliseconds (ms), and the longest durations decrease from about 450 ms to 150 ms as peak acceleration increases to about 7 g. The variation in the impact duration for a given peak acceleration is caused by several variables, including craft weight, speed, wave height, impact angle, deadrise, and where the craft impacted the wave (e.g.; on the leading flank, crest, or following flank).

Fig.10: Impact Pulse Duration

2.4 Shock Response Spectrum

Figs.8 to 10 illustrate how acceleration data recorded during seakeeping trials is used to characterize wave impact severity in terms of pulse shape, amplitude, and duration. Once those characteristics have been identified, the shock pulse can be used for estimating how the individual shocks affect structure, equipment, or humans. One of the most useful mathematical tools for evaluating shock effects is the shock response spectrum (SRS). A shock response spectrum is the calculated maximum response of a set of single-degree-of-freedom, SDOF, spring-mass-damper oscillators to an input acceleration. Fig.11 illustrates the SRS concept for SDOF natural frequencies from 5 Hz to 40 Hz. The natural frequency of each SDOF is a function of its mass (m) and stiffness (k). The input acceleration is applied to the base of all oscillators, and the calculated maximum response of each oscillator versus the natural frequency make up the spectrum, *Harris (1995)*. The equations for predicting the responses are found in numerous engineering handbooks and *ISO-18431-4 (2007)*.

Fig.11: Shock Response Spectrum Concept

The predicted maximum responses of the SRS can be in terms of the maximum absolute acceleration of the mass, the maximum relative displacement (Δ) of the spring-damper assembly, or a relative velocity term. The maximum relative displacement is an intuitive parameter for potential shock damage because the maximum relative displacement across the spring is proportional to the strain in the spring. The shock pulse that results in the largest strain in the spring is the most severe shock pulse with the largest damage potential. The next section presents examples of the use of SRS to evaluate wave slam effects.

3. An Integrated Approach

The repeatability of types of wave slams and their pulse shapes provides the motivation for studying the physics of individual wave impacts, but not at the expense of the wealth of knowledge accumulated from statistical approaches. Both approaches are needed, especially in light of the inability to measure individual wave heights during seakeeping trials. Relating the craft acceleration responses to the seaway environment requires $A_{1/N}$ and $H_{1/N}$ statistics. When both deterministic and statistical approaches are applied they provide lessons learned for addressing a broader range of design and comparative analysis topics than obtained from just one approach.

Fig.12: An Integrated Approach to Studying Wave Slam Effects

Fig.12 illustrates the taxonomy for conceptualizing an integrated approach to studying wave slam effects on high speed craft. The goal is to apply a common approach to defining wave impact load for studying effects on structure, equipment, and humans (i.e.; with knowledge from both deterministic and statistical approaches depending upon the level of physical complexity). Level I studies individual wave impacts to gain basic understanding of the physical phenomena and the mathematical models that best describe the physics. Level II extends the knowledge base by investigating how combined effects of multiple impacts of equal severity affect outcomes. Level III adds the complexity of differing sea conditions and what maximum loading conditions can be expected. It is important to note that the end products of applied research may not have to evolve through all three phases. For example, a design approach based on a single severe shock pulse may not require Level II or III studies. The following examples show how the Fig.12 integrated approach can be implemented.

3.1 Hull Design Acceleration

In early hull design studies the static equivalent of the dynamic load acting on the bottom of a craft hull was defined as the static pressure which produces the same maximum strain in a structural element as the dynamic load, *Heller and Jasper (1960)* and *Allen and Jones (1978)*. Several assumptions can be used in a deterministic approach to transition this definition to an equivalent static acceleration, *Riley and Coats (2012)*. The first assumption is that the vertical dynamic acceleration at a cross-section of a craft has the shape of a half-sine pulse given by equation (3-1) where the pulse duration in this example is $T/2$.

$$A(t) = A_{MAX} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) \quad (3-1)$$

The second assumption is that there is an equivalent average acceleration $\bar{A}(t)$ with a rectangular (or square) pulse shape and maximum amplitude given by equation (3-2) that produces the same strain in a structural element (i.e.; equivalent damage potential) as the half-sine pulse given by equation (3-1).

$$\bar{A} = \frac{A_{MAX}}{T/2} \int_0^{T/2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) dt = \frac{2}{\pi} A_{MAX} \quad (3-2)$$

The equivalency of the $A(t)$ half-sine pulse and the $\bar{A}(t)$ rectangular pulse can be demonstrated by comparing the maximum relative displacement SRS (DSRS) of each pulse.

Fig.13 compares the DSRS for three different pulses shown in the insert. One pulse is a 5g – 200 msec half-sine acceleration pulse (square symbol) that represents a wave impact shock pulse. The 3.18g – 200 msec rectangular pulse (blue circles) has the same 200 msec duration with a reduced constant 3.18 g amplitude computed using 5 g in equation (3-2). The predicted DSRS curves for the 200-msec pulses above 10 Hz are nearly identical, indicating the 5 g – 200 msec half-sine pulse and the 3.18 g – 200 msec rectangular pulse have the same damage potential for response modes above approximately 10 Hz (i.e.; they are equivalent severity pulses).

Fig.13: Relative Displacement SRS for Half-Sine and Square Pulses

The 3.18g - 2000 msec pulse (black triangles) is also included to explain the concept of an equivalent static pulse. Typically the word static elicits the thought of a constant phenomenon with infinite duration, but in structural dynamics, where a maximum strain value is of interest, a load with short duration (e.g.; 200 msec) can produce the same maximum strain as a lower amplitude load whose duration is much longer. As the duration of the pulse increases, the maximum strain responses in the spring do not change because they occurred early in the response time (in this case within the first 200 msec). As long as the maximum strain occurs within the duration of the half-sine acceleration pulse, the

DSRS are the same (i.e.; the maximum strains are the same). In the limit, as the rectangular pulse duration becomes large (i.e.; approaches static) the maximum relative displacements (i.e.; strain) for all natural frequencies of interest remain constant. The concept of static equivalency can be used for high speed planing craft because structural frequencies are typically greater than 15 Hz with corresponding periodic response times on the order of 66 msec and less (i.e.; short compared to the relatively long wave impact durations).

When a maximum shock pulse for a single wave slam (i.e.; the design severity pulse) is modeled as a half-sine pulse, equation (3-2) can be used to calculate its equivalent static acceleration. The equivalent static acceleration (i.e.; the load impact factor) can be used in developing hull design methods similar to the *Allen and Jones (1978)* method.

3.2 Equipment Ruggedness Testing

The DSRS can also be used to establish laboratory testing criteria for minimizing the risk of equipment failure or malfunction while operating in a wave slam environment. For example, when a single long-duration wave slam pulse is selected as a maximum shock pulse, its DSRS can be compared to the DSRS of a shorter duration laboratory shock machine pulse to ensure the laboratory pulse is more severe than the wave slam pulse. The plot on the left in Fig.14 shows a wave impact shock pulse with duration equal to 120 msec (triangle symbol) and a shock machine pulse with a 23-msec duration (smooth curve). The plot on the right shows the relative displacement DSRS for the two shock pulses.

Fig.14. Example SRS for Laboratory Shock Test Machine

The DSRS curve for the shock machine pulse (smooth curve) is greater than the DSRS for the wave shock pulse (triangle symbol) for natural frequencies greater than 10 Hz. Since the shock machine pulse is more severe it can be used to test equipment (with natural response modes greater than 10 Hz) in the laboratory before installation in a craft.

3.3 Shock Isolation Seat Drop Testing

The half-sine pulse shape of a severe wave slam (i.e.; the wave impact load) can also be used to develop drop height criteria for laboratory test and evaluation before installation in a craft, *Riley et al. (2015a)*. For example if a 10 g – 100 msec half-sine pulse is selected to represent the maximum severity wave impact load, the change in velocity of this pulse (i.e.; the area under the acceleration curve, approximately 20.5 feet per second) is equal to the drop-test impact velocity, which can be used to calculate the planned test drop height (e.g.; 6.5 feet for the 10 g – 100 msec shock pulse).

The DSRS of acceleration data recorded during the seat drop test can be used to compute a seat performance measure, *Riley et al. (2015b)*. For example, if vertical accelerometers are installed at the base of the seat and on the seat pan, the recorded pulses can be used to compute the maximum relative

displacement SRS for the base input and the pan response. A ratio of the DSRS can then be used to define a mitigation ratio that is a measure of the percent reduction in the shock input to the seat.

3.4 Ride Quality

The crew comfort and performance criteria listed in Table 1 were developed based on subjective crew feedback after being subjected to high-speed runs in varying sea states. Unfortunately there has been no systematic research performed to advance the state of the art in understanding or quantifying human comfort at sea, including the study of surge and sway accelerations and rapid pitch and roll effects. In the absence of dedicated research the only recent addition has been a refinement of the vertical acceleration criteria (i.e.; $A_{1/10}$ values) based on recent crew feedback from rough water seakeeping trials. Many of the rough water trials recently analyzed included runs where the coxswain was directed to achieve a maximum safe speed in each heading with no throttling. Systematic analysis of archived data and subjective feedback from the experienced test coxswains, test engineers, and naval architects participating in the trials resulted in an interesting observation. During the maximum safe speed runs in head seas (i.e.; typically the most uncomfortable ride tolerated by the coxswain), the $A_{1/10}$ values varied from 2.7 g to 3.2 g, which correlated well with the 3-g extreme discomfort level in Table 1. Table 2 lists this range with others that were developed based on recent test crew subjective feedback.

Table 2. Interim Transition Zones for Human Comfort and Performance

$A_{1/10}$	Transition Zones
< 1.5 g	Conditions typically result in a comfortable ride with effective performance for 4 hours or more
1.5 g - 2.0 g	Conditions may transition from a comfortable ride to a ride with limited discomfort
2.0 g - 2.7 g	Conditions transition from a comfortable ride to a ride with discomfort and limited performance
2.7 g - 3.2 g	Conditions transition from discomfort to the onset of extreme discomfort
3.2 g - 5.5 g	Conditions transition from extreme discomfort to the onset of concern for personnel safety
5.5 g - 6.0 g	Conditions transition from extreme discomfort and concern into potentially unsafe conditions with increased risk of safety mishaps

An example application of the statistical $A_{1/10}$ ranges from Table 2 is shown in Fig.15. The plot abscissa is a linear scale of all the peak accelerations largest to smallest output by StandardG for a test run. The ordinate is a logarithmic scale of the percent of peaks greater than or equal to that peak-g value (i.e.; similar to a cumulative distribution in log format). Peak accelerations for two sets of data recorded during different seakeeping trials are shown. It illustrates a useful visual display of two very different rides. The upper curve was a ride that included wave slams that were described as extremely uncomfortable (i.e.; some peak accelerations in the orange zone up to 5 g.) compared with another ride that was called an “easy day underway” (i.e.; all peak accelerations in the green zone). The color shading corresponds to the transition zones listed in Table 2. On the logarithmic scale the value of 10 corresponds to 10 percent of the data, so all the peaks to the left of 10 percent were the peaks used to compute $A_{1/10}$ for that run. Likewise a value of 1 corresponds to 1 percent. All peaks to the left of 1 percent were the ones used to compute $A_{1/100}$.

Fig.15: Ride Severity Profiles for Two Seakeeping Trials

4. Research Opportunities

The deterministic analysis of wave impacts offers a consistent engineering approach to defining impact loads that can be applied with common engineering rationale regardless of the topic of interest (e.g.; structure, equipment, human comfort). It has the benefit of aligning maximum peak accelerations observed in testing with design loads and criteria with known design margins. The applications summarized in section 3 are early examples based primarily on vertical craft motions, so final results are yet to be achieved. There is ample opportunity as summarized below for additional research and continued improvement.

4.1 Instrumentation

During full-scale seakeeping trials the response of a craft to wave impacts can be measured with good accuracy, including rigid body accelerations and rotations, vibration motions, strain, and craft speed just to name a few. Recording and interpreting impact pressure data is more difficult to the extent that the cost of installation precludes frequent attempts at the measurement. The independent variable that cannot be measured confidently at full-scale is the relative motion between the craft and each incident wave (either distance or velocity). The height of individual waves cannot be measured or correlated with individual peak acceleration responses. Development of a measurement sensor that could close this gap would significantly improve understanding the cause and effect physics and modeling assumptions of different wave impacts.

4.2 Model Testing

It was hypothesized that irregular seas should be simulated “to determine the actual forces and motions that may truly be anticipated”, *Michel (1968)*. It is not clear that this hypothesis also applies to wave slam effects in small high-speed planing craft. A research opportunity therefore exists to study wave impact responses on model scale. Wave heights in tank tests can be measured with good accuracy, and the variation of maximum impact acceleration with speed and wave period (just to name a few parameters) can be pursued in a deterministic approach. As an example, Fig.16 shows two test matrices where each triangle is a scale model run in a tank. Each matrix has a unique wave period. The goal is to investigate and model the mathematical relationship between the maximum wave slam severity and the three independent variables. This approach could potentially obviate the issue related to

how many impacts are required for tank testing to calculate $A_{1/100}$ or $A_{1/10}$, and it could be applied to other dependent variables like maximum surge acceleration and maximum pitch angle. It could also be used to investigate how craft motions transition from Type Charlie slams, to Type Bravo slams, to Type Alpha slams as speed and wave height increases.

Fig.16: Scale-model Test Matrices

4.3 Hull Design

Assumptions related to effective bottom pressure loads and impact load factors have resulted in tractable design approaches for the very complicated dynamic environment of small high-speed planing craft. However, the dichotomy of designing hulls with the average of the top one percent of wave impact loads (e.g.; $A_{1/100}$) rather than a maximum operational load (e.g.; $A_{1/100}$) plus a margin suggests that published planing hull design equations have unknown safety factors or margins that result in maximum impact loads. There is an opportunity for research that unravels the dichotomy and better defines equations with known allowances for design margins.

4.4 Human Comfort and Performance

Table 2 is a rough order of magnitude estimate of how human discomfort and reduced performance varies with increasing vertical acceleration amplitudes. Although recent personnel feedback correlates well with the historical descriptions of extreme discomfort, the current descriptions at the high end are broad, and it is well known that transverse accelerations and multi-axis rotations can also cause extreme discomfort. There is a need for systematic research for effects other than vertical, and there is a need for controlled studies to better describe and quantify the bounds of human discomfort. This knowledge will improve the ability to set operational limits that avoid the more severe environments that transition into unsafe conditions.

The 3.2-g value at the upper end of the extreme discomfort zone in Table 2 has no current basis in human comfort research. It is a rough estimate based on the perceptions and feedback of test coxswains. The equivalent static acceleration from equation (3-2) for a 3.2-g half-sine pulse is 2 g, but the question remains, is some other value like 2.5 g more appropriate. Additional human comfort research is required to establish test-based rationale for defining the transitions zones listed in Table 2.

5. Summary and Recommendations

The development of computational methods for high-speed craft hull design and human comfort evolved with a reliance on statistical parameters to quantify the wave impact environment. This was a natural evolution dealing with wave heights in irregular seas best characterized by statistical methods and the evolution of computer data processing in the early 1970's. Across diverse communities of interest however, different statistical approaches for processing recorded acceleration data were de-

veloped for different applications that have no common engineering rationale or consistency in the metrics for quantifying wave impact load.

More recent advancements in general purpose data analysis software speeds the process of analyzing acceleration data and allows a focus on studying responses to individual wave impacts. This has revealed interesting observations related to elements of wave slam repeatability even in a random wave environment. Instead of statistical averaging of many impacts, the deterministic approach has provided improved understanding of the cause and effect physics of individual wave impacts and allows for consistent engineering rationale to be applied for studying severe impact effects. The primary focus of recent deterministic studies has been on the vertical inputs and responses in high-speed craft. It is recommended that the deterministic approach also be pursued in studying other important response motions (e.g.; surge and sway impact components, as well as pitch and roll effects).

The pursuit of individual wave impact knowledge should not be at the expense of the wealth of knowledge accumulated from statistical approaches. Both approaches are needed, especially in light of the inability to measure individual wave heights in the open ocean environment. Relating craft motion responses in a seaway over time requires statistical description. When both deterministic and statistical approaches are applied they provide lessons learned for addressing a broader range of design and comparative analysis topics than obtained from just one approach. It is therefore recommended that further deterministic research be pursued by numerous organizations to expand the knowledge base in craft motion mechanics.

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Impact of Air Cavity Technology on Ship Drag Reduction: Experience from Research Studies

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Abstract

A series of recent studies looking into the issues raised by implementation of IMO CO₂ regulations have shown that air supply techniques are probably the last-hope offer for merchant ships to achieve the prescribed 25-30% reduction of the energy efficiency design index (EEDI) without substantial reduction of speed. The Krylov State Research Centre has introduced and continuously developed the air cavity (ACS) technology. At the same time, whilst an alternative method of viscous drag reduction based on supply of air bubbles under ship bottom is being intensively explored. Great experience of KSRC in air-cavity ships as well as some experience in research studies on air bubble lubrication of hull bottom enable to formulate and analyze the scientific problems which arise in both areas of development. The efficiency of air cavity technologies is demonstrated by analysis of two projects, a tanker and a containership, with consideration of both hydrodynamic and economic prospect.

1. Introduction

The deadline of 2025 is imminent, when according to the regulations of IMO Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) the EEDI of newbuildings shall have to be 30% lower as compared with the ships built before 2015. Realistic expectations of further EEDI reduction through hydrodynamic improvements can be listed as follows:

- resistance reduction from optimization of ship dimensions and hull lines via analytical and numerical methods is limited to 3-5 percent;
- special-purpose coatings for underwater hull (anti-fouling, anti-frictional and self-polishing paints) could also provide a 5 to 7 percent reduction in frictional resistance even though these paints had already been in use before 2015;
- energy saving devices of various types, which have been widely introduced in the early implementation phases of IMO regulations, can give not more than 4 to 6% savings in fuel consumption.

Further reduction in EEDI can be achieved at the cost of quite substantial speed loss, the so-called slow steaming, which is used as a notion for ships sailing below their design speed. This strategy is not necessarily the best option for the shipping industry from an economic perspective. Apart from slow steaming, only two realistic options are left to reduce the level of harmful emissions. One is to improve the main engine performance (including conversion to gas fuel); another is to apply unconventional hydrodynamic techniques with efficiency of at least 15% in order to achieve higher performance of the hull-propeller system that primarily leads one to consider various systems using air supply for resistance reduction.

The idea of introducing a gas layer to isolate the ship bottom from the water in order to attain lower frictional resistance was originally suggested long time back in the mid-1800s, *Stevens and Stevens* (1848); however, it was not put into practice then. There are three options of air application to reduce ship resistance: thin air layer, air bubbles and artificial air cavity system (ACS). The air bubble and air cavity techniques have been tested in full-scale conditions.

The main purpose of this paper is to compare the drag reduction capacity of air bubble and air cavity methods, as well as to overview the results of some application of the ACS technology. Some issues related to ACS technology implementation on ocean-going ships are outlined. Two ships, a tanker and

a containership, are taken as case studies to present the results of ACS development studies covering both scientific and economic aspects.

2. Advantages and Disadvantages of Air Bubbles and Air Cavity Systems

First attempts to develop air-cavity ships were undertaken in Russia back in 1961 at Krylov Shipbuilding Research Institute (now Krylov State Research Centre, KSRC), *Butuzov et al. (1999), Sverchkov (2002)*. To move to a reliable and highly efficient solution for application on merchant ships a new bottom configuration with recess has been developed over long-term R&D efforts. This configuration enables allows the forming of air cavities which follow the path of wave profile yielded by the ship herself while running.

The recess is built in the flat part of the ship bottom, whose fore end is formed by a transverse head step. The recess is enclosed by a set of intercepting transverse fins and longitudinal keels, which enhance initial stability, prevent air leakage and air flow from side to side under rolling. In the aft end the hollow of the recess is connected to the bottom with a smooth stern slope.

Fig. 1: Bottom configuration for air cavity generation by KSRC method

So far, research and design studies on fourteen ACS projects of various merchant ship types have been carried out in Russia, including inland vessels and barges, sea-river vessels, HANDYMAX bulkers, VLCCs, general-purpose bulk/container carriers and containerships. In all cases, the air cavity technology provided a stable reduction in resistance by 15-25 percent (full scale) at Froude numbers between 0.12-0.21 at design draft.

Among these research projects, an example is illustrated below. The ACS technology was tested in full scale on a 1000-ton river barge of 72-m in length and 14-m in breadth, at loaded/light drafts of 1.5/0.6 m and design speed of 11.5 km/h. The barge bottom had a recess measuring 57×13×0.3m. After model studies and development of the air cavity generation system and recess for the full-scale barge, sea trials were conducted to see how the air-cavity demonstrator barge compares with a conventional barge of the same hull form and size. Both barges were tested in the same water area after a short time interval using the same push tugboat. Drag of the barges was measured with a dynamometer coupler placed between the barge and push tugboat.

Fig. 2: Towing resistance of barge models, R_t , versus Froude number, F_n , and resistance reduction, ΔR_t , obtained for model and full-scale barge

The model test results are given in Fig. 2 as towing resistance of both barges versus Froude number in deep water. The plot also shows the resistance reduction of the ACS barge obtained in model and full-scale experiments. As it can be seen, the resistance reduction measured in full scale is in good agreement with the model test data: the air cavity technology provides about 30 percent of reduction in resistance at towing speed of about 6 knots.

Up to the present there have been many attempts to use other types of air supply systems such as air bubbles, partial cavity and cells technology. The efficiency of air bubbles might reach 10 percent, but mostly stays in the range of 3-4 percent. Application of partial cavity and cells technology can reduce resistance up to 15 percent. Table 1 compares the efficiency of various air supply systems.

Table 1: Efficiency of various air supply systems

<i>Air supply systems</i>	<i>Energy saving</i>
Air bubbles	
Mitsubishi Air Lubrication System (MALS)	About 8-12%
MALS on the coal carrier <i>Soyo</i> , developed together with Oshima Shipbuilding Co. Ltd.	About 4% at deep draft and about 8% in shallow draft
Silverstream® System	3.8% in laden condition and 4.3% in ballast
Winged Air Induction Pipe (WAIP) technology	No significant net energy savings
Sea-trial on the cement carrier <i>Pacific Seagull</i>	5% in full-load and 10% in ballast
Minibubbles for the <i>Seiun-Maru</i>	2% at one speed
Reduction of frictional resistance by air bubble Lubrication by MARIN	No significant net energy saving
Partial cavity and cells technology	
Air Chamber Energy Saving (ACES) by DAMEN	About 15%
Air Cavity System (ACS) by DK Group	No information about resistance reduction in full-scale
Project Energy-saving air-Lubricated Ships (PELS) by MARIN	No information about resistance reduction in full-scale
Multi wave cavity	
AirMAX by STENA	About 20%
Air Cavity Ship by KSRC	15-25%

KSRC has conducted experimental and analytical studies of an air bubble supply system at model scale using a “standard” ship model of about 12-m in length and a simplified model intended to simulate the air outflow from outlets at full-scale flow velocities. Results of model tests as well as attempts of computer simulations to analyze distribution and motion of air bubbles as well as influence of air bubble on resistance enable the authors to judge the merits and drawbacks of the two technologies using air for resistance reduction, namely, air bubbles and air cavity techniques.

As seen in Table 2, each of these techniques has its advantages and disadvantages, but the achievable energy-saving efficiency makes the air cavity technology a considerably more attractive option in spite of some tangible drawbacks: it is impossible to generate and maintain stable air cavities in stormy seas and at large trim angles. For some ship types the air cavity technology could bring up to 20 percent reduction in resistance, with 12-15 percent being practically granted for ocean-going displacement ships, which compares favourably with the 10 percent (declared in one case only) and average 2-3 percent drag reduction provided by the air bubbles technology. As disadvantages of the air bubbles system one ought to consider that it is difficult to develop this technique in model scale since it is highly sensitive to external factors. Moreover, there is lack of information about this technology as regards efficiency in case of hull fouling.

The above comparisons allow KSRC to hold the opinion that the air cavity technologies offer a much greater promise for implementation, and more so in view of the latest solution suggested and patented by KSRC. Transverse steps have been introduced, which can be nestled to align with the bottom, so

diminishing economic penalties (practically to zero) at the time when the air cavity cannot be maintained on the hull bottom because of stormy seas or too large trim angles, *KSRC Patent* (2016).

It should be noted that thorough studies on physical models combined with theoretical computations are required to enable successful application of the air cavity technology. It appears that deficit of research experience in this area has led to a number of serious setbacks in implementation of air cavity systems in Europe, which unfairly discredited this technology. It is not the purpose of this paper to provide a full description of the technology or technical solutions to ensure transverse ship stability and avoid air escape, etc. Nevertheless, it should be emphasized that today it is necessary to take a number of key decisions in cooperation with classification societies for more effective implementation of ACS technology on issues such as load line, possibility to arrange the recess in double bottom structure, etc.

Table 2: Comparative advantages and disadvantages of air supply systems

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Air cavity</i>	<i>Air bubbles</i>
Physical principle behind resistance reduction	Isolation of hull bottom from water to reduce frictional resistance.	Not clear.
Retrofit	Major hull modifications are required to make a recess in bottom, easier to implement on new-buildings.	Can be retrofitted on existing ships.
Additional equipment for air supply	Compressed air supply (air compressor, turbocharger, etc.), simple piping system.	Large compressed air supply (air compressor, turbo-charger, etc.), huge piping system.
Performance in unfavorable conditions (large trim in ballast, stormy seas,)	Continuous air cavity breaks down into air pockets. Resistance may grow higher in comparison with the basis hull.	Air supply system is switched off and the ship operates in conventional configuration.
Resistance reduction in calm water	Stable reduction of 15-25%.	Maximum declared reduction is 10%; typically 3-5%.
Power required for air supply	About 2% of the main engine horsepower.	About 2-6% of the main engine horsepower.
Modeling and extrapolation of test data from model- to full scale.	Extrapolation can be developed on models based on Froude similarity criterion. Physically grounded method for scaling model test data to full-size is available.	Air outflow from a single outlet can be modeled using a specially prepared simplified model. Realistic bubble behavior patterns cannot be modelled even on large models (12-m length). Scaling procedure is not clear. Finalization in full-scale conditions only.
Possibility of applying CFD analysis and high-performance computations	Air cavity geometry is analytically described by cavitating flow equations applicable both to model and full-scale ship. Computations can be performed on PC.	Numerical modeling of air flow from a single outlet on a simplified model and full-scale ship is not a problem. Air supply through a large number of nozzles on model can be modelled on a 40- teraflop computer. Computers of much higher performance are required to compute jets released from many nozzles and distribution of bubbles on bottom of full-scale ship.

3. Case Studies: Tanker and Containership

The achievable efficiency of ACS technology depends on the ship type chosen for implementation. Obviously, the larger the area of parallel middle body, the larger the bottom surface that can be covered by the air cavity. Since air cavities mainly serve to reduce frictional resistance, the operating Froude number is a critical parameter; i.e. the lower the Froude number, the larger the frictional component in the total hull resistance. Hence, a greater resistance reduction effect can be expected from the air cavity application.

In the following the ACS efficiency will be assessed for two ship projects, namely, a Post-Panamax containership and a BaltMmax supertanker studied at KSRC, Table 3.

Table 3: Main characteristics of ships under study

<i>Ships</i>	<i>Tanker</i>	<i>Containership</i>
Length overall [m]	326.77	338.50
Length on waterline [m]	315.40	312.00
Breadth maximum [m]	55.00	45.60
Depth at midship [m]	25.00	25.10
Design draft [m]	14.00	14.75
Block coefficient	0.826	0.664
Deadweight [t]	149,708	104,000
Maximum speed [kn]	14 ($Fn = 0.13$)	24 ($Fn = 0.22$)
Service speed [kn]	12 ($Fn = 0.11$)	19 ($Fn = 0.18$)
Main engine power [kW]	2 x 19620	42910
Propeller diameter [m]	6.80	9.05
Range [nm]	15,000	11,000

The BaltMax is a restricted-draft oil tanker with Arc4 ice class notation for year-round oil export from Baltic ports; the twin-shaft power plant of 2×19620 kW enables the ship to sail in 1-m thick ice without icebreaker assistance. The ballast system is designed to provide even-keel trim in ballast condition, which is almost a must for efficient operation of the air cavity technology. Fig. 3 shows a perspective view of the tanker.

Fig. 3: External view of the BaltMax tanker

The Post-Panamax containership of 9500 TEU was designed by Navalprogetti (Italy) in cooperation with the University of Trieste (Italy) to a level of detail sufficient for preliminary estimates of building costs and operation expenses. A noteworthy feature of this containership is that as per the schedule it will be operated with practically no trips in ballast condition.

Models of these ships were manufactured for towing tests, see main data in Table 4. Photos of these models are given in Figs. 4 and 5.

Table 4: Main characteristics of the models

<i>Main data</i>	<i>Tanker</i>	<i>Containership</i>
Scale	1:41	1:70
Length overall [m]	7.970	5.181
Length on waterline [m]	7.693	4.979
Maximum breadth [m]	1.341	0.651
Draft [m]	0.341	0.203
Volume of displacement [m ³]	2.720	0.427
Wetted surface area [m ²]	13.655	4.103
Area of recess, [%]	36.5	34.6

For the sake of comparison, both models were first tested in basis configuration with the recess closed; afterwards the hull recess was opened and the models were tested with the air supply system in operation.

Fig. 4: Photo of tanker model with recess

Fig. 5: Photo of containership model with recess

Figs. 6 and 7 show the power curves obtained by scaling to full scale the model test data. These plots also carry the air cavity effect as percentage savings in shaft power and towing power for the tanker and the containership, respectively.

Fig. 6: Shaft power P_S and shaft power saving ΔP_S versus tanker speed V_S

Fig. 7: Effective power P_E and effective power saving ΔP_E versus containership speed V_S

Based on the results of the studies the following main conclusions can be drawn as regards performance of the ships and air cavity effect:

1. The bottom profile examined in the studies ensures generation of a stable air cavity. For the tanker the air cavity isolates 36.5 percent of the wetted surface area from contact with the water at full-load draft and 43.8 percent in ballast condition. For the containership the air cavity covers 34.6 percent of the wetted surface area at full-load draft. That translates into the following full-scale savings of effective power in calm-water condition and up to sea state 4 for both ships:
 - 17 percent for the tanker at maximum speed of 14 knots, whereas for the containership at maximum speed of 24 knots the towing power reduction reaches 15 percent;
 - at service speed, savings are 20 percent for the tanker, and 16 percent for the containership.These figures are also indicative of the reduction in the levels of fuel combustion emissions to atmosphere. The ballasting system of the tanker mentioned above (to get an even keel) ensures a higher reduction effect from the air cavity: even 19 percent at 15 knots and 24 percent at 12 knots. The drag reduction obtained for the containership might be slightly optimistic. From model tests of other ship types with block coefficient around 0.650 it follows that on average the resistance reduction due to ACS can reach 12-13 percent at $Fn \cong 0.22$.
2. Seakeeping model tests of the tanker show that the air-cavity beneficial effect reduce in sea states higher than 4: down to 12-14 percent at sea state 5 and to 6-8 percent at sea state 6. Experiments have shown that at sea state 7 the resistance of the basis ship and air-cavity ship is almost the same. The cavity has no significant effect on ship motions parameters.
3. In view of the specific requirements for the tanker, its model was also tested to find out the tanker performance in shallow water and in ice. No problems with maneuverability or propeller aeration by cavity air were observed.

In shallow water conditions with 3-m of water under the tanker keel, the air cavity saved 5-7 percent of the required power with respect to the basis ship.

Air supply to cavity has a minor (3-5%) positive effect on ice resistance in level and broken ice conditions. At full power provided by 39 MW main engines the tanker was able to sail in 1-m thick ice at 2 knots. It is essential to note that ice pieces passing under the ship bottom were not trapped in the recess.
4. According to extrapolated model test data the power required for air supply does not exceed 2 percent of the total propulsion power for both the tanker and the containership.

4. Economic Efficiency of the Air Cavity Technology

Once the ACS technology is shown to yield a significant reduction in power demand, the next fundamental consideration is the cost effectiveness of the system. To focus on the effects of ACS, it has to be pointed out that no 'performance-based navigation system' or any other energy-saving operational tool or software (optimization of weather routing and ballast, minimization of rudder usage, optimization of trim) has been taken into account to enhance fuel efficiency of ship in service. Hull and propeller roughness management has not been considered too.

The key factors in the economic analysis associated with shipping consist of capital costs, operation costs, voyage costs, and cargo-handling costs. Type, size, age, speed and the financial structure of the ship purchase and/or innovation in technology determine the level of overall cost.

Application of the ACS technology might increase the building cost, ship lightweight and, therefore, reduce the cargo-carrying capacity of ships to some extent. On the other hand, smaller main engine(s) could compensate the increase of building cost due to the ACS installation.

In this study the economic performance of the air-cavity ships was assessed in terms of savings in fuel consumption in comparison with the basis ship (i.e., without cavity) at the same service speeds. A built-in cash flow model has been implemented where all nominal values are discounted to account for the fact that a cost some years from now has a far lower effect on a shipowner's return on investment calculations today. Of course, returns on equity may be different depending on leverage. The Baltmax tanker is a newbuilding whereas the containership is considered for retrofit.

4.1 The BaltMax tanker

The air-cavity effect for the BaltMax tanker was estimated on the trade lane Ust-Luga (Russia) – Rotterdam (Netherlands) with a one-way voyage of 1,360 nautical miles.

The cargo load on the ACS tanker is lower than for the basis ship because the ship has draft limit when it sails through Denmark Strait between Baltic Sea and Northern Sea. When the tanker has no draft limits, cargo loads are equal. Income is estimated at an average for one year time charter rates. The income of both variants is adjusted for the ships’ different deadweight capacity maintaining the same income in dollars per deadweight ton per day. Income is used to account for the opportunity cost of downtime during repairs (lost income).

In the cash flow calculations the total income over the life of the ships and their end value is charged with the cost of acquisition, operation repairs and downtime.

Daily running expenses are estimated at USD 4,500 per day. They include provisions for USD 450,000 per scheduled repair period in order to include dry-docking and other maintenance costs. This represents about USD 500 per day. Dry-docking costs from last dry-docking to the year the ship goes to scrap are reversed and credited to the cost calculations.

Operating expenses do not include steel renewals. Both ships will be scrapped at 25-years lifetime based on today’s experience and the fact that it may prove difficult to find charterers willing to use ships of this age. An average scrap value of about USD 240 / lightship ton is assumed. The nominal income from the ship sale is discounted for year 26.

All figures in the cash flow calculations are adjusted for inflation at 3.5 percent to depict the nominal values of any year. These nominal values are then discounted at 5 percent per annum, which is realistic for returns on a shipping project going forward in Russia.

The number of turnaround voyages per year is 30 with about 280 days at sea per annum. Main economic parameters of the air-cavity and basis versions of the BaltMax estimated for the reference shipping line are given Table 5. Apart from payback time, reported figures denote values per annum. Transport tariff is assumed as 7.8 USD/t. It is clear that the tanker with air cavity technology is superior to the basis ship.

Table 5: Summary of the BaltMax tanker economic parameters

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>BaltMax</i> (basis)	<i>BaltMax</i> (air cavity)	<i>Air cavity effect</i>	
			units	%
Weight of cargo [10^3 t/y]	4601.4	4325.3	-276.1	-6.0
Operating costs [mmUSD]	24.843	22.655	-2.188	-8.8
Income [mmUSD]	30.508	28.677	-1.832	-6.0
Present value [mmUSD]	5.665	6.022	0.357	6.3
Payback time [y]	13.0	12.2	-0.8	-6.1

From the summary analysis of the economic parameters specific to the BaltMax tanker it is found that with reference to the Ust-Luga – Rotterdam line the air-cavity technology can reduce the total operating costs by 8.8 percent, decrease the income by 6 percent, reduce the payback time by 0.8 years, yielding a positive profit expressed in terms of net present value (*NPV*). The payback period is often used as a “quick and dirty” measure of profitability. It is defined as the time for the cumulative cash flow to achieve a value of zero. Usually, payback time does not consider interest.

To estimate the overall savings offered by the ACS, the *NPV* for both tankers was calculated over ship lifetime. Results are given in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: NPV and fuel cost savings over years of the two tanker variants

4.2 The Post-Panamax containership

This case study has the objective to demonstrate basically the overall economic convenience of retrofitting a large containership with the ACS technology. To determine the ability of the ACS technology to yield profit to the shipowner, a liner service cash flow model was implemented which measures the cost and revenue items that underlie a container shipping cash flow. It combines the effects of inflation rate and interest rate to arrive at realistic economic evaluations. An interest rate is usually assumed also in retrofitting analysis to reflect the time value of money.

Here, a simplified version of the model is used since the purpose is not to derive quite accurate costs of containership operation but, rather, to assess differences in fuel expenditures between the two variants. Therefore, inaccuracies and/or imprecision in cost functions and factors affecting ship productivity have very poor influence in pairwise comparison between ships of the same deadweight and service speed.

4.2.1 Retrofit cost

The cost for retrofit is an upfront cost that constitutes the fixed cost component of the investment (Capex). Typically, it includes design, material, labor, installation and commissioning costs. The overall retrofit cost is dependent on place and time of manufacturing, delivery date, financial conditions as well as on negotiations. Here, prices are of course indicative price lists in an Italian dockyard, but sufficiently valid for a comparison between the two variants. Summary of average retrofit costs in a Mediterranean dockyard is given in Table 6.

Table 6: Retrofit costs for ACS

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weight</i> (t)	<i>Material</i> (USD)	<i>Labor</i> (USD)	<i>Total</i> (USD)
Design and tests	-----	-----	-----	400,000
Steel	552	175,000	1,420,000	1,595,000
Outfitting	21	725,000	120,000	845,000
Blowers and systems	27	340,000	400,000	740,000
Grand total	600	1,240,000	1,940,000	3,580,000

Neither development of special technologies nor acquisition of special equipment, are required in the dockyard to retrofit a ship with the ACS technology.

4.2.2 Operating costs

Whichever operating cost model is made up of many items, namely, capital cost, fuel cost at sea and in port, crew wages, insurance cost, cost of maintenance and repairs, cost of providing containers, cost of victuals, inspections/renewal of certificates and miscellaneous charges. Costs of the crew, consumption of the auxiliary, expenditures in port, cost of ports (ship dues, pilotage, towage, mooring) are equal for both the basis and ACS containership.

The diesel oil consumption for auxiliary engines at sea and in port is assumed equal for the two variants. The cost of daily lubricating oil consumed by the main engine at sea represents about 3 percent of fuel oil cost. It must be pointed out that the ACS does not require any special activity for its maintenance since only a blower, a coiler water piping and insulation of the compressed air piping are required.

Downtime due to maintenance and repairs is typically assumed as 10 days per year so adopting a constant capital commitment throughout the year, regardless of whether the ship is in or out of service. The modelling of total voyage cost, composed of the cost of time at sea and the cost of time in port, must assume some voyage and port characteristics such as voyage length, container handling rate, time for port entry, and so on. The assumptions underlying the following sensitivity analysis are: (a) both variants have sufficient cargo available to offer the desired frequency of service; and (b) port charges and cargo handling costs are not included since they are the same for both ships. The handling rate is assumed to be the same. In other terms, port productivity is the same everywhere.

4.2.3 Simulation on a Trade Lane

The regular schedule shipping round voyage between Santos (Santos) and Leghorn (Italy) is considered in order to evaluate the effect of ACS on fuel savings in a deterministic way.

Calculations of daily and annual fuel consumption at sea for the main engine were performed while considering both the slow steaming and the normal speed profiles. To distinguish the days at sea in the two specific speed profiles for the all-water service between Santos and Leghorn considered as gateway ports, the following was assumed:

- 355 days at sea, with 15 days off hire per annum (time out of service and time out for drydocking);
- 3.0-3.5 days in each port for loading/unloading, assuming that both can deploy six cranes per vessel with a productivity of 70-80 container moves per-hour (JOC, 2015).

With a round-voyage distance of 10,400 miles and one port call only, each ship can make one round-voyage every 23 or 18 days if she averages 19 and 24 knots, respectively. The results needed to calculate the annual consumptions in loaded days at sea are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Days at sea for different speed profiles

<i>Running Profile</i>	<i>Slow Steaming</i> ($V = 19$ kn)	<i>Normal Speed</i> ($V = 24$ kn)
Turnaround loaded days at sea per voyage	23	18
Days in ports per voyage	6	
Number of turnaround voyages per annum	12.0	14.5
Days at sea per annum	276	261

When multiplying the propulsion power demand with a specific fuel oil consumption of 174 g/kWh, the daily fuel consumption was found making it possible to evaluate the annual fuel saving of the ACS ship in comparison with the basis containership for the given speed regimes. As one can see in Table 8, on average the annual savings correspond to little more than 13 percent for the slow steaming profile and to 15 percent when the containerships sail at normal speed.

Table 8: Annual savings on fuel consumption via ACS

<i>Item</i>	<i>Slow Steaming</i>		<i>Normal Speed</i>	
	Basis	ACS	Basis	ACS
Daily Consumption [t/d]	103.44	89.75	221.91	188.70
Annual Consumption [t/y]	28,549	24,771	57,919	49,251
Annual Saving [t/y]	datum	3,688	datum	8,668

4.2.4 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis using different values of variables is simply a form of analysis with certainty, except that the analysis is repeated with different values, each estimated with certainty. The resulting economic figures are computed to determine the decision’s sensitivity to different estimates for one or more variables. For the slow steaming and normal speed running, computations of fuel cost savings on operation are based on IFO 180 priced in different dates as reported in Table 9, after averaging between the prices in the Italian and Brazilian ports (sources: BP International Bunker Prices Schedule and BunkerIndex). Here, the dates considered are referred to the last year which saw a high volatility of barrel price with a minimum on January 28, 2016.

Table 9: IFO 180 prices (USD /t)

<i>Date</i>	June 01, 2015	January 28, 2016	July 25, 2016
<i>Price</i>	375	136	270

Under the assumed scenario, the alternative container ships have outputs reported in Table 10 where consumption in port and maneuvers have been assumed equal to about 6% of consumption in transit. The total consumption per year includes 4 percent allowance. Economic outputs indicate a project with serious investment potential since the ACS technology allows lower installed power and less fuel consumption.

Table 10: Annual expenditures and ACS savings on fuel costs (mmUSD/y)

<i>Speed Regimes</i>	<i>Slow Steaming</i>	<i>Normal Speed</i>
IFO 180 Price = 375 \$/t		
Basis Ship	10.706	21.719
ACS Ship	9.289	18.469
Saving	1.417	3.250
IFO 180 Price = 136 \$/t		
Basis Ship	3.883	7,877
ACS Ship	3.369	6.698
Saving	0.514	1,179
IFO 180 Price = 270 \$/t		
Basis Ship	7.708	15,638
ACS Ship	6.688	13,298
Saving	1.020	2,340

The bar diagram in Fig. 9 summarizes savings in annual fuel expenditure by comparing the total main engine operating costs per year, based on different fuel prices and considering volatility in fuel prices.

It has been assumed that there is 90 percent stowage factor in the outward leg and 80 percent on the return leg. At these capacity levels each ship could transport an annual number of TEUs as reported in Table 11 for given service speeds. On this basis the reduction in annual cost of providing one TEU of transportation capacity on the considered round-voyage was calculated and shown in Table 11.

Fig. 9: Comparison among annual fuel costs and savings at slow steaming and normal speed

Table 11. Annual reduction in cost per TEU [USD/TEU] by using the ACS ship

Item	Slow Steaming	Running Speed
Containers volume per annum	144,168	174,203
Fuel cost at 375 USD/t	9.83	18.66
Fuel cost at 136 USD/t	3.57	6.77
Fuel cost at 270 USD/t	7.08	13.43

The relative savings in operating costs over ship lifetime are expressed as *NPV*, with the conventional containership used as basis, in Figs. 10 and 11 for the slow steaming and normal speed profiles, respectively, where values of inflation (2% as expected in the European Union), interest rate (4% for 5-years loan period), tax rate (20%) and retrofit cost (3.58 million USD) are fixed, while fuel price is the parameter. Savings in different years and payback periods depending on fuel price and speed profiles can be seen in Table 12.

Fig. 10: Expected savings in operating costs at slow steaming

Fig. 11: Expected savings in operating costs at normal speed

Table 12: Savings and payback periods

<i>Speed Profile</i>	<i>Slow steaming</i>			<i>Normal speed</i>		
Fuel price [USD/t]	375	136	270	375	136	270
Saving [mmUSD]						
- 10 years	7.537	0.088	4.264	3.318	5.812	15.627
- 15 years	12.966	2.057	8.174	36.079	10.440	24.815
- 20 years	18.137	3.933	11.897	48.232	14.847	33.565
Payback period [y]	3.0	8.5	4.3	1.3	3.5	1.9

4.5 Summary

The engineering and economic analysis has shown the following:

- in ship lifetime, additional income due to lower fuel demand will be significantly higher than the marginal costs required for ACS installation even for retrofitted container ships;
- lower fuel expenditure in the range 1.0-1.5 million USD per year, according to fluctuation of fuel price in the last year, for a 9500 TEU ACS containership operating about 275 days a year at slow steaming;
- additional investment in retrofitting a containership with ACS will be compensated by an average fuel cost payback of 3-4 years at slow steaming, depending on bunker fuel price, dockyard, ship size and operational speed;
- economic advantages for the ACS retrofitted ship would be much more relevant at normal (design) speed;
- lower air pollution at sea, as required by IMO.

5. Conclusions

In an industry which is very cautious about changes, especially when it involves innovative technologies, IMO measures aimed at improving ships' eco-efficiency through the EEDI regulatory framework instigate innovation in new technologies for reduced fuel consumption. There is a lot of scope for reducing GHG emissions on ocean-going ships by reducing ship resistance. To comply with environmental requirements, the ACS energy efficient technology is the most promising and, probably, the only one that can yield 15-20% reduction in EEDI of ocean-going ships, while offering added value at all levels, both strategic and operational.

Research and development studies show that the air-cavity technologies should be considered as promising tools for reducing resistance of ships operating at Froude numbers approximately up to 0.22, i.e. in the range where the viscous resistance component is predominant.

The case studies have demonstrated that investment in innovating tankers and containerships with ACS is technically feasible and financially affordable.

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Multi-Body Dynamics Modelling on a Self-Propelled Pufferfish with its Application in AUV

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Abstract

We developed a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) based tool coupled with a Multi-Body Dynamics (MBD) technique to investigate a self-propelled pufferfish motion within a still water environment. The 3D pufferfish model consists of body, caudal, dorsal and anal fins. The locomotion of fish is entirely determined by the computation and fully induced by the oscillation motion of fish fins. The influence of the phase angle difference on the fish swimming behaviour is examined by varying the angle difference between the caudal, dorsal, and anal fins. The swimming displacement, hydrodynamic force and the wake pattern are analysed.

1. Introduction

Along with the exploitation of sea resources, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV) have become an important tool as they are suitable for long-term, regular or risky tasks, such as the exploration of deep sea oil, the inspection of fatigue problems of offshore platforms and so on. Living in the ocean for thousands of years, fish has the best propulsion and manoeuvring ability to adapt to the aquatic environment. Studies into the locomotion of fish swimming and manoeuvring have provided vital insights for the AUV design. Comparing with the traditional AUVs, the fish-like robots have their advantages of effective propulsion, stable and flexible features.

According to the study of *Sfakiotakis et al. (1999)*, there are two types of propulsion mechanisms, i.e. the Body and/or Caudal Fin (BCF) and the Median and/or Paired Fins (MPF). Generally, previous studies about the locomotion of fish swimming can be divided into two groups based on the aforementioned two mechanisms: (a) investigation on the fish body motion by prescribing the motions of fish while omitting the influence of fins except the caudal fin; (b) researches on the effect from an isolated fins, such as pectoral, dorsal and anal fins, on propulsion efficiency. Within the former group, typical studies of numerical simulations about anguilliform and carangiform swimming have been carried out by *Kern and Koumoutsakos (2009)*, *Borazjani and Sotiropoulos (2008, 2009, 2010)*. Most researches within the latter group used experimental measurements. Foil-like fins, standing for pectoral fins, were investigated by *Lauder and Madden (2007)* to analyse the kinematics and hydrodynamics of the fins. Other work was also reflected in the paper of *Barbera et al. (2011)* and *Beal et al. (2007)*. Recently, studies with a combined motion of pectoral fins and fish body are considered by researchers, such as *Xu and Wan (2012)*. Nevertheless, the influence of dorsal and anal fins on swimming behaviour is usually ignored because of the complexity of the problem.

One typical example of fish species adopting the MPF swimming is pufferfish. Biologically, it appears an extraordinary performance on manoeuvrability although it swims slowly. *Itai and Tamar (2003)* found that the shape of the pufferfish body can deform passively to accommodate the higher

swimming speed. Meanwhile, the flapping motion of dorsal and anal fins was in phase with each other and had a phase difference of 180° with the pectoral fin.

In the present work, numerical simulations are carried out to investigate the pufferfish model, which is based on a live fish experimental testing conducted at SJTU as shown in Fig. 1. The dorsal, anal and caudal fins are taken into account while all the fins are considered to be rigid. Phase angle difference is tested to examine its influence on the swimming performance. To achieve this goal, the modelling system is constructed by a series of interconnected bodies. An in-house code based on the theory of Multi-Body Dynamics combined with a Computational Fluid Dynamics tool is used.

Fig. 1: A photo of pufferfish experiment done at SJTU

2. Problem description

2.1. Multi-Body fish model and kinematic equations

The 3D pufferfish model, shown in Fig. 2, is extracted from a live fish experimental data, which was tested in Shanghai Jiao Tong University (SJTU), China. The fish model consists of four parts: the main fish body, dorsal, caudal and anal fins. The total length is about 0.12 m. The shape of each cross-section of body is approximately elliptical. The largest major- and minor-axis of fish body are about 0.04 and 0.03 m, respectively.

Fig. 2: 3D pufferfish model

Fig. 3: Numbering for each part of the fish model

Four parts are numbered from N_{b0} to N_{b3} as shown in Fig. 3. Each fin is connected to the main body with a virtual hinge joint. The fins in the present work are considered rigid. The density of whole body is the same as the environment (water). To carry out the numerical modelling, the surface of the fish model is meshed with unstructured grid while tetrahedral cells are used for the rest of fluid field, and the total number of grid cells is about one million. In order to ensure the accuracy of numerical simulation, the

computational domain should be large enough, where the length (X direction) of the domain is 12 times of the body length (BL), while its width (Y direction) and height (Z direction) are 10BL.

Unlike most existing researches, where the fish swimming speed and path are prescribed, here, only the rotational motions of the fins are given as a function of:

$$\gamma = A\sin(\omega t + \varphi)$$

where A is the amplitude, ω is the frequency which is identical for all the motions, and φ is the phase angle. The amplitude and frequency of each fin are obtained from the experimental testing and summarised in Table I. In the present study, the undulation of caudal peduncle is omitted implying that there is no deformation along the main body of the fish.

Table I: Motion parameters for the fish model

	Dorsal fin (d)	Caudal fin (c)	Anal fin (a)
Amplitude (rad)	0.94	0.45	0.94
Frequency (rad/s)	21.4		
Phase angle (rad)	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{4}, \pi$	0

2.2. Numerical simulation

The commercial software ANSYS Fluent 15.0 is used for solving the fluid field based on a finite volume method. The governing equations are the three dimensional incompressible continuity and momentum equations:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$$

A first order implicit time matching scheme is used for the transient term. Second-order upwind scheme is employed for diffusion term discretization. Pressure-Velocity coupling can be achieved by the Fractional Step scheme. The in-house code of Multi-body dynamics algorithm is written in the User Defined Function (UDF) and compiled into Fluent. In order to maintain the mesh quality during the simulation, smoothing and re-meshing mesh functions are employed with Diffusion and Local Cell settings in ANSYS Fluent.

2.3. Solution algorithm

We follow the following four stages in one time marching step during the simulation. At the beginning, the velocity of the fish and fins are estimated with our in-house code using Multi-Body Dynamics Theory. The main body (N_{b0}) is set as the reference body, and its initial information such as the location and velocity are given. Fins are connected to the main body via virtual hinges. Apart from the global coordinating system, each body N_{bn} has its own local reference frame F_n . The velocity of body j is a (6×1) matrix:

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_j = \left(\mathbf{V}_j^T, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j^T \right)^T$$

and can be transformed to the local reference frame of Body i by following the adjoint map operator which can be expressed as:

$$Ad_{j g_i} = \begin{pmatrix} {}^j R_i & {}^j R_i {}^i \hat{P}_j^T \\ 0 & {}^j R_i \end{pmatrix}$$

where ${}^j R_i$ and ${}^i P_j$ are the orientation matrix and the position vector of F_j with respect to F_i .

Based on the reference body and the relative relations, the position and velocity of other bodies can be calculated. The information of velocity is then transferred to CFD software. Using Dynamic Mesh tool, the body position is updated. At the third step, the fluid field around fish is solved by CFD, so that the force and moment of the fish body and fins are obtained. Finally, this information is passed back to the UDF and the in-house code will calculate updated velocities.

3. Results and discussions

According to the experiment, the phase angles between dorsal and anal fins are almost identical. Therefore, only phase angle difference between caudal and dorsal fins is tested in the present work with their specific values of $\frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{4}, \pi$. The fish body displacement in the X direction, hydrodynamic force imposed on the fish and the relevant fluid field will be presented in the following parts.

3.1. Displacement

Fig. 4 (a) shows the fish body displacement in the X direction during the first 8 periods for the four cases associated with different phase angle difference. The displacement is shown as negative as the fish model swims towards the negative direction of the X axis.

(a) Displacement for 8 periods

(b) Displacement in 7th and 8th period

Fig. 4 Comparison of the fish body displacement in the X direction

There is no significant discrepancy among $\frac{\pi}{4}$, $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\frac{3\pi}{4}$. As can be seen from Fig. 4 (b), where an zoom-in plot is presented, the displacement for the case with a phase angle difference of π between caudal and dorsal fins is slight smaller from the others, meaning the pufferfish model swims the most slowly when the caudal fin is out of phase with the other two fins.

3.2. Hydrodynamic forces

The resultant hydrodynamic forces along X direction within 6th to 8th period are compared in Fig. 5 for various cases. For all cases, two peaks are observed in one oscillating period. The resultant force for a phase angle difference of $\pi/2$ is dramatically different from the other three cases. Although the motions of the fins are prescribed by notable phase angles difference, no obvious phase lag is noted for the resultant force.

Fig. 6 shows the force on the fish body and fins from 6th to 8th period. Both dorsal and anal fins produce thrust and the force on the dorsal fin is slightly larger than the anal fin. This is because the area of former is a little larger than that of the latter. Biologically, the caudal fin plays the most important role during the self-propulsion swimming process, thus the force generated by the caudal fin contributes most to the resultant force as indicated by Fig.6.

Fig. 5: Comparison of resultant force for cases with various phase angle difference

Fig. 6: Comparison of force on fish body and fins with a phase angle difference of $\pi/2$

3.3. Wake pattern

Fig. 7 shows the snapshots of flapping motion and development of wake pattern of the fish and fins within 10th period for phase angle difference of $\pi/2$. The iso-surface is generated when the vorticity magnitude is 10. As all three fins generate vortices as well as the fish body, the vorticity field is rather complex as can be seen from the figures. The detailed examinations are performed in the on-going research.

Fig. 7: Iso-surface of fluid field vorticity coloured by pressure

4. Conclusions

With a use of numerical modelling method, we investigated the influence of phase angle difference on a self-propelled pufferfish model. For the first time, a Multi-Body Dynamics theory is combined with a CFD method in order to solve the free swimming fish problem propelled by flapping fins motions. Our simulation results shown that for the displacement of the pufferfish, there is no significant difference. In terms of the resultant force, the result from the case with a phase angle difference of $\pi/2$ differs from the others dramatically. By investigating the resultant forces around fish body and fins, it is noted that the caudal fin plays a major part for propulsion force generation. The overall thrust they

generated is quite small which is possibly related to the fact that all the fins are modelled as rigid which are actually flexible in reality. The study on flexible fins driven self-propelled fish will be presented in a separated paper in the near future. With its application in bio-inspired AUV design, the present study indicated that, in addition to caudal fin which is always used in the past, the contribution of dorsal and anal fin may also need to be considered for the system thrust generation.

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A Fleet of Sea-Cleaning Autonomous Units Managed by Waste-Recovery Island

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Abstract

This paper describes the concept of a fleet of sea-cleaning autonomous units managed by a waste-recovery island. A multitude of small “foldable”, autonomous, versatile catamarans will allow cleaning up the water surface from spilled oil, litter and micro-plastics. The preliminary design of a single unit of the envisioned fleet (BlackSheep) has been implemented, assembling an efficient recovery systems based on wool. The study of the waste-recovery island has become the object of interest both in terms of feasibility and in terms of instrumental layout settings.

1. Introduction

Water pollution has become one of most serious ecological threats we face today mainly due to oil (oil spills, routine shipping, run-offs...) and waste dumping. Cleaning huge and extended amount of water surfaces is very costly and time-consuming and most of the time the cleaning solutions available either “hide” the problem or are not effective.

The cleaning of spilled oil is a hard task since it depends on many factors such as the oil type, water temperature (which influences evaporation and biodegradation), the kind of shoreline involved. Several researchers suggest different approaches, e.g. *Kakalis et al. (2008)*, *MIT (2010)* and *Pashna et al. (2013)*.

The main cleaning methods adopted are:

- Bioremediation. This method uses biological agents to remove the oil. The so-called “bioremediation accelerators” (hydrophobic substances) contain bacteria which chemically bond to hydrocarbons (soluble or not). This way, floating molecules conglomerate in a jelly substance, which can later be removed;
- Use of dispersants. These dispersants act as detergents: surrounding the oil spheres, they allow them to be transported in water. The water surface aspect improves, but smaller drops of oil are trailed behind by currents and could contaminate water flora;
- Watch and wait. In some occasions, the natural thinning of oil could be the most appropriate solution, especially in sensitive marine areas;
- Dredging of dispersed oils and of oils heavier than water;
- Skimming methods require calm water;
- Solidification. Thickeners are made of dry, absorbent hydrophobic polymers. They transform the physical state of oil from liquid to semi-solid, in a way that the spilled material will look like rubber floating on water, therefore easy to be removed. Their toxicity has been tested;
- Vacuum and centrifugation. Oil can be sucked up together with water. Centrifugation of the fluid will allow the separation of the two liquids.

From a deep analysis of all the above mentioned methods, skimming has turned out to be the most efficient and absolutely noxious-free method for the environment. Many kinds of skimmers exist and their efficiency will depend upon oil thickness and viscosity, suspension degree, sea state and stocking capacity. Despite this, it is important to keep in mind that none of the skimmers commercialized so far has been 100% efficient and able to collect only oil and no water.

In the last few years, it was brought to media attention that coarse wool is waterproof and lipophilic, i.e. absorbs oil without absorbing water. The BlackSheep project, *Valenti (2012)*, used this

information to develop a 26 m workboat with the aim to clean up water surfaces from spilled oil without chemicals:

- in the “greenest” possible way
- with the possibility to reach shallow waters
- giving the possibility to re-use the recovered spilled oil.

Besides being a natural material, wool has the property of soaking up 10 times its weight of oil of any kind and any thickness. By squeezing the skimmer, it is possible to separate the absorbed oil from the wool. This process can be repeated as many as ten times without any significant loss of efficiency. The recovered hydrocarbons could be reused as if they had never been spilled. It is easy to understand why wool has been chosen as main element in this feasibility study.

This paper will describe an autonomous system made of a “master” island and six “slave” boats that use rolls with wool to clean up limited waters (ports, lakes...) suffering from a semi-constant pollution.

2. The boat

The boat is designed as a catamaran. The overall dimensions were determined based on the models with specific operability characteristics proposed in literature as *Karlson (1993)*, *Varyani et al. (2000)*, *Dunbabin et al. (2009)*, and described in the following paragraphs. Particular reference was made to specific analysis, *Valenti (2012)*, Fig.1, oriented to determine the hull geometry (and the equipment required on board) based on the kind of tasks that the ship has to perform. The BlackSheep project, *Valenti (2012)*, Fig.1, showed that there is a way to successfully clean up water surfaces from spilled oil without chemicals,

Fig. 1: Reference boat

Fig. 2: Catamaran preliminary sketch

In order to take that preliminary project to a further stage, by means of prototyping the whole recovery system to test its real efficiency (at low cost without expensive machinery), brought the need of developing a smaller boat, which is described here. The main features characterizing the idea (catamaran geometry, wool as skimmer...) have been transferred to this feasibility study. Furthermore the design has been improved by making the boat smaller and autonomous.

The catamaran's main dimensions are: $\Delta=1000$ kg; $L=8$ m; $B_{tot}=5$ m; $B_{hull}=1.20$ m; $D=1.5$ m.

The displacement hulls give the necessary buoyancy (when fully loaded). The speed requirements during working conditions are very low (about 3 knots). Propulsion is obtained through two fixed pitch propellers powered by electric motors: according to the boat's operational requirements (see par. 10.4). The power installed onboard will not exceed 20 kW. Superstructures are not necessary for this autonomous vehicle. The only volume extended above the main deck is determined by the system rolls-rug, whose geometry is later on described.

The free surface of the main deck will be covered with solar panels to ensure a minimum autonomy of the machinery onboard (GPS, positioning lights, unwind and rewind of the rug). For the overall dimensioning of these components, see par. 10.4.

3. The wool rug and the rolls

The winding plastic cylinder has an external diameter of 0.2 m. This system allows the rolling up of about 100 m of wool rug, 30 mm thick, giving a final cylinder diameter of 1.40 m. The rug is realized as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Scheme of the wool rug attached to its cylinders (out of scale)

The rolls have a “sprocket”-like geometry, Fig. 4; once the wrapping of the rug has been completed, the edge of the secondary roll fits on the edge of the primary roll in a way that the hubs’ inter-axis of the two rolls is determined. This dimension will characterize the system that handles the rolls-rug on the island.

Fig. 4: Sprocket like geometry of the rolls (out of scale)

This geometry with two rolls has been chosen both to improve the stability of the wool rug during the floating phase and to simplify the rolls’ squeezing process (as will be described later on). Architectural details both of the roll and of the inter-axis between the roll centers (described here after) were calculated such that the rolls can be easily transferred to the squeezing machine. A segment of the hub of the primary roll is characterized by a rectangular section, Fig. 5. This section is needed to allow the anchorage through a vacuum system, described in more detail in par.4.

The ends of both roll hubs have a hole contoured with radial grooves so that an automatically inserted plug, connected to the electric engine, can be inserted as connector to the engine axis.

Fig. 5: Architectural detail of the hubs' ends (out of scale)

An asymmetric septum on the inside of the roll's outer section is created, Fig. 5, so that the buoyancy of each roll is predetermined. A GPS module is placed in the primary roll's cavity, together with all the equipment needed by the geo-localization (antenna, signal lights etc. ...). The anchoring buoy of the rug consists of a set of primary and secondary rolls, Fig. 4.

Each section of the wool rug can be bought commercially off the shelf or "homemade" by assembling flakes of coarse wool between two fine mesh nets, "quilt" sewed. The roll dimensions are shown in Tables I and II:

Table I: Wool rug characteristics

wool thickness=	0,03	[m]
ρ wool=	2,2	[kg/m ³]
roll lenght=	3	[m]
linear volume (1m)=	0,09	[m ³]
weight for linear meter=	0,198	[kg]
η squeezing (initial)=	0,8	
η squeezing (final)=	0,65	
ρ oil=	980	[kg/m ³]

Table II: Wool rug properties

	[m]	[m]	[m]	[kg]	[kg]	[m ³]	[kg]
n. of wrappings	diameter	perimeter	sheet length	weight cleaned sheet	weight of the recoverable oil (theoretical)	volume of the recoverable oil (theoretical)	recoverable oil (1 sheet x 1 time) η
iniziale	0,2	0,628	0,628	0,124	1,243	0,0013	0,895
37	1,31	4,113	90,087	17,837	178,371	0,1820	128,427
38	1,34	4,208	94,294	18,670	186,703	0,1905	134,426
39	1,37	4,302	98,596	19,522	195,220	0,1992	140,558
40	1,4	4,396	102,992	20,392	203,924	0,2081	146,825
41	1,43	4,490	107,482	21,281	212,815	0,2172	153,227
42	1,46	4,584	112,067	22,189	221,892	0,2264	159,762

One of the major "issues" of the shown solution is the great efficiency of wool absorbance that leads to long recovery operations. This led to the idea of making the rug "detachable" from the boat. Once the rug is left to float (anchored to the buoy rolls), the boat can go back and forth from the "island" to bring the used material to the squeezing system or to redeploy it.

This allows cleaning up of a wide area of the sea surface in relatively short time. The concept will be explained in more detail in chapter 6.

4. Rug release on water and recover onboard

The operational stages (for the rug to be released on water and to be recovered from it) are:

- the rug is wrapped on the primary roll;
- it is taken to the working area and it is unwrapped solely by the boat movement;
- the rug is released on water;
- the recovery uses the geo-localization system and connects rug, primary roll and vacuum system;
- the primary roll is connected to the supports onboard the boat;
- the pneumatic rotating plugs insert automatically;
- the primary roll starts to rotate and the rug recovery begins;
- this action ends when the edges of the “sprockets” of the rolls make contact
- the roll-rug system is ready to be taken by the manipulation unit set in the island.

5. Rolls' recovery method

The primary roll can be released and recovered from the boat via a vacuum system. Such systems are already available on the market, e.g. the solution by ZAD Marine, CCM-Octope, Fig. 6). The secondary roll is trailed by the rug and spontaneously reaches the configuration reported in Fig. 4. The following figures show the operating principle. Dimensions are adapted to the specific application.

Fig. 6: Example of vacuum system available in the market

Vacuum systems like these usually operate at 12 V, with electrical absorption in the order of 95 W. The vacuum unit is turned on only during the recovery phases. The ship brings the rug (wrapped on the primary roll) to the releasing area. The releasing operation foresees the detachment from the vacuum system.

During the recovery phase, the buoy position is precisely and easily found by the boat throughout the GPS set in the rolls (see par. 3): in proximity of the primary roll, the vacuum actuator is activated such that its flat edges adhere to the flat area of the hub's roll, obtaining the hooking. The recovery of the wool rug towards the boat sets its winding on the primary roll. Both the primary and the secondary roll are floating, modified inside as previously stated.

6. Arrangement of the rolls in water

Each boat has the task of managing several rolls in 24 h. The island position can be either symmetric or asymmetric with respect to the interested sea areas: the first arrangement sets the same workload for every boat, while the second could be adopted, for example, if one item of the fleet is less performing for some reasons.

Fig. 7 (a) shows the situation of five operative areas with “symmetric island” condition: each area is considered to be rectangular. The rugs' arrangement in each working zone is sketched in Fig. 7 (b): ample space for maneuvering was left to avoid overlapping of rugs due to currents or waves.

Free deck areas on the island, i.e. areas without machinery, are dedicated to storing 25 rolls (clean or dirty). Considering that at the beginning of the operations 5 of the 6 boats managed by the island already mount their own system roll-rug during their transfer (with the island) to the working area, we have a total of 30 recovery system available. Each boat will therefore have to manage 5 rugs.

Given the wool's characteristics and properties, each boat will be able to clean up an area of 17200 m² (240 m x 72 m). Therefore the whole island system could clean a surface of 17200 x 5 rugs x 10 times = 86000 m², with a total amount of about 9.3 m³ (1.55 x 6) of pollutant recovered.

Fig. 7: a) possible arrangement of working areas (left); b) detail of small section of a working area (right)

If the area to be cleaned is smaller, one could use the same number of boats and rug-rolls to perform periodic work in the area. The efficiency of each working cycle is summarized in Table III.

Table III: Efficiency of working cycles

n. of used times	η squeezing	weight of recoverable oil @each trip [kg]
1	0,800	143,692
2	0,788	141,619
3	0,777	139,547
4	0,765	137,474
5	0,754	135,402
6	0,742	133,330
7	0,731	131,257
8	0,719	129,185
9	0,708	127,112
10	0,696	125,040
11	0,685	122,967
12	0,673	120,895
13	0,662	118,822
14	0,650	116,750
Volume of recovered oil [m ³]=		1,62
(one roll used 10 times)		

As far as time is concerned, the following working schedules are proposed (for each boat):

- the boat moves to and from the island with a speed of 6 knots (3 m/s);
- the cleaning surface is a multiple of the elementary area (72 m x 240 m): a minimum of ten times bigger since each roll can be used at least 10 times;

- the numbers of treated areas is 5, since 5 are the rugs manageable from each boat; therefore there will be an imaginary “pentagon” surrounding the island;
- the maximum distance that has to be run from each boat is equal to the diagonal of every single cleaning area 2500 m ($((2400^2 + 720^2)^{1/2})$).

This gives a travel time to the furthest angle of the area of almost 15 minutes. We considered in addition: 10 min to release the rug in the wanted place, 20 min for the recovery of the dirty rug from the water, 5 min to load/unload the rug on/from the island. The total amount of time for the whole operation is a little more than 1 hour. Therefore, each boat works 50 h (1 h x 5 rugs x 10 times). At a first estimation, the six boats can operate totally at the same time. In the hypothesis of a continuous working cycle (24h/24h), the boat’s autonomy is 2 days.

In the above estimates, the time required for battery charging on the boats has not been considered. This time depends on the kind of batteries installed. On the other hand the assumption of boats traveling always the greatest distance is conservative. The effects should largely cancel and the above estimates are deemed to be realistic.

8. The island

The concept includes an island as the place where the squeezing of the wool takes place and other operations are carried out. The island’s dimensions are 30m x 30 m. Two parallel channels, running for the whole length of the platform, allow the “storage” of the boats during non-working hours, facilitate the charging of the boats’ batteries and the loading/unloading of the rolls in a safer way. The channels are 5.50 m wide, a little wider than the boats. The inner overall volume of the island is therefore $3.6 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$. According to preliminary estimation, this will be sufficient to give enough buoyancy to the whole system, Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Island overall dimensions

We designed two channels to have flowing operations and movements “onboard” the island, differentiating them by task. One channel is dedicated to the unloading of the dirty rug, the other to the loading of a cleaned or reusable one.

The island length, (therefore the channels’ as well) allows the “storing” of three boats simultaneously, allowing smoother operability of more vehicles at the same time and avoiding waste of time during loading/unloading operations. The same considerations motivated the decision of having the channels running the whole length of the island, avoiding rear mode manoeuvres and the blocking of the entrance opening.

These design decisions then implied the positioning of the machinery for the management and movement of the rolls on the “roof” of the structure that holds the solar panels.

The channels have the additional role of boathouse, sheltering also in case of adverse weather conditions. During bad weather, the time is used to recharge the batteries of the boats.

The coverage of the whole island allows a large amount of solar panels, Fig. 9, making the platform completely autonomous in terms of energy, see par. 10. Each channel has grooves at the sides, see Fig. 10. Pneumatic and/or vacuum mechanisms (detailed below) can block the boat in the wanted position along the grooves. Once the boat has been secured, it is possible to start the island's operations. A mechanical system (see par. 9) transfers the rolls to the squeezing machine. For anchorage and/or island positioning the following alternatives are proposed:

1. anchoring to the seabed throughout chains and/or cables. This can be achieved in "shallow" waters and when the area to be cleaned up does not require movement of the island in order to avoid collision with other floating structures.
2. dynamic positioning - The island is equipped with four bow-thruster at its far edges. Their combined start-up will allow both translation movements and rotations to and from a referring initial GPS point. The island can thus compensate movements due to current, waves, etc.

Fig. 9: Island coverage

Fig. 10: Channel detail

Fig. 11: Boat entering the island

9. Rug-roll system from boat to island

The initial condition is of rug wound up on the primary roll, with touching sprocket-like ends (of the two rolls); then the inter-axis is unequivocal and well determined. The rug-rolls system is onboard the boat entering the channel of the island. The boat reaches the desired position and is blocked pneumatically or by a vacuum unit or other equivalent system. It then starts the transversal translation of the portal with the handling machinery, using tires running on aluminum rails. The rails run right below the cover with solar panels, Fig. 12.

The gantry consists of:

- a rectangular structure with constrains at the four edges, on top of tires engaged in rails with bilateral constraints;

- four pneumatic cylinders equipped with clamps at one end to anchor the rolls hubs to allow the transfer;
- two screw actuators (actioned by an electric motor with conical torque) with the aim of varying the vertical position of the “millwork” roll, in the following “squeezing” phase.

Fig 12: a) left: handling gantry sketch (out of scale); b) right: detail of the rails

Fig. 13: Gantry scheme (out of scale)

The gantry operation is shown in Fig. 12 (a) along with a detail of the pneumatic actuators' tires engaged in the rails in Fig. 12 (b). The gantry scheme is shown in Fig. 13. When the gantry is above the boat, the clamps, after being started, anchor the rolls' hubs, lifting the system rug-rolls. Once the boat has been freed from the rolls, it can proceed towards the other channel to be reloaded. At this point, the loaded gantry brings the rolls on the lean on surface of the squeezing system as shown in Fig. 13. This figure only refers to one of the two rolls, but the functioning will be the same also with the couple of them. The rolls have been set in a fixed position on two supports with a saddle shape, Fig. 14. Pneumatic clutches (one in each side) fasten the axis of each roll, Fig. 14, to an engine that will start its rotation to transfer the rug from the primary to the secondary roll of the system.

Once the rug has completely been rolled up in the second roll, the motion is reversed while a millwork roll approaches the rug, Fig. 15. The rug goes from the first to the second roll and vice-versa until the oil has been completely squeezed out. Underneath the rolls a hopper collects the recovered fluid, sending it to some inner tanks of the island using a pump. At the end of the millwork operation the rug-rolls system is in the same condition as when it left this position from the gantry. Thus the same sequence of operation can be performed in the reverse order to load the rolls back into the boat.

Fig.14: Detail of the squeezing system (out of scale)

Fig. 14: Transversal section of the squeezing system (out of scale)

10. Energy balance

The electric power needed by the island to perform its duties was evaluated approximately, Table IV. The worst scenario in terms of electric power request will require 7.36 kWh. In order to have a safety margin, an average of 10 kWh will be considered for each trip in the next considerations. Due to the short time required in loading/unloading, it is pointless considering recharging the boat's batteries in this time frame. Instead, after three round voyages the boat will have to stop for 30 to 60 minutes to be recharged.

Table IV: Requested electric power

Evaluation of electric power										
	Activities description	Speed	Travelled distance (average)	Average time	Average time	Required power [kW]	Time	Time	Boat kWh	Island kWh
		[ktn]	[km]	[sec]	[h]		[sec]	[h]		
1 st cycle	Boat leaves the island	12,000	2,500	404,97	0,1125	12	404,97	0,112	1,35	
	Boat unrolls the rag in its position	3,000	0,100	64,79	0,0180	6	469,76	0,130	0,11	
	Boat enters the island	12,000	2,600	421,17	0,1170	12	890,93	0,247	1,40	
									0,247	2,862
2 nd cycle	Allining and fixing of the boat to the island			300	0,0833	10	300	0,083		0,83
	Loading of rag-rolls system on the boat			600	0,1667	10	900	0,250		1,67
	Battery charging of the boat			500	0,1389	10				1,39
	Boat leaving the island	12,000	0,500	80,99	0,0225	12	980,99	0,272	0,27	
	Boat unrolls the rag in its position	3,000	0,100	64,79	0,0180	6	1045,79	0,290	0,11	
	Boat recovers cleaning system	1,500	0,100	129,59	0,0360	8	1175,38	0,326	0,29	
	Boat enters the island fully loaded	12,000	0,600	97,19	0,0270	14	1272,57	0,353	0,38	
				1772,6				0,353	1,044	3,889
3 rd cycle	Allining and fixing of the boat to the island			300	0,0833	15	300	0,083		1,25
	Unloading of the rag-rolls system from the boat			600	0,1667	10	900	0,250		1,67
	Boat load a new cleaning system			600	0,1667	10	1500	0,417		1,67
	Battery charging of the boats (5 at once)			500	0,1389	10				1,39
	Boat leaving the island	12,000	0,500	80,99	0,0225	12	1580,99	0,439	0,27	
	Squeezing of the rag	0,2	100,000	500	0,1389	10				1,39
	Boat unrolls the rag in its position	3,000	0,100	64,79	0,0180	6	1645,79	0,457	0,11	
	Boat recovers cleaning system	1,500	0,100	129,59	0,0360	8	1775,38	0,493	0,29	
	Boat enters the island fully loaded	12,000	0,600	97,19	0,0270	14	1872,57	0,520	0,38	
									0,520	1,044

10.1 Power supply from solar panels plant

The electrical power supply necessary for the island is generated by a cover of photovoltaic solar panels, extended over the whole island. Considering mono-crystalline silicon panels (CIS), the installed overall installation generates 110-130 kWp. Fig. 16 shows the general layout of the electrical plant.

Fig. 16: General layout of the solar power plant

10.2 Power intake from millwork

The squeezing procedure of the rug is similar to a millwork operation. In order to determine the requested engine torque during winding up and unwinding of the rug (i.e. the power intake), the force acting on the rolls was evaluated.

$$F = p L_D S$$

p is the contact pressure among the two rolls and the rug, $S = 30$ mm the initial thickness of the rug and L_D the contact length determined by:

$$L_D = \sqrt{R \Delta H}$$

$R = 250$ mm is the radius of the roll and ΔH the thickness variation of the rug during its squeezing. Assuming $\Delta H = 2$ mm (going from $S_1 = 30$ mm to $S_2 = 28$ mm) and a maximum contact pressure of 100 kPa, the force acting on the rolls is equal to $F = 210$ N. The torque needed is:

$$C = 2 F \mu L_D$$

Assuming the friction coefficient among rolls and rug to be $\mu = 0.5$, the required torque is computed to $C = 14.7$ kN. For a given rotational speed of $\omega = 0.1$ rad/s, we then compute the power intake:

$$P = C \omega = 1.47 \text{ kW}$$

This we round up to 2 kW to compensate for assorted approximations made in the calculation.

10.3 Power intake during the rug wind up

The traction resistance gin pulling of the rug during its winding up was calculated approximating it as pulling on the water surface a thin foil with a total area equal to the unwound rug surface:

- rug width: 3 m
- rug length: 100 m
- rug surface: $S = 3 \times 100 = 300 \text{ m}^2$

The frictional resistance R_f of a thin foil is:

$$R_f = \frac{1}{2} C_f \rho v^2 S$$

C_f = friction coefficient (function of Reynolds number)

ρ = sea water density = 1025 kg/m³

v = dragging velocity

The maximum value that C_f can assume is 0.0075. For a dragging speed of 3 kn (1.5 m/s), the resistance is $R_f = 3459$ N, rounded to 3500 N. The initial roll diameter is thought to be 0.2 m (200 mm). Therefore the torque required to the engine during the winding up is $M = R_f D/2 = 3500 \times 0.2/2 = 350$ Nm. The rotational speed of the roll is $\omega = v/R = 1.5/0.1 = 15$ rad/s. Then the required power follows to $P = M \omega = 350 \times 15 = 5250$ W = 5.25 kW. This value is rounded up to 6 kW to include a safety and uncertainty margin.

Reducing the dragging speed of the roll would reduce the required power. The roll radius increases with the number of rug layers around the roll. The value assumed for C_f is conservative as it is the limit extrapolation for zero speed and C_f decreases with increasing speed (and Reynolds number).

10.4 Power available onboard of the boat

The ship resistance is particularly influenced by speed, size (displacement), and hull form. The total calm-water resistance R_T can be decomposed into three main components: frictional resistance, residual resistance, and air resistance. Frictional and residual resistance depend on how much of the hull is below the waterline, air resistance on how much of the ship is above the waterline.

$$R_T = R_F (1 + k_1) + R_{APP} + R_W + R_B + R_{TR}$$

R_{APP} : appendage resistance

R_W : wave-making and wave-breaking resistance

R_B : additional pressure resistance due to bulbous bow near the water surface

R_{TR} : additional pressure resistance of immersed transom stern

Based on many model basin tests, semi-empirical methods have been established for calculating all the necessary non-dimensional resistance coefficients C . The frictional resistance R_F of the hull depends on the wetted area S , the speed and frictional resistance coefficient C_f . We computed it following ITTC 1957, Table V. The wetted surface is computed following a semi-empirical formula used in ship design.

$$P_e = R_t V$$

$$R_T = \frac{1}{2} \rho V^2 S C_f$$

$$C_f = \frac{0.075}{(\text{Log } Re - 2)^2}$$

$$S = l (2T + B) \frac{1}{\sqrt{C_M}} \left(0.453 + 0.4425 C_B - 0.2862 C_M - 0.003467 \frac{B}{T} + 0.3696 C_{wp} \right) + 2.38 \frac{ABT}{C_B}$$

Table V: Frictional resistance and power

L= 8,0	[m]	V= 1,54333	[m/s]
T= 0,9	[m]	$\rho= 1025$	[kg/m ³]
B= 1,1	[m]	$\mu= 0,0012$	[kg/m s]
$L_{pp}= 7,3$	[m]	Re= 9,56E+06	
$L_w= 7,4$	[m]	S= 23,48	[m ²]
$A_m= 1,8$	[m ²]	$C_f= 0,003$	
$A_w= 8,0$	[m ²]	R= 86,66	[N]
$\nabla= 7,3$	[m ³]	$P_e= 334,38$	[W]

The computed power considers only the frictional resistance, since the velocity is very low. For the same reason, the interference between the two hulls can be neglected.

10.5 Dimensioning of the vacuum stations

Each boat in the fleet has a vacuum system for the automated mooring of the rug-rolls. The mooring is set in the plane sections of the hub in the primary roll. Using a control unit able to generate 0.07 MPa on two plane surfaces 550 x 350 mm, it is possible to obtain ~8000 N in traction and 20000 N in compression.

The control unit is assembled in an aluminium container and has an electrical protection degree IP67. It encumbers 500 mm x 500 mm x 450 mm with a weight of 450 N. The weight of the two telescopic arms is ~400 N each. This gives a total value of 1000 N with the superstructures included. The energy supply is given at 12 V and the discontinuous energetic consumption is ~100 W for each mooring unit. We foresee 200 W for each boat, allowing a very long anchoring time.

The island is equipped with similar mooring systems allowing coordinated movement during berthing. There are two vacuum systems on each side (eight in total). The anchoring dimensions are similar to the ones on the boats. The control unit on the island has dimension 1.5 m x 1 m x 1 m. The estimated total consumption is 800 W.

10.6 Dimensioning of the mechanical transmission for the transfer on the island

The gantry unit transferring the system rug-rolls uses two electric motors to move the transversal rails, two brushless motors to move the millwork and four pneumatic axes with clamps at one end to grasp the rolls. There are four telescopic plugs to start the rotation of the rolls once they have been transferred on the island. This movement is achieved with a brushless rotor (one for each roll) connected to the transmission with a pneumatic plug. The pneumatic plant is also able to supply the pneumatic plugs and the inserts to start the rotation of the rolls. The pneumatic control unit has a rotating compressor powered by an electric motor working at 200 V; its working pressure is 6 bar and its maximum (at the tank) is 9 bar. The compressed area (stored in a 1000 l tank) guaranties a long working autonomy. Its dimensions are the same as a cylindrical body with 900 mm diameter and 1300 mm height. The compressor takes up a space of ~ 600 mm x 600 mm x 1000 mm. The total energy consumption is estimated to 10 kW, considering the discontinuous working pattern.

11. Complete operational sequence

Each single operation is automatic and managed by PLCs (a central one, on the island and one in each boat). The controller is modular, supplied by low tension and has inlets and outlets both digital and analogic based on the need. The initial configuration is when all the boats are moored to the island, three in each channel. Five of the six boats mount one of the system rug-rolls. The complete sequence of the average operation is as follows:

- the boat is detached from its mooring to the island;
- the boat leaves the channel and reaches the target area;
- the rug is released and unwound thanks to the relative motion of the boat;
- the primary roll is detached from the boat;
- one by one, each boat leaves the island, operating as described above;
- the first boat return to the island;
- it performs a mooring manoeuvre;
- the handling system goes on top of the boat;
- the four pneumatic actuators lift the rolls system from the boat through the clamps grasp;
- the system is translated to the supports on the squeezing region;
- the millwork roll is lowered by screw actuators, until the rug is in the squeezing position;
- the rug goes back and forth from the primary roll to the second and vice versa, while the position of the millwork roll is lowered at each round;
- at the end of the squeezing procedure, the millwork rolls is lifted;

- the actuators with clamps grab the system rug-rolls and place it back in the boat;
- the handling system goes back to its position in the island;
- the boat releases its mooring and leaves the channel;
- the boat takes the roll to another target pertinence area;
- these operations are repeated 10 times for each boat;
- finally the last boat uses up its last roll in the second channel;
- The island returns to shore.

12. Additional considerations

The following additional elements are worth to be mentioned:

- presence of a wireless video camera system for the remote monitoring of the operations. Each action can be controlled onshore, with the recording of the operational stages and warning of unexpected functioning;
- inspections with drones. The operative area can be inspected with drones that complete the information coming from the fixed cameras;
- periodic interventions on the island. The island autonomy is wide: therefore once in a while the intervention of skilled personnel is requested both for general checks, disposal of the recovered material and the dirty used rolls;
- autonomous operation of each boat. Each operation is automatically managed. A net of assorted sensors and transducers is therefore foreseen to measure and detect position, pressures, and forces. Each of these signals is input to the control units both on the island and on the boat;
- autonomy time. The operative autonomy of each boat is estimated to be two days, continuously working. The island has eight days autonomy;
- emergency generator. For emergency service, the island has a small generator;
- wind power plant. The solar power plant is integrated with vertical axis wind generators (Darrieus kind). Those generators can be placed in between the island's planking level and the island cover: eight of these generators could be placed along the island perimeter;
- positioning of pneumatic and electric sub-station, recovered oil tank and other sub-units. The compartmented structure of the island allows easy storage of each service unit;
- desalination plant for the cleaning of solar panels. To optimize the panels' performances a micro-desalination plant is installed onboard to periodically clean the solar panels.

13. Prototyping

Several experiments on prototypes of boat and of transfer machinery are under development. Fig. 17 collects some aspects of this prototyping phase.

The tests concern in particular:

- the development of hulls with low friction resistance;
- the hull optimization;
- the study of the electro-pneumatic gantry unit;
- the choice of the optimal gripper geometries for the rolls transfer;
- the implementation of automatic control procedures based on the use of mini and micro PLCs, field bus architectures or industrial PCs;
- the selection of sensors and transducers and their applicability under heavy working conditions.

Fig. 17: Prototyping

14. Concluding remarks

The proposed solution is of low costs, due to the simplicity of the used components and for the employment of devices available on the market. Cleaning operations can be performed on shallow and on deep water. The versatility of the solution allows modular implementation by increasing number of boats or islands. Using wool as skimming device creates an additional market for this natural product. The project shall develop an operative prototype, both for boats and island, to validate the choices made during the feasibility study and to start the engineering of the system. The concept is designed to recover and recycle oil spills. However, the system could be modified in the collecting apparatus to recover floating litter, in particular plastics and micro-plastics.

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Biomimetic Approaches for Ship Drag Reduction – Feasible and Efficient?

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Abstract

The surface properties of a ship hull have a significant influence on the drag of a vessel. Several approaches to reduce drag are being discussed in the recent literature. This paper presents two approaches that are currently under intensive investigation at Fraunhofer IFAM. (1) Riblet-coatings, mimicking the skin of a shark, have proven their capability to reduce surface drag by more than 5% as being measured in cooperation with Hamburg Ship Model Basin (HSVA). The producibility under shipyard conditions was demonstrated and the chemical approaches for efficient suppression of biofouling are currently being developed. (2) Compliant coatings, inspired by the properties of the dolphin's skin, appear to be efficient in order to postpone transition from laminar to turbulent flow as demonstrated by numerical calculations, carried out by HSVA. Recent developments focus on two different approaches: on the one hand, the use of novel polymeric materials with unique high-damping properties (monolayer system), on the other hand a bilayer model according to synthetic dolphin skin with soft and elastic blubber as well as stiff and rigid dermis. The results on both concepts concerning accomplished and running projects are presented. The feasibility and potential of each concept is discussed.

1. Introduction

The drag of a vessel is a decisive factor for the direct operating costs, because it can directly be translated to fuel consumption. The drag of a ship comprises several components:

- Pressure drag due to the pressure difference between the side experiencing the flow (e.g. the bow of a ship) and the opposite side (e.g. the stern);
- Induced drag on objects that generate lift (e.g. hydrofoils);
- Wave drag due to the bow wave and stern wave;
- Frictional drag due to the friction of the fluid (air or water) at the surface

The frictional drag, namely the friction between the solid (coating) surface and the flowing fluid, can be influenced considerably by the properties of the coating, *Stenzel and Rehfeld (2011)*. The frictional drag plays a major role for ships and can be more than 50% of the total drag, *Fukuda et al.(2000)*. In times of “slow steaming” the portion of frictional drag can be even significantly higher. Consequently it is worth considering the options available for influencing the frictional drag by means of coating technology.

The frictional drag is highly dependent on the flow conditions. In particular two different flow regimes have to be considered:

- Laminar flow which is free from vortices and turbulence, resulting in minimum frictional drag
- Turbulent flow which is characterized by turbulences and vortices. These vortices have components in both the flow direction and perpendicular to this. The frictional drag in turbulent state is up to one magnitude higher than in laminar state, *Rechenberg (2001)*.

When a vessels travels through the water, the flow along the hull is typically starting as laminar flow (depending on the flow status of the surrounding water). During travel along the solid surface, the flow undergoes a transition phase, where it changes to turbulent flow after going through an unstable

transition, Fig.1. Waves develop in the transition region (Tollmien-Schlichting waves) which then become larger and eventually change into wholly turbulent flow, *Schlichting (1968)*.

Fig. 1: Transition from laminar to turbulent flow

For typical commercial ships the transition from laminar to turbulent flow occurs very early in the bow region. Due to this situation there are two basically different approaches to influence surface drag through coatings technology:

- Postponing the transition from laminar to turbulent flow in order to gain a higher proportion of laminar flow
- Reducing the friction when the flow is already in turbulent state

Both approaches are currently under investigation. A feasible coating technology for this purpose does not only have to have drag reducing properties, anti-fouling or fouling release properties are indispensable as well.

2. Drag reducing coating technologies

2.1. Compliant coatings, inspired by dolphin skin, for transition delay

Since the drag in laminar flow conditions is significantly lower than in turbulent flow regime, it may be advantageous to keep the flow laminar as long as possible. For typical commercial ships the transition region is very near the leading edge of the bow, Fig.2.

Fig.2: Transition (indicated by red dots) along flow lines in the bow region (source: HSV)

If the transition could be postponed, the total drag of a vessel could be reduced significantly. Figure 3, left, shows the shear stress at the hull surface when the transition occurs near the leading edge of the bow. The area under the curve indicates the surface drag of the vessel. Fig.3 (right) shows the shear stress when a delay of transition for only a short distance (approx. 1/10 of the ship length) could be achieved. The surface drag is reduced significantly, because the high peak of the shear stress in the bow region could be cut off. This simplified calculation, carried out by Hamburg Ship Model Basin (HSVA), shows the potential for drag reduction by transition delay.

Fig.3: Shear stress on ship hull for turbulent flow conditions (left) and with delay of transition (right) (source HSVA)

How can this delay of transition be achieved? The best example for transition delay from nature is the dolphin, that reaches an underwater speed of up to 10 knots and the flow around the body is predominantly laminar, *Kramer (1961)*. From early on it was assumed that special mechanical properties of the skin of dolphins played a key role here. In the late 1950s a series of experiments was carried out which indicated that soft coatings inspired by the properties of dolphin skin were able to significantly reduce the drag of surfaces in water. Since that time these coatings have been known as Kramer-type coatings. The effect of such coatings is based on the fact that the soft surface dampens the formation and development of Tollmien-Schlichting waves via energy absorption (damping) and means that the transition from laminar flow to turbulent flow occurs later. This leads to drag reduction because a larger portion of the surface is subject to laminar flow which is the more favourable condition. This explanation appeared plausible to start with, but this effect could not be reproduced in later studies and so doubts about the results arose. Subsequent studies, *Carpenter and Garrad (1986)* have shown, however, that Kramer-type coatings are theoretically able to reduce drag, but the mechanism is considerably more complex than outlined above.

New polymers with optimized damping properties and adjustable viscoelastic properties appeared recently on the market which open up new opportunities for the formulation of compliant coatings that are adjusted to the flow properties of a given ship design and operational profile. The project "FLIPPER" aims at the development of a compliant coating material based on elaborated flow simulations, performed by HSVA and Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH). New polymers with high damping properties, developed by ARKEMA, as well as polymers representing "synthetic blubber" and mimicking the skin structure of dolphins according to the results of flow and material simulations, could be provided. Details about FLIPPER, the numerical simulations and tests are given in the paper "Drag Reduction for Ships: Drawing Inspiration from Dolphins" by Lars-Uve Schrader from HSVA.

2.2. Riblet ("shark-skin") coatings for friction reduction in turbulent flow

2.2.1 Basics of riblet technology for ship application

It has been known for many years that the skin of fast-swimming sharks is equipped with a riblet-structure aligned to the main axis of the body. The hypothesis was drawn that this topography is

hydrodynamically advantageous. Detailed studies, for instance studies carried out by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) have elucidated the mechanism of wall friction reduction, *Bechert et al. (1985)*, and artificial surface structures, mimicking the function of shark skin, were derived, *Bechert et al. (2000)*.

Turbulent flow, similar to laminar flow, has a main flow direction. For turbulent flow, however, this is also superimposed by oscillations transverse to the main flow. In the direct vicinity of the wall streak-like structures form which can be thought of as counter-rotating vortices. The riblets parallel to the main flow direction cause the origins of the longitudinal and transverse components of the turbulent flow to be differently affected, Fig.4. The transverse component, which is primarily responsible for the higher turbulent drag, is affected more and its origin is further from the wall than that in the main flow direction. This difference means that less friction is transferred to the wall. Somewhat more graphic, though not wholly correct, is the explanation that the vortex components in the transverse direction now only act at the crests of the riblets and contribute less to the frictional drag than for smooth surfaces.

Fig.4: Effect of riblets on the components of turbulence perpendicular to the main flow, *Hage (2004)*

In experiments with adjustable riblet surfaces in an oil tunnel it was found that the ideal height of the riblets equals half the distance between the riblet tips, *Bechert et al. (2000)*. The optimal riblet interval depends on the flow conditions at the surface, as defined by the Reynolds number (Re). Riblet height and distance are in the μm range for many technically relevant flow conditions. As an example: For an 8 m long object in water and a flow velocity of 10 m/s (corresponding to a Re of approx. $8 \cdot 10^7$), a riblet interval of approx. 50 μm and a corresponding height of 25 μm is optimal. Fig.6 shows the result of an experiment carried out with a 7.5 m long torpedo-shaped specimen. This test body was covered with a polymeric layer and then mounted into a cavitation tunnel, Fig.5, capable of applying a water current with up to 10 m/s speed (test carried out in HYCAT of HSVA). The drag was measured using force sensors in the mounting equipment.

Fig.5: Test specimen mounted to the top-cover of the test section of the HYCAT cavitation tunnel (source: HSVA)

The drag of the specimen was measured twice: The first measurement was done with a polymeric layer showing a smooth surface and subsequently with a polymeric layer showing riblet structures with an interval of 50 μm and a height of 25 μm . Fig.6 shows the result of these measurements.

Fig.6: Drag measurements of smooth and riblet-structured surface with increasing Re-number (10 m/s current speed in maximum)

It could be clearly proven that a reduction of surface drag by 5.2 % at higher Re-numbers was achieved through changing the surface structure from smooth to the riblet topography. This result corresponds to aerodynamic measurements carried out in wind-tunnels and oil channels, *Grüneberger and Hage (2011)*. Riblet geometries with a crest angle of 45°, Fig.4, have been demonstrated to be the best compromise between effectiveness and manufacturability/stability. The best results are obtained with a riblet surface where the direction of the riblets does not differ by more than $\pm 10^\circ$ from the main flow direction. Numerical simulations, carried out by HSVA, have shown that differences in draft have a minor influence on the drag-reducing performance of the riblets.

2.2.2 Painted riblets for ship application

The structuring of the top-layer of a paint built up is a favourable way to produce riblet surfaces. Reasons are:

- It is possible to produce the riblet surface even on curved, even paraboloid geometries (in contrast to foils)
- No risk of detachment/delamination? (in contrast to bonded films)
- Stripping can be carried out with the usual equipment (e.g. high-pressure water blasting)
- The chemical composition can be very similar to already qualified paint systems

Fig.7: Scheme of the riblet-paint application device (left), prototype handled by a robot (right)

The process for applying a micro-structured paint on large surfaces combines application, embossing and curing in one single process. Fig.7 shows a schematic representation of the application device. During application, the device is guided over the surface to be coated. The process consists of the following steps:

- application of a paint film on the embossing foil carrying the negative riblet structure
- the wet paint film moves under the soft roller and is pressed onto the surface and structured
- the paint film is (partially) cured with the UV-lamp shining through the transparent foil
- the device leaves a track of micro-structured paint behind

The paint formulation should contain a certain amount of UV-curable resin leading to tack-free and non-reflowing film directly after application, *Stenzel et al. (2011)*. Fig.8 shows a SEM picture of a paint surface that was produced following this process.

Fig.8: SEM picture of painted riblets

Fig.9: Application of painted riblets in dry dock

It could be proven that the described application process can be carried out in the rough environment of a dry dock. Fig.8 shows a production trial in a dry dock in Emden, Germany. During this trial approx. 40 m² of painted riblets were produced on a steel wall in the dock.

2.2.3 Status of anti-fouling technology for painted riblets

One major challenge for the application of painted riblets to ships is the prevention of biofouling. It is obvious that even a thin deposition of biofilm would largely neutralise the positive effect of the riblets. Investigations of the biofouling behaviour of micro-textured surfaces, including riblet surfaces, have shown that the settlement of certain species, e.g. barnacles, can be hampered by a riblet topography, *Berntsson et al. (2000)*. Unfortunately this is not true for the majority of fouling organisms. In general the higher roughness of the riblet surfaces provides a better settling ground for biofouling organisms than a smooth surface with the same chemical composition. Consequently it is necessary to take additional measures to keep the paint surface free from biofouling. The benchmark for the durability of an anti-fouling coating for commercial shipping is 60 month. Three different approaches for fouling control of riblet-textured coatings have been investigated: i) biocidal coatings, ii) fouling release coatings, and iii) in-service cleaning:

- Formulations containing biocides
The state-of-the-art biocide containing coating systems like self-polishing coatings are no option here due to their self-sacrificial function which would destroy the topography soon.

Biocide-containing hard anti-fouling coatings have the potential to maintain the topography of the paint surface. A paint formulation containing biocides based on copper pyrithione and zinc-pyrithione, both typical biocides in anti-fouling coatings, was tested in the North Sea (Norderney). For up to 6 months the surface stayed completely free from biofilm and macro-fouling, Fig.10 (left). After 12 months exposure macro-fouling was clearly visible, Fig.10 (right). The biocides work very efficient as long as the concentration at the surface is sufficiently high. Due to the leaching of the biocide out of the paint surface, the concentration of biocides decreases over time. After 12 months the biocide concentration was obviously not high enough to prevent biofouling. The biocide containing hard anti-fouling approach does not have the potential to keep the surface free from biofouling for 60 months.

Fig.10: Biocide-containing riblet-coating after 6 months (left) and 12 months exposure in the North Sea

- Fouling release coating

The working principle of fouling release coatings is the prevention of adhesion between fouling organisms and the paint surface. The classical commercially available silicone-coatings cannot be applied for this purpose because they are not compatible with the riblet paint application procedure and are not mechanically stable enough. A promising approach is a model coating system, that can be partly UV-cured and riblet-structured or, with an alternative crosslinking-promoter, be cured by ambient temperature without UV-light. The UV-cured version of this coating can be applied with the coating procedure described above, Fig.7. This coating system forms hydrophobic and hydrophilic domains at the surface. These domains, Fig.11, have a size of several microns and have the potential to repel the larvae of certain organisms (e.g. barnacles) and to reduce the adhesion of the majority of fouling organisms. First field tests carried out under dynamic conditions using a rotating device and by test application of an operating vessel, indicate the potential of this coating. In both test scenarios it could be shown that the model coating stays nearly free from any biofouling for the time it was tested up to 6 months. Fig.12 shows the model coating in comparison to other coating approaches. It could be demonstrated that new chemical approaches open the possibility to combine the drag-reducing effect with anti-fouling properties. The future investigations will show if the desired durability for industrial application (60 months) could be achieved.

Fig.11: left: topography of the hydrophobic surface carrying hydrophilic domains forming spherical hills of approx. 500nm height, right: analysis of mechanical properties of domains (indicated by phase-shift of AFM-measurement)

Fig.12: left: Model coating in rotating test device after 3 months in the north sea, outer speed representing 35 kn, inner speed representing 16 kn, right: Test patches on the hull of WEGA after 6 months in service

- In-service cleaning

Another option is to keep the riblet surfaces free from biofouling by cleaning with a gentle cleaning method that removes the fouling but does not destroy the riblet-topography. Such cleaning methods are currently investigated. One promising approach is the cleaning by use of cavitation (“CaviBlaster™”). First trials for removal of fouling from riblet-surfaces show good cleaning results and the micro-topography of the riblets could be largely maintained, Fig.13. The first trials show, that cleaning of fouled painted riblet surfaces is possible without destroying the topography. For industrial use the cleaning methods have to be optimized and further developed.

Fig.13: Riblet coating cleaned with CaviBlaster™ and subsequent fine cleaning with brushes (upper half)

3. Conclusion

Sharks as well as dolphins use interesting methods in order to reduce surface drag and to save energy for swimming. Technical solutions, based on the working principles of these animals, are in different status of maturity.

The dolphin's approach is based on compliant coatings that delay the laminar-turbulent transition. Since the drag under laminar flow regime is approx. one magnitude lower than under turbulent regime, the delay of transition would significantly contribute to drag reduction. Material parameters for a compliant wall that should be appropriate for the transition delay for one particular hull geometry and operating profile were calculated based on hydrodynamic numerical simulations by HSVA. A polymeric material was developed meeting the simulated viscoelastic requirements. A test campaign in a cavitation tunnel with this new materials applied to a ship model will be carried out soon. The outcome of this experiment will show if this approach is technically feasible.

The shark's approach, based on a microtextured surface ("riblets"), was adopted for technical purposes. A technology for the production of such surfaces via a painting process was developed. The drag reduction by painted riblets was tested successfully for different applications like aeronautics, wind energy and shipping. For all applications surface drag reductions by 5-8 % could be measured in wind-tunnel or cavitation tunnel experiments. The main challenge for application of painted riblets for shipping is still the prevention of biofouling. In order to solve this problem several research projects are ongoing that aim at the utilisation of new biocide-free chemical approaches. The first results, covering exposure times of approx. 12 months, are promising. New cleaning methods like cavitation cleaning appear to be suitable to clean riblet surfaces from fouling organisms without destroying the microstructure.

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Autonomous Shipping – A Concept for an Autonomous Firefighting and Rescue Vessel

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Abstract

This paper describes a concept design for an autonomous fast response fire-fighting and rescue vessel. The intent of the concept is to illustrate the possibilities for autonomous shipping to undertake dull, dirty and dangerous roles, to enable discussion of the considerations needed for the naval architecture and design of autonomous vessels. After outlining the design intent and process of requirement development, the design process is described including safety considerations, operational philosophy and redundancy, application of rules and regulations and the steps taken to mitigate potential risks involved in the operation of an unmanned vessel.

1. Introduction

The last few years have seen a marked increase in interest of autonomous technology. Whether it is in the automotive, aviation or maritime industry, it is easy to envisage a future not so far away where this technology can play a significant role. In the marine industry, there are already numerous small scale unmanned vessels such as the ASV C-Worker product line, carrying out tasks such as hydrographic survey, which are proving the worth of this technology. Whilst these vessels are currently remote controlled or pre-programmed to follow a defined set of waypoints, many of these vessel operators are developing the capability of automating situational awareness and the ability of the vessel to self-navigate. As the technology advances, autonomous vessels will become larger, more capable and operate in a wider range of areas.

Typically, areas of adoption for autonomous technology include clearly defined tasks which are dull, dirty or dangerous. In addition, there needs to be a clear economic benefit to the introduction of new technology, in order to outweigh the costs involved with the associated unknown risks. For the use of an unmanned autonomous vessel to become reality, all stakeholders need to be convinced of the benefit and safety of its use, including owners, financiers, insurers, flag states, classification societies, charterer and end client.

With considerable experience in the design and operation of unmanned aerial vehicles and robotics, QinetiQ sought to utilise this experience to develop a concept design for an autonomous / unmanned ship, to illustrate the possibilities for autonomous shipping and to enable discussion of the considerations needed. The intent of the project focused on the naval architecture, marine engineering and the overall philosophy behind the ship, rather than on sensor technology and the decision making algorithms which are currently under development.

QinetiQ sought to identify a role which could be conducted by an autonomous / unmanned vessel which would fulfil the ‘dull, dirty and dangerous’ criteria often applied to the decision to automate tasks.

In considering potential applications for an unmanned vessel, offshore fire-fighting is an obvious application which can be clearly defined. It meets the criteria for dull stand-by duties and a dangerous environment in fire-fighting. Given that for this type of vessel crew costs may account for a significant proportion of operational expenditure there is also clear potential for economic benefit, particularly if a shore based control centre is utilised to oversee multiple autonomous vessels.

2. Development of key requirements

2.1. Design intent

Offshore operators (duty-holders) on the UK continental shelf are required to have a safety case and emergency response plan which reduces potential hazards to ALARP (as low as reasonably practicable). They must take into account the hazards of the activity and the availability of emergency response resources.

The primary design intent for this vessel is to form part of the emergency response provision in place to fulfil the safety case, by providing a high performance unmanned firefighting capability for a number of offshore installations, with particular emphasis on the North Sea and UK continental shelf.

The operational philosophy behind the concept involves the vessel loitering in the field for extended periods, sprint capability to an installation in the event of fire, followed by firefighting duties. This capability is supplemented by the ability to recover persons from the sea or survival craft to a place of safety.

The design of the vessel takes a holistic approach, predominantly focusing on design for the autonomous operation and the consequences of operating an unmanned vessel. The design adopts the latest commercially available technology, and maintains a firm grounding in practicality that would allow the vessel to be cost effectively constructed using today's technology, in order to demonstrate the feasibility of constructing an autonomous ship.

Based upon the design intent above, the following key requirements are defined for the vessel:

2.1.1. Autonomy

QinetiQ recognise that the acceptance of fully autonomous vessels is some years away. As such, the requirement for the vessel was set as being able to be controlled by a crew on an occasional basis, controlled ashore but unmanned during emergency response tasks and transit / berthing and fully autonomous when loitering / on standby.

Autonomous operation results in a need for the vessel to be fitted with sensors which can detect its surroundings, and computational ability to interrogate and act upon that information in an equivalent manner to human provision on a manned vessel. Secure and redundant communications to shore are required for issuing commands, monitoring of the vessel, and remote control if required.

2.1.2. Loitering

QinetiQ envisage this vessel would loiter in a strategic location such that it would be not more than 60 nautical miles (110km) from any installation it is intended to protect.

Loitering would be conducted on a purely autonomous basis including operation of all vessel systems, navigation, situational awareness and decision making. This may involve following a strategic set of way points at extremely economical speed of 3 – 5 knots, or maintaining position using dynamic positioning capability. The vessel should be capable of remaining at sea in all anticipated weather conditions, which for the North Sea means significant wave height can be up to 10m, according to global wave statistics. Fuel consumption whilst loitering should be reduced to an absolute minimum and running hours of machinery should also be minimised in order to reduce maintenance requirements, such that the vessel can operate for up to 90 days without bunkering or human intervention.

2.1.3. Sprint

If an alarm is raised by an installation in the field, an operator would be notified who would command the vessel to proceed to the location. This voyage could be made autonomously or via remote control. It was decided that the vessel should be able to arrive on the scene of an incident to support firefighting within three hours, resulting in a required design speed of 20 knots. The vessel can therefore provide coverage for an area of approximately 40,000km² within 3 h, as illustrated in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Illustration of potential oil field coverage

2.1.4. Firefighting

In order to provide the best possible protection to designated installations, it was decided that the vessel should have the most high performance firefighting system available to DNV FIFI Class III notation capable of delivering 9,600m³/h and sufficient fuel capacity for a minimum of 96 h of continuous firefighting. Firefighting could be conducted autonomously using a variety of sensors and control algorithms or through remote control with a human operator either ashore or on a separate mothership.

2.1.5. Rescue

Whilst the primary objective of the vessel is to conduct firefighting duties, it is also required to have the capability of recovering persons from the sea or survival craft. SOLAS regulation III/17-1 requires all ships to plan to be able to recover persons from the water and from survival craft. It was therefore decided that the vessel should meet 'Standby Vessel' notation with capacity for 150 survivors, complete with hospital facilities, WC's and showers etc.

Integrating this requirement into an autonomous vessel is something of a challenge, with a range of potential options regarding the philosophy of rescue operation:

1. Self-help option only, as a safe haven of last resort. Survivors board the vessel by themselves using automatically or remotely deployed scramble nets;
2. Automated mechanical retrieval of survivors or survival craft from the water;
3. Deployment of a rescue team to board the vessel, by FRC from another mothership in the field or by helicopter from land.

The vessel is designed to provide self-help recovery, with the option of crewed recovery using a rescue team.

2.2. Redundancy

With the role of the vessel defined, the question of how to assure safe operation and fulfilment of the role by an unmanned vessel was considered. It is easy to think at first that without crew on board, safety is less of a consideration; however this is not the case. The protection of other vessels and installations remain an important consideration, particularly in an oil field where there are considerable assets on the surface and subsea, damage to which could cause loss of life, capital loss and damage to the environment. In fact, without crew on a vessel to rectify any component failures, the question of designing safety into the vessel through redundancy of systems and criticality of components becomes more important in order to prevent an incident developing. To define the required level of redundancy, the potential failure modes need to be identified.

Major sources of potential failure were identified including but not limited to:

1. Fire in machinery or other spaces;
2. Flood caused by collision or otherwise;
3. Loss of sensor / positioning sensors or false sensor readings;
4. Loss of communications with remote control centre;
5. Mechanical / electrical failure of critical systems and / or components;
6. Piracy / hijack, either physically or by cyber-attack.

Many of these risks are the same as those identified on offshore support vessels (OSV) fitted with dynamic positioning systems, hence the implementation of DP systems on offshore vessels can be investigated for guidance in answering these questions and similar solutions implemented in terms of redundancy of systems.

In the event of a failure on a manned support vessel however, the crew remain on hand to identify and resolve the problem. The consequence of a failure is therefore somewhat different. On a manned vessel, the master is able to recognise a problem, move the vessel to a safe location and implement a solution.

An example of this is the Bibby Topaz incident of September 2012, where the vessel experienced a DP drive off situation. A fault in the DP system caused the loss of all connectivity to position reference systems and thrusters causing the vessel to drift off position by 240m. One of the saturation divers working on the seabed at the time was left stranded with his umbilical severed as a result of the accident. Fortunately, the crew of the vessel were able to rapidly resolve the situation, regaining manual control of the thrusters and rescuing the diver who was fortunate enough to survive (IMCA Safety Flash 02/2013).

In the case of an unmanned ship, what would the consequence of this type of failure have been? If a failure were to occur where the sensor systems provide the navigation system with an erroneous position, how would the vessel know it was in the wrong place or doing the wrong thing? If there was an electrical failure causing a loss of sensors and communications, how would the vessel know where it was or what to do?

Without crew to recognise the fault and take manual control, it is conceivable that an unmanned vessel could pose a major hazard to other shipping and installations. So how can the vessel be designed to ensure that the vessel fails into a safe position? The ship cannot be instructed to stay put or move position if it does not know where it is, as it may inadvertently sail or drift into another ship or installation. Nor can it drop anchor and wait for help in an oilfield, where there may be subsea pipelines, risers, wellheads etc.

Significant consideration of potential hazards and the possible mitigation will need to be undertaken, but ultimately there is not a fail-safe position for every eventuality. However, the same can be true of a manned vessel. The primary difference is that there is no-one on-board to repair a failure.

By designing sufficient redundancy into an autonomous vessel, it is possible to provide an equivalent level of safety as a manned vessel. It was therefore decided that the vessel should be generator-electric, with two independent engine rooms and propulsion rooms, akin to a DP3 or safe-return-to-port classed vessel, which would be safer in many respects than an existing standard DP2 OSV. Where possible passive components should be used to minimise risk of failure, for example a large battery bank can be utilised to provide power.

The autonomy related systems would need to have sufficient sensors, inputs and system monitoring capabilities to identify any failures in the system as a whole. An existing DP2 ship would have two DP systems for redundancy, with the master acting as a third arbiter of decisions, able to take manual control in the event of system-wide failure. The autonomy related systems on this vessel should therefore be triplicated, as would be the case on a DP3 vessel, such that voting can occur between systems to provide the same equivalence as a manned vessel.

In terms of other legislation, it was decided that the vessel should still comply with extant legislation for a manned vessel as far as practicable, such as international convention on load-lines and 2008 intact stability code, as the 'rescue' role will result in persons on board the vessel. There is also little perceived benefit in this instance of not complying with these rules. In the early years of introducing the technology it will be prudent to comply with applicable codes and legislation to aid the process for adoption.

2.3. Environment

QinetiQ consider that the environmental considerations for an autonomous vessel are no different than for a manned vessel. It should comply with MARPOL and Ballast Water Management legislation.

The greatest challenge in meeting MARPOL regulations will be detection of an oil leak and response to a spill. It is not possible to remotely detect a small amount of oil sheen on the surface; however it is possible to detect oil loss from the vessel. This technology is mature and in many cases has been proven to detect a leak more promptly than crew observations. For this reason, the design should incorporate as much mitigation against the possibility of an oil spill as is reasonably practicable.

For a vessel of this type, which requires enough power for 20 knots sprint speed and 96 hours of firefighting capability, a purely electric battery powered vessel is not economically feasible with today's technology, so the ship must be powered by fossil fuels. To reduce the risk of pollution, it was decided that the vessel would have clean design notation, to avoid fuel oil storage tanks against the vessel shell plating. Sensor systems can be utilised to detect any oil leaks into cofferdam and other spaces to alert the vessel to any leaks.

Use of oil is reduced by preference for electrical frequency controlled deck machinery over hydraulic, and retractable thrusters are avoided with preference for traditional tunnel thrusters. Oil/water interfaces are reduced by preference for fixed pitch propellers over controllable pitch for example.

Shaft lubrication oil/water interfaces can either be removed by use of water lubricated bearings, or protected by triple-seal arrangements with oil sensors in interstitial cofferdams to detect seal failure before oil breaches the outer seal.

With the above mitigations in place the risk of oil spill is significantly reduced, and any release of oil can be detected and identified by the vessel. The final remaining challenge is that of oil spill response, particularly in the case of a catastrophic failure or rupture of fuel oil tanks. It is not particularly feasible to fit the vessel with any form of automated containment boom or oil recovery equipment, so the only remaining options are to rely upon a mothership or other third party vessel to assist in the event an alarm is raised, or to have a response team deployed to the vessel by helicopter or another ship.

3. Design process

3.1 Selection of hull form

Selected hull forms were evaluated against a range of criteria and given weighted scores, Table 1.

Table 1: Hull form evaluation for autonomous fiifi ship

	Weighting	Scores		
		Monohull	Multi-hull	SWATH
Cost & ease of construction	7	3	2	1
Efficiency	6	3	1	2
Sprint speed	5	2	3	1
Station keeping	4	3	1	2
Endurance / deadweight	3	3	2	1
Sea-keeping	2	2	1	3
Stability	1	1	3	2
Final Score:		75	50	43

With a score of 75 points, the monohull is clearly the optimum solution for this vessel based upon the defined criteria. Principally, it was considered that the monohull would provide the most cost-effective solution. It was estimated that efficiency would be best for the monohull as it is likely to have the smallest windage area, resulting in the lowest power requirement for station-keeping which

will be the most common operational mode. Multi-hulled vessels would have more windage due to the need for a large wet-deck clearance in order to avoid slamming in higher sea states. For endurance, a reasonably high deadweight is required for fuel storage, for which a monohull would typically have a higher TPC immersion than a multi-hulled vessel.

3.2. Power generation

A full range of options were considered for means of power generation including full battery / solar electric, hydrogen fuel cells and fossil fuels. A purely electric solution with batteries and solar panels was considered but would not have sufficient capacity to meet the requirement for endurance, particularly for sprinting and firefighting. Similarly, hydrogen fuel cells would not have sufficient capacity and would also pose a fire / explosion risk if exposed to heat during firefighting operations. LNG power was also eliminated due to fire risk.

This leaves diesel engines or gas turbine generators, either of which could be suitably employed. Whilst gas turbines may theoretically be a better option for unmanned ships due to their simplicity, the level of development and commercial experience is some way behind diesel. Therefore diesel generators were selected as data is more readily available, and to illustrate that despite their higher maintenance requirements it is entirely feasible to utilise a diesel engine in an unmanned vessel, provided running hours and maintenance are adequately planned into the design and operational concept. Reduction in engine running hours can be achieved by inclusion of large battery banks and photovoltaic panel arrays in the design, sufficient for 12-24 h operation of low power requirements such as loitering or holding station in field. Thus the ship can operate on battery power for the majority of the time. When engines are running, they can be run at their optimum efficiency near full power, with excess power being used to charge the battery banks. The charging capability is supplemented with solar panels to extend battery usage periods.

3.3. Propulsion

For propulsion our intention once again was to take the approach of minimised maintenance and reduced risk of failure. The means of propulsion therefore has to be simple with few moving parts, leading us to select a traditional shafted arrangement with fixed pitch propellers over an azimuthing thruster arrangement commonly observed on offshore vessels. The relatively narrow beam of the vessel also restricted the ability to consider azimuthing thrusters due to potential thruster interaction. For dynamic positioning, the main propulsion is supplemented by tunnel thrusters at the bow and stern, once again with variable speed fixed pitch propellers.

3.4. Firefighting capability

The Fifi III notation provides a very clear definition of the requirements for the firefighting capability. For redundancy, the vessel is provided with four fire monitors of 2400m³/hr, each with individual motor driven pumps. Data from equipment suppliers indicated that each fire pump would have a requirement for approximately 1200kW electrical power, or 4800kW total power requirement.

3.5. Hull-form development

The hull-form was then developed using QinetiQ's Paramarine software and a functional building block approach to the design. The hull-form was developed with a wave-piercing bow in order to provide optimum performance in a larger sea-state, both in terms of economy in station-keeping and performance in sprint mode. In order to minimise wave-making resistance in sprint mode Froude Number would need to be below the resistance hump, which at 20 kn implies a length of approximately 80 m. Empirical data of similar vessels was studied to determine ranges of length / breadth and length / depth ratios.

With these basic parameters a parametric 3D model was created within Paramarine in which the principal particulars of the vessel could be altered to quickly evaluate stability and powering requirements to optimise the hull-form. Following this optimisation process, the final hull-form parameters were defined as follows:

L _{OA} :	80.0m
Beam:	12.0m
Depth:	7.0m
Draught:	4.6m
Displacement:	3100 tonne

3.6. Powering and machinery

Based upon this hull-form, a conservative powering estimate of 10MW was made including sea-margins. As the vessel is required to have redundant propulsion, it was decided that this would be provided with two 5MW shaft lines. Empirical data was analysed to derive a powering requirement for the bow thrusters, which when considered with the powering requirements of the firefighting system, provided a total installed power requirement for the vessel of approximately 12MW.

It was decided that power generation would be provided with four large generator sets of 2700kW each, plus two smaller auxiliary generator sets of 625kW, in order to meet the total powering requirement in an effective way, whilst providing substantial redundancy and operational flexibility.

To determine the required capacity for the battery bank, it was estimated that the vessel would require approximately 500 – 1,000 kW power for economical station keeping. In order to provide power for 12 - 24 h, the battery bank would therefore need a capacity of 12,000 kWh, which is feasible with today's battery technology. The inclusion of two battery banks in the design ensures the redundancy concept is maintained and reliability is increased through use of passive system components, thus ensuring the safety of the vessel.

By running each engine in turn to charge the batteries, a conservative estimate would see 1000kW utilised on vessel power leaving 1,500kW available to charge the battery bank. A full charge could be therefore be achieved in approximately 8 h providing 12 h operation on batteries. This equates to 216 running hours per engine for every 90 days of stand-by duty.

A typical vessel with 2 or 4 engines would be required to run at least two engines at all times to comply with DP2 requirements, so in the case of a vessel with four engines their running hours would be 1080 hours for an equivalent 90 day period. Therefore the battery bank philosophy, combined with the lower power requirements of a vessel without large accommodation loads, reduces engine running hours by 80% compared to a typical four engine vessel.

Depending upon the model of engine major overhauls are required after 12,000 to 24,000 h, which under this scenario would be in excess of 13 years, far beyond classification society five-year survey requirements. Even the most routine of maintenance requirements such as changing oil filters need only occur once every 200 hours, so by including a redundant selectable automated system to change over filters once or twice per 90 day period, the need for human attendance is removed.

3.7. General arrangement development

Throughout the design process, the emphasis remained on maintaining simplicity in design with respect to maintenance and operation. The final concept design, Figs. 2 and 3, presents a traditional monohull vessel, with a high degree of redundancy in systems and spaces to avoid failures, or minimise the consequences of failure during operation. Unmanned operation allows the removal of spaces required for human habitation, cabins and accommodation for example. This allows the accommodation superstructure of the vessel to be much smaller than a traditional manned vessel,

which will subsequently improve station keeping performance and economy through reduced windage area and reduced lightship weight of the vessel.

Fig.3: Concept design render

The fire monitors are positioned forward to provide the optimum position for firefighting duties whilst exposing the smallest aspect of the vessel to the heat of an installation fire. The mooring decks are also enclosed to provide protection from heat.

With a beam of 12m the vessel is too narrow for a full helideck, so a helicopter winch space is provided forward of the bridge, compliant with CAA CAP437 requirements, in order to land emergency maintenance teams or a rapid response rescue team in the event of an incident.

A small bridge is provided for manual operations or for pilotage in ports where perhaps an autonomous vessel is not permitted to berth in an unmanned mode. This bridge could also be used by a rescue team as an incident control room, with full 360° visibility.

Communications to shore would be conducted via VSAT for which three VSAT domes are provided for a triple redundant system. Two of these are located toward the aft end of the vessel to minimise risk of heat damage or smoke interference when firefighting from the bow.

The design is fully compliant with load-line and stability regulations for safety and ‘clean design’ notation for environmental protection.

Rescue zones are provided port and starboard, compliant with ‘rescue vessel’ notation, with markings on deck directing survivors to the safe haven area where seating and facilities are provided. An A-frame is provided on the transom for recovery of a lifeboat, up to approximately 100 persons, which could be manually operated by a deployed response team or developed for autonomous operation. Life rafts are provided at the aft end, either for survivors in the event of a secondary incident, or to deploy for use by survivors in the water.

Fig.4: Concept general arrangement

3.8. Finance

The design aims to balance the cost benefits gained from an unmanned ship with the additional cost of sensors and redundancy together with a shore side control centre (ideally controlling a number of unmanned / autonomous ships). Equipment on board has been selected to be as simple as possible not

only to minimise maintenance and failure rates, but also to minimise capital and operating cost. However it must be considered that the firefighting role necessarily puts the vessel at risk of damage, especially since there is no crew and is able to remain on station fighting a fire much longer than would be safe for a crewed vessel. Indeed the decision could be taken to keep the vessel conducting firefighting which could lead to destruction and loss of the vessel, balanced against the recovery of personnel from the incident or keeping the incident contained.

4. Conclusions

Whilst widespread use of fully autonomous ships may still be some time away, the naval architecture, marine engineering, and technological solutions to support autonomy are available now. This concept was developed to illustrate the possibilities for an autonomous vessel in a role ideally suited to use of autonomy, and to enable discussion of the considerations required for autonomous vessel design.

The design was intentionally kept reasonably traditional, partly to illustrate that autonomous technology can be utilized on a standard vessel and also to maintain focus on the autonomous aspect of the design. The primary consideration in the design was that of redundancy in order to ensure safe operation of the ship. This is essentially a development of existing dynamic positioning technology and philosophy of operation, ensuring that systems are sufficiently duplicated to diminish the consequence of any single system or component failure.

Integrating an autonomous vessel into existing regulatory frameworks also represents a challenge. Many regulatory requirements are prescriptive in nature and offer no scope for removal of the human, and as technology progresses these challenges will have to be addressed by the regulatory bodies. By adopting an approach of equivalence in the design by specifying duplication or triplication of systems, the risks associated with maritime operation and unmanned operation can be reduced, meeting the intent of regulation. Alternatively regulatory approaches which develop specific autonomy biased roles may be the way forward in the long term.

Implementation of autonomous technology will take time - it is unlikely that the maritime industry will take a giant leap en-masse to full autonomy in the near future. It will require a combination of approaches to prove the technology before mass adoption takes place. This 'proving' phase may happen on manned ships with partially un-manned bridge operation, or on smaller ships operated remotely or in limited areas of navigation with mothership oversight. In both cases, the concepts presented here will need to be implemented on new-build vessels as interest in autonomous technology increases, in order to facilitate the 'proving' of autonomous technology to often sceptical and risk averse owners, financiers and insurers.

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Energy Efficient Maritime Accommodations

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of a study on energy savings strategies in maritime accommodations. An offshore accommodation with a capacity of 37 persons on board is used as a case study. A base case model is built in dedicated software where yearly simulations are run using weather data from hot and cold environments. The relation between the number of person on board (POB) and the total yearly energy consumption (W) is given by the following equations for hot and cold environments:

$$W_{total, cold\ environment} = 0.013 \cdot POB^2 + 23.84 \cdot POB + 160.83$$

$$W_{total, hot\ environment} = 0.044 \cdot POB^2 + 18.32 \cdot POB + 93.04$$

Most energy is consumed by the HVAC system. A package of energy saving strategies is proposed and evaluated, leading to 32% yearly energy savings with a payback time of 2 years for newbuilds and 4 years for retrofits.

1. Introduction

The environment is one of the world's biggest concerns of the moment and sustainability is a widely spread theme in technical developments. Emissions can be reduced in two ways: reducing the amount of energy consumed or generating energy by using non-fossil energy sources. Many ways to reduce the energy consumption of buildings and houses have already been developed and show satisfying results. Buildings can be 'zero-energy' or can even produce more energy than they consume. An example is the 'Sun Ship' built in 2004 in Germany. This not only reduces CO₂ emissions but may also reduce costs. The design of offshore accommodations, however, is lagging behind in energy saving strategies compared to on-shore building technology.

Crew is needed in offshore environments such many as oil fields or offshore windfarms. These people can be transferred every day from the shore by either a ship or a helicopter. Another option is to accommodate the crew on the platform itself or a separate accommodation platform. The choice between these two options is determined by the time needed for the job and the distance from the working location to the shore. Since offshore fields are located farther and farther away from the shore, the demand for offshore accommodations is increasing, *O'Connel (2012)*. According to the 'World Offshore Accommodation Market Forecast 2015-2020' by *Douglas-Westwood (2016)*, the demand for offshore accommodation vessels will average almost 42,000 Personnel on board per year. This is an increase of 14% compared to the six-year period before. Since the capacity of the offshore accommodation fleet is increasing, savings in the energy consumption of accommodation units become more relevant. Also, low selling prices of oil are raising the need for cost saving innovations in offshore activities, *NN (2015)*.

Techniques to save energy used on-shore cannot be directly translated to offshore accommodations, because of environmental, compliance and operational differences. Costly downtime has to be avoided. Techniques therefore have to be reliable and low-maintenance. The offshore industry also is a volatile business dependent on the oil price. This leads to operators demanding short payback times. It is therefore necessary to keep the capital expenditures (CAPEX) moderate and the operational expenditures (OPEX) as low as possible. In the end, energy saving investments will only be made if they prove to be profitable.

Otheguy (2014) showed that energy savings up to 40-50% for a windfarm transformer substation in the North Sea are achievable at an extra upfront cost of approximately 9% of the total cost of the accommodation block. Energy saving strategies such as double insulation and LED lighting were evaluated separately. However, the effect of strategies might not be independent which leads to increased or decreased savings when strategies are combined. Therefore it is important to cover the problem with a whole-building approach to compare the various energy saving strategies. Since the cost savings and payback times are important, it is also valuable to be able to run yearly simulations in order to model the actual savings in a year.

The research question that is addressed in this paper is: Which strategies applied to a retrofit and a newbuild lead to savings in the costs of energy consumption by an offshore accommodation unit and what is their expected payback time? The goal of this paper is to supply ship owners with a profitable package of knowledge, energy saving strategies and their evaluation which can be applied to an existing accommodation or a newbuild.

To answer these questions, a computer model of the accommodation block is built in DesignBuilder. This software package is widely used in the on-shore building sector to run whole-building yearly simulations of energy consumption. With the base case model, the yearly energy consumption and its distribution over the consumer categories are determined for each geographical location and associated weather file. A parameter study is done to find the relation between the number of persons on board and the total yearly energy consumption of the accommodation. Five promising strategies are applied to the base case model to obtain yearly energy savings. Then an evaluation of the CAPEX and maintenance cost is made based on quotations and in-house knowledge of Keppel Verolme BV. In parallel, the cost of energy on board is modelled and estimated to calculate the payback time. Sensitivity studies show the effect of changes in relevant parameters. The savings and payback times are calculated for each energy-saving strategy individually and combined. Unless otherwise specified, all assumed values correspond to in-house know-how of Keppel Verolme BV. The payback time calculations are done for both retrofit and newbuild of accommodations, and for hot and cold environments. For this purpose, the Gulf of Mexico (GOM) and the Norwegian North Sea (NS) are used. These regions concentrate most of the existing offshore rigs worldwide, *NN (2016a)*.

This research focuses on the energy consumption of the accommodation unit (as part of a rig or a dedicated platform) from the ‘plug’. Further energy-saving measures or low-emission energy production by the generator sets or other systems on board the platform are possible but are not taken into consideration. The focus is on the energy flows in the accommodation unit. The base case model, which is used as a benchmark, is based on data from existing platforms built at Keppel Verolme BV. The accommodation unit has a capacity of 37 people and a floor area of 960 m². All equipment items considered for the energy saving strategies are off-the-shelf and commercially available products, designed for marine applications when possible.

2. Computer model

2.1. Case study

The input for the model includes construction data, activity data, heating ventilation and air-conditioning data and weather data. The main dimensions of the model are shown in Table 1. The base case model has all areas which are typical for offshore accommodations.

Table 1: Main dimensions of base case model

Length	20.00	m
Width	16.00	m
Deck height	2.90	m
Number of decks	3	
Total floor area	960	m ²

2.1.1. Construction data

Construction elements such as walls, panels and doors are based on technical specifications by an approved supplier. Important for the thermal calculations are the thermal resistance values (R-values) of the construction elements. These are shown in Table 2. Windows have a size of 550 by 750 mm. The total windows-to-wall ratio of the base case model is 4.16%. Lighting is modelled by an average power density of 16 W/m². This represents fluorescent lighting and is based on the lighting plans of existing accommodation units.

Table 2: R-values of construction elements

Construction element	R-value (m ² K/ W)
External wall	4.056
Internal wall	2.044
Floors	2.816
Roof	4.829
Internal doors	0.916
External doors	1.427
Windows	0.350

2.1.2. Activity data

The heat gain by lighting, people and equipment depends on the activity of the people on board. For this purpose, a working schedule is set up. The schedule has two groups of 15 crew members who work 8 hours a day with a 12-hour phase difference and eat three times a day. They also spend time in the recreational areas and cabins. The remaining crew is divided in two groups and is responsible for cooking and laundry. The power consumption and heat gain of equipment such as galley appliances and laundry machines is based on the specified load list.

Domestic hot water is the hot water which is used for showers and taps. For showers, a consumption rate of 9.5 l/min for 8 minutes per person per day is assumed. For taps, the consumption is based on 4.7 l per person per day. The mess has an additional consumption of 188 l/day. This is based on DesignBuilder standards and represents the washing of hands. The output temperature for showering and washing hands is set to 40 °C. This is achieved by mixing hot water from the boiler with cold water from the fresh water tank. The cold water from the tank is assumed to have a temperature of 10 °C in the North Sea and 15 °C in the Gulf of Mexico. The hot water is supplied by a boiler with a volume of 0.75 m³ and a heater capacity of 25 kW. The setpoint temperature of the boiler is 65 °C.

2.1.3. Heating, ventilation and air-conditioning

The heating, ventilation and air-conditioning system (HVAC) is modelled by three systems which are described in this section. The main system supplies the cabins, offices, circulation areas and recreational areas. This system is operated by an air handling unit (AHU) comprising a heater, cooler, humidifier and a fan. The conditioned air stream can then be adjusted to personal preferences using a reheater contained in the supply units in cabins, office areas, recreational spaces and mess. The AHU has an airflow rate of 13865 m³/h. The rest of the airflow is returned to the AHU, part of which is recirculated to obtain 40% of the supply air as recirculation. The supply air temperature of the AHU is set to 14 °C in the summer and 18 °C in the winter.

The second HVAC system supplies the galley. It contains a heater, cooler and a fan. The AHU has an airflow rate of 3000 m³/hour. The supply air temperature setpoint is set to 18 °C throughout the year.

The third HVAC system supplies the store areas and the HVAC rooms. It contains a heater, cooler and fan. The AHU has an airflow rate of 7000 m³/h. The supply air temperature is set to 15 °C throughout the year.

2.1.4. Weather data

DesignBuilder uses yearly weather data as part of the simulation of the annual energy consumption. This data contains temperatures (dry-bulb, wet-bulb and dew point), humidity levels, solar irradiance, wind speed and wind direction for a given geographical location. For this case study, weather data of two locations is used: the Norwegian North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico. A summary of the weather data is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Summary of hourly-average weather data of the North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico

		North Sea		Gulf of Mexico	
		Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter
Temperature (°C)	Min	2.5	-2.8	20.5	16.6
	Max	20.5	15.2	28.8	27.7
	Average	11.7	5.0	26.2	21.9
Relative humidity (%)	Min	47	40	49	50
	Max	98	101	90	97
	Average	81	80	65	73
Absolute humidity (kg/m ³)	Average	0.008	0.005	0.016	0.013

2.2. Cost breakdown of energy on board

The cost of energy on board is needed to convert the saved kWh into saved €. This is necessary to calculate the payback time. The cost of energy is divided in three parts: the cost of fuel, the cost of transport and the purchase and maintenance cost. For this case study, the electric power is generated by diesel generators sets (gensets). A 1800 kW rated electric power genset is chosen, commonly seen on board a range of platforms suitable for this project. All cost estimated in euro per kilowatt-hour are summed up to obtain the total cost of energy on board.

The cost of fuel depends on the specific fuel oil consumption (SFOC) of the genset and the bunker cost of marine diesel oil (MDO). The chosen genset has a typical SFOC of 186 g/kWh. The bunker price of MDO is based on the average MDO bunker index over the period June 2015 to June 2016 published online. This is €412 per metric ton, resulting in a fuel cost of €0.08 per kWh.

Fuel is purchased on a nearby coastal supply location and shipped to the platform in a supply vessel. A representative supply vessel sailing 300 km to a platform for divers supplies leads to a transport cost of €0.11 per kWh.

The purchase cost of the genset is based on quotations by selected suppliers for Keppel Verolme BV as per 2016, assuming a service life of 20 years. The maintenance cost are about 10% of the purchase price per year, assuming that the genset runs half of the time on full power. Combined, this results in a cost of purchase and maintenance of €0.01 per kWh

Summing up the components of the cost of energy on board as above lead to a total cost of €0.20 per kWh. However, this cost depends on volatile parameters such as the bunker price of MDO. If, instead of a 1-year average, the chosen data period would have been the last 20 years, the fuel price would have been 23% higher. For a period of the last 12 years, it goes up to +65%, while the last 5 years give +87%, *NN (2016c)*. This is estimated based on Ultra-Low-Sulfur No. 2 Diesel Fuel in Los Angeles, US, assuming MDO prices following same correlation along time. The SFOC depends on the load on the engine. The SFOC increases by 15% if the engine runs at 25% of its maximum continuous rating, *Klein Woud and Stapersma (2002)*. The cost of fuel would then increase from €0.08 to €0.09 per kWh. The purchase and maintenance cost depend on the lifetime of the engine. If the lifetime is reduced to 10 years, the purchase and maintenance cost would increase with 25%, however increasing the total cost only by €0.0036.

3. Base case results

3.1. Yearly energy consumption

The computer simulation with the base case model gives a detailed distribution of energy consumption on board across the largest categories, Table 4. Amongst these, the auxiliary equipment energy consumption contains all minor items, e.g. computers, power sockets, gym equipment, etc. Table 5 compares the average total energy consumption per day for the base case accommodation compared to on-shore hotels.

Table 4: Yearly energy consumption in the North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico in MWh and %

Consumer category	North Sea		Gulf of Mexico	
<i>Heating</i>	387	38%	32	4%
<i>Cooling</i>	24	2%	302	34%
<i>Humidification</i>	50	5%	0	0%
<i>Fans</i>	114	11%	114	13%
Total HVAC	576	57%	449	51%
Lighting	74	7%	74	8%
Laundry	74	7%	74	8%
Galley	159	16%	159	18%
Aux	79	8%	79	9%
DHW	52	5%	43	5%
Total	1013	100%	877	100%

Table 5: Energy consumption of offshore accommodation and on-shore hotels

Total average energy consumption per day	North Sea/ Gulf of Mexico	Hotels
kWh per m ²	2.89/ 2.50	0.55 to 1.10 ¹
kWh per person	75/ 65	46 to 68 ²

¹ For European hotels, *HES (2011)*

² Worldwide, *NN (2016b)*

The consumption rates for offshore accommodations are higher than those of hotels, even though some hotels in historical buildings may consume more energy than modern buildings. This has the following possible reasons:

- High number of air-changes-per-hour (elaborated upon in section 3.2)
- Fixed temperature settings of air handling unit (elaborated upon in section 3.2)
- 24/7 activity. Whereas in hotels and office buildings, most spaces are unoccupied during night time, in the offshore accommodation day and night shift cause the accommodation to be occupied and active 24 h/day.
- Occupant density. When comparing hotels to offshore accommodations, hotels have a lower occupant density. Hotel rooms are generally larger than cabins in offshore accommodations.

3.2. Heat balance

The biggest contributors to the total energy consumption are the HVAC systems. These systems have to compensate for the heat loss or gain in the accommodation. It is therefore interesting to see how this heat balance is distributed. Fig. 1 shows a schematic view of the sensible heat balance of the accommodation as modelled in DesignBuilder.

The HVAC system balances the results of the heat addition by people, lighting and equipment and heat transfer through the building's envelope (walls and windows). Heat transfer through the walls and windows is the sum of conducted heat transfer and heat gain by solar radiation. Table 6 shows the heat transfers over a week in the summer and winter in kWh for the North Sea and Gulf of Mexico.

Fig. 1: Heat gains and losses of accommodation

Table 6: Weekly heat gains and losses in kWh

	North Sea		Gulf of Mexico	
[kWh]	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
Windows	-176	71	96	238
Walls	-852	-324	-246	170
People	311	328	309	328
Lighting	1411	1411	1411	1411
Equipment	1913	1913	1913	1913
HVAC	-2607	-3399	-3484	-4059

The heat gain by lighting, people and equipment is constant. The heat transfer through the walls is negative as long as the inside temperature is higher than the outside temperature. The heat transfer through the windows in the summer in the North Sea and in the Gulf of Mexico is positive due to the solar penetration. Table 6 shows a net cooling effect by the HVAC system. The heat lost due to the exhausted air by the HVAC systems accounts for 93% of the heat loss compared to 7% due to heat transfer through the building's envelope. Fig. 2 shows a schematic view of the main HVAC system.

Fig. 2: Schematic view of main HVAC system

Although there is a net cooling requirement in the accommodation, the installation has an energy consumption for heating the outside air to the fixed temperatures of 14 °C and 18 °C. Also, the HVAC system in has an energy consumption for heating in the Gulf of Mexico because the cooled air of 14 °C needs to be reheated in order to maintain an interior average temperature of 20 °C.

The HVAC system has a constant air flow to maintain 6 fresh-air-changes-per-hour (ac/h). This causes high energy consumption for the HVAC system. A high amount of air needs to be conditioned to a temperature closer to the room temperature (20 °C). Offshore accommodations require an air exchange rate of 6 ac/h according to the ILO Maritime Labour Convention, 2006, *ABS (2014)*. This is relatively high compared to 0.5 – 3 ac/h, typical in on-shore buildings, *Beekers and Steemers (2000)*. Also in requirements for sea going vessels, one finds high air exchange rates up to 30 ac/h for example for cargo holds of livestock carriers, *GL (2014)*. Simulations with the model show that if the ac/h is reduced to 3, the energy consumption for the HVAC system is reduced by approximately 25%. This includes savings in fan power, and also in heating, cooling and humidification because less air needs to be conditioned. The airflow however is also used to condition the spaces. If the airflow is further reduced, the AHU is not able to maintain the temperature and humidity setpoints.

3.3. Energy consumption per person on board

This section discusses the relation between the energy consumption of the accommodation and the capacity, expressed in number of persons on board (POB). Each consumer category is analysed. The consumption for lighting and HVAC depend on the total floor area of the accommodation. A relation between the floor area and the number of POB is estimated based available data from 18 offshore accommodations. This leads to the relation given by Eq.(1), where A is the floor area of the accommodation and POB is the number of persons on board.

$$A = 21 \cdot \text{POB} + 233 \quad (1)$$

The lighting power density of the base case model is 16 W/m². The area-weighted average usage factor of lighting in the accommodation is calculated to be 0.66. The yearly power consumption of lighting can be calculated with Eq.(2). W_{lighting} is the yearly energy consumption of lighting in kWh.

$$W_{\text{lighting}} = 16 \cdot 0.66 \cdot (24 \cdot 365) \cdot A = 1943 \cdot \text{POB} + 21554 \quad (2)$$

The energy consumption for heating of water depends linearly on the number of persons on board. The energy consumption for DHW per person is calculated by the energy needed to heat water to the required temperature of 65 °C based on the following assumptions for showers and taps:

- Consumption rate 30989 l per person per year
- Temperature of water 40 °C
- Inlet temperature 10 °C in North Sea and 15 °C in Gulf of Mexico
- Outlet temperature 65 °C
- Specific heat of water 4.18 kJ/ Kg K
- Density of water (at 35 °C) 994 kg/m³
- Efficiency of boiler 90%

This results in the relation given by Eq.(3).

$$W_{\text{DHW}} = C_{\text{DHW}} \cdot \text{POB} \quad (3)$$

W_{DHW} is the yearly energy consumption for domestic hot water in kWh. C_{DHW} is the hot water consumption rate of 1202 kWh/person in the North Sea and 1093 kWh/person/year in the Gulf of Mexico.

The energy consumption for the galley, laundry and auxiliary are assumed to depend linearly on the number of POB. Data on these consumer categories of other platforms is not available. To get an estimate on the consumption rate, the energy consumption of the base case is divided by the number of POB in the base case accommodation (37). The consumption rates in MWh/person/year are as follows: galley 4.3, laundry 2.0 and auxiliary 2.2.

To gain insight in the relation between the consumption for HVAC and the floor area of the accommodation, a simplified version of the base case model is made in DesignBuilder. This model has the same dimensions per deck as the base case model. The HVAC system is the same system as the main system in the base case model. The total floor area is increased by increasing the number of decks. According to this model, the relation between the yearly energy consumption for HVAC and the number of POB is given by equation 4 for the North Sea and equation 5 for the Gulf of Mexico.

$$W_{\text{HVAC, North Sea}} = 3 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot A^2 + 0.57 \cdot A + 4.84 \quad (4)$$

$$W_{\text{HVAC, Gulf of Mexico}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot A^2 + 0.28 \cdot A + 0.82 \quad (5)$$

W_{HVAC} is the yearly energy consumption for HVAC in MWh. The energy consumption for heating, cooling and humidification increases linearly with the increase in size of the accommodation. When the size of the accommodation is increased, the airflow is increased to maintain the number of ac/h. The pressure drop is also increased to reflect the increase in ducting length. This combined leads to an

exponential increase in fan power with an increase in the size of the accommodation, assuming an increase in the AHU size but not in number of AHUs. In this model, the fan motor is placed in the air stream of the air handling unit. Waste heat of the fan motor is then released in the air stream. This decreases the heating load and increases the cooling load. The AHUs are mainly cooling in the Gulf of Mexico and heating in the North Sea. The increased heat gain due to the fan motors is, therefore, more disadvantageous in the Gulf of Mexico. Therefore, the total energy consumption for the Gulf of Mexico exceeds the energy consumption in the North Sea at 190 POB.

All the energy consumers are summed to obtain the relation between the total yearly energy consumption in MWh and the number of persons on board. This relation is shown in Fig.3 and given by Eq.(6) for the North Sea and Eq.(7) for the Gulf of Mexico.

$$W_{\text{total, North Sea}} = 0.013 \cdot \text{POB}^2 + 23.84 \cdot \text{POB} + 160.83 \quad (6)$$

$$W_{\text{total, Gulf of Mexico}} = 0.044 \cdot \text{POB}^2 + 18.32 \cdot \text{POB} + 93.04 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3: Yearly total energy consumption vs. persons on board

4. Assessment of energy saving strategies

There is a wide range of energy-saving strategies found in on-shore buildings. Of these, five promising ones have been selected according to their potential in marine and offshore applications: an enthalpy wheel, LED lighting and occupancy sensors, a drain water heat recovery system, demand controlled ventilation and a water sourced heat pump. These strategies are applied to the base case model and the yearly energy savings are calculated. The payback time is calculated by dividing the extra capital expenditures (CAPEX) by the savings in operational expenditures (OPEX). The extra CAPEX are the sum of the purchase price and the cost of installation. These are based on quotations by suppliers and in-house knowledge of Keppel Verolme BV. The savings in OPEX are determined by the savings in energy consumption minus the increased cost of maintenance. The savings are obtained by multiplying the saved MWh by the cost of energy. For this section, a cost of energy of €0.20 per kWh is used.

4.1. Enthalpy wheel

An enthalpy wheel is used to recover heat and humidity from the exhaust air flow. It is a rotating wheel consisting of a matrix structured heat and moisture transporting material. The wheel is placed half in the incoming and half in the outgoing airflow which have to be adjacent. Warm exhaust air heats the wheel. The wheel rotates and then preheats the incoming air flow. The same principle

applies to precooling and humidifying the air streams.

An enthalpy wheel is applied to the main air handling unit in the base case model. The efficiency of the enthalpy wheel is based on data obtained from suppliers and is about 58% for sensible and latent heat recovery. The wheel also causes a pressure drop 113 Pa, which is manually input in the software. The enthalpy wheel is installed after the recirculation. If an enthalpy wheel is installed, further savings can be obtained by switching off recirculation. The number of fresh ac/h is kept at 6. However, because there is no recirculation, the airflow now contains 100% fresh air. Therefore, the total airflow can be reduced, leading to savings in fan power.

Installing an enthalpy wheel leads to savings in the HVAC energy consumption of 19% in the North Sea and 3% in the Gulf of Mexico. The temperature difference between the inside and outside air is bigger in the North Sea, which causes higher savings. Besides that, savings in the energy consumption for humidification are also obtained in the North Sea which is not the case in the Gulf of Mexico since the outside air contains already enough humidity. When recirculation is switched off, savings in the HVAC energy consumption of 24% in the North Sea and 28% in the Gulf of Mexico are obtained. A reduced airflow reduced the amount of air which is overcooled, which is mainly relevant in the Gulf of Mexico.

The investment cost for installing an enthalpy wheel in a newbuild accommodation is relatively low. However, installing an enthalpy wheel in an existing platform might not be feasible because the air handling unit must be replaced and there might be no space available. The high savings and low investment cost lead to a payback time of about 3 months for installing an enthalpy wheel and switching off recirculation.

4.2. LED lighting and occupancy sensors

The LED lighting is modelled in the software using its normalised power density, corresponding with the technical specifications from the supplier. The occupancy sensors are modelled by setting the schedules for lighting according to the occupancy schedules for the corresponding zones. This is done for all zones except the circulation areas, where lighting is assumed to work 24/7. LED lighting and occupancy sensors combined lead to 68% energy savings on lighting power. These savings lead however to an increased in heating usage, because all the lighting power is eventually dissipated as heat. Hence, lower power needed for the same light also means lower heat gain from lighting. This leads to extra energy consumption by the HVAC system of 3% in the North Sea and 2% in the Gulf of Mexico.

The purchase cost of LED lights are about 1.5 times as much as fluorescent lighting according quotations for Keppel Verolme BV as per 2016. No extra installation costs are involved if LED lighting is installed in a newbuild. In case of retrofitting, all lighting fixtures need to be replaced, increasing the investment cost. LEDs are more expensive than fluorescent lights; however, LEDs have a longer life span. This leads to savings in the cost of maintenance. The payback time for newbuild is 3 years in both North Sea and Gulf of Mexico, while retrofitting brings it up to 9 years in the North Sea and 7 years in the Gulf of Mexico.

4.3. Drain water heat recovery

The drain water from showers contains a significant amount of heat which can be recovered with a drain water heat recovery (DHW) system. This system brings the still hot drain water through a pipe system adjacent to the incoming flow. Heat is there transferred and preheats the incoming cold water flow.

The savings by a DWHR system are modelled by hand calculations. It is assumed that 76 litre of shower water is used per person per day. The drain water is assumed to have a temperature of 37 °C. The cold water flow has a temperature of 10 °C in the North Sea and 15°C in the Gulf of Mexico. The specific enthalpy difference between the drain water and the cold water is used to calculate the

amount of heat that is theoretically available. According the supplier, 35% of this heat can be recovered. This results in 24% savings in the energy consumption of the boiler in both the North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico.

The installation cost for retrofits will be high because wall panels need to be removed and extensive adjustments have to be made in confined spaces. The results show a payback time for newbuild of 7 years in the North Sea and 9 years in the Gulf of Mexico. The payback time for retrofit will be 21 years in the North Sea and 26 years in the Gulf of Mexico.

4.4. Demand controlled ventilation

As stated in section 2, the AHUs have a fixed airflow rate and fixed temperature settings. Air is overcooled and reheated to adjust the temperature of the spaces to personal preferences. With demand controlled ventilation, the temperature setpoints and/or the airflow rates of the air handling units are determined by the actual demand of the controlled spaces.

Demand controlled ventilation is modelled by setting the supply air temperature to an average of the demanded temperature in the conditioned spaces at any time. The airflow is kept constant. The results show savings in the energy consumption for HVAC of 11% in the North Sea and 48% in the Gulf of Mexico. The main benefit of demand controlled ventilation is the prevention of overcooling. This happens mostly in the Gulf of Mexico. Besides that, there is an increase in energy consumption for humidification in the North Sea. In the model, the humidity is controlled by a minimum relative humidity of the supply air. With demand controlled ventilation, the temperature of the supply air is higher, which means a higher absolute humidity for a constant relative humidity.

Temperature sensors and a system network need to be installed to feed the temperatures in the spaces back to the AHU. The installation cost on retrofits will be higher than for newbuilds. The results show a payback time for newbuild of 1.1 years in the North Sea and 0.3 years in the Gulf of Mexico. The payback time for retrofit will be 1.8 years in the North Sea and 0.5 years in the Gulf of Mexico.

4.5. Water sourced heat pump

A heat pump transfers heat from a source to a sink with a refrigerant liquid. This principle is also used in, for example, refrigerators. For this application, heat is extracted from sea water and used for heating in the AHU and heating of domestic hot water. The process is reversible and can therefore also be used for cooling.

The savings of a water sourced heat pump are modelled by hand calculations based on information from suppliers by Keppel Verolme BV as per 2016. Two heat pumps are required to fulfil the heating and cooling load in the main AHU and the hot water boiler. The possible savings are calculated per month by the supplier based on monthly sea water temperatures in the North Sea. These savings in percentages are applied to the energy consumption per month for heating and cooling of the main air handling unit and the hot water boiler. For the Gulf of Mexico, an average saving of 70% is applied.

The purchase price of the heat pumps is dominant in the total investment cost. The difference in installation cost for newbuild and retrofit will therefore not make a remarkable difference in the payback times. For newbuild, the results show a payback time of 2.2 years in the North Sea and 2.4 years in the Gulf of Mexico. For retrofit, the results show a payback time of 2.5 years in the North Sea and 2.7 years in the Gulf of Mexico.

4.6. All strategies combined

If all strategies are combined, the results show savings on the total energy consumption of 28% in the North Sea and 34% in the Gulf of Mexico. This is less than if all savings by the individual strategies would be combined. Firstly, if LEDs are installed, the supply air temperature of the AHU has to be

increased due to a decreased heat gain by lighting. This results in a higher humidification need as explained in section 5.4. Secondly, the enthalpy wheel, demand controlled ventilation and the heat pump lead to savings that are a percentage of the base case consumption. If the strategies are combined, the absolute savings for each energy-saving strategy considered are, therefore, lower. Table 7 shows a summary of the savings in % of the total energy consumption and the payback times for each strategy individual and for all strategies combined.

Compared to the newbuild price of a typical offshore accommodation unit based on existing platforms built at Keppel Verolme BV, the total extra CAPEX for all strategies combined correspond to +4% for newbuild and +7% for retrofit. This represents the extra upfront cost of implementing these strategies. All strategies combined have a payback time of 2 years for newbuilds and 4 years for retrofits.

Table 7: Summary of the savings in % of the total energy consumption and payback times in years

	Newbuild		Retrofit	
	North Sea	Gulf of Mexico	North Sea	Gulf of Mexico
LED lighting and occupancy sensor	3%/ 3	5%/ 3	3%/ 9	5%/ 7
Enthalpy wheel, excl. recirculation	14%/ 0.2	14%/ 0.2	14%/ 0.3	14%/ 0.3
Drain water heat recovery	1%/ 7	1%/ 9	1%/ 21	1%/ 26
Demand controlled ventilation	6%/ 1	25%/ 0.3	6%/ 2	25%/ 0.5
Water sourced heat pump	18%/ 2	17%/ 2	18%/ 2	17%/ 3
All strategies combined	29%/ 2	34%/ 2	29%/ 4	34%/ 4

5. Conclusion

A model of a maritime accommodation is made with DesignBuilder based on data from existing platforms built at Keppel Verolme BV. Yearly simulations are done with hourly weather data from the Norwegian North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico. The case study has a capacity of 37 persons on board and a floor area of 960 m² equally divided over three decks. The results of the simulations showed yearly energy consumptions per person of 27 MWh in the North Sea and 24 MWh in the Gulf of Mexico.

The heating, ventilation and air-conditioning (HVAC) installation is the biggest contributor to the total energy consumption. An analysis of the heat balance, excluding the HVAC systems, showed to that there is a net cooling demand in the accommodation throughout the year in both hot and cold environments. The high energy consumption of the HVAC system is caused by the fixed temperature setpoints of the air handling unit and the high airflow rate. A model has been developed relating the total yearly energy consumption with the number of persons on board.

The cost of energy on board a typical offshore platform has been modelled and calculated to be €0.20 per kWh, including cost of fuel, transport of fuel and purchase and maintenance of the generators sets. Five most promising energy saving strategies are applied to the base case model to simulate the yearly savings and payback times, both for newbuild and retrofit and in the North Sea and Gulf of Mexico.

Based on calculations on the base case model, a combined package of energy saving strategies leads to 29% savings in cold environments (the Norwegian North Sea) and 34% in hot environments (Gulf of Mexico). This package contains an enthalpy wheel, LED lighting and occupancy sensors, a drain water heat recovery system, demand controlled ventilation and a water sourced heat pump. This leads to a payback time of 2 years for newbuild and 4 years for retrofit. Compared to the newbuild price of a typical offshore accommodation unit based on existing platforms built at Keppel Verolme BV, the total extra CAPEX for all strategies combined correspond to +4% for newbuild and +7% for retrofit.

This represents the extra upfront cost of implementing these strategies. Based on the results, it is recommended in general to install an enthalpy wheel (for retrofit, only in case it is technically feasible), a demand controlled ventilation system and a water sourced heat pump. LED lighting and a drain water heat recovery system are only recommended for newbuild due to extra retrofitting costs.

For further research it is recommended to assess additional savings such as discrete savings coming from down-sizing equipment as a result of less power needed. Also, it is recommended to assess in detail the reasons behind the requirement of six fresh air changes per hour, as this is driving up the HVAC energy use. Additionally, energy recovery across on board processes, as well as the feasibility of generating energy from sustainable sources, e.g. solar, wind or wave energy.

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The Internet of Things for Smarter, Safer, Connected Ships

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Abstract

A lot of sensors, devices, and equipment systems on Ships have always collected data. The difference now is that advances in technology, and in particular connectivity as well as cloud and big data, will put ship intelligence at the forefront of the next major transition for the shipping industry. From ship design, to supply chain to support services and environmental solutions, analytics are allowing vessel owners to connect data sources and analyze data that previously resided in separate silos. Operational Technology (the bespoke systems that manage the ship) is now able to converge with Information Technology, specifically big data and analytics. This convergence is providing valuable business insights and helping maritime customers reduce costs and improve vessel efficiency and safety. This paper presents different approaches to managing data, and gives an overview of Internet of Things (IoT) developments in other industries that could easily be applied to the maritime industry. It describes many of Dell's technologies that will be part of the intelligent ships of tomorrow.

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) has captured the attention of organizations because of the profound insights that it can provide. In the past, computers—and, therefore, the Internet—were almost wholly dependent on human beings to input information. However, sensor technology has enabled computers to observe, identify and understand the world—without the limitations of human-entered data. And so at its core, the concept of the Internet of Things, first coined in 1999 by Kevin Ashton of Proctor & Gamble, is simple: it is about connecting devices over the internet, allowing them talk to us, applications, and to each other.

We live in an increasingly connected world. Today, there are about 8 billion connected devices. This is predicted to rise to 26 billion by 2020. From monitoring diesel engines for marine power generation applications to tracking the navigation path of ships at sea, sensors coupled with analytics and data visualization tools can help companies get much more out of their physical assets – improving the performance of machines, extending their lives, and learning how they could be redesigned to do even more. Many companies are already starting to challenge existing business models to create smart, innovative ways of providing new services, managing assets and developing new products.

A recent McKinsey report estimates the potential economic impact – including consumer surplus – of as much as \$11.1 trillion per year in 2025 for IoT applications in nine settings, namely: home, office, factories, worksites, retail, cities, vehicles and the outdoors. Our conclusion: the potential for the maritime industry is hugely significant as ships belong to all of these categories. .

2. Managing Data: Different Approaches

The next logical question is what data can be collected, what data should be collected, how long should the data be retained, and what data should be analyzed and where? There are many different approaches to managing IoT data based on your business objectives and the technical challenges. Organizations are using centralized cloud and data center environments in certain situations to support IoT based analytics. This centralized data integration approach is especially important in analyzing disparate data sources and when real time and speed are not priorities. However, there are other situations where IoT data needs to be analyzed in near real time in order to ensure rapid execution and effect change. For example, real-time analysis of sensor data on a manufacturing system can detect too much moisture or too high a temperature. This situation will require immediate action to prevent

failure. Achieving this type of rapid response creates a new set of requirements in areas such as storage, security, data management and bandwidth. Without an infrastructure that supports this type of real-time action, many companies are not realizing the full potential of IoT data.

One of the ways organizations are beginning to gain more insight and value from IoT data is by architecting for analytics at the “edges” of their environments. This architecture requires that analytics be embedded both directly within endpoints such as sensors, controllers, equipment, and machines, and in nearby aggregation locations such as on the ship’s deck, in its engine control rooms, in data closets and ceilings. Collecting and analyzing data close to the endpoints means that action can take place locally in real or near-real time. In this way, only meaningful information needs to be backhauled to the datacenter or cloud for storage, benchmarking or advanced statistical analysis.

3. Managing and Executing Analytics on Sensor Data from a Centralized Location

There are many complexities involved in gaining the type of insights that businesses increasingly require from their IoT data. To be successful, organizations need to have the right foundation in place. These organizations need to make it a priority to evaluate the potential challenges of executing analytics on IoT data from a centralized environment. Some of the challenges are caused by the nature of the data itself and the physical environment where the data resides. Other challenges are related to how to protect highly sensitive data.

In addition, companies need to be mindful of issues related to latency, and the overall complexity of the environment. The challenges are based on four imperatives:

- **IoT infrastructure is highly fragmented**
An IoT environment is typically comprised of a myriad of sensors and devices communicating over non-standard protocols that are difficult to integrate and manage. This is especially the case in commercial and industrial environments where organizations need to integrate legacy equipment. Additionally, wireless mesh sensors are often capable of running for years on a single battery by requiring small amounts of power and not connecting directly to the Internet.
- **Latency and inconsistent connectivity can be inhibitors**
IoT solutions often require rapid data insights and control responses. Typically, you cannot achieve the required speed if latency is introduced from sending data and application calls between remote devices and centralized systems. For example, there are many use cases where inconsistent wide area connectivity can make centralized analytics impractical. Depending on the use case, a large organization could have hundreds to millions of sensors constantly going on and offline.
- **Data movement and storage can be costly**
Billions of devices, sensors and networks are connected to the Internet and create and receive data around the clock. This generates tremendous amounts of data that must be transferred to a location for storage and analysis. As the number of devices expands and the volume of data increases, the costs of data transport and data storage can quickly become prohibitive.
- **Connecting infrastructure and devices can introduce security risks**
Security is paramount to any data-driven solution. Traditionally, IoT solutions have been designed to be closed-loop networks that have no exposure to the Internet. While isolation is certainly a way to avoid risk, it also prevents the system from taking advantage of the value of external data feeds and tapping into even more powerful remote processing to supplement local analytics capabilities. In addition, many connected devices that collect and transfer data to a centralized repository lack the capability to deploy sophisticated security controls and safeguards. Further, if every single IoT device were linked across the Internet to a centralized cloud, it would expose an incredibly large attack surface for hackers to gain access to critical data and applications. Even more troubling, this centralized approach can potentially send malicious control commands back to the devices. One effective solution is to consolidate mul-

multiple sensor connections into a secure aggregation point behind a firewall. Centralizing data behind the firewall helps reduce the overall attack surface.

4. Managing and Executing Analytics on Sensor Data Using Edge Computing

A new generation of devices – the intelligent edge gateway – is providing enterprises with the option of performing critical data analytics close to endpoints at the edge of the network. In addition to unifying fragmented sensor data, an intelligent edge gateway has the processing capacity to perform additional analytics in real or near-real time to make data-driven decisions as close to the data generation as possible. Performing analytics on the gateways helps reduce network bandwidth cost because only meaningful information needs to be sent to the next tier, whether it is another gateway, the data-center, or cloud. In contrast, analytics in the datacenter or cloud is often focused on larger data sets and performed in batches. Distributed IoT architectures that include intelligent gateways help balance the overall system and reduce the big data burden on the datacenter and cloud.

Fig. 1: Using Intelligent Edge Gateways to Solve Industry Specific Challenges

As Fig. 1 shows, an IoT analytic system can be broken up into four key elements:

- **Data sources**
The system can consist of a variety of endpoints that gather and transmit data. The data sources can be discrete endpoints such as sensors, machines, energy producers, medical devices or even security cameras. In addition, the data sources can be entities that aggregate many endpoints, for example a building, factory, or vehicle. The data coming from these endpoints is often transmitted in a variety of protocols including DNP3, LAN, ZigBee and SCADA.
- **Edge aggregation and analytics**
Depending on the use case, the data sources may be set up to feed data directly into an edge aggregation and analytics device or directly to the cloud. In the case of an intelligent gateway, some data can be processed with local analytic software in real or near-real time to generate data-driven actions and insights. Additionally, data may simply be passed through to the next tier such as another gateway, datacenter or cloud. In the framework presented in Fig. 1, several gateways have been deployed. Some of the gateways have a single endpoint feeding it data while one of the gateways has several endpoints streaming data to it in a variety of protocols. Consider an intelligent gateway inside of a ship's HVAC unit that collects hundreds of data points a second. The organization's central monitoring station may require only a few key points be sent every day. Meanwhile, the gateway can be used to analyze every piece of col-

lected data in real time in order to optimize performance or sense an impending failure. The gateway can then trigger events to alert repair crews or safely shut itself down. Once in the centralized system, the subset of data from the HVAC unit can be used for batch analytics and longer-term energy efficiency planning. Transferring only the most important information greatly reduces the amount of data sent across the network while still providing insights and business value to the end user.

- Storage and analytics

Sensor data sent to the datacenter or cloud can be stored and further analyzed for benchmarking, predictive analytics, and other long-term planning. In Fig. 1 some of the data is transmitted from the gateways to the cloud via a wireless wide area network while other gateways transmit data to a datacenter. Data scientists can run advanced analytic algorithms against the data to gain new insights and fine-tune the analytics performed on the edge device.

- Data insights

The final element in an IoT system is the ability for customers and employees to gain insight from the data. To gain deeper contextual insight, IoT data can be blended with internal and third-party data sources. For example, IoT data can be integrated with CRM or ERP system data, as well as social media or weather data. In addition, organizations can provide rich analytic-based applications for customers to view and interact with their data.

5. The Benefits of Bringing Analytics to the Edge

Intelligent, purpose-built gateways are valuable tools to offset many of the cost and performance issues associated with running all analytics in a centralized location. For system integrators and OEMs, these gateways provide a flexible platform to develop analytics solutions that make big data more manageable, increase efficiency, maintain operations, and improve scalability. In this section we highlight some of the reasons why organizations are considering intelligent gateways as part of a distributed IoT architecture.

- Better efficiency and ‘less-big’ data

Intelligent gateways can help organizations filter data close to the point of inception through real or near-real time analytics such as stream or Complex Event Processing (CEP). Only the most meaningful and pre-processed data and events are sent to a centralized data-hub. The ability to filter out noncritical data and only transfer the most important data to centralized data centers is a key capability of gateways and reduces the consumption of network bandwidth. The pre-filtering of data is especially critical in use cases such as smart city, fleet and remote applications where cellular is a common communication choice.

- Self-sufficiency

Intelligent gateways are capable of bi-directional data flow in terms of aggregating new sensor data and pushing back control to connected actuators and equipment. With local intelligence, an edge gateway can execute either pre-programmed or dynamic control instructions based on analytics, autonomously from the backend. The ability to store data locally avoids the potentially catastrophic problems caused if an Internet connection is lost.

- Improved security

The processing power of an intelligent gateway can help secure IoT solution because the gateway has the processing capacity to encrypt data from less capable connected devices and sensors. The increased processing power allows the gateway to run local stream analytics that can search for behavioral anomalies. Security measures can be built into the gateway solution to ensure that only trustworthy devices are allowed to connect. Gateways also aggregate data streams from otherwise cloud-connected devices, thus reducing the overall attack surface between the enterprise firewall and the cloud for hackers to exploit.

- Highly adaptable to vertical use cases and industries

Compared to legacy controllers and appliance-like routers, intelligent gateways can run modern operating systems and are designed to be highly extensible through new applications. The gateway’s operating system and flexibility allows partners and customers to develop and de-

ploy purpose-built applications that meet specific industry and use-case requirements. Examples of edge analytics solutions that have been implemented or are currently underway include energy management within buildings, predictive maintenance for industrial equipment, video analytics for quality control, tracking for critical shipments using wireless mesh sensors and intelligence within vehicles for reducing fuel consumption and breakdowns.

- Leverages existing assets
Even if existing assets and systems were not originally designed to connect to the Internet and share data, data can still be collected from these previously untapped resources by attaching intelligent gateways.

Fig 2: The Dell Edge Gateway 5000 can be mounted on the wall and operate in extreme temperatures

6. IoT Implementations in Other Industries

Intelligent edge gateways provide a robust development platform for partners and customers to create industry and use-case-specific analytical solutions. Here are just some examples from other industries where there is a corresponding or similar application potential for maritime.

6.1. Mines and Datacenters

ELM Energy is a solution provider that monitors and manages power to critical work sites such as mines and datacenters. One of ELM Energy's clients is a mining company that operates an off-the-grid mine. The mine has a number of electrical sources, including solar, battery and generator. The challenge for the mine was that it needed a way to manage the power sources in real time so that the most efficient source could be utilized while at the same time never losing power. The need for real-time analytics and the fact that the mine is located in an off-the-grid location made an on-site solution mandatory.

ELM Energy deployed its software solution called FieldSight that runs on a Dell intelligent gateway. The solution monitors the mine's energy requirements and the output from energy sources and then changes the energy source as needed in real time. For example, as solar power decreases the organization needs the system to be able to monitor and either pull energy from battery storage or increase generator output. In addition to performing local analytics on the gateway, the gateway transfers pre-processed data to a cloud-hosted version of its FieldSight software. Once the data is transferred to the cloud, further benchmarking and advanced analytics can take place. In addition, the maintenance of the gateway can be performed remotely.

This is especially important for ELM Energy because the company often works with clients that have isolated sites. With its solution, customers are able to run reports, perform further analytics, and view the data via ELM's Software as a Service (SaaS) application. By implementing Dell's intelligent edge gateway in its IoT strategy, ELM Energy is able to make automated, real-time energy decisions on client sites while at the same time, transfer the most meaningful data to its cloud for even deeper analytics.

6.2. Facilities Management

Dell is currently working with a customer to develop a bespoke solution for a large facilities management customer, responsible for 2,000 buildings. In this instance, the customer has to proactively send an engineer to the boiler room in each facility every two to three weeks to check for leaks and monitor carbon monoxide levels. As you can imagine, the cost overhead is considerable, particularly as most visits do not discover any problem. Of course, there is also the potential that an incident may go undetected for some weeks in between visits.

As part of a proof of concept, the customer has installed a Dell Gateway with 3G card and connected sensors in a number of the boiler rooms. The sensors message information back to the Gateway, which in turn communicates in real-time to the control center. Motion sensors on the door detect unauthorized access; others monitor carbon monoxide, humidity and temperature levels while another device detects any leakages. The net result? Engineers are only called out when required, leading to huge efficiencies and cost savings. It is not difficult to imagine similar benefits being replicated on board the ship.

Looking specifically at the transport/vehicle market, according to McKinsey, Air China is installing a system that will download performance data from aircraft to ground-based systems in real time. The goal is to improve maintenance effectiveness, reduce downtime and the cost of routine maintenance, and lengthen the useful life of equipment. McKinsey estimates that condition-based maintenance in airplanes could reduce maintenance spending by 10 to 40 percent for air carriers by shifting from rules-based maintenance routines to predictive maintenance based on actual need, which is made possible by connected sensors and real-time monitoring. The new maintenance regime could also reduce delays due to mechanical issues by 25 percent and cut the instances in which equipment must be replaced by 3 to 5 percent. Again, this scenario has the potential to be applied to the maritime industry.

7. Specific Challenges & Opportunities within the Maritime Industry

It is important to recognize that a ship is not just a floating city made of steel. The number one priority has always to be the safety of the people onboard. Vessels also require a great deal of ongoing maintenance, for example excess vibrations can cause a ship to be removed from service.

The crew needs to be on high alert, prepared for mechanical mishaps, fires, open-sea rescues, and extreme weather of all kinds. From an IoT infrastructure perspective, one cannot always assume access to “a cloud” when navigating on the high seas. The conveniences of unlimited bandwidth and “always on” connectivity to the computers and devices industry takes for granted shore-side is not a given. As Fig. 3 illustrates, siloes of connected systems that exist in isolation do not make a ship smarter; systems have to inter-connect and scale not only within the ship but also to the terminal, shore, and HQ office.

Fig 3: The Connected Ship

Dell believes that the Internet of Things has transformative potential for the maritime industry. Businesses that adopt IoT systems can improve operations and gather greater insights for data-driven decision-making. As the graphic below illustrates, we believe that the biggest opportunities are through connected devices, smart asset management and remote monitoring. Areas with the highest potential include:

- Intelligent data analytics and virtual reality for remote maintenance service via the Internet or to dispatch replacement parts before a failure occurs.
- Alarm monitoring and remote asset management in the control room
- ECDIS systems to provide routing based on traffic, port, safety information and weather conditions
- Energy distribution and usage in engine rooms and HVAC systems for improved energy management
- People-counting analytics to enable rescue teams to be deployed quickly in an emergency
- Purchasing and operational software to be linked to backend databases to manage operational logistics for all job roles onboard like a change in port of call
- Video surveillance and security systems, point of sales and card reader technology for onboard purchases, entertainment systems for passengers, email and telephone service for crew wellness.

When we discuss with shipping leaders ways to capitalize on the Internet of Things, their five key focus areas are: energy efficiency (route optimization, speed control; predictive maintenance through collection and analysis of data from onboard systems; emission control and reporting; crew welfare and ship to shore links with ports and terminal authorities on documentation and reporting.

Additionally, experts say that connected navigation has the potential to generate significant savings across different modes of transportation and sectors of the economy. McKinsey estimate that raising average ship speeds using IoT technology could reduce transportation costs by 11 to 13 percent, which could have an economic impact of \$4.5 billion to \$9.3 billion per year in 2025.

Fig 4: The potential of the Internet of Things onboard ships

8. Conclusion

The need for more analytics, control and greater insight on IoT systems cannot be met by just connecting more sensors, endpoints and other devices to the Internet. It is imperative to take a holistic approach to creating an environment that provides a scalable, predictable, secure, and manageable solution. This engineered approach to IoT allows customers to be able to control costs by leveraging the most effective way to manage data movement, compute and storage. By creating a platform that

supports change and growth, IoT environments can become a way to protect company assets and enable new business opportunities.

As enterprises increase their investments in the Internet of Things, intelligent gateways can play a significant role in keeping the balance between expansion and security. Intelligent gateways enable organizations to securely connect and process data at the place where it makes the most sense. Many of these IoT gateways must operate in harsh conditions where traditional devices such as PCs, routers and servers would be ineffective. Pushing analytics to the edge of the network with intelligent gateways for IoT data is also helping organizations make real-time decisions close to the data and reduce data storage and transfer challenges by focusing on the most meaningful data.

Dell believes that these innovations present a true advantage and are game-changers for the marine equipment supply chain: helping customers to integrate operations, reduce production costs, improve safety, and effectively manage changes in technology to meet global distribution and service needs. Processing power combined with the Internet of Things and data analytics onboard vessels will revolutionize the maritime industry, making it easier for shipping, ship management, transportation, and logistics companies to transport goods from point A to point B.

It is important to point out that even today where organizations are capturing data; it is mostly used for anomaly detection and control, not optimization and prediction, which provides the greatest value. According to the McKinsey report, only 1 percent of data from an oil rig with 30,000 sensors is examined. The net conclusion is that a great deal of additional value – even from organizations currently leveraging the Internet of things - remains to be captured.

The key take-away is that businesses that fail to invest in capabilities, culture and processes as well as new technologies are likely to fall behind competitors that do.

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Concept Design of Rudders Using Pneumatic Artificial Muscles

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Abstract

The paper describes two unconventional solutions proposed for rudders actuation, based on the use of Pneumatic Artificial Muscles (PAMs), designed for boats 15-24 m length. In the first prototype muscles are arranged on board, orthogonally with respect to the rudder axis. The second one experiments a mounting with muscles integrated in the rudder blade and arranged parallel to the rudder axis. The motion is managed by miniaturized servo-pneumatic valves; control solutions can be realized using customized panels running on PC, able to acquire position and pressure signals from muscles and drive the valves by means of integrated PID controls.

1. Introduction

Here are proposed different and innovative mounting solutions in order to take advantages of the characteristics of the pneumatic systems and to be able to compare it with conventional steering. This comparison allows the identification of the range of applicability of these actuators. The possibility to obtain, with fluidic muscles, the same torque as that of the conventional drives, leads to the conclusion if and where the traditional steering systems can be replaced with the innovative ones. In addition to the cost, light weight, cleanness, compactness, high power / weight and power / volume ratios, common to all pneumatic actuators, fluidic muscles present the follows advantages:

- Static sealing, which results in the absence of friction losses caused by contact seals and leakage of the working fluid;
- Versatility in relation to the working fluid, then use of secure fluids, explosion-proof, low-cost and lightweight;
- Service opportunities in hostile environments, with strong temperature changes, vibration, dust and electromagnetic interference;
- Mounting configurations, with possibility to compensate misalignments;
- Force available at the beginning of the contraction 10 times larger than that produced by pneumatic cylinders of equal diameter;
- Suitable for both movements characterized by low and high frequencies;
- Direct connection to the devices to be moved;
- Easiness of replacement;
- Low maintenance;
- Safety in the operation.

These actuators, however, show disadvantages:

- You can contract a maximum of 25% of the length at rest; you can't then optimize the overall dimensions;
- In the elongation behavior is different from that in the contraction, with maximum elongations of 3 ÷ 5% of the length at rest; the increase of extensive capacity can be obtained pre-loading the muscle;
- The compressibility: low accuracy in the position control, and then need to non-linear complex algorithms, such as adaptive control and linearization techniques; during air discharge part of the energy is lost and not used to do useful work;
- Non-linear behavior: the area of the section varies with the square of the diameter; the length is linked corner of interweaving of the fibers with trigonometric relations;
- Have a "shape memory", thus present a hysteretic behavior related to the force-length characteristics.

During the last decade, there has been a significant increase of the use of industrial and scientific PAMs thanks to their advantages, among which the high strength and low weight. Typical applications are bio-robotics, medical, industrial and aerospace markets.

2. Applicability to boat steering

To choose and size preliminarily the right steering system is necessary to know the torque required from the helm, both in terms of maximum value and of performance as a function of the rudder angle. The possibility to know the hydrodynamic characteristics of the blade is therefore essential to be able to choose with better accuracy and correctness the capacity of the steering system, *Whicker and Fehlner (1958)*. The maximum value of the hydrodynamic torque is obtained at the profile stall angle, which usually does not match the maximum rudder angle required (35°). In the design phase, the capacity of the steering system must be established so that it is able to ensure the maximum torque required by the blade, but the configuration must allow reaching the maximum bar angle. Referring to a hypothetical application of fluidic muscles, these concepts influence the choice of a configuration that allows realizing the maximum torque and affect the evaluation of the correct nominal length, of which only 25% is a useful movement.

2.1. Rudder operation prediction

The rudder performance can be predicted following different methods, as described hereafter.

2.1.1. Registers of classification

DNV-GL classification rules (2015, 3rd part) evaluate the rudder force C_R as:

$$C_R = 132 k_1 k_2 k_3 A v^2 \quad (1)$$

A is the area of the rudder blade, v the maximum service speed, k_1 a factor depending on the aspect ratio λ , k_2 a coefficient depending on the type of rudder and on the rudder profile, k_3 a factor related to the position of the rudder. As well known, the aspect ratio is evaluated as:

$$\lambda = b^2 / A_t \quad (2)$$

b is the mean height of the rudder area (in m) and A_t is the sum of the rudder blade area A and the area of rudder post and rudder horn (in m²).

The rudder torque is calculated as:

$$Q_R = C_R r \quad (3)$$

$r = c(\alpha - k)$ (in m), c the mean rudder breadth, $\alpha = 0.33 - 0.66$, $k = A_f/A$ with A_f the portion of the rudder blade area situated ahead of the center line of the rudder stock.

2.1.2. Fehlner and Whicker proposal

Whicker and Fehlner, on the base of wings theory, derived the analytical formulations developing experimental tests on different profiles under different operating conditions. The resultant force F generated by hydrodynamic actions on the blade can be decomposed in lift L and drag D , or in normal and axial direction to the profile (F_N and F_A). Starting from lift and drag coefficients C_L and C_D , the L and D values can be obtained, so the F_N value, necessary for the torque evaluation.

$$F_A = D \cos \alpha - L \sin \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$F_N = D \sin \alpha + L \cos \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$C_L = \left(\frac{\partial C_L}{\partial \alpha} \right) \alpha + \frac{C_{Dc}}{2AR_{geo}} \left(\frac{\alpha}{57,3} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial C_L}{\partial \alpha} \right) = \frac{0,9 * 2\pi * 2AR_{geo}}{57,3 \left[\left(\cos \Omega \sqrt{\frac{(2AR_{geo})^2}{\cos^4 \Omega} + 4} \right) + 1,8 \right]} \quad (7)$$

$$C_D = C_{D0} + \frac{C_L^2}{2\pi AR_{geo} e} \quad (8)$$

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_L A V^2 \quad (9)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_D A V^2 \quad (10)$$

where α = rudder angle [deg]

C_{Dc} = drag coefficient function of the rudder shape

AR_{geo} = aspect ratio = b/c

Ω = sweep angle

C_{D0} = minimum drag coefficient

e = Osvaldo coefficient

Fig.1: Geometric characteristics of the blade

The torque Q [Nm] generated on the blade from the hydrodynamic force can be estimated if the distance of the center of pressure CP and the rudder stock (CP_C) is known. Being d the distance between the tip and the rudder stock (measured at the same height of CP), the F_N arm is equal to $(d - CP_C)$, then the torque is calculated as:

$$Q = F_N (d - CP_C) \quad (11)$$

2.1.3. Manufacturers' formulations

Several manufacturers propose different methods of calculation. With reference to the simplified rudder geometry shown in Fig.2, the formulation proposed by Ultraflex and valid for boat with maximum speed below 25 kn, considers the torque equal to:

$$Q_r = A * [(0.4 * b) - e] * V^2 * K \quad (12)$$

where Q_r = torque in kg m

A = rudder surface in sq m ($h * b$)

h = rudder height in m

b = rudder width in m

e = compensation in m

V = maximum speed in kn

K = coefficient according to total rudder angle

Port to starboard 70° $K = 15.89$
 Port to starboard 80° $K = 17.80$
 Port to starboard 90° $K = 19.52$
Correction in function of the type of boat
 For sailing boat $Q_r * 0.5$
 For a boat with a steering nozzle $Q_r * 2$

Fig.2: Rudder geometry

Table I summarized the main dimensions of a rectangular rudder blade, assumed as reference, and the results corresponding to the three methods previously described.

Table I: Dimensions and torque

Rudder data		
Area	0.23	[m]
Height	0.63	[m]
Breadth	0.37	[m]
Aspect ratio	1.7	[m]
Speed	18.00	[kn]
Compensation	0.08	[m]
Method	Torque	
DNV-GL	569.40	[Nm]
Whicker&Fehlner	551.01	[Nm]
Ultraflex	800.55	[Nm]

The results of DNV-GL and Fehlner & Whicker are comparable, while the manufacturer one uses simplified relationships so the torque is estimated by excess, but it can be used to quickly estimate the rudder torque. For the dimensional and performance analyses reported in par. 2.2, the rudder sizes reported in Table I will be used and the nominal torque will be assumed equal to the DNV-GL result.

2.2. The steering system configuration

The muscle incapacity to generate forces that act in opposed directions, makes it necessary to realize solutions with at least two muscles, one for each rudder's direction of rotation. Any additional muscles would have, for example, the purpose to increase the power of the steering system if arranged in parallel to each other. An example of mounting solution for this scope is the *antagonistic* configuration, *Deaconescu and Deaconescu (2008)*, *Pitel (2008)*, *Kang et al. (2009)*. In this case, muscles are arranged in such a way that when one muscle is pulling a load, its opposite stretches acting as a brake to stop the load in the wanted position. The former of these muscles is called flexor, the latter extensor. In order to move the load in the opposite direction the actuators will exchange their function.

For the fact that the muscle has a different behavior in contraction and extension, this type of configuration is functional only if muscles are connected in such a way that the movement of the flexor is not symmetric with the one of the extensor and to avoid exceeding the limit of muscle extension.

2.2.1. The polygon configuration geometry

The polygon configuration is a type of antagonistic configuration. Fig.3 shows a graphical representation of this configuration. The polygon is the figure formed by the triangles enclosed between the elements that constitute the steering system, the pneumatic muscle and the lever. This configuration is studied in order to let the PAMs assume two different positions, one in contraction and one in extension, and to better exploit the actuator stroke in these two distinct conditions. The total length of the muscle ($L_{TOT} = L_{nominal} + L_{fittings}$) and the size of the lever (b) and the distance (y) between the fulcrum and constraints of the two muscles are closely related; wanting to maximize the extension of the muscle (5%), but not to exceed it, must apply the following relationship:

$$L_{TOT,max} = L_{TOT} + 0.05 * L_{nominal} = l + y \quad (13)$$

Fig.3: Polygon configuration

As a function of these three variables the angle β between l and y and the angle γ between the levers, are determined:

$$\beta = \arccos\left(\frac{l^2 + y^2 - L_{TOT}^2}{2 * l * y}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$\gamma = 2\pi - 2\beta \quad (15)$$

The length of the muscle can be calculated at the varying of the angle γ of a quantity α (rudder angle); subtracting and adding up α to β the lengths (in mm and as a percentage of the nominal length) of the contracted and extended muscle are obtained:

$$L_{TOT}(\beta) = \sqrt{l^2 + y^2 - 2 * l * y * \cos(\beta)} \quad (16)$$

$$L_{contracted/extended}(\beta) = L_{TOT}(\beta) - L_{fittings} \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta L_{contracted/extended}(\beta) = \frac{L_{contracted/extended} * 100}{L_{nominal}} \quad (18)$$

Obtaining the value of the angle θ between the muscle and the direction fulcrum-constraints (y), the value of the arm of the force produced by the muscle can be calculated:

$$\theta (\beta) = \arccos \left(\frac{y^2 + L_{TOT}^2(\beta) - l^2}{2 * L_{TOT}(\beta) * y} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$b (\alpha) = y * \sin (\theta) \quad (20)$$

Table II: Example of muscle sizing

	$L_{adapters}$	200.00	[mm]	l	140.00	[mm]		
	$L_{nominal}$	400.00	[mm]	y	480.00	[mm]		
	L_{TOT}	600.00	[mm]	β_0	144.93	[deg]		
	$L_{TOT,max}$	620.00	[mm]	γ_0	70.14	[deg]		
Agonist muscle								
α	β	$L_{TOT,contracted}(\beta)$	$L_{contracted}$	ΔL	F_{max}	θ	arm	$M_{contracted}$
[°]	[°]	[mm]	[mm]	[%]	[N]	[°]	[mm]	[Nm]
0	144.93	600.00	400.00	0.00	4000.00	7.70	64.35	257.41
5	139.93	594.01	394.01	1.50	4000.00	8.73	72.82	291.29
10	134.93	587.30	387.30	3.18	4000.00	9.72	81.01	324.03
15	129.93	579.88	379.88	5.03	4000.00	10.67	88.86	355.46
20	124.93	571.80	371.80	7.05	4000.00	11.58	96.35	385.41
25	119.93	563.08	363.08	9.23	3596.02	12.44	103.43	371.93
30	114.93	553.76	353.76	11.56	3118.91	13.25	110.04	343.22
35	109.93	543.89	343.89	14.03	2646.05	14.00	116.16	307.35
Antagonist muscle								
α	β	$L_{TOT,extended}(\beta)$	$L_{extended}$	ΔL	F_{max}	θ	arm	$M_{extended}$
[°]	[°]	[mm]	[mm]	[%]	[N]	[°]	[mm]	[Nm]
0	144.93	600.00	400.00	0.00	0.00	7.70	64.35	0.00
5	149.93	605.24	405.24	-1.31	290.80	6.66	55.63	16.18
10	154.93	609.70	409.70	-2.43	681.58	5.58	46.70	31.83
15	159.93	613.38	413.38	-3.35	1166.06	4.49	37.60	43.84
20	164.93	616.26	416.26	-4.07	1682.72	3.39	28.35	47.71
25	169.93	618.33	418.33	-4.58	2269.71	2.27	19.00	43.13
30	174.93	619.58	419.58	-4.89	2624.08	1.14	9.58	25.15
35	179.93	620.00	420.00	-5.00	2744.53	0.02	0.13	0.36
Polygon								
	α	M_{TOT}						
	[°]	[Nm]						
	0	257.41						
	5	275.12						
	10	292.20						
	15	311.62						
	20	337.70						
	25	328.80						
	30	318.07						
	35	306.99						

Deducting the force produced by the muscle from the characteristic graph (Festo catalogue) at 6 bar (maximum value for the contracted muscle) and at 0 bar for the antagonist muscle, the moment produced by the two actuators and thus the total torque acting on the rudder stock can be calculated:

$$M (\alpha) = F * b (\alpha) \quad (21)$$

$$M_{TOT} = M_{contracted} - M_{extended} \quad (22)$$

In Table II is reported the numerical example of the torque produced by two antagonistic muscles MAS-40 of nominal length equal to 400 mm with a lever of 140 mm, maximum dimensions of 520x284x80 mm and mass of 2.4 kg. The examined solution ensures the blade rotation of 35° to port and starboard, as required in a yacht. The muscle that behaves as an agonist will contract of 13.5% ca. to achieve this rotation, at the same time will be exploited the maximum extension of the antagonist muscle.

2.2.2. The integrated configuration geometry

The second approach on innovative solutions for rudders command is, in particular, oriented to the actuation of small and medium rudder sizes. Similarly, to the previous described solution one or more artificial pneumatic muscles are applied. Also in this integrated solution you can find again a type of antagonistic configuration: the innovative aspect concerns on the muscles positioning, not external to the rudder blade but internally. Fig. 4 shows graphical representation of this configuration.

Fig. 4: Blade-integrated configuration

The vertical axis of the rudder is moved through a bevel gear: one gear is fixed to the rudder axis and the other one to a horizontal lever arm on which one of the ends of the pneumatic muscle is articulated by a spherical joint. The other end of the muscle is articulated to the body of the blade. The contraction of the muscle generates a rotation of the lever arm and, consequently, a rotation of the rudder axis. The rudder axis is fixed to the blade and its top ends are coupled to bearings. The rotational motion of the blade generates the rotation of the muscle, varying its relative position with respect to the bevel gear: consequently the oscillating lever must be a grooved guide where the spherical joint of the muscle is articulated.

In this way the contraction of the muscles generates the rotation of the blade. However, using only one muscle this rotation is asymmetrical respect to the middle position of the rudder blade. In order to obtain a symmetrical rotation the mechanism must be duplicated: in addition to an agonist muscle must be faced an antagonist one.

This configuration is strongly influenced by the size of the rudder blade, in particular the length of the oscillating lever. For the assumed blade geometry this size is not greater than 115 mm, because over this distance from the rudder axis the thickness of the blade is not enough to allow the mounting of the actuator.

If $a = 115$ mm, considering a contraction of 25% (muscle length 200 mm) the rotation angle β of the lever is 23.5° . Consequently, in order to reach the requested bar angle (typically 35°) a multiplier bevel gear having a transmission ratio of 1:1.5 must be used. This is advantageous from the displacement point of view but disadvantageous with reference to the torque generated on the rudder axis. The research of an acceptable compromise is one of the challenges of this innovative analysis.

Fig.5: Oscillating lever geometry

In order to check the feasibility of the use of muscle made available on the market an example of dimensioning is proposed hereafter. Following the DNV-GL rules of classification, a simplified geometry of rudder is considered, with respect to a real geometry (see Fig.6) and assuming a NACA 0020 profile and a maximum service speed of 18 knots.

Fig.6: NACA 0020 profile

Taking into account the mounting of agonist and antagonist muscle, an overall dimension of 295 mm can be used. Therefore a pneumatic muscle MAS having diameter 40 mm and length 200 mm is considered. The reference dimensions (compatible with the internal space of the rudder blade) assumed for muscles are $L_{\text{fittings}} = 95 \text{ mm}$, $L_{\text{initial}} = 295 \text{ mm}$, $L_{\text{nominal}} = 200 \text{ mm}$, pre-load 0%. In this case a simple mounting to connect the muscles to the oscillating lever, would have led to an extension of the antagonistic muscle equal to the contraction of the agonistic one, not acceptable. To solve the problem, muscles could be preloaded so that the extension limit will not be exceeded. However this solution causes first a reduction of the muscle performance, secondly an inversion of the moment on the rudder axis.

It is necessary to release the movement constraint between the two antagonistic muscles, installing a one-way mechanism: when one muscle contracts its mechanism is not active, while the antagonistic muscle keeps its position and its mechanism follows the opposite actuator.

Fig.7: One-way mechanism

During the contraction phase the one-way mechanism is locked and moves the guide, allowing the rotation of the rudder blade. During the extension phase the mechanism allows the relative motion between slide and guide and the guide is stationary: the terminal of the muscle runs in the slide but it is not actuated by the opposite muscle. The performance of the muscle is reported in Table III.

Table III: Muscle performance

		$L_{adapters}$	95.00	[mm]	Arm	115.00	[mm]		
		$L_{nominal}$	200.00	[mm]	Gear ratio	1.5			
		L_{TOT}	295.00	[mm]	Pre-load	0	[%]		
Agonistic muscle									
α	$\alpha_{withgear}$	$L_{TOT,contracted}$	$L_{contracted}$	$\Delta L_{contracted}$	$\Delta L_{contracted}$	$F_{max,contracted}$	$M_{contracted}$	$M_{contracted,withgear}$	
[°]	[°]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[%]	[N]	[Nm]	[Nm]	
0	0.00	295.00	200.00	0.00	0.00	4000.00	460.00	306.67	
5	3.33	288.30	193.30	6.70	3.35	4000.00	460.00	306.67	
10	6.67	281.56	186.56	13.44	6.72	4000.00	460.00	306.67	
15	10.00	274.72	179.72	20.28	10.14	3411.01	392.27	261.51	
20	13.33	267.74	172.74	27.26	13.63	2719.14	312.70	208.47	
25	16.67	260.57	165.57	34.43	17.21	2100.24	241.53	161.02	
30	20.00	253.14	158.14	41.86	20.93	1500.62	172.57	115.05	
35	23.33	245.39	150.39	49.61	24.80	919.90	105.79	70.53	

A successful alteration at the design of the rudder transmission can be applied using a mechanism based on inverse kinematic cam, instead of the lever arm. The working principle is reported in Fig. 8 while the operating solution is sketched in Fig. 9.

This solution allows correlating the contraction of the muscle with the rotation of the lever arm through the synthesis of the cam profile.

The groove is designed starting from the function contraction-angle. In this way the maximum vertical displacement corresponds to the maximum allowed contraction of the muscle and the maximum rotation of the lever arm can be assumed to be 35° , using bevel gears with ratio 1:1, with evident advantage on the output torque. The description of the contraction-angle law can be freely defined by the user, but singular points must be avoided in order to have corresponding finite derivative functions.

Fig.8: Cam working principle

Fig.9: Operating solution: inverse cam with one-way mechanism

2.2.3 Functioning comparisons

The two proposed solutions can be compared both from the constructive point of view and from the performance point of view. The polygon solution presents constructive advantages such as the simplicity of assembly and the availability of onboard spaces. The available space in the steering compartment can be exploited in the plan, but also in the height thinking of a solution with muscles mounted in parallel. A solution of this type allows to multiply the force produced by the number of muscles used, consequently the useful torque to the rudder axis. This solution with muscles of sizes equal to those considered in the previous paragraph generates sufficient torque arranging two polygons in parallel.

Table IV: Polygon performance

L_{nominale}	400.00	[mm]
B	140.00	[mm]
$M_{\text{TOT, single at } 35^\circ}$	306.99	[Nm]
$M_{\text{TOT, parallel at } 35^\circ}$	613.98	[Nm]
$\text{DNV-GL } M_{\text{required}}$	569.40	[Nm]

The integrated solution allows to free the space occupied onboard and to gather the steering gear inside the sealed rudder blade. The only connection to the steering system is given by the air tube that

feeds the actuators. The operation of this type of solution is possible only excluding the antagonistic configuration. This could be a positive aspect in terms of opposite torque related to the antagonistic actuator, which is null. However the performance of the system is critical, mostly for the presence of the bevel gears which reduce the useful torque, and requires more than one muscle arranged in parallel. In this case the available space is limited by the dimension of the blade, allowing the installation of two parallel muscles at maximum.

The inverse cam design eliminates any type of transmission ratio and with two muscles arranged in parallel the performance of the system is acceptable. In a first approximation, the arm can be considered equal to the mean arm of the two parallel actuators and the force produced by the muscles can be assumed being normal to the oscillating lever for all the angular positions. Setting a contraction-angle relationship with its limit equal to 15%-35°, the maximum force of each muscle can be derived from the characteristic curve of MAS-40 (Festo catalogue). This value, at a pressure of 6 bar, is equal to 2474.51 Nm. In Table V are resumed the results of this configuration. It can be observed that the useful torque is similar to the required one, so the cam mechanism is the best to realize a performing solution.

Table V: Cam mechanism performance

L_{nominale}	200.00	[mm]
arm	100.00	[mm]
M_{TOT, single at 35°}	247.50	[Nm]
M_{TOT, parallel at 35°}	495.00	[Nm]
DNV-GL M_{required}	569.40	[Nm]

Complications deriving from the cam transmission are connected to the relation between the contraction of the actuator, which happens at a constant speed, and the positioning of the cam which follows the groove. The result could be a different sensibility on the wheel. The control system could be implemented in such a way that the response of the proportional valve will be related to the law of the inverse cam.

3. Prototyping

In the prototyping phase a control system has been implemented and a physical model, Fig.10, has been built to test its operation. For the assembly of the system and the connection of the components an anchoring plane is used. One end of the muscle is fixed to the surface through a metal bracket on which is screwed the actuator. On the opposite side of the plane another bracket constrains the position transducer that is aligned to the muscle. The electronically controlled proportional pressure valve is also fixed to the surface. It is connected on one side to a pressure regulator, which controls the air supply provided by the compressor; on the other side it is attached to a pressure transducer, which measures the pressure value of the air entering the muscle. The air flows from this last transducer into the muscle, passing by the same entrance from which it will exit. Venting occurs through the valve exhaust. The circuit is of the open type. A spring is mounted between the muscle and the position transducer. A box holds the spring to the movable muscle terminal, in order to avoid the relative translation between the two elements. The other end of the spring is instead constrained to the plane through a metal bracket. The actuator contraction will result in an extension of the spring, in the direction of the inflation. The position transducer is connected to the box, which follows the actuator in its movement. Moreover, to represent the rudder movement, a simulator is realized with two metal profiles mounted at 90° in respect to one another. The simulator is fixed to the surface with a constraint that allows it to rotate around a vertical axis, and it is bound with a ball joint to the box, which is integral with the movement of the muscle. Finally, the presence of a quick exhaust valve, between the proportional valve and the pressure transducer, is to be acknowledged. This valve is useful to empty the muscle in case of emergency.

A National Instruments data acquisition device reads the signals of position and pressure, which are respectively relative to the position transducer and the pressure transducer. All the signals are con-

nected to a terminal block .The National Instruments LabVIEW 8.5, used to implement the control system, is also used to monitor and collect the data imported through the DAQ device, and to manipulate the output control signal to the proportional valve. The control system implementation relates to a single PAM.

Fig.10: Prototype of rudder drive

This, however, is not to be mistaken for a code limitation even when it applies to an antagonistic set-up. As a matter of fact, in the antagonistic configuration the muscles move one at a time, and never both together. The experiment is then licit and also finds application in a more complex system in which the aim is to control the movement of the actuator. The muscle is tested by setting a constant of the blade position, at first without generating any disturbance, then simulating one introducing a variable signal in time. The force applied to the muscle, that simulates the force of the hydrodynamic actions, is generated by the connected spring. The aim to get a constant position is to simulate the maneuver of the pilot, in which a rudder angle different from the current one is required. Whenever the helmsman acts on the steering wheel, he seeks a change of the rudder angle. This can happen if the agonist muscle contracts and, in the antagonistic configuration, the antagonist one extends, obtaining a torque acting on the rudder axis.

Fig.11: Controls and indicators for a rudder angle of 12.5°

The generation of the disturbance is useful to observe the readiness of the actuator response. The muscle has a good behavior both at low and high frequencies. It is expected to observe a continuous contraction close to the one necessary to obtain the rudder required position. Test without disturbance consisted in setting some bar angle and keep them for a few moments, bringing the rudder from 0° to 12.5°, passing through 7.5°, and back to 0°, through 5°. For the test with disturbance, a signal generator is used (variable in amplitude, frequency, type of wave), which is activated after bringing the rudder in a certain rudder angle (10°).

Fig.12: Sine wave disturbance with a 0.5 Hz frequency

From the analysis of the test results without disturbance, there is a minimum pressure difference between the requested and the one realized by the valve actuator in the process of shortening, this is because the equilibrium of the valve is established when the downstream pressure is equal to voltage signal applied to it, but it is still an acceptable difference. Results show that the actuator position is achieved with a tolerance of a tenth of a millimeter. In the extensional phase, the pressure value measured by the sensor diverges from the null value only due to the valve hysteresis, which is around 0.05 bar.

Fig.13: Blade-integrated muscles

Analyzing the behavior of the actuator after the introduction of disturbance, it is observed a good responsiveness of the muscle which tends to maintain the required position set. The actuator performs small contractions, which happen in the proximities of the required position. The system reaction

quickness is a measure of the efficiency of the tracking PID, and it also depends on the gains of the latter.

Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, show by way of example, the front panel relative to the position of 12.5° for the test without the disturbance and the front panel of the sine wave of low frequency for the test with the disturbance. A prototype blade with integrated muscle is at the moment under study. Fig.13 collects some corresponding details. The prototype under development shows limits of backlashes and local deformations: these aspects are at the moment subject of analysis. The pneumatic actuation uses a miniaturized proportional valve connected to the blade with a hose. The logics of control and command are very similar to those implemented to the other prototype, previously described.

4. Some concluding remarks

During the design phase of a boat the steering prediction operation has a fundamental role to determine which is the best steering system to be used. The type of plant is related to the performance to be obtained, both at the level of sensitivity to the means of government both in accuracy and speed level reached during the desired maneuver. The decision to propose an innovative system such as that based on fluidic muscles is mainly justified by the positive characteristics of the pneumatic systems in general, which represent a valid alternative to hydraulic systems commonly used on board. The presence on board of a compressed air system can be exploited to replace also other systems that use oil, such as those for the movement of doors, lifting units, emergency components and other similar devices.

The governing unit controlled by air is easier, as air is available anytime and anywhere, safer in terms of fire hazards, of environmental pollution in surrounding areas and for the operator in its nearby, more lightweight due to the constitutive elements, more reliable being characterized by a reduced number of failures during operation, longer life since the lack of moving parts relative gives a greater fatigue strength, more economic both in terms of the cost of components and in terms of maintenance during operation.

The possibility to use other fluids as an alternative to air, for example water, is not to be excluded but strongly consider in the marine application. The analysis of the space on board is important to determine the best configuration to place the steering system. The polygonal structure analyzed to carry out the feasibility study is just one of many possibilities. It opens the possibility of design and study of alternative configurations that can improve the capabilities of the chosen solution. The proposed analysis shows the possibility to apply alternative and innovative solutions on a class of boats largely present on the market.

About the actuation control, the implemented procedure allows to obtain excellent results. The response of muscles to a change in the direction requested from the navigating bridge is rapid and precise. Also the reaction behavior under any disturb that retracts the actuator from the position in which it is located, is satisfactory, with responsiveness both high and low frequencies.

The tests lead to the conclusion that the fluidic muscles can be an interesting alternative to the steering board, within a panorama continuously looking for innovative ways enable to achieve the desired goal with weight and cost savings and with integration of human and environmental technologies.

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Drag Reduction for Ships: Drawing Inspiration from Dolphins

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Abstract

The drag of a ship is often dominated by friction between the hull and the water. This study explores ways of reducing the frictional ship resistance in a manner inspired by dolphins. These possess a soft skin believed to diminish drag by delaying transition from laminar to turbulent flow. The underlying mechanism builds on a stabilisation of the laminar boundary layer by the pliable surface. In order to transfer this mechanism to ship hulls, a compliant coating similar to dolphin skin has been developed, soon to be tested in a water tunnel. This paper reports on numerical calculations for the design of the compliant coating.

1. Introduction

Dolphins are able to sustain an underwater speed of about 9 m/s across long distances, *Carpenter et al. (2000)*. This fascinating endurance has led to the hypothesis that the thick, pliable dolphin skin, Fig.1a, keeps a large portion of the boundary-layer flow in a low-friction laminar state through a delay of transition to turbulence, *Gad-El-Hak (1996)*. The present paper reports on possibilities of applying a drag-reducing “artificial dolphin skin” in the form of a compliant coating to the bow of a small search and rescue (SAR) vessel, Fig.1b. This ship has been chosen because of its simple bulb-less bow shape, creating a weakly accelerated boundary-layer flow.

Fig.1: (a) Bottlenose dolphins (source: <https://www.czs.org>). (b) SAR vessel of German Maritime Search and Rescue Association DGzRS, designed by Fassmer (source: <http://www.fassmer.de>)

2. Water-tunnel tests

Polymeric coatings with properties similar to those of dolphin skin have been developed. These are currently tested in HSVA's Hydrodynamics and Cavitation Tunnel (HYKAT), using a 1:3.2 scale model of the SAR vessel (Fig.2). The experiments will be conducted at a tunnel speed above the cruising speed of the real ship so as to obtain a large laboratory Reynolds number of about 50 million, Table I. This is just by a factor of 2.4 below the Reynolds number of the real vessel such that test results with relevance for field applications are expected.

Table I: Length, breadth, draught, speed and Reynolds number of the SAR vessel and the test body

	L_{wl} [m]	B_{wl} [m]	T [m]	U_0 [m/s]	Re_L [$\times 10^6$]
SAR vessel	18.3	4.61	1.27	7.7 (cruising)	120
Test body (scale 1:3.2)	5.72	1.44	0.40	10	50

Fig.2: Streamlined underwater-hull model (no appendages) of SAR vessel for water-tunnel testing:
 (a) Main body during construction, not yet painted. (b) Exchangeable bow segment with recess for compliant coating

The test model is equipped with interchangeable bow segments to be coated with different polymers and with a standard paint for reference, Fig.3a. This setup facilitates a swift test procedure and a straightforward comparison of different compliant coatings. The bow segments are mounted in an overhung arrangement to the main test body such that the drag force acting on the coated and uncoated bows can be measured by a load cell, Fig.3b-e.

Fig.3: (a) Schematic of water-tunnel experiment: Hull model, mounted at ceiling of test section, equipped with a removable bow segment for different coatings, supported by load cell. (b-e) Setting up the experiment: (b) Main body with load cell (bow segment removed); (c,d) After installation of reference bow segment (standard paint). (e) First test run (functionality check)

3. Natural transition

In calm water, laminar-turbulent transition is usually initiated by the excitation and amplification of minute boundary-layer disturbances called Tollmien-Schlichting (TS) waves, *Schmid and Henningson (2001)*. The role of the compliant coating is to attenuate or even suppress these TS waves so as to stabilise the laminar state of the boundary layer and to slow down the transition process. The coating design requires knowledge about the frequencies and growth rates of the TS waves that ultimately trigger the breakdown from laminar to turbulent flow. This knowledge can be gained using boundary-layer linear stability theory (LST) based on the Orr-Sommerfeld equation (OSE) in conjunction with the e^N transition criterion, *Smith and Gamberoni (1956)*. Here, the OSE solver from KTH Stockholm has been adopted, *Schmid and Henningson (2001)*.

4. Compliant coating

A dynamical model of dolphin skin has been implemented into the OSE solver, *Carpenter and Garrad (1985)*, intended as a design tool for compliant coatings with drag-reducing mechanical properties. The coating model is composed of an array of springs and dampers and a flexible membrane, mimicking the thick blubber and the thin dermis of dolphin skin, Fig.4. The membrane is supported by the springy layer in such a way that it only executes vertical motions and bending. Under this assumption, the coating dynamics are governed by

$$\rho_d h_d \frac{\partial^2 n_w}{\partial t^2} + \frac{E_b^*}{h_b} n_w + \frac{E_d^* h_d^3}{12(1 - \nu_d^2)} \frac{\partial^4 n_w}{\partial s^4} = -\delta p_f,$$

where the indices ‘b’, ‘d’, ‘w’ and ‘f’ stand for ‘blubber’, ‘dermis’, ‘wall’ and ‘fluid’, respectively. The coordinate s is along the undisturbed surface, t is time and n_w is the normal displacement of the compliant wall. The thickness of the “synthetic blubber” is h_b , while h_d , ρ_d and ν_d are the thickness, density and Poisson’s ratio of the “synthetic dermis”. The quantity δp_f is the pressure perturbation due to the TS waves in the boundary layer above the wall. The viscoelastic behaviour of the compliant coating is captured by the complex elastic modulus

$$E_j^* = E_j(1 - i \tan \delta_j), \quad j = 'b', 'd'.$$

E_j is the storage modulus (stiffness) and $\tan \delta_j$ is the loss tangent (damping) of the two viscoelastic coating layers, where the degree of viscoelasticity is determined by the phase shift δ_j between the flow-induced stress and the resulting strain of the compliant coating. E -modulus and loss tangent of various viscoelastic polymers have been measured through dynamic mechanical analysis, Fig.5. In general, both quantities vary with the excitation frequency.

Fig.4: Dolphin skin: (a) Schematic of a cross section. (b) Mechanical model

Fig.5: Dynamic mechanical analysis of a polyethylene film (data by Fraunhofer-IFAM): (a) Stiffness (E -modulus) and (b) damping (loss tangent) versus excitation frequency. The shaded area marks the frequencies of interest for transition delay.

5. Transition delay

The potential of “artificial dolphin skin” as a passive device for transition delay has been explored through an extensive parametric study of the mechanical coating properties, using the OSE-based fluid-structure model outlined above. The study has revealed that a thick synthetic blubber layer of low stiffness is required for an effective mitigation of the TS waves; moreover, the damping should be as low as possible. While being counterintuitive at first sight, the latter result is attributed to the nature of the TS waves which are viscosity-driven boundary-layer instabilities, *Schmid and Henningson (2001)*. The synthetic dermis, on the other hand, should be thin and resistant to bending so as to suppress flow-induced surface instability (FISI) waves borne by the soft blubber layer underneath. These FISI waves must be avoided because they may lead to self-sustained absolute flow instabilities and rapid transition, *Gad-El-Hak (1996)*.

6. Application to the ship bow

The laminar boundary layer along the bow of the SAR ship model has been obtained by adapting a Falkner-Skan boundary-layer profile, *Schlichting (1968)*, to a RANS solution of the outer flow field, *Schrader (2015)*. This profile has been subject to a LST study in order to calculate the amplifying TS waves, considering a rigid (painted) and a compliant (coated) surface. The coating presented here consists of a very soft silicone “blubber” layer covered by a stiff polyethylene “dermis”. The outcome of the LST analysis is a stability diagram showing TS-wave frequencies versus downstream distance from the stem of the ship model, Fig.6. The area inside the loop-shaped curves corresponds to regions of amplifying (unstable) TS waves. A single unstable region (grey curve) is observed in the case of a rigid wall while this region splits into two much smaller loops (green curves) for the compliant surface, highlighting the ability of the “synthetic dolphin skin” to suppress many of the unstable TS waves. In particular, no unstable waves at all are seen in the range from 210 mm to 280 mm downstream of the stem.

Next, the e^N transition criterion along with Mack’s correlation, *Mack (1975)*, has been evaluated in order to compute the location of laminar-turbulent transition, assuming a turbulence intensity of 0.5% inside the HYKAT test section, Fig.7. This requires the calculation of the individual TS-wave amplification curves (blue lines) and their envelope (black line).

Fig.6: Stability diagram for slightly accelerated Falkner-Skan flow (acceleration exponent $m=0.044$), modelling the laminar boundary layer along the bow of the SAR vessel. The diagram shows regions of amplifying TS waves for a rigid (uncoated) and a compliant (coated) bow surface (“blubber”: silicone, “dermis”: polyethylene)

For the rigid surface, Fig.7a, transition to turbulence occurs ~ 0.5 m downstream of the stem of the ship model, while the compliant coating, Fig.7b shifts the transition point by ~ 2.4 m in the downstream direction, Table II. This remarkable transition delay is mainly due to a substantial mitigation of the growth rates of all TS waves by the compliant coating.

Fig.7: Prediction of the transition point in slightly accelerated Falkner-Skan flow by the e^N criterion along with Mack’s correlation, assuming a turbulence intensity of 0.5% in the test section of the HYKAT water tunnel. (a) Rigid surface: Transition to turbulence occurs approx. 0.5 m downstream of the stem (red arrow). (b) Compliant surface (“blubber”: silicone, “dermis”: polyethylene): Transition occurs approx. 2.9 m downstream of the stem (red arrow)

Table II: Streamwise transition location and Reynolds number along with associated TS-wave frequency in a slightly accelerated Falkner-Skan boundary layer for a turbulence intensity of 0.5%. Rigid surface versus compliant surface (“blubber”: silicone, “dermis”: polyethylene)

Surface	s_0+s_{tr} [mm]	$Re_s [\times 10^6]$	f_{tr} [Hz]
Rigid	490.5	4.76	329
Compliant	2891.1	30.35	56

7. Summary

Compliant coatings appear to be an attractive means of boundary-layer transition control: their technological implementation seems more straightforward and possibly less expensive than that of active flow-control devices such as “air-lubrication systems”. This motivates the present report, dealing with a numerical procedure for the design of drag-reducing compliant coatings for maritime applications. The ingredients consist of a classic transition-prediction methodology based on linear stability theory – widely used in aeronautics – and a simple mechanical coating model inspired by dolphin skin. The new tool has been applied to the boundary layer along the bow of a small SAR vessel so as to establish values of the coating thickness, stiffness and damping suited to effective transition delay. This has resulted in an “artificial dolphin skin” made of silicone and polyethylene. The compliant coating is predicted to shift the transition location by almost 2.4 metres under idealised conditions following from the model assumptions, leading to a significantly enlarged region of low-friction laminar flow along the ship hull. This corresponds to an increase of the transition Reynolds number by a factor of six, which is comparable to results for flat-plate flow reported in the literature, *Carpenter and Garrad (1985)*. The drag-reducing potential of the synthetic dolphin skin is currently tested in the HYKAT water tunnel at HSVA to verify the numerical predictions as well as the suitability of the compliant-coating model. Preliminary experimental results will be included in the conference presentation.

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Comparison of Hydrogen Production Methods for Shipboard Usage

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Abstract

In this paper applicability of eleven hydrogen production methods for shipboard use is investigated. Various criterions including safety, applicability to ships, feedstock need, maturity, reliability, efficiency, and hydrogen production cost of the systems are used for evaluation. Alkaline electrolysis and polymer electrolyte membrane electrolysis gets the highest evaluation points with 25. Polymer electrolyte membrane electrolysis has electrolyser material, low capacity, and hydrogen production continuity problems, for this reason it is not commercial for now. As a result alkaline electrolysis is the most applicable method for shipboard hydrogen production with its maturity and reliability.

1. Introduction

The most important transportation sector is sea transportation which forms the 90% of world trade, *Harrould-Kalieb (2008)*. Globally ships consume 300 million tons of fuel annually, and NO_x, SO_x, CO, CO₂ and PM emissions were 19.002 million tons, 10.240 million tons, 936 thousand tons, 949 million tons and 1.402 million tons on 2012 respectively, *IMO (2014)*.

Emission limitations are more strict at maritime sector by incoming emission regulations. To conform to the emission regulations, studies about emission mitigation techniques are continuing. There are different emission reduction methods like structural changes on ship, after treatment technologies, engine modifications, operational measures etc. Using alternative fuels as a fuel onboard is one of the emission abatement methods. There are various alternative fuels which can be used at vessels. These fuels are liquefied natural gas (LNG), methanol, ethanol and hydrogen. Main drawback of most of these alternative fuels is storage difficulty due to need of special safety and operational precautions. However hydrogen can be produced by alkaline electrolysis system onboard, and directly given to the main engine as additive fuel. A study was made, and hydrogen use as additive fuel by the production from alkaline electrolysis system is found as the future alternative to LNG fuel, *Deniz and Zincir, (2016)*. These type of hydrogen supply systems have been used at land based facilities, vehicles, and few applications are done to the inland vessels. Using alkaline electrolysis system, its system parts, and working procedures are mentioned at previous study, *Zincir and Deniz, (2014)*, but the reasons why alkaline electrolysis system for hydrogen production are suitable to use at land based facilities and vehicles are not indicated adequately. In addition to this there are not any studies about selection of hydrogen production system for shipboard use.

In this study, various hydrogen production methods are referred, and comparison of these methods are made by taking into consideration, safety, applicability to ships, feedstock need, maturity of the system, reliability of the system, efficiency of the system, and hydrogen production cost criterions. Finally comments are made, and suitability of alkaline electrolysis system for ships is found.

2. Hydrogen production methods

Hydrogen can be found all around the world, but it is not present on its own, and it is in compound with other molecules. For this reason hydrogen has to be produced from these compounds. Hydrogen can be produced by hydrocarbons, water, biological and biomass.

2.1. Production from hydrocarbons

Methods of hydrogen production from hydrocarbons are steam reforming, partial oxidation, and auto-thermal reforming. Liquid fuels, natural gas and coal as hydrocarbons are used at these processes.

2.1.1. Steam reforming

Steam reforming is the process which natural gas or other methane stream like biogas or landfill gas is used to produce hydrogen, *Lipman (2011)*. Methane stream reacts with water vapour, and hydrogen and carbon monoxide are formed. Process is endothermic, and required heat is provided by some of the methane stream. Reaction occurs at the temperature ranges between 700 to 850° C, and the pressure ranges between 3 to 25 bar, *IEA (2006)*. Thermal efficiency of the process can be reacted up to 85%, *Holladay et al. (2009)*. Main disadvantage of the steam reforming is large quantities of CO₂ formation, after the production of hydrogen, *Kathari et al. (2008)*.

2.1.2. Partial oxidation

Partial oxidation process is the partial combustion of hydrocarbons to produce synthesis gas which includes carbon monoxide and hydrogen, *Pilavachi et al. (2009)*. Reaction is exothermic, and there is no need for external heating, *IEA (2006)*. Process can operate with or without a catalyst at moderately high pressures, *Kathari et al. (2008)*. Temperatures can be at 1300-1500° C when the reaction occurs, and the thermal efficiencies are 60-75%, *Holladay et al (2009)*. However this process is more practical and compact due to no need of external heating, it is difficult to do thermal control of the system. Another disadvantage of partial oxidation is that it forms CO and CO₂, *Kathari et al. (2008)*.

2.1.3. Auto-thermal reforming

Auto-thermal reforming is a combination of steam reforming and partial oxidation processes. Steam is added to catalytic partial oxidation process, *Holladay et al. (2009)*. The total reaction is exothermic, reaction temperature is around 950-1100° C, and pressure can be raise to 100 bar, *IEA (2006)*. Thermal efficiency of reaction is same as partial oxidation, around 60-75%, and less than steam reformers, if methane is used at process, *Holladay et al. (2009)*.

2.2. Production from water

Methods of hydrogen production from water are alkaline electrolysis, polymer electrolyte membrane electrolysis, high temperature electrolysis, photo-electrolysis, and high temperature decomposition.

2.2.1. Alkaline electrolysis

Generally, electrolysis is the process that water is split into hydrogen and oxygen by using electrolysis cell with electricity. Electrolysis is the only method that does not need fossil fuels for producing hydrogen, and it is applicable for small and large scale production, *Kathari et al. (2008)*. Alkaline electrolysis is a mature technology which use an aqueous potassium hydroxide (KOH) or sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution as an electrolyte. Process can be done either at low pressures or high temperatures up to 25 bar, *IEA (2006)*. Alkaline electrolyzers have efficiencies around 50-60%, and producing hydrogen is more expensive than producing from fossil fuels, *Holladay et al. (2009)*.

2.2.2. Polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolysis

PEM electrolysis does not have liquid electrolyte. Electrolyser electrolyte is an acidic polymer membrane. Water passes from acidic polymer, and split into hydrogen and oxygen. PEM can operate at pressures up to several hundred bar, more safer than alkaline electrolysis due to solid electrolyte, and more compact. On the other hand, it has high cost, low capacity, poor efficiency, short lifetimes, and not mature as alkaline electrolyzers, *IEA (2006)*. PEM electrolyzers have system efficiencies of 55-70%, *Holladay et al. (2009)*.

2.2.3. High temperature electrolysis

High temperature electrolysis is derived from high temperature fuel cell technology. Solid oxide

based electrolyzers are used at this method, which do not include liquid electrolyte as alkaline electrolysis, *Holladay et al. (2009)*. Energy need for the hydrogen production at 1000° C is lower than electrolysis at 100° C, *IEA (2006)*, for this reason overall system efficiency is around 85-90%, *NAS (2004)*. The main drawbacks of the method are material development which resists to high temperature, and cost of this material.

2.2.4. Photo-electrolysis

Photo-electrolysis is the process that sunlight is used to split water into hydrogen and oxygen. The process can be done in two ways. First of them is to get electricity from photovoltaic cells, and use at electrolyzers by two step mechanism. Second one is combined system which is called photo-electrolyser. The photo-electrolyser is fixed into the water, and it produces hydrogen when it gets sunlight, *Kathari et al. (2008)*. Photo-electrolysis has not been commercialised yet, material costs are high, and conversion efficiency of photovoltaic cells to hydrogen production is low, *Dincer and Joshi (2013)*. Solar to hydrogen conversion efficiencies are reached up to 16%, *IEA (2006)*. There are various laboratory scale photo-electrolysis devices, but material and efficiency problems has to be solved to commercialise the system.

2.2.5. High temperature decomposition

High temperature decomposition is the reaction that water is split thermo-chemically into hydrogen and oxygen at the temperature of 3000° C. 10% of water is decomposed, and 90% of water can be used again at this temperature, *IEA (2006)*. The overall efficiencies can be reached to 90% at this method, *Dincer (2012)*. It is hard to develop materials resist to high temperatures, and also have safety concerns of this method due to handling of high heat.

2.3. Biological production

Biological production of hydrogen can be done by green algae or bacteria. There are various ways, but most improved one is by photosynthesis. By the microorganisms, solar energy converts carbon dioxide and water to carbohydrates and oxygen, while this process will happen, hydrogen is produced. This method is at laboratory base, and has many challenges. Large surface area is needed to collect sufficient sunlight by the microorganisms to provide light utilization efficiency of up to 15%, *Holladay et al. (2009)*. In addition to this, continuous hydrogen production is 1 second at 2006, and target was 10 minutes of continuous operation at 2013, *DOE (2007)*. Also light to hydrogen efficiency of the method is around 0,5%, *Holladay et al. (2009)*.

2.4. Production from biomass

Production from biomass technologies are thermo-chemical and biochemical processes. Thermo-chemical processes are gasification and pyrolysis. Gasification of biomass is similar to gasification of hydrocarbons, and pyrolysis is the heating of biomass in the absence of oxygen which results with hydrogen rich gas stream. Biochemical processes can be done at limited places like wet, sugar-based feedstocks, *Lipman (2011)*. There are not any adequate method to be commercialised, and biomass feedstocks have inconsistent quality, for this reason production from biomass is at only demonstration phase, *IEA (2006)*.

3. Comparison of hydrogen production methods

Hydrogen production methods are compared according to criteria of safety, applicability to ships, feedstock need, maturity of the system, reliability of the system, efficiency of the system and hydrogen production cost. Each hydrogen production method gets level of points as plus for the mentioned criterions. Table I shows the evaluation points, and their descriptions.

Table I: Evaluation points and descriptions

Level	Description
+	Impracticable
++	Low
+++	Moderate
++++	Fairly well
+++++	Excellent

3.1. Safety

Safety is one of the most important things at the ships. System operation properties such as high pressures, high temperatures, and corrosive liquids increases risk factor onboard, and threaten the safety. Table II shows system operation properties of each hydrogen production methods. High temperature, high pressure, corrosive liquid, and thermal precaution elements are taken into consideration to determine safety level of the hydrogen production methods. A tick at an element reduces one plus from the hydrogen production method, and (+) which mean impracticable does not give to the methods because these methods are used or planned to be used.

Table II: System operation properties of hydrogen production methods

	High Temperature	High Pressure	Corrosive Liquid	Thermal Precaution
Steam Reforming	✓	✓	-	✓
Partial Oxidation	✓	✓	-	✓
Auto-thermal Reforming	✓	✓	-	✓
Alkaline Electrolysis	-	-	✓	-
PEM Electrolysis	-	-	-	-
High Temperature Electrolysis	-	-	-	✓
Photo-electrolysis	-	-	✓	-
High Temperature Decomposition	✓	-	-	✓
Biological	-	-	-	-
Biomass (thermochemical)	✓	✓	-	✓
Biomass (biochemical)	-	-	-	-

Steam reforming, partial oxidation, auto-thermal reforming, and biomass(thermochemical) processes get (++) for their high temperature, high pressure and thermal control needs for the system operation. High temperature electrolysis and high temperature decomposition gets (+++) due to high temperature and thermal control need, and alkaline electrolysis and photo-electrolysis gets (++++) by the reason of corrosive liquid need of the processes. PEM electrolysis, biological and biomass (biochemical) processes have (++++), because there are not any safety concern for these hydrogen production methods.

3.2. Applicability to ships

Applicability to ships of hydrogen production methods is evaluated by taken into consideration large space need, complexity, thermal control and commercial effect of the method. Space need is related with dimensions of system equipments. Complexity is about the number of equipment, and difficulty of operation. Thermal control is whether system needs thermal control or not. Commercial effect means system reduces commercial interest or not. Table III shows the requirements of hydrogen production methods, and each tick reduces one plus from the evaluation point.

Steam reforming, partial oxidation, auto-thermal reforming, high temperature decomposition, and biomass (thermochemical) processes get (+). Biological and biomass (biochemical) processes get (+ +). High temperature electrolysis and photo-electrolysis has (+ + +), and alkaline electrolysis and PEM electrolysis has (+ + + + +).

Table III: Requirements of hydrogen production methods

	Large Space Need	Complexity	Thermal Control	Commercial Effect
Steam Reforming	✓	✓	✓	✓
Partial Oxidation	✓	✓	✓	✓
Auto-thermal Reforming	✓	✓	✓	✓
Alkaline Electrolysis	-	-	-	-
PEM Electrolysis	-	-	-	-
High Temperature Electrolysis	-	✓	✓	-
Photo-electrolysis	✓	✓	-	-
High Temperature Decomposition	✓	✓	✓	✓
Biological	✓	✓	-	✓
Biomass (thermochemical)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Biomass (biochemical)	✓	✓	-	✓

3.3. Feedstock need

Feedstock need of hydrogen production methods are evaluated by main element, aid element, and external energy request of the processes. Main element is hydrocarbon, water or biomass. Aid element is catalyst or microorganisms, and external energy is heat or electricity. Sunlight is not assumed as external energy, because it is renewable source. Request of the processes are shown at Table IV. There is not any perfect system, for this reason no any system gets (+ + + + +) at this criterion. Evaluation point is started from (+ + + +), and steam reforming, partial oxidation, auto-thermal reforming, alkaline electrolysis, PEM electrolysis, high temperature electrolysis, high temperature decomposition, biomass (thermochemical), and biomass (biochemical) has (+ +). Photo-electrolysis and biological processes get (+ + +).

Table IV: Request of the processes

	Main Element	Aid Element	External Energy
Steam Reforming	✓	-	✓
Partial Oxidation	✓	✓	-
Auto-thermal Reforming	✓	-	✓
Alkaline Electrolysis	✓	-	✓
PEM Electrolysis	✓	-	✓
High Temperature Electrolysis	✓	-	✓
Photo-electrolysis	✓	-	-
High Temperature Decomposition	✓	-	✓
Biological	-	✓	-
Biomass (thermochemical)	✓	-	✓
Biomass (biochemical)	✓	✓	-

3.4. Maturity of the system

Maturity of the system is evaluated by Table V. According to literature review, steam reforming, partial oxidation and alkaline electrolysis is at commercial level, for this reason these systems get (+ + + +). Auto-thermal reforming and PEM electrolysis will become commercial in near term, so these systems get (+ + + +). Biomass (thermochemical) process will become commercial in long term by the increase at use of biomass, as a result it gets (+ + +). High temperature electrolysis, photo-electrolysis and high temperature decomposition processes are at laboratory base, and has (+ +). Biological and biomass (biochemical) processes are only at demonstration base, and impracticable for now, for this reason these get (+).

Table V: Maturity evaluation table

Level	Description
+	Impracticable
++	Laboratory based
+++	Commercial in long term
++++	Commercial in near term
+++++	Commercial

3.5. Reliability of the system

Durability of the system means continuous hydrogen production, and durability of the hydrogen production methods. References are taken into consideration to evaluate hydrogen production methods for this section. Steam reforming, partial oxidation and alkaline electrolysis processes have continuous production of hydrogen, and the systems are durable for working long time period. For this reason (+ + + + +) is given to steam reforming, partial oxidation and alkaline electrolysis. Auto-thermal reforming has continuous production of hydrogen, but it is new system, and can be some durability problems related with used materials. So it is evaluated as (+ + + +). PEM electrolysis has short lifetime due to electrolyser material, and has reasonably continuous hydrogen production. (+ + +) is given to PEM electrolysis. High temperature electrolysis and high temperature decomposition needs material development for high heat resistant material, and it is also effects continuous production of hydrogen, by this both processes get (+ +). Also biomass (thermochemical) process get (+ +), due to inconsistent quality of biomass which effects hydrogen production rate and quality. Photo-electrolysis has material and efficiency problems, biological production has continuity problem, and lack of system equipments, and biomass (biochemical) process has inconsistent quality of biomass and continuity problems, for these reasons these systems get (+).

3.6. Efficiency of the system

Efficiency of the system depends on the conversion efficiency of the feedstock to hydrogen production. According to *Holladay et al. (2009)*, efficiency of steam reforming, partial oxidation, auto-thermal reforming, alkaline electrolysis, PEM electrolysis, photo-electrolysis, biological production, and biomass (thermochemical) process are 70-85%, 60-75%, 60-75%, 50-60%, 55-70%, 12,4%, 0,5%, and 35-50% respectively. High temperature electrolysis has the efficiency range of 85-90%, *NAS (2004)*. High temperature decomposition efficiency is 90%, *Dincer (2012)*. Biomass (biochemical) method has low maturity and reliability for this reason, its efficiency assumed to be about the same with biological production. Efficiency ranges are divided, and five levels are formed for evaluation at Table VI.

Table VI: System efficiency evaluation

Level	Efficiency Range (%)
+	0 - 20
++	20 - 40

+++	40 - 60
++++	60 - 80
+++++	80 - 100

Photo-electrolysis, biological production and biomass (biochemical) methods are (+), alkaline electrolysis, and biomass (thermochemical) process are (++), steam reforming, partial oxidation, auto-thermal reforming, and PEM electrolysis are (+++). High temperature electrolysis and high temperature decomposition has the highest efficiency, and gets (+++++).

3.7. Hydrogen production cost

Hydrogen production cost of photo-electrolysis, biological production, and biomass (biochemical) processes are unknown, because these methods are in improvement stage. Hydrogen production costs of other methods are shown at Table VII, and cost ranges and evaluation levels are shown at Table VIII.

Table VII: Hydrogen production costs

	Hydrogen Production Cost	Reference
Steam Reforming	6,0 \$/kg H ₂	<i>IEA (2007)</i>
Partial Oxidation	1,2 \$/kg H ₂	<i>IEA (2007)</i>
Auto-thermal Reforming	2 \$/kg H ₂	<i>Chen and Elnashaie (2005)</i>
Alkaline Electrolysis	6-7 \$/kg H ₂	<i>Lipman (2011)</i>
PEM Electrolysis	5 \$/kg H ₂	<i>Ainscough et al. (2014)</i>
High Temperature Electrolysis	2 \$/kg H ₂	<i>Lipman (2011)</i>
Photo-electrolysis	Unknown	N/A
High Temperature Decomposition	2,4 \$/kg H ₂	<i>IEA (2007)</i>
Biological	Unknown	N/A
Biomass (thermochemical)	5-7 \$/kg H ₂	<i>Lipman (2011)</i>
Biomass (biochemical)	Unknown	N/A

Table VIII: Hydrogen production cost evaluation

Level	Cost Range (\$/kg H ₂)
+	5,6 - 7,0
++	4,2 - 5,6
+++	2,8 - 4,2
++++	1,4 - 2,8
+++++	0 - 1,4

Steam reforming, alkaline electrolysis, and biomass (thermochemical) process gets (+), PEM electrolysis gets (++), auto-thermal reforming, high temperature electrolysis, and high temperature decomposition gets (+++++), and finally partial oxidation gets (+++++).

4. Results & Discussion

Hydrogen production methods are evaluated at various criterions, and final comparison table is formed. Table IX is the final comparison table of hydrogen production methods. According to the table, two hydrogen production methods with the highest points are alkaline electrolysis and PEM electrolysis which get 25 points. Partial oxidation has 24 points, auto-thermal reforming and high temperature electrolysis has 21 points, and steam reforming has 20 points. High temperature decomposition gets the point of 19. Lastly, biomass (thermochemical) process gets the lowest point of 14. Final point of photo-electrolysis, biological production and biomass (biochemical) processes cannot be determined, due to lack information about their hydrogen production costs.

It is shown at the study that best suitable hydrogen production methods for onboard use are alkaline electrolysis and PEM electrolysis. However PEM electrolysis gets the same points with alkaline electrolysis, it is not commercial for now, has material based problems which is also effects continuous hydrogen production. After PEM electrolysis method will be improved, and all the problems will be solved, it can take the place of the alkaline electrolysis method. On the other hand, alkaline electrolysis has been used for many years at industry and land based vehicles, provides continuous hydrogen production. Until the PEM electrolysis will be improved, alkaline electrolysis method is the most suitable way to produce hydrogen at vessels.

Table IX: Final comparison table of hydrogen production methods

	Safety	Applicability	Feedstock	Maturity	Reliability	Efficiency	Cost
Steam Reforming	++	+	++	+++++	+++++	++++	+
Partial Oxidation	++	+	++	+++++	+++++	++++	+++++
Auto-thermal Reforming	++	+	++	++++	++++	++++	++++
Alkaline Electrolysis	++++	+++++	++	+++++	+++++	+++	+
PEM Electrolysis	+++++	+++++	++	++++	+++	++++	++
High Temperature Electrolysis	+++	+++	++	++	++	+++++	++++
Photo-electrolysis	++++	+++	+++	++	+	+	N/A
High Temperature Decomposition	+++	+	++	++	++	+++++	++++
Biological	+++++	++	+++	+	+	+	N/A
Biomass (thermochemical)	++	+	++	+++	++	+++	+
Biomass (biochemical)	+++++	++	++	+	+	+	N/A

5. Conclusion

In this study, hydrogen production methods are compared for shipboard use. Safety, applicability to ships, feedstock need, maturity of the system, reliability of the system, efficiency of the system and hydrogen production cost criterions are formed for evaluation of the hydrogen production methods. At the result of the evaluation, alkaline electrolysis and PEM electrolysis gets the highest points of 25 which shows that these methods are more suitable for onboard use. Other methods are not effective to be used onboard.

Alkaline electrolysis is fairly well safe, excellently applicable to the ships, mature and reliable, moderately efficient, on the other hand its feedstock need gets low grade, and hydrogen production cost is high. PEM electrolysis is excellently safe and applicable. Its maturity and efficiency is fairly well. Reliability is moderate, feedstock need and cost is low. Main reason that PEM electrolysis cannot be used onboard for now is electrolyser material improvement need, low capacity, and hydrogen production continuity problems related with materials. As a result, alkaline electrolysis is the most suitable hydrogen production method for onboard use at directly delivery of the hydrogen to the main engine as additive fuel.

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Drift Forces – Wingsails vs Flettner Rotors

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Abstract

When sails produce thrust, they also produce side force, which makes the ship move with a drift angle. The drift angle increases the resistance of the ship, which cancels some of the positive effect from the sails. This paper explores the importance of drift for two different types of sail technologies. A general cargo ship is analyzed, using historical wind data on an example route from Rotterdam to Trondheim, using wingsails and Flettner rotors. The analysis uses CFD and a custom route simulation software.

1. Introduction

Using sails on modern cargo ships, as a way to reduce the fuel consumption, has been suggested many times by both researchers and commercial companies. Recent examples include the “Wind challenger” project from the university of Tokyo, *Ouchi et al. (2013)*, and the work presented in *Traut et al. (2014)* where a Flettner rotor is compared to a kite. There are also many older, but more famous projects such as the Walker Wingsail, *Walker (1985)*, the “turbo sail” developed by the Cousteau foundation, *Charrier et al. (1985)* and the original Flettner rotor ship. Although many solutions exist, the two most popular wind propulsion technologies seem to be wingsails and Flettner rotors. Both of these technologies, create thrust mainly by using “lift”, i.e. the force normal to the incoming wind velocity. A single element symmetric wingsail creates this lift by having an angle of attack relative to the wind, while Flettner rotors are spinning cylinders that create lift by utilizing the Magnus effect. One of the consequences of creating thrust in this way is an unavoidable side force. That is, as long as the thrust from the sails is created by lift, there is no way of pushing the ship forward, without also pushing it sideways. How much the ship is pushed sideways is dependent on the apparent wind direction. If the wind is coming directly from the side of the ship, the only contribution to the side force is from the drag on the sails. However, if the apparent wind is from any other direction, the lift will also contribute to the side force. The result is that in typical conditions, the side force is often many times larger than the thrust. This side force has an effect on the flow around the ship hull. Since the hull is pushed sideways, it starts moving with an increasing drift angle, until the drift induced side force on the hull is equally strong, but with opposite direction to the side force from the sails. The drift angle makes the ship hull into a lifting surface. The problem is, as is the case with all lifting surfaces: with lift, there is also lift induced drag. That is, due to the drift angle, the resistance on the ship hull is increased, which cancels some of the positive effect from the sails. How big of a problem this is, is dependent on several factors, such as the hydrodynamics of the ship hull, the side force to thrust ratio of the sails and the amount of thrust that is generated from the wind. An interesting aspect of modern sails, which are not much studied previously, is the difference in side force to thrust ratio. For instance, Flettner rotors generate very large forces, relative to the sail area. Dependent on the speed of the ship, and the wind direction, the result is often that a Flettner rotor can generate much more thrust than a wingsail, with equal sail area. However, the side force to thrust ratio is also larger, which means that for the same amount of thrust, the ship is also pushed sideways with a much stronger force.

This paper explores two main questions: how big of a problem is the drift-induced resistance for a normal cargo ship with modern sails, and how much difference is there between wingsails and Flettner rotors?

The case study chosen in for these questions is a 120 m long general cargo ship, with 40 m tall sails, on an example route from Rotterdam, Netherlands to Trondheim, Norway. Historical wind data,

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis of both the sails and the ship hull, and a route analysis code, is used to calculate the importance of drift induced effects. The Flettner rotor in this analysis is a simple spinning cylinder, without any end plates or flaps, while the wingsail is a two-element wing, where both elements are of equal length. We limit the study to one aspect ratio for the sails, which is equal to 5. However, the number of sails is varied between 1 and 8, in order to change the amount of thrust produced from the wind. Two different control strategies for the sail are tested: maximum power delivered from the sails, or maximum effective power delivered. The effective power is the power from the sails, minus the added required power due to the sails. In this analysis, the sails generate added resistance due to two main components: the added resistance on the hull, and the added resistance on the rudder. These two are considered to be different effects, as the rudder might be necessary in order to balance the ship hull at the right drift angle. A keel model will also be used to assess the effect of installing a simple keel on a normal cargo ship, with regard to drift-induced resistance. We will also run the analysis with two different assumptions regarding the sail mechanism: one where the sails cannot be retracted, or stowed away when they are not in use, and one where they can. Since the main focus of this study is to evaluate the importance of drift, some simplifications regarding other effects have been made. For instance, we have not calculated added resistance due to waves, interaction effects between sails, or used any form of engine model. The energy savings presented in this paper should therefore be evaluated critically, and the focus should rather be on how including drift changes the results predicted by the simplified model.

All the code used for creating the results in this paper is published on Jarle Kramer's GitHub page, *Kramer (2016)*. This includes a library and scripts used to set up CFD simulations, a ship analysis library, a geometry handling class, a route simulation code, a particle swarm optimization algorithm, a non-linear lifting line code, and weather data analysis code. Everything is written in Python or Cython. Most of the code is written in an object oriented way, with classes that sometimes inherits from each other. Due to page limitations, not everything in this paper is explained in detail, but references will be made to the GitHub page, where the specific code is available for further study, if this is of interest.

2. CFD simulations

CFD is used to analyze both the hull and the sails with the open source software library OpenFOAM, version 3.0+, <http://www.openfoam.com>. A custom python library written specifically for OpenFOAM simulation setup is used. This library can be found on GitHub, *Kramer (2016)*, along with example scripts that show how it is used. There is one general library, called "myPyFoam", in addition to three specialized classes, called "TowingTank", "WingSimulation" and "FoilSimulation" which is used to set up simulations of ship hulls, 3D wings, and 2D foil geometries respectively. This approach to CFD simulation setup is based on the idea that, for a specific type of simulation, such as foil simulations, there is a general strategy for setup, that are not very much dependent on details in the geometry. That is, a simulation strategy that works for one foil should also work for another foil, if the Reynolds number and main dimensions are the same. Based on experience developed while running CFD simulations in the past, as well as recommended best practices from different sources, the setup library manages both the meshing process and solver settings automatically, with main dimensions and velocity as input. This scripting approach to CFD ensures that we set up the simulations in a consistent matter, every time.

Three different types of OpenFOAM solvers are used for this case study:

- simpleFoam, which is a steady state incompressible solver that uses the SIMPLE algorithm, *Patankar and Spalding (1972)*. This solver is used for the wing and foil simulations.
- pimpleFoam, which is an unsteady, incompressible solver that uses a mix between the SIMPLE algorithm and PISO algorithm, *Issa et al. (1986)*, to deal with large time steps. The time loop is driven forward with the PISO algorithm, with the option of doing several "inner iterations" using the SIMPLE algorithm. This solver is used for all the simulation classes.

- interFoam, which is an unsteady, incompressible solver, similar to pimpleFoam, but with support for two fluids, such as air and water. The interface between the two fluids are tracked using the Volume of Fluid (VoF) method, *Hirt and Nichols (1981)*. This solver is used to find the wave resistance for the ship hull.

All the simulations in this case study use Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes (RANS) turbulence modelling. The setup library supports several turbulence models, but the $k-\omega$ SST, *Menter (1994)*, is the default, and has been used for all the simulations for this paper. A continuous wall function is used, which is an implementation of the equation presented in *Spalding (1961)*. The initial conditions for the variables in the turbulence model follows standard practices, with 1% inlet turbulence, http://www.esi-cfd.com/esi-users/turb_parameters/. The meshing is done with the OpenFOAM meshing tool “snappyHexMesh”. SnappyHexMesh generates hexahedra and split-hexahedra mesh cells, by iteratively refining and moving a background mesh. The process is controlled by specifying refinement levels, and wall-layers, at the geometry present in the simulation, as well as in optional refinement regions. The size of the cells closest to a geometry is adjusted based on a target y^+ value and a case specific maximum size. The length of the cells corresponding to a certain y^+ value is calculated with a friction line, and the Reynolds number for each simulation. The background mesh is adjusted based on a target size alone. The CFD simulations for ships and 3D wings use wall functions, and general guidelines for wall functions often suggest y^+ values between 30 and 100, which is in the range of the logarithmic law of the wall. Both too small and too large y^+ values can be problematic, as is for instance shown in *Hympendahl and Ciortan (2015)*. The y^+ values chosen by default by the setup library is 60, if wall functions are used, otherwise it is 1. However, depending on the Reynolds number and mesh settings, this can sometimes lead to a too coarse mesh, which in our experience are worse than “wrong” y^+ values. Each case class therefore uses a custom maximum size, for the mesh cells right outside the wall layers. If the target y^+ value suggest that the mesh will be too coarse, the library will first try to alter some mesh settings, such as layer expansion. The maximum layer expansion factor is 1.5, but this is generally reduced to about 1.1-1.3 automatically by the library. If this does not work, a smaller y^+ value will be used. If the y^+ value drops below 30, a warning is generated, so that we can decide if we need to resolve the boundary layer instead. Some important simulation parameters are presented in Table 1. “L” and “U” is reference to the characteristic length dimension (ship length and chord length) and inlet velocity in the simulation respectively. The “max feature cell” size is a reference to the smallest cell size used in the simulation outside the wall layers, which are generated at “features”, or sharp edges in the geometry. All the other cells close to a geometry will be one refinement level less, or twice the size. The number of refinement levels varies, depending on the ratio between the background mesh and the feature cells, but are never larger than 8. The time step in the simulation is adjusted so that the Courant number is never above a maximum limit, which is adjusted automatically by OpenFOAM, in addition to a maximum absolute limit that is proportional to the characteristic length dimension divided by the inlet velocity.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

	Foils	Wings	Ships
Max feature cell size/L	0.001	0.005	0.001
Max background cell size/L	0.1	0.5	0.1
Number cells per refinement level	10	5	5
Number of wall layers	15	5	5
Target y^+ value	1	60	60
Approximate number of cells	100 000	10 million	1-5 million
Max Courant number	10	10	10
Max time step $\cdot U/L$	0.005	0.005	0.0025
Simulation time $\cdot U/L$	15	35	14
Max steady state iterations	10000	6000	Not used

In addition to different maximum sizes, different case classes have different refinement regions, which primarily is made to capture the wake in the simulations. This includes refinement in the kelvin wake for ship simulations, tip wake for 3D wings, and a wake that starts at the trailing edge for 2D foil profiles. The ship simulations also use anisotropic refinements only in the vertical direction, in the region where the free surface is located. This is necessary to keep the boundary between water and air relatively sharp. The different meshes used in this analysis can be seen in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Mesh used for the different simulation cases

The parameters shown in Table 1 are the default settings for each simulation class, corresponding to a “medium” mesh. However, each class also have the option of creating “very coarse”, “coarse”, “fine” and “very fine” meshes. When these settings are activated the length dimensions in the mesh is either multiplied or divided by a factor. A “very coarse” and “coarse” mesh corresponds to a mesh where the maximum length dimension is multiplied with two or the square root of two respectively. For a “very fine” and “fine” mesh, the length dimension is divided by two or the square root of two respectively. This is used to do mesh convergence studies, and the result of such a mesh study for the ship hull can be seen in section 3. The setup library has also been used to perform validation simulations. Some of these validation experiments will be presented along with the numbers for this case study.

3. Description of the case study

3.1 Ship

The ship chosen for this case study is a 120 m long general cargo ship. The main dimensions, as well as the service speed, are chosen so that it is similar to a real general cargo ship, and can be seen in Table 2. Both the full-scale values, and the model scale values used in the CFD simulations are shown. A small, relatively slow, cargo ship is considered to be an interesting case study, simply due to the size; we are mostly interested in ships where a significant portion of the total thrust comes from the sails. A very large ship would also need very large sails in order to generate significant amounts of thrust. Very large sails can be problematic, both from a structural point of view, and from practical point of view, due to bridges and cranes in harbors. A smaller ship might need larger sails relative to its own size, as larger ships are more efficient, but the absolute size can still be reduced. It therefore seems more realistic that a small cargo ship can get a large portion of the total thrust from sails, at least in the near future.

Table 2: Ship main particulars

	Full scale ship	CFD model ship
Lwl [m]	120	7
Bwl [m]	20	1.167
D [m]	12.5	0.729
T[m]	5.5	0.321
Volume displacement [m ³]	7990	1.586
Wetted surface, w.o. rudder [m ²]	2591	8.817
Rudder planform area [m ²]	11.25	0.0383
Keel planform area [m ²]	22.5	0.0766

Service speed [m/s]	7	1.69
Service Froude number	0.204	0.204
Resistance coefficient, $C_T \cdot 10^3$	3.149	4.256
Friction resistance coefficient, $C_F \cdot 10^3$	1.723	3.041
Roughness resistance coefficient $\Delta C_F \cdot 10^3$	0.211	0
Pressure resistance coefficient $C_P \cdot 10^3$	1.215	1.215
Propeller diameter, D [m]	4	0.233
Propeller pitch P/D	0.997	0.997
Propeller number of blades	4	4

The hull geometry is a custom design. The reason for designing a new geometry, rather than using an already existing design, is that most open ship geometries are either very large tankers or very larger container ships. The hull design was created with the goal making a realistic, but simple ship. It does not have a bulb, but instead a straight slender bow. It was made using a Catmull-Clark subdivision surface, *Catmull and Clark (1978)*, in the open source geometry modeling software Blender, <https://www.blender.org>. The subdivision surface representation of the geometry was chosen due to its flexibility with regards to topology. Unlike for instance NURBS based geometry, a subdivision surface can have arbitrary topology, i.e. the entire ship hull can be created as one surface, rather than several individual NURBS patches. Fig.2 shows the hull lines; the 3D model can be downloaded from GitHub.

Fig.2: Line drawings of the ship hull

The hydrodynamic forces on the ship are modeled with the “Hull” class in the “Ship” library that can be found on GitHub. This class is initialized with the main dimensions of the ship. Based on the main dimensions, the class estimates the forces that act on the ship hull as function of Froude number, Reynolds number and drift angle, either using simplified theories and empirical models or results from CFD simulation and experiments. For this analysis, CFD is used to compute all the necessary values. When using CFD to estimate the calm-water resistance, the pressure resistance and friction resistance from the simulations are extracted individually. The CFD simulations are performed in model scale, for several Froude numbers. When calculating the full-scale resistance, the pressure resistance is assumed to be independent of Reynolds number, but dependent on Froude number, while the friction resistance is dependent on both. In order to scale the friction resistance to full scale, for a given Froude number, a friction line is used, along with an empirical roughness factor. The scaling factor is the value of the friction line at full scale, divided by the value of the friction line in model scale. The friction line used is a numerical friction line, based on the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model, which can be found in *Eca and Hoekstra (2008)*. The reason for choosing a numerical friction line, rather than the more standard ITTC-57 friction line, is based on the work published in *Raven et al. (2006)*. The paper suggests that using the ITTC-57 friction line might not be the best scaling strategy, and that for instance a numerical friction line is a better choice. The CFD values and scaled values for the resistance coefficients in calm water at service speed can be seen in Table 2.

In order to calculate the side force and added resistance due to drift, CFD simulations of the ship hull

with a drift angle, but without free surface modeling is used. The free surface has previously been found to not be very important for estimating the drift-induced forces, and neglecting the free surface simplifies the simulations, *Kramer and Steen (2015)*. The hull is simulated with five drift angles. The data from the simulations are then fitted to second-order polynomials by the “Hull” class, as this is a model that have been found to work well for drift induced forces. The induced drag coefficient is defined as the drag at a specific drift angle, minus the drag at zero drift angle. That is, it is the added resistance due to drift. The computed lift, lift-induced drag, and yaw moment, as a function of drift angle can be seen in Fig.3. The coordinate system is located in the bow of the ship, with the x-axis pointing towards the stern, when the drift angle is zero, and the z-axis pointing up. F_x is the force in the x-direction, F_y is the force in the y-direction, while M_z is the moment around the z-axis. The coefficients are defined as follows, where L is the ship length, T is the ship draft, U is the ship velocity, ρ is the water density and α is the drift angle:

$$C_L = \frac{F_y}{0.5\rho L T U^2}$$

$$C_{Di} = \frac{F_x(\alpha) - F_x(0)}{0.5\rho L T U^2}$$

$$C_M = \frac{M_z}{0.5\rho L^2 T U^2}$$

The CFD values are plotted for three different meshes: coarse, medium and fine. This is to show that the result is not very dependent on the mesh resolution. The result for the fine mesh is used in this analysis. The polynomial curve fit is shown as solid lines. In order to validate the CFD simulations, the setup scripts have also been used to generate simulations that reproduce the experiments published in *Kramer et al. (2016)*. In this experiment, a foil-like ship is towed in a towing tank for three aspect ratios, two bottom edge shapes and two Froude numbers. The experimental data shown in Fig.3 is for the lowest aspect ratio, with the rounded bottom edge, and Froude number 0.1.

Fig.3: Lift, lift-induced drag and yaw moment coefficients for cargo ship and validation experiment

We are also interested in the effect of rudder and a keel. The rudder was present in all the CFD simulations performed for the ship hull, but only with zero rudder angle. The effect of setting the rudder angle to something other than zero is modeled with the “Rudder” class in the ship library. This is a simple model of a lifting surface, based on a simplified rudder model suggested in *Bertram (2012)*. The exact flow around a rudder is a complicated phenomenon, with very high Reynolds number, presence of a propeller slip stream and interaction from the ship hull. The details of this flow has been neglected. Rather, steady state CFD simulations of the rudder geometry is performed, where the rudder is standing on a symmetry plane in order model the presence of the ship hull. The CFD simulations are performed for a Reynolds number equal to $2E6$, but the since the rudder will actually be experiencing a Reynolds number more close to $15E6$, the friction resistance on the rudder is scaled in the same way as for the ship hull. Only rudder angles well below stall is simulated. Rudder stall is not directly modeled in the route simulation, but the magnitude of the rudder angle is evaluated to assess whether stall is a likely problem or not. The values for lift and drag from the CFD simulations

are then used to construct polynomial models. The lift is assumed to be linearly dependent on the rudder angle, while the lift-induced drag is assumed to be a second order polynomial. The rudder geometry is a spade rudder, with NACA 0018 foil profile, aspect ratio of 2.22 and taper ratio of 0.83. Fig.4 shows the computed lift and drag coefficients.

Fig.4: Lift and drag coefficients for the rudder and the keel

The area of the rudder, A_R , is calculated from a recommended formula in *Bertram (2012)*, as follows:

$$\frac{A_R}{L \cdot T} \geq 0.01 \left(1 + 25 \left(\frac{B}{L} \right)^2 \right)$$

The effect of the propeller slip stream is treated by adding lift, ΔL , and drag, ΔD , as a function of thrust, T , to the lift and drag calculated by the coefficients from CFD. The formulas are taken from *Söding (1998)*. C_{Th} is the thrust coefficient for the propeller, and α is the rudder angle.

$$\Delta L = T \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + C_{Th}}} \right) \sin \alpha$$

$$\Delta D = T \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + C_{Th}}} \right) (1 - \cos \alpha)$$

The incoming velocity to the rudder is assumed to be following the ships center line, as the rudder is located in the ship and propeller wake. That is, the lift and drag from the rudder is in a ship fixed coordinate system, and must be rotated when they are added to the global forces. The keel is modeled in the same way as the rudder, only with twice the area, and with the assumed incoming velocity to be in the ship traveling direction. The yaw moment from both the rudder and the keel is calculated by multiplying the force normal to the ship centerline with the distance from the bow to the rudder/keel. The rudder is located at the stern of the ship, so the distance is $0.95 \cdot L$, while the keel is located in the middle of the ship, or $0.5 \cdot L$, which is also the assumed mean center of pressure for the sail. Global forces and yaw moment on the ship hull as function of drift and rudder angle, with and without keel, at service speed can be seen in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Forces on the ship as a function of drift and rudder angle, with and without keel

3.2 Sails

Two different types of sails are modeled in this paper: a two-element wingsail and a Flettner rotor. Both sails have a geometric aspect ratio of 5 but they are assumed to stand on a large deck structure, so that the effective aspect ratio is 10. That is, we assume that the deck acts as a symmetry plane. The Flettner rotor analyzed is a spinning cylinder, with a constant diameter along the span of the rotor. The wingsail is assumed to have a taper ratio of 0.4. The leading element of the wingsail is based on the NACA 0020 profile, while the trailing element is based on NACA 0015. Both elements are of equal length. The maximum flap angle is 15 degrees. The hinge point of the flap is at the quarter chord of the foil as a whole, or halfway into the first element. The sails are modeled with the “Sail” class in the “Ship” library published on *Kramer (2016)*. This class consists of methods for calculating lift, drag, thrust and side force, as well as a method that can optimize the sail control parameters based on an arbitrary input objective function. The forces are determined from force coefficients. More specifically, the input parameters used to initialize the sail class are the area of a single sail, the height of the sail, the number of sails in total, the lift and drag coefficients for a single sail, along with the corresponding control parameters. For the Flettner rotor, the power coefficient is also needed, which tells us how much input power is required in order to spin the Flettner rotor at a given speed. The control parameter can be either the spin ratio (Flettner rotor) or the angle of attack and flap angle (wingsail). The coefficients are defined as follows, where A is the sail planform area and U is the wind velocity:

$$C_{L/D/x/y} = \frac{\text{Lift/ Drag/ Thrust/ Side force}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AU^2}$$
$$C_p = \frac{\text{Sail input power}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AU^3}$$

The optimization of the sail control parameters can be done with several methods: brute force, built in optimization methods from the SciPy library, <http://scipy.org>, or a custom written optimization method, based on the particle swarm method, *Eberhart and Kennedy (1995)*. For the wingsail in this analysis, the particle swarm method is used, while the Flettner rotor is optimized with brute force.

The force coefficients for the wingsail are analyzed using a combination of 2D CFD and a non-linear numerical lifting line. The non-linear numerical lifting line uses the basic principle of the traditional lifting line, *Prandtl and Tietjens (1934)*, but with linear foil theory exchanged with a non-linear viscous 2D lift coefficient, as well as an iterative method to solve the equations. This approach for analyzing 3D wings in general is for instance described in textbooks such as *Anderson (2005)*, but has also been used specifically for modelling two-element wingsails in the scientific literature, *Graf et al. (2014)*. Details of the algorithm can be found in *Anderson (2005)* chapter 5, while the implementation used specifically for this analysis can be viewed in the “LiftingLine” code on *Kramer (2016)*. The work presented in *Graf et al. (2014)* shows that the method works well for predicting the lift and drag on the sail while the flow is attached. The method can also work for stalled wings, which is shown both in *Anderson (2005)* and *Graf et al. (2014)*. However, *Graf et al. (2014)* show that the maximum lift coefficient can be over predicted compared to 3D CFD, and when the maximum lift coefficient is very large, there is sometimes problems with convergence for the iterative solver. The wing used in this analysis has a large maximum lift coefficient. From the 2D analysis, the maximum lift coefficient is 2.26, which happens with an angle of attack of 12.5°, and a flap angle of 15°. In order to avoid the convergence problems with the method, we have used the lifting line method for angles of attack almost up to stall for the largest flap angle, but not above. A stalled wing is in general of little interest, as this will only be useful when there is a tail wind, with a speed that is higher than the ship speed. The maximum angle of attack used with the lifting line method is 13.5°, which gives a lift coefficient of 2.04 for a flap angle of 15°. Larger angles of attack caused convergence problems for the largest flap angle, and based on the lift coefficient, this is fairly close to stall. The benefit of the method is calculation time. Since the wingsail is a two element wing, the forces depend on both the angle of

attack and the flap angle. The number of simulations that must be performed in order to get a complete picture of the forces on a wingsail can quickly become large. For instance, in this case, 4 flap angles have been simulated with at least 18 angles of attack each, giving more than 72 CFD simulations. 2D CFD allows for simulations with a higher resolution relative to the chord length, at a much shorter time, compared to the 3D case. The resulting lift and drag coefficients used in this analysis for the wingsail can be seen in Fig.6.

Fig.6: Lift and drag coefficients for the wingsail as function of angle of attack and flap angle

In order to get values for the lift and drag for the Flettner rotor, 3D CFD simulations have been used. The non-dimensional value for the spin velocity is called the spin-ratio (α), and is calculated as the velocity of the outer surface of the cylinder, divided by the incoming wind velocity. The flow around a Flettner rotor can be both steady and unsteady, depending on the spin-ratio, and both aspect ratio and Reynolds number have an effect on the resulting forces. The little experimental data that is available is only for very small Reynolds numbers, well below realistic conditions for a Flettner rotor on a cargo ship. It is therefore hard to say much about the uncertainty of the forces we have calculated. Many study this phenomenon using very high fidelity simulations, with many cells, small time steps and LES turbulence models. However, this is very time consuming, and only practical for smaller Reynolds numbers. The work presented in *Zhang et al. (2013)* show fairly good agreement between experimental values and steady state CFD values for both lift and drag, with meshes with less than 10 million cells, and a Reynolds number of 40000. The difference between simulation and experiments are between 1-15% depending on spin ratio, number of cells and turbulence model. The same approach was used to analyze the Flettner rotor in this paper, as it is both practical and relatively accurate. We have also simulated the case presented in *Zhang et al. (2013)*, with the same setup script as used for our case. The “WingSimulation” class applies slightly different settings due to the low Reynolds number, for instance for the wall functions, but the overall rules for setting up the mesh are the same. The difference between simulations and experiment for the low Reynolds number case, as well as the values for the lift, drag and power coefficients for our high Reynolds number case can be seen in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Lift, drag and power coefficient for the Flettner rotor

The lift and drag coefficients is used to calculate thrust and side force. Fig.8 shows the calculated thrust coefficient and side force to thrust ratio for the two different sails, with different ship speed to wind speed ratios, as a function of true wind direction. 0° are head wind, 90° are wind directly from the side and 180° are tail wind. The thrust coefficient is made non-dimensional with the wind velocity, so an increase in ship speed can actually increase the thrust coefficient for the wingsail. This is not the case for the Flettner rotor, which has a lower lift to drag ratio. The figure also shows the difference between the wingsail and the Flettner rotor when it comes to the amount of side force relative to the thrust. In general, the Flettner rotor has significantly higher side force, for the same amount of thrust.

Fig.8: Thrust coefficient and side force to thrust ratio for the sails, at different ship speed to wind speed ratios

3.3 Route and wind

The wind data used in this analysis is taken from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA-interim reanalysis dataset *Berrisford et al. (2011)*. This dataset includes the wind velocity 10 m above the surface, covering the entire globe with a spatial resolution of 0.75° , and four time instances per day. Data from the beginning of the year 2000 until the end of 2015 is used in this analysis. The discrete points making up the route traveled by the ship is created by manually mapping out rough waypoints, and then calculating the great circle lines between the waypoints with the “Route” class located on *Kramer (2016)*. The distance between each discrete point is set to be 50 km. The route is plotted on top of the world in Fig.9, with the average wind velocity for the used dataset as a color map in the background. In order to find the wind velocity on a specific point and a specific time, cubic spline interpolation is used, with the help of the SciPy library. Details can be found in the “Wind” class on GitHub.

Fig.9: Example route plotted on maps with average wind speed color-mapped to the background

A histogram plot of the wind direction and velocity for this specific route can be seen in Fig.10. The wind direction is relative to the ships center line, where 0° is head wind, 90° side wind, and 180° tail wind. The wind data is only shown for $0-180^\circ$ due to symmetry. In total, the number of individual discrete points with wind data for this route is 1,262,304. In order to decrease the computational time,

the dataset used in the simulation is reduced by randomly picking 10 000 points from the overall dataset. This reduction is not expected to alter the overall statistics. Both the reduced dataset and the full dataset is shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10: Wind statistics

4. Route simulation

The route simulation is based on steady state evaluation of the ship at each discrete point in the route and weather data. The resulting statistics will therefore tell us how the ship will perform if it is located at a random place on the route, at a random time. Details on how exactly the ship is moving, i.e. when it is located at a specific point, is neglected, as it is considered to not be relevant for this study. Using the data presented in section 3, the following steps are performed in order to evaluate the ship and sails:

- The performance of the ship without sails is evaluated for the given ship speed. This includes wave resistance, friction resistance, with roughness, and propeller characteristics, such as efficiency.
- For a given wind speed, direction and sail loading, the forces on the sails are computed. That is, both thrust, side force and yaw moment.
- The necessary drift angle is found numerically using Newton's method, from the SciPy library. The input function to the numerical solver is a function that returns the side force from the sails, minus the side force from the hull, keel and rudder, with a drift angle as input. For a given drift angle, the rudder angle is calculated such that it balances the yaw moment. However, for an arbitrary sail loading, it is not guaranteed that there is a drift angle that provide balance both in terms of side force and yaw moment. In addition, the function that gives side force as function of drift, with the rudder always balanced might have local maxima/minima, which can be problematic for the numerical solver. In order to handle this problem, several initial values for the drift angle can be used. First, 5° are tried as default. If this does not lead to a solution, random values between 0° and 30° are tried, either until the maximum number of tries are reached, or a solution is found. The maximum number of tries is set to be 10. If the algorithm cannot find a solution, the hull drift angle is set to a very large value (90°), which causes the added resistance due to drift to become so large that the sail control algorithm will avoid the specific sail loading.
- When the necessary drift and rudder angle is found, the forces on the ship is recalculated, and the effective thrust is found by subtracting all the added resistance that is caused due to drift and rudder angles. The necessary power to the propeller is found by multiplying the total resistance on the ship hull, keel and rudder with the ship velocity, and dividing it with an estimated propeller efficiency.

In order to decide the sail control parameters for each discrete point in the route simulation, the built in sail optimization method is used, as described in section 3.2. The objective function in the sail optimization will be delivered power to the propeller, calculated with and without drift-induced

effects. When drift-induced effects are not considered, the wingsail will deliver maximum thrust, independent of what the consequences of this strategy will be, while the Flettner rotor will deliver maximum power. The power from the Flettner rotor is calculated as the thrust multiplied with the ship velocity, minus the required input power. When drift-induced effects are included, the sail loading might decrease in order to reduce added resistance due to drift and rudder angles. Even when drift-induced effects are not included in the optimization of the sail, there will always be an explicit check of how the performance of the ship would be without the sails “turned on”. That is, either how the ship would be without sails altogether, if the sails are retractable, or how it would be with the control parameters set to zero, if the sails are not retractable. If the control parameters from the sail optimization gives worse performance than a sail in “off position”, the sail control algorithm will choose to turn it off. This is to model a situation where the captain on board the ship will decide to turn of the sails, if he detects that the sail control program increases the fuel consumption.

5. Results

Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show the predicted reduction in delivered power to the propeller, due to the sails, as a percentage of the necessary power in calm water without sails. Fig. 11 is the data for the non-retractable sails, while Fig. 12 is the data for the retractable sails. The power reduction is shown as a function of number of sails, as well as with and without drift-induced effects, with and without rudder and keel, and with and without hydrodynamics in the sail control.

Fig. 11: Average power reduction, with non-retractable sails

Fig. 12: Average power reduction, with retractable sails

A lot of data is generated in the route simulation, regarding the details of the ship as a system. Fig. 13 is used to represent some of this data. It shows histogram plots, and mean values of the drift and rudder angle, for the case with 6 non-retractable sails. Similar patterns can be generated for all the other cases as well, only with smaller/larger values, depending on how many sails there are. This figure is included, as it shows an important result, which is discussed in section 6.

Fig. 13: Drift and rudder angle statistics, for 6 non-retractable sails

6. Conclusion and discussion

Whether drift is an important effect or not is dependent on the sail type, the amount of thrust generated from the sails, the sail control strategy, the sails ability to be stowed away, and of course the hydrodynamics of the ship hull. When just one sail is used, there is only a small reduction in the energy savings due to drift. When more sails are used, and the amount of thrust from the wind increases, the hydrodynamic effects get more and more important, which is not very surprising. What is interesting is the effectiveness of including the hydrodynamics into the control algorithm of the sails. For instance, with the most extreme example, which is the case with 8 non-retractable Flettner rotors, the energy savings due to sails are increased from roughly 10% to almost 30%, by just including the information about the hydrodynamics in the sail control. When the hydrodynamics of the ship hull is considered, the loading of the sail, or amount of thrust produced, is sometimes reduced. That is, sometimes it is better to produce less thrust from the sails, in exchange for less added resistance. Another consequence of considering hydrodynamics is that the sails can be used more often. In the route simulation, there is a very basic “captain model”, that will always turn off the sails, if having the sails on is worse than having them off. When we look at the mean values for drift angles in Fig. 13, we can see that it is slightly larger for the case with hydrodynamics in the sail control, than it is for the case without. Considering that drift causes added resistance, this might seem strange. If drift is the problem, how can a larger mean drift angle cause more power reduction for the ship? The reason for this is simply that the captain will allow the sails to be turned on more often when the hydrodynamics are included in the control algorithm. That is, without hydrodynamics in the control algorithm, the sails will sometimes produce so much side force that all the thrust, and more, is lost to drift-induced resistance. This will cause the captain to turn off the sails, which results in no thrust from the sails at all, but also smaller drift angles. By including hydrodynamics in the control algorithm, the sails will operate at a lower loading, ensuring that they actual produce positive effective thrust, but also a larger drift angle compared to the sails in off position. There is a clear difference in the importance of drift between wingsails and Flettner rotors. Flettner rotors, which have larger side force to thrust ratios in general, have more added resistance due to drift, for the same amount of thrust. This is true both for the retractable sails and the non-retractable sails, although the pattern is more clear for the non-retractable sails. For the Flettner rotor, the difference between retractable and non-retractable sails is large. This is explained by the relatively large drag coefficient in off-position.

Not only can a non-retractable sail generate drag by itself, it can also push the ship sideways, whenever the wind is coming from the side. It seems that a Flettner rotor in off position is a large source of added drift-induced resistance. The performance of the wingsail is much less affected by the ability to retract when not in use, as the drag coefficient in off-position is very small. It is interesting to see how the rudder is greatly increasing the performance. At first, one might think that the only purpose of a rudder is to balance the yaw moment from the sails. However, in doing so, the side force on the ship as a whole is greatly increased. As the rudder is an effective lifting surface, it is much better to produce side force with the rudder than it is to produce it with the ship hull. The fact that the keel has a very small effect on the overall performance of the ship can also be explained by this. Since the keel is increasing the stabilizing yaw moment on the ship hull, there is less need for the rudder. However, the rudder was not actually the problem. Since the rudder is less needed for balancing the yaw moment, it produces less side force, which must instead be balanced by the ship hull and keel. This is part of the reason why the mean drift angle is increased when the keel is added. Another reason is that the sail control algorithm allows larger drift angles, as the keel improves the drift characteristics of the ship hull. The influence of the rudder could change significantly if the balance of the hull was different. For instance, if the yaw restoring moment from the hull was larger than the yaw moment from the sails, the rudder would have to be turned in the opposite direction, in order to balance the ship. This would produce a side force in the same direction as the sails, which would increase the drift angle. Since the yaw moment from the keel affects how the rudder is used, the position of the keel can probably be optimized to give better results. From a purely steady state perspective, where rudder stall is not an issue, the more optimal position would be further forward, so that it generates less stabilizing yaw moment. However, this could be problematic from a maneuvering perspective, as the necessary rudder angle for turning might increase. Maneuvering and hull balance is in fact already an issue. The necessary rudder angle calculated by the route simulation code is sometimes larger than 30 degrees, which would probably cause the rudder to stall in reality. That is, some of the events that happened in the simulation is not realistic, and in reality, the sail loading would need to be reduced in order to avoid rudder stall. This would further reduce the predicted energy savings due to the sails. The rudder angle is in general larger when Flettner rotors are used, than it is when wingsails are used, which means that this problem is more severe for the Flettner rotor. Moving the keel further back should help the rudder stall problem. Even if the rudder is not stalling in steady state condition, it might stall if a turning maneuver is necessary, which is an argument for putting the keel further back.

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Future Directions towards Low-Friction Hulls

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Abstract

The present talk will try to look into the future of hull surfaces from three angles:

- *Skin friction, looking for solutions to achieve lower surface roughness or hydrodynamically efficient surface textures.*
- *Minimization of added roughness during service. Again, three routes will be discussed in this direction:*
 - *Improved antifouling/fouling release properties*
 - *Advanced hull husbandry solutions*
 - *A combination of both*
- *Minimizing the environmental impact from hull coatings*

Using publically available examples, the talk aims to inspire new cross-industry solutions to this long-standing challenge for the marine industry.

1. Introduction

Fuel efficiency measures, triggered by both regulatory efforts and high fuel costs, led to a reduction in sailing speeds and an interest in larger vessel capacities. Both trends go in the direction of frictional resistance becoming a bigger portion of the total resistance of a ship. Despite the current oil prices have somewhat slowed changes down, it is fair to say that low fuel consumption from reduced hull friction will remain a major focus area for the industry moving forward. Just another example of this is the growing interest in reliable methods to quantify the hull performance of vessels, which is becoming higher on the agenda of ship owners and ship operators in order to enable improved decisions.

This paper will try to highlight the most likely research directions in the next decades with regards to hull surfaces.

2. Decrease baseline hull roughness

Ship hulls are not as optimized for frictional resistance as e.g. airplane wings and are unlikely to become so in the next decades. Awaiting revolutionary new methods such as e.g. 3D printing, ship building methods are not believed to change significantly in the years to come, so blasted and welded steel plates coated outdoors are still expected to dominate the worldwide fleet in the foreseeable future. In this regards, several are the possibilities in order to minimize frictional resistance in the undamaged hull.

2.1. Improved surface preparation

Today, there are two main types of surface preparation performed on ship hulls prior to coating application:

- Spot repairs, where local areas showing coating defects (e.g. blisters, cracking, mechanical damages, corrosion etc.) are grit blasted or hydrojetted down to bare steel. A new full coating system is applied only on those areas, while the aged coatings in the remaining of the hull are “refreshed” with new Fouling Control Coatings. This induces significant roughness due to the application on aged, porous coatings, but also due to the difference in dry film thickness between the spot repaired and the rest of the area.
- Full removal of the existing coating system, so a complete new coating system is built from the bare steel. This results in a significant smoother hull overall.

An example of the below was shown by Propulsion Dynamics during their talk in the Ship Efficiency Conference in 2013. Two sister ships entered drydock with a similar hull efficiency according to the measurements made by this company. However, one of the ships repaired a much smaller portion of the hull compared to her sister. The results after the dry docking show that there was a significant difference in frictional resistance between both vessels, Fig.1, but there are certainly too many variables and uncertainties to establish a general comparison between both types of surface preparation.

Fig.1: Differences in added frictional resistance between two sisters vessels undergoing significantly different surface preparation during drydock. When only minor repairs are performed, the improvement of the frictional resistance of the hull due to the dry dock decreases significantly.

As hull efficiency becomes a more critical aspect of shipping, there is no reason to believe that full coating removal will not become a standard during every dry dock operation, or at least much more frequently than today (typically, every 10-15 years). Blasting robots (see also section 2.3.1) are also a likely part of that future.

2.2. Smoother hull coatings

Very few coating chemistries are able to prevent fouling during service (see section 3.1). From those which demonstrated to have wide-spectrum and long lasting fouling prevention capabilities, silicone-based coatings stand out from a hydrodynamic stand point. It has been widely acknowledged in the scientific literature that the application of a silicone-based top-coat will result in a smoother hull compared to applying a conventional antifouling system, Table 1. This is due to different formulation scaffolding: whereas self-polishing copolymer (SPC) coatings are generally formulated with high pigment volume concentration (from e.g. biocides), silicone coatings contain very little pigmentation combined with the very low surface energy and good flow properties of the silicone binder.

Table I: A summary of the reported differences in friction coefficients between freshly immersed antifouling coatings and freshly immersed silicone-based coatings. A positive relative difference (Δ) in friction coefficient is in favour of the silicone based coating technology.

Source	Δ Friction coefficient%	Remarks
Weinell et al. (2003)	6.1%	Rotary study. Topcoat on smooth PVC
Candries et al., (2003)	3.5%	Rotary study. Full system on smooth PVC
Schultz (2004)	3.0–4.0%	Full system on 304SS. No sandpaper strip
Candries and Atlar (2005)	5.3%	Topcoat on smooth steel. Turbulent boundary layer measurements
Westergaard (2008)	1.4%	Towing test. Full system on smooth Al/smooth undercoats
	5.0%	Towin test. Full system on Rz ₅₀ 467 μ m panels

To investigate how the surface roughness develops during service, surfaces of a silicone based and a conventional SPC coating have been measured by laser when freshly applied and after having been dynamically exposed to 30°C seawater for 7 weeks and at 12 knots, Fig.2. The differences persist also after seawater-exposure. In fact, the difference between the silicone surface and the antifouling surface becomes larger during dynamic seawater exposure. This is because the silicone coating is largely unreactive while most of the SPC ingredients are either water soluble or hydrolysable.

Fig.2: Surfaces displaying micro roughness of a silicone based coating and a conventional antifouling measured by laser when freshly applied and after being exposed to seawater at 30°C for 7 weeks, at 12 knots.

2.3. Improved application techniques

Regardless of the choice of coating technology, it is likely that the application methods will improve significantly over the next years. Two likely examples are presented below.

2.3.1. Painting Robots

Today, hull painting is frequently carried out by unskilled labor under outdoor conditions. Hence, “dry spray or spray dust” due to e.g. poor spraying technique and wind, paint sags (paint running down due to an excess of wet thickness) etc. are frequent defects encountered on hulls. Painting robots, such as the HTC from Palfinger Hubert claim to achieve a very low macro-roughness, in line with the values that can be obtained in lab (ideal) spraying conditions, Fig.3, *Hentschel et al. (2016)*.

Fig.3: Coating roughness from HTC applied coating surfaces show a significant longer value that the typical 100-150 microns encountered in real life.

2.3.2. Pre-applied adhesive sheets

The maximum level of smoothness can probably be achieved by adhesive sheets applied in a carefully controlled painting line and then “glued” to the ship hull. PPG Industries in collaboration with a number of industrial partners have recently announced a project to develop such sheets, coated with their silicone-based SigmaGlide hull coating technology and to decrease the application time. The eSHaRk project will address two key aspects relating to marine antifouling coatings. The first is productivity improvement through the development of an easier and faster application of the fouling release system without the traditional constraint of overcoating intervals. The second is ensuring the minimum impact on Environment, Health and Safety requirements, waste reduction, no VOC emission and minimising the need for safety equipment at time of application. Furthermore, the project team announces that the surface morphology of the film will be optimised to enhance drag reduction, fuel savings and emissions reduction benefits to a level previously unattainable. Shark skin surface topographies (see e.g. *Stenzel et al. (2016)*) or riblets are likely under consideration.

3. Minimize the build-up of added roughness during service

The accumulation of biofouling on ship-hulls has adverse effects for the ship operator and the environment. The increase in skin friction, arising from the added roughness caused by the fouling organisms, decreases fuel efficiency significantly. This means that more fuel has to be spent for a ship to cover the same distance, and as a consequence the fuel bill and the emission of greenhouse gasses are increased. Heavily fouled ships may need to increase shaft power with up to 86% to compensate for the speed-loss inflicted by the increased drag resistance, *Schultz (2007)*. However, the extent of biofouling does not have to be high for it to be problematic. Even when hulls are covered in light slime, the change in shaft power required to counteract the speed loss can amount to about 10 %, *Schultz (2007)*. The choice of hull coating can have a dramatic impact on the settlement of fouling on the hull, Fig.4. While the hull coating market is dominated by low to medium cost coating solutions, the most advanced coatings in the market can delay fouling settlement and its undesired consequences, dramatically.

Fig.4: An advanced coating being applied side by side to a conventional antifouling coating. The fouling observed on the main area of the hull is expected to slow the ship down more than 20% according to *Schultz (2007)* vs. a ship fully coated with the product applied on the test patch.

3.1. Improved antifouling protection from coatings

3.1.1 Conventional antifouling paints

Very few significant changes have happened with regards to self-polishing antifouling technology from the *Yebra (2004)* review paper published shortly after the market shift from tin-based coatings. The silyl acrylate technology, already commercial in the early 2000s but significantly expanding since then, seems to be slowly shifting from triisopropyl methyl acrylates to triisopropyl methyl methacrylates, a small change that mostly affect mechanical properties and which should not imply a major change in its fouling prevention capabilities, *Nimoto et al. (2013)*. The Nano Acrylate

Technology was launched in 2005 by Hempel, *Yebra et al. (2006)*, and the Lubyon® technology was launched in 2013 by Akzonobel. These two are, perhaps, the largest “new” binder technologies which add to the “classical” tin-free metal acrylate technologies and silyl acrylate technologies.

There is not much innovation either from the active ingredient side, with cuprous oxide, pyrithiones, DCOI and zinc dithiocarbamates dominating the market. Two new substances have reached commercial stage, but their main features are their environmental profile (heavy-metal free copper replacements) than performance. Selektope®, for example, has very good activity at extremely low concentrations, but it is rather specific against barnacle fouling, i.e. with a much narrower spectrum of action than e.g. cuprous oxide. Econeal® is the other copper alternative in the market. Their commercial penetration is, to date, still modest.

3.1.2 Biocide-free silicones

Silicone-binders for Fouling Control coatings were first invented in 1972. However, not until the middle 1980’s were the mechanisms behind unveiled. The Baier curve depicted in Fig.5 shows the relative adhesion of marine bacteria as a function of surface tension. Baier explains the superior properties of silicone surfaces against fouling by its high hydrophobicity coming from the very low surface-tension. However, as seen in Fig.5, the surface tension of polyfluorinated materials is even lower, which is not reflected in the relative adhesion of marine bacteria to these substrates. *Brady and Singer (2000)* explained the superior performance of silicone compared to fluorinated polymers by the elasticity. Silicones are inherently flexible, and as seen in Fig.5, the combined surface tension and flexibility proposed by Brady and Singer nicely predicts the relative adhesion of marine bacteria.

Fig.5: The ‘Baier curve’: Relative adhesion as a function of surface tension (left) and relative adhesion as a function of the square root of the product of the substrates elasticity and surface tension, *Brady and Singer (2000)*.

Contrarily to early technologies, modern silicone based coatings include hydrogel precursors for the formation of an extremely hydrophilic hydrogel on the outermost surface of the coating. This is inspired by state-of-the-art biomedical research, and even though it may seem contradictory that the very same technology that was introduced due to highly hydrophobic properties would benefit from introduction of a hydrophilic hydrogel to its surface, the technology provides state-of-art non-fouling properties, *Yebra and Catalá (2011)*. The reason has been explained by *Baier (2006)* by the expansion of the Baier curve to also cover hydrophilic surfaces. The data reported by *Baier (2006)* is illustrated in Fig.6.

Since water has a surface tension of 72 dynes/cm, the hydrogel induced on the surface of these coatings therefore belongs to the highly hydrophilic part of the Baier curve. It was concluded by Baier, Fig.6, that hydrophilic surfaces also pose non-fouling properties (so-called zeta-surfaces). The actual working mechanism of the modern silicone-based hull coatings containing hydrogel precursors is three-fold. The hydrated layer of the hydrogel-polymers can be considered similar to the co-existence of water and ice at low temperature, *Yebra and Catalá (2011)*.

Fig.6: Relative adhesion as a function of critical surface tension; modified from *Baier (2006)*.

Water trapped in this layer exhibits a gradient from liquid water to more gel-like, trapped water. This gradient presents the biofouling organisms encountering the hydrogel-layer with a surface unlike other surfaces in the marine environment. Those fouling organisms, actively exploring the surface, do not recognise the surface of a hydrogel and the opportunistic foulers that do not exhibit exploratory behaviour, cannot displace the water-molecules bound in the hydrogel-layer with their glue. As a third level of protection, the silicone-based matrix underneath the hydrogel layer offers very low surface energy for the fouling organisms to anchor their glue, and as outlined above, silicone is well known for its Fouling Release characteristics. These three effects combined offer a potent means to protect against biofouling organisms, which surely will be optimized further in the years to come.

3.1.3 Silicone-based coatings containing biocides

To the author's knowledge, only two such products exist in the market. HEMPAGUARD®, based on the Actiguard® technology, *Sorensen et al. (2015)*, works by forming a biocide-activated hydrogel on the surface of the coating. The hydrogel traps the biocide during diffusion out of the film thereby increasing the surface concentration of the biocide and prolonging the retention time of biocide in the coating matrix and on the surface. Fig.7 shows the working mechanism of Actiguard®. The concentration of biocide in the hydrogel surface of the coating increases for a coating based on Actiguard®. This is because the biocide is trapped in the hydrogel on the way out of the coating. In addition to very effectively utilising a minimal amount of biocide, it also means that the biocide concentration can be kept at a level where the silicone coating retains its silicone properties. There is not much public info on the other product claiming similar working principles, Bioclean Plus (ex. Chugoku Marine Paints).

Fig.7: Working mechanism of ActiGuard®

3.2. Increase frequency of underwater cleaning operations

In contrast to hull coatings bearing the responsibility to stay clean for e.g. 5 years, a relatively mature alternative is to have underwater cleaning as the main mechanisms for fouling protection or, at least, as a complement to hull coatings. This is the business model of e.g. ECOSPEED, a glass-flake reinforced high-build anticorrosive coating whose absence of significant antifouling properties is compensated by regular underwater cleanings.

On conventional coatings, aggressive underwater cleaning will markedly shorten the life time of the coating. For this reason, a number of Remotely Operated Vehicles are already on the market, claiming both a very mild impact over the hull coating but also, the ability to capture any debris from their operation, hence eliminating environmental risks from this activity. This is done, of course, without risking the lives of divers in such dangerous working conditions.

The next step from ROVs is certainly Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV), *Albitar et al. (2016)*. The US Navy's HullBUG, *Tribou and Swain (2010)*, is probably one of the first prototypes. The Robotic Hull Bio-Mimetic Underwater Grooming system, or HullBUG, is an autonomous underwater hull grooming robot specifically designed to prevent the accumulation of marine fouling. The current developmental model of the HullBUG uses four wheels and a negative pressure alternative device assembly for attachment to the hull. A suite of on-board sensors will provide obstacle avoidance, path planning and navigation capabilities that include detection of fouled and groomed surfaces. By reducing marine fouling on ship hulls, the HullBUG will help ensure peak ship performance, reduce fuel consumption associated with increased drag from accumulated biofouling and decrease the U.S. Navy's carbon footprint. Risk of hull invasive species transfer may also be reduced.

4. Conclusions

Looking into the crystal ball for upcoming trends, ships will likely be fully blasted after short regular intervals (3-6 years) to eliminate the added roughness caused by mechanical impact, corrosion and old coating systems. This will be backed up by advanced hull performance studies which will clearly show the positive business case of such operations compared to the added fuel cost of doing only partial surface preparation. The hull will subsequently be protected by a smooth new coating system via painting robots and/or pre-applied adhesive sheets. During operation, the hulls will be kept free from significant fouling-related roughness partly via more frequent underwater cleaning operations potentially using automatic underwater vehicles. Such a strategy will increase the demand for milder methods to clean the surfaces and/or tougher hull coatings with enough antifouling protection to protect the hull between cleaning operations.

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Control Concepts for Navigation of Autonomous Ships in Ports

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Abstract

In this paper we present a solution for autonomous navigation of ships in a port environment. Said environment is characterized by continuous communication between vessels and traffic control stations, which poses various challenges for autonomous navigation. We tackle these challenges in four control levels that permit the navigation of an autonomous vessel in today's port environment, based on whether the ship is underway and the need for VHF-communication. The paper concludes with the development and evaluation of operational concepts to make autonomous navigation within the control levels possible. However, (partly) human control is still assumed to be necessary in critical situations.

1. Introduction

Contemporary developments in autonomous transportation like Tesla Motors' autopilot, Google's trials with selfdriving cars but also developments in the field of drones, will spill over into the shipping sector sooner rather than later. Although research for autonomous shipping is younger than its land- and air-based counterparts, recent studies show the potential of increasing autonomy in one of the oldest and most conservative industrial sectors. Both the European research project MUNIN, *Burmeister et al. (2014)*, the zero-emission, unmanned, short sea concept of DNV GL, *Tvete and Brandsæter (2015)*, and a cooperation between among others Rolls-Royce and DNV GL in the AAWA project, *Rolls-Royce (2016)*, are conducting research into the topic of autonomous shipping. The focus here lies on longer distance autonomous and unmanned sailing outside ports, presenting impressive figures on cost savings due to the absence of crew on board, *Burmeister et al. (2014)*. On the other hand there is a noticeable drive towards increasing autonomy in the optimization of inter-terminal transport of containers by using autonomously guided vehicles (AGVs) within the port of Rotterdam to reduce costs and waiting times, *Negenborn (2014)*, *Brands (2015)*. Here the focus was on autonomous transport over land, with in one case also on waterborne AGVs, *Zheng et al. (2015)*. This last research however assumes a fully autonomous environment. Neither one of those researches looks into the application of an autonomous container shuttle within the current port environment, characterized by otherwise only manned ships. The reason for this exclusion are the challenges posed by the combination of autonomous and conventional vessels in close spaces as ports, *Porathe et al. (2013)*.

This paper addresses the navigation aspect within the port environment. Navigation in ports is marked by a vast amount of traffic situations. At this point in time, VHF-communication is paramount in port movements and inter-vessel communication. Computerized VHF-communication within this context being currently unrealistic, a different way is needed to communicate vessel intentions between manned and unmanned ships.

Within this paper we provide an overview of different solutions for autonomous vessel navigation in an environment of manned vessels. We have evaluated these solutions using a framework of possible future developments. This paper adopts the inter-terminal transport of containers in the port of Rotterdam as a framework for the solutions on navigation of autonomous vessels. It is our aim

however that the reader can use this paper as a general outline and starting tool for research into autonomous navigation in ports.

The paper first elaborates on the research method used to structure and analyze the process of navigation in ports, followed by the different solutions that have been identified. Subsequently, possible future developments are introduced that provide the framework to evaluate the different solutions. Finally, this paper offers a more in-depth discussion and conclusion on the solutions and the framework that was used to evaluate them.

2. Approach

To get an overview of solutions for autonomous navigation inside the port environment, the navigation process is split into control levels so its different aspects can be structured and analyzed. The applicability of the solutions is then analyzed and evaluated based on the area of operation and prospective operators of the autonomous vessel. The technical feasibility is assessed by determining the demands of different solution concepts for innovations in sensing and artificial intelligence.

2.1. Classifying autonomous navigation into control levels

Similar to the use of control levels in management and for the purpose of this research, four control levels for navigation are identified: strategic, tactical, critical and super critical. Clear and strict boundaries between control levels are applied. This way all possible situations are inside the scope of the control levels and thus can be handled. The inputs and outputs of each control level are used to identify and evaluate multiple particular solutions. In the following four subparagraphs, each of the control levels is briefly linked to the issue of autonomous navigation.

The strategic control level only spans decision making before the autonomous vessel leaves the berth. This level relates to all preliminary planning of the autonomous vessels. This requires information about destination and estimated time of arrival (ETA) from the operator, as well as information about the fixed environment such as port structures and buoys and possibly information about previous voyages and expected traffic density within the area. Actual location and behavior of other vessels is not taken into account to determine a preliminary route and sailing profile for the autonomous vessel. Real-time behavior of vessels is constrained to subsequent control levels.

The tactical control level starts as soon as the autonomous vessel leaves the berth and becomes part of active traffic. In this control level the main goal is to follow the route that has been determined in the strategic level. The autonomous vessel now has to deal with live information about other vessels which operate in the area. The tactical control level contains solutions which can deal with predictable behavior of the other vessels, so that no VHF-communication or special intervention of any kind is required.

The critical control level narrows the tactical decision making down to dealing with unpredictable behavior of other vessels. Communication between autonomous and manned vessels is, however, possible. Solutions within this control level are mainly concerned with changing autonomous vessel speed and heading so that the situation can be solved.

As an extension of the critical level, we define the super critical level. Within this control level the autonomous vessel now not only has to deal with unpredictable situations, but also with alien objects within its perimeter with whom, to solve the situation, communicating is deemed impossible. This includes but is not limited to a person or object in the water, a vessel with a black-out or without communication equipment and oil spills. For these situations special solutions are required.

Fig.1: Control levels and interconnections

2.2. Evaluating solutions based on operational scenarios

The solutions for autonomous navigation are subsequently evaluated by means of two domains of future development. A first evaluation was made by assessing the applicability of the solutions based on the area of operation; i.e. the traffic density and range of the autonomous vessel. Next, we looked at prospective operators and investors. Based on personal communication and research we were able to profile their priorities and the influence these had on the applicability of the solutions. Finally we were able to also link the solutions to necessary technological breakthroughs in the field of sensing and development of artificial intelligence.

3. Concept solutions for handling navigation planning and inter-vessel communication in ports

For each of the four control levels various concepts have been identified. These concepts transform the inputs of each control level to outputs that will be used for the next control level. It is possible to create concepts that focus solely on one control level. In practice however, there are preferable combinations of concepts in different control levels due to similar organizational or technical requirements. This is of importance for the selection of an all encompassing navigation system which has solutions on all control levels.

3.1. Solutions within the strategic control level

The inputs of the strategic control level are the current position of the autonomous vessel, the destination of the vessel and the corresponding scheduled time of arrival. The solution concepts for this level provide the preliminary route from the current position to the set destination as well as a corresponding sailing profile for the autonomous vessel.

- **Liner service scheduling and route planning**
The liner service concept is based on a shuttle service between two or more container terminals, with a fixed route. This route is dependent on participating terminal operators. The port authority has the best overview of vessel traffic flows and collects lots of data of ships and their positions. This knowledge of vessel traffic could be used to avoid busy waypoints in the initial route planning, based on statistical traffic density. Therefore involving the port authority in the implementation of an autonomous vessel in a port would be favorable to

minimize the impact of the fixed route on non-automated traffic. The departure and arrival times are also predefined and can be optimized based on information about transport supply and demand of the participating terminals. This is an economical trade-off, for which a fair amount of information sharing between terminals is required.

- **Cargo based scheduling and route planning**
The cargo based concept that has been evaluated uses a dynamic route planning to minimize the impact on other traffic inside the port. More specifically this translates to a route near the right side of the waterway and usage of waypoints as in aviation. The knowledge of the port authority could again be used to avoid busy waypoints in the initial route planning. Individual arrival and delivery times of containers at terminals form the constraints for the scheduling of the autonomous container shuttle. This means that in this concept the destination and ETA are based on previously gathered information. This can be solved by the extension and more widespread use of the current Portbase system. This is a logistical planning tool for cargo vessels used by several Dutch ports.

3.2. Solutions within the tactical control level

For the tactical control level, the inputs are the preliminary route and the corresponding sailing profile chosen within the strategic control level with an according ETA. The outputs from the tactical solution concepts are continuous iterations of the original route, sailing profile and ETA as the autonomous vessel deals with predictable behavior of other traffic participants.

- **Following manned ships in platoons**
The concept of ship platooning implies the autonomous vessel following manned cargo ships that sail (partly) the same route on a fixed distance to get to the desired destination. All communication about traffic situations is handled by the manned vessel, so that the autonomous vessel merely has to mimic the leading vessel's behavior. This reduces the amount of situations that fall inside the critical control level. It is important to stress that the leading - manned - vessel will not assume the responsibility for the unmanned vessels in the platoon. The leading ship merely provides a 'safe-to-sail' route for the unmanned vessels. Ship platooning requires manned vessels that pass through the area of operation of the autonomous vessel to determine and communicate a preferred route based on waypoints. These routes are then centrally monitored by the ship owner within a shore control center (SCC). Involving the port authority for traffic monitoring is preferable. Three main elements are needed from an organizational point of view. First, an online platform is needed where captains of manned ships and terminal operators enter ship and route information. This online platform is monitored within the SCC. Ship routes can subsequently be set by using waypoints and more strictly determined lanes from which captains can only deviate in case of emergency or special maneuvers (e.g. mooring). This concept works best when it is applied in larger areas of operation with relatively high traffic. To ensure maximal efficiency on longer routes, the third organizational element needed is thorough coordination between current VHF-sectors in the port. In this way, both manned and unmanned vessel predictability is highest.

Within this concept the autonomous vessel can make decisions about the best combination of ships to follow, based on the constraint of the initially determined ETA and the available vessel routes. The combination that comes closest to this original ETA will be chosen and communicated with. Captains of manned ships have the last word in approving the platoon with the autonomous ship. This concept requires exact positions and speeds of possible platoon combinations. This could be realized by increasing the Automatic Identification System (AIS) accuracy and refresh rate as well as further improvement of the possibilities regarding route projection of AIS. To determine the safe following distance, the autonomous vessel needs information about ship characteristics and cargo hazards. This could be provided by the Harbour Master Management Information System (HaMIS). Thorough data integrity and security is needed for the transfer of this data. To mimic movements of the leading vessel,

Laser Imaging, Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) sensors could be used to constantly maintain the autonomous vessel within a fixed distance interval in a line behind the leading vessel. Whenever the autonomous vessel is not in a platoon (i.e. between the release and rendezvous points), other tactical solution concepts are required to navigate the vessel to the next platoon. Another possibility would be to control the autonomous vessel remotely from the SCC in these instances. Finally we foresee the need for the development of a module on board the manned ships which would transfer and display all ship and platoon information for the participating captains.

- **Anticipating traffic situations**
The second concept is based on the capability of the autonomous vessel to anticipate traffic situations. This means adapting the sailing profile and route to avoid critical situations (i.e. the need for communication with manned vessels). For anticipation traffic situations two major parties should be involved. The port authority that already has the general overview of traffic inside the port, and a SCC that also requires the same overview to be able to monitor or control the autonomous vessel remotely. Within this concept solution different gradations of autonomy can be chosen with consequences for technical requirements and the organization of the SCC. This is visualized in Table 1. The information about manned vessel positions and behavior can be communicated to the autonomous vessel by either SCC or port authority. In case of local, fully autonomous anticipation, a combination of AIS, LIDAR and stereo cameras is recommended for complete situational awareness. Traffic cameras on shore near harbour entrances would provide better vision for blind spots behind buildings. Prediction of planned traffic participants could (for the port of Rotterdam) be provided by an extension of HaMIS. The range of the route optimization distance could be set to 2 km ahead of the autonomous vessel, based on practical observations. The optimal route is chosen with the original ETA as constraint. Furthermore a safety perimeter, based on ship and cargo characteristics, around autonomous and manned vessels is advised to ensure safe passing of ships. The critical control level will be triggered once the safety perimeter is breached.

Table I: Gradations of autonomy and shore control center role within the concept of anticipating traffic situations

Degree of autonomy	Role of shore control center
Remote control	Determines path solution, controls autonomous vessel
Remote decision, local control	Determines path solution, communicates solution
Local decision and control, remote approval	Checks autonomous path solution
Fully autonomous	Monitors autonomous vessel behavior only

- **Portwide route optimization for all vessels**
The concept of portwide route optimization assumes that routes of all cargo vessels in port are centrally planned based on actual time of departure from berth, destination and ETA. This concept drastically reduces the need for direct communication between vessels in the area of operation. The central planning system would need to process a substantial amount of information from ships and terminals to determine the optimal routes for all vessels in port. A possibility would be to use the current HaMIS system as a starting point for further development, albeit with an extension for inland vessels. The autonomous vessel would follow the route and sailing profile set by the central planning system to its destination. The captains of the manned ships would also need to follow the set path and speed instructions for their vessels. The way the routes are displayed for the captains would be based upon the current Electronic Chart Display and Information System (ECDIS), accompanied by the sailing profile. Current port regulations as e.g. preference for portside-portside crossings and right of way for ‘vessels constrained by draft’ are accounted for in the central planning. Nonetheless, captains are still required to apply ‘good seamanship’, i.e. use their own judgement, in case of an emergency. This concept is, however, not easy to realize. The

requirement of an extension of HaMIS and the implementation of an update of the ECDIS systems on board of inland and seagoing ships will take several years. It is therefore unlikely this concept will be realized within the next few years.

3.3. Solutions within the critical control level

For the critical control level, the inputs are the current location, path and vessel speed. The ETA is not an input for the critical control level. The critical control level is triggered by unexpected situations in the surroundings of the autonomous vessel. These need to be identified first, then evaluated and solved. The first part of this paragraph is on the identification. After consulting with parties involved, human intervention was seen as necessary for problem-solving at the critical level and is discussed subsequently. The outputs of the critical control level are an altered path and speed (as a solution of the situation) and the autonomous vessel's navigation model returns to the tactical control level.

- **Identification of unexpected situations**
A whitelist is a first way to identify unexpected situations. This whitelist contains previously known information about the immediate surroundings of the autonomous vessel. By using different types of sensors, the actual perception of this environment can be compared to the whitelist. If the information does not match, an unexpected situation is identified and the critical control level is triggered. Constant human supervision is the second way to identify such situations. This would translate into continuous camera-based surveillance as in automated industrial processes. Human judgment of possibly critical situations would in this case trigger the critical control level. The third method of identification uses a safety perimeter around the autonomous vessel. The size of this safety perimeter depends on characteristics and status (underway, mooring and anchored at berth) of the autonomous vessel. The critical control level would in this case be triggered by a violation of said safety perimeter by another vessel.
- **Handling the critical control level**
Three ways have been identified to solve critical traffic situations by human intervention from the SCC. A first way is to introduce a remote control handover to an operator. Based on a virtual reality bridge and simulation like transmission of acoustic and motion senses this operator would be able to solve the situation. In this case, getting the human-machine interaction right is extremely important. A quick selection of waypoints by the SCC is a second way to solve the situation, be it on a much smaller scale than previously discussed within the tactical control level. After identification of a critical traffic situation, a shore-based operator could use a selection of waypoints to set a new path for the autonomous vessel. Alternate route proposal is the third way by which the critical control level can be handled. In this case, whenever the tactical route planning of the autonomous vessel has failed and the critical control level is triggered, a human operator asks the autonomous vessel for a series of new paths to solve the situation. The operator then selects the optimal path based on his judgment. In any such case, the human operator uses the VHF-infrastructure to communicate about his actions to other traffic participants in the sector.

3.4. Solutions within the super critical control level

The super critical control level is triggered when the critical solution model is unable to solve the situation. The inputs are the same as for the critical control level. However communication with the super critical element is impossible, and the control level therefore requires more specialized concepts that do not rely exclusively on externally provided information.

- **Identification of super critical situations**
Super critical situations require sophisticated sensors and control systems on board of the autonomous vessel to identify alien elements in the immediate surroundings. To classify situations like encountering a person or debris in the water or an oil spill as (non-)hazardous,

a whitelist could be used again. This idea has been introduced in paragraph 3.3.1. A blacklist can be used as an alternative. In that case a list of hazardous items and corresponding reactions is used to assess and, in the next stage, solve the situation. A last possibility is again continuous human supervision. This would require extensive concentration and high work load for the operator at any time and is therefore not recommended.

- Handling the super critical control level

This control level can be handled in three ways. Either the systems on board the autonomous vessel are fully autonomous. In this case, an autonomous reaction of the vessel is triggered when a super critical situation is encountered. This requires significant advances in artificial intelligence research. The second way is again remote control. This possibility does not differ significantly from the concepts proposed in paragraph 3.3.2 and will not be further elaborated in this research. A third conceivable concept would be to have an automatic reaction to super critical situations, i.e. a warning to the SCC or other vessels, after which remote control takes over to actually solve the situation.

4. Future developments

By outlining certain future developments, it was possible to link the identified concepts to certain developments and provide a discussion on their applicability. Both the area of operation as well as possible investors are used to assess the qualities of the concepts. The concepts each require certain technical breakthroughs to assure their full functionality. This is treated in the third paragraph of this section.

4.1. Area of operation

Within the area of operation domain there are two main parameters that influence the concept solutions of control levels. In the first place the operational range for the autonomous shuttle service determines the size of the area of operations. The operational range influences the design (i.e. capacity) of the vessel. Furthermore, the operational range determines the organizational complexity for monitoring/controlling the autonomous vessel. Secondly the traffic density, i.e. the amount of vessels in the area of operation, is of importance.

- Operational range

The operational range has two major extremes: locally, within a single port basin, and covering the entire harbor. This influences the maximum distance the autonomous vessel has to travel. Increasing the operational range of the autonomous shuttle service influences organizational requirements the most. Examples are the increased risk of disruptions in planning schedules and difficulties regarding intersectoral communications and autonomous vessel coordination. Furthermore, increasing the range means a longer tactical route, with possibly more elaborate information processing requirements followed by an increased likelihood of critical and super critical control level triggers. On the strategic control level, a longer distance makes a liner service preferable. The cargo based concept solution would be much more organizationally complex due to the increased number of variables in container transport time optimization. On the tactical level, a longer distance results in more possibilities for ship platooning. For critical situations the use of safety perimeters or a whitelist are preferred because continuous human supervision would not be feasible on the long distance.

- Traffic density

An increased number of vessels and thus a decrease in the amount of space for maneuver directly results in more situations that pertain to the critical control level. The volume of container transport by ship is expected to grow within the port of Rotterdam, *Rotterdam Port Authority (2011)*, which stresses the importance of this parameter mainly for critical solutions. On the strategic control level, a higher traffic density has consequences for route planning abilities in for instance the cargo based solutions. The strategic control level does not use real-

time vessel locations, but does benefit from statistical traffic data. By using statistical data on traffic density more efficient routes can be planned, which avoid high traffic areas as much as possible. On the tactical level higher traffic density favors the portwide route optimization most, since in this concept all routes are planned. Therefore critical are situations avoided and communication through VHF becomes unnecessary. On the critical and super critical level, sensor systems and object classification systems would seem more suitable for a white- or blacklist, as more information could be processed faster compared to human supervision.

4.2. Investors

The second subject of future development refers to parties that could be interested in investing in the concept of an autonomous container shuttle. Five major possible investors have been identified: terminal operators, the port authority, the inland shipping community, shippers and external high-tech companies. The vision on the priorities and attitudes are based on interviews conducted with different parties prior to this paper.

- **Terminal operators**
The first possibility is that one or more terminal operators invest in the concept. The important aspect in this case is that there should be no interference with the schedules of their clients; i.e. the seagoing ships. The priorities of terminal operators are flexibility and realizing a profit by saving time (and preferably also money) compared to alternatives like inland shipping. On the strategic level, cargo based scheduling provides the most efficient and flexible solution for the terminal operators. On the tactical control level, the concept of anticipating traffic situations is preferred. The flexibility of ship platooning is deemed too low because of the dependency on other vessels to follow and the portwide route optimization is too expensive for terminals. Having continuous human supervision is quite expensive, since a specially trained person will have to be employed. On the critical and super critical control level, autonomous identification of these situations is therefore expected.
- **Port authority**
The port authority already gathers and processes large amounts of information on vessel and planning information with systems like HaMIS and Portbase for the port of Rotterdam, which stresses their organizational value. The port authority is concerned with improving the port image by investing in innovation whilst still maintaining high standards of sustainability and safety. This safety constraint might lead to a less progressive stance than terminal operators. The port authority will not become an operator of the autonomous vessel, but its involvement is favorable, because of the existing IT infrastructure and data provided by HaMIS and Portbase. Within the strategic control level, the cargo based scheduling could use the mentioned infrastructure and is therefore the preferred solution. On the tactical level portwide route optimization is favored because it offers a route optimizing solution for the entire port and therefore improves planning not only for the autonomous vessel, but also for other vessels. However, due to the far-reaching implications of this concept it will not be easily implemented. For reasons of safety, human supervision and remote control are expected to be favored on the critical and super critical control level.
- **Inland shipping community**
The Dutch community of inland shipping has already expressed some interest in autonomous shipping in talks with this sector. Its main characteristics are the limited budget available for research and development purposes and a rather conservative overall stance. This means they remain a strong advocate of the current system of VHF-communications. The autonomous vessel should, understandably, interfere as little as possible with manned (inland) vessels. On tactical level this means that strong resistance against the concept of portwide route optimization is to be expected, since the job of captain would lose a lot of its prestige. Ship platooning is likely to be the best accepted solution within this community. On the critical and super critical level a combination of a whitelist or blacklist and a safety perimeter is to be expected, coupled to an automated object detection system.

- **Shippers**
Shippers choose the modalities used for container transshipment and the technology of the chosen modality is secondary to the costs of the transport. Their priorities lie with safety, reliability and sticking to the set schedule for the container transport. They might see the concept of an autonomous container shuttle as a way of lowering the cost of container transport within the port. On a tactical level anticipating traffic situations is favored, based on the ability to find the fastest route to the destination without deviating too much from the original planning. Ship platooning could be an alternative, but only in combination with a long operational range due to possible lack of effectiveness (i.e. lack of sufficient ships to follow) otherwise.
- **External high-tech companies**
External companies involved in high-tech system development could see the autonomous container shuttle as a source of income. If profitable, the concept could be used to showcase the state-of-the-art in technological achievements of the company. The concept could also be implemented in various ports. External companies hold little to no relation to the port organization. As a result and because of stringent organizational requirements throughout the concept solutions it is unlikely that any such party would be the sole investor. The drive for innovation within these companies combined with their technical expertise leads to critical and super critical concepts which are outside the current scope of this research due to their expected complexity. Highly automated detection and response systems are to be expected from this party.

4.3. Required technological evolutions

After discussing the possible control concepts by looking at the area of operation and possible investors in the previous two paragraphs, it is now possible to link them also to necessary technological breakthroughs or innovations. We look at the field of sensing and artificial intelligence and then discuss the concepts that are the most demanding.

- **Sensing**
Within the field of sensing, one can distinguish the detection of situations or obstacles around the vessel and the ability of humans to remotely monitor these surroundings and interpret the information as if they were on board themselves. As the facilities for remote control, not the suggested control concepts, largely determine the quality of remote sensing, we focus solely on improvements in the field of camera optics, LIDAR range and imaging improvement as well as object identification and classification. On the tactical level, the concept solution that benefits most from this development is the anticipation of traffic situations. This is due to the requirements for this concept regarding LIDAR range and accuracy. Ship platooning would also benefit from this development, however the requirements are less stringent because of the shorter range needed. On the critical level object classification and improved situational awareness make the whitelist concept more likely. This whitelist could be more detailed and therefore critical situations could be identified earlier, with fewer false alarms.
- **Artificial intelligence**
The form of artificial intelligence that we suspect to be of major importance for the application of autonomous ships is machine learning. This denotes the ability of the system to learn from previous experiences and use this gained experience for solving or avoiding future situations. As the machine learning ability of the vessel increases, this directly influences the autonomy and the involvement of humans in the control. On the tactical level, evolution in this field would be most beneficial to the concept of anticipating traffic situations, since this is the most autonomous within the provided concept solutions. On the critical control level, increased autonomy in combination with a continuously decreasing blacklist can in the long run replace the currently expected need for remote control in critical and super critical situations. If improvements in artificial intelligence are linked to speech recognition technology, this combination would strongly influence the ability of the autonomous vessel to

participate in port traffic through the current standards of VHF-communication. The autonomous vessel would be able to interpret and broadcast information through the existing VHF-infrastructure. This evolution would be the most useful for anticipating traffic situations as intentions can now be easily communicated to other non-autonomous vessels.

5. Conclusions and discussion

The various challenges that present themselves when an autonomous vessel navigates between conventional vessels in a port environment have been classified into four control levels: strategic, tactical, critical and super critical. This has proven to be a useful way to identify solutions that are able to address these difficulties. Mainly the critical control level remains a challenge to solve autonomously, and human control is currently seen as the only way to solve these situations. Critical and super critical situations could however be detected by autonomous systems, which then transfer the control to a shore-based operator. To simplify the interaction between autonomous and conventional vessels, vessel behavior needs to be made more predictable. This predictability can be increased by sharing routes and schedules between autonomous and conventional vessels. The main requirement for an integration of manned and unmanned vessel routes is the gathering of information from multiple sources. Such can be concluded from the presented concepts on the strategic and tactical level. As the port authority already gathers a lot of this required information, we advise to include said party in the further development of this application of autonomous navigation. Collecting accurate vessel and route information will remain a challenge in the future.

VHF-communications are expected to remain of great importance. For the autonomous vessel this means that a part of the VHF-communication is to be taken over by a shore control center. On condition of further development of current systems like AIS and ECDIS, the remainder of the communication, i.e. communication regarding vessel intentions, can be sent digitally between vessels or from the autonomous vessel to the shore control center. This will strengthen concepts within the tactical control level.

We have assumed no change in responsibility for the platooning solution. It would be an interesting first application however to have a manned ship sailing a fixed route within the port, followed by a platoon consisting of various autonomous shuttles. The shuttles could then serve different terminals, joining and leaving the platoon when required. In this case it would be more convenient to make the leading vessel responsible for the autonomous vessels in the platoon. A special training for the captain of said vessel will probably be necessary.

One of the most important uncertainties that significantly influences the effectiveness of the proposed solutions, is the cooperation and the sharing of information between the various involved parties. Our experience is that there are objections mainly from terminal operators against sharing detailed information about for instance individual containers. The reason for this is their fear to endanger their market position by sharing information about their clients. In the view of the authors, cooperation remains however the ultimate means to realize the goal of an effective autonomous container shuttle within the port of Rotterdam. Leverage through policy control measures at the state level could be a conceivable move forward.

The role of the government can either be directive, subsidizing or facilitating. In the directive case, the government would actively pursue further research into autonomous waterborne transport in ports, by imposing e.g. innovation quota. That way strong incentives would be created for companies to participate in research and pilot projects. The subsidizing role implies that the government limits itself to creating financial stimulants, in order to passively stimulate innovative projects not specifically related to the implementation of autonomous waterborne transport in ports. A facilitating government would mean that the government creates a legal framework which simplifies implementation of autonomous waterborne transport in ports by solving the inherent legal and ethical issues.

No matter the assumed role, the government has to play an important part in regulating operational safety and acceptance by the general public. Regulation backlog on technological advances should at all times be minimized. For the application of autonomous transport within the port area, a small scale closed pilot and open test should be performed with permission from the regulatory bodies to gather information. In view of a possible control system failure, a thorough failure mode effect analysis should be performed for propulsion, navigation and communication systems on board the autonomous vessel. Subsequently emergency procedures should be determined. For classification societies it would be an option to introduce the autonomous vessel as an entirely new class. As with all autonomous systems, there is a large uncertainty about accountability and legal liability for the actions of the autonomous vessel. In case of remote control the liability is easier to determine than in case of fully autonomous concepts. Finally, we recommend consulting and working with a representation of the general public for a successful implementation and to enlarge public support for autonomous waterborne transport.

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Silverstream[®] System – Air Lubrication Performance Verification and Design Development

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Abstract

In this paper Silverstream Technologies present their experience of developing air lubrication technology and proving the effectiveness of their system through the use of tank testing, full scale sea trials and long term performance monitoring. The challenges of demonstrating in-service performance and the techniques used to account for weather and sea state effects are outlined, as are the developments in the design of the system to further increase its simplicity. The result of these efforts has led to proven net savings in excess of 4%, commercial contracts and projected savings of 8% across vessel types.

1. Introduction

Air lubrication has long been thought of as a viable method for reducing the frictional resistance of waterborne vessels. Many methods have been proposed and tested over the last decades, but no single method of achieving the desired net energy reduction has been fully adopted by the industry. Silverstream Technologies air lubrication system, the Silverstream[®] System was created from the experience gained through trialling differing designs, with varying degrees of success. This process of designing and testing in full scale began around a decade ago and has culminated in a constrained set of parameters that are used to achieve the efficient production of micro-bubbles beneath the ship's hull.

The first installation of the Silverstream[®] System, retrofitted on the 40,000 dwt chemical tanker M/T AMALIENBORG, was followed by ballast and laden sea trials. This demonstrated that the air lubrication system delivered overall net savings of 4.3% and 3.8% respectively. This initial installation was sponsored by Shell and the savings were independently verified by LR and HSVA. To go a step further, it was decided that the energy savings in normal operational conditions should be investigated. Over a period of 11 months of operation, performance data was collected and analysed to demonstrate actual energy savings, this showed savings in excess of 4% for unfavourable fully loaded deep draught conditions, the details of this analysis will be outlined in this paper.

The close cooperation of Dannebrog Rederi, the ship owner of this installation, has allowed Silverstream Technologies to monitor the vessel over the past two years of operation, answering many of the questions that are commonly raised with this technology. These include the effect of waves on performance, marine growth on the hull and air ingestion into the propeller, details of which will be outlined in this paper.

In addition to performance of the system, continued efforts have been made to improve the practicality and usability of the system reducing its impact on the crew and the vessel, making it more cost effective and easier to install. These developments include an updated control and monitoring that allows the system to self-adjust without crew intervention. The drag of the cavities when the system is switched OFF has also been reduced by over 50% through design optimisation and the results of this will be outlined in this paper.

2. In-Service Performance Monitoring

The air lubrication technology has the main advantage that it can be switched ON and OFF at any time so that the resistance reduction effect can be immediately measured. A performance monitoring system has been installed on the vessel which collects all the required parameters for the reliable evaluation of performance and efficiency gain. High frequency data and 5-minute average data have been collected, these are primarily main engine RPM, speed through water and GPS, shaft power (torque), compressor power consumed, fuel consumption through mass flow meters and other weather parameters from the hindcast model. An example of the effect of the Silverstream® System on the shaft power reduction and speed increase can be seen below in the 5-minute output data.

Fig. 1: Example Air Lubrication Effect from Monitoring System

2.1 Data Set

Given the complexity of analysing the in service performance of the vessel, which is affected by many variables most of which can become non-linear, it is necessary to organise and filter the data in a logical and accepted method. Guidance has been obtained from the draft ISO standard 19030, 'Measurement of Changes in Hull and Propeller Performance'. The performance data was filtered to include only moderate environmental conditions, it is Silverstream Technologies opinion that accurately monitoring and determining the performance in heavy seas introduces uncertainties in the results due to the non-linearity of ocean sea states and vessel response. This methodology is also reflected in the draft ISO standard 19030. The following criteria was used for the data filtering:

- Significant Wave Height < 2.5m (Sea State 4) – This is in line with the recommendations in ISO 15016 sea trials standard and reduces the influence of added resistance due to waves.
- True Wind Speed < 7.9 m/s (BF 4) – This is in line with the recommendations of the draft ISO 19030.

- Water depth > 60m – Water depth was limited to ensure shallow water effects were not included and in accordance with the draft ISO 19030. This also serves to increase the accuracy of hindcast data used to determine the wave height.
- Rudder Angle $-1^{\circ} < \text{Angle} < 2^{\circ}$ – This is used to minimise the effect of added resistance due to rudder angle. As propeller rotation causes a small turning moment on the vessel, there is always a small positive rudder angle. The limitations, therefore, allowed for this constant small rudder angle.
- Rate of Turn $< \pm 0.01^{\circ}/\text{s}$ – Data was filtered to remove the effects of manoeuvring, performance monitoring has shown that this has a significant effect on vessel speed and shaft power.
- RPM > 90 – Only of interest is vessel data whilst underway. Anytime the vessel is below 90 RPM indicates a transient phase (i.e. slowing down or speeding up) this should therefore be removed.
- Log Speed > 10 knots – Speeds below 10 knots were considered anomalies for RPM greater than 90 and removed.
- Shaft Power > 2500 kW (30% MCR) – The few data points where shaft power was less than 2500 kW for an RPM greater than 90 are considered outliers and removed.
- Silverstream[®] System Power < 80 kW – To avoid 5 minute points which contain the transient period of system ON/OFF.

An 11 month data set was taken from the performance monitoring system for the period of March 2015 to January 2016. The filtered data was organised by loading condition, the predominant draught is laden between 10 to 11m, this accounts for 60% of the filtered data. Only 15% of the data was for ballast condition. As the vessel is predominantly trading in a laden condition, the proportion of ballast data in the observation period is insufficient for the analysis. The ballast data is also recorded over a limited range of RPM values, this causes unrealistic power curves to be plotted and results are considered to be inaccurate. For this reason, the analysis is limited to laden condition with average draught between 10 and 11 m.

It was found that increasing the draught range in the data set only serves to increase the inaccuracy of results as the separation of system ON and OFF data become blurred by the increase and/or decrease in vessel resistance due to the draught.

When sufficient ballast data is available, a similar analysis as outlined in this document to be undertaken as it has been shown that efficiency gain results are more favourable in the lower draught ballast condition. This is due to a larger proportion of the wetted surface area being lubricated and there is a lower power requirement for the compressors due to the lower back pressure.

2.2 Data Analysis

The initial data set included around 100,000, 5 minute average data points. After removing data through the filtering limitations described above, this data set was reduced to 13,800 data points that were considered in the performance analysis. This comprised around 8,400 ‘System ON’ and 5,400 ‘System OFF’ data points. In order to determine the effect of the Silverstream[®] System the data was first divided into system ON and OFF. A scatter plot of the data points can be seen in Fig.2.

It is not possible to accurately plot a speed-power trend line directly through a scatter plot, such as that seen in Fig.2, using automated graphing functions. The vessel does not spend an equal amount of time at each RPM and therefore there is not an equal number of system ON and OFF data points. The fitting of the power curve would be biased towards those speeds where most of the data points lie, the result of this is inaccurate fitting of the trend line. Therefore, the system ON and OFF data is arranged in terms of shaft RPM and the average speed and power at each RPM is taken. With sufficient data, this forms a scatter of data points that can be used to estimate the power curve with equal weighting given to all RPMs (speed and power). The result of this ‘RPM averaged data’ is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.2: Filtered Laden Data

Fig.3: Average Shaft Power for given RPM against Speed

The trend line is plotted using the regression function that produces a line with the formula $y = ax^b$. This is considered appropriate for the purpose of comparison of data; however the shape of a ships speed-power curve will likely be different. Using the formula for the trend line for system ON and OFF data, the gross savings due to the air lubrication have been presented over the range of operating

speeds in Table 1. The values were not corrected for compressor power or drag of the air release units and these savings represent the pure effect of the air on the hull resistance.

Table 1: Gross Power Savings (not corrected)

Log Speed knots	Shaft Power – OFF kW	Shaft Power – ON kW	Gross Saving kW	Gross Saving %
11	3089	2935	155	5.0%
11.5	3632	3432	199	5.5%
12	4240	3988	252	5.9%
12.5	4919	4605	314	6.4%
13	5673	5287	386	6.8%
13.5	6509	6039	470	7.2%
14	7429	6865	565	7.6%

The power curve trend lines for system ON and OFF, shown in Fig.3, must be corrected to account for the additional drag of the air release units when the system is turned OFF and the consumption of the Silverstream® System. The drag was estimated for the AMALIENBORG through CFD calculations to be 1.3% of shaft power in laden condition. Therefore, the system OFF curve is reduced by 1.3% to allow for the fact that part of the efficiency gain is the reduction of the drag. Drag of the air release units will be further discussed in Section 5.0. The system ON curve is also adjusted by combining the average power consumption of the compressors at each RPM and the shaft power value. The corresponding separation of the curves is therefore the net efficiency gain attributable to the air lubrication effect. This is shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Corrected Average Shaft Power for given RPM against Speed

Using the produced formula for the power curves of system ON and OFF data, the indicated net savings can be calculated over a range of vessel log speeds. These are presented for the operational range of the vessel in Table 2 and shows increasing savings with increasing speed.

Table 2: Calculated Net Efficiency Results

Log Speed knots	Shaft Power - OFF kW	Shaft Power - ON kW	Net Power Saving kW	Net Saving %
11	3049	3048	2	0.1%
11.5	3585	3553	32	0.9%
12	4185	4115	70	1.7%
12.5	4855	4737	118	2.4%
13	5600	5424	176	3.2%
13.5	6424	6178	246	3.8%
14	7333	7004	329	4.5%

3. Performance in Waves and the Path of Improvement (Skewed Ladder)

A question that is often asked about air lubrication is how effective the drag reduction remains when the vessel is operating in a seaway, pitching and rolling due to the waves. To demonstrate the effect, the following data shows how the air lubrication remains effective with increasing wave heights.

An example of a typical data set obtained over a three day period from 7th to 9th February 2015, is shown in Fig.5. This was a period of constant main engine (ME) / Propeller RPM and with varying weather conditions. This was during a ballast voyage in the Indian Ocean where conditions were variable and significant wave heights ranged from 0.7 to 2.2 m. These changing conditions combined with changes in heading of 80 degrees resulted in spreading of the ON/OFF results at constant RPM.

The shaft power is plotted against log speed for the system ON and OFF condition. As can be seen in the figure, we obtain a separation between the 'ON' and 'OFF' points and the data scatter exhibits a curved tail trend. Each point on the graph represents a 5 minute average value. The ballast speed-power curve of the vessel is also plotted to demonstrate that how the weather effects the performance.

Fig.5: Silverstream ON/OFF

The vessel, with a fixed ME RPM setting, requires more power and moves slower through the water as it encounters heavier weather. Points to the right represent smaller wave heights with significant wave height (H_s)=0.75 m and to the left, bigger waves of H_s =2.2 m (maximum wave heights (H_{max}) of 1.25 m to 3.6 m, respectively). Angle of incidence of waves also has an effect, but provided the vessel maintains course, the changes are generally slower over time.

The system was turned OFF approximately twice per day for about one hour, in order to establish the baseline data for the prevailing conditions. In order to demonstrate how the performance changes when the system is operational, the data can be further divided into smaller time frames to capture similar headings and wave heights. Fig.6 shows multiple data sets for similar vessel headings on each of the three days.

Fig.6: Divided Data

The data falls into two groups, these relate to different headings, whilst the remaining scatter is due to the effect of added resistance due to waves. It is also shown that the results show a reduction of shaft power and a gain in speed when the system is activated. Taking the average of each data group of ON/OFF periods and plotting these points onto the original data set, the shift of the trend line can be demonstrated based on this further analysis of the data.

As can be observed from the change in all weather conditions that the power reduces and the speed increased. Although the changes do not always follow the same gradient, due to various factors, the underlying trend indicates that a function exists between the ON and conditions. The varying sea states giving rise to the indicated skewed ladder function, and demonstrating that the performance gain due to the Silverstream[®] System continues with increasing sea states.

Fig.7: 7th to 9th February Performance Shift due ON/OFF in Varying Weather Conditions

4. Hull Coating and Propeller Condition

The most common questions around air lubrication technology surrounds the effect of the air bubble layer on the ships propeller and the hull surface. Before the first installation there were concerns that the micro-bubble layer created by the air release units could cause cavitation damage to the propeller or damage the paintwork, and even increase the hull fouling. It has since been demonstrated that these fears were onerous and the bubble carpet has no negative impact on the vessel.

Cavitation erosion is caused by the implosion of a vacuum bubble that collapses on the surface of the propeller due to rapid changes in pressure, this can lead to damage to the metal surface. The air bubbles introduced onto the hull bottom surface are pressurised bubbles of air and therefore cannot implode like a vacuum bubble to cause damage to the propeller. In addition, as the air layer is reducing the load on the propeller (by reducing the resistance) the chance of cavitation damage is also reduced as the operating point of the propeller moves away from the cavitation point.

Fig.8:Two Year Dive Survey - Propeller

To confirm this theory, measurements were taken during the sea trials and annual dive surveys have been carried out since the system installation. These have shown the propeller to be in good condition with no signs of damage or marine growth. It is therefore evident that the small quantity of air that

may be ingested into the propeller poses no risk to cavitation damage. It is also evident that the condition of the propeller remains clean and there has been no requirement for propeller polishing, contrary to what might be expected two and half years after dry docking. The condition of the propeller on the second annual dive survey are shown in Fig.8.

The condition of the hull has also been closely monitored since the installation. Annual dive surveys confirm that the hull bottom was free of marine growth and the antifouling remains effective. In general, it can be said that the condition of the hull bottom appears in a good condition, and is considered better than what could be expected after two years of operation. Images of the hull condition from the second annual dive survey can be seen in Fig.9.

Fig.9: Two Year Dive Survey - Hull

The conclusions from this monitoring through regular dive surveys confirm that there are no adverse effects to the vessel from the air micro-bubble carpet. It is too early at this stage to conclude that the air bubbles are reducing the onset of hull and propeller fouling, although the evidence points to this significant secondary saving effect. Future dive surveys will provide further evidence for this added benefit from the Silverstream® System.

5. Air Release Unit Drag Reduction

Silverstream Technologies have invested significant effort in improving the simplicity and usability of its system. Besides improving the layout of the system to reduce the space requirements and advances in automation and control, significant reduction in the drag of the air release units have been made. They were modified to reduce the drag created in the event that the system is turned OFF. This was achieved by testing new patented configurations of the air release units.

A cavitation tunnel was used to simulate in full scale the conditions experienced beneath the ship hull. The resistance is measured directly in the cavitation tunnel, the air release unit is in full scale and the water is at real speeds. First, the resistance of the whole model of the plate with the air release units closed is measured and then the resistance of the whole plate with air release units 'open' is measured. Each air release unit was also tested to ensure the lubricating bubble layer was produced effectively.

The force is measured on a plate around 8 m long, this includes the air release unit along with an area of plate downstream. Therefore, the resistance measurement will also capture the turbulent flow created downstream of the air release unit. The graph below shows the measured resistance of one air release unit when the system is turned OFF (no air supply) the previous 2015 design, along with the current 2016 design of air release unit.

Based on the measured drag of the air release unit, the overall effect on a typical cruise vessel can be calculated for both the 2015 and 2016 design. The vessel resistance is calculated using an estimated propulsion efficiency and comparing the increase in resistance of a complete Silverstream® System installed in the hull bottom, without the air compressors activated.

Fig.10: HSVA HYKAT Layout

Fig.11: Drag Comparison Based on HSVA Data

Table 3: Air Release Unit Drag % of Ship Resistance

Speed	Vessel Resistance	ARU 2015 Resistance (14)	ARU 2016 Resistance (14)	ARU 2015 Resistance (14)	ARU 2016 Resistance (14)
[kn]	[N]	[N]	[N]	% of Total	% of Total
15	867013	7725	3584	0.89%	0.41%
18	1248345	10689	4667	0.86%	0.37%
20	1541096	12928	5456	0.84%	0.35%

The above calculation shows clearly the 2016 insert design delivers over 50% reduction in drag compared with the 2015 design and has a calculated resistance of 0.35% at 20 knots. The previous insert resistance had a calculated increase of 0.84% at 20 knots for a typical cruise vessel. Estimates have been made for other vessel types such as LNGCs which confirm negligible resistance increase due to the air release unit design.

6. Conclusions

Conclusions from In-Service Performance Monitoring

- A method for calculating the long term efficiency gain has been developed and is considered sufficiently robust.
- The analysis indicates increased efficiency savings with increasing speed that is consistent with previous tank testing and sea trials findings.
- At current vessel operating speeds of 14 knots, equivalent to 70% MCR, gross savings of 7.6% and net savings of 4.5% have been demonstrated.
- The Silverstream System continues to work effectively in service and provides a long term benefit in terms of energy and consequential fuel saving.
- It is reasonable to conclude from the findings and tank tests that a vessel with higher operating speeds greater than 17 knots and with a larger lubricated flat bottom area can expect savings of 6% to 8%.

Conclusions of Hull and Propeller Monitoring

- The air bubble layer poses no risk to cavitation damage to the propeller.
- The air bubble layer has not eroded or damaged the antifouling coat of the hull.
- The air bubble layer has not affected hull fouling and evidence suggests that marine growth may be inhibited on the flat bottom and the propeller.

Conclusions of the Drag Reduction

- Overall relative drag effect of the air release units reduces with speed.
- The drag has been reduced by over 50% compared to previous designs whilst maintaining the lubrication effect.
- Estimated drag of the air release units for an LNGC or typical cruise vessel is well below 0.5%.

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Experience with Rim-Driven Azimuthing Thrusters on the Research Ship “Gunnerus”

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Abstract

The research ship “Gunnerus” of the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) is one of the smallest ships in the world that has a fully-featured diesel-electric propulsion plant. This, together with it being a research vessel already, was an important pre-requisite for it being selected as test platform for a new line of Permanent Magnet (PM) rim-drive azimuthing thrusters from Rolls-Royce. Replacing the original twin fixed-pitch ducted propellers with azimuths, we expected to get increased low-speed manoeuvrability and dynamic-positioning capability. However, the PM rim drive technology is expected to have other important benefits, especially in terms of responsiveness. In order to document the changes in performance, we performed an extensive full scale test program covering performance with respect to speed, bollard pull, inboard and emitted noise, and manoeuvring in low and cruising speed, testing the ship first with the conventional propellers and then with new PM azimuth propellers. Some of the results were as one could expect, other findings were surprising. The paper explains some novel analysis methods, outlines the results and discusses reasons for the differences in performance, as well as discussing the potential of PM thruster technology in combination with new power plant configurations, such as hybrid power plants.

1. Introduction

Azimuthing thrusters are increasingly used also for main propulsion of specialized ships, due to the excellent station keeping and low speed manoeuvrability they offer. Also, propulsion plants for such vessel are increasingly diesel-electric, rather than the directly driving diesel plants of standardized merchant vessels. Conventional azimuthing thrusters have a complicated mechanical drive-line, involving at least one, usually two bevel gear stages to link the propeller to the inboard motor. The pod, having the electric motor integrated into the lower gear housing of the thruster, was introduced to get rid of the gears and mechanical drive line. The recent rapid development of Permanent Magnet motor technology has enabled making such electric pods also in smaller sizes, and many manufacturers have developed designs to utilize this in their thruster products. The permanent magnet motor technology also makes it practically possible to realize the old idea of driving a ducted propeller from the duct rather than from a shaft connected to a central propeller hub. Driving the propeller from the rim, integrated into the duct, means that one can reduce the dimensions of hub and shaft, and if bearings are also integrated into the duct, one can get rid of the hub entirely, and the propeller tip gap is eliminated. Brunvoll and Voith have developed such units, where the blades are actually not connected in the centre. Rolls-Royce has developed tunnel thrusters of the rim-drive type, using PM motors and bearings integrated in the tunnel. For their more recent azimuthing thruster design, they have decided to keep a central shaft with bearings.

The research vessel “Gunnerus”, Fig.1, owned and operated by the Norwegian University of Science and Technology was delivered from Larsnes Mek in 2006, and with a length of only 31.25 m (see Table 1 for further details) it is believed to be one of the smallest ships with a fully-featured diesel-electric propulsion plant. The ship has a twin skeg aft body, and when delivered it was equipped with twin conventional five-bladed fixed-pitch propellers in 19A ducts, delivered by Finnøy Gear & Propeller.

Fig.1: The research vessel “Gunnerus” (Photo: Fredrik Skoglund)

Table 1: Main dimensions of R/V “Gunnerus”

Length overall [m]	31.25
Length between perp. [m]	28.90
Length in waterline [m]	29.90
Breadth middle [m]	9.60
Mean Draught [m]	2.60

The small size of R/V “Gunnerus”, the fact that it has a diesel-electric propulsion plant and is already a research vessel means that it was a perfect choice for being a test platform for the new PM azimuthing thruster by Rolls-Royce. Therefore, during winter 2015 the twin ducted propellers and rudders were removed and replaced with two Rolls-Royce PM Azimuth thrusters. Photos of the stern of the vessel before and after the retrofit are shown in Fig.2, while the old and new propellers are shown in more detail in Fig.3.

Fig.2: Stern arrangement of “Gunnerus” before (left) and after (right) retrofit of azimuth thrusters.

Fig.3: Old (left) and new (right) propeller systems

The original propellers were five-bladed, high skew propellers of 2.0 m diameter in a 19A duct, while the new azimuthing thrusters had an innovative forward skew propeller design with four blades, while the duct profile is Rolls-Royce InnoDuct. The split strut is patented, and Rolls-Royce has found that it gives a significant improvement in efficiency. The original propeller installation had rather large ice-fins, Fig.3, which were removed when the thrusters were installed.

To document the effect of the change of propulsion system, an extensive test program was carried out both before and after retrofitting the PM azimuthing thrusters. The tests comprised:

- Speed-power trials
- Acceleration
- Cruising speed manoeuvring
- DP and low speed crabbing
- Underwater and inboard noise

2. Instrumentation, measurements and test campaigns

2.1 Test campaigns

R/V “Gunnerus” has been subject to several test campaigns, in both calm water and in waves, investigating both straight-ahead performance and various manoeuvres. In this paper, the results of the following campaigns are presented:

- Before retrofit:
 - Original noise trials, performed by DNV shortly after delivery in 2006, in Rovdefjorden
 - Calm water performance, performed August 2013 by MARINTEK and NTNU, in Trondheimsfjorden
- After retrofit:
 - Calm water performance and noise measurements, performed August 2015 by MARINTEK, NTNU, and DNV-GL in Trondheimsfjorden.

2.2 Instrumentation

“Gunnerus” is equipped with a Kongsberg Seapath 330, which was used to obtain measurements of position, course, heading, speed over ground, and motions and accelerations. An anemometer was mounted to measure relative wind speed and direction. For the original configuration, the rudder angles were measured by mounting wire-over-potentiometer sensors directly on the rudder stocks. Due to extremely short lengths of the propeller shafts it wasn't possible to measure the propeller shaft torque. Instead, the power supplied to the propeller motors were measured from outputs of the motor drives. For the azimuthing thrusters, azimuth angle, electric power supplied to the PM motors, and propeller RPM were measured by interfacing with the Rolls-Royce Health and Monitoring System (HEMOS). All the mentioned measurements were collected on the same PC, to minimize phase difference between signals and to ease the subsequent analysis.

3. Test Results

3.1. Speed-power trials

When the project started very small changes were expected in the powering performances of the vessel; this combined with the radical changes to the machinery of the vessel requires care in carrying out the tests and interpreting the data. Due to the limited length of shaft of the original propulsive system and the total absence of inboard shafts for the new system, a traditional torque measurement was not possible. It was decided instead to focus on the power delivered by the power converters to either the electric motors or the rim driven thrusters; although this choice does not allow for

comparing directly the hydrodynamic performances of the propellers, it provides a consistent measurement point across the two configurations and points in the direction of a systemic view of the propulsive system; point of view that has been sought throughout the entire project. The present paragraph details how the measurements were carried out and the results from the tests in 2013 with the shaft driven propeller and in 2015 with the rim driven thrusters.

The 2013 and 2015 sea trials were conducted in the same area of the Trondheimsfjord. The water depth at the location of the tests is on average 250 meters, i.e. the tests have been performed in deep water. The weather condition in the Trondheimsfjord are typically rather unstable, but high sea states are seldom encountered especially during the summer months. Fig.4 depicts a comparison of the ship motions in 2013 and 2015 in terms of standard deviation of pitch and roll motions; the figure clearly show that the ship motions were small and almost identical in amplitude.

Fig.4: Comparison of ship motions in 2013 and 2015

In Fig.5 the wind condition in 2013 and 2015 are reported; it shall be noted that a wave buoy measured the wind in 2013, whereas the same buoy was not available in 2015 and the wind data have been collected on board of the vessel. It shall further be noted that some runs were performed with the vessel keeping a course 90 degrees apart from the standard "0 – 180 degrees to the wind" track used during sea trials; this last series of runs were performed in order to further reduce the influence of the environmental condition on the results.

Fig.5: Wind condition in 2013 (left) and 2015 (right)

Finally, in 2015, the vessel was loaded to have a water line as close as possible to the waterline tested in 2013; the two waterlines are compared in Table 2. The differences between the two waterlines are limited to 7 cm in trim and less than 3 t in displacement; it is, therefore, possible to use the Admiralty-formula to account for the small discrepancy in the loading condition as suggested also by the ITTC procedure for full-scale sea trials.

Table 2: Loading conditions for the vessel in 2013 and 2015

	Measured	Estimated	Measured	Measured	Deviation
Date	13.08.2013	14.08.2013	15.08.2013	11.08.2015	2015 vs 2013
Draught AP	3.37		3.40	3.37	
Draught FP	2.20		2.10	2.20	
Mean Draught (m)	2.60	2.58	2.56	2.60	0.68 %
Trim (Aft +) (m)	0.09	0.16	0.23	0.09	
Displacement (MT)	412.20	409.84	407.47	412.50	0.65 %

The tests were conducted using the double run procedure as described by the "ITTC recommended Procedure and Guideline 7.5-04-01-01.1" and performed when stable weather condition were encountered. In the double run procedure, two runs on the same track but in opposite direction are performed for each of the tested conditions. In the analysis of the data no correction was applied to the single runs either for the sea state or for the wind, but the two (or in some cases four) runs corresponding to the same power settings have been averaged and hence, the averaging process cancelled out most of the effects of the weather condition on the speed-power curve. Although it is acknowledged that the effect of the wind will not be fully cancelled by this procedure, it is still considered acceptable, since the wind was light (about 5 m/s) and quite the same for both test campaigns. In order to ease the comparison, the data have been interpolated and the two power curves presented as a function of the ship speed as shown in Table 3 and in Fig.6. The data collected in 2013 have been corrected to 2015 displacement of the ship by means of the Admiralty-formula.

Table 3: Ship – Power characteristic for the vessel Gunnerus in 2013 and 2015. N is propeller speed and PTOT is the total power supplied to the electric propulsion motors

V [kts]	PTOT-2013 [KW]	PTOT-2013 CORR [KW]	PTOT-2015 [KW]	N-2013 [1/min]	N-2015 [1/min]
8.0	201.0	201.8	196.6	123.6	121.5
8.5	232.4	233.4	237.2	129.7	129.9
9.0	282.5	283.7	286.2	138.2	138.7
9.5	351.0	352.5	346.3	148.4	147.8
10.0	437.5	439.4	420.4	159.7	157.4
10.5	541.8	544.1	511.3	171.5	167.5
11.0	663.4	666.2	621.9	183.2	178.1
11.5	802.0	805.4	755.1	194.1	189.4
12.0	957.2	961.4	913.5	203.7	201.5

Fig.6: Speed-power curves before (2013) and after (2015) retrofit of thrusters

Besides the obvious observation that the overall efficiency of the propulsive system is slightly better for the PM system compared to the original traditional shaft configuration, with the new system the propeller operates at a higher cavitation number; a fact that might have some positive influence on cavitation and hence on noise emissions. The reason why the efficiency of the new propulsive arrangement is better than the old one can be related to many aspects besides improved hydrodynamic design of the propulsion system; for example, the ice-fins have been removed, the hull has been overhauled while on dry dock for changing the propulsive system and the wear and tear of the old propulsive system cannot not be easily quantified. All the above mentioned aspects do not allow for definitively stating that the new system outperforms the old one from a pure speed-power curve point of view, but one can cautiously note that at least the two systems are comparable and since the new system was supposed to have better manoeuvrability characteristics at the expenses of free sailing performances, the performance of new system are better than the expectations.

3.2. Acceleration tests

This section presents surge acceleration tests carried out in 2013 and 2015 after retrofitting, and results are compared. After setting the vessel heading against mean direction of environmental forces, as good as possible, both thrusters are set to zero speed and zero azimuth angle. The tunnel thruster is also set at zero thrust and kept at zero thrust during the test. From zero motion, a step input is sent to both propulsion thrusters from 0 to 5%, the test is continued until forward speed is at steady state. Then, the test is continued with further step inputs to both propulsion thrusters (5% → 10%, 10% → 15%, 15% → 25%, 25% → 40%, 40% → 0%, 0% → 80%, and finally 80% → 0%).

To quantify the results of the surge acceleration tests a novel methodology is adopted where series of parameters are identified to fit the measured results to a simple dynamic model of the vessel. Then, the identified parameters are compared with each other and the comparison shows that the new configuration with PM azimuthing thrusters is (almost) always faster than the old configuration except when the step function is a negative one (i.e. 40 → 0% and 80 → 0%). In what follows the results are explained in detail.

For a bow-stern symmetric vessel operating in low speed, one may ignore the nonlinear damping (i.e. resistance) - When the resistance of the vessel is known, one can subtract the quadratic resistance from the total force before applying the model fitting - and describe the uncoupled surge dynamics as

$$(m - X_{\dot{u}})\dot{u} - X_u u = F_{surge} \quad (1)$$

$m - X_{\dot{u}}$ is extended mass, X_u models linear damping in low speed, and F_{surge} is the sum of control forces in surge and finally u and \dot{u} are surge speed and acceleration respectively. If we assume that F_{surge} is the force generated by propellers only, we can replace F_{surge} with a linear function of square root of propeller rotation speed. In the following tests, we have considered the square root of the propeller rotation speed as an input and the surge speed as an output.

In frequency domain, input output relation can be modelled as a first order transfer function described by

$$G(s) = \frac{K}{1 + T_p s} \quad (2)$$

Since no sync signal was measured for start of the step tests, we have augmented this model with a dead-time (between input and output) as

$$G(s) = \frac{K}{1 + T_p s} e^{-T_d s} \quad (3)$$

to minimize the effect human errors in finding the exact start time of the test.

The measured surge speed in the acceleration test of (0% → 80%), compared with the surge speed generated from a first order system with a dead time is pictured in Fig.7, where a good agreement is easily noticed. In order to compare the results quantitatively, we define the settling time of the response (denoted by T_s) as the length of time it takes the system output in response to a step input to reach and stay within a specified tolerance about the final value of the output. In this section, the tolerance for settling time in the step response will always be $\pm 5\%$ of the final value, assuming that the final value is non-zero. For a first order system with a dead time, described in Eq.(1), the $\pm 5\%$ settling time can be approximated by

Fig.7: Graphical representation of the data in an acceleration test.

$$T_s \approx T_d + 3T_p . \tag{4}$$

The comparison of the settling time in acceleration tests before and after retrofiting is summarized in Table 4. The comparison shows that the new configuration is (almost) always faster than the old configuration, except when the step function is a negative one (i.e. 40 → 0% and 80 → 0%). We believe that this is due to the different setting in the new and old configuration where one has locked or fixed propeller and the other has freewheeling propeller at zero revolution speed.

Table 4: Comparison of the computed settling time in surge acceleration tests performed on vessel Gunnerus in 2013 and 2015

Power setup	Test condition (year)	Settling Time (T_s) [sec]
0 → 5%	2015	233.23
0 → 5%	2013	246.44
4 → 9%	2015	58.41
5 → 10%	2013	205.84
9 → 15%	2015	46.73
10 → 15%	2013	445.04
15 → 25%	2015	42.10
15 → 25%	2013	184.43
25 → 40%	2015	22.20
25 → 40%	2013	100.75
40 → 0%	2015	130.88
40 → 0%	2013	52.67
0 → 80%	2015	53.34
0 → 80%	2013	45.62
80 → 0%	2015	115.27
80 → 0%	2013	22.44

3.3. Cruising speed manoeuvring tests

Standard IMO manoeuvring tests were conducted, and reported here both as result of a spiral test and a zig-zag tests. The cruising speed manoeuvring testes where performed in order to compare the manoeuvring performance of the two system, not necessarily being a good measure of the daily manoeuvring capabilities of the vessel. As for all tests, the tests are conducted with the system as-is, meaning that some responses might be due to system settings (e.g. rates) or other factors (e.g. generators), not necessary the performance of the propulsion system.

Spiral tests are conducted in order to investigate the directional stability of the vessel. During the retrofit, both ice fins and rudders where removed, which lead to questioning if the vessel still would be directionally stable. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a graphical presentation of the results of the spiral tests. The figure shows that *Gunnerus* is directionally stable both before and after retrofit. Further, the figure shows that the PM system is capable of generating a higher rate of turn than the conventional system with flap rudders.

Fig.8. Graphical presentation of the spiral tests results before and after retrofit.

Two selected 20/20 zig-zag tests are presented and compared with the first rudder deflection to starboard side. The difference between them are velocities and power. It is also worth noticing that none of the zig-zags are 100% correct, however good enough to identify some differences between the two propulsive systems. Fig.7, Fig.10**Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**1 show a comparison between test 4015 (PM thruster) and 2012 (conventional system). The figures show that the steady rudder rate of the conventional rudder and the azimuth PM thruster are close to equal, meaning that the rudder reaches 20 degrees at about the same time. Further, it is seen that the heading change is faster with the azimuth PM thruster compared to the rudder. The overshoot angles are typically smaller for the PM thruster than for the rudder. This shows that *Gunnerus* is able to obtain rate of turn faster with the azimuth thrusters than with rudders. The figures also show that the roll angles are close to each other between the two different propulsion systems, while the power consumption is lower for the PM thruster. Our main finding from the zig-zag tests is that the yaw checking ability is better with the PM system. *Gunnerus* reacts faster to a given rudder angle with azimuth PM thrusters than with rudders. The yaw rate is higher with PM thrusters compared to the rudders. Further, it is seen from the plots, that with approximately the same speed, the PM thrusters

uses less power than the conventional propulsion system. It is worth noting that the conventional system has ice fins which were removed during the retrofit.

Fig.9. Comparison of heading and rudder angle before and after retrofit during a 20/20 zig-zag test

Fig.10 Comparison of velocities and roll before and after retrofit during a 20/20 zig-zag test

3.4. DP and low speed crabbing

This section presents results of three series of tests: yaw acceleration tests, sway acceleration tests, and thruster agility tests (without yawing moment), both carried out in 2013 and 2015, before and after retrofitting.

Fig.7. Comparison of power and RPM before and after retrofit during a 20/20 zig-zag test

3.4.1 Yaw Acceleration Tests

In yaw acceleration tests (or yaw step tests), the vessel heading should be kept against mean direction of environmental forces, as good as possible, and both propulsion thrusters are set to forward speed with zero azimuth (or rudder) deflection to obtain a specified forward surge speed with constant heading. The tunnel thruster is kept at zero thrust during the test. Then a step input to azimuth (or rudder) angle is sent. To account for possible nonlinearities, several steps ($0 \rightarrow 18^\circ$, $18 \rightarrow 35^\circ$, and $35 \rightarrow 0^\circ$) in each direction, starboard and port, are executed. The objective is to identify the yaw moment time constants that results in slow speed yaw motion responses. The test is repeated at two different forward speeds. Totally four yaw step tests were executed. Two sets of tests, where the vessel turns starboard (at speeds of 3 and 6 knots), and two sets of tests where the vessel turns port (at speeds of 3 and 6 knots). For all the yaw step tests carried out in 2013 with the old configuration, both rudders are first stepped to 20 degrees, and then the rudders are stepped to 47 degrees, and finally commanded to zero degree. For all the yaw step tests carried out in 2015 with the new configuration both the azimuth thrusters angles are first stepped to 18 degrees, and then the rudders are stepped to 35.7 degrees, and finally commanded to zero degree.

To quantify the results for ease of comparison, a Nomoto model is used to describe the relation between azimuth (or rudder) angles and yaw rate as described by

$$T_{p1}T_{p2}\ddot{r} + (T_{p1} + T_{p2})\dot{r} + r = K_p(\delta + T_z\dot{\delta}) \quad (5)$$

normally simplified to

$$T\dot{r} + r = K\delta \quad (6)$$

where δ and r are the azimuth (or rudder) angle and yaw rate, respectively. In the frequency domain it can be rewritten as

$$\frac{r(s)}{\delta(s)} = \frac{K}{1 + Ts} \quad (7)$$

In the analysis of the yaw step test a first order Nomoto model is fitted to azimuth angles and yaw rate that makes the comparison simpler. The results of the test campaign in 2015 after the retrofit are compared with those obtained in 2013 before the retrofit in Table 5 **Error! Reference source not found.** and Table 6 **Error! Reference source not found.**. It can be concluded that while the responsiveness of the system (how fast the system reaches its steady state) has not changed much after the retrofit, the effectiveness of the side moments (how much yaw rate the ship gets for a fixed change in rudder/azimuth angle) has improved. Furthermore, in the old configuration, before the retrofit, the rudders experienced a severe stall when they were commanded $20^\circ \rightarrow 47^\circ$ or $-20^\circ \rightarrow -47^\circ$ (and hence, the Nomoto model does not fit anymore to the system), but the azimuth systems show a uniform performance during all three parts of the yaw step tests.

Table 5: Summary of the computed parameters in yaw step test (first speed) performed on vessel Gunnerus in 2013 and 2015

Azimuth Step (deg)	Test Condition	Forward speed (knot)	K	T
$-0.2^\circ \rightarrow -17.6^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	2.6	-0.0724	3.73
$-1.7^\circ \rightarrow -21.3^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	3.22	-0.0575	3.27
$0.3^\circ \rightarrow 17.6^\circ$	To Port (2015)	2.9	-0.0845	4.45
$-1^\circ \rightarrow 18^\circ$	To Port (2013)	3.09	-0.0664	5.5
$-17.6^\circ \rightarrow -35.6^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	2.6	-0.0417	1.66
$-21.3^\circ \rightarrow -46.8^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	3.22	NA	NA
$17.6^\circ \rightarrow 35.3^\circ$	To Port (2015)	2.9	-0.0357	2.23
$18^\circ \rightarrow 46.5^\circ$	To Port (2013)	3.09	NA	NA
$-35.6^\circ \rightarrow 0.3^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	2.6	-0.0502	7.37
$-46.8^\circ \rightarrow -1^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	3.22	-0.027	11.2
$35.3^\circ \rightarrow -0.3^\circ$	To Port (2015)	2.9	-0.0616	8.91
$46.5^\circ \rightarrow -1.73^\circ$	To Port (2013)	3.09	-0.0249	7.34

Table 6: Summary of the computed parameters in yaw step test (second speed) performed on vessel Gunnerus in 2013 and 2015

Azimuth Step (deg)	Test Condition	Forward speed (knot)	K	T
$-0.3^\circ \rightarrow -17.6^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	6	-0.1352	1.92
$-1^\circ \rightarrow -21^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	6	-0.0973	1.87
$0^\circ \rightarrow 17.4^\circ$	To Port (2015)	6	-0.146	1.66
$0.34^\circ \rightarrow 19.5^\circ$	To Port (2013)	5.8	-0.1114	2.11
$-17.6^\circ \rightarrow -35.2^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	6	-0.0605	0.11
$-21^\circ \rightarrow -47^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	6	NA	NA
$17.4^\circ \rightarrow 35.8^\circ$	To Port (2015)	6	-0.0583	0.15
$19.5^\circ \rightarrow 44.5^\circ$	To Port (2013)	5.8	NA	NA
$-35.2^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$	To Starboard (2015)	6	-0.0962	4.43
$-47^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$	To Starboard (2013)	6	-0.0441	5.54
$35.8^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$	To Port (2015)	6	-0.0973	5.2
$44.5^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$	To Port (2013)	5.8	-0.0541	5.49

3.4.2 Thruster Agility Tests (without yawing moment)

In the thruster agility tests without yawing moment, we start from zero configuration with ship at rest. Using joystick, a command is sent to the DP system to move the ship in direction of 0° , 45° , 90° , 135° , 180° without changing the heading. All the tests are carried out at 50% power. The test is stopped when steady-state velocity is reached. The goal is to study responsiveness of the thruster system. Fig.12 shows a schematic of the thruster agility test. To quantify the responsiveness of the system the settling time is used. Fig.13 summarizes the results of thruster agility test graphically in the actual direction that vessel travelled (which is very different from the asked direction set-point in 45° , 90° , and 135°). It can be easily seen that, compared to the old configuration before the retrofit, the new configuration has faster settling time in every direction except 90° ; However, we should highlight

that in the old configuration, it is very hard to perform a thruster agility test in 90°, and the ship gets a considerable surge speed, which influences the sway settling time in favour of the 2013 tests.

It is worth to highlight that thruster agility test in 90° is similar to a sway acceleration test, however, it is different than normal crabbing tests in ITTC Recommended Procedures due to existence of DP system during the experiment.

Fig.12. Schematic description of thruster agility tests.

Fig.13. Graphical presentation of the spiral tests results before and after retrofit.

3.5. Underwater and inboard noise

The inboard noise and the noise emitted to the sea were measured by DNV-GL. The “before retrofit” measurements (Newman and Abrahamsen 2006) were performed shortly after delivery of the ship, while the “after”-tests were done in August 2015, in the same campaign as the other reported tests (Abrahamsen, 2015). For both campaigns, a pressure probe was mounted in the hull above the propeller to measure the pressure pulses from the propeller on the hull, while a hydrophone was mounted on a tripod located about 1 m above the sea floor at about 30 m depth. Inboard noise was measured using portable precision noise and vibration meters. Noise was measured in three operational conditions: 8 knots silent, 85% MCR and 100% MCR. For the 8 knots condition, only one generator was running, and each propeller motor consumed only about 100 kW. For the two other conditions, all three gen-sets were running, and the propeller motors consumed about 410 kW and 500 kW respectively. Fig.14 shows results of the radiated noise measurements from the bottom-mounted hydrophone. It can be seen that in silent condition, the new thrusters have significantly less emitted noise in all frequencies, except at high frequencies, where the electric switching frequencies of the rim thruster motors is seen. The conventional system shows higher noise levels, particularly at about 20 Hz and at 250 Hz, the first being the blade-pass frequency and therefore most likely related to cavitation. For the 85% MCR condition (Fig.14, right), the PM Azimuth thrusters have similar or lower noise levels than the conventional, except for 12,5 Hz and 250 Hz. 12,5 Hz corresponds to the blade-pass frequency and is believed to be cavitation-related, while the 250 Hz is electrical-related noise, which might be caused by the electromagnetic forces of the electric motors. The emitted noise at 100% MCR was very similar to 85% MCR.

The level of inboard noise increased in some locations, but decreased in most locations. Local resonance problems were identified, which is also to be reduced by corrective actions.

Fig.14: Results of noise measurements from the bottom-mounted hydrophone for 8 knots silent (left) and 85% MCR (right) from before and after retrofit of PM Azimuth thrusters.

3.6. Bollard pull tests

Bollard pull tests were conducted both before and after retrofit, in the same suitable location. As was specified above, the power reported is from the frequency converters in both cases. Therefore, a direct comparison of the two propulsion systems is possible. A comparison of specific load (Pull/Power vs. Power/A0) is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.5** where A0 is the propeller disc area. The figure shows that the PM thruster is performing significantly better than the original system. The values shown are high compared to other much more powerful vessels with typical conventional ducted propeller and rudders. The PM system shows better performance than the original system even though the propeller diameter is reduced by 0.1 m. The propeller diameter is very important for bollard pull performance. There might be several reasons for the PM thruster to perform better, one being that there is no rudder for the PM system.

Fig.15: Comparison of specific load in bollard pull before and after retrofit (PM(Observed) is from manual reading of the force cell before it stopped working, no time series available)

Other reasons might be that there is a larger clearance between the propeller and skeg, no ice fins, different duct profiles (19A vs. Innoduct for the new PM), different fastening of rudder/duct to the

hull (headbox and rudder stock for the conventional system, and split-bracket between duct and hull for the PM system) and different position of the propeller (both vertically and longitudinally). The specific load performance of the PM thruster is in the same range as a much more powerful azimuth ducted pod.

4. Conclusions

The performance of the research vessel “Gunnerus” was tested before and after retrofitting new Permanent Magnet Azimuthing thrusters, utilising motors integrated into the rim of the ducted thrusters. It is found that the speed performance of the ship after retrofit is slightly better at high speeds, while little difference is found at lower speeds. The bollard pull performance increased significantly, even though the diameter of the new propellers is 5% less than for the old ones. The main reason is believed to be better inflow conditions for the new propellers, and better mounting arrangement for the ducts.

The surge acceleration test shows that the PM thruster almost always has a faster response than old configuration except when the step function is a negative one (i.e. $40 \rightarrow 0\%$ and $80 \rightarrow 0\%$). The responsiveness of the system in yaw (how fast the system reaches a steady yaw velocity) has not changed much after the retrofit, but the effectiveness of the side moments (how much yaw rate ship gets for a fixed change in rudder/azimuth angle) has improved with the PM thrusters. Furthermore, in the old configuration, before the retrofit, the rudders experience a severe stall when they are commanded $20 \rightarrow 47$ or $-20 \rightarrow -47$ (and hence, the Nomoto model does not fit anymore to the system), but azimuth systems shows a uniform performance during all three parts of the yaw step tests ($0 \rightarrow 18^\circ$, $18 \rightarrow 35^\circ$, and $35 \rightarrow 0^\circ$).

Gunnerus ability to move in different directions without yawing movement has improved with PM thrusters compared to the conventional system. The noise emitted to the sea is particularly important for research vessels. For the 8 knots silent condition, the noise levels were generally reduced, except at the highest frequencies. For the 85% MCR and 100% MCR conditions, noise levels were also significantly reduced, except for some cavitation-related noise at the first blade-pass frequency, and noise at 250 Hz believed to have its origin in the electrical system. The latter is being investigated in order to remove this noise source.

As a final remark, we would like to mention that the dynamic response of the PM Azi propulsion system could be improved even more by utilizing a hybrid machinery system incorporating batteries or high-power capacitors, since currently the dynamic response is limited by ramps set in order not to overload the gen-sets.

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Power-Saving Device for Air Bubble Generation using a Hydrofoil to Reduce Ship Drag

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Abstract

We have developed a new power-saving device to reduce the drag of a ship's hull using small bubbles. The device reduces the energy required for bubble generation. The device, which consists of angled hydrofoils with air introducers, uses the low-pressure region produced above the hydrofoil as the ship moves forward to drive atmospheric air into the water. Microbubble generation is by Kelvin Helmholtz Instability and Hull Tightening Force by rising Microbubble interfered with generally existing longitudinal vortexes. Full-scale tests have shown that, with correct operation, our device can produce a net power saving of 5–15% for ships.

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, the mechanism of air lubrication has been investigated for reduction of the friction drag on a ship's surface and to reduce CO₂ emissions. Three physically different air lubrication techniques have been identified: air cavity, air film, and small bubble methods. The classification of the working principle in these different drag reductions was explained by *Ceccio (2010)*. The small bubble method, which utilizes functions of micro- to sub-millimeter bubbles, has an advantage over the air cavity and air film-based methods in that it reduces friction without requiring any change in the form of the ship's hull. Another advantage is its large impact to the drag reduction ratio per void fraction supplied into the boundary layer. The impact is ordinarily larger than unity, and reaches 100 on ideal conditions as reviewed by *Murai (2014)*. Researchers in this field use the term “microbubble drag reduction” as they expect turbulence modification realized by eddy-suppressing small bubbles inside turbulent boundary layer. Practical application of microbubble method to ship drag reduction has been actively studied in recent years because of the potential energy savings and the environmental benefits in terms of marine pollution. *Kodama et al. (2008)* reported approximately 10–15% saving of the total energy consumption for an experimental ship.

Mizokami et al. (2010) also succeeded in about 10% fuel saving as bubbles were injected below a vessel with wide flat bottom surface. Their ships of air lubrication system are already in commercial uses. For challenging further improvement of drag reduction, *Mäkiharju et al. (2012)* proposed high-void fraction type of air-layer drag reduction and estimated its usefulness to large tankers. *Jang et al. (2014)* also reported 5–6% net power-saving estimated for a bulk carrier as they scaled their towing model ship experiments considering the power for bubble injection.

One of concerns toward further improvement of microbubble method is the fact that the energy required to supply air bubbles using conventional bubble generators is quite significant, and it occupies 3–10% of the total energy consumption of a ship dependent on the depth of bubble generation. This explains that the required power for bubble generation in worse operations cancels out the power saved by drag reduction.

To overcome this obstacle, we invented a new bubble generation device suitable for its installation to ship, *Takahashi and Murai (2004)*, *Murai and Takahashi (2008)*. Fig.1 shows the new device, which is called a winged air induction pipe (WAIP). This device, which has an angled hydrofoil with an air introducer, provides the low-pressure region above the hydrofoil as the ship moves forward. The low pressure drives the atmospheric air to a critical water depth without significant air compression, depending on the flow conditions around the hydrofoil, the hydrofoil's shape, the angle of attack, and

other factors. Interaction between the hydrofoil and upper deformable free surface was investigated by *Duncan (1983)*. In our case, the hydrofoil is located at a small distance from the flat wall so that air and water join smoothly to flow out downstream. This device also generates small bubbles without the use of bubble fragmentation devices such as porous plates. We confirmed that the small bubbles are generated by the instability of the air–water interface, which is subject to a high shear rate along the surface of the hydrofoil. The number density of bubbles increases with the subsequent wave-breaking phenomenon which occurs just behind the hydrofoil, *Kumagai et al. (2010)*. We installed WAIPs on a coaster and achieved a net power saving of 10–15% as being elaborated in this paper. Full technical data of this summary are available upon request.

Fig.1: Winged air induction Pipe (WAIP) : (a) Photograph; (b) Schematic drawing of WAIP cross section. The hydrofoil is a NACA 653-618 (chord length 40 mm, span-wise length of 240mm, and angle of attack 12°).

2. Hydrofoil device bubble generation process.

Fig.2 demonstrates towing experiments on bubble generation by a moving hydrofoil close to an air–water interface. After the atmospheric air is entrained by the negative pressure, instability takes place on the air–water interface so that smooth interface naturally transits to turbulent state as seen by the dark area in the photograph. The transition occurs because of wave-breaking, i.e. upstream water which is accelerated by the hydrofoil’s curvature to be faster than the gravitational wave propagation velocity dashes into the slow downstream water region. The wave breaking threshold is given by the wave steepness (the height/length ratio of a wave) and it was found to be ~ 0.1 , *Kumagai et al. (2010), (2011a,b)*. Beyond this threshold, small bubbles are naturally ventilated into a thin layer just beneath the original gas–liquid interface, and this phenomenon supports continuous but active release of small bubbles for the downstream region close to the wall. It is worth noting that this threshold is not a specific finding only for the WAIP system, but is known as a general trend of deep water wave-breaking mechanism reported such as in ocean wave breaking, *Peregrine (1983), Toffoli et al. (2010)*.

Small bubble generation observed behind the hydrofoil is interpreted as energy conversion from the wave energy to turbulent kinetic energy. Since the wave energy is produced by the rapid deflection of water flow above the hydrofoil, the design of the hydrofoil should be optimized to promote the wave-breaking. In its downstream, bubbles of various sizes are potentially generated because of a broad

spectrum in wave number coming out on the turbulent interface. Among them, large bubbles are un-survivable in strong shear so that only small bubbles occupy the downstream turbulent boundary layer.

Fig.2: Bubble generation by a moving hydrofoil

3. Air bubble release for drag reduction

To reduce the drag on a ship's hull at 15–20 knot, the injection of small bubbles (~0.5 mm) into the turbulent boundary layer is desirable, because only an adequate supply of these small bubbles can markedly reduce the turbulent momentum transfer, i.e., the skin friction of the wall. Although the mechanism of the drag reduction produced by such small bubbles remains an open question academically, the current common understanding from historical experimental observations is that the injection of these small bubbles into the turbulent region causes reduction of the Reynolds shear stress, *Kitagawa et al. (2005)*. This implies that the ideal condition is to have the highest bubble number density at the peak Reynolds shear stress position, which is located between the viscous sublayer and the buffer layer of the turbulent boundary layer, *Murai (2014)*. Additionally, small bubbles tend to be accumulated naturally into the turbulent shear layer, as reported in previous studies of bubbly two-phase jets and also for hydrofoil, *Ohashi et al. (1990)*. To be precise, small bubbles tend to remain in a high-entropy region where the second invariant of the velocity gradient tensor has a negative value, *Kitagawa et al. (2001)*. In the flow beneath a moving ship, this region corresponds to the layer with the most active turbulent eddies, and thus the small bubbles remain for a long period inside the turbulent boundary layer and resist the turbulent diffusion effect

For provision of a supply of these small bubbles to the turbulent boundary layer, the method of air injection is highly important. Fig.3 shows an illustrative comparison how the present WAIP system should be operated. When the ship's draught is shallow (0.5 m), the hydrofoil works as a self-priming pump, as discussed in Section 2. As a result, the small air bubbles are released near the ship's hull by the hydrofoil device. For larger vessels with deeper draughts (3), the pressure reduction by the hydrofoil is insufficient and a moderate air pressure rise is required to maintain bubble generation. In this case, the air–water interface should be placed between the AIP outlet and the top surface of the hydrofoil (Fig. 3a). Otherwise, for example, if we use blowers with high air volume flow rates, the upper surface of the hydrofoil would be covered with air cavities (Fig. 3b), and it would no longer be able to work as an air inducer using the pressure lowering effect of the hydrofoil. On this condition, the hydrofoil's own drag would be highly increased because of different phase (gas/ liquid) between the top and the bottom surfaces. Further increases in the air-volume flow rate using blowers would leave the hydrofoil completely isolated from the ambient water flow (Fig. 3c), and only large bubbles

would be produced outside the boundary layer. More-over the hydrofoils would work as a resistance of the air injection by blowers. We must avoid such situations, which are simply a waste of bubble generation energy. Therefore the pressure regulator from the air reservoir of the compressor, instead of the blower, is necessary for the WAIP system to control the position of the air–water interface above the hydrofoil.

Fig.3 Methods of air supply over a ship's hull

- (a) WAIP with natural ventilation
- (b) WAIP with blower (where hydrofoil is useless as a self-priming pump)
- (c) WAIP with blower (air flow is too high)

4. Applications to various ships

Our previous studies and experiments have shown that significant drag reduction can be obtained by the installation of hydrofoil devices (i.e. WAIPs) on a long flat plate. The actual applications of four practical full scale trials are summarized below.

4.1 Adventurer 2

In December 2002, we installed two hydrofoils beneath a small fishing boat, Adventurer 2, Fig 4(a) historically the first feasibility test of the WAIP system. Two WAIPs were fitted in line, Fig.4(b), to the main stream and the downstream one was activated, and as expected microbubbles were observed in the site glass as per Fig.4(c). The power saving effect depends on the ship's speed, and a fuel saving (using flow meters) of about 4% was recorded at approximately 29 knots. Trials were carried out in Imari Bay Nagasaki, Japan. This trial showed a modest result, with some variables, but encouraged the team to proceed to investigate the WAIP application on larger ships.

Fig 4. (a) A full size ship test on adventurer 2-12.62LPP,2.7m beam,0.83m Dmd (moulded) ,500ps (power) (b) arrangement of hydrofoil (c) Site glass bubble clouds (d) WAIP fuel consumption graph

Fig.5: Santander Ferry 1

4.2 Santander Ferry 1

The second sea trial was a ferry boat (28.8 m long, 5.45 Bmd, 1.55 Dmd) named Santander ferry, Fig.5(a). Ten WAIPS were installed on the ship's hull, Fig 5(b), and the ship cruised at 12 knots. We conducted the WAIP performance test twice for the ferry in December 2004, and February 2005. The location for both of the Sea trials was Santander (Cebu Island) and Dumaguete (Negros Island) in the Philippines and these tests were carried out on commercial operations. From the first test in September 2004, we confirmed 10% savings.

4.3 New Ferry Misaki

The third application of the WAIP System, we chose a 68 m long cargo vessel called New Ferry Misaki Fig 6, and it cruises at about 18 kn at sea. Since New Ferry Misaki is much larger than previous test cases, we installed 34 WAIPs. Another feature is that we introduced compresses to assist the WAIP System because of the deeper draft. This allowed a constant pressure that could be adjusted so that no original performance was lost on the hydrofoil at the air and water interface. This vessel was operated on a commercial shipping service from Nagasaki to Wakamatsujima. She cruised 77 days without air injection to be without WAIP influence, and 148 days with the WAIP in operation. The fuel consumption rate for her engine has been reported to the authors from the chief engineer's logbook. The resultant fuel saving of the main engine with 34 WAIPs was 9.1%. The results recorded revealed it was apparent that with the installation of the WAIP (34) during this time, the main engines fuel consumption was 9.1% better with the technology installed.

Fig.6: New Ferry Misaki

4.4 Filia Ariea

The fourth Sea trial was for an 85 m long coaster, named Filia Ariea in July 2008. Fig 7 shows a photograph of the side surface of the Filia Ariea in a dock. The total number of WAIPs installed on the ship was 52. 34 WAIPs were submerged in the sea because of her draft was shallow (2.5 m, mean). Two blowers of 2.2 kW were mounted to the WAIP system to see the influence of additional air supply to the natural ventilation, although it was unnecessary in her original design. Measurement of the ships speed and maneuvering work carried out by Belkonhed Marine Service b.v. According to ISO15016:2002(guidelines for the assessment of speed and power performance by analysis of speed trial data). Filia Ariea had the WAIP System installed, and Filia Nettie did not. Filia Ariea achieved a power saving ratio of 10%. The two sister ships are exactly the same in geometry, engines, interior structures, and surface coating the only difference is the WAIP System. Originally a blower system which was connected to the wipes system made no saving at all. The blower was removed and a temper sent saving was achieved.

From this blowing condition, we infer that too much it was forcibly injected into the WAIPs so that the white file to release small bubbles in the desired position, for affective drag reduction.

For earning proper WAIP performance, we should again place a special emphasis with the fact that only a moderate air pressurization keeps the air/water interface just above the hydrofoil so that the water and the air behaves in a smooth confluence above the hydrofoil to generate small bubbles in the downstream region.

Fig.7: Filia Ariea in dock

5. Conclusions

We developed a device to be used as a bubble generator for drag reduction of ships; the device consists of an air induction pipe (AIP) and an angled hydrofoil, and is called the winged air induction pipe, or WAIP. Yeah bubbles are released from the induction pipe outlet into the turbulence boundary of the ship's hull via the negative pressure produced above the hydrofoil beneath the AIP.

The theoretical principle of an entrainment by this device was confirmed by a series of laboratory experiments. A simple theoretical analysis for critical velocity at which air bubbles start to release was in good agreement to the observation in a towing tank experiment.

Four kinds of full-scale tests were carried out to demonstrate the feasibility of the white system while individual tests were conducted in different schemes going to there is restrictions in the sea trials. For a small fishing boat Adventurer 2 a single WAIP operation earned 4% of fuel saving, but it was not fully guaranteed as we consider the fluctuating nature in sea states.

Passenger ferry Santander Ferry employed 10 WAIPs and obtained 16% of fuel saving for four round trips a day. In order to obtain higher statistic reliability in long operations, we advanced to a 148 day sea trial using a long cargo ship New Ferry Misaki which had 34 WAIPs installed. She obtained 9% reduction in main engine fuel oil consumption in her commercial shipping service, by which fuel oil of 55,204 L were saved in 148 service days.

The next trial was done with the 90 meter long cargo ship Filia Ariea with 34 WAIPs operating out of a total of 52 units, in the underwater region, and a power saving of about 10% was achieved. As we experienced in large vessels with deeper drafts, the WAIP requires the assistance of an air compressor, since the negative pressure realizing natural ventilation. To the contrary a surplus supply from blowers into it the induction pipes alters the two phase flow structure around the hydrofoil to totally lose the hydrofoil performance.

A recent publication from Nanyang Technological University (NTU) published on the 27.10.2015 which can be found on the web <http://www.mae.ntu.edu.sg/Research/Pages/Detailed->

Page.aspx?news=1cc89591-2747-4213-b842-4c12f03472eb about a Research Collaboration Agreement (RCA) of the WAIP “ Two issues on a novel Air Lubrication system for the ship drag reduction” which aims to quantify the energy saving potential of WAIP for ship applications by investigating few fundamental and key issues - with the NTU and RDE Japan, the inventors and owners of the patented technology, was awarded one of the top 3 projects at the Singapore Maritime Institute (SMI) Forum.

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Combine and Conquer – Ships and Shipping of Tomorrow

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Abstract

The paper discusses key trends in ship design, ship building and ship operation and attempts to extrapolate those trends into the future. We believe that high speed and multi-hulls will play a minor role only in this scenario. In fact, trends are moving in the opposite direction of lower speed with a growing emphasis on simple hull shapes, wind assisted technologies and propulsion improving devices. Cleaner fuels, most notably LNG, and condition-based maintenance will lead to low-maintenance and low-crew ships. Meanwhile, a proliferation of sensors and increased satellite bandwidth will fundamentally change logistics. Augmented Reality will become a key technology from design to operation. Together, this combination of technologies will enable the next wave of innovation.

1. Introduction

In the 1970s book, “Ships and Shipping of Tomorrow” Schönknecht *et al.* (1973), wonderful artistic visions predicted a future of nuclear powered submarines transporting crude oil with giant hydrofoils bringing people around the world and streamlined catamarans carrying containers at speeds of up to 35 knots across the Atlantic. These various visions have changed over time, Fig.1. And while some predictions have proven to be correct, at least in some aspects, many more have been completely wrong.

Fig.1: Ships of the future over time: conveyor belt loading and unloading ro-ro ship,1950s (top left), transatlantic giant hydrofoils, 1960s (top right), Luigi Colani design for fast container ships, 1970s (bottom left), 2010 NYK’s Super ECO-ship, 2030 (bottom right).

When we first came up with the idea of speculating on ships and shipping of the future, our first port of call (to borrow a maritime phrase) was to browse through the bookshelf and conduct some research on the Internet. When you enter a google search for “ships of the future” you could be misled into concluding that the world’s future fleet will be evenly divided between cruise vessels and warships.

We have a very different view of where the maritime industries and associated technologies are heading. In the following pages, we will draw on our own research, industry best practices and the views of key experts to hopefully sketch a more realistic scenario of the ships of the future (for definition purposes, let us say the “next-generation” ships, some 30 years from now). At this point, we should acknowledge that DNV GL’s report “The future of shipping”, *Longva et al. (2014)*, has been a key resource for us in this endeavor.

2. Hardware - Ships of Tomorrow

Broadly speaking, ships of the future will evolve naturally in line with economic trends and advancing technologies becoming widely available.

2.1. Ship types and hull shape

“Air transporters” (navy ships, megayachts, ferries, cruise vessels) often influence public opinion about the appearance of future ships. Below, we see exotic hull forms (like pentamarans), Fig.2, hydrodynamic concepts (planing, boats, hydrofoils, air cushions, etc.), Fig.3, and materials (such as high-tech composites); in short, think of aerospace technology meeting creative design.

Fig.2: Futuristic SWATH design
Source: Sean McCartan

Fig.3: Futuristic hydrofoil ferry design
Source: EMIT

However, the world’s fleet is and will continue to be much more mundane and pragmatic. Shipping of the future will still mean mainly dry bulk, liquid bulk and general cargo. However, it is true that global trends (growing world population and economies especially in Asia) will bring some slow shifts in the mix of cargo types, for example:

- Oil Tankers: crude oil production has reached and passed beyond its zenith. As the production of remaining resources will become increasingly expensive, crude oil shipping will slowly decline with fewer and on average smaller tankers available.
- LNG Carriers: Liquid natural gas (LNG) tankers are likely to increase in numbers and average size as transport and power generation become increasingly fueled by LNG.
- Bulk Carriers: bulkers will continue to be the working horse of the world economy, transporting a steady stream of raw materials around the globe. The average carrier size should remain stable with numbers slowly increasing as overall economic activities increase.
- Multi-Purpose Vessels (MPVs): MPVs are likely to decline as developing regions of the world catch up with container port infrastructure.
- Containerships: more containers will be shipped with average and maximum containership size likely to increase, Fig.4. This development will be driven by economic frameworks (large alliances will result in the bundling together of container volumes) and developing port infrastructure (faster and cheaper handling of containers in port).

The long-term economic and ecological pressure for energy efficiency will inevitably lead to lower ship speeds. At the same time, smarter design processes will look at power requirements in realistic operational scenarios, i.e. variations of operational conditions (speed, load) and ambient conditions (sea state) to minimize yearly fuel consumption, as envisioned in *Hochkirch and Bertram (2012)*. As a result, bulbous bows are likely to decline on many ships and some may even feature straight stems as seen in DNV GL's concept studies, Green Dolphin (bulk carrier), Fig.5, and ReVolt (container feeder), Fig.6.

Fig.4: LNG-powered 20000 TEU containership study PERFECT. Source: DNV GL

Fig.5: "Green Dolphin" bulk carrier design
Source: DNV GL

Fig.6: ReVolt container feeder concept
Source: DNV GL

2.2. Materials

We believe that ship hulls will continue to be made of steel, simply because it is cheap, strong and easy to recycle. However, better coatings and inspection programs will compensate for steel's main shortcoming, namely, corrosion. By controlling density, the properties of steel components will be significantly modified to allow steel to be used in more collision-resistant structures. Intelligent condition monitoring schemes will provide the appropriate technologies to extend the average life-span of steel structures while reducing (if not avoiding completely) the risk of structural failure:

- **Big Data:** embedded monitoring systems and conventional surveying schemes will generate huge volumes of data across fleets of ships in service and offshore platforms. Cross-referencing this data will support future intelligent condition monitoring systems.
- **Image Processing:** image processing techniques are likely to be used to automatically detect and quantify paint defects, extent of corrosion and cracks, for example, *Mavi et al. (2012)*. The progression of such defects will likely be mapped and quantified through the use of images from different time periods. The availability of cheap miniature cameras (as embedded in mobile phones) is also likely to lead to wide-spread installation and automatic surveying schemes.
- **Corrosion Prediction Schemes:** using Artificial Intelligence techniques, classical corrosion prediction schemes will be improved, providing a more accurate prediction of location, extent and type of corrosion. *De Masi et al. (2016)* provide an example of pipelines.
- **Simulation technology:** using 3D ship product models and fast finite-element modelling techniques, the as-is condition of a ship will be capable of being simulated at any time, as sketched in *Wilken et al. (2011)*.

In summary, the life-span of ships will be extended with 30 to 35 years likely to become the new norm. Composites will be increasingly used for high-speed craft (HSC), super-structures for stability-sensitive ships (like passenger ships or naval vessels) and selected equipment and outfitting. However, due to strength and production considerations, the use of composites in hulls will continue to be limited to vessels up to 100 m length only. Of course, recycling of composites is an issue that also applies to automotive and aerospace applications, *Gramann et al. (2008)*. On that basis, we would conclude that it is likely that the marine industry will follow general trends and increasingly deploy composites based on natural organic materials, Fig.7, as alternatives to classical glass or carbon fiber composites.

Fig.7: Composites based on renewables (left) and metal foam (right), Source: wikipedia

It is interesting to note that metal foams (both aluminum and steel), Fig.7, offer interesting possibilities for ships, improving weight-to-strength ratios, noise and vibration characteristics as well as thermal insulation. In the future, steel may well be combined with metal foams to give higher bending stiffness and lower weight than solid steel constructions. A sandwich panel with steel faces of 1 mm with a 14 mm metal foam core has similar bending stiffness as a 10 mm solid steel plate, but with only 35 percent of the weight, *Longva et al. (2014)*.

Fig.8: Nano-coating

Fig.9: Underwater hull cleaning robot

Antifouling paint will see a shift towards more sustainable technologies for energy efficiency reasons but also to prevent the spread of invasive species, for example:

- Mechanically repellent surfaces – for example, nano-coatings with microscopic surface structures, Fig.8, making adhesion difficult, similar to anti-graffiti coatings on houses. Nano-coatings are mechanically more robust than foul release (“silicone”) coatings.
- Frequent robot-based grooming – proactive grooming (mild cleaning) of hulls addresses both energy efficiency and the spread of invasive species. Autonomous underwater cleaning robots, <http://auvac.org/community-information/community-news/view/672>, Ishii *et al.* (2014), resemble lawn-mowing robots, Fig.9. While, these robots have yet to become affordable and widely available, they also need to be equipped with cognitive, cooperative capabilities. Progress in this area may benefit from related work for robotic underwater surveys or robotic marine rescue operations, Odetti *et al.* (2016).
- Ultra-sonic protection schemes – this is a complementary technology for regions that have limited or difficult access (difficult coating and cleaning), Kelling (2016).

2.3. Fuels and machinery

The broader trend towards cleaner fuels combined with lower design speeds will affect maritime propulsion profoundly. LNG is expected to replace heavy fuel oil (HFO) as a standard fuel, Chryssakis *et al.* (2015). This will affect the whole machinery system. Diesel engines will no longer need separators and filters as the fuel itself is so clean. As for cars, we will see hybrid propulsion, combining combustion engines with electric drives, Fig.10. With LNG as a fuel, today’s four-stroke diesel engine generator sets as the standard option for auxiliary power may be replaced by fuel cells and batteries. Again, we will see a combination of technologies being deployed to maximize individual strengths. Highly efficient fuel cells will supply rather constant base load; batteries will supplement them for short-term peaks in power requirement and fast reaction. Overall, cleaner fuel and the more robust set-up of the engine room together with smarter condition-based maintenance schemes will reduce the workload of the engine department.

Fig.10: Zero-emission ferry design with fuel cells and batteries, supplemented by Flettner rotors harnessing wind energy, Rohde *et al.* (2013)

Nuclear power remains the wild card. The pressure to reduce carbon footprint, especially in shipping, is the main argument in favor. Liability issues (possibly also for the flag state), a shortage of marine engineers who are qualified in nuclear reactor operation and the general political climate (at present) towards nuclear energy are the main arguments against. Of course, the environment may well change over the next 30 years with progress in nuclear technology and changes in the political and public perception of fossil fuels versus nuclear fuels perhaps swinging the balance. However, any prediction

in this area remains highly speculative. The scenario of nuclear shipping cannot be ruled out. However, we are unlikely to witness it in the next 30 years as we should still have abundant sources of LNG available by 2050 with most stakeholders far more comfortable with this option as a standard fuel for shipping.

As previously stated, the quest for transport efficiency (reducing fuel bill and emissions alike) will favor lower ship speeds. Ships are likely to become wider and shorter with propellers having fewer blades. Propulsion improving devices (PIDs, also known as energy saving devices, ESDs) may become standard. There are various technical solutions, some dating back to the 1970s, *Carlton (2012)*, *Bertram (2012)*, which may see a widespread renaissance:

- Asymmetric sterns may see wider adoption after patent claims expire.
- Pre-swirl fins (often combined with nozzles such as in the popular Mewis duct for full hulls or twisted fins for slender hulls) can be attached to gain two to three percent.
- Contra-rotating propellers or vane wheels are likely to play a larger role as better design procedures and lubricants solve traditional issues with these devices.
- Costa bulbs or similar devices (for example, “the Ultimate Rudder” of Nakashima Propellers) may become standard, possibly combined with twisting the rudder.

Fig.11: Twisted fin as typical PDI
Source: Becker Marine

Fig.12: ‘MT Amalienborg’ of Shell Shipping equipped with air lubrication system

Air lubrication has enjoyed much attention over the past decade, *Thill (2016)*. The technology has matured and evolved from laboratory tests and theoretical consideration to several installations worldwide. While it is too early to predict the future of air lubrication, if the recent installations of the European Silverstream system, *Silberschmidt (2016)*, and the Japanese MALS system live up to expectations, we can certainly expect to see a lot more of such installations. Of course, the general trend towards lower speeds and wider ships in favor of air lubrication technology.

Low speed also helps the case of wind-assisted propulsion. There is no shortage of debate on this theme, mainly coming from academic studies and small players in the market. Right now, there are very few (< 10) full-scale installations on cargo ships. However, thanks to increasing fuel prices and consolidation occurring in the wind-assisted propulsion technology market with small vendors being acquired by larger players, we may well see a proliferation of professional systems for harnessing wind energy for ships. In this context, only robust and highly automated systems make sense, for example, those based on Flettner rotors, Fig.10, or employing kites.

Falling costs for sensors, computing power and satellite communications make it a safe prediction that ships of the future will be “smart”, i.e. they will be equipped with various embedded data processing. Sensors will become smaller, more robust and cheaper to acquire. As a result, they will be more widely distributed with redundancy built-in coupled with options for intelligent sensor fusion. We envisage sensors being literally “everywhere”, in the hull, main engine, auxiliary machinery and even small equipment items. And they will be smart. “Today’s mobile phones have the processing power of desktop computers 10 years ago. In 2020, mobile phones will have the power of today’s PCs. Cheap and

small distributed sensors will have the abilities of today’s mobile phones, and so on,” *Longva et al. (2014)*.

3. Software – Design, Construction and Operation of Tomorrow

3.1. Design

Progress in CAD (computer aided design) systems towards 3D product data models (PDMs) allows us to not only perform a large variety of analyses and simulations, but also deliver photo-realistic virtual reality displays. The traditionally experience-based ship design has already moved considerably towards simulation-based (a.k.a. first-principle) design, Fig.13. The exchange of information between different software and more intelligent pre-processors have dramatically cut down the time and cost associated with running simulations. Cloud-computing with on-demand business schemes gives advanced simulation access to small and medium enterprises, for example, *Hildebrandt and Reyer (2015)*. Simulations are also getting more sophisticated with increased detail represented in captured geometry and more advanced physical models, for example, *Köhlmoos and Bertram (2012)*, *Peric and Bertram (2012)*.

We also see the scope of simulations expanding beyond the classical stability, strength and hydrodynamics simulations, for example, aerodynamics, fire, ice-breaking, evacuation, manufacturing, energy generation and consumption in the ship systems, etc. Systematic simulations may be used to derive tailored “numerical series” or knowledge bases. These simulation-based knowledge bases provide highly accurate estimates that are virtually instantaneous, *Harries (2010)*, *Couser et al. (2011)*.

Fig.13: Seakeeping simulation in ship design

Fig.14: Virtual Reality for interior design of a megayacht, *Lukas et al. (2015)*

When human interaction is important, we increasingly use Virtual Reality as a key technology. Virtual Reality uses 3D models of the world with fly-through or walk-through capabilities, and typically some user interaction; in essence, it is the same technology used in video games. This technology is gaining popularity for training, but also for aesthetics (interior design), Fig.14, orientation in ships (cruise vessels or large navy ships) and operational aspects in design (reachability, visibility). Considerable progress has been made by adding real-time physics, thanks to “physics engines”, fast emulators of typical kinematics and dynamics of objects. This progress in simulations has been accompanied by similar advance in visualization techniques. In many cases, we can analyze the time-dependent performance of a system in photo-realistic 3D simulations while the visualization allows intuitive assessment, Fig.15, *Chaves and Gaspar (2016)*.

Despite numerous attempts, no single monolithic software program has emerged that is optimal for all ship design tasks. We believe that coupling dedicated software packages is a better strategy than trying to develop the “one code to solve all problems”. In short: cooperation beats integration. A “plug-and-play” culture is developing where software codes and companies learn to work smoothly together

to provide better or new solutions. Best-of-breed solutions are being developed across geographical and company boundaries, using flexible alliances and web-based technology, for example, *Denis et al. (2016)*, *Harries et al. (2015)*, Fig.16.

Fig.15: Employing game technology allows rapid and intuitive assessment of design performance, *Chaves and Gaspar (2016)*

Fig.16: Distributed web-based development, combining best-of-breed software, *Harries et al. (2015)*

3.2. Construction

We envisage that very similar technologies will be used in ship construction and in ship maintenance/repair. With 3D product data models (PDMs) available, the door to Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) is wide open. The 3D models will be updated as the ship is built and modified over its lifecycle. “As-built” PDMs will be passed to owners for asset management, *Thomson and Gordon (2016)*. Affordable 3D scanning will be widely used, both from the outside (for example, for more accurate performance monitoring models) and the inside (for as-built/as-modified models), Fig.17, *Morais et al. (2011)*.

In Augmented Reality, computers (for example, tablets) overlay a live image with computer generated information. For example, a building block may be shown with a part to be installed, illustrating how both fit together, Fig.18, *Kohei (2016)*. The fitting of parts becomes very intuitive, reducing assembly time and the likelihood of errors. A number of advanced shipbuilding nations are active in Augmented Reality applications for shipbuilding. This technology becomes truly powerful when used in combination with vision technologies (for example, marker recognition), PDMs, positioning methods, hands-free operation technology (smart glasses), etc., *Patterson and Webb (2016)*.

Fig.17: 3D laser scan of as-built ship, Source: SSI

Fig.18: Augmented Reality in ship construction, *Kohei (2016)*

Industry 4.0 will also encompass shipyards and the maritime supply industry. The Internet of Things will change (and accelerate) logistics, especially for time-critical and highly interconnected supply networks, *Borgia (2014)*, *Etienne and Sayers (2016)*. Drones may be used to deliver required parts to remote areas, such as ships, as demonstrated in 2016 by Maersk. However, often, delivery will no longer be needed. Instead, 3D printing may generate required parts, mainly in the supply industry and on ships. For example, the Hamburg Ship Model Basin uses 3D printing for appendages (for example, rudders) for model testing. The technology has progressed rapidly and is currently achieving 15 m parts.

3.3. Operation

General developments in ICT (information and communications technologies) will have a profound effect on the shipping industry. Of course, ICT allows us to perform traditional tasks better (faster, cheaper, or more accurately), but perhaps even more importantly, ICT opens the door for us to consider completely new options. Some predict that ICT will “revolutionize” shipping. However, the truth is that computers and telecommunications are not new to shipping and evolution will continue, albeit at an accelerated pace. We will witness “more” of the same trends as in the past decades: an increase in the exchange of data and more collaboration between stakeholders.

Various developments will make ships easier to operate. Examples are condition-based maintenance systems (diagnosing eventual problems at an early stage and supporting the fixing of the problem, for example, by ordering spare parts, preparing 3D printing or guiding repair by ordinary persons without expert knowledge on the system, using Augmented Reality for intuitive guidance). Along with reduced workload in the engine room due to cleaner fuels, this will allow further reductions in minimum crew sizes. This development resembles trends in the automotive industry: we have smart cars (automatic brake systems if pedestrians are crossing; valet parking; self-monitoring tire pressure; ability to drive autonomously on highways, etc.) as well as Google’s self-driving car. For ships, we will have low-crew smart ships (with automatic collision avoidance; automatic berthing; self-monitoring for hull, engine and cargo; ability to sail autonomously for limited time in certain conditions, etc.) and no-crew drones for specific applications (for example, short-distance ferries, tugs and fireboats).

Fig.19: Highly automated, smart ships with low or no crew will serve highly automated, smart ports

Whether ships are operated locally or by remote control, operational decisions will be data driven, for example, using AIS (Automatic Identification System, which is a satellite-based data exchange, allowing tracking of virtually all cargo ships) for ship routing, factoring in weather, traffic situation and port capacities. Combining (big) data, simulations and Artificial Intelligence techniques will deliver business and logistics transparency with both economic and ecological benefits. The Internet of Things will play a key role in this development.

With ICT becoming an indispensable part of shipping, cybersecurity will become a key concern, both for autonomous and manned shipping. Awareness of the cybersecurity issue is already evident in the maritime industry with at least partial solutions on the horizon, for example, *Rødseth and Lee (2015)* and DNV GL's cybersecurity recommended practice. The technology on ships will largely follow the cybersecurity technology employed for other large assets, such as power plants, traffic control centers, etc.

4. Conclusions

Stand-alone techniques have already reached a high degree of maturity and we believe that further progress is best obtained by partnerships and an appropriate combination of technologies and techniques, as illustrated in the individual chapters. We see this trend continuing apace: simulation tools with Virtual Reality displays and Artificial Intelligence for user guidance, Big Data using Artificial Intelligence to derive trends for profiles used in formal optimization, etc.. In short, it is all about combining and conquering (the future).

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Development of the Osaka University Squid-Like Underwater Robot

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Abstract

With the aim of developing an underwater robot with a new propulsion system, a Squid-like robot with two undulating side fins has been developed at Osaka University. The body and propulsion system of the robot follow the swimming mechanism of flat-fish that use undulating side fins, e.g. Squid, Stingray Cuttlefish and Manta. The Squid-robot is now in its 6th generation. Progressing generations have improved cost and ease of production for the robot. The paper describes the development history, tests performed so far and intended further developments.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we introduce the development of an underwater robot with two undulating side fins. This underwater robot is a kind of biomimetic underwater vehicle which is created with inspiration from usual swimming style of squid, and we often participate in some event with this robot, “Squid-like robot”. Though many new concepts of bio-inspired underwater propulsion systems have been developed, research on an underwater vehicle which obtain thrust and turn by undulating its side fins like squid, stingray and flounder have been conducted for several years. We introduce robots we have built so far.

2. Why squid?

First the reason why squid is chosen is explained. Speaking of squid, a jet propulsion is imagined firstly. But looking the swimming style of squid in the water tank in Japanese restaurant or aquarium, they usually don't swim with jet propulsion but undulating side fins. Their swimming style show some advantages, such as precise motion control ability including motion stopping ability and low frequency sound noise. We considered that this feature can be used to underwater vehicle which need precise motion, for example undersea observation. Fig.1 shows squid swim in an aquarium. This picture was taken every 0.5 seconds. As this picture, they are able to change their attitude quickly. In this motion, they use only their side fins and their body mostly move only their running direction.

Fig.1: Swimming of Japanese common squid in the aquarium

Fig.2: Broad club cuttlefish and oval squid

Fig.2 show other creature undulating side fins to obtain thrust. They are Broad club cuttlefish and oval squid. Their fin motion are easier to observe than the one of Japanese common squid. Here though example of squid is shown, stingray also undulates their side fins to obtain thrust. But stingray don't repeat forward and backward motion, so we call this robot "Squid-like robot". And flounder also has the same fin and glide on the bottom. Various creature use this system to swim in the ocean smoothly and quickly. This method can be useful underwater technology, so we started to apply on the underwater vehicle.

As shown above, Squid-like underwater robot can move by using not jet propulsion but undulating side fins. Squid usually seems not to use jet propulsion. Now, the mechanism how fin can obtain thrust is explained. Here 2-dimensional wavy motion is used for simple explanation. Now we consider a 1m wave (wave length is 1/3 [m], frequency is 1 [Hz]). The equation is as follows. Here x is coordinate of direction of fin's length, and y is vertical displacement.

$$y = 0.05 \sin(2\pi kx - 2\pi ft) = 0.05 \sin 2\pi k(x - ct) \quad (2.1)$$

k : wave number 3(1/m), f :frequency 1(Hz), c :phase velocity of the wave 1/3(m/s)

Fig.3 shows the shape of fin every 1/8 seconds. And on upper fin ($t=0T$), normal velocity vectors of fin surface are also drawn. We consider that this fin do not move forward and undulating at the same place. High pressure is observed in the right hand side (upper surface) of negative gradient surface because upper surface push the water, and low pressure is observed in the left hand side(lower surface) at same place because under surface move away from the water. So in the negative gradient area, leftward force is obtained because of the difference of pressure between upper and lower surface. Since other area is same, total force is leftward. In the same undulation, Fig.4 show fin go to negative direction as fast as phase velocity. In this case, the pressure force cannot be obtained because the shape in water is same and the leading edge is moving leftward direction. As shown here, since relative phase velocity of fin's traveling wave against the water influence their thrust. So, the large breaking force is expected if the phase velocity direction changed. This effect can be seen from some experiment and calculation.

Fig.3: scheme of fin motion

Fig.4: scheme of fin progress

3. The research so far

As shown in prior chapter, we are interested in bio-inspired propulsion system by using undulating side fins like squid, stingray or flounder so we have researched so far. At first we considered simple shape with thin side fins. Before this thought, we considered a flat disk surrounded by fin as shown Fig.5 (a) because this model would be able to move in all direction. But it is difficult to make a mesh in CFD calculation, so we considered a simple model as shown Fig.5 (b). According to CFD calculation of this model, thrust can be obtained by undulated side fins.

Fig.5: Modelling

Since it is difficult to eliminate vertical force in CFD calculation, we considered a flat body because additional mass and drag for vertical direction of this shape is large, so then motion except travelling direction can be minimize. And we captured that fin is made by a lot of bones and film, so many bones need to be moved. Each bone is installed in order to rotate on its supporting point. This mechanism is so simple that we can reproduce by using cheap motor. A squid-like underwater robot with two undulating side fins has been studied by authors' group. For almost 15 years, 6 models were developed and tested in towing tank. Following is a series of Squid-like underwater robot.

3.1. Model 1

For first model, we used centipede toy as reference and apply a pair of DC motor. Each rotary shaft has 15 small gears and these gears turn clockwise or counter clockwise. By these small gears, the independent large gears rotates. The rotating motion of the gear is transformed into sinusoidal motion by scotch-yoke system. So the first preliminary model, Model-1, was using 15 Scotch-yokes unit in the air and making the travelling wave motion for each side fin. Fig.6 show the 1st model.

This model has a large strut compared with the body and has a large weight. So this robot was installed to double-hull boat to conduct a free run experiment. In spite of the resistance of the double-hull boat, 3[Hz] vibration of the fin gave this model about 0.2[m/s] speed. In back and forth progress test by switching the rotation direction, it was found that this robot could change its travelling direction. And this robot could rotate at one point with the right and left side fin's vibration reversed without moving its center of gravity. The experiment showed that the undulating side fins can produce the thrust and can be used as the thruster of underwater robot. In addition hydrodynamic force measurements were carried out using this model (Toda et.al, 2002) and we found it is possible to estimate hydrodynamic force by CFD.

Fig.6: Model-1

3.2. Model 2

For the 1st model, it was difficult to change the shape of fin because of using scotch-yoke system. So the Model-2 was introduced. This model had 16 servomotor units for each side fin to make the undulating fin motion. From those units, cables are connected to the control unit. Each servomotor was controlled separately by a remote computer to make any mode of fin motion. These units are connected to the control computer by 32 cables, as shown Fig.7.

By using Model 2, it became possible to measure hydrodynamic force at the different shape of the fin (wave number, amplitude distribution and so on). And it was found that a large angular velocity was obtained from rotating at one point. Free-running tests were also carried out for Model-2 (Toda et.al, 2004). We confirmed that this robot could move to sway direction by vibrating only side fin as standing wave.

Fig.7: Model-2

3.3. Model 3

Model 1 has a large strut and Model 2 consists of bulky cables which interfered the free movement. Later, an enhanced model, Model-3, was constructed without strut and bulky cables (Toda et. al, 2006). As shown Fig.8, the head of this model was round shaped, and it had 17 servo motors for each side to produce fin motion with the servo controller and the microcomputer installed inside the model. It had the caudal fin to change the depth. These fins also can be controlled timely by the ground computer. Various motions were demonstrated through free-running experiment. The model could turn over on its back. The 6-DOF direction motions were demonstrated and controlled easily on Model-3. However, the gravity center adjustment device was attached on the body which causes the resistance and induced some asymmetric hydrodynamic forces. The camera sensors were equipped.

Fig.8: Model-3

3.4. Model 4

Model-4, an updated version of Model-3 had the 17 servo motor units at each side to produce fin motion; the servo controllers and the microcomputer unit were installed inside the model. The model had one thin cable (6 m) that is connected to the floating wireless communication units to the computer on the ground for control. Additionally, it had two caudal fins longer than Model-3 had that is used to change the trim angle to change the depth during swimming. The wireless communication

system was changed to the general wireless LAN from RS232C system for better communication for both distance and speed. The center of gravity position and buoyancy could be adjusted by the system inside the model both vertically and horizontally. The outlook of Model-4 and some free run results were shown in Fig.9 and 10. The braking performance of the undulating fin propulsion system was investigated through free-running experiment, *Rahman et al. (2013)*.

Fig.9: Model-4

Fig.10: Model-4; swimming in Suma aquarium

As shown Fig.10, this robot can swim in the aquarium without attacking fish because frequency is not so large. And we decided the hydrodynamic force of equation of 6-DOF motion and made a simulator. We also conducted detailed braking test and confirmed that this robot could stop rapidly during translational and rotary motion.

3.5. Model 5

Although the performance of Model-4 was satisfactory, because of its large number of servo motors and complex control system the model was expensive and not so easy to be maintained. For Model-5, the underwater scotch yoke systems including gear systems were attached to the both side of the resistance body. Fig.11 show the outlook and Fig.12 show the scotch yoke system. Based on the experiment, the Model-5 configuration can be applied for small underwater vehicle for practical use. Because the mechanism is simple and the present control system is very simple set, the smaller and cheaper model can be built. The free-running test showed that performances of Model-5 for translational movement, turning motion and braking are good, *Rahman et al. (2014)*.

Fig.11: Model-5

Fig.12: Scotch-yoke system

By moving the caudal fin, the vehicle changes its depth during forward or backward motion like a glider. This way requires a long moving distance and it is hard to rearrange vehicle's attitude. Therefore, the next objective was to make the vertical motion in narrow space while keeping its horizontal attitude for Model-5. Model-5 can rotate at one point by introducing single motor control unit to each motor of the side fins. By using the rotational movement, two end fins on Model-5 can generate the lift to change the depth. The experiment was conducted by using different size of end fins and the results were obtained. Through the present study, the vertical motion of Model-5 using rotating motion and end fin was confirmed. The estimation method of vertical velocity using very simple wing theory can be used for rough prediction. By this vertical motion, the vehicle can look around in narrow space while changing its depth. The vehicle moving fast is not our interest. In addition to the precise motion at low frequency and stopping ability of Model-5, this vertical motion will be useful for the underwater activities.

Fig.13: End fin

Fig.14: Photos of experiment

4. Current research –Model 6-

Through the research of Model-5, it was found that the underwater scotch yoke systems are very convenient to make a cheaper and simpler one. So by using this system, we consider that a bigger model of this robot can be built in order to ride on it. Firstly we made a bigger fin including motor and gear, *Toda et al. (2014)*. We should have confirm whether this fin had a power to ride human and move. So then we conducted experiment and analysis to obtain the information of thrust, velocity and resistance in this fin.

4.1. Outline of the new model (one side fin)

Table I and Fig.15 show the dimensions or mass data. And I use an electric drill's motor because drill's motor is designed to stop once when excessive load is applied. In developing the new model, we suppose human ride on it. So since this safety design is useful, I use this motor. And Scotch yoke system was used. The small gear shaft is driven by DC motor and turns clockwise or counter clockwise. By this small gear, the large gear rotates. There is a pin distant from the pivot of the large gear. This pin sits in the slot of the yoke. Then the rotating motion of the gear is transformed into sinusoidal motion. The pin on the end of frame sits in the slot of the other side of the yoke so the frame's motion is sinusoidal and travelling wave of fin can be obtained.

Table I: Outline of 6th model

Entire weight	15.6(kg)	A side fin	
Resistor		Length	89.0(cm)
Length	127.3(cm)	Length of bone	18.7(cm)
Width	15.8(cm)	Thickness	0.5-1.6(cm)
Thickness	10.0(cm)	Number of bone	9
		A space between bones	11.0(cm)
		The maximum of swing angle	44.8(degrees)

Fig.15: Model 6 (a side fin)

And following equation express the form of this fin motion. Here x_m is the coordinate in the direction of the fin length and z_m is vertical displacement.

$$z_m = A_{max} \sin 2\pi(tf - x_m/\lambda) \quad (4.1)$$

- | | |
|---|---|
| A_{max} : Maximum amplitude of side fin $L \sin \theta_{max}$ (m) | f : Frequency of side fin |
| L : Length of side fin 0.876(m) | λ : Wave length of side fin L/k (m) |
| θ_{max} : Maximum angle of side fin $\pi/4$ (degree) | k : Wave number 1 |
| t : Time (s) | |

4.2. Thrust measuring test

Fig.16: Thrust measuring test

By using this new side fin, I conducted a thrust measuring test in order to check the thrust of fin in the rotary tank. As shown Fig.16, we fixed this side fin with dynamometer. And vibrating fin, we dash the water from forward at a regular speed. The difference of force between fin and water became load, and by measuring this value, we can measure the thrust T. Then we can get thrust coefficient and advance ratio by using T and other value. In each velocity of flowing water, I obtain the performance curve. If we know this curve, we can calculate and simulate the various performance value of some model. And Fig.17 show a look at experiment. We read the frequency of vibration from a picture filmed by two camera.

Fig.16: Thrust measuring test

Conducting this experiment, we could derive the relation (equation (4.4)) between J and K_T at the each velocity of a flowing fluid. To obtain this relation is important in our field in order to calculate velocity, thrust or acceleration. In Fig.17, the right hand side of the graph is part of forward motion and left hand side is part of backward motion. It is continuous at 0 point. This is the reason why the undulating side fins system has a high stopping ability. Unlike fin, the relation curve of propeller is not continuous at 0 point, like this. Then we use this relation to analyze.

Fig.17: Performance curve

$$J = \frac{u}{fD} \quad (4.2)$$

$$K_T = \frac{T}{\rho f^2 D^4} \quad (4.3)$$

$$K_T = -0.0137J^3 + 0.0588J^2 - 0.0918J + 0.0353 \quad (4.4)$$

J : Advance ratio K_T : Thrust coefficient
 u : Velocity f : Frequency of side fin
 D : Length of side fin T : Thrust ρ : Density

4.3. Motion estimation coming from numerical calculation

We simulated the motion of model-6 by solving motion equation and compared with actual motion of this model. Fig.18 show a coordinate system of this simulation. And equation (4.5) translates body-fixed system of coordinate into space fixed system of coordinate.

Fig.18: Coordinate system

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi & -\sin \psi & 0 \\ \sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.5)$$

By using this equation, relations between $\frac{dX}{dt}, \frac{dY}{dt}$ and u, v are expressed as following Eq.(4.6) to (4.8).

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = u \cos \psi - v \sin \psi \quad (4.6)$$

$$\frac{dY}{dt} = u \sin \psi + v \cos \psi \quad (4.7)$$

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = r \quad (4.8)$$

Next we show the motion equation to solve which is used to simulate.

$$\text{x-direction: } \frac{du}{dt} = (T_x - R_x + (M + M_y)rv)/(M + M_x) \quad (4.9)$$

$$\text{y-direction: } \frac{dv}{dt} = (T_y - R_y - (M + M_x)ru)/(M + M_y) \quad (4.10)$$

$$\text{z-axis : } \frac{dr}{dt} = (T_\psi - R_\psi)/(I_{zz} + J_{zz}) \quad (4.11)$$

Here, $T_x, T_y, T_\psi, R_x, R_y, R_\psi$ are expressed as following equation;

$$T_x = f_{xr} + f_{xl}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_y &= \frac{1}{2}|f_{xr}| - \frac{1}{2}|f_{xl}| \\
T_\psi &= (f_{xr} - f_{xl})(bB + fB)/2 \\
R_x &= C_x u |u| \\
R_y &= C_y v |v| + R_{yuv} \frac{u}{|u|} \\
R_\psi &= C_\psi r |r| + \frac{bL}{4} R_{yuv}
\end{aligned}$$

And each letter means as follows;

u, v	: Velocity in x or y direction(m/s)	r	: Angular velocity around z-axis(rad/s)
T_x, T_y	: Thrust of side fin(N)	T_ψ	: Moment of side fin(N · m)
R_x, R_y, R_ψ	: Resistance of body(N) or (N · m)		
M	: Mass(kg)	M_x, M_y	: Additional mass(kg)
I_{zz}	: Moment of inertia(kg · m ²)	J_{zz}	: Additional moment of inertia(kg · m ²)
f_{xr}, f_{xl}	: Thrust of each side fin(N)	bB	: Breadth of body 0.815(m)
fB	: Breadth of side fin 0.187(m)	bL	: Length of body 1.291(m)
C_x, C_y	: Resistance coefficient in each direction	C_ψ	: Resistance coefficient around axis
R_{yuv}	: Thrust in y direction generated in having inclination from travelling direction(N)		

Thrust T_x is expressed by thrust of each side fin f_{xr}, f_{xl} and T_y is defined as half of T_x . Moment of side fin T_ψ is also expressed by f_{xr}, f_{xl} . And f_{xr} and f_{xl} are calculated by performance curve of side fin. Following are specific equations.

$$J_{xr} = \frac{u + ((bB + fB)/2) \cdot r}{N_r \cdot fL} \quad (4.12)$$

$$J_{xl} = \frac{u - ((bB + fB)/2) \cdot r}{N_l \cdot fL} \quad (4.13)$$

$$K_{Tr} = -0.0137J_{xr}^3 + 0.0588J_{xr}^2 - 0.0918J_{xr} + 0.0353 \quad (4.14)$$

$$K_{Tl} = -0.0137J_{xl}^3 + 0.0588J_{xl}^2 - 0.0918J_{xl} + 0.0353 \quad (4.15)$$

$$f_{xr} = \rho \cdot K_{Tr} \cdot N_r^2 \cdot fL^4 \quad (4.16)$$

$$f_{xl} = \rho \cdot K_{Tl} \cdot N_l^2 \cdot fL^4 \quad (4.17)$$

J_{xr}, J_{xl} :	Advance ratio	K_{Tr}, K_{Tl} :	Thrust coefficient
N_r, N_l :	Frequency of each side fin	fL	: Length of side fin

Based on these equations, we solve 3-DOF motion equation by using fourth-order Runge-Kutta method to simulate.

4.4. Motion comparison

To check accuracy of motion simulation as shown in Chapter 4.3, we compared calculation result with actual motion of the model.

4.4.1. Outline of the Model-6

In order to compare, we pinched two side fins model by upper and lower wood board, as shown in Fig.19 and Table II shows the size of this instant model. In thrust measuring test, an electric drill's motor were used because it was designed to stop once when excessive load is applied. But because of the performance, experiment in high frequency could not be conducted. So in this experiment, we replaced new motor which has high revolution, generate larger torque and is easy to control. This motor is connected to the panel and controller as shown in Fig.20.

Fig.19: Instant model

Table II: Size of this instant model

Side fin		Wood board		Instant model	
Length	129.1(cm)	Length	104.2(cm)	Length	129.1(cm)
Width	15.8(cm)	Width	70.0(cm)	Width	81.5(cm)
Thickness	10.0(cm)	Thickness	1.2(cm)	Thickness	12.4(cm)
Weight	22.2(kg)	Weight	6.5(kg)	Weight	75.9(kg)

Fig.20: Panel and controller

4.4.2. Self-propulsion test

Self-propulsion test was conducted in the towing tank in Osaka University and states of motion were filmed by upper fixed camera as shown Fig.21. In order to assign side fin under the water surface and keep this model horizontal, balance weight and styrene form were installed as shown Fig.22. And we conducted a free running test, translational movement test and rotary motion test. In addition we also checked stopping ability.

Fig.21: Condition of experiment

Fig.22: Photo of used model

4.4.2.1. Free running test

We confirmed that this model could move freely in the water. Since battery was not inside the body, cable was connected. If battery and some control device can be loaded into the body, it will be possible to ride on and operate only by using two waterproof switch. Fig.23 shows the state of free running test.

Fig.23: Free running test

4.4.2.1. Translational movement test

First, we compared in translational movement. Variation of frequency is 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.1 and 1.2 Hz. It is assumed that C_d in x direction is 2.0, which is estimated from the shape of this instant model. Fig.24 shows the result in each frequency. When the velocity becomes larger, experiment value is smaller than estimation one. This would be because wave occurred on the water surface and pitch motion increased resistance. And Fig.25 show the comparison for translational movement in 0.75 Hz. The pictures were filmed every 2 s.

Fig.24 $f - v$ graph

Fig.25: Translational movement (0.75[Hz])

4.4.2.2. Rotary motion test

Next we compared in rotary motion. Frequency pattern was same as translational movement test. It is assumed that C_d around z axis is 8.0, which is also estimated from the shape of this instant model. Fig.26 shows the result in each frequency. When the velocity becomes larger, in similar to translational movement test, experiment value is smaller than estimation one. Styrene form reshaped when frequency was large, so this would increase resistance or one can think that tension of the cable affected. And Fig.27 compares for rotary motion in 0.75 Hz. The pictures were filmed every 2.0 s.

Fig.26 $f - \omega$ graph

Fig.27: Rotary motion (0.75[Hz])

4.4.2.3. Braking test

Finally we confirmed braking ability. Frequency pattern was 0.75 and 0.833[Hz]. Fig.28 shows the comparison for braking in 0.75 Hz. The pictures were filmed every 2 s. We could check that this model was able to stop rapidly and change the traveling direction quickly.

Fig.28: Braking test (0.75 Hz)

4.5. Future prospects

This present model is roughly made and cable is connected, so resistance was very large. Now we are making proper streamlined body form loaded a battery and other device. Switch lever and speed adjustment equipment will be also installed. After that we will conduct a residence and free run test. Fig.29 is a plan of this new model and Fig.30 is an expected appearance. In the future we will conduct free-run test ridding on it in the pool or sea.

Fig.29: Plan of the new model

Fig.30: An expected appearance

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Ship Design, Engineering and Construction in 2030 and Beyond

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Abstract

Technologies such as 3D Laser Scanning, Augmented Reality, Enhanced Visual Communication, Automation on the Shop Floor, Internet of Things, Materials Enhancements, Cloud Computing, 3D Printing, and Generative Design are all rapidly improving and more importantly, are set to converge in a synergistic way, enabling an explosion of technology that will affect all industries including shipbuilding. For various structural reasons, the shipbuilding industry may be hesitant to embrace these changes but countervailing forces will overcome this and result in different methods being used for design, engineering and construction in 2030 and beyond. This paper examines those technologies and the forces driving change.

1. Introduction

Due to structural reasons, the shipbuilding industry has historically been conservative regarding adopting new technology and embracing innovation. Authors of this paper have elaborated on those impediments extensively, *Morais et al. (2002)*. Yet, we now contend that the shipbuilding industry is at a tipping point, leading to a significant change in the way we build ships. Because technology innovations are happening on a broad front, we forecast significant real-world implications in the relatively near future (circa. 2030 and beyond). The structural impediments to embracing these changes will still be in place for the most part but the countervailing forces are set to overcome them.

2. Why change is about to happen

Four things will drive the change:

1. The hard times the shipbuilding industry is experiencing
2. New customer requirements
3. Evolving industry trends
4. Innovation across a broad spectrum

Let us look at each of those in turn. While examining these factors, think about how several of them re-inforce each other and further increase the likelihood of change.

2.1. The hard times the shipbuilding industry is experiencing

If we look at history, most companies innovate out of desperation, not when times are good. If we look at many sectors of the shipbuilding industry currently, they are definitely hitting hard times. If history repeats itself, we should see companies take drastic measures to become relevant again or stay as a market leader. These companies may be the first to free themselves of the baggage of traditions and embrace change.

2.2. New Customers Requirements

Customers are increasingly requiring and demanding much more sophisticated and complex ships. These requirements can be sourced from:

- Environmental regulations: There have been several regulations that will impose a reduction in emissions of up to 70%. This will require dramatic changes to ships from the shape of the

hull, the type of fuel, the materials used and even the type of paint required.

- Autonomous or semi-autonomous vessels: Shortages of over 92,000 ships' officers are expected by 2020. Hence, the desire to reduce or eliminate ship staff.
- Similar or shorter delivery cycles: Customers do not want to wait.
- Ship service lifecycle management: The cost of building a ship can be a small portion compared to the operating cost of a ship for its lifespan. This will require more digital information to be transitioned to the owner when they take possession and require more physical instruments to be added to today's designs. This will require inputs such as power and signal lines with redundancy that will take up space in an already cramped ship.
- New markets to be exploited: New markets are being discovered by various companies that did not exist in the past. These will require ships with unique functions and abilities.

Technology and process improvements can be used to address all these issues.

2.3. Evolving Industry Trends

Another factor driving change is evolving industry trends. These trends include:

- Demand for support of distributed concurrent environments: Shipbuilding projects are far more complex than almost any other manufacturing/construction projects. They involve coordination across a distributed environment of different departments, companies, offices, cities and countries. Furthermore, this work is not done in a linear fashion but in parallel (concurrently). Increasingly there is a demand for technology to support this better.
- Aging workforce: The shipbuilding workforce is aging and it is difficult for design agencies, engineering firms and shipyards to find highly skilled workers. Therefore, companies will be forced to turn to technology to help.
- Quality: It seems that quality is now appreciated again after a period of sacrificing quality for cost. Technology can be used to reduce errors.
- Automation: Currently, many activities are manual. However, lately, we have seen shipyards automating many of their processes including everything from communication to control of machines from 3D data. Automation allows a process to be repeatable, eliminates human error and allows workers to concentrate on other value-added activities. Automated processes also work on weekends and overtime at no additional cost. The incentive to change is clear.

2.4. Innovation across a Broad Spectrum

The fourth big driver of change is related to the nature of innovation itself. To understand the importance of this, you must realize that often when people examine innovation, they focus on the wrong thing. They pay attention to the pace of advancements in a particular technology and then use that to make predictions about the future. These predictions are usually wrong because you should never look at innovations in any particular field in isolation. The critical thing to watch is the breadth of innovation. You need to examine what innovations are happening in parallel fields. This is because, for any new technology to be adopted in the real world, a variety of supporting technologies have to be in place as well. Interestingly enough, this is what we now see happening. We see innovation across a broader spectrum than ever before and this is creating mutually reinforcing relationships.

For example, think of social networks such as Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn. The innovation of these social networks could not have happened if we did not have the internet, mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, and improved cellular data coverage at reasonable costs.

An innovation more related to shipbuilding is the 3D Laser Scanner for high definition surveying. 3D capturing devices have been around for a long time. However, it has only been recently that 3D laser scanning has become common in our industry. One reason is that laser scanners have significantly dropped in price. Just as importantly is the fact that the software to process the captured data now

requires very little training to use. Another factor is that most of the CAD software we use today can now handle enormously large point cloud datasets generated in shipbuilding at virtually little to no additional investment. The combination of these factors has led to the recent increased utilization of laser scanning in shipbuilding. One of them on its own would not be enough.

As we look to the future, we see increasing convergence and mutually reinforcing technologies such as Big Data analysis techniques that are enabled by increased processing power and harnessing the cloud. We see hardware and software supporting IoT (Internet of Things) becoming a reality which increases the amount of data available and spurs the development of machine learning algorithms. We are setting up the conditions for a technological explosion because we have never had so many technologies improve so rapidly at the same time. The combination of these will put many more tools in our toolbox.

3. How Engineering Design will work in the future

3.1. Client's requirements/ specifications

You can see the interaction of various technologies and industry trends in relationship to heightened customer requirements. Customer requirements were mentioned earlier in this essay but the importance of these cannot be stressed enough. In both the purchasing and operation of ships, clients are forced to make difficult decisions. For instance, determining the details of a ship's specifications and requirements can be challenging. Furthermore, if you consider that the lead-time to build a ship can be years, the best time to buy is not always clear. Every decision can be facilitated by having good data. A modern vessel generates about 20 GB of data per day. Fortunately, technology is now making this data available. In the future, we will aggregate all of it together and analyze it with Big Data techniques and artificial intelligence algorithms. This will enable owner/operators to understand the performance of certain routes with variables such as weather and cargo, etc. Increased data analysis will also assist them in determining the need for repairs or buying a new vessel.

3.2. Design of the Ship

After a client makes their list of requirements clear, new technologies will continue to help naval architects and engineers create better designs to suit the client's needs. Consider how things are currently done. For the initial design of a ship, naval architects perform many different calculations regarding hydrostatics, hydrodynamics, layout arrangements, loading information, seakeeping, manoeuvrability, safety scenarios, collision scenarios etc. They use several pieces of software to run through all the analyses. Unfortunately, the algorithms used today were designed to be run on a single physical box and therefore make several "assumptions" or "simplifications" to reduce the amount of time to do the analysis. Furthermore, each calculation performed has a symbiotic relationship to other calculations with one's outputs being the other's inputs. This creates a long chained feedback loop. Because each of these calculations can affect the design of a ship, after one calculation is run and decisions are made, naval architects input the modified design into another calculation. Then, its output results are fed into another calculation and so on. This iterative approach currently takes a long time for the designer. In the future, naval architects will leverage the power of the infinite computing of the cloud to speed up this process.

Infinite computing in the cloud will provide two significant benefits. First, because of the increased processing power, it will allow designers to modify algorithms so that they do not require the removal of details via simplification. Secondly, it will allow better integration between the products selected to do the analysis because vendors of cloud applications will increasingly handle this rather than the client. The result will be the ability to chain one set of calculations to another set of calculations with very little effort by the designer.

Because calculations will be so much easier, naval architects will be able to set a larger set of criteria and constraints and have several calculations generated depending upon different scenarios with each

cloud application feeding its output into another application's input. This could happen several hundreds of times, giving the designer the ability to analyze many more concepts and make more and more refinements.

The technology to do this will keep getting better and that will give designers even greater flexibility. The cloud application calculations will use existing algorithms but will potentially be developed differently to leverage the infinite parallelism of the cloud. There will also be new algorithms, which could possibly be a generative design of the hull shape, or an algorithm that takes information from the real world such as the previous operating cost of a ship or even the cost of manufacturing at a specific yard/region.

When the appropriate calculations are complete, they will allow orders of magnitude more variations than are done today. We are thus primed to see a greater variety in ship designs because we will have the ability to analyze designs more easily.

3.3. Integrating Customers into the Design

Greater design choice will be a significant change. Another will be increased interaction between customers and designers. There are some companies that already involve the customer in the design process; however, in the future, this is going to happen earlier and the time between customer feedback and a modified design will be very short.

The first time the customer will be able to review concept designs will be much earlier than is done today, largely because many of the calculations will be cloud based. When the concepts are presented to the client, they will be done visually, often using virtual reality, which will enable the customer and the designer to be on the same page from the start.

As the virtual reality model is reviewed, the designer will be able to point out various characteristics of the concepts and then get feedback from the client. Since there are always compromises that have to be made when designing a ship, the client might want to see a concept prioritizing one requirement over another (e.g. capacity vs. performance, changing a supplier or where it is manufactured, deck layout, etc.) Depending on the feedback, the designer will be able to update the criteria and re-run the analysis done in the initial phase. Again, using the cloud and potentially only a subset of calculations (just in order to get an idea) the new modified concept with all related data including the virtual reality model will be updated. This more interactive and instant feedback will significantly improve the results of meeting customer expectations as well as complete the overall task in less time.

After several comments and feedback from the client, the designer will generate a more complete set of calculations then detail the concept on which the customer and designer have collaborated. As you can see, this process will be a significant change from existing practice and it will be enabled by the technological industry trends already described.

4. How Detail Design and Planning will work in the future

4.1. Concurrent Engineering today

To understand this concept, let us review today's methods involving concurrent engineering. We all know there are thousands of activities that have to happen to build a ship. Performing many of these tasks in parallel (concurrently) rather than one after the other in a linear fashion theoretically reduces the duration needed for completing a project. However, things often do not happen as efficiently as planned. This is because concurrent work methods introduce new challenges, especially around communication, and require a different process, tools and also a new culture.

Fig.1: Linear vs. Concurrent Engineering

Progress has been made and is being made. Yet, if we examine how today’s concurrent workflows function, we will see that they are actually made up of many discrete static chunks; one set of tasks is completed by a person or team then moved to another. That is one reason we have not really resolved the challenge of departmental silos. Departments are producing smaller deliverables, which reduces the time it takes to pass on information to another department; yet, they are still working in their own bubbles with the information contained in their own systems.

Fig.2: Reality of Concurrent Static

Fig.3: Future: Concurrent Dynamic

In the future, we will be taking the next leap, moving from this “concurrent static” workflow to a “concurrent dynamic” workflow. This will result in information being available with significantly higher frequency, allowing better decisions based on up-to-date information.

4.2. Transparent Connections between people and systems

What we are talking about is a way for one system to provide information instantaneously to another system or stakeholder in a context that they can use, and at the time they need it.

4.2.1. Live – always on

Comparing the difference between concurrent static systems and concurrent dynamic systems is like this: Concurrent Static is analogous to watching the TV weather channel and waiting several minutes before the local forecast appears on screen. Concurrent Dynamic is like glancing at the home screen of your smart phone where you have set it to show the updated current weather forecast for your location. Concurrent Dynamic systems are always live, and always on.

4.2.2. Transparent to users

The underlying technology behind this will be quite sophisticated but it will be transparent to the end user; the end user will not be aware of the complexity. As the technology improves, the transfer of information between computer systems used in detail design will become more and more seamless. Much of the tedious serial and manual generation of data with low fidelity between teams will be eliminated. Information from each required discipline will be available when the need arises and in the correct context and format.

4.2.3. New systems to provide guidance

With new technology, we will start to get Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data systems that will be connected to various aspects of the shipbuilding process. These will be used during detail design and production planning to help planners analyze and take into account complex factors such as:

- Amount of sick days employees take during the week a block is being built
- Current cost/resources of lifting and turning using previous shipyard data
- Cost/resources of moving assets around the yard
- Risk of supplier delays during specific seasons

Analyses such as these will help in making better decisions to improve efficiency.

4.3. No more changing context and waiting

With a dynamic concurrent environment, the way we access information will also fundamentally change. Right now, when engineers have completed a static task, a person or multiple people generate different formats/representations of that information and pass it to a different department. This manual task will be automated in the future. There are several ways information will be passed. These are outlined as follows:

4.3.1. User Initiated Request

A person will be able to query/request information from another system without changing applications. This will allow the user to stay in the context (application) that they will use to make a decision based on the information they received. We will no longer have over 30% of people's time looking at and translating information from other teams into a different format.

Another reason that users will not have to change contexts is because there will be increasing use of Intelligent Virtual Assistants. These assistants are derived from the current chat bots we are hearing about from Microsoft and Facebook among others. Chat bots allow users to ask questions to the assistant and get answers. Examples could be:

- Who made modifications to ...?
- What parts were modified in ECR 123?
- What are the types of equipment's I can use in zone X?
- What compartment is this object in?

Intelligent Virtual assistants will also be able to perform actions. Examples could be:

- Open the drawing where this part is modelled
- Create me a visual representation of all changes in ECR 123
- Get me the Vendor Furnished Information for pump ABC

4.3.2. Asynchronous Automatic System Determination

In the future, people will not have to manually request information so much. They will be notified of issues they need to know about automatically, with the relevant information supplied and (depending on the complexity), little to no extraneous details. An example could be a weight engineer who is automatically sent information from the detail design model of a potential issue in a certain weight zone. The weight engineer will review the information provided and could then make a decision without changing context (applications) to:

- Ignore the automatic error/warning.
- Create a task for another team member to investigate and add additional notes.
- Choose to solve the issue at that time.

Another example would be planners who would get information relevant to them at an appropriate time, which would be different from the information received by workers on the waterfront.

4.3.3. Synchronous Knowledge Aware Engineering

Another difference in the future is that when a user is performing an action, a system will refer the result of what is being done to information contained in other connected systems. If there is a discrepancy, it will inform the user and in certain cases provide advice on what action to take. A couple of examples of this would be if the designer is modelling a frame and they accidentally selected the wrong stock of a plate or stiffener. The synchronous system would compare the result of what the user did with the information in the classification drawings. It would provide a window in the CAD application and tell the user that the stock they picked does not match the classification drawing. It would then provide an option to ignore this or change the stock.

The second example would be to have the synchronous system check a rule based knowledge system. These systems will continue to gain and build on their knowledge using artificial intelligence and machine learning strategies. The workflow would be similar to when the user models a deck drain system as usual but if a rule is not met (e.g. such as not extending a drain hole inlet a certain distance from the deck to account for the final surfacing), a window will be displayed about the error listing several actions the user could take.

4.4. Finally, the future has an As Built 3D model

Perhaps the best news is related to how detail design will work in the future is that As-Built 3D models will be widely used. Up until now, shipbuilders have not believed that the benefits were worth the costs. In the future, we predict this will change. There are three reasons for this:

- Context is king in the future
- Realization of benefit for production
- Digital Ship (aka. Digital Twin)

4.4.1. Context is king in the future

With the higher frequency of information being exchanged in the future, it will become more annoying to try to interpret the information provided into actionable decisions without some visual

context. Leveraging the 3D model and incorporating information in the model would be a much faster way to communicate. You can communicate more information with greater clarity compared to any textual method if you experience it visually. Visualization of information is a powerful thing so the shipbuilding industry will want As-Built models to use.

4.4.2. Realization of benefit for production: Shop Floor 3D

The production floor will be reaping the benefits of the 3D model. 2D paper documents may not totally be gone but a digital representation of the ship will be used on every production floor. There will be various ways to access it, possibly with some new technologies not even invented yet. Automation of shop floor machines will come directly from the 3D model, which will force the 3D model to be 100% accurate. Once the digital model is used on the waterfront, shipyards will start gaining the benefit of keeping the model up-to-date. This additional benefit will encourage shipyards to invest more in maintaining an As-Built model and drive its adoption into the mainstream.

4.4.3. Digital Ship (aka. Digital Twin)

There is no argument that maintaining an As-Built has additional costs. Therefore, probably the strongest driver for As-Builts will be the customer. As mentioned previously, future ship owners will need to have a better understanding of their asset and one way they will do this is with their requirement for a Digital Ship. It will be so important to them that they will pay extra cash to get an As-Built Model. This is because a digital ship will save them a lot of money during operations.

5. How Manufacturing will change in the future

5.1. Communication and Verification

The future will see improved communication before any physical construction starts, enhanced communication during manufacturing and more accurate views of progress along the way.

5.1. Paperless

One notable change will be the transition to digital communication. At the moment, most communication is via 2D paper drawings with special symbols. Experienced experts can translate the information in these drawings into a mental 3D view of the ship but this skill of interpretation is not being passed on well. This will hasten the move away from 2D paper drawings.

5.2. Virtual Reality

We will also see increased use of Virtual Reality (VR) as a communication tool to improve Production Engineering. Everyone knows that when designing a marine structure, you always need to be aware of your production capabilities. This includes the materials you purchase, equipment, facility constraints such as crane size per station, fabrication capabilities, and preference of construction sequence, etc. Unfortunately, even though designers are aware of the majority of these considerations, often, a single constraint is overlooked which can have significant downstream consequences.

VR continues to get better and better so will facilitate enhanced communication between Production and Manufacturing to prevent these kinds of problems. Virtual Reality will be used to show the final 3D model with rich data. It will further allow anyone (without any CAD experience) to move through the model, retrieve properties as well as mark up and comment on the design. It will be done in a Virtual Cave environment or using multiple large 3D screens without requiring special glasses.

A benefit we will have from Virtual Reality is that we will be able to see how the ship will be constructed at the yard. This will be done by connecting to other systems that have information about the schedule and logistics of the resources required and knowledge of movement of assets. Virtual

Reality representations will show the sequence of each block at each station and the progression of the blocks to create the ship. There will also be a virtual representation of the shipyard, by either 3D laser scanning or a 3D model. This will provide an improved experience and understanding of what is happening and offer the potential to find interferences during the moving of assets.

At any time, we will be to interrogate the information at each stage, such as the amount of welding and type, the work force estimate, and transport requirements, etc. This type of communication will present the whole picture with extreme clarity for all stakeholders. Decisions will be able to be made and in some cases will be displayed visually immediately during the meeting instead of days afterwards. This will improve collaboration between all stakeholders and allow them to first identify and then correct any critical issues before they become real issues.

5.3. 3D Printing / Holograms / Augmented Reality

Another form of communication will be with 3D Printing. Virtual communication is great and has tremendous benefit; however, in some cases it will be easier to communicate with the shop floor via something physical. The ability to 3D print a miniature size version of a particular stage will be able to communicate the design intent very clearly. We will also be able to use different colors to represent the items that are already built vs. items that need to be installed at this stage.

Another new communication method might be some sort of hologram. Still, another method will be the use of Augmented Reality, similar to what people are currently familiar with due to playing Pokémon Go. In manufacturing, shipbuilders will use Augmented Reality to “see” what they are producing in relation to the items already built. Tests on using Augmented Reality in shipbuilding have already being done *Matsuo (2016)*.

Fig.4: Snapshot of AR Application in a shipyard. From: *Matsuo and Shiraishi (2016)*

Consider the advantages of this. For instance, imagine you are pre-outfitting an assembly and you have the ability to use the information you retrieve to overlay what is to be added at this stage (e.g. pipes). It will be 100% clear what the assembly will need to look like when it is completed. In this Augmented Reality view, you will be able to see dimensions and all the relevant information you require. You will also be able to interrogate the virtual items to get more information.

5.4. Communication of Progress

By reflecting on these newer communication methods, we can see how progress will be tracked in the future. Using the Augmented Reality view or the Virtual Reality model, a user will simply check off the items installed and/or the welds completed and/or the items fabricated. This information will go back to a system monitoring the schedule to identify bottlenecks or potential costly delays.

If, during construction, there is a problem with the design, the shop floor user will be able to request guidance from an engineer via their virtual dashboard. This request will be processed by an external system that knows which engineer to request taking into account knowledge of the specific design in question, their vacation schedule, and various other considerations. The contacted engineer and the shop floor stakeholder will resolve any issues/questions and if there is a potential design change, the 3D design model will be updated to reflect the decisions they have chosen.

A final step of verification would be to laser scan the assembly to be stored for future reference. The scan would be conducted automatically either by pre-installed 3D scanners at the workstation or by drones which are equipped with the appropriate cameras/scanners. This 3D captured data would be used to validate what was actually built with what was designed by using a comparison tool that exists even today.

6. Worker Safety & Security

A further change regarding manufacturing will have to do with worker safety and security. Walking on the shop floor will probably look and feel much different from what it does today. One thing you will notice will be that when going through security, you will get a special badge or vest that will wirelessly transmit your location and monitor your vitals. This will not necessarily be because Big Brother wants to track every movement, but rather, it will be for the security and safety of workers.

From a security perspective, it will ensure that only the personnel with the correct security clearance could enter the appropriate areas of the yard. This will especially be used for yards building military vessels but also will be used for commercial yards if they may have some intellectual property that they do not want to share with certain visitors.

From the safety side of things, the badge or even a bracelet type of device will be able to report the worker's location and vitals. This will be especially important when working in very harsh environments where workers can get dehydrated and suffer from various symptoms that could be fatal. Alternatively, it could be for when the employee needs to work in an enclosed area with the potential of having very little oxygen. The tracking device will notify the worker when levels exceed safety limits and transmit the location of the worker when they are critical. In case of an emergency such as a fire, the shipyard will know if all workers are safe and accounted for. This will significantly reduce the injuries and fatalities due to environmental factors but also general health issues. This method also provides safety in the shipyard since it gives drones and cyber-physical systems awareness of where personnel are so they can avoid any potential of an incident with the workers.

7. Cyber-Physical Systems and Automation of Machines

Speaking of cyber-physical systems, in the future, we will see humans and robots work together. The robot will be aware of its surroundings including the human(s) they are working with. This means the robot will be able to respond and react to its environment to accomplish a task and never put the human at risk, even when the worker is doing something they should not.

There will also be numerous machines that will work 100% autonomously with no user input at all. This is not too far from what we have in some shipyards today where machines receive information directly from a 3D model to cut a raw plate stock or even a profile. There should be no need to have a human translate a drawing and input the data into the machine. These machines will also have auto loading capability, either from the machine itself and/or a general-purpose gantry that will load the material and take the end product to the appropriate location.

However, there will also be semi-automated systems that require human input. This will be due to the complexity of some of the tasks required to build unique and complex items. Examples of this could be aiding a robotic welder to weld two blocks together or an automatic lifting and turning system that will require some supervision and guidance.

8. Drones (UAV) & Autonomous Vehicles

Another thing you will notice at the shipyard of the future is the use of drones, aka. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV). You will see autonomous vehicles transporting materials and assets from one location to another location at the yard. This will allow yards to require less real estate for the shipyard. Aerial drones will move materials and assets during the night or off hours in order to prepare for the next shift. This will include bins of parts and materials such as rags, welding material, equipment, etc. It will closely resemble an Amazon warehouse where containers are packaged with a pick list of items required for the next day.

Drones will also be used by the shipyard and classification society to conduct verification and checks. These drones will be equipped with various types of sensors and a camera that will capture the information needed to verify what has been constructed. Indeed, DNV GL has already used drones for inspection.

Fig.5: DNV GL inspector with drone

9. IoT (Internet of Things)

Internet of Things (IoT) or variations of it such as Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), or Internet of Everything (IoE) will also change the landscape of the shipyard. IoT will allow sensors to track the location of every single part in the shipyard as well as the environment the part is in. IoT devices will be extremely small and durable to handle the harsh environment of shipbuilding. They will require no additional power source and most importantly, they will be so cost effective that they will be considered as disposable as today's paint stick.

These small devices will enable many of the technologies mentioned above, from drone delivery and autonomous vehicle delivery, to the ability to have real time knowledge of where every asset is located at the shipyard. Inventory of material will also automatically be managed by using the data provided by IoT.

IoT will provide valuable information on how the shipyard actually functions. This data will provide the Big Data required to get a holistic view of the shipyard and allow artificial intelligence algorithms to identify patterns and suggest improvements. Furthermore, IoT used on equipment will be used on the production machines on the yard including the new cyber-physical systems and drones deployed at the shipyard. The IoT on these devices will allow proper maintenance on the machines to identify when a machine needs attention. Once identified, the machine could be scheduled for maintenance with the appropriate parts being ordered ahead of time.

10. 3D Printing (Additive Manufacturing)

Increasingly, shipbuilding will use 3D printing. We will not be at a stage where the entire ship will be able to be 3D printed but some major blocks where it will be used are in the super structure. There, shipbuilders will leverage several new types of material such as graphene which is 100 times stronger than steel and less corrosive than stainless steel.

With 3D printing, shipbuilders will be able to generate new designs that are not possible today because the cost of using today's manufacturing techniques would be too high. With 3D printing, the possibility of creating new and innovative designs will inspire a new set of creativity and we will start seeing designs that are unique, aesthetically appealing, and very strong, with reduced weight, improved safety, and much more. This technology will feed back into the engineering of a ship and potentially change the way we design ships. It will not matter what type of ship you are creating; everyone will have a 3D printer just as everyone today has a Plate Nesting CNC machine.

3D printing will also be used to create new equipment and accessories. The ability for a supplier to be able to send their 3D printable part to your machine and for the yard to print it when it is required will be a common occurrence. Not all equipment will be printed like this but there will be a significant amount. This will reduce the amount of logistics and risk when it comes to sending physical parts.

Last but not least, 3D printing will be used to print shop tools and manufacturing aid tools. If a tool is broken, a request for a tool could be made so that it could be 3D printed on the spot. In addition, if a unique tool is required for a manufacturing station, a tool could be printed using the geometry of the parts to be assembled, getting a perfect tool each time.

11. The Journey Forward

As you read this paper, you will note that it has used bold language and made several predictions that admittedly might seem outlandish. Since we do not have a crystal ball, it is doubtful that all of these predictions will be correct. However, the things discussed are not so farfetched. Many of the solutions and technologies discussed are close to becoming mature (1-5 years) or are already being implemented at some shipyards. There are some powerful forces driving the industry to change and some good and mature technologies becoming available. Thus, it is reasonable to predict that the future will be at least somewhat as described. Furthermore, if history is any guide, we will see technologies developed that are not even imaginable at the moment and these will lead to changes that today would seem even more amazing.

Yet, things will not happen all at once. It will be a journey to the future and on this adventure, there will be many speedbumps, minefields and what today seem like impassable roadblocks.

12. People - Obstruction or Boost?

The biggest unknown with respect to which path we will take to the future of shipbuilding has to do with people, not technology. Three groups will have particular impact: regulators, classification societies and key influencers. Here is how they could affect this.

- **Regulators**
Shipbuilding is a very highly regulated industry. Regulations are required to keep the general public safe and ensure that industries and individual companies are operating within a certain code of ethics. However, regulations are often outdated and created by policy makers who do not have a holistic view. In some cases, regulations are created more for a political benefit than economic or citizen benefit.
- **Classification Societies**
Classification societies have a huge role in the future of shipbuilding. The majority of ships have to go through class approval so the rules and regulations classification societies develop

and impose are going to be very important. Classification societies are increasingly involving themselves with many innovations with hopes of being the dominant regulatory society. It will be interesting to watch how classification societies handle 3D printing and the new materials that are being developed.

- Industry Key Influencers
Every industry has several key figures who we look up to. When they talk, people listen. These leaders can have a tremendous impact on how fast or slow an industry will adopt something new.

13. Bits & Atoms

To see how regulators and other people can interact with the pace of technology, it is worthwhile to consider technology innovation in terms of bits & atoms. In this way of looking at things, Bits, in essence, translate to something that is digital and Atoms, to something that is physical. Here is an example. If you are reading this on a screen, the software you are reading this essay with is because of innovations in bits and the physical thing you are looking at (computer, tablet) is the atoms. Before the "Information Age", atoms were the dominant source of all revolutionary and evolutionary innovations in human history. In the digital revolution, bits have been at the epicentre of the majority of innovations. Relatively recently we have seen more focus on innovations combining bits and atoms which has been influenced by the tremendous parallel acceleration of bits and atoms innovations. Call this, "Bit-Atom" Innovation. Some examples are:

- Smart Phones - Atoms: powerful computer the size of a credit card; cameras; battery power; touch screen; storage; etc. Bits: social media; cloud apps; infinite computing; etc.
- Smart watches - Atoms: battery power; powerful miniature computers; sensors (e.g. heart rate, accelerometer); etc. Bits: software; connection to digital life; apps, etc.
- 3D Printing - Atoms: Material Development; quality components which are cost effective Bits: Easy creation of 3D model; generative design; free form; converting of 3D capture data
- Robots – Atoms: powerful and small microcontrollers; inexpensive components; sensors; etc. Bits: development tools; artificial intelligence; etc.
- Home automation - Atoms: small; cheap sensors; locks; motors; etc. Bits: cloud; personal command centers; analytics; big data; artificial intelligence; etc.

Fig.7: Innovation Trajectory: Bits, Atoms, and Bit-Atoms

The collision of bits and atoms is creating another inflection point where innovation will increase its rate of impact on what we do. We will see innovations in three areas: Bits, Atoms and the synergistic combination of both bits and atoms, Bit-Atoms, Fig.7. Innovation regarding bits has been rapid while innovation with atoms slowed in the latter decades of the 20th century. Part of this had to do with higher costs but part of it had to do with the fact that bits were less regulated—it was too difficult to regulate bits compared to atoms! In the new world of bit-atom innovation, atoms will start to evolve at a quicker pace as well, though there will still be challenges from people opposed to change. Hopefully, regulators will evolve their process, culture and mind-set to create wise regulations that protect us but do not inhibit innovation unnecessarily.

14. How this affects shipbuilding

While many manufacturing industries are starting to adopt more Bit-Atom (e.g. cyber physical) systems, the shipbuilding industry is still in the middle of its digital age and is mainly concentrated on bits. There are always occasional instances where shipbuilders are working with innovations with Bit-Atoms such as the autonomous ships, drones or cyber-physical systems; however, the short term focus will be still be on bits. Shipbuilding will start to focus on Bit-Atoms in the next few years on a larger scale as well as atoms (e.g. 3D printing with new material); however, there may be some challenges related to people-factors.

Regulators and classification societies could be an obstacle but they also have an opportunity to be an enabler of innovations in the future. Since shipbuilding still has a few years before reaching the next inflection point, there is an opportunity in that we can learn from the mistakes in other industries. There are some good signs in that classification societies are evolving and even driving some innovations, as in the usage of drones mentioned earlier. It will be important that this trend continue.

15. Conclusion

In summary, we have seen innovation across a broad front. It has most recently been with atoms but increasingly involves the interplay of both bits and atoms in a mutually reinforcing relationship. The stage is set for a technological explosion and new methods to be developed. The industry will be increasingly receptive to new methods for design and production and if not hindered unnecessarily, we will see higher quality ships produced more efficiently. Exciting times are ahead.

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1, 2, 3 – How Many Hulls Should a High-Performance Vessel have?

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Abstract

This paper describes design considerations of A&R shipyards for ship design, reflecting experience with monohulls, SWATH catamarans and SWASH trimarans. The paper explains the strengths and shortcomings of the various hull configurations. Different operational requirements lead to different "optimum" configurations. Examples from our shipyard's experience illustrate possible applications for the various hull configurations.

1. Introduction – What is good, what is best?

There has been a long discussion on what is the "best" hull configuration (monohull, catamaran, trimaran, or whatever), both in internet communities and in conferences such as HIPER, e. g. Bertorello *et al.* (2001), Thomas (2006), Davis and Holloway (2006), Klaka (2014). The word "best" is the superlative of "good". But good in what sense? What criterion do we pick to judge a design?

The answer will generally be "not a single one". We generally understand ship design as multi-criteria design or more recently as multi-criteria optimization. Formally, multi-criteria optimization is nonsense, as mathematically only a single function can be optimized, Bertram (2003). This apparent contradiction is solved in practice (in multi-criteria optimization projects) in two ways: (1) one criterion is selected as objective and the other criteria are formulated as constraints; (2) a weighted sum of multiple criteria forms an abstract optimization objective (best compromise).

As we have multiple criteria and possibly different weights (priorities) for these criteria in different applications (projects), it is not surprising that the "best" solution will vary and no single solution fits best for all. This will be discussed in more detail in the following.

2. Design Considerations

There are many criteria to consider in designing a ship, including:

- Building costs – often driven by the complexity of the design
- Operating costs – often (but not always) driven by energy efficiency respectively required propulsion power
- Seakeeping – comfort and operational limits may drive the utilization of a vessel.
- Maneuverability – may directly affect income for some working boats, such as tugs and offshore supply vessels.
- Deck area – may directly affect income for ferries or come with minimum requirements, e.g. for a helipad.
- Aesthetics – while subjective, this may be a key criterion for yachts where hull shapes may affect perceptions and limit designer options.
- Main dimensions like length, beam, draft and height for locks, harbors and bridges

Different projects will have different priorities and constraints in design criteria which give a first indication for the choice of hull configuration. For example, supply vessels and yachts often operate at low or zero speed. Then seakeeping aspects gain in importance and propulsion power requirements lose in importance, compared to e. g. a containership design project. Long and slender designs are often preferred by yacht designers for reasons of aesthetics, accepting corresponding challenges in maneuverability. For working boats, time is money and much time spent in maneuvering means that here shorter designs (often as multihulls due for power requirements) are chosen. In summary, there is no "one size (or hull configuration) fits them all".

3. Design Examples

3.1. Monohulls

A&R has built many kinds of monohulls. Starting from traditional sailing yachts, traditional minehunters, fast patrol craft, SAR cruisers, coastal freighters, numerous workboats and a large number of motor yachts was built. Not all of them were displacement ships. In 1972/73 the fastest diesel motor yacht "Kalamoun" was built by A&R, Fig. 1. Currently, A&R offers both, conventional minehunters, Fig. 2, and monohull navy vessels, like the project shown in Fig. 3. Most of the monohulls A&R builds today are luxury motor yachts, such as the "Secret" shown in Fig. 4.

A few years ago, a 60 m yacht was big; today it is "small". Lürssen built the 180 m yacht "Azzam". A&R is able to build up to 125 m.

Fig. 1: Planning Motor Yacht "Kalamoun"

Fig. 2: Conventional Minehunter

Fig. 3: Monohull Navy

Fig. 4: 83 m Monohull Yacht "Secret"

3.2. Catamarans / SWATHs

In the 1990s, when the HSC catamaran market was booming, A&R started cooperating with Linstøl in Norway. This resulted in a one-off delivery of the "Elbe City Jets" by A&R in 1996. We decided not to follow this development, but rather to investigate SWATH technology, Figs. 5 to 7.

A SWATH (Small Waterplane Area Twin Hull) is a catamaran with largely submerged buoyancy volume and relatively small waterplane area, <http://www.stabilityyachts.com/swath-history.html>, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Small-waterplane-area_twin_hull. Thus exciting forces in waves are much smaller than for other craft. SWATHs follow the principle of semi-submersible offshore rigs, designed to provide a working platform with minimized motions in open sea.

The SWATH idea is older than 100 years. During the 1960s and 1970s, naval architects reinvented the SWATH idea for research and military vessels in different countries. In Germany, major SWATH

activities started in the early 1990s. *Fach (2012)* gives a historical overview of SWATH technology with special focus on German developments.

Key characteristics of SWATH vessels are:

- Superior seakeeping
SWATH seakeeping is superior to similar-sized (conventional or unconventional) craft, over the whole speed range including zero speed.
- Large deck area
As all multihull ships, SWATH vessels feature a large deck area, typically 70% larger than in comparable monohulls. This is attractive for helicopter operation or passenger seat capacity.
- Higher power requirements, compared to monohull vessels with same length
As all multihull ships, frictional resistance is higher due to typically 30-40% larger wetted surface. As frictional resistance generally dominates, required power and typically also fuel consumption are higher than for monohulls. Depending on Froude number, *Fritsch and Bertram (2002)* give 20% higher power demand for catamarans than for monohulls.
- Weight sensitivity
Due to the small waterplane area, changes in weight and weight distribution lead to large changes in draft and trim. These affect then freeboard (safety considerations) and power requirements.
- Large draft
With largely submerged volume, you automatically have larger draft than in ships of comparable size or carrying capacity. This may be a constraint in some cases.
- Higher acquisition and operating costs, compared to monohull vessels with same length
Multihulls need more Aluminum or steel (typically 20%) and are frequently more complex in the design of machinery spaces. Consequently design and construction (both in terms of material and man-hours) costs more than for monohulls.

Fig. 5: Family of SWATH Pilot Vessels

Fig. 6: Crew Transfer Vessel for Offshore Wind Farm Service

Fig. 7: 62 m SWATH Design Study

Fig. 8: Futuristic SWATH Design FSY by Simon Geilen

SWATH technology has come a long way since the first patent in 1880. It is no longer regarded as an "unconventional" or even exotic concept, but has established a firm niche position whenever platforms with excellent seakeeping are required: SWATH vessels have been designed and built as pilot vessels, offshore wind farm service vessels, yachts, research vessels and navy vessels.

Fig. 8 shows a futuristic SWATH.

3.3. Trimaran / SWASH

There are different kinds of trimarans. *Armstrong (2004)* describes a stabilized monohull and compared the operability of monohulls, catamarans and trimarans in the Western Pacific. The idea for a SWASH (Small Waterplane Area Single Hull) arose, when smaller vessels than the successful 25 m SWATH design were asked for. Downsizing the 25 m vessels was not an option due to weight and cost issues.

Spethmann et al. (2012) reported that more than 70 year ago the "Deutsche Kriegsmarine" performed tests with a monohull semi-submersible. Also in USA, tests were made with such a vessel (Fig. 9). Essential for these vessels is a sophisticated ride control system. Assorted designs of such HYSWAS (Hydrofoil Supported Small Waterplane Area Ship) vessels appeared in the 1990s, in Germany, Japan and the USA.

Fig. 9: HYSWAS

In 2012, construction work started on the A&R SWASH, Fig. 11, *Fach (2012)*. The A&R SWASH is in essence a trimaran with a single, small waterplane area central hull for buoyancy and two very thin outriggers for stability. The A&R SWASH is 20 m long; its outriggers are 8 m long. The vessel is intended for pilots, offshore wind farms, patrol boat or others. Building costs are lower than for a SWATH, but higher than for a monohull. In many ways, the SWASH can be seen lying between monohull and SWATH in its characteristics.

The SWASH "Explorer" does not only explore new hull concepts, but also new propulsion concepts. In cooperation with Siemens, we tested hybrid diesel-electric low-speed propulsion as an attractive answer to operational challenges with frequent stop-and-go profiles, as for pilot vessels on the Elbe River.

Fig. 10: SWASH Concept - Outside (left) and Inside (right)

4. Conclusion

Structure follows strategy – also in ship design. The best hull configuration depends on the individual project specifications. Monohulls, catamarans (SWATH) and trimarans (SWASH) all coexist legitimately, as they all have specific strengths and shortcomings. Best is what best fits the requirements of the customer. 1, 2 or 3 hulls – he decides. A&R is prepared to follow the different requirements.

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Air Lubrication Technology – Past, Present and Future

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Abstract

This paper presents the span from the historical roots and background of air lubrication to actual research project results derived from full-scale demonstrators or as expected from the EcoLiner currently being under construction. Three techniques are discussed: Air Cavity Ships, Air-film and (micro-)bubble drag reduction.

1. Introduction

Strategies to reduce the frictional resistance of a ship has traceable been discussed even by one of the founding fathers of maritime research, Sir William Froude. The most intuitive approach to reduce ship resistance is to replace parts of a ship's flat bottom by actively ventilated recesses such that these areas insulate the ship's hull from the surrounding water. As friction in air is about just 2% of friction in water, the achievable drag reduction theoretically scales with $49/50$ and the area fraction that is exploited by such a cavity. However, additional free surfaces can, if not designed properly, cause a new wave-making or wave-breaking resistance once waves are generated inside these cavities. In the worst case, disturbances imposed by edges of the recesses are even spoiling the radiated waves of the ship. Samples of that are shown and discussed in the following.

Techniques to separate the hull from water by air could also be based on water repellent surfaces, so called air-film techniques. Contrary to constructive recesses, these techniques can do almost without hull-shape modifications, however, generating a sustainable (super-) water repellent surface effect to real ship hulls is challenging in many ways: toxic or luxuriant ingredients are practically not applicable and aging of the effect by unavoidable seawater pollutants or bio fouling are just a few problems faced. In theory, drag is reduced as high as in the air cavity case, however, practically the ineluctable instability of air films is restricting the achievable circumference of the air patches and this way causing a suboptimal crop of insulation.

The third technique discussed in the following is the control of turbulence by means of e.g. (micro-) air bubbles. Here the presence of the bubbles of dedicated size, and in particular regions of the boundary layer, is seen accountable for a reduced turbulent drag production. However, clustering of bubbles (coalescence) and washing out of bubbles into regions of less turbulence production activity is a yet unresolved problem causing relaxation of the drag reduction effect. Furthermore, the theoretical achievable drag reduction is limited to the laminar drag as still a Stokes-condition is valid at the hull and nevertheless a boundary layer is formed.

2. The past of air lubrication (up to 1999)

Since science discovered the composition of ship's drag, the idea arose to affect or minimise the frictional resistance, *Thill (2010)*. In 1875, Sir William Froude wrote to Bruno Joannes Tideman on the subject of air lubrication. In other words, as soon as scientists understood that a ship's drag can roughly be split into frictional and a residual resistance they not only brainstormed ideas to reduce the residual resistance, e.g. by streamlining the ship to reduce wave height and to avoid flow separation, but also ideas how to directly affect the frictional resistance.

2.1. Air based drag reduction techniques of the past

In the years till 1999 air lubricated vessels were not massively applied but still there are some examples worth being mentioned in the following.

Wing in Ground effect (WIG) - The wing in ground effect is a phenomenon increasing the lift of a moved forward profile by a favourable interaction of ground and pressure side of the profile. To be honest, a WIG is much more an aeroplane rather than a ship. However, until hovering the vessel is really sailing and the problems in the transition from sailing to hovering is a highly challenging research field yielding some innovative combinations of ship- air cushion- and WIG techniques, *Fischer (1998)*. Furthermore, in most countries a captains license is sufficient to “sail” such a vessel and not a pilot diploma. This makes WIGs an ultimate example of an air lubricated vessel, whereas “ship” here is purely seen from a legal perspective and the moment till hovering.

Hovercraft - A hovercraft is an air lubricated vessel. It is one of the few maritime applications that insulates by 100% the ship’s surface from the water and this way expose the whole usually wetted surface to gaseous friction. The company Hoverspeed successfully operated the English Canal from Dover to Calais in the years from 1981 onwards, with 6 SRN4-Hovercrafts at the beginning of service. Though with respect to time this formed the fastest link from continental Europe to England, the fleet was reduced to 2 vessels in 1990 and taken out of service in October 2000. Despite sailing without water contact, hovercrafts are not competitive with “traditional” vessels as they require an enormous amount of energy just to “float” and replace the air escaping between the flexible seals and the water surface, they do have a wave resistance as the moving pressure field is generating a wave pattern and the energy dissipating with the radiated waves originates from the propelling engines of the craft. Just two SRN4 Mk III vessels escaped from dismantling and are displayed in the Hovercraft Museum Lee-on-Solent. Any other application is mainly restricted to spare-time or military purposes.

Surface Effect Ships (SES) - The total insulation of the hull from the water is not fully avoiding a wave resistance, but, at the other hand, goes hand in hand with tremendous air losses and the inherently required power to compensate for that. So what if the sideward flexible seals of a hovercraft are replaced by –of course– streamlined bodies, preferably slender hulls from which a low resistance is known. This, in rough lines, is the philosophy of surface effect ships (SES), looking like a catamaran with very slender hulls and hovercraft-alike flexible seal creating a pressure tight compartment between the bridge deck and the hulls. This pressure tight compartment is actively filled with air. This pressurised air raises the vessel more out of the water than a traditional catamaran would sail. SES are used for fast transportation purposes, *Ozawa (1997)*, or military and patrol purposes, respectively, *Steen (2001)*. Even if often claimed to be the benefit of a SES, it is not a reduced displacement that is potentially improving the vessel’s performance. Resistance-wise it doesn’t matter whether air or steel is displacing the water. It is the net reduced wetted surface that reduces the drag of a SES when the vessel is carefully designed. Thus, even a SES is a successful representative of an air-lubricated vessel. However, for drag and friction reduction, respectively, a pressurised compartment between two catamaran’s hulls is not required, a much thinner layer of air is accomplishing the same job.

Air Cavity Ships (ACS) - When successively reducing the height of the cavity of a SES and displacing a higher percentage of the ships weight again by rigid steel rather than a dynamic cushion of air, the design principle of an air-cavity-ship is reached. By coincidence it is exactly the principle Sir Froude was discussing in the letter with Mr. Tideman. Even the subject of the discussion, the formation of an additional free surface at the ship’s bottom, is still an issue of concern and scientific research. Furthermore, air volumes within a fluid are seeking the way towards the upmost possible position; spirit-levels are based on this principle. As a consequence, any motion of a ship furnished with an air cavity in its flat bottom bares the risk that air from the cavity is escaping. This way, ACS are extremely sensitive to roll- and pitch-motions that they should – as much as technical feasible – avoid. Consequently, inland navigating ships are the lowest hanging fruits. ACS have a long record in the former Soviet Union for fast and slow sailing ships, *Sverchkov (2010)*, *Gorbachev (1993)* with good success. Unfortunately, the positive experience did scarcely (except for e.g. *Matveev (1999)*) penetrate through the iron curtain such that in Europe, despite the potential and plausible benefit of the ACS principle just a few and sometimes even inept attempts were made for an application. One typical example for the latter is the case of the inland navigating vessel TMS Myriam, now TMS Echternach. A feasibility study on this vessel at MARIN showed that there is a drag reduction potential of up to 40%. This figure is roughly in line with the fraction of the flat bottom that could be

used for hosting air cavities and the reduction of fluid friction to gaseous friction. Despite this promising potential, dockyard and owner opted for a traditional ship hull with add-on cavities as such cavities can be removed when not functioning. Trials indicated a much smaller but still positive drag reduction of just one third of the expected value. Since the principle failed the expectations by a factor of three, the cavities have been removed and the principle was for decades seen as not truly functioning. When estimating the additional resistance of an added-on cavity, however, the discrepancy of the imposed expectations can easily be explained. The necessity of severe structural modifications of the hull is seen as motivation of yet another air-lubrication technique.

Micro Bubble Drag Reduction (MB) - Tiny little bubbles in shear layers of fluid can –when having the right size and are kept at optimal distance to the surface– reduce the drag onto this surface by up to 80%, *Guin et al. (1998)*, yielding achievable net energy reductions for ships of up to 60%, *Merkle and Deutsch (1992)*. The principle is promising in many ways, as air is not seen as possible pollutant to water, as the technique can do almost without changing the ship's lines and structure, and as in theory it should be applicable to perpendicular walls as well. The latter could meanwhile be refuted in the EU project SMOOTH, *Thill (2010)*. Contrary to the previous techniques, MB drag reduction is not insulating the hull from the surrounding water, it is affecting the flow itself beneficially. As the flow cannot be released from a Stokes-boundary condition, the achievable drag reduction is more limited than the previous techniques. One thinkable restriction is seen in the laminar flow condition. In other words, MB drag can at the utmost reach the lower resistance of laminar flows.

2.2. Alternatives to air for reducing drag

For the sake of completeness, the pros and cons of alternative techniques will briefly be discussed as they yielded to the focusing to air lubrication as subject for vanguard maritime research.

Surfactants (polymers) - Adding polymers with certain features into a turbulent boundary layer (TBL) has shown severe drag reductions in lab-conditions, *Lumley (1973)*, *Virk (1975)*. It was discovered unexpectedly by Toms in 1946, *Schrauwers (1996)*. Irrespective of questionable environment implications, this technique requires a continuous seeding and the related infrastructure and procurement aboard. Polymer additives or other surfactants are, therefore, not seen as an applicable technique in naval architecture. However, the deeper and ever-growing understanding of the physics of polymer drag reduction, *Virk (1971,1975)*, *Warholic et al. (1999)*, *Brasseur et al. (2005)*, is relevant and helpful for the understanding of MB drag reduction.

Grooved surfaces (shark skin) – These are copied from nature and were investigated e.g. by Tang and Clark (1993). The orientation and shape of the grooves generate small vortices that interact with burst events in a turbulent boundary layer favourably. However, the vulnerable small structure plus the threat that they could lose their beneficial effect when overgrown by bio-fouling led to the decision to not focus on such techniques for naval applications.

LEBU and OLD - Large Eddy Break Up devices and Outer-Layer Devices firstly generate a penalty on drag as they are emerged structures onto a flat surface. Nevertheless they can be net efficient when beneficial affecting the momentum exchange in a TBL. Seen the fragile size and biofouling implications, these techniques were seen not suitable in naval applications.

Compliant coating – As the grooved surfaces, perpendicular to the flow direction deforming and vibrating surfaces, for instance being enabled by compliant coatings, can beneficially interact with the TBL yielding a net drag reduction as firstly been reported by, *Kramer (1957)*. As the response of the surface should meet the actual flow (speed-) requirements, the technique works either well at just one (ship's) speed, or an active adaptation of the skin is required. Nature could solve this by actively affecting the features of the skin, *Kramer (1960)*, for naval application this was seen far beyond technical possibilities. Furthermore, aging and fouling matter could spoil the benefit by shifting the beneficial frequencies, such that this technique is mentioned just for the sake of completeness.

2.3. Management summary of drag reduction techniques

The technologies as described in section 2 have been summarised in Table 1, *Thill (2002)*. Based on this information it was decided to concentrate further to air cavities and –films and to micro bubble drag reduction.

Table 1: Overview and implications of drag reduction techniques

Technique	Possible drag reduction in [%]	Problems in naval application
Aeronautical techniques	<20	Different Reynolds number
Air cavity	80	Air control and stability
Air film in combination with HWR coating	90	Control at vertical side walls
Bionics	!	Lack of rotating propulsors
Boundary layer suction	20	Is applied to some extent (e.g. by the efficiency increase caused by a working propeller)
Compliant coating	<7	Maintenance, earnings and aging
Magneto Hydrodynamics	?	Efficiency and complexity
Micro bubbles	80	Control and relaxation
OLD / LEBU	7-40	Bio fouling and slamming
Oscillating hull surface	<45	Mechanical complexity
Polymer additive	<80	Environment
Riblets	7-10	Bio Fouling
Slipping skin	9	Mechanical complexity
Transition delay	0	Too high Reynolds number of ships
Vortex generation	0	Effect not measurable

3. The present of air lubrication (2000-2016)

3.1. Sailing ships

A rather comprehensive overview of the impressive fleet of air lubricated vessels operating in Russia is given by *Sverchkov (2010)*. A full scale demonstrator was built within the research project PELS 2, Fig.1. At the left of Fig.1 the free surface underneath the ship is clearly visible. The painted chessboard pattern was used to determine the wave length and amplitude optically.

Fig.1: MS *Kraichgau*, experimental air supply system (left) and view inside an air cavity (right and close up left), courtesy of Damen (PELS 2 project)

3.2. Recent Research Projects

3.2.1. PELS 1

The project energy-saving air-lubricated ships (PELS 1) started in 2001 and was funded by the Dutch research funding platform e.e.t. (Programme office Economy, Ecology, Technology of the Dutch ministry of economy affairs). Four dockyards, one engineering office and two branch organisation together with MARIN joined forces on fundamental research on the subject of applicable drag reduction techniques for ships. A sound literature review addressed three techniques as interesting candidates for practical maritime applications, being air-cavity-ships, micro-bubble drag reduction and air films on super water repellent (SWR) coatings, *Fukuda et al. (2000)*. The latter was seen most promising as it could likely do with least constructive changings and, therefore, is suitable for retrofitting existing ships with drag reduction techniques. For the SWR tests an available painting was selected that is used to keep military antenna (domes) free from dust and dirt as rain cleans the treated surface from such impurities as the water droplets (including the pollutant particles) simply roll off. However, for maritime this painting is much too expensive with litre prices of several hundred dollars. Nevertheless, SWR coatings created large air carpets onto the treated surface that insulates the hull from water and this way generated the desired effect. They could do with the least air supply as the air verbatim stuck to the hull. The high degree of water repellence is expressed by a contact angle larger than 170° and is tried to visualise in the photographs in Fig.2.

Fig.2: SWR coating (HYREC™)

The principle of MB drag reduction was studied in detail. Dedicated LDV techniques that can do with bubble-light-scattering were developed and applied. The local void-fraction of gas could be measured and optical tracking of the bubbles was realised in a master thesis within the project, *Leijnse (2003)*.

Fig.3: LDV set-up (left) and void fraction measurement result (right)

The analysis of the bubble deformations showed that the bubbles oscillate in position and slightly in size and shape. A Fourier-analysis showed a distinct peak at – in this case a frequency of about 500

Hz, Fig.4 (right). This frequency coincides perfectly with the frequencies of ejection events in a TBL of 5-6 times T^+ as found by *Bogard and Tiederman (1987)*. Fig.4 (left) shows a comprehensive summary of flow phenomena in a TBL, *Meng (1998)*. Here T^+ is about 100, thus the hypothesis was derived that the bubbles interact with burst- and ejection events in a beneficial way, for instance that the inhibit or spatially restrict the ejections and this way reduce the turbulent drag production mechanisms. This would explain a net drag reduction in the flow, *Thill (2004)*.

Fig.4: Flow phenomena in a TBL (left) and analysed MB dynamics (right)

Besides this fundamental investigation practical developments were required to accurately use and measure gas flow quantities in maritime model tests. As if dealing and measuring two types of fluids wasn't demanding enough, all these techniques were designed to work even in vacuum, as the resistance and propulsion tests at MARIN were conducted in the depressurised towing tank or in the large cavitation tunnel of TU Berlin. The latter as Reynolds effects were suspected to play a role in particular for MB drag reduction. As the highest achievable Reynolds number in a towing tank is restricted and full scale measurements of drag are challenging in many ways, a section of a ship's bottom have been built in the large cavitation tunnel of Berlin and tested at flow speeds up to 11 m/s. This way a Reynolds number of about $8E7$ was realised. Drag reductions of about 40% have been validated and a slight dependency on the ambient pressure was observed.

Fig.5: High Reynolds number set-up (left) and results (right)

Besides MB and SWR, air cavities have been tests in PELS 1 as well, see Fig.6. All tests were conducted at two different scales, from which the small model was built in 10 segments and used for comprehensive seakeeping and manoeuvring tests as well, *Walree (2002)*.

The final findings of the PELS 1 project including visualising photographs are summarised in Table 2.

Fig.6: Large model (left) and small model (right)

Table 2: PELS 1 results

	Micro bubbles (MB)	Air film (SWR)	Air cavities (ACS)
Photograph:			
C_F Reduction (bottom area)	>40 %	>30 %	Dry bottom area measured and C_F of air used
Net power reduction	± 5 %	>5 %	>7 %

Fig.7: Ventilated propeller open water tests (left top), details of the propulsor (left below) and results (right)

All three techniques have been tested in waves, manoeuvres and calm water. The latter in terms of resistance and propulsion tests. Though ventilation of the propellers was as far as possible avoided by constructive means (rudder propellers with slender struts to let the air pass above the propeller and not leak along the low pressure domain along a traditional shaft, see Fig.7 left below), the behaviour of ventilated propellers was investigated in terms of enforced ventilated propellers, Fig.7 left top and related open water tests, Fig.7 right), *Thill (2005)*.

It was found that conventional propeller can cope with a rather huge amount of air before starting racing and that even when racing the total efficiency is not decreasing. However, when racing the advance coefficient changes unfavourably such that either constant ventilation should be enforced or CPP propellers should be used to compensate the virtual pitch reduction of a racing propeller. Either way, even this aspect is solvable, such that the next step consequently was the application of this technique, preferably within another research project.

3.2.2. PELS 2

PELS 1 was dedicated to fundamental research. Seen the encouraging results of Table 1 and Fig.7, a new consortium teamed up and successfully applied for research funding, this time within the Dutch Senter Novem. Target of this project was to apply the gained results of PELS 1, to close possible knowledge gaps and building the first full-scale demonstrator, Fig.1. In this consortium also issues such as the engineering of the air supply system and the development of dedicated bridge control systems were picked up. As lowest hanging fruits inland navigating vessels were addressed as here excited severe motions by external waves that could hamper the application due to increased air losses and resulting higher power demand of the blowers are of minor importance. Shallow water aspects were investigated within the largely parallel conducted SMOOTH project. Within PELS 2 air cavity ships were envisaged to be surveyed applied to inland pusher barges. These barges were “on stock” at one of the project’s partners and are regularly maintained. Within one of such a maintenance period one barge could have been converted and tested parallel to the original barge as plenty of them are available. However, after thorough CFD testing it needed to be concluded that the barges’ fullness and blunt bow is imposing severe 3D pressure fields over the whole length of the barge making it impossible to achieve a stable wave pattern inside the cavities. It was, therefore, decided to test the technique on a self-propelled inland navigating ship, the MV Kraichgau. A model was built at a scale of 1:7.7 and tested for reference purposes with a flat bottom and with several air cavity configurations within inbuilt recesses inside the flat bottom, Fig.8.

Fig.8: Model of MV Kraichgau (left) and a sample of tested bottom configuration (right)

Barges could have been tested parallel as the standard design would be available in large numbers for reference testing. The self-propelled vessel, however, needs to be tested as reference, thereafter being retro fitted with air cavities to eventually be tested as air cavity ship again. This complicated the field tests as weather conditions needed to be comparable. Too much trials measurement corrections were seen as not helpful as the applicability of air cavities should result from a direct comparison and not from comparing two sets of corrected trials measurements. In the end, depending on speed and loading conditions an impressive power reduction of $\pm 15\%$ was determined by means of model tests and full scale trials, Fig.9.

Fig.9: Trials of MV Kraichgau (left) and results (right)

3.2.3. SMOOTH

The 7th framework EU project Sustainable Methods for Optimal design and safe Operation of ships with air-lubricated Hulls (SMOOTH) brought drag reduction techniques for maritime applications to international EU level. MARIN initiated and coordinated this project with 11 European partners plus a supervisory board consisting of leading European end-users. Once it became apparent that both applied for projects were granted, the workscope of both projects (PELS 2 and SMOOTH) was mutually with the both financiers adjusted to avoid overlapping work and double funding. This allowed for an even more thorough approach and measurement campaign. The always constructive cooperation of the EU officer in this regard is gratefully acknowledged here. As identical models were shipped between 4 different test facilities, even possible facility effects could have been addressed. The answer beforehand: within the state of the art measurement accuracy no facility effects were observed.

Another topic was the full-scale survey of microbubbles enabled by the MB equipped inland ship Till Deymann provided by the SMOOTH partner New-Logistics. As this vessel is equipped with 4 rudder propellers for propulsion with poor accessibility of the shafts for placing the torque sensors, new equipment was developed at MARIN for the envisaged measurement campaign, Fig.10. Ship model and full-scale hull of Till Deymann were equipped with single ventilation strips at the bow made from dedicated porous media. Little – if any – drag reduction that was found at model scale could not be confirmed at full-scale. Seen the length of the full-scale ship (110 m) and the scale factor of $\lambda=9.286$ this was seen as evidence for relaxation phenomena as shown e.g by *Merkle and Deutsch (1992)*. In the light of these adverse findings on MB drag reduction it was decided to cancel further tests on Till Deymann and to “borough” the ACS ship Kraichgau from the PELS 2 consortium. This way interesting additional tests could have been conducted, for instance addressing the effect of different types of water (salt and fresh water). One remarkable work-package of SMOOTH was WP2 devoted to the development of SWR coatings for maritime application. The experimental one of PELS 1 is simply too expensive and the application rules are also not doable in the rather robust environment of a dockyard. Field tests on SWR were no part of the SMOOTH project. Model tests were performed at Istanbul Technical University and MARIN. One practical implication was found when handling the SWR coated ship models. Hydrophobic surfaces usually are lipophilic, in other words as the reject water they attract oil. Finger prints of staff handling the ship model already reduced the water repellent effect. One can easily imagine what remnants of oil will do to a SWR coated ship. Even if the painting was cheap, putting the vessel out of service for regularly repainting jobs would simply not be affordable. The segmented model of the PELS 1 project could have been tested at the large circulating tunnel of SSPA. The strong dependency of the cavity length with the drag reduction could

be investigated in more depth as in a tunnel there is no free surface at the ship's waterline that is affecting the wave pattern inside the cavity, too. In Fig.11 the setup in the tunnel is shown and one exemplary result of the local resistance measurements, *Thill (2010)*. If the design of the cavity is not appropriately selected, the expected drag reduction can, thus, even revert to a drag increase.

Fig.10: Till Deymann (left) and new torque sensors (right)

Fig.11: Local drag force measurements at the SSPA tunnel (left) and results (right)

3.2.4. STW (Stichting Technische Wetenschappen = Foundation of Technical Sciences)

There are, in general three thinkable ways to locally insulate a ship's hull from the water, Fig.12, *Rotte et al. (2016)*. Within a STW research project, Zverkhovskiy (2014) concentrated on external air cavities, Fig.12 (b)), in particular the stability of yet another free surface underneath a ship's hull. He could validate that the maximum stable length of such an enforced cavity is about half the length of a gravity wave length of that speed. This, as such a cavity reaches the hull's surface at the position of the first node.

Fig.12: Air layer techniques: natural air layer (a), external cavity (b) and hull integrated (internal) cavity (c)

The internal cavity can afford more lengths as there is sufficient height to cover the forthcoming wave crest of a gravity wave length, which explains the optimum at about 80% of the length as found in Fig.11. Zverkhovskiy showed also that it does matter where an enforced cavity starts, i.e. the increasing local Reynolds number does affect the stability of the free surface, Fig.13. This imposes an uncertain scale effect even to air cavities as the Reynolds number of ships could not have been tested in laboratories. However, averaged over time these effects vanish, Fig.14, and the amplitude of the disturbance is small enough to play a secondary role for full scale ships with integrated cavities. Within the same project, *Harleman (2012)* investigated experimentally and numerically the effect of turbulence on bubbles in wall bounded flows for better understanding of MB drag reduction. Within his set-up, tests at high Reynolds numbers were not possible. At the Reynolds numbers of his survey, even a drag increase by (electrolytic generated) MB was observed. It is not clear when and whether this will change at higher Reynolds numbers and provides thus space for future research.

Fig.13: Cavity stability

Fig.14: Different wave-systems on the external cavity surface, $V=1.5$ m/s. Top: instantaneous wave profile; Bottom: time averaged wave profile

4. The future of air lubrication (beyond 2016)

Drag reduction techniques are rightly in the focus of maritime (and fundamental) research. Admittedly at the start of the period used for section 3 the pressure due to high fuel prices was higher. Nevertheless, drag reduction is worth a closer look as it besides improving the profitability of the ship the technique can contribute to attain the climate targets as defined in Paris.

Even with the progress being made as described in this paper, there is still the desire, if not even the need, for future research as will be outlined in the following. Basic physics of micro bubble drag reduction are badly lacking at least for the high Reynolds numbers of sailing ships. Though remarkable progress is made in the field of direct numerical simulation (DNS) of turbulent structures, Fig.15, a DNS simulation of a complete ship including full two way bubble interaction is still too far away. Phenomena like clustering of bubbles and local turbulence interaction, e.g. for a better understanding of relaxation of drag reduction are still an important issue that for the meantime needs to be addressed experimentally. Three surface instabilities are limiting the applicability of enforced air

cavities and that they might play a secondary role for the reattachment features of the free surface for an internal air-cavity as well. Even if this is regarding the exploitable length of the cavity a second order effect, it might play a dominant role for estimating air losses at the trailing seal of a cavity and this way play a role for the overall energy balance of the ship. Air losses in calm water and seakeeping have been addressed by *Thill et al. (2005)*. The procedures developed for model tests are transferrable to full-scale air-supply control mechanisms, however, the control of air for an air-lubricated vessel can go much beyond than this; partly switching on and off parts of the lubricated ship's bottom can improve manoeuvring performance, safety (by reduced stopping distances) and comfort for passengers (noise and acceleration levels). Even after the two decades of applied research, there is still much work to be done.

Fig.15: DNS results of turbulent boundary layers, $Re=80 \dots 1000$.

Following the promising results of model and full scale tests, Damen decided to develop a new inland waterway standard as a successor of the Damen Riverliner. With the Ecoliner concept of Damen, Fig.16, the realisation of the innovative combination of Air-Lubrication (Air cavities), Hull Optimisation (CFD), Propulsion System (Flex-Tunnel) and Power Generation (LNG) is integrated to maximize energy efficiency and minimize emissions.

Fig.16: Damen Ecoliner concept (green above LNG system, blue air cavities, remaining figures CFD and hull details)

5. Conclusion

From the three surveyed techniques for air lubrication applied to ships air cavities are seen as the most promising. Consequently one prototype has been built on specs already. A potential of 15% net energy reduction was already confirmed, even for a 70m full scale demonstrator. Much research has been accomplished, much still has to be done, either for enabling practical applications for air-films or MB drag reduction, or for smart(er) control for improving the yet encouraging results of air cavity ships.

Acknowledgements

The author's first involvement in air lubrication applied to ships was at MARIN. Firstly pure in industrial research projects that cannot be made public here. MARIN very early decided to spend own efforts in the development, design and purchasing of suitable equipment to handle air in maritime research for being prepared once the market is requesting support. The far-sightedness of this vision and the freedom to actively shape this process is gratefully acknowledged. As a consequence, MARIN was well prepared applying for funded research projects on the subject, e.g. PELS 1&2 and SMOOTH. Without the funding by e.e.t., Senter Novem and the EU these projects could never be conducted, thus many thanks for the unique chance provided by these institutions. DST joint the SMOOTH project and provided the possibilities to continue the research in particular in the field of inland navigating vessels. Even after accomplishing the funded research projects, MARIN, DST and Damen continued dedicated research at own expenses to close some remaining knowledge gaps.

Last but not least thanks is owed to DUT, providing now the resources to consolidate the research and disseminating the achieved knowledge, either in terms of lectures and scientific exchange opportunities or writing papers like the presented one. Also DUT is actively pushing the knowledge further in terms of dedicated research projects. In this regard DUT is deeply beholden to STW, providing the means of funding that is essential for academic research in the Netherlands.

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A Novel Wind-Assistance Concept – Design by CFD

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Abstract

This paper presents a CFD analysis of a novel wind-assistance concept using STAR-CCM+ and a design optimisation tool OPTIMATE. The optimisation study takes into account the real operating conditions and the final results represent the best compromise between the key variables that affect the fuel consumption over realistic operational profiles.

1. Introduction

Electricity generation relies on converting energy from other sources of primary energy. It is still most commonly generated at power stations, primarily driven by heat engines that are fuelled by chemical combustion or nuclear fission. However, recently more and more emphasis is placed on generating electricity by other means such as the kinetic energy of flowing water and wind etc.

Ships operate in a wide range of environmental conditions and are constantly exposed to wind. If this source of energy can be tapped into to provide local source of electricity, it would reduce emissions and increase efficiency of ship operations. In normal operations this interaction produces only additional resistance, but CFD could help explore ways where the wind energy could be converted into useful energy by using novel devices.

2. Objective and Scope of the Work

The main challenges for such kind of devices are the amount of energy produced with respect to the additional drag generated from the device and any negative impact on other aspects of ship design such as structural strength or seakeeping characteristics. It is also important to ensure that the device can produce useful energy under majority of different operational conditions.

So far in the industry, wind tunnel tests are mainly used to perform such analyses. However, these results have their own drawbacks due to scaling effects and extrapolation techniques used. Hence, this paper looks at the possibility of exploring an idea for such a novel device which could be operated on ships to generate useful energy. The main objective is to develop and showcase a methodology that can be implemented to optimise the device within STAR-CCM+ at full scale.

3. Methodology

Starting from the basic idea of a ducted rotating device producing a torque as a consequence of the interaction with the fluid, the aim of the activity was to provide a possible methodology to apply in CFD that results in valid configurations in all the scenarios of interest. The CFD analysis of such device representing a novel concept has been conducted using STAR-CCM+ 11.02 (for the fluid dynamic part of the activity) and HEEDS/Optimate+ (for the optimization part of the activity).

The optimization study has been done on a simplified version of the geometry. In particular, the ship itself has been replaced by a step with the aim of reproducing the typical shape of the super-structure of the ship. All the studies were done in ship scale to eliminate any scaling errors. For the simplified geometry used for setting the methodology, a constant velocity profile for the wind, along the vertical direction, has been used. Due to the wide range of conditions in which a ship can operate, the study took into account different wind speeds (u_{ref}). In this case we limited this range to three values. In STAR-CCM+ these 3 wind speeds were described via a single Field Function, using a double *If Statement*:

$$u_{ref} = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } \$Time \leq 120 \\ -3 & \text{if } \$Time > 120 \text{ \& \& } \$Time \leq 170 \\ -4.5 & \text{if } \$Time > 170 \end{cases} \text{ [m/s]} \quad (a)$$

A plot of the u_{ref} as function of time is showed in Figure 7.

In this study, the 3 wind speeds used were:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{ref_1} &= 3 \text{ [m/s]} \\ u_{ref_2} &= 4.5 \text{ [m/s]} \\ u_{ref_3} &= 6 \text{ [m/s]} \end{aligned}$$

A specific “weight” w was assigned to each of them when the performances of the device was investigated:

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 &= 0.1 \\ w_2 &= 0.7 \\ w_3 &= 0.2 \end{aligned}$$

equivalent to percentage of time it is encountered.

In particular, the torque generated by the rotating device and the drag of the entire system were defined as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total Weighted Torque} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{Q}_i \cdot w_i \\ \text{Total Weighted Drag} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{D}_i \cdot w_i \end{aligned}$$

where $n = \text{number of wind speed}$
 $\bar{Q} = \text{mean value of the torque}$
 $\bar{D} = \text{mean value of the drag}$

Due to the number of variables involved in such a kind of study, a fully automated optimization analysis was performed in order to find the best combination of geometry configurations and the positions on the superstructure of a ship.

3.1 Geometry of the Step case

An overview of the computational domain is provided in Figs.1 and 2. The *Overset Region* in the shape of a cylinder included the rotating device and was completely built inside the 3D-CAD. This gave the possibility to parametrize the geometry and expose all parameters inside HEEDS/Optimate+ as variables of the optimization study. The rectangular domain (*Background Region*) containing the simplified geometry of a ship’s superstructure and the duct of the rotating device as shown in Fig.2.

3.2 Parametrization of the Geometry

In order to expose the geometric parameters in HEEDS/Optimate+, it is necessary to draw the geometry in the 3D-CAD tool. A sketch with some of the turbine parameters is shown in Figs.3 and 4. The initial idea of exposing independently all the blades’ (P_i , *blade’s Length*, *blades Number*, *Overset TranslationY (OTY)* and *Overset TranslationZ (OTZ)*, with $i=1,2,3,4$) and duct’s control points (P_i , *horizontalDistance* and P_i , *horizontalDistance*, P_i , with $i=1,2,3,4$) proved inefficient for an optimization study. The lack of constraint preventing intersections between the duct itself and the rotating turbine were producing a too large number of invalid geometry configurations for HEEDS/Optimate+, affecting the quality of the optimization process.

For this reason, a specific procedure was implemented where some of the parameters were defined as “dependent variables” of other quantities explicitly treated as variables of the optimization study.

The same approach has been used to parametrize the shape and the position of the duct. This has been modelled via a spline with 4 control points (P_i , $i=1, 2, 3, 4$. $P1$ and $P4$ were the control points of the Leading Edge and the Trailing Edge, respectively).

In addition we specified:

- Independent Turbine Variables
bladeNumbers: number of blades.
P1, P2, P3: control points coordinate of the spline used to model the blade shape.
OversetTranslationY (OTY): horizontal position of the turbine.
OversetTranslationZ (OTZ): vertical position of the turbine.
K1: vertical distance between the turbine blade and the duct.
- Independent Duct Variables
P1horizontalDistance: horizontal position of the Trailing Edge of the duct.
P4horizontalDistance: horizontal position of the Leading Edge of the duct.
P4verticalDistance: vertical position of the Leading Edge of the duct.
K4: scaling coefficient for the Trailing Edge vertical position.
- Independent Shared Variables
K2: it controls the vertical distance between the turbine blade and the superstructure by modifying the length of the wind turbine blade. It also influences the vertical position of the duct control point P_2 .
- Dependent Variables
 These are variables that are part of the optimization process but, in order to reduce the number of invalid geometry configurations, their values are not explicitly assigned by HEEDS/Optimate+/user. These values are calculated via specific formula as function of one or more independent variables:

$$BL = K_2 \cdot OTZ \quad (1)$$

It defines the length of the turbine blade as function of the vertical position of the turbine itself.

$$P_2vD = 5 + K_1 \cdot (OTZ + BL) \quad (2)$$

Vertical position of the duct control point, P_2 ($=P_2verticalDistance$).

$$K_3 = (OTY_{max} - OTY) / (OTY_{max} - OTY_{min}) \quad (3)$$

It is a “distance coefficient” that varies linearly from 0 to 1, inversely proportional to *OversetTranslationY*.

OTY_{max} and OTY_{min} are the maximum and minimum horizontal translation of the wind turbine.

$$P_1vD = K_4 \cdot [K_3 \cdot P_2vD + (1 - K_3) \cdot \min(P_1vD)] \quad (4)$$

Where P_1vD is the vertical position of the duct Trailing Edge ($=P_1verticalDistance$).

With this formulation, the position of the Trailing Edge of the duct moves up when the turbine is close to it, in order to avoid collision and invalid geometries (Figure 5).

$$P_3vD = (1-K_3) \cdot P_2vD + (K_3) \cdot \min(P_3vD) \quad (5)$$

Where P_3vD is the vertical position of the duct's control point, P_3 .

Fig.6 shows how the dependency of P_1vD with respect the horizontal position of the turbine, K_3 , and K_4 .

3.3 Physics

Only the part of the domain exposed to the air was defined, so a single phase approach was used. The turbulence model used is the Realizable K-Epsilon and the flow is solved as Segregated. The Two-Layer All Y+ wall treatment was used to solve the boundary layer. Due to the transient nature of the flow, the Implicit Unsteady solver was used (1st Order Temporal Discretization scheme). The flow was considered incompressible. In STAR-CCM+, Moments of Inertia and rotations are always calculated with respect the position of the Centre of Mass (*CoM*) and this quantity depends on the position of the wind turbine.

3.4 DFBI motion

The motion of the rotating device was totally un-prescribed and it was dependent on the geometry of the device itself and the duct. For this reason, the DFBI solver has been enabled. This solver required the definition of the mass properties and in particular of the initial conditions. The wind turbine location was a variable of the optimization study (*OversetTranslationY* and *OversetTranslationZ*) so a Java Macro has been defined (*MoveOversetMesh.java*). This macro was then used to update the initial position of the *Centre of Mass* accordingly with the overset translation chosen by the optimization algorithm.

3.5 Overset Approach

The Overset Methodology allows superimposing arbitrary number of meshes over each another. The component grids are allowed to overlap and flow field information is transmitted from one grid to another through the overlap region.

This methodology has been used in order to model the rotating device and is particularly suitable for this kind of analysis allowing easy movement the rotating device around the ship without involving any extra operation (i.e. *Boolean > subtract*, definition of sliding interfaces).

As soon as the overset interface is defined a layer of ACCEPTOR cells is identified. This acceptor or ghost cell must provide information to allow the calculation of cell center values in active cell and Face fluxes on the face between active cell and the acceptor (ghost) cell.

For each acceptor cell there are a number of donor cells in the other mesh that are used to determine the contribution of the acceptor cell. The exact relationship between donor and acceptor cells depends on the interpolation scheme used. In this case the *Linear Scheme* was used.

3.6 Mesh Strategy

The computational domains were discretised using a trimmed-cell mesh, comprising of hexahedron cells aligned with the direction of the nominal flow. This way, the mesh-induced numerical diffusion is kept to a minimum.

The mesh strategy has been partially affected by the overset methodology. It actually imposes that "mesh sizes had to match as much as possible around the overset boundary". In general it requires the definition of a volumetric control with the same mesh settings in both regions.

Due to the fact that the overset region position is a variable of the optimization study, it was necessary to define a specific strategy to ensure that the volumetric control was always in the correct position. To do this, the volumetric control has been defined in the Body 1 coordinate system such that it is constantly updated via the Java macro.

The same procedure has been used for defining all the volumetric controls for the refinement in the turbine's wake. This ensured that the same mesh strategy was applied in all the geometric configurations.

The duct geometry (profile's shape and length) is also part of the optimization study and so it is affected by modifications. A fixed volumetric control would have worked only if a similar strategy was used for the wind turbine. Instead of using another (and similar to the previous) Java macro, the STAR-CCM+ Wake Refinement feature has been used, instead.

By specifying the *Distance*, *Direction*, *Spread Angle*, the *Target Size* and the boundary (the duct, in this case), a “*shape independent*” fully automated wake refinement was defined, Fig.5.

4. Optimization Strategy

The aim of the study was to find the geometric configurations of the duct and the wind turbine (shape and position) which are able to generate the highest power at the minimum cost in terms of additional produced drag, at three different wind speeds. This meant that the final result was the one that represented the best compromise between the variables involved rather than performing best at any particular wind speed.

Using the formula for the Weighted Torque

$$Total\ Weighted\ Torque = \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{T}_i \cdot w_i$$

and the definition of Power generated by a wind turbine: $P = W / dt = T \theta / dt = T \omega$ [W]

where

dt = time taken [s]

$\omega = \theta / dt = 2 \pi n$ = angular velocity [rad/s]

In HEEDS/Optimate+ the objective function for the power to be maximized, was defined as:

$$Total\ Weighted\ Turbine\ Power = \sum_{i=1}^3 \bar{T} \omega_i \cdot w_i \quad (6)$$

The second objective was to minimize the Drag, defined as:

$$Total\ Weighted\ Drag = \sum_{i=1}^3 \bar{D}_i \cdot w_i \quad (7)$$

Due to the fact that two objectives were defined for this simulation, the MO-SHERPA algorithm for the definition of the Pareto front was used in the optimization study.

4.1 SHERPA and MO-SHERPA algorithm in HEEDS/Optimate+

SHERPA is a proprietary hybrid and adaptive search strategy available within the HEEDS software code, which forms part of CD-adapco software suite. During a single parametric optimization study, SHERPA uses the elements of multiple search methods simultaneously (not sequentially) in a unique blended manner. This approach attempts to take advantage of the best attributes of each method. Attributes from a combination of global and local search methods are used, and each participating

approach contains internal tuning parameters that are modified automatically during the search according to knowledge gained about the nature of the design space. This evolving knowledge about the design space also determines when and to what extent each approach contributes to the search. In other words, SHERPA efficiently learns about the design space and adapts itself so as to effectively search all sorts of design spaces, even very complicated ones.

Another important feature of SHERPA is that it is a direct optimization algorithm in which all function evaluations are performed using the actual model as opposed to an approximate response surface model. MO-SHERPA (Multi-Objective SHERPA) is a specific version of the algorithm SHERPA for multi-objective Pareto search. It works fundamentally like SHERPA, but has the advantage of handling multiple objectives independently of each other to provide a set of solutions, each of which is optimal in some sense for one of the objectives.

5. Results

The first objective was to develop a sufficiently robust methodology for an optimization study. The quite large number of totally independent geometric variables involved in the optimization study was unavoidably generating a too large number of invalid configurations. In a preliminary CAD Robustness test performed in HEEDS/Optimate+ only 31.5% of designs resulted valid. By using the methodology described by the formulas (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5), the CAD Robustness test showed a score of 91.5%, Fig.8.

It has been chosen to run 128 designs for the optimization study and this allowed building the Pareto Front for the Total Weighted Drag vs the Total Weighted Turbine Power, Fig.9. By looking at all the Non-Error Designs the first important information that was obtained was that a non-negligible number of designs showed a very low Turbine Power with a quite high Drag (left hand side of the plot showed in Fig.9). By analysing the results, these designs were all characterized by an “oscillating” turbine. In other words, the interaction with the flow was not able to let the turbine start rotating, resulting in an oscillation of the rotational speed around 0 rad/s.

Fig.10a shows a comparison between the instantaneous drag of the baseline and some of the best designs identified by SHERPA. It appears evident that the mean value of all the best designs are lower than the baseline (from a minimum of ~9% to a maximum of ~22%, depending on the wind speed). This result has been justified by the fact that the baseline case was characterized by a large flow recirculation downward the step, Fig.10b. This separated flow was mostly reduced (in some cases completely removed) by the action produced by the duct. The expected extra resistance produced by the turbine was, in the Pareto Front designs, lower than the reduction produced by the “duct effect”. If confirmed on a ship, an important consequence of this is a reduction of power required to keep the ship’s cruise speed, under these wind conditions.

In terms of Total Weighted Power, it is important to highlight that a not negligible aspect in this study was “the time required for the wind turbine to produce power”. For this reason, in this activity a physical time of 220 s was fixed and the performances of the different designs were evaluated only within this interval of time. With this assumption, the designs on the Pareto Front are the ones that, limited to the first 220 s, are producing the largest amount of ideal power at the minimum cost in terms of drag. Fig.11 shows the instantaneous torque produced by some of the design on the Pareto Front. In this plot, the curve named Torque001 refers to the baseline design run in HEEDS/Optimate+. All the designs on the Pareto Front are optimized compared to it.

6. Conclusions

This activity was primarily focused on showcasing how current state of art CFD technology, available in STAR-CCM+, allows exploration and testing of ideas, such as performance optimization study on a novel green energy concept under several wind conditions. The parametrization of the geometry, achieved using 3D-CAD in STAR-CCM+, gave the possibility to expose these quantities in

HEEDS/Optimate+ and easily update the configuration during the run. In order to improve the quality of the optimization study, it proved necessary to define some design parameters as function of others. This allowed to automatically control the shape of the geometries in order to reduce as much as possible the number of invalid configurations (~8.6%).

An additional achievement obtained with this approach, was represented by the reduction of the number of parameters to optimize (11). The mesh strategy applied (wake refinement feature and volumetric controls location defined as a function of the Centre of Mass of the turbine) guaranteed a consistent method and quality of the mesh, fundamental for a comparative study. In terms of flow solution, the studies on the simplified version of the ship identified some geometric configurations that were not able to let the wind turbine “start” i.e. rotate, resulting in a very low level of power produced. The optimization was performed based on “weighted” quantities, but looking at the instantaneous values and comparing Pareto front design with the baseline showed a large improvement at each wind speed, Fig.12. The effect of the duct reduced the total drag of the system and all the designs on the Pareto Front resulted in better performances than the baseline geometry (no duct, no turbine).

7. Future Development

The next step is to apply the same methodology on actual geometry of a ship superstructure. At the moment, two possible approaches are under investigation:

- The device is optimized on a simplified geometry and then “installed” on the ship.
- The optimization study is done directly on the ship geometry. This second approach is more computationally expensive but at the same time gives the opportunity to let HEEDS/Optimate+ to do a deeper investigation, exploring a wider range of possible locations for the device. It also gives the possibility to define structural constraints.

Fig.1: Overset Domain containing the turbine

Fig.2: Background Domain containing the flap and the simplified ship geometry

Fig.3: Parametrization of the blade profile in 3D-CAD

Fig.4: Parametrization of the duct profile and position

Fig.5: Mesh Refinement in the Overset (red) and Background (black) region

Fig.6: Position of the duct's TE as function of the horizontal position of the turbine

Fig.7: Wind speed has function of time

Fig.8: Non error designs vs error designs due to unfeasible geometry configurations

Fig 9: Pareto Front calculated by SHERPA

Fig.10a: Comparison between the drag of the baseline (no turbine, no flap) with the drag generated by some of the Pareto Front designs.

Fig.10b: Effect of the duct on the recirculation of the flow

Fig.11: Instantaneous Torque produced by the Pareto Front Design vs the Design 001

Fig.12: Instantaneous Power produced by the Pareto Front Designs vs the Design 001

Flagella Inspired Propulsion for AUVs

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Abstract

This paper presents an original design of an autonomous underwater vehicle where thrust force is created by the helicoidal shape of the hull. Propulsion force is created by counter-rotating bow and stern parts. The middle part of the vehicle contains all control mechanisms and communications that control the orientation of the vehicle. To solve the orientation problem special code is required using Arduino capabilities, adapting stabilization method of torques directed in opposite directions. The dynamics of AUV are simulated using multibody simulation software MSC Adams. Surrogate polynomial metamodels are created for simulation of water resistance forces and torques.

1. Introduction

Currently the most common underwater propulsion types are propellers. This propulsive force generator is also used for automated underwater vehicles, such as ships and other water vessels. As there has always been a tendency to borrow new mechanical ideas from nature and biological organisms, in past years many autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) have been implemented according to the principle of fish-movement body/caudal fin propulsion. But in the world of bacteria, one of the ways to obtain locomotion is by rotating (like cork-screws) all parts of the body or flapping flagella, Purcell (1977), which is the simplest swimming method for a micro system. Bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Spirochaetes* and many others move by rotating flexible parts of the body – one or many flagellas, Eisenbach (2011). At present there exist several scientific works on the simulation of flexible flagella motor-actuated bacteria dynamics and some physical experiments have been done with rotation of flexible helical tail constructions, Flores (2005), mainly using external magnetic field to drive them, Ishiyama (2000). Contra-rotating propellers (CRP) are well established as one of the most efficient technologies, Caponnetto (2000), but in this paper we study contra-rotating parts of hull. So far there is no known functioning AUV that works on the basis of this principle. Only similarity in 2 dimensions from one point of view can be found in a robot based on the black ghost knife fish or *Apteronotus albifrons*, which uses inward counter-propagating waves for hovering or vertical swimming, Curet (2011). For human beings travel in a vehicle where all parts are rotating is not acceptable, but with the help of a rapid control system this is not an obstacle for AUV's.

Fig.1: The structure of Durbis-2. 1, 2 – rear and front screw, 3 – mid-body front part, 4 – mid-body rear part, 5 – cross/ vector kite gimbal, 6 – servo, 7 – servo connector, 8 – shaft connecting connector and gimbal ring, 9 – analog signal receiver, 10 – battery, 11 – PDM type speed controller for DC motors, 12 – hull with DC motor and reducer, 13 – drive shaft, 14 – screw axis.

At Riga Technical University the design of AUV was developed using two reflection-symmetric parts with a helical shape. The parts are connected with motorized rotational joints. The vehicle contains a central part, Fig.1, with the hull built from elastic material. The central part contains a Cardan (universal) joint with two servomotors. The motorized Cardan joint implements the two-directional bending of the hull and allows maneuvering the vehicle. The direction control algorithm uses angular orientation sensor information. The AUV has 10 degrees of freedom.

2. Model design

The initial idea for the model came from the E. Coli bacteria that use external rotating body parts, called *flagellas*. Later we studied other bacteria that have the entire body in the form of a spiral (*Spirochaetes*) and move by a drilling motion of the body through a viscous environment. One approach to propelling microrobots in liquid environments is to mimic the flagella motor, which has been an object of investigation for several decades. In 1952 Taylor, *Taylor (1952)*, explored the swimming behavior of cells and bacteria, *Bell (2007)*. Retaining the idea that the entire body could rotate and generate drive force, a model design was developed for an underwater vehicle that consists of several (rather than one) rotating bodies. The initial conception was that one of the bodies will serve as a cargo space while the bow and the stern would serve for generating drive force. Since, generally, the entire body is used for generating drive force, as in the case of spiral bacteria, while the bow and the stern nevertheless are separately rotating parts that create driving (pushing and pulling) force, similar to E. Coli *flagellas*, then this idea of this model design can be considered to be a combination of both of the aforementioned bacteria. The cargo compartment must be static around its central axial axis (as far as possible, the top remains above and the bottom below), in order to successfully transport the cargo, therefore it is necessary to develop a method that would compensate the torques created by both threads on the middle body.

As for most water vehicles, the body form is similar to water organisms. Since least possible fluid flow resistance force is an important factor, it is necessary to adapt the vehicle form. To reduce drag of large submerged vehicles such as airships and submarines, their form is shaped according to proven physical principles. This can lead to unusual shapes which are impractical for submarines. To obtain a valid streamline shape for the hull, one way is to go back to basics, to find a solution which has developed naturally. Carmichael, *Carmichael (1966)*, tested streamlined torpedo shapes in drop tests in the Pacific Ocean. One shape, the “Dolphin”, had half the drag of a conventional torpedo due to a long run of laminar boundary layer. Therefore, the accepted body form is an ellipse, the “ideal streamline form”, *Joubert (2004)*, with the least pressure drag. Fig.2 shows that the bow is intended as parabolic, nevertheless, our vehicle is intended to be symmetric in order to avoid the necessity of reorienting the front for changing direction. This property would be very useful when moving in pipes where turning around is impossible. Since the body has a thread shape, the friction drag, which is one of the components considered in submarine form analysis, *Joubert (2004)*, will undoubtedly be large, but that is not an obstacle since the thread is the component that does the actual work. Therefore, in terms of choosing the form the most important goal is to obtain optimal streamlining.

Fig.2: Ideal hull form, *Joubert (2004)*

Since the thread bodies we have introduced cannot be considered to be propellers, propeller theory cannot be directly applied to them. The *flagella* of a spermatozoid was taken as a point of reference in creating the thread geometry. The maximum angle of the undulation (angle of attack in propeller terminology) where optimal efficiency is achieved is $\theta_{max} \approx 40.06^\circ$ (Fig.3), *Lauga (2013)*. However,

the bodies in our research are intended to be more similar to screws that drill the water, therefore another point of reference was the geometry of wooden screws. For wooden screws this thread angle in cross-section in relation to central axis (angle of attack) is ~15 degrees. Bearing this in mind, in the model this thread angle is ~22 degrees, with a pitch 106 mm. The thread body is covered by a double thread.

Fig.3: Angle of deformation of flagella.

The middle body serves both as a cargo compartment and implements the direction change function. It is intended to be flexible, allowing to change the driving force vector direction, changing the direction of the vehicle speed vector.

3. The control of helicoidal AUV with bending joints

The control principle of the AUV Durbis-2 is based on bending the Cardan joint in such a way that the rotation axis of the bow (front) screw would be oriented in the target direction. The rotation axis for tilting the bow screw from current position to the required direction is perpendicular to screw rotation axis unit vector b and to vector a from the center of vehicle to the target. The unit vector T of this finite rotation is equal to the cross product of both vectors, divided by the norm of vector a . Fig.4.

Fig.4: Kinematic diagram of Durbis-2. 1, 5 – bow and stern screws, 2 and 4 front and rear drive sections, 3 – Cardan journal cross (spider), φ_y , φ_z – tilt angles around Cardan joint axes, a – vector from the middle point of the Cardan joint to the target point, b – unit vector of bow screw rotation axis.

$$T = \frac{1}{\|a\|} b \times a \quad (1)$$

However, it should be taken into account that the control drive torques q_z and q_y are intrinsic, and the rear part of the vehicle will bend in opposite direction. We assume that the control system is equipped with sensors that give both current angles φ_y and φ_z of the servo-drives, as well as the projections of direction vector a on the axis of the central coordinate system (fixed on the Cardan journal cross). The control servo-drives can implement the required angle or rotation speed. In the case of speed control, a relatively simple control law can be implemented:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\varphi}_y = -k_c \arcsin(T_y) \\ \dot{\varphi}_z = k_c \arcsin(T_z) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where k_c – constant coefficient. The control algorithm can use the vehicle linear velocity vector instead of axis vector \mathbf{b} . The main practical problem is the sensor system, which should include three-axis orientation sensors, because the middle part (middle body) can rotate around the longitudinal axis of vehicle. This fact makes simple manual control of the vehicle with two direction controllers impossible, because, due to rotation, the turn φ_z for the middle body is not always equal to yaw and φ_y is not always equal to pitch rotation.

4. Stabilization

In the case of Durbis-2, the stabilization problem applies specifically to the middle body where it is desirable to maintain the original orientation. Since the body includes the control system, in order to ensure its functioning, it is necessary to maintain the top part on top and the bottom part on the bottom. For the currently developed prototype Durbis-2, this middle body could easily turn upside down. The driving principle as such was not disturbed by this, however, the control system as impacted since all values become inverted, namely, the right side becomes the left side and the top becomes bottom. For the human brain it is difficult to quickly process such changes, therefore it is easy to lose control. To eliminate this drawback of Durbis-2, additional mass was added. In the new Durbis version it is planned to achieve this stabilization by compensating mutually opposed torques created by the thread bodies. A gyro-accelerometer with MEMS technology will help achieve this. This device will provide a direction for the Cardan cross coordinate system. For this purpose, an MPU-6050 gyro-accelerometer will be used, connected to an Arduino UNO microcontroller board. Our MEMS technology will electronically determine the model center coordinate system axis direction described by the angle $\Delta\varphi$, and it will be compensated with a control force created by one of the thread bodies (or both of them together). The idea was borrowed from the inverse pendulum stabilization problem described by the equation:

$$f(t) = k_1x(t) + k_2x'(t) + k_3(\theta(t) - \frac{\pi}{2}) + k_4\theta'(t) \quad (3)$$

Since the model may rotate around the z- and y-axis without losing the top orientation of the middle body, then the compensation is necessary for rotation around the model longitudinal central axis z, or deviation from z-axis, Fig.5.

Fig.5: Schematic description of middle body stabilization (z-y cross-section)

This condition makes our problem 1 dimensional:

$$f(t) = k_1\varphi(t) + k_2\varphi'(t) \quad (4)$$

The desired result is to maintain a single movement speed for the vehicle. Stabilization would be achieved by manipulating the projections of thread rotation speeds $\Delta\omega_i$ for each driving body on the longitudinal axis of cardan joint coordinate system:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\omega_1 = k_1\varphi + k_2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} \\ \Delta\omega_2 = -k_1\varphi - k_2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

To have a clearer view, it is only necessary to provide that the mid body does not turn around the central longitudinal x-axis, Fig.6. It can turn about other axis (y and z), while the vehicle makes movements to right-left, up-down. Thus we need only to attend so the Cardan journal cross y-axis, that at the beginning is at horizontal state and perpendicular to vertical z-axis, is always perpendicular to vertical z'-axis, which is given by sensor. This means that residual between vectors vertical direction of sensor and cross-joint vertical (originally) z-axis vector has to be projected on cross-joint axis, which primary was longitudinal axis.

Fig.6: Schematic description of middle body stabilization

5. Creation of surrogate models of water resistance

Since it is practically impossible to simulate a moving mechanism with 10 degrees of freedom in CFD programs, taking into account full interaction between fluid and mechanism links, in practice the metamodeling (surrogate modeling) technology is broadly applied, *Carroll (2013)*. This requires the creation of simplified models of water resistance, obtained by planned experiments with CFD software. There are several good review papers that describe different aspects of surrogate modeling and advantages to numerous methods and they provided the background for choosing the appropriate method, *Forrester (2009)*, *Queipo (2005)*. The authors of *Carroll (2013)* used the classic Response surface method based on second order polynomial approximations of computer experiments with CFD software ANSYS FLUENT.

We used the software EDAOpt for design, analysis and optimization of computer experiments, created at Riga Technical University, *Auzins (2014)*. The polynomial surrogate models for water resistance forces \mathbf{F}_i and torques \mathbf{T}_i are created in the form

$$\mathbf{F}_i = -\mathbf{A}_i^T \mathbf{V}_i - \|\mathbf{V}_i\| \mathbf{B}_i^T \mathbf{V}_i \quad (6a)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_i = -\mathbf{C}_i^T \boldsymbol{\omega}_i - \|\boldsymbol{\omega}_i\| \mathbf{D}_i^T \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \quad (6b)$$

where \mathbf{F}_i – column-vector of total water resistance force on the i -th body, \mathbf{T}_i – column-vector of total water resistance torque acting about the center of mass of the i -th body, \mathbf{V}_i – column-vector of translation velocity of center of mass of i -th body, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ – column-vector of translation velocity of center of mass of i -th body, \mathbf{A}_i , \mathbf{B}_i , \mathbf{C}_i , \mathbf{D}_i – columns of coefficients, obtained by least-square approximation. All vector projections are calculated in body (moving) coordinate systems. When creating such surrogate models, the flow change from vehicle bending in the Cardan joint is not taken into account.

6. Simulation of rectilinear motion

Commercial CFD software ANSYS FLUENT, COMSOL Multiphysics, STAR-CD, Flow-3D and others provide limited capacity for modelling fluid-mechanism interaction dynamics. In these programs it is possible to insert into a fluid flow rigid bodies with all 6 degrees of freedom or constrain the motion excluding some translation or rotation degrees. The so-called General Moving Object (GMO) components can be of a mixed motion type, namely, have translational and/or rotational velocities that are coupled in some coordinate directions and prescribed in the other directions. A body-fixed reference system (“body system”), defined for each moving object, and the space reference system (“space system”) are employed. Therefore, these rigid bodies can be coupled with the ground using rotational or translational joints. Unfortunately, it is not possible to connect two moving bodies among themselves using rotational joints.

To model rectilinear motion using software Flow-3D we used the following approach. Three main parts: bow (front) screw, middle body and stern (rear) screw are placed in alignment, allowing only rotation around longitudinal axis x . The middle body is standing still. In this model none of the three parts have any contact with each other and there are no contact forces or friction forces between them. An external torque Q around x -axis acts on the bow screw and the opposite torque $-Q$ acts on the stern (right) screw. The mesh domain size in y and z directions was built in accordance with the recommendations given in *Watanabe (2003)* - approximately 1.4 times larger than the diameter of vehicle. We used the specified pressure conditions instead of wall-type boundary conditions. We used the idea that is applied in all wind tunnel experiments: the object may be moving through a stationary fluid, or the fluid may be flowing past a stationary object - these two are effectively identical since, in principle, it is only the frame of reference of the viewer which differs. In our simulations the vehicle is placed in such a way that its center of mass is fixed in the inertial coordinate system and the water flows past a stationary vehicle. CFD software calculates the fluid pressure and velocity in all mesh points as well as the total resistance forces and torques acting on all GMOs. The program also calculates the reaction forces and torques created by motion constraints. In our case there are three components of support reaction force and two components of reaction torque for each part of vehicle. The most important are the reaction force components in longitudinal direction, the other forces and torques are relatively negligible. In order to assume that the modelled movement is equivalent to a vehicle swimming with constant drive torques $q_1 = q_2 = Q$, it is necessary that the sum of reaction forces (called residual control x -force in the program Flow-3D, *Wei (2005)*) in longitudinal direction would be equal to zero, Fig.7:

$$R_{x1} + R_{x2} + R_{x3} = 0 \quad (7)$$

This condition can be satisfied only by experimentally determining the (external) drive torque value Q for each given fluid velocity value V_x , trying out different software input settings.

Fig.7: Top view of Durbis-2 in the finite volume mesh of the software Flow-3D

The Chen-Kim modification of Renormalized group (RNG) $k-\epsilon$ model, *Flow Science (2011)*, *Chen (1987)*, has been used for turbulence modeling with following coefficient values:

$$(\sigma_k, \sigma_\varepsilon, C_{\varepsilon 1}, C_{\varepsilon 2}, C_\mu, \beta) = (0.7194, 0.7194, 1.42, 1.68, 0.0845, 4.38, 0.012) \quad (8)$$

Figs. 8 and 9 show the water streamlines and flow horizontal velocity contours for the fluid common velocity 0.6 m/s. The rear screw works inefficiently and pulls along the water behind it.

Fig.8: Water streamlines around Durbis-2. Velocity 0.6 m/s

Fig.9: Fluid x-velocity contours in the middle section

Fig.10 shows the stabilization of rotational velocity of bow and stern screws and the oscillation of summary longitudinal reaction force for the given flow velocity 0.6 m/s and drive torque 0.146 Nm.

Fig.10: Stabilization of the screw rotation speed (left) and summary support reaction (right)

Fig.11 shows the approximated dependence of the drive torque on the velocity of rectilinear motion. Only four numerical experiments were used for obtaining this second order polynomial approximation. The adjusted R-square criterion value is 0.9997 and the value of the relative leave-one-out cross-validation, *Auzins (2014)*, is 5.3%, confirming the high adequacy of the approximation. The second order polynomial approximation contains a linear term that is insignificant in practice, see Pareto chart (*Auzins (2014)*, *Montgomery (2013)* p. 264), Fig.12.

Fig.11: Approximate dependence of drive torque (left) and screw angular velocity (right) on the linear velocity of AUV

The right graph of Fig. 11 shows the approximated linear dependence between the velocity of rectilinear motion and angular velocities of bow and stern screws. The relative cross-validation error of approximation is about 1%. As can be seen, at equal (opposite) drive torques, the rear screw rotates significantly slower than the bow (front) screw. The fluid pressure and shear force analysis showed that the contribution of the rear screw in the creation of the thrust force is also significantly smaller.

Fig.12: Pareto plot for the torque dependence approximation

The transverse motion velocity during vehicle turns is much smaller than the longitudinal speed. The surrogate water resistance force models were created by simulation of flow acting in the perpendicular direction. The water resistance torques around the transversal axis were calculated under the assumption that they are created by distributed pressure, proportional to squared velocity.

If the resistance force in the transverse direction can be approximated as $F_y = -k_y V_y^2$, then the simplest approximation for resistance torque for rotation around the perpendicular axis through middle point of a prolonged object will give $T_z = -\frac{k_y L^3}{32} \omega_z^2$, where T_z – the resistance torque around z-axis, ω_z – the angular speed of rotation around z-axis, L – the length of the body in longitudinal direction. Of course, this is a highly simplified approximation that does not take into account the interaction of rotation and translation movement, added mass effects, flow changes from the connected adjacent body parts.

7. Full dynamic simulation with MSC Adams

MSC Adams is world’s most famous and widely used 3D Multibody Dynamics (MBD) software tool for dynamical analysis of mechanisms and machines, including mechanisms with rigid and flexible links, drive and control system. The mathematical model in the form of internal systems of differential-algebraic equations is built automatically according to the kinematic diagram which can be imported from any CAD software. Here we used MD Adams 2011, ID C00FD03A-BB49AF41.

The simulated mechanism contains 5 rigid-body links, connected with 4 rotational joints, Fig. 13 and 14.

Fig.13: Durbis-2 in MSC Adams. Outside view. Cardan journal cross not shown

Fig.14: Durbis-2 in MSC Adams. The inner structure

Therefore, the model has 10 degrees of freedom. The water resistance forces and torques are given as external forces, using the created surrogate models and the possibilities of the function builder in MSC Adams. Fig.15 shows the “General force” property for the bow screw, which is in fact the realization of quadratic approximation of flow simulation results (6a, 6b).

Fig.15: Water resistance surrogate model

The thrust and bending electro-drive dynamics were not simulated in detail. It was assumed that the thrust drives generate the necessary torque and orientation drives generate the necessary rotation speed. The angular velocity of bow and rear screws was varied in the range from zero to 20 RPM. When modelling rectilinear motion, at ± 10 RPM the linear velocity of vehicle was obtained as about 0.6 m/s. Fig.16 shows the vehicle following a target, using an automatic control law (2). The spherical target moves in three dimensions according to sinusoidal law $x(t) = 0.7\sin(0.5t)$, $y(t) = 0.7\cos(0.5t)$, $z(t) = 0.46\sin(1.5t)$. The optimal value of the coefficient of control law (2) $k_c = 110$ was found using computer experiments.

Fig.16: Following a moving target

8. Prototype of DURBIS-2 and validation

The physical prototype of the AUV DURBIS-2 was built in the master thesis of Marcis Eimanis, *Eimanis (2014)*, using CAD software SolidWorks and the Mass Portal 3D Printer Pharaoh Delta. The bow and stern screws were printed using PLA plastic. The screws are rotated with an LN22 Series electro drive individually connected to each screw (2 drives in total), using 7.4V Lipo battery, the reducer generates ~ 600 RPM and torque of about 0.06 Nm (controlled by *pulse-duration modulation*). Direction is controlled by 2 servo motors: Blue Bird High speed BSM-706, low profile (torque at 4.8V – 0.46 Nm; speed at 4.8V – 8 rad/s at no load). Low profile servomotors were deliberately selected to obtain additional free space for other components. The middle bending body consists of a Cardan-type cross construction, the material is 4mm thick EN-AW-5754 aluminum with an elastic silicone cover.

The middle body is water-proof and may be used as a “cargo compartment”. The drive body is located on the central shaft that turns the spindle connected with the screw, causing it to rotate. The central shaft is fixed in a stationary position at the ends of the middle body. Model dimensions: total length 590mm, maximum diameter together with the screw 87.25mm, maximum diameter of hull 84mm, length of screw 190 mm, pitch of helix 106 mm. The range for the Cardan bending angles is $\pm 30^\circ$. The prototype is not equipped with orientation sensors; therefore, it is controlled using a 40 MHz, 4.5-7.5V receiver placed in the vehicle body and a three-component control transmitter console. Due to the absence of middle body vertical orientation control and a sensor system for the prototype, an additional mass was placed in the lower part of the middle body to avoid its rotation around the longitudinal axis. This allows good remote control of the prototype. The remote control is possible at a distance of about 20 m and at about 2 m depth of submergence.

Fig.17: The prototype Durbis-2

The prototype Durbis-2 demonstrated very good maneuverability. The only measured parameters were linear velocity (about 0.6 m/s) and angular velocity of screws (about 600-700 RPM). This gives good agreement with simulation results from CFD and multibody dynamic simulation software. The real velocity and maneuverability of Durbis-2 is so high that the vehicle can move vertically and almost jump out of the water like a fish, Fig.18.

Fig.18: Durbis-2 „jumping” out of water

9. Conclusions

- Nature contains many organisms that provide new ideas for solving existing and future problems, particularly in regards to the microscopic world. Adapting microorganisms to technology allows solving problems from a new point of view and in greater detail.
- The numerical and physical simulation results have proved the functionality, maneuverability and energy efficiency of the proposed propulsion principle and control system. It must be noted that this principle can be used not only for underwater vehicles, but also for devices that move in granular, loose ground, as well as in pipes filled with fluid, including blood vessels. The experiment's measurements are compared with the results predicted using the computational model. The comparison shows that the model can predict with reasonably good accuracy the dynamic performance of the AUV with double helicoid hull shape.
- Further research should include more accurate analysis of the turbulence and cavitation effects.
- The stabilization problem is currently solvable by manipulating torques and thread body rotation speeds, each compensating the other, and retaining a stable movement speed as a result. This system employs MEMS technology together with Arduino programming capabilities, serving as the “brain” of the vehicle.

- Shape optimization of the hull and both screws would also be necessary. With the current design where the vehicle has almost completely symmetrical bow and stern parts, the stern screw has a mostly supportive function and the main thrust force is created by the bow screw. If the symmetry principle is abandoned, it would be possible to create a more energy-efficient shape for the double-helical vehicle.

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Concept of Local Hull-Shape Adaptation by Means of Inflatable Flow-Resistors

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Abstract

This paper presents the concept of local hull-shape adaptation by means of inflatable flow-resistors. A methodical approach was used to derive the concept of an ideal flow resistor. Finite element models were created to calculate the deformed shape of a prototypical design. Based on this design a demonstrator was realized and tested. The numerical model then was validated using laser-scanning data of the deformed shape.

1. Introduction

Today's sea logistics suffers from a tremendous cost pressure and ship operators have to face a continuous optimization process. One possibility to succeed in this competition is to introduce more flexible operation profiles for ships concerning load, speed, route etc. This implies that the ships have to be more versatile and cost efficient in operation. One crucial cost driver is fuel consumption which is mainly depending on the power installed, the total resistance and the velocity.

The design of a vessel depends on owner's requirements, shipyard's possibilities, classification rules etc. Normally the layout is optimized for one particular operational scenario (calm deep water, one fixed speed, specific environmental conditions etc.). This scenario is called trial design and is the basis for the contract. The speed possible with this trial design is called the trial design speed. This scenario is relevant only for the contract but does not fit the real operational conditions necessarily. In reality a lot more and different conditions can occur. As result ships are often operated under suboptimal circumstances. An efficiency gain is therefore necessary and can be obtained by making the ships smarter. Beside logistic and powertrain optimization reduction of wave and drag resistance seem to be the most promising approaches.

Whereas the reduction of drag-resistance deals mostly with the properties and the degree of fouling of the hull-surface the reduction of the wave-resistance can be obtained by changing the hull-geometry either locally or globally. Since the affection of surface properties is the topic of a different research project (FLIPPER - Flow improvement through compliant hull coating for better ship performance (03SX374A)) this paper will focus on adaptation capabilities at the hull to reduce the wave-resistance.

2. Design approach

Due to a lot of dependencies, requirements and constraints the design of structures being able to introduce adaptation capabilities (adaptive structures) at the hull will be rather complex. It is therefore recommended to use a methodic approach which will increase the probability of an appropriate design and decrease the probability of design mistakes. Possible solutions will be found. For this project a methodical design process according to *Pahl and Beitz (1993)* was utilized. They identified 4 main phases during the design process:

- Clarification of the task
- Conceptual design
- Embodiment design
- Detail design

Within any of these phases different main work steps have to be carried out. The results of each work step are then the basis for the following work step. Fig.1 shows a model of the methodical design process schematically. According to this model the design process is of dynamic nature which means that solutions may be dropped due to a gain of knowledge.

Fig.1.: Methodical design process *Pahl and Beitz (1993)*

2.1. Clarification of the task

Any ship travelling at a speed v will be passed by a flow at the same speed. The flow has the specific kinetic energy

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 \quad (1)$$

The flow will then be affected locally by the ship's shape which results in a local change of pressure and flow speed.

Along a flow channel the physical effect which describes the dependence between kinetic and potential energy is represented by Bernoulli's equation. Drag due to viscous effects is not considered yet.

$$\frac{p_1}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2}v_1^2 + gh_1 = \frac{p_2}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2}v_2^2 + gh_2 = \frac{p_3}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2}v_3^2 + gh_3 = \text{const.} \quad (2)$$

Here p_i denotes the pressure, v_i the flow velocity, h_i the geodetic height, ρ the fluid density and g the gravitation acceleration at the cross section i of the flow channel.

At the waterline the pressure must equal the ambient pressure p_∞ . So Eq.(2) can be rewritten for cross section i as

$$\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 - p_\infty = \frac{1}{2}\rho v_i^2 + \rho gh_i \quad (3)$$

If the velocity varies the energy at cross section i can only be kept constant if the height at this location changes. This will result in a primary wave field. The shape of this primary wave field depends on the hull geometry and the travelling speed.

The primary wave field can be affected by changing the local flow velocity. By considering a constant mass flow the local flow velocity at location i can be derived from the continuity equation

$$\frac{d}{dt}m = \dot{m} = \rho A_i v_i \Leftrightarrow v_i = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho A_i} \quad (4)$$

Additional displacement will accelerate the flow and decrease the wave height and reduced displacement will decelerate the flow and increase the wave height. Additional displacement is synonym for decreasing the cross section of a flow channel and reduced displacement is synonym for increasing the cross section.

Since the primary wave system can be considered as a travelling pressure point it is the source of a secondary wave field. This secondary wave field has to be kept alive by the ship and since the wave energy is proportional to square of the wave height this amount of energy has to be provided by the ship's powertrain, *Bertram (2000), Krueger (2009)*.

For different operating conditions the task is therefore to introduce a displacement adaptation which enables to tune the ship's primary wave field in order to reduce the wave resistance.

One essential work step during the clarification phase is the elaboration of specifications. The specifications can be classified by main characteristic features. These main characteristic features that are in general relevant for the design of any technical device shows Table I. The collection of given examples is not exhaustive and not every topic might be applicable but this is a valuable guideline.

Table I: Systematical collection of requirements and examples

	Main characteristic feature	Examples
1	Geometry	Size, height, width, length, diameter, space requirement, arrangement, completion and extension, ...
2	Kinematics	Kinematical quantities, kind of motion, moving direction, rate of motion, speed, acceleration, ...
3	Forces	Quantity of force, direction of force, frequency of force, weight, load, deformation, stiffness, spring properties, stability, resonance, ...
4	Energy	Power, efficiency, loss, friction, storage, pressure, temperature, resilience, transformation of energy, ...
5	Material	Physical, mechanical and chemical properties, prescribed materials and process materials, ...

6	Signal	Input and output signal, kind of signal, ...
7	Safety	Safety engineering, protection systems, operating safety, protection of labour, environmental protection, ...
8	Ergonomics	Man-machine-relationship: operation, control, operating facility, clearness, illumination, design, ...
9	Production	Restrictions due to: manufacturing place, preferred manufacturing method, dimension limits, manufacturing facilities, possible quality and tolerance, ...
10	Verification	Measuring and testing methods, special regulations, numerical modelling, calculation and verification, ...
11	Assembly	Special regulations for assembly, assembly, handling, ...
12	Transport	Restrictions due to necessary transport (size, weight, etc.), kind and conditions of forwarding, ...
13	Lifetime	With little noise, rate of wear, use, range of application, place of application, operating temperature, other operating environmental conditions (i.e. humidity), ...
14	Maintenance	Maintenance-free or easy to maintain, maintenance accessory, maintenance rate and cost, replacement, corrective maintenance, coat of paint, cleaning, ...
15	Recycling	Reutilization, repeated application, waste disposal, final waste disposal, elimination, ...
16	Costs	Admissible production costs, tooling costs, investment, amortisation, ...
17	Deliverables	Time schedules, dead line date of development, intermediate steps, time of delivery, ...

2.2. Functional structure

As outlined above the task is to introduce a displacement adaptation at the ship's hull to influence the local wave height. On an abstract level the overall function can be denoted as "change cross section of flow channel".

To comply with this function will necessitate the introduction of a flow resistor. The physical effect that describes the flow resistance is governed by

$$F_r = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 c_d A_p \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 = \frac{F_r}{c_d A_p} \quad 2.2. -1$$

In this equation c_d denotes the drag coefficient and depends on the resistor's shape, F_r represents the reaction force and A_p is the projected area normal to the flow. In this context we can find the set of sub functions which is necessary to comply with the above mentioned function. They can be denoted as "actuate resistor", "support reaction forces" and "control the shape". The first function will need an auxiliary function "actuate the adjustment".

Fig.2: Functional interrelationship for a flow resistor

The outlined functional interrelationship, Fig.2, is valid for any adaptive structure no matter where it is located or whether it has local or global impact on the flow velocity.

2.3. Embodiment design

By having derived the functional interrelationship we are now able to create principle solutions for each particular sub function. In the following principle solutions shall be derived and evaluated according to the requirements derived before. To start with the derivation of principle solutions a classification shall be given. According to the function analysis a classification of the resistors can be given by the type of shape, Fig.3, by the type of actuation, Fig.4, or by the type of their support, Fig.5.

Fig.3: Classification of flow resistors by shape

Fig.4: Classification of flow resistors by actuation

Fig.5: Classification of flow resistors by structural support

3. Ideal flow resistor

Any kind of technical solution for adaptation capabilities will consist of materials or combinations of materials and has to match a lot of requirements which often necessitate a compromise between conformance to requirements and technical feasibility. According to the above classification a lot of principle solutions are possible which have typical advantages and disadvantages. The question now is how an ideal flow resistor can look like?

This resistor:

- would have a flexible surface to create single curved as well as doubly curved surfaces preventing excessive turbulences
- could be placed parallel to the hull and would not need much assembly space
- would have a smooth transition zone to the hull to prevent excessive turbulences
- could withstand any environmental harm
- could withstand operational loads
- would carry reaction forces as surface loads to avoid load concentrations
- could be verified by numerical and experimental investigations
- could be easily operated without extensive maintenance
- would not affect the ship structure

Fig.6: Ideal flow resistor

Fig.7: Ideal flow resistors (operational mode)

Fig.6 shows a possible set-up. The resistor consists of an opened front plate, a flexible reinforced membrane which is fixed by compensator springs to a massive frame, flexible inflatable actuators and a back plate which supports the actuators. Fig.7 shows the mode of operation. The actuators are

inflated by a hydraulic fluid (for environmental reasons this should be water) and act on the backside of a flexible reinforced membrane. The membrane is extruded through the window of the front plate and will form the outer shape of the resistor. The resulting shape is depending on the number and shape of actuators and the degree of anisotropy of the reinforced membrane.

4. Demonstration model

According to the above considerations a demonstration model was designed and built. It consists of a frame from aluminum profiles, a base plate, and a front plate with a quadratic hole, Fig.8. The base plate has dimensions of 700 by 700 mm. The front plate has dimensions of 780 by 780 mm and the cut has the dimensions 480 by 480 mm. A stack of inflatable actuators is assembled on the base plate.

Fig.8: Overview of the demonstration model

Fig.9: Rubber membrane forming the outer surface

Two deformable membranes of dimension 600 by 600 mm had been manufactured from rubber sheets, Fig.9. These sheets were laminated together in an autoclave using a contact adhesive. Along one direction stainless steel ropes of one mm diameter at a distance of 70 mm were placed between

the rubber sheets. To prevent the ropes from splitting the sheets rubber patches had been bonded on both sides of each rope. The end of the ropes were formed to grommets and connected to stainless steel springs with a spring rate of 0.55 N/mm. The steel ropes were then pre-stressed and fixed to the frame.

Fig.10: Stack of inflatable actuators

The actuators consist of an unreinforced rubber liner which is inflated by pressed air. To prevent the liner from excessive distortion it is covered by a fabric hose. The inflated diameter was 61 mm and the length approx. 320 mm. Sets of one, two and three actuators had been bundled and stacked. Bundling prevents cleavage between the inflated actuators. The stack of uninflated actuators is operated by compressed air. Fig.10 shows the uninflated (left) and inflated stack (right).

Fig.11: Stages of deformation of the rubber membrane

Due to the inflated actuators the membranes are stretched and a particular deformed shape is introduced, Fig.11. In this case the reinforcement of the membranes is crosswise at an angle of 90 degrees. It is also possible to introduce additional membranes under different angles to achieve a higher degree of anisotropy. Together with different stacks of actuators of different shape this design concept offers a wide variety of deformed configurations to satisfy the shape requirements from hydrodynamic calculations. By inflating different combinations of stacks different deformation figures can be realized, Fig.12. The operation of the actuators can be easily achieved by a simple pneumatic or hydraulic circuit.

Fig.12: Different combinations of inflated actuators

5. Verification

To calibrate the numerical model experiments with the demonstrator had been carried out. For simplicity only one membrane and actuator was assembled. For the first experiment the actuator was placed in the middle of the base plate. The axes of the reinforcement and the actuator were under an angle of 90° . The deformed geometry was scanned using a laser scanning system. The data then was used to create files in a stereo lithography format (STL-files) of the deformed geometry.

A robust FE-model, Fig.13, of the demonstration model was developed and different load cases were calculated. These calculations include several nonlinearities like multiple areas of mechanical contact and nonlinear elastic material behavior. Since the displacements and deformations can be considerably large a nonlinear geometrical theory has to be used.

Fig.13: Finite element model for the symmetric load case

The front and the base plate were represented by a rigid body. The membrane consisted of 4-node shell elements with reduced integration order. The reinforcement was realized by the introduction of truss elements which share the same nodes at the specific spatial coordinates. Instead of using fixed boundary conditions the membrane section was linked to the ground by spring elements with appropriate spring rates.

The actuators consisted also of 4-node shell elements with reduced integration order. Both ends were represented by membrane elements of very small thickness. Instead of modelling the inner rubber liner and the outside fabric the inflated diameter was calibrated by a mixture of material stiffness and shell thickness. The inner volume of the actuator was modelled due to special fluid elements which can represent the behavior of hydraulic as well as gas fluid. The load was applied due to a pressure vs. time curve. To prevent numerical difficulties during the contact iteration the actuator model was linked to the ground by spring elements with a very small spring rate. Since only displacements were of interest the mesh size could be rather coarse. This helped to reduce calculation time. The model consisted of about 110.000 variables and took approximately 20 minutes of calculation time on a double core PC.

The displacement amplitudes of the symmetric load-case are shown in Fig.14. At an internal pressure of 8 bars the maximum displacement is in the range of 25 mm. The displacement data then were exported in a VRML format that could also be introduced into the CAD model.

Fig.14: Displacement amplitude for the symmetric load case

Fig.15: Merged experimental and numerical deformation data

Fig.15 shows the numerical and experimental results merged into the CAD-model. The calculated results seem to be reasonable. The differences between numerical and experimental results are of order 15 % which represents a good agreement. A better accordance of numerical and experimental results should be expected by replacing the rigid bodies in the FE-model by elastic structures.

6. Conclusion and outlook

A concept of local hull adaptation had been derived from theoretical considerations. This concept has been realized in a demonstrator. It has been shown with this demonstrator that a combination of flexible membranes from reinforced elastomers together with a set of inflatable actuators can produce a great variety of deformed shape for local hull adaptation.

A robust FE-model of the demonstrator had been developed and two different load cases had been calculated. The deformed shape from these load cases then had been measured experimentally. A comparison between the experimental and numerical results showed a good accordance.

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Operational Performance of Wind Assisted Ships

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Abstract

The „Wind Hybrid Coaster“ was a sub project in MARITIM (2016) under the European INTERREG Deutschland-Nederland programme within which Dutch and German partners from the maritime industry and research institutions were developing a new type of “green” coastal ship equipped with a wind assisted hybrid propulsion system. MARIN was asked to predict the performance of the Wind Hybrid Coaster in a realistic operational scenario. For this purpose MARIN conducted a large number of hydrodynamic model tests, powering predictions in calm water including wind assistance and finally voyage simulations for multiple routes including voyage optimisation.

1. Introduction

The main objective of the project was to develop a prototype Flettner rotor to be used on coastal vessels. MARIN was asked to work on a secondary objective: to predict the overall performance of a ship using the Flettner rotors as developed in the project. In addition to directly determining the performance, time was taken to do some variations on the main scope in order to find out what is the appropriate scope to determine the performance of a wind assisted ship. MARIN took up the following tasks within the project:

- Preliminary potential flow and CFD calculations to check the hull form
- Captive model tests to build a numerical model of hull forces and a performance prediction for the vessel in calm water
- Voyage simulations to predict the operational performance of the vessel on a number of routes

The emphasis in this publication is on the voyage simulations.

After concluding the project, the core of the Wind Hybrid Coaster group (without MARIN) has continued under the name “ECO-FLETTNER” and is due to install its first rotor on general cargo vessel Fehn Pollux.

2. Ship design and Flettner rotor specifications

Table I shows the main particulars of the Wind Hybrid Coaster, as considered in the project. Fig.1 shows an artist impression.

Fig.1: Artist's impression of Wind Hybrid Coaster (rendering courtesy of CIG Maritime Technology)

It is a design that has not yet been built. The overall design is done by CIG Maritime Technology (<http://www.centralindustrygroup.com/companies/cig-maritime-technology>) and is based on other designs by them. The superstructure is positioned forward, which ensures free visibility and also allows integration of the rotors. This vessel was considered a suitable base for wind assisted propulsion that could be equipped with Flettner rotors. The vessel has a relatively low design speed. This is favourable because the wind does not tend to come from the bow as often as on faster vessels. The operational speed considered in the study is even on the lower spectrum of typical operational speed for such a vessel. A relatively low GM was chosen.

Table I: Ship main particulars

L_{PP}	85.0	[m]
B_{WL}	14.0	[m]
T	4.7	[m]
Deadweight	3930	[t]
GM	0.7	[m]
V_s (operational)	8.5	[kn]

The propulsion installation is simple with a single direct propulsion line and rudder. The controllable pitch propeller is driven by the 1520kW main diesel engine. A shaft generator is available.

For wind assistance, two Flettner rotors are planned directly aft of the wheelhouse. Table II shows the main particulars for both rotors. The rotors are driven by electric motors. The power is delivered by the shaft generator when in transit at sea. Fig.2 shows the rotors in more detail.

Table II: Flettner rotor particulars

L	18.0	[m]
D	3.0	[m]
n_{MAX}	280	[RPM]

Fig.2: Flettner rotors (rendering courtesy of CIG Maritime Technology)

When reference is made to savings of the “wind assisted” Wind Hybrid Coaster, these statements are made for a comparison against a “conventional” reference which is simply the same vessel without Flettner rotors. This is considered realistic as, other than the rotors themselves, the vessel still resembles a typical coaster. However it should be noted that the weight and consequential increase in displacement has not been accounted for. The impact on resistance is however expected to be small.

The working principle and lift and drag of a Flettner rotor is shown in Fig.3. Due to rotation in an incoming flow, a rotor generates lift and drag force.

Fig.3: Schematic Flettner rotor lift (L) and drag (D), rotation direction and flow (wikipedia)

Lift and drag for a Flettner rotor rise with the relative rotation rate, λ , which is described as:

$$\lambda = \frac{D \cdot n}{V_W}$$

D is the rotor diameter, n is the rotor rotation rate in rad/s and V_W is the apparent undisturbed wind velocity in m/s

The lift-drag characteristics used for the MARIN work was a project-specific data set. However, it was very similar to data published by *Ackeret (1925)*, except that the data included a wider range of relative rotation rate, leading to a larger obtainable lift and drag. For voyage simulations, the relative rotation rate was limited to a maximum of 4.0. The gain in extra propulsion is very small compared to the extra power that is required when exceeding this value. This led to a maximum thrust coefficient of 11.5 at an apparent wind angle of 120° and a maximum side force coefficient of 9.9 at an apparent wind angle of 60° . The thrust and side force coefficients are defined as:

$$C_X = \frac{F_X}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V_W^2}$$

$$C_Y = \frac{F_Y}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V_W^2}$$

F_X is thrust force, directed forward in a ship fixed reference frame, F_Y is side force directed to port side in a ship fixed reference frame, ρ is air density and A is the projected area of the rotor.

The power consumption of the Flettner rotor was based on an empirical formula, which yielded a maximum power of 60 kW per rotor when rotating at maximum velocity. Finally, as the rotors are positioned side by side, losses can be expected for the leeward rotor when operating in beam wind. These were modelled with a 50% reduction of lift of the leeward rotor. Results from a later aerodynamic study, including wind tunnel tests and CFD led by Hochschule Emden-Leer, suggest that the adopted reduction of lift of the leeward rotor and the power consumption of the rotors as adopted in the present study are conservative. It is expected that aerodynamic data obtained within the project will be published by Hochschule Emden-Leer.

3. Hull form verification and model tests

The initial hull form was analysed using MARIN's in-house codes DESP for empirical resistance prediction, RAPID for inviscid wave making drag and ReFRESCO for inviscid flow. The main

change to the initial hull form were the bow area and the shape of the buttocks in the transom area. It was expected that an operational profile for a wind assisted vessel will see larger ship speed fluctuations, which means that the speed range for optimum performance also needed to be wider. That was the main motivation for changing the hull form. No changes were made to improve the lift production of the hull.

After this preliminary analysis, a model was built to a scale ratio of 1:16.7. This model was subjected to a large test programme in MARIN's Deep Water Basin, involving a variation of ship speed, the percentage of propeller thrust (relative to self-propulsion), drift angle and rudder angle. The test set-up can be seen in Fig.4. The model was fitted on a turntable to realise the drift angle. A 6-component force measurement frame was positioned between the carriage and model to measure the overall forces. Except for one series of bare hull tests, the model was fully equipped with appendages: rudder, propeller, bilge keels and bow thruster tunnel with dummy propeller. The model tests resulted in a complete description of the overall performance of the hull at various speeds, drift angles and propeller thrust levels.

Fig.4: Model test

4. Performance prediction for calm water

MARIN's in-house manoeuvring code SURSIM is normally used to predict e.g. zig-zag and turning circle manoeuvres. As such the code contains descriptions of hull forces as occur for a vessel sailing with non-zero drift and rudder angle, although these descriptions are normally geared primarily for larger drift, rudder angles and non-zero yaw rates. For the present project relevant coefficients in the equations of motion of SURSIM were adjusted to arrive at a good correspondence with the model tests over the full range of drift angles, speed and thrust levels as included in the tests. Fig.5 illustrates the correspondence of ship-fixed overall forces at ship speed V_S of 8 kn and leeway β of -3° . It appears that correspondence is in general good, particularly for sway force and yawing moment. However, the total surge force appears not to match as accurately as the other forces. This is because it is a subtraction of resistance by propeller thrust. The resulting number is small. Therefore the absolute difference is also small. The centre of effort of the side force for the hull and rudder at centre line is positioned just in front of the bow. Fig.5 shows that with rudder angles of about 13 to 20° (depending on thrust level) the yawing moment can be reduced to about 0, which corresponds to a centre of effort at midship.

The SURSIM numerical model was used to derive a performance prediction for the vessel in calm water. Fig.6 shows the required thrust to maintain a ship speed of 8 kn. It is seen that with low values of TWA (True Wind Angle; wind coming from the bow) the required thrust is actually increased due to the parasitic drag of the rotors. However for a TWA larger than about 30°, there is a clear benefit of the propulsion with Flettner rotors. With a beam to stern wind of 30 kn, the vessel can sail completely on wind propulsion. As the yawing moment is also part of these calculations, it was ensured that the vessel can keep course, at least in calm water.

Fig.5: Comparison of model test results and SURSIM at $V_s = 8$ kn; $\beta = -3$ deg (drift velocity to SB)

Fig.6: Required propeller thrust to maintain $V_s = 8$ kn as function of True Wind Angle (TWA) and True Wind Speed (TWS; see legend)

Fig.7 shows the induced drag versus lift for both the hull and rudder for each data point in the performance prediction. Lift and drag of the rudder was determined relative to the undisturbed inflow. These results show that for modest levels of lift (at low wind speeds or favourable angles) the rudder is more efficient at generating lift than the hull. However, the chart for a wind velocity of 30 kn shows that there is a clear upper threshold of lift. The rudder induced drag suddenly increases for lift values beyond about 75 kN. This is where stalling starts to occur. This observation means that it is in principle favourable to have the centre of effort of the side force generated by the wind propulsors far aft at low wind speeds. However, at larger wind velocities, it is favourable or even required to have the centre of effort further forward, so that the hull carries the majority of the side force and there is sufficient margin in rudder forces to steer the vessel. For vessels with a larger contribution of wind propulsion, it will be more important to generate the majority of the side force with the hull.

As a final analysis step, the total additional drag of the hull and rudder was expressed as ratio of dynamic pressure times Flettner rotor projected area as follows:

$$C_R = \frac{F_{X \text{ WITH FLETTNER}} - F_{X \text{ WITHOUT FLETTNER}}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot V_W^2 \cdot A \cdot \text{number of rotors}}$$

Fig.7: Induced drag versus lift for hull and rudder at a ship speed of 8 kn; 10 and 20 kn wind velocity in the left chart and 30kn wind velocity in the right chart

This can be compared directly to C_x , the thrust coefficient of the Flettner rotors. Fig.8 shows that this coefficient peaks at a value of about -1.5. In that same condition, the aerodynamic C_x of the Flettner rotors is close to 10.0. Thus, the increased resistance of the hull in this case causes about 15% of the aerodynamic thrust to be lost.

Fig.8: Hull and rudder additional drag due to Flettner lift

5. Seakeeping calculations

Seakeeping is an integral part of operational performance. Thus, motions, relative wave height, and accelerations were calculated for the vessel using MARIN's in-house strip theory code SHIPMO. Added resistance in waves was calculated according to the SPA method as described in *R. Grin (2015)*. The results were taken into account in the voyage simulations. Exceedance of typical operability criteria, e.g. green at the bow, were registered. However, seakeeping is not discussed further due to the restricted length of this publication and the fact that the percentage of time that the criteria were exceeded was not very large.

6. Voyage simulations

The voyage simulations, conducted with the in-house developed tool GULLIVER, *Dallinga et al. (2004)*, can be seen as the culmination of work done by MARIN for the Wind Hybrid Coaster project as all results obtained in the previous tasks are brought together. The voyage simulations result in the most complete prediction of the operational performance of the vessel. Based on an analysis by ship operators in the Wind Hybrid Coaster group the scenario for simulations was set. It was decided to focus on an almost full load condition and a ship speed of 8.5kn. The Wind Hybrid Coaster can sail considerably faster. However, it was found that sailing at full speed only occurs for a small fraction of time for similar vessels. Table III and Fig.9 show the routes that were considered. The routes along the Western European coastline and through the Mediterranean were considered representative for the type of vessel. The route crossing the Atlantic, from Gibraltar to Trinidad, was added as it was considered interesting from a research perspective. Trade winds could lead to favourable performance on the westbound voyage. It was however realised that such a route is not very realistic for the size of vessel. Return routes were modelled also, albeit with less detail as described later.

Table III: Routes

Departure port	Arrival port	Distance	Sailing time at V_S 8.5 kn
Gibraltar	Izmir	1576 nm	184 h
Gibraltar	Skagen	1760 nm	217 h
Gibraltar	Trinidad	3328 nm	408 h

Fig.9: Routes

The GKSS Research Center Geesthacht GmbH database was used for all routes for wind and wave data for one year with a half degree grid and 1 h time step for all routes. Tidal current was included for the Gibraltar-Skagen route. The tidal currents were obtained from the TOPEX/Poseidon inverse tidal model of Oregon State University, USA. Ocean current was included for the route Gibraltar-Trinidad. These ocean currents were taken from OSCAR, which provides worldwide ocean surface currents with a 1° resolution and a 5-day interval. This database is based on satellite altimeter and scatterometer data. No current was modelled on the route Gibraltar-Izmir under the assumption that the passage through the strait of Gibraltar does not significantly affect the overall results. The Mediterranean Sea itself is known to have very little current.

The simulations were conducted for the full year of 1999. A ship departure was modelled every three days, such that the route was always covered with several ships in parallel. A simulation time step of 3 h was used. A trip duration threshold was defined for each trip, corresponding to a minimum speed of 8.5 kn on the shortest distance. Voyages were required to arrive within the threshold or earlier.

Pre- and post-processing of GULLIVER allows speed and route optimisation. This was assumed to be important as a wind assisted ship may need to anticipate actual weather conditions to make best use of the wind. A grid was designed for each route. This grid consists of waypoints (the intersections where routes cross) and legs (the sections of the routes between the nodes). For each departure date, all individual segments were simulated at all different times that a ship could theoretically pass there. Additionally, this was done for three speeds per leg. After all these individual simulations were conducted, these were used to compose all possible combinations to do the trip, with the following constraints:

- The ship arrives on time (or earlier) at the end destination
- The passage through a waypoint should be possible: i.e. the ship should not leave earlier on the next leg than the arrival from the previous leg.

From this entire set of simulations the best realisation was selected for each departure date.

This is a brute force approach to voyage optimisation. However, more efficient methods, such as the isochrone method, have restrictions on the cost functions that can be minimised. The presently used method is flexible in this regard. Furthermore, this simulation method effectively assumes that the captain already knows before leaving what the actual weather on the route will be. Of course in reality this will not be the case and consequently performance may be worse, especially on long routes. The calculations and optimisation were conducted on MARIN’s CONDOR High Throughput Cluster as the number of combinations was rather large as shown in Table IV.

Table IV: Number of routes and speed possibilities per trip departure

Route	Number of possibilities in millions
Gibraltar - Izmir	9
Gibraltar - Skagen	3362
Gibraltar - Trinidad	26741

7. Results and discussion

Fig.10 shows the apparent wind as seen in the total simulations result. The graphs are polar histograms with percentage on the polar axis. The figure shows that the wind velocity on the Gibraltar-Izmir route was rather modest and mostly from the bow. This is the case because of the ship velocity and little wind overall. There is in general more wind on the Gibraltar-Skagen route. There, wind is also mostly from the bow. However, a relatively large percentage also comes in from the port side beam. Finally, on the Gibraltar-Trinidad route wind often comes in over the port side quarter as expected. However, the wind speed over deck is very modest.

Fig.10: Wind conditions (180° is head wind – 0° is stern wind)

The simulation results as shown here were conducted in one year of environmental data. One could argue that statistically this is not much to obtain a statistically certain answer. Some individual simulations were repeated for a longer duration. The wind speed and compass angle were compared

for each route for a duration of 1 and 5 years. It is shown that in this case, there is very little difference between 1 and 5 years of data. For the present case, the results are considered that contain only little statistical uncertainty.

Table V: Wind speed in knots for 1 and 5 years of data (average and 10% exceedance threshold)

	Gibraltar-Skagen		Gibraltar-Skagen	
	Mean	10% exceedance	Mean	10% exceedance
1 year (as simulated)	12.3	21.4	11.8	17.7
5 years	12.0	21.0	12.1	18.0

Table VI: Wind direction in deg for 1 and 5 years of data (average and RMS)

	Gibraltar-Skagen		Gibraltar-Skagen	
	Mean	RMS*	Mean	RMS*
1 year (as simulated)	291	44	67	48
5 years	295	45	67	49

*Root Mean Square

Fig.11 shows the Flettner rotor rotation rate on the most demanding route. The bottom right figure shows the distribution, where it can be read that there is approximately an 11% chance to exceed 280 RPM, which is in fact the maximum rotor rotation route. This limit was not enforced in simulations, and will result in a slightly overestimated thrust and power consumption on the route Gibraltar-Skagen. On the route Gibraltar-Izmir this chance is about 0.7% and it is 1.0% on the route Gibraltar-Trinidad. Hence, the impact there on overall results is judged to be very small.

Fig.11: Flettner rotor rotation rate on the route Gibraltar-Skagen

Fig.12: Histograms of required Flettner power

The Flettner rotors also require power to rotate. As the Flettner rotor rotation rate is a function of the apparent wind speed, the power is also dependent on the actual weather conditions. Fig.12 shows that, whereas the Flettner thrust was similar on the routes Gibraltar-Skagen and Gibraltar-Trinidad, the

required power is much higher on the route Gibraltar-Skagen. This can be explained by a higher apparent wind speed over deck. The rotor rotation then also needs to be higher to achieve the same relative rotation rate and thrust coefficient. On the route Gibraltar-Izmir the power is not negligible at all, although the contribution in thrust is small.

Fig.13 shows the histogram of thrust generated by the Flettner rotors for the three routes. It appears that the mean wind induced force is very similar on the routes Gibraltar-Skagen and Gibraltar-Trinidad. Apparently, the more favourable wind direction on Gibraltar-Trinidad and the higher average wind velocity on the route Gibraltar-Skagen yield a very similar result. The thrust has a much wider fluctuation on the route Gibraltar-Skagen. Gibraltar-Izmir shows much lower forces overall, which can be explained by the lower wind speed and less favourable angle.

Fig.13: Histogram of wind thrust

The (quasi-)steady heel angle reaches 8° when sailing in 30 kn beam wind winds. Such a condition, or worse, occurs rarely, such that the heel angle is hardly a problem for this vessel. However, combined with roll motions due to waves, it could become a problem. The steady heel could be reduced by ballasting. The considered loading condition, with a GM of 0.7 m, is very demanding. Most of the time a ship like this will sail with more stability.

Fig.14 shows the engine power versus rotation rate with a schematic (indicative) envelope for normal engine loads. The right figure shows this for the vessel without wind propulsion. Already there it is shown that loads drop very low very regularly. This is the case because the operational speed is low in comparison with the maximum speed. This is aggravated for the vessel with Flettner rotors. The spreading of the loads also clearly becomes bigger. The blue straight lines represent isolines for specific fuel consumption according to a simplified model that relates specific fuel consumption only to torque. The low loads end up also at areas that are far from the optimum, leading to a large specific fuel consumption. In reality, with a more detailed modelling, this result is likely worse.

A consequence of wind assistance is that propeller loading will be affected, which in turn influences propulsion efficiency. Fig.15 shows the propulsion efficiency for the wind assisted and conventional vessel. The propeller efficiency of the conventional vessel is limited at 67% due to relatively high loading. A lower average loading improves the efficiency for the wind assisted vessel to 73%. However, in cases with very large wind assistance, the propeller efficiency becomes “negative”, i.e. power is absorbed by the propeller. The average is shown without those values by the vertical blue line. In order to handle such situations efficiently, it is important either to be able to windmill the propeller with very little friction on the shaft or to adopt a very large pitch angle. The present simulations included a range of pitch angles.

Fig.14: Engine diagrams on the route Gibraltar-Skagen

Fig.15: Histograms of propeller efficiency

Fig.16: Power balance for the wind assisted vessel on the route Gibraltar-Skagen at level of fuel input

A Sankey diagram as shown in Fig.16 shows the power balance, with the energy input on the left and the output (losses) on the right. The width of the arrows indicate the relative size of a particular component. The largest input by far is still fuel. The energy directly extracted from the wind is proportionally very small. However, the energy extracted from the wind (almost) directly contributes to thrust, whereas the fuel input power incurs various losses, most notably the direct “main engine loss” (heat), before it contributes to thrust.

Fig.17 again shows the power balance, but now with the input system boundary at the level of thrust. This shows more clearly the significance of the wind thrust. It is also apparent that, on average, the leeway induced resistance is small. Only in specific time steps in the simulations does it become very large. However, it is still relevant from the perspective of course keeping and being able to extract gains also in high wind conditions at low ship speed.

Fig.17: Power balance for the wind assisted vessel on the route Gibraltar-Skagen at the level of thrust

Fig.18: Fuel consumption for conventional and wind assisted vessel with and without voyage optimisation

Fig.18 shows the overall fuel consumption for both the conventional vessel (without rotors) and the wind assisted vessel. Results are shown for voyages without optimisation (“shortest”) and with optimisation (“optimized”). It is shown that the additional gain due to optimisation is small but consistent on the routes Gibraltar-Skagen and Gibraltar-Trinidad. It is negligible on the route Gibraltar-Izmir. It is noted that the results shown here are averages. Individual routes could be much worse or better.

Fig.19 shows the effective fuel (and emission) savings of the wind assisted vessel relative to the conventional vessel. It is seen that these savings vary between about 5% and 10% on the chosen routes.

Fig.19: Fuel saving

Simplified simulations were also done for the return routes. Fig.20 shows the fuel consumption. These simulations were conducted without voyage optimisation. The results show that small savings can still be achieved on the routes Izmir-Gibraltar and Skagen-Gibraltar. On the route Trinidad-Gibraltar, there is a “negative saving”, i.e. the vessel with Flettner rotor needs additional fuel.

Fig.20: Fuel saving on return routes

8. Conclusions

The operational performance of the Wind Hybrid Coaster was predicted. Fuel savings on the selected routes varied between 5% and 10%. Important aspects in the performance were shown to be the performance of the Flettner rotors themselves, and certainly also the wind conditions, engine and propulsive performance. The leeway induced resistance was small for the adopted amount of wind assistance. However, the efficiency of the hull and yaw balance is still important at specific instances with large wind assistance and low ship speed, both for performance and to keep course.

9. Recommendations

Although it is considered that the present project was finished with a very complete modelling of operational performance, there are some further improvements possible.

The modelling of engine efficiency was relatively simple. A more detailed engine map that accounts for both the influence of power/torque and motor rotation rate will most likely lead to different results. The present vessel probably has little benefit from a more specific propulsion arrangement, because wind assistance is modest. However, other vessels with more wind assistance could benefit from e.g. a diesel-electric propulsion installation. Changes in losses of other components in the propulsion line, e.g. shaft losses, may also need to be reconsidered.

The ability to keep course and the acceptance of heel angles should be studied further. In the present work only the steady values were looked at in the performance prediction prior to voyage simulations.

Which steady heel angle is acceptable, in combination with roll motions in waves needs to be studied. The ability to keep course is affected by waves and should also be looked at to confirm that in favourable stern quartering wind (and waves) the vessel can be steered with low levels of thrust.

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Innovative Energy Saving Device Designed by Virtual Prototyping Method

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Abstract

This paper describes the development of “Ultimate Rudder” new design concept based on FRP construction. The paper describes the CFD process to optimize the rudder profile. An efficiency increase from 4.9 to 5.4% is confirmed in self-propulsion tests.

1. Introduction

EEDI (Energy Efficiency Design Index) came into effect mandatory in January 2013, and ship owners definitely required higher efficiency propulsion systems. Hence, the shipyards have been conducting an optimization of ESD (Energy Saving Device) system in self-propulsion test for each project. As the results, the shipyards have installed a rudder bulb as an effective ESD. The rudder bulb is a popular ESD system from a long time ago. *Mewis and Deichmann (2013)* described that the rudder bulb was developed by Costa in 1952 and the efficiency improve by the rudder bulb for a container vessel was 1% on average. *Fujii et al. (1995)* developed “MIPB (Mitsui Integrated Propeller Boss)” as an advanced rudder bulb. The feature of MIPB was a streamlined profile from propeller cap to rudder. According to their paper, the efficiency improve by installing MIPB was 2-4%.

Recently, Nakashima Propeller Co. Ltd. developed ECO-Cap (economical propeller cap), *Okada (2013)* as a new ESD with FRP (Fiber Reinforced Plastics). The strength of FRP is higher than that of NAB (Nickel Aluminum Bronze); therefore ECO-Cap was able to adopt thin fins on propeller caps for low resistance. Although the material used for the energy-saving propeller cap was generally NAB, the research results on FRP showed that FRP could be used as ESD due to their properties such as lightweight and flexibility.

As explained above, the authors thought that there was a possibility to evolve the rudder bulb profile using the easily moldable FRP compared with NAB. This paper described about the development of “Ultimate Rudder” of new design concept by FRP. The authors optimized the profile of “Ultimate Rudder” by CFD and confirmed the efficiency increase from 4.9 to 5.4% in self-propulsion test.

2. Design Concept

The rudder bulb is adopted as the ESD due to the rudder for improving the efficiency. The mainly effects of hydrodynamics by the rudder bulb were known to the following items.

- a) Decrease of contraction flow behind a propeller
- b) Elimination of a propeller hub vortex
- c) Homogenize of wake distribution and improvement of the hull efficiency by wake gain

To attain the above items effectively, the bulb mounting position is thought to be as close to the propeller plane as possible. In the case of MIPB, the bulb position was closer than past rudder bulb by installation of the divergent propeller cap and the efficiency was improved. Thereafter, some ESD manufactures installed the divergent propeller cap for their own rudder bulb. However, it was difficult to make rounded cap profile like a conventional rudder bulb by the NAB casting, the divergent propeller cap usually has straight outline. If the propeller cap has the rounded profile like a rudder bulb, the efficiency will improve due to wake gain.

In this study, FRP material was used to Ultimate Rudder, and the propeller cap, which was adopted the rounded profile shown in Fig.1 to compensate the drawback of NBA casting. The Ultimate Rudder

with FRP were developed by CFD analysis, furthermore the model test was conducted for a confirmation of an effect on the efficiency of Ultimate Rudder.

Picture of Ultimate rudder Structure of rounded cap(A)
 Fig.1: Profile of Ultimate rudder

3. Analysis Model By CFD

NP208BC was bulk carrier that used for CFD analysis of the Ultimate Rudder, and four- blade propeller was installed. Figs.2 and 3 show hull & propeller profile. Table 1 shows hull dimension and propeller particulars. A normal rudder, a conventional rudder bulb and two kinds of Ultimate Rudder were analyzed by CFD and Fig.4 shows each rudder profile. Two different profiles of Ultimate Rudder were designed as bulb diameter series. Ultimate Rudder1 (UR1) with small diameter and Ultimate Rudder2 (UR2) with large diameter.

Fig.2: Hull profile of NP208BC

Fig.3: Propeller profile

Table 1 Hull dimension and propeller particulars

	Hull dimension		Propeller particulars	
	Actual	Model	Number of blades	
Lpp (m)	295	6.54	Dia. (m) Actual/Model	4
B (m)	50	1.1085	Pitch ratio	8.8 / 0.195
d (m)	16.1	0.3569	Boss ratio	0.75
Cb (-)	0.839		Exp. area ratio	0.18
				0.4

Fig.4: Rudder profile for CFD analysis

The RANS analysis was performed by SOFTWARE CRADLE SCRYU/Tetra Ver.10, which was a commercial CFD code and was based on a finite volume method with unstructured grids. The Shear Stress Transport $k-\omega$ model is applied to the turbulence model of present simulations. A full hull body submerged under the design load water line is modeled. The rotational region is introduced to simulate the propeller rotational condition. Fig.5 shows the present computational domain and the surface mesh around the hull with a propeller and rudder. Constant velocity and zero pressure are prescribed at the inlet and the outlet boundary respectively. The numerical mesh is an unstructured grid, and basic cells are tetrahedral and prismatic cells are applied to near the surface for resolving the boundary layer. The first layer thickness of the prism layer was set to a non-dimensional wall distance for a wall-bounded flow $y^+ = 1$. The total number of meshes is about 45 million.

A symmetry condition (double-body model) at a still-water surface is implemented in the present analysis. The wave resistance coefficient cannot be calculated and is given by the results of the resistance test. RANS simulations of the resistance test, self-propulsion test and propeller open water test are performed to analyze the self-propulsive performance at the thrust identity condition as used in the self-propulsion test. At the self-propulsion point, the total resistance of the ship including an additional towing force (ex. Skin friction correction) is balanced by the delivered thrust from the propeller. The required propeller thrust is obtained by interpolating the results of three rotational rates of the propeller. The Froude number 0.271 is equivalent to 13.5kt at full scale.

Fig.5: Analysis model of CFD

4. Analysis Results By CFD

Fig.6 shows the comparison of the wake distribution of towed condition. The calculation results of axial and tangential wake by CFD were almost similar distribution compared with measurement results of model test. This model and condition of CFD analysis was good-enough accuracy for the development of the rudder bulb.

Fig.6: Wake distribution (model test/CFD)

4.1 Survey of Ultimate rudder profile

The CFD analyses for survey of Ultimate Rudder profile were carried out. Fig.7 shows the vortex behavior by the iso-surface of Q-function, which means the second invariants of the velocity gradient tensor. The normal rudder was confirmed the strong vortex behavior from the rear of the propeller cap to the rudder plane. On the other hand, the conventional rudder bulb, UR1 and UR2 were reduced the vortex behaviors by the rudder bulbs. The self-propulsion factors of each rudder bulb are shown in Fig.8. These values of each rudder bulb are divided by those of the normal rudder. In this graph, the direction for increase of the efficiency was presented to positive value about self-propulsion factors. $1-t$, $1-w$ and η_r of both Ultimate Rudder were better than those of the normal rudder and the conventional rudder bulb. Especially, $1-t$ and $1-w$ of Ultimate Rudder was remarkable. $1-w$ was improved by the displacement effect of Ultimate Rudder. Wake gain of UR2 was increased compared with UR1. This indicated that the rounded cap of large diameter was effective than that of small diameter. In comparison with the normal rudder, the improvement of $\eta_h \cdot \eta_r$ was 3.5% at UR1 and was 4.1% at UR2 respectively. In this way, the effect of Ultimate Rudder installed rounded cap was confirmed by CFD analysis. As the results, UR2 was selected as the most effective rudder bulb for NP208BC.

Fig.7: Vortex behavior by the iso-surface of Q-function.

Fig.8: Self-propulsion factor at $Fn=0.134$

4.2 Comparison of normal rudder and UR2

The detail results of UR2 were compared with the normal rudder. The turbulent energy of normal rudder and UR2 were visualized in Fig.9. The streamline of UR2 was smoothly and the turbulent energy of UR2 was smaller than the normal rudder. Therefore, UR2 was confirmed the elimination of the propeller hub vortex. Fig.10 shows the pressure distribution of the normal rudder and UR2. The negative pressure generated at the propeller cap rear in the normal rudder, and this pressure induced the thrust of aft direction. The leading edge of rudder of UR2 was increased negative pressure and this pressure induced the thrust of fore direction. Therefore, total thrust of UR2 was increased.

Fig.9: Turbulent energy of normal rudder and UR2

Fig.10: Pressure distribution of normal rudder and UR2

5. Model Test Results

Self-propulsion test was carried out for confirmation of propulsion efficiency in SRC(Shipbuilding

Research Centre of Japan). The hull dimension and propeller profile in model test were used the same as CFD analysis. The comparison of model test and CFD was shown in Fig.11. Each values of self-propulsion factor for UR2 were divided by the normal rudder. The improvement of self-propulsion factor was confirmed by model test results. The $\eta_h \cdot \eta_r$ of UR2 at each F_n were increased from 4.9 to 5.4%. In comparison of model test and CFD, the improvement rate of $1-w$ and η_r in model test was almost same as CFD analysis. However, the improvement rate of $1-t$ in model test was about 1.3-1.7% higher than CFD analysis.

Fig.11 Self-propulsion factors by model test and CFD

6. Conclusions

The improvement of efficiency by Ultimate rudder installed rounded cap was confirmed by CFD analysis. The improvement of $\eta_h \cdot \eta_r$ by CFD analysis was 3.5% at UR1 and was 4.1% at UR2 compared with the normal rudder.

The following effects of Ultimate Rudder were confirmed by visualization of CFD analysis:

- Decrease of the turbulent energy due to the propeller hub vortex.
- Revision of the pressure at the propeller cap rear and at the leading edge of rudder

The improvement of self-propulsion factors was confirmed by model test results. The $\eta_h \cdot \eta_r$ of UR2 at each F_n were increased from 4.9 to 5.4%. The tendency of improvement of self-propulsion factors by Ultimate rudder could be estimated by CFD.

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An Open Source Approach for a Conceptual Ship Design Tools Library

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Abstract

This work proposes an investigation about how the conceptual design phase of a vessel can be approached and improved using an open source library connected to knowledge-based and system-based ship design. It provides a set of design tools to be applied in the beginning of a vessel design process. The development of the tools library considers the vessel being subdivided using system-based ship design theory to make the design task less cumbersome and easy to be handled by the tools library. JavaScript is used as an open standard to implement the tools library in a web-based platform. The way JavaScript should be used in order to better deal with the vessel subdivision is also discussed, putting some light in the object oriented programming methodology. Once the tools library is implemented, a case study is conducted to evaluate how well and appropriate its performance is in a real world problem.

1. Introduction – Common platform for early design

With the continuous development of ship design techniques, a continuous increase in the amount of information generated and handled by the design process can be noted, *Gaspar et al. (2012)*. During the vessels' life-cycle, all these information need to be handled and exchanged by several people, being them part of the same company or members of different organizations involved with the vessels' life-cycle. In order to make the design process as efficient as possible, it is important a common standard to identify vessel's systems and components to be used for all the parts involve in the life-cycle, *Monteiro et al. (2015)*. One example of this kind of standard is the SFI Group System, which is a coding system to unequivocally identify any vessel component at any point of the vessel's life-cycle. This kind of coding system is useful for solving communication, cost and control issues. SFI is the most used and well-known coding system used around the world for vessel design, *Fonseca and Gaspar (2015)*.

Besides the standard for components and systems identification, there is also the need for a common platform for handling different types of analyses results involved in the vessel design process. Ship designer already have at their disposal advance techniques to evaluate the vessels' performance according to different merit figures, such structural resistance, hydrodynamic forces, seakeeping capabilities, stability and so on. A common open library platform to perform all these kinds of analyses, handle the results and combine the data could definitely improve several aspects of the design process by means of accelerating the design tasks, reducing rework, saving time and money and etc.

The main objective of this study is to develop an open source conceptual ship design tools library which will address vessels' conceptual design problem using knowledge based design and system based design approaches.

At first, the concept of a tools library needs to be approached. The term library here refers to a collection of objects, which work together to accomplish the required design task. These objects are the tools which the library contains and organizes. Think in these objects as structures to store and handle knowledge or perform functions, calculation or operation. Secondly, the concept of open source software (OSS) is relevant here, since it provides a powerful and yet free platform where the tools library can be implemented. Being developed in an open platform allows the library to not be bounded to any proprietary software, which adds freedom and flexibility while developing and integrating different tools. Last but not least, the conceptual design phase is the beginning of the design process, but still holds a big potential affects the final design. Decisions taken here affect

largely the cost structure of the product while being cheap to be done, making this phase an obvious target for improvement search, which the tools library will try to address.

2. Knowledge and System Based Design

2.1. Knowledge Based Design

The knowledge-based design (KBD) process can be seen as a problem solving process of searching through a state space defined by the syntactic knowledge (design variables) and the interpretative knowledge (design performances), where the states represent the design solutions. The searching process should be done using reasoning based on goal and decision variables, which can be constrained by the world or context where the design is applied or produced, *Coyne et al. (1989)*.

Given that designers design from experience, it is needed a system of storing this experience in a coherent structure, *Gero and Rosenman (1990)*. The prototype should be understood as a conceptual schema for knowledge or a clear way of representing the design and its properties. The prototype represents a class of elements from which instances of elements can be derived. A prototype brings together the three types of variables groups (function, structure, behavior) which define the designed artifact and the relation between them, which includes process for selecting and obtaining values for variables.

Instance can be derived by inheriting properties, functions and variables from a generic prototype. It is possible to derivate new instance from prototype which have already been derivate from other prototype, which make possible to develop a complex hierarchy in the design process, *Gero and Rosenman (1990)*.

A diagram of a prototype schema can be seen in Fig.1. The function properties include the intended function in the form of goals and requirements, and the expected behaviors as attributes and variables. The structure properties include the vocabulary, the prototype description, its configuration and the actual behaviors as attributes and variables of the prototype. Knowledge plays a big hole into the prototype schema. Relational knowledge is required for every mapping from a property to another property. Besides the relational knowledge, the prototype also stores qualitative knowledge, computational knowledge and context knowledge. The qualitative knowledge complements the relational knowledge and provides information on the effects of changing structure variables values on behavior and function properties. The computational knowledge is the quantitative counterpart of qualitative knowledge and specifies symbolic or mathematical relationships among the properties variables. The context knowledge identifies the external variables for a design situation, which should come from the context where the design is inserted. The qualitative and computational knowledge is subjected to constraints, which on function properties appear as expected behaviors and on structure properties reduce the set of possibilities.

2.2 System-Based Ship Design

System-Based Ship Design (SyBSD) works as a framework for the vessel design task. This framework is structured over the idea of dividing the vessel in different systems, based on their functions, which work together to accomplished the desired ship mission, *Levander (2012)*. Different from a top-down design approach where the design starts from the vessel and continue to detail the vessel's systems, the SyBSD uses a bottom-up approach, going from the vessel's required functions to the composition of the vessel itself. The designs start from the mission specification, which defines task, capacities and expected performance by the vessel's stakeholders. This approach straightens the beginning of the design spiral, delaying the beginning of the decision process and reduces the number of iterations needed to find a feasible solution.

Fig.1: Prototype schema diagram, *Gero and Rosenman (1990)*

A functional breakdown is used in order to divide the vessel in systems. The vessel is split into the categories Ship Systems and Payload Systems. The Ship Systems are all systems related to the safe and correct operation of the vessel, without taking the cargo into consideration. The Payload Systems are functions and requirements which generate cash flow for the vessel, which can include cargo and cargo related systems but also specific systems for specialized vessel such offshore support vessels, which can have winch and heavy lift cranes. Due to these special cases, the Payload Systems can also be called Task Related Systems. An example of this division can be seen in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Payload and ship functions in a cargo vessel, *Levander (2012)*

In order to facilitate data collection, the SyBSD divides the systems based on the structure of the SFI Group System, *Urke (1976)*. The correlation between SyBSD and SFI is not completely accurate, since the former does not distinguish between payload and ship systems, Fig.3, which results is some

minor differences between the subdivision of these two structures. Although some differences exist, they can be overcome making some special relations among discordant items, *Erikstad and Levander (2012)*.

Fig.3: SFI main groups structure, *Utne (2009)*

Since the vessels are usually generic, SFI follows a design pattern based on previous experience with resembles a scaling process. This traditional approach easily locks the designer to his first assumption, making him patch and repair the same design, what makes this traditional method not prone to innovation. The SyBSD, using a bottom-up approach determines the needed area, volume and weights for each vessel's function, and from this figures estimates the displacement, main dimensions and building costs. By doing this evaluation without defining the vessels dimension, the SyBSD method does not lock assumptions in the conceptual phase and supports a more creative process in the start of the project. The SyBSD method is suitable for the early design decisions, and can be considered as a checklist that reminds the designer of all the factors that affect the design and record his choices. Its use ensure that the design is based on the most fitted basis ship, and reduces the number of iterations in the design spiral later on, *Vestbøstad (2011)*. The final product of the SyBSD method application is a complete description of the new ship, which can be used as an advanced start point for the next design phases.

3. Open Source Technology and JavaScript

3.1. Object Oriented Programming in JavaScript

In this section, JavaScript is presented as an Open Standard (an open computational language), stating its background, main features and justifying why it will be the choice for developing the conceptual ship design open source tools library.

Object-oriented programming (OOP) is a programming paradigm based on the concept of "objects", which may contain data and code. In OOP, computer programs are designed by making them out of objects that interact with one another. The most popular and developed model of the OOP is the class-based programming (CBP). In this model, objects are entities that combine data, behavior and identity. The structure and behavior of an object are defined by its class, which includes all objects of a specific type. The objects are created based on classes and are considered instances of them, inheriting some of their properties.

JavaScript does not follow the CBP model. It is structured as a class free language, where object inherit properties from other objects. This model is called prototype-based since behavior reuse is performed via a process of cloning existing objects that serve as prototypes, *Stefanov (2010)*. This approach is powerful, making the inheritance process easier to implement, but it is also different from what a conventional CBP language is, *Crockford (2008)*.

An object, which is the JavaScript's core data type and its only complex one, is an unordered list of primitive (Number, String, Boolean, Undefined, and Null) and complex data types that is stored as a

series of key-value pairs. The key property serves as an identifier while the value represents the value of the expression, which can be a primitive or an object value. Each item in the list is called a property or, if an item is a function, it is called method, *Stefanov (2010)*. This easy notation inspired JSON, a popular data interchange format, *Crockford (2008)*. An example of an object (car) containing both properties (type, model and color) and methods (showColor ()) can be seen below.

```
var car = { // car object.
  type: "Fiat", // property.
  model: "500", // property.
  color: "white", // property.
  showColor: function () { // method.
    alert(this.color)
  };
}
```

One of the fundamental concepts from OOP is the inheritance concept. Usually in a CBP language, objects are instances of classes, from which they can inherit properties and functions. In JavaScript, this process is a little different since object inherit from other objects. Other important concept of OOP is the encapsulation concept. Encapsulation refers to enclosing all the functionalities of an object within that object so that the object's methods and properties are hidden from the rest of the application, allowing us to abstract or localize specific set of functionalities on objects. These two concept will be important since they allow the build of applications with reusable code, scalable architecture, and abstracted functionalities.

3.2. Why JavaScript?

The idea in this work is not only create an open source tools library, but also to create a ship design tool which is simple to use, not computational intensive and requires as minimum effort as possible to share designs and results. Working with a software which requires to be installed in the computer could make it difficult to share result with clients, team members or other stakeholders. Using an online platform for the vessel design can reduce these information sharing difficulty, as the only thing one need to access the information about the design is a web browser, and the only thing needed to edit is a text editor, reducing the need for client-side software to a minimum. Also, since all the processing is done in browser, the computational requirements are very low.

Web development is not restricted to one operational system or one platform, since internet is universal. When thinking about client-side web development, JavaScript is an obvious choice. JavaScript is so important and popular because it is the language of the web browsers, *Crockford (2008)*. It is supported by all modern web browsers without the need of plugins, since each browser has its own built-in JavaScript engine, *Flanagan (2011)*. JavaScript composes a triad of web technologies essential for web development, together with HTML to specify the content of the web page and CSS to specify the presentation of the web page. JavaScript is responsible for describing the behavior of the web page, *Flanagan (2011)*.

The position of JavaScript as the main languages in web browser makes it development very fast, with new tools and libraries been developed all the time, by the gigantic JavaScript's community. Since JavaScript is prototype-based with first-class functions, supporting object-oriented, imperative, and functional programming styles, its prototype and inheritance capabilities make it a good choice for dealing with objects to handle the vessel subsystem division and the knowledge base data. It has a simple API for working with text, arrays, dates and regular expressions, which can be completed using third parties' APIs. It has no input-output functionalities, relying on the environment where it is embedded to handle these operations, *Flanagan (2011)*.

The biggest drawn back of JavaScript is the fact that it is an OOP language which is PBP model. This makes it an unusual language for most developers, which are used to conventional CBP model. Using,

directly, programming techniques from CBP will not work in JavaScript, which can be frustrating for an unadvised programmer, *Crockford (2008)*.

4. Tool Library Framework

The methodology for this work will be developed following the system architecture presented in Fig.4, where the tools library components are organized and their relations established. The User provides inputs to the library and receives outputs from it. The Tools Library is developed using JavaScript, for both Prototype and Knowledge-Base. The Prototype contains the most important KBD elements, namely Function, Behavior and Structure. The User's inputs feed the Function block, while the Structure and Behavior blocks are developed using SyBSD theory. The Structure and Behavior blocks receive information from the Knowledge Base through an Inference Mechanism, respectively from the SyBSD Structure Database and Regression Database blocks

Fig.4: Conceptual Ship Design Open Source Tools Library architecture

4.1. Knowledge-Base

One important element in KBD is the knowledge-base. It is responsible for storing knowledge about the design process, which can be accessed by some sort of inference mechanism to retrieve facts, knowledge and control whenever the reasoning process requires. The tools library knowledge base was constructed to be the most generic as possible in order to provide knowledge to the design of several kinds of vessels and is composed by two databases: Regressions Database and SyBSD Structure Database.

The regression database contains important vessel design coefficients regression and knowledge about previously built vessels of several types, including container carriers, bulk carriers, tankers, ferries, roro and offshore support vessels.

The SyBSD database contains classes definitions based on the SyBSD structure. These classes are used to instantiate vessel elements, which compose the vessel's subsystem, which compose the vessel's systems. Whenever the user instantiated a new element, this database will be accessed and the required class structure will be retrieved.

4.2. Vessel Prototype Subdivision Hierarchy

The proposed vessel prototype subdivision hierarchy is presented in Fig.5. SyBSD uses a simple division for the physical structure of the vessel. There are two main groups of systems: Task Related

Systems [1.1] and Ship System [1.2]. The Task Related Systems group includes any cargo and cargo handling systems and specialized system for offshore support vessels which are not related directly to cargo but is related to the money making capacity of the vessel. The Ship Systems group includes any system required for the vessel to safely operate and considers the Outfitting [1.2.1], Crew [1.2.2], Service [1.2.3] and Machinery Systems [1.2.4].

Besides the vessel physical structure, there is also other important elements to consider in the prototype structure. We are defining two JavaScript objects to store data. The first one is related to the required functions of the vessel, namely the Mission Requirements object [1.4]. The second one is responsible for storing the vessel's main dimensions and behaviors, namely the Main Dimensions object [1.5].

Last but not least the prototype will hold several JavaScript methods (or function), which will be responsible for data handling, reasoning, knowledge retrieve and knowledge application. The methods present in the vessel prototype are: Prototype [1.3.1], Area [1.3.2], Volume [1.3.3], Light Weight [1.3.4], Dead Weight [1.3.5], Displacement [1.3.6], Main Dimensions [1.3.7], Holtrop [1.3.8], Seakeeping [1.3.9] and Hull Lines [1.3.10].

Fig.5: Vessel prototype subdivision hierarchy

4.3. System-Based Ship Design Process

In order to apply the SyBSD methodology, the workflow presented in Fig.6 was developed. It includes the main design process the user should perform while applying the ship design tool library. Some of the phases rely on users' knowledge, while others rely on the developed knowledge-base. The tools library user will have direct interaction with phases 1 2 and 7 of this workflow. The phase 1

and 2 are used for data input while the phase 7 is used by the user to check the feasibility of the obtained concept. If the answer for phase 7 is negative the user needs to redefine some systems input and reapply the tolls library.

Fig.6: System-based ship design process workflow

4.4. Vessel Prototype

We are going to represent the vessel using an open prototype and in order to construct it, we are going to implement the tools library using object oriented programming concepts and JavaScript language as an Open Standard. JavaScript was not design as a conventional CBP language, but its object concept can be used to work around this issue.

4.4.1. Object Oriented Programming Implementation in JavaScript: Encapsulation and Inheritance

In order to implement the OOP in JavaScript, we are going to use to different techniques. The first one will be the encapsulation, for creating objects with specialized functionalities. The second one will be inheritance, for code reuse.

The encapsulation concept basically means to put all the inner workings of an object inside that object. To do so, we need to identify and define the properties and methods of that object, so we can apply an encapsulation pattern to construct the object. Implementing inheritance in this application will allow to inherit functionality from parent functions so that we can easily reuse code in the application and extend the functionality of objects, which can make use of their inherited functionalities and still have their own specialized methods and properties.

The best encapsulation mechanism in JavaScript is the Combination Constructor/Prototype Pattern, Zakas (2009). This method is not only capable of dealing with the encapsulation matter, but it is also possible to use it in order to implement inheritance through Prototypical Inheritance. The use of encapsulation makes no sense if one just wants to store some data inside an object. For this kind of

task, writing the object using object literal is sufficient. But when one need to create several object with similar properties and methods, it makes sense to encapsulate all this properties and methods inside a function and use it to construct these objects.

In order to exemplify the use of Combination Constructor/Prototype Pattern technique in JavaScript, we are going to approach the implementation of the systemPrototype method, which is held by the vessel object and is used to instantiate new system objects. Each system object will contain subsystem objects instantiated by the user, following the defined SyBSD structure database. So the systemPrototype method will need to write down the instantiated subsystems as pairs key-property inside the system object. Also, each system object will have the following method: add, area, delete, input and volume. Since all system objects will have the same methods, the Prototypal Inheritance will be used to make the child system objects inherit the methods from the parent system object. Each system object will be afterward specified with the relevant properties addressed by the user. Since we want all vessel systems to have the same methods, we can use a constructor function (class in OOP) to encapsulate these methods. In order to create the constructor function, we will use the Combination Constructor/Prototype Pattern technique.

The first step of the creation of the constructor function is to initialize the instance properties. These properties will be defined on each System instance that is created. The object doesn't have default properties, but has a code routine responsible for getting the constructor input, searching in the SyBSD structure database for the subsystem classes and instantiate the required classes as properties. So the properties values will be different for each System, depending on the user's input.

After the constructor is defined, the next step is to overwrite the prototype property with an object literal, where we define all the methods that will be inherited by all the System instances. By overwriting the prototype with a new object literal we have all the methods organized in one place, effectively implementing the encapsulation.

When overwriting the prototype property, we are preparing the function to provide Prototypal Inheritance. The properties and methods added on the prototype property will be inherited by each instance of the System object, so they can use them and also receive new properties and methods.

4.4.2 Class Diagram Representation of the Vessel Prototype

For modeling the static design view of the vessel prototype the UML Class Diagram, *Booch et al. (1998)*, is going to be employed. It is the most common diagram for modeling object-oriented systems and presents the systems' classes, interfaces, collaborations and their relationships. Using the UML class diagram the object-oriented vessel prototype is modeled. The representation is crucial for presenting such a complex relational structure of all the classes composing the vessel prototype.

The representation done here is a simplified one, where some less relevant aspects of the class diagram were neglected, such as methods' arguments, relations' labeling and responsibilities' definition. The neglected aspect can be useful in several situations, but for the reason the diagram is used here (mostly to make the relations between classes clearer) they are not needed. The main objective with this simplification was to make the diagram more readable in the limited space provided by this report's pages.

The vessel prototype class diagram can be seen in Fig.7. The main class of the vessel prototype is the Vessel class. Its attributes and operations are specified, although the input parameters for the operations were omitted. The Vessel class is composed by System classes. This System classes are related to the Vessel class by mean of composition relations of multiplicity zero or one, since each Vessel class can have zero or only one of each System class. The System classes don't have any default attribute or operation, but they inherit operations from the class VesselSystem, which they are connected to by inheritance relations (which have no multiplicity). The attributes of the System classes are represented by the Subsystem classes, which are connected to their respective System class

by mean of composition relations of multiplicity zero or more. This happens because System classes can contain any number of their respective Subsystem classes.

All the attributes and operations of the vessel prototype were considered public, since they all need to be manipulated by the Vessel class.

Fig.7: Vessel prototype class diagram

5. Case Study

The case study is based on the PSV NAO FIGHTER. The vessel belongs to the PX121 product family (which is a medium-size class) and was designed by Ulstein Design & Solutions AS, constructed by Ulstein Verft AS and is owned by Nordic American Offshore (NAO). In this case study, the tools library is applied aiming to attend the NAO FIGHTER's mission requirements, Table 1. The results obtained from the tools library application are compared with the real vessel parameters in order to verify how realistic (or unrealistic) the final concept is. Since the result of the tools library is only a preliminary concept, it is not expected to obtain a perfect match between the results, but instead, a

deviance of about 10% to more or less is expected and considered fine. The library application will be done considering a subsystem division which is common for PSV vessel but can be a little bit different from the NAO FIGHTER’s subdivision since its exact subdivision is unknown, but it is expected close results anyways.

Table 1: NAO Fighter’s mission requirements, *Ulstein (2016)*

NAO FIGHTER Requirements	
Tunnel thruster	1
Retractable thruster	1
Azimuth thruster	2
Speed (max)	15.9 kn
Accommodation	24 POB
Deck area	850 m ²
Fuel Oil (MDO)	1474 m ³
Fresh Water	1033 m ³
Ballast water/Drill water	1676 m ³
Liquid mud (sp. gr.2,8 t/m3)	1307 m ³
Brine (sp. gr.2,5 t/m3)	1307 m ³
Cement (4 tanks)	254 m ³
LFL* (4 tanks)	153 m ³
Base oil	259 m ³

5.1. Tools Library Application

In this case study, the vessel has all the ship systems. In the task related systems, the only present is the cargo system, since this vessel is a PSV which the only attribution is to transport cargo. The system breakdown structure can be seen in Fig.8.

Fig.8: Case study system breakdown

In order to construct this PSV structure, we need to begin by instantiating a new vessel object using the tools library Vessel constructor. This vessel object will hold all information about the ship and its systems. The input parameters are vessel type (“PSV”), cargo hold capacity (4000 t), cargo deck capacity (2025 t), crew size (24), vessel speed (15.85 kn), installed power (6000 kW), autonomy (1000 km) and operational area (“North Sea”).

The next step consists of instantiating system objects, to hold subsystem object instances, which hold elements instances. After defined, the elements need to be initialized, inserting the required properties. In this case study, the instantiated systems, subsystems and elements are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Instantiated systems, subsystems and elements

<p>cargo system cargo decks general: open cargo deck cargo tanks liquid and dry bulk: brine and mud, fresh water, lfl, base oil, cement cargo related spaces: transfer pumps and piping</p> <p>outfitting ship equipment: tunnel thrusters, retractable thrusters, steering gear, mooring deck forward, mooring deck aft, incinerator plant, decks stores, rope stores rescue firefighting: fast rescue boats, life saving appliances, fire monitors</p> <p>crew facilities crew accommodation: captain class suite, officer cabin, crew single, crew double, cabin corridors wall lining crew common spaces: mess room, officer dayroom, crew dayroom, duty mess, gymnasium, laundry linen, change room, toilets, corridors crew emergency stairways: main stair, service stairs fore, service stairs aft</p> <p>service facilities ship service: wheelhouse, ship offices, iscp office, conference room, hospital catering spaces: galleys, galley provision store, dry provision store, cold provision store, scullery hotel services: linen store, ship laundry, storage spaces in the accommodation, cleaning lockers technical spaces accommodation: ac rooms and ducting, electric substations, instrument room under wheelhouse, void spaces in deckhouse</p> <p>machinery machinery spaces: main and auxiliary engine rooms, shaft lines propellers propulsion thrusters, emergency generator and battery room, pump rooms and equipment spaces, workshops and stores, ecr and switchboard room, firefighting system and CO2 room, engine casing, air intakes, funnel consumables tanks: fuel oil, lub oil, fresh water, sewage and grey water ballast and voids: ballast water</p>

The hull subsystem does not need to be instantiated. It will be defined according to the required area and volume for the vessel. Once all the required systems and subsystems are instantiated, the last step in the conceptual design phase for obtaining the vessel's main dimensions is using the mainDimensionCalc method, held by the Vessel object. This method does not require any input, since all need information is gathered from the tools library database and from the instantiated systems.

5.2. Results and Analyses

The results obtained from this design example can be seen on the mainDimensions object, held by the Vessel object, Table 3. The obtained results don't show anything which raises any worried about the feasibility of the design. All the parameters are quite normal for a PSV of this size. It is also possible to apply the shipMotion method to obtain an estimative of the vessel response for a specific sea state. For example, the method can evaluate the vessel response (in its center of gravity) for a sea state of wave in beam sea, with 2 m amplitude and natural period of 6.5 s. Fig.9 shows an example of movement plot from the shipMotion method.

Other method implemented in the library and which can be applied in this case is the holtrop method. It can give a rough guess about the resistance the vessel would experience while cruising in a specific speed. Fig.10 shows the expected curve of resistance for the vessel for different Froude numbers (and consequently, different speeds), although it is possible to also obtain the resistance value for a specific speed.

Table 3: Conceptual design results – main parameters

Beam (m)	19.39
Metacentric height above center of buoyancy (m)	6.52
Beam/Depth	2.44
Block coeff.	0.675
Center of gravity coeff.	0.74
Mid ship coeff.	0.985
Prismatic coeff.	0.685
Vertical prismatic coeff.	0.807
Waterline coeff.	0.836
Depth (m)	7.94
Froude number	0.28
Metacentric height above center of gravity (m)	1.19
Vertical center buoyancy(m)	2.73
Vertical center gravity (m)	8.06
Length/Beam	4.48
Length/Depth	10.93
LCB (%)	-0.022
Length perpendiculars (m)	84.29
Length waterline (m)	86.82
Draft (m)	4.93
Draft/Depth	0.62
Deadweight (ton)	2997.06
Displacement (ton)	5568.23
Installed Power (kW)	7789.15
Lightweight (ton)	2571.17
Slenderness ratio	4.94

Fig.9: Vertical motion (m/m) as function of wave frequency. Combined movement from the pitch and heave at Center of Gravity

Fig.10: Total resistance (kN) in function of Froude Number

The results obtained from the application of the tools library can be compared with the original vessel’s parameters. Table 4 presents these figures and also the deviance of the obtained values from the original design. Some parameters have no deviance at all, since they were set as required values, from which the design was built around. For the other main parameters, it is possible to verify cases where the deviation goes almost 10% up and almost 10% down.

At the end of the evaluation process, the obtained values are all inside the established range of $\pm 10\%$. If the obtained results were not as close of the real vessel as these ones, it would not necessarily indicate a failed design. As long as none of the parameters make the design unfeasible for any reason, it can be considered as a new design solution.

Table 4: Comparison between case study and NAO Fighter parameters

	Case Study	NAO FIGHTER	Deviation
Length	84.20 m	83.40 m	1%
Beam	19.30 m	18.00 m	7%
Dead weight	2997 tonnes	3300 tonnes	-9%
Draught (max)	6.53 m	6.00 m	9%
Speed (max)	15.85 kn	15.85 kn	0%
Accommodation	24 POB	24 POB	0%
Deck area	850 m ²	850 m ²	0%

6. Concluding Remarks

After applying the open source conceptual ship design tools library in a real design problem, we concluded that the tools library can be successful used to handle the conceptual design phase of a

vessel. The quality of results is strongly connected to the designer's knowledge about the vessel structure, subdivision and elements. The library also relies on an extensive database constructed using information from previous vessel. The quality of this database also has the potential to greatly impact the final concept, so it should be kept updated in order to ensure the most trustable results.

The use of OOP and the concept of classes to represent vessel's systems and subsystems proved to be a very efficient way of handling the conceptual design knowledge. Having the vessel divided in subsystems and elements, which can be attributed to classes in an OOP language, works well to approach a complex design problem by dividing it in smaller and simpler problems, which can be solved individually.

The biggest drawn back of the tools library is that it applies the SyBSD theory directly, with does not provide a mechanism to consider the systems, subsystems and elements interdependencies and interfaces. In a product with such a complex structure as a vessel, neglecting this type of relation will, inevitably, lead to design problems, especially in the more advanced design stages. Since these effects are less relevant in the conceptual design phase, the tools library can be applied to the conceptual design but should not be applied, in its current development stage, to further design phases.

Since the tools library is developed in an Open Standard, it is free and, consequently, more accessible to end users. Since the code is open, the tools library can be continuously improved by interested users. There is no limitation to its functionality, since when a limitation is found, it can be corrected or extinguished by the adding of new tools. The choice for JavaScript as an Open Standard was not aleatory. At first, it is a web-based programming language which is present in all the web browsers. Developing the library to be accessed via web browsers reduces the needs for client side software to a minimum, also reducing the computational requirements for the user's hardware, while making it accessible for any operational system and device.

One of the strongest points in the conceptual ship design tools library is its modularity. The library in composed by several design tools organized under the Vessel object's methods. New tools can be added to the library without the need to modify the functions that are already there. The new functions just need to be developed having in mind the Vessel object's hierarchy and structure. New systems and subsystem structures can also be easily added by just updating the SyBSD Structure Database. The modular characteristic makes the tools library a very flexible and powerful ship design tool.

The tools library is suitable enough for addressing the conceptual design phase, but lack support for further and more details stages of design. The capacity to store and handle data can be increased in order to make detail design a reality, especially considering the systems communication and interfaces, implementing a mix of SyBSD and Holistic design processes. This improvement in the library can be difficult to implement, since its whole structure is based on isolating systems, subsystems and elements, but definitely worth investigating in a further study.

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Biologically Inspired Force Enhancement for Maritime Propulsion and Maneuvering

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Abstract

The move to high performance applications greatly increases the demand to produce large instantaneous fluid forces for high-speed maneuvering and improved power efficiency for sustained propulsion. Animals achieve remarkable feats of maneuvering and efficiency by changing their body shape to generate unsteady fluid forces. Inspired by this, we have studied a range of immersed bodies which drastically change their shape to produce fluid forces. These include relatively simple shape-changes, such as quickly changing the angle of attack of a foil to induce emergency stops and the use of tandem flapping foils to generate three times the average propulsive force of a single flapping foil. They also include more unconventional shape-changes such as high-speed retracting foil sections to power roll and dive maneuvers and the use of soft robotics to rapidly shrink the frontal area of an ellipsoid to power 50% efficient fast-start maneuvers or even completely cancel the drag force with 90% quasi-propulsive efficiency. These systems have been investigated with analytics, experimental measurements and Cartesian-grid immersed-boundary numerical simulations.

1. Introduction

With the expansion of human activities in the oceans towards more extreme environments, state-of-the-art maritime technologies have progressively become less suited at coping with the increased degree of complexity of their missions. As an example, the offshore oil industry is more and more involved in operating in deeper waters and need to acquire baseline and on-going surveys throughout the life history of submerged infrastructures and their interaction with the surrounding ecosystems. Currently, operations of this kind rely heavily on expensive and slow human divers because traditional robots are simply not suitable to acquiring in-situ measurements in very close proximity to submerged structures or living organisms.

Aerial and marine animal achieve remarkable feats of maneuvering and efficiency by changing their body shape to generate unsteady fluid forces. For example, birds execute precise maneuvers, such as banking, braking, takeoff and landing, all with minimal power expended *Provini et al. (2014)*. This is in stark contrast to current “flight-type” marine and aerial vehicles with fixed wings that have a fixed minimum operating speed and slow response time, or “hover-type” vehicles with multiple thrusters which have limited mission lives due to their inefficiency.

Starting with the seminal work of *Lighthill (1960)*, which mathematically formulated how fish produce large forces and high efficiency with undulatory motion, there has been significant research in studying shape-changing unsteady biological flows and exploiting them in maritime engineering designs. While fish swimming itself has now been well studied, *Triantafyllou et al. (2000)*, and applied to small robotic vehicles, *Triantafyllou and Triantafyllou (1994)*, the mechanical complexities make adapting fish-propulsion to broader applications difficult. In this manuscript, we review some recent work on biologically inspired mechanisms that generate strong forces, are highly efficient, and are achieved with relatively simple actuation methods, all of which makes them potentially suited to maritime applications.

2. Heaving and pitching foils

The first biologically inspired force-producing device was certainly a flapping wing, dating at least as far back as Da Vinci ca. 1485, *McCurdy (1941)*. Modern research has revitalized this concept, showing that lifting surfaces that are actuated to dynamically heave and/or pitch have potential advantages over either fixed lifting surfaces or standard propellers. Studies on the thrust forces

generated by an oscillating foil have shown the potential for impressive thrust coefficients (maximum of $C_T = 2.4$) and efficiency regions of 50-60%, *Read et al. (2003)*. It has also been shown that an oscillating foil can be used to manipulate incoming vorticity for energy extraction, with efficiencies at and above 45%, *Simpson et al. (2008)*. However, there is a wide range in observed efficiencies and force magnitudes, and these parameters vary with oscillation type, planform and flexibility of the foil. This section reviews two studies on actuated rigid foils that demonstrate large force production at high efficiency levels with simple kinematics.

Fig.1: Simulated streaklines for the two-dimensional flow past a single flapping foil and tandem flapping foils. The streaklines are visualized by continuously releasing tracer particles on either side of the foil at the quarter-chord. The tandem case has phase lag $\phi = 1.75\pi$, and spacing $s = 2c$.

2.1 Tandem flapping foils to balance forces and utilize wake energy

A fundamental issue with implementing a flapping foil as a marine propulsor on an otherwise conventional ship or underwater vehicle is the large variation in thrust and side force. Additionally, propulsive efficiency in the range of 50-60% is not optimum, indicating that mechanical power is being wasted in energizing the wake. A recent study by *Epps et al. (2016)* investigated the use of tandem flapping foils to mitigate the unbalanced forces and potentially increase efficiency by utilizing energy in the wake of the forward foil.

In this study, the foils undergo prescribed harmonic heave h and pitch θ , defined as

$$h_f(t) = c \sin(\omega t), \quad h_b(t) = c \sin(\omega t + \phi) \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_f(t) = \frac{\pi}{4} \cos(\omega t), \quad \theta_b(t) = \frac{\pi}{4} \cos(\omega t + \phi) \quad (2)$$

c is the chord length, ω is the flapping frequency and ϕ is the phase lag between the foils, and the f, b subscripts refer to the front and back foils respectively. The frequency is set to achieve a Strouhal number of $St = 4\pi\omega c / U = 0.4$, known to be at the upper end of the range resulting in high thrust for a single foil, *Read et al. (2003)*. The flow speed U is set to achieve a Reynolds number of $Re = Uc/\nu = 10^4$.

This flow was studied using the Lily Pad computational fluid dynamics software. As discussed in *Weymouth (2015)*, Lily Pad is a two-dimensional Cartesian-grid flow solver that uses the Boundary Data Immersion Method, *Maertens and Weymouth (2015)*, and has been extensively validated for unsteady fluid-body interaction problems. For these simulations, a grid spacing of $h=c/64$ and a domain size of $16c \times 8c$ was used.

Fig.1 shows a set of Lily Pad results for the flow around single and tandem flapping foils. Streaklines in Fig.1(a) show that the characteristic reverse Karman street has formed, accelerating the flow behind the single foil. Fig.1(b) shows a set of streaklines for a tandem case where the leading edge of the back foil is spaced $s = 2c$ behind the trailing edge of the front foil and the motion is lagged by $\phi = 1.75\pi$. The wake in the tandem case has narrowed and lengthened compared to the single foil case, indicating greater speed and possibly efficiency.

Fig.2: Performance coefficients for the tandem foils shown in Fig.1b; front foil (red), back foil (green); dashed lines are the mean values over the cycle.

A set of performance metrics are shown in Fig.2. The thrust T and lift L are defined as the integrated fluid force inline with and perpendicular to the oncoming flow, as usual. The general equation for the power transferred from the body to the fluid is

$$P = \oint_S (\vec{f}(s, t) \cdot \vec{u}(s, t)) ds \quad (3)$$

\vec{f} is the local fluid force per unit area on the body surface, \vec{u} is the local body surface velocity, $\oint_S ds$ is an integral over the body surface. This formula automatically accounts for both the pitch and heave motion and is also valid for the flexible and deforming bodies used in the next sections.

Another key performance metric is the efficiency, which is the rate of useful work done per unit power consumed. As such, the hydrodynamic efficiency of a propulsive actuator operating at a steady forward speed is simply

$$\eta_t = \frac{TU}{P} \quad (4)$$

TU is the rate of work done in the inline direction.

The results in Fig.2 are for the tandem case, but the performance of the front foil is essentially independent of the back foil for $s > c$. The front foil results compare well to those presented in the literature for single flapping foils, with a mean thrust coefficient of $C_{T,f} = T_f / (\frac{1}{2} \rho U^2 c) = 0.52$, mean lift of zero, and mean power coefficient of $C_{P,f} = P_f / (\frac{1}{2} \rho U^3 c) = 1.04$. Therefore the efficiency for this simple choice of kinematics is 50%.

The back foil undergoes the same motion as the front, but operates in its wake, which significantly changes the response. Most noticeable is the large increase this enables in the back foil thrust, $C_{T,b} = 1.02$, twice the value of the front foil. In other words, adding a second foil has not doubled the total thrust, but instead tripled it. This is due to the positive wake interference of the two foils. Negative interference is also possible, and *Epps et al. (2016)* develops a relationship between the spacing and phase to characterize this interference.

In addition, the peak forces on the hind foil are phase shifted by ϕ relative to the front foil. By properly setting the spacing and phase, *Epps et al. (2016)* shows that a tandem foil propulsion system would be capable of greatly reducing the variation in the thrust force compared to a single flapping foil. It is also possible to reduce the variation in lift, but because the thrust peaks are twice as frequent, two foils cannot perfectly cancel both thrust and lift variation. Finally, the increased thrust on the back foil shown in Fig.2 does require increased power, but not disproportionately. In fact, the efficiency of the tandem foil system overall is $\eta_t = 53\%$, slightly better than that of the front foil alone.

Fig.3: Kinematics and forces on a foil with rapidly increasing pitch during acceleration, reproduced from *Polet et al. (2015)*. The force coefficients from two-dimensional simulations at $Re = 2000$, experiments at $Re = 22000$, and an inviscid flow model are given over three maneuver speeds

2.2 Rapid pitch-up for impulsive stopping force

One of the most striking advantages of flying animals over fixed-wing aircraft is their ability to come to a complete and controlled landing in only a few body lengths; even large gliding birds such as an eagle, *Carruthers et al. (2007)*. Like aircraft, flight-type underwater vehicles have a minimum operating speed to maintain their depth, and because maritime vessels are proportionally much heavier than aircraft, they are even slower to stop. *Polet et al. (2015)* studied a simple model of wing kinematics during perching and found that very large dynamic lift and drag forces are produced - and these forces could potentially be utilized to impulsively stop heavy and streamlined maritime vehicles.

Polet et al. (2015) focused on one key kinematic characteristic of bird perching, the rapid increase in pitch of the wings during deceleration. Lily Pad simulations ($Re = 2000$) and experiments ($Re = 22000$) were performed in which the foil speed and pitch angled were varied during the maneuver as

$$U(t) = U_0 (1 - t^*) \quad (5)$$

$$\theta(t) = \theta_{final} \left(t^* - \frac{\sin(2\pi t^*)}{2\pi} \right) \quad (6)$$

U_0 is the initial velocity, $\theta_{final} = \pi/2$ is the final pitch position, and $t^* = t/\tau$ is time scaled by the period of the maneuver τ up to $\theta = \pi/2$. A NACA0012 foil section was used and the center of rotation was set $c/6$ from the leading edge.

We quantify the impulsiveness of the maneuver using the shape-change number from *Weymouth and Triantafyllou (2013)*

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{V}{U_0} \quad (7)$$

which is the speed of the shape-change V relative to the flow. For this maneuver we choose $V = c/\tau$, the average cross-flow velocity of the trailing edge.

Fig.3 shows the resulting forces from the simulations, experiments, and an inviscid flow model described in *Polet et al. (2015)*. Forces increased with increasing shape-change number, and at $\mathcal{E} = 1/2$ the values are ten times larger than the lift and drag at the corresponding static pitch angle, which would help birds maintain lift and come to a controlled stop. However, the drag forces are

negative at the end of the maneuver which decreases the average stopping force. *Polet et al. (2015)* postulate that the unwanted thrust generation is due to the prescribed constant rate of deceleration, which does not match the natural fluid-structure interaction in true perching.

Fig.4: Foil vorticity field for free-running simulations of an ellipsoid undergoing a stopping maneuver by rapidly pitching foils with $\Xi = 1/2$, $\theta_{\text{final}} = \pi/2$

Fig.5: Results for four stopping maneuver cases; $\{\Xi, \theta_{\text{final}}\} = \{1/2, \pi/2\}, \{1/4, \pi/2\}, \{1/2, \pi\}, \{1/4, \pi\}$. Points in (a) show increments of $tU_0/c=1$

To test this theory and to determine the applicability of pitching foils on maritime vehicles we next carry out free-running simulations of a stopping maneuver. The vehicle is set to be a neutrally buoyant ellipsoid with uniform density, diameter c and length $8c$, Fig.4. A NACA0012 foil with span c is mounted on either side of the body center and the pitch relative to the body is given by Eq.(6). We set $Re = U_0 c/\nu = 22000$. The dynamics of the vehicle are modeled as

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{D - \frac{1}{2} C_x \rho A_x \dot{x}|\dot{x}|}{m + m_{xx}}, \quad \ddot{y} = \frac{L - \frac{1}{2} C_y \rho A_y \dot{y}|\dot{y}|}{m + m_{yy}}, \quad \ddot{\psi} = \frac{M}{I + m_{\psi\psi}} \quad (8)$$

where x, y are the body centroid location, ψ is the heading, $\dot{x} = U$, $\dot{y} = V$ are the velocity components, m is the mass, I is the moment of inertia, and C_a, A_a, m_{aa} are the drag coefficient, taken from *Hoerner (1965)*, projected area, and potential flow added-mass in the a-direction. Note that while the fluid forces on the body are modeled analytically, D, L, M are the measured lift drag and moment of the foil in the coupled simulation.

The results of the maneuvering simulations are shown in Fig.5. Increasing the shape-change rate increases the forces, and the peak drag magnitudes are similar to the prescribed deceleration case results in Fig.3. However, the free-running case results in only positive drag force, verifying the *Polet et al. (2015)* discussion, and helping the vehicle stop. The resulting trajectories show that the pitch-up maneuver is capable of stopping the body's forward motion in $1.6c$, only 20% of the body length. Fig.5 also shows two cases where the final pitch has been increased to π , e.g. the foil keeps pitching until it is faces backwards. This motion ensures that it is the dynamic forces responsible for stopping the

body - not just bluff-body drag on the sideways foil. The results show the body not only stops, but also fully reverses, and does so with relatively little vertical drift.

3 Size and shape-changing bodies

In contrast to rigid body kinematics, such as flapping, little research has been devoted to explosive size and shape-change despite its prevalence in nature. For example, many animals use “burst and coast” gaits when performing maneuvers to reduce the cost of transport by as much as 50%, *Weihs et al. (1984)*, *Chung (2009)*. Extreme shape change is also often used in “survival” hydrodynamics, i.e. to help an animal hunt or evade attack where extreme accelerations are required, *Triantafyllou et al. (2016)*. In this section we review two series of recent studies on using size-change as a novel form of force generation. Surprisingly, the ‘ballistic’ nature of these novel actuation methods often makes them simpler to implement than the controlled kinematics of the previous section. And advances in soft-robotics are enabling the first tests of these size-and-shape changing devices.

3.1 Span-wise retraction to shed vorticity

When birds and marine mammals perform “burst and coast” maneuvers they rapidly pull their wings or flippers against their bodies - causing them to effectively ‘vanish’ from the flow. Classic studies such as *Taylor (1953)* showed that this sudden disappearance would leave a significant vortex in the fluid, generating large forces. *Wibawa et al. (2012)* attempted to experimentally and numerically study this vanishing phenomenon by quickly retracting a foil along its span while towing it forward. Retraction is much simpler and less power-consuming than flapping and could be easily used in practical maritime designs.

The study used a foil with a rectangular planform, square tip, and NACA0012 cross-section. The foil was towed along the tank at $Re = Uc/\nu = 14000$ at a 10° angle of attack and was retracted a distance $1.4c$ with an average speed of $6U$. Experimental results showed that while some circulation was shed, it was less than half of the bound circulation before retracting, and it decayed so quickly that it couldn't be feasibly used to generate maneuvering forces.

Three-dimensional simulations were performed to visualize the complete flow. Fig.6 (a) shows a similar simulation, but run at $Re = 1000$ to clarify the vorticity structures. The wake structures were found to be highly complex because the impulsive retraction of the foil generated its own wake, which mixed and disturbed the shedding of the bound vorticity. Again, this limits the amount of useful work that the maneuver can achieve.

Fig.6: Simulations of the retracting foil at $Re = 1000$ for three foil geometries. $t^* = tU=c = 0$ is when the foil crosses the PIV plane (green line). The left and right of each panel show λ_2 and ω_z iso-surfaces, respectively. Reproduced from *Steele et al. (2016)*.

In a follow-up study, *Steele et al. (2016)* showed that the shape of the foil geometry can be easily adjusted to achieve different kinds of fluid response. Fig.6 shows the result of the same retraction maneuver on two other foil shapes; a foil with a streamlined and rounded wing tip, and a foil which is hollow and open on the wing tip to allow fluid to pass through. Fig.7 shows the result of using dye visualization in an experimental test of the retracting hollow foil. The results show that because the hollow foil does need to pull fluid up to fill the wake of its retraction, the vorticity is shed in two large clear vortex structures which could be used to induce dynamic roll moments on trailing control surfaces.

Fig.7: Experiment with dye injection of the retracting open hollow foil at $Re = 13700$. The orange dye is from inside the foil, while the green is from the outside. The left image is around $t^*=0.15$, right around $t^*=1.15$. Reproduced from *Steele et al. (2016)*

3.2 Shrinking to recover added-mass energy and cancel drag

The streamlined foil result in Fig.6 is entirely different than that of the hollow foil. Consider the cross-section of the streamlined foil as it retracts through the PIV plane. This is not a ‘vanishing’ body, but a shrinking one. The key difference, as shown in *Weymouth and Triantafyllou (2012)*, is that the shrinking body pulls in fluid to fill the void left by its retraction, while a vanishing hollow body does not. In both cases, the reduced size of the body means a corresponding reduction in the fluid added-mass. However, the resulting dynamics of the fluid, and its force on the body could not be more different. For a vanishing body, the surplus fluid kinetic energy goes into the generation of shed vortical structures as shown in Fig.6(c). For a shrinking body, two related effects were found:

1. The rapid motion of the boundary generates a layer of vorticity which can cancel the boundary layer vorticity for high shape-change numbers. This is demonstrated by the small amount of shed vorticity in Fig.6(b).
2. The cancellation of bound vorticity enables the transfer of the fluid added-mass energy back into the body, resulting in significant instantaneous forces.

In the case of an inviscid fluid, the bound vorticity cancellation is perfect, and the resulting force is simply

$$F = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(m_{xx} U) = -\dot{m}_{xx} U - m_{xx} \ddot{x} \quad (9)$$

where \dot{m}_{xx} is the rate of change of the added-mass. The final term is the standard added-mass force due the body acceleration, but the first term is due to the recovery of added-mass energy by the body. For large shape-change numbers $\dot{m}_{xx} U$ could be sufficient to completely cancel the body drag force.

Giorgio-Serchi and Weymouth (2016) used a volume-changing oscillator to test this method of drag cancellation. They simulated the flow on a spherical body with radius r connected to a spring and immersed in water. If this body is released from a large displacement, say $x_0 = 2r$, it will oscillate with a natural frequency ω_n but the amplitude will quickly decays to nothing due to the drag of the fluid, Fig.9(a, non-excited). However, if the radius of the sphere is made to change in time with

amplitude a , then added-mass energy will transfer back and forth between body and fluid, exciting oscillation, Figs. 8 and 9(a, excited).

Fig.8: Evolution of the λ_2 vortex criterion during one oscillation after attainment of zero-damping regime in response to the sharp and smooth radius variations, Fig.9. Reproduced from *Giorgio-Serchi and Weymouth (2016)*

This is called a parametric-oscillator, and just like a child on a swing changing their center of effort, this can lead to sustained large amplitude oscillations if the oscillator is pumped near the natural frequency. But while a swing would work underwater, the amplitude would be tiny due to drag. By shrinking and growing, the sphere's large bluff body drag force is canceled, enabling oscillation amplitudes up to $X = 4.7a$ and $3.5 r_0$, Fig.9.

Fig.9 also compares the results to an analytic parametric-oscillator model developed in *Giorgio-Serchi and Weymouth (2016)* using the inviscid force equation, and while the frequency match is excellent, the model over predicts X for large a because of the imperfect recovery of added-mass energy. Indeed, Fig.8 shows the simulated flow features large scale vortex shedding - indicating that at least some portion of the energy is spent stirring up the fluid.

To quantify how much energy is wasted, we need to revisit the definition of efficiency. While the standard definition of efficiency applies well to propulsors in isolation, the useful work is ill-defined for a self-propelled body. As discussed in *Maertens et al. (2015)*, this is because the net force on a steady self-propelled body is zero by definition and the power lost to the environment depends sensitively on the propulsion method. Instead, we must use the quasi-propulsive efficiency

$$\eta_{QP} = \frac{P_{tow}}{P_{self}} \quad (10)$$

Fig.9: Transverse response x of the oscillating sphere, with and without volume-change excitation. Sharp excitation refers to the ‘saw tooth’ pattern at the top of (a), while smooth excitation is a simple sin wave pattern. The grey lines in (c) assume 100% efficient added-mass energy recovery, while the dark lines assume $\eta = 0.9$. Reproduced from *Giorgio-Serchi and Weymouth (2016)*.

P_{tow} is the power lost to the fluid when towing the rigid body at its operating condition, and P_{self} is the power usage measured in the self-propelled test.

This is, in fact, the standard measure of efficiency used in Naval Architecture. In the case of a propeller-driven ship at steady-ahead conditions the efficiency is

$$\eta_{QP} = \frac{RU}{Q\omega} \quad (11)$$

where the towed resistance R times the speed U is the towed power loss, and the propeller shaft torque Q times the rotation rate ω is the self-propelled power usage. When using the efficiency equation, the towed body should be rigid and bare (no propulsor) but otherwise operated at the same conditions as the self-propelled test.

Applied to the case of the volume-changing and oscillating sphere, we first select a self-propelled case, say $a/r_0 = 0.35$ and $\omega = \omega_n$ which achieved in $X/a = 4.7$ using the smooth profile. We then repeat this case with a rigid sphere towed at the same frequency and amplitude of motion. After measuring the power used in both cases, the quasi-propulsive efficiency is found to be $\eta_{QP} = 0.91$. This was found to be a representative value for the smooth profile cases. (Note that the power transfer during sharp inflation is infinite, making this a rather poor choice for energy efficiency. Even using the slightly smoothed profile, the extreme magnitude of the power peaks made computing a meaningful average impossible.) Using this value, the analytic prediction can be corrected and agrees well with experiments, Fig.9.

If drag cancellation with 90% efficiency seems too good to be true, it may be explained (or perhaps

rationalized) by considering that the growing and shrinking of a shape in water induces a completely irrotational fluid motion. Unlike the rotation of a propeller or flapping of a foil then, an inflate-deflate cycle is perfectly reversible, resulting in a zero net transfer of energy to the fluid over the cycle. As the maturing field of soft robotics enables designs with highly deformable parts, *Giorgio-Serchi et al. (2013)*, such efficiencies may soon be realized experimentally.

3.3 Deflating to power an ultra-fast start

Cephalopods, such as squid and the octopus, greatly increase their size by filling with water, before ejecting the water in a propulsive jet, reducing their size and helping them make a quick escape, *Huffard (2006)*. As a final example, we review a series of studies that investigated a jet-propelled shrinking vehicle as a model of this system both analytically and experimentally.

Weymouth and Triantafyllou (2013) consider three types of jet-propelled bodies; a rocket in the vacuum of space, a rigid 5:1 ellipsoidal torpedo in water, and an octopus-like vehicle which shrinks from a sphere to a 5:1 ellipsoid as it jets. The acceleration of all three is governed by the simple equation

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{F - \dot{m} U_J}{m} \quad (12)$$

where F is the fluid reaction force and $-\dot{m} U_J = T_J$ is the jet thrust, which is the rate of change of mass of body (which is negative) times the jet velocity.

Fig.10 shows the results for all the three cases when jetting from rest until 96% of the initial mass m_0 has been expelled, keeping U_J constant for the majority of the maneuver.

- In a vacuum, $F = 0$ and the net force $\sum F$ equals T_J . The rocket accelerates at an increasing rate due to decreased inertia, accelerating far beyond the jet velocity.
- If we model the fluid reaction force on the rigid torpedo with Eq.(9), then the body experiences no drag, but will have an ever increasing added-mass force such that $\sum F \ll T_J$. In essence, the torpedo's added mass is an additional payload which is never sheds, limiting its acceleration.
- The octopus-like vehicle start as a sphere, meaning its inertia is initially 50% greater than the rocket in space. However, unlike the rigid torpedo, this is not payload - it is additional propellant! As the body shrinks, the added-mass energy is recovered in the form of thrust. In the second half of the maneuver, when the inertia is reduced, this results in $\sum F > T_J$.

Fig.10: Comparison of three jet-propelled rocket fast-start maneuvers using Eq.(9) to model the fluid reaction force

The final result being that the octopus-like body accelerates up to $3.5U_J$, much faster than the rigid torpedo, and even faster than a rocket in the vacuum of space.

As discussed above, the successful recovery of added-mass energy requires that the energy is not lost to shed vorticity. *Weymouth et al. (2015)* investigated this process analytically and developed a new parameter to predict the recovery efficiency. As the octopus-like vehicle shrinks, it induces a normal velocity, which draws in the fluid in the boundary layer. If this inward velocity is strong enough to overcome the diffusion of the boundary layer, then the vorticity can be annihilated and the flow energy recovered. *Weymouth et al. 2015* likens this to the application of suction on a rigid boundary layer. In analogy to a suction parameter, they define a shrinking parameter

$$\sigma^* = V \sqrt{\frac{L}{U\nu}} = \mathcal{E} \sqrt{Re} \quad (13)$$

where V is the cross-flow velocity of the deforming body, in this case the rate of change of the minor-axis radius. This modification of the shape-change number includes the rate of boundary layer diffusion, and axis-symmetric boundary layer theory suggests that $\sigma^* > 9$ should be a threshold value for delayed separation and energy recovery. Note that this threshold is easier to achieve at larger Reynolds numbers, and therefore large body-sizes.

Based on this, *Weymouth et al. (2015)* designed a prototype soft robotics vehicle to maximize σ^* during a jet-propelled fast start maneuver. The octopus-inspired vehicle consists of a rigid neutrally buoyant skeleton with an elastic membrane stretched around it to form the outer hull. As with the mantle of the octopus, this membrane can be inflated, giving it an initially bluff shape and storing sufficient energy to power its escape. The fully deflated hull shape is approximately a 5:1 ellipsoid, and is sufficiently streamlined to allow the body to coast dozens of body lengths. The body is $L = 26 \text{ cm}$ long and the volume when fully deflated is 1030 cm^3 , so the ‘payload’ mass accelerated by the maneuver is $m_f = 1.03 \text{ kg}$.

Once inflated, the robot is released from a mount allowing it to accelerate forward in open water under its own power. The resulting fast-start maneuver performance is measured using high-speed cameras at 150 frames/second. Fig.11 shows the rapid acceleration and deflation of the shrinking robot from a self-propelled run. The velocity peaks above 10 L/s or 2.7 m/s around $t = 0.96 \text{ s}$ after release. Based on this and scale of deformation of the body we have $\mathcal{E}_{ave} = 1/24$, $Re_{ave} = 350000$ and the shrinking parameter is $\sigma^* > 77$ throughout the maneuver, well above the threshold. This high shrinking parameter indicates we should have efficient energy recovery. To quantify this the outline of the body is measured from the images to estimate the mass flux and therefore the jet thrust, and compare it to the acceleration and net force. Fig.11 shows that the peak net force is 130% greater than T_j , similar to the analytic predictions.

We can also measure the kinetic energy and the integrated power delivered by the jet given by

$$P\Delta t = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\tau \dot{m} U_j^2 dt \quad (14)$$

Fig.11 shows the ratio of these values. However, this is not the quasi-propulsive efficiency. The useful work done is the change in kinetic energy plus the power lost when towing the rigid (deflated) body through the same maneuver, which has been neglected above. This loss is estimated using the empirical values C_D and m_{xx} values for an ellipsoid and gives a quasi-propulsive efficiency of $\eta_{QP} = 68\%$. This efficiency is on par with the theoretical propulsive efficiency of rocket accelerating from rest in a vacuum, which peaks at about 65%, *Ivey (1947)*.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Vorticity generation is the key to all fluid force generation. It is text-book knowledge that increasing the speed of a body will generally generate more vorticity and increase the force. Slightly less well known is that added-mass in a viscous fluid is also based on vorticity generation on the body surface, making this a uniting theme in fluid dynamics, *Leonard et al. (2001)*.

Fig.11: Results of self-propelled test of the octopus-inspired vehicle. Reproduced from *Triantafyllou et al. (2016)*, where $F_j = T_j$ is the jet force

In this context, one characteristic stands out in the biological-inspired studies above:

Unsteady biologically-based propulsors optimize the generation of vorticity by coordinating their kinematics and shape-change with the state of the flow.

The additional degrees of freedom in biologically-based systems gives them the potential to add that vorticity when and where it will be most useful, and this can be used to efficiently generate large forces for maritime applications.

- In the case of tandem flapping foils, proper phase and distance gaps between the foils enable positive interference to double the thrust on the back foil, or to reduce the variation in lift and thrust.
- A foil pitched-up rapidly is capable of generating large vorticity if the shape-change number \mathcal{E} is increased, and can bring a streamlined body to a complete stop in 20% of its length.
- Spanwise-retraction of a hollow foil minimizes the generation of new vorticity, freeing the bound vorticity to do other useful work.
- On the other hand, retracting a foil with a streamlined planform generates opposite-sign vorticity on the boundary, annihilating the bound vorticity.
- This annihilation enables a body to recover the fluid's added-mass kinetic energy in the form of a large unsteady force. If timed with the natural frequency, this can be used to cancel drag on a size-changing sphere with 91% efficiency.
- Finally, by treating the added-mass as additional propellant, stored up initially and released throughout, a shrinking rocket can achieve an ultra-fast start.

This recovery of fluid energy in the form of thrust is especially interesting, and occurs readily as long as its shrinking rate σ^* overcomes viscous diffusion. As this number increases with Reynolds number, even greater quasi-propulsive efficiency may soon be realized experimentally.

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Cable Towing with an Autonomous Sailboat

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Abstract

This paper presents the use of a small autonomous sailboat at approximately 4 m length overall for collecting marine data with the use of a cable towed after the boat. A dynamic model for the sailing boat towing a cable is described; simulations are presented and compared to measurements from a real system. The feasibility of cable towing with a small autonomous sailboat are discussed.

1. Introduction

Åland Sailing Robots is a project at the Åland University of Applied Sciences concerned with various aspects of autonomous sailing. One of the goals of the project is to develop a platform for marine measurements using wind and solar energy. The use of autonomous sailing robots for collecting data in marine environments has some appealing features, e.g., it is without the noise of engines for propulsion, it has very low environmental impact locally and it can cover large areas with no human interaction.

One such important application is to measure and monitor high-frequency cetaceans, such as porpoise species, and this is also the main application considered in the current study. High-frequency cetaceans produce echolocation clicks for purposes of navigation, communication and prey detection. The echolocation clicks have a peak frequency of approximately 130 kHz, and are strongly absorbed during propagation, with the effect that the acoustic detection range is limited to a few 100 meters *Klinck et al (2016)*. Two populations of the harbor porpoise, *Phocoena phocoena*, exist in the Baltic Sea, where the Baltic Proper population is critically endangered, *Benke et al (2014)*. Efforts have been made to estimate the size and spread of the populations, both by modelling from satellite telemetry of tagged animals, and by using static acoustic monitoring (C-PODS), *Mikkelsen et al (2016)*. Acoustic detections of *Phocoena phocoena* have also been made with a hydrophone mounted to the keel of an autonomous sailboat, *Klinck et al (2016)*. A moving platform is suitable for this kind of monitoring, because habitats are utilized differently in different times of the day and year.

Mounting the hydrophone directly to the keel has drawbacks. Moving actuators in the sailboat for rudder and sheeting control cause noise that is propagated to the keel. This affects the quality of the recordings, and makes the subsequent analysis more time-consuming. The waves at the surface also contribute noise, so being able to submerge the hydrophone further is an advantage. Therefore, the feasibility and limits of towing a submerged cable with a small autonomous sailboat is investigated. These are the central topics of the current paper.

Models for the cable as well as for the sailboat are described and simulations illustrated. Also, experiments using a boat similar to the planned platform towing a cable with a pressure sensor are presented. Data from these tests are compared to simulations. The use of the models for controller design as well as the ability of the models to predict the depth of the cable is evaluated.

2. Cable Modelling

There are several possibilities for modelling the cable. In the present study, two options are considered:

1. Treating the cable as a stiff pendulum with a lumped mass.
2. Treating the cable as several connected, stiff, rods.

With partial differential equations to model the cable and finite element methods for numerical analysis, more detailed solutions can clearly be obtained. However, the added complexity does not seem motivated in light of the results of the present study. The model for the cable is added to the modified sailboat model in order to study the behaviour of the overall system.

2.1. Simple Pendulum

If the cable is taken as a simple pendulum (lumped mass) of mass m and length l when the boat is towed at a constant speed and constant heading, the equilibrium state of the pendulum can be studied.

Fig.1: Representation of cable as a simple pendulum

\vec{F}_g is the gravitational force and \vec{F}_l represents the Archimedes principle, \vec{F}_d is the force of drag, i.e., resistance due to the fluid and \vec{T} is the force of the base on the cable. \vec{v}_c is the speed of the base, i.e., the boat, and $(m; l)$ is the mass and length of the pendulum. If the system is at equilibrium then the speed of the cable is the same as the speed of the base.

$$\vec{0} = \vec{T} + \vec{F}_d + \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_l \quad (1)$$

Furthermore

$$\vec{F}_d = -C_D(2rl)\rho \frac{|v_c|}{2} \vec{v}_c \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{F}_g = m\vec{g} \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{F}_l = -\rho\pi r^2 l \vec{g} \quad (4)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient, ρ is the density of the fluid, g is the gravitational acceleration and r is the radius of the cable.

If Eq. (1) is projected on \vec{u}_θ , \vec{T} can be eliminated and

$$\vec{0} = (mg - \rho\pi r^2 g) \sin(\theta) - C_D(2rl)\rho \frac{v_c^2}{2} \cos(\theta) \quad (5)$$

is obtained. Thus, the angle θ can be found if $m - \rho\pi r^2 > 0$, i.e., the cable has a higher density than the surrounding fluid,

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{C_D l 2r \rho}{2g(m - \rho\pi r^2)} v_c^2\right) \quad (6)$$

With this formula the depth of the end of the pendulum can easily be computed as a function of the speed of the boat and for different parametric values. In Fig.2, a varying length of the cable is considered and in Fig.3 a varying linear mass.

Fig.2: Depth as a function of boat speed depending on the length of the cable

Fig.3: Depth as a function of boat speed depending on linear mass of the cable

2.2. Connected Rods

The present model is developed based on *Johansen (2007)*. Within this approach, the rods are modelled by orientation and centre of gravity. Thus, different forces can be applied to the cable and fluid friction is included in the current paper. A rod can be characterized by two vectors, Fig.4.

Fig.4: Representation of r and b

$$r = \begin{bmatrix} r_x \\ r_y \\ r_z \end{bmatrix} \text{ is the center of gravity} \quad (7)$$

$$b = \begin{bmatrix} b_x \\ b_y \\ b_z \end{bmatrix} \text{ is the vector for the rod orientation} \quad (8)$$

The forces acting on the cable are applied at the end of each rod. For instance, the force of gravity is split in two forces acting on each side of the bar. This gives the basic model:

$$\ddot{r} = \frac{1}{m} (f_a + f_c) \quad (9)$$

$$\ddot{b} = \frac{6}{m} (f_a + f_c) \cdot \frac{b}{L^2} \left(\frac{6}{m} b^T (f_a + f_c) + \dot{b}^T \dot{b} \right) \quad (10)$$

where a and c are the extremities of the bar, f_x is the force applied at point X and L is the length of the rod.

In addition, the model uses the Baumgarte stabilization constraint, *Baumgarte (1972)*, to meet the

physical constraint on the bar, length and position of possible fixed points. The stabilization technique depends on some design parameters in a variable-step solver. Changing coefficients can improve the simulation at the cost of computational effort.

Johansen proposes three scenarios for the use of this model, a free cable, a fixed-free scenario where one end of the cable is attached to a point and a fixed-fixed scenario where both ends are attached to points. In our case, the cable is fixed-free with the boat as attachment point.

The external forces acting on each of the rods of the cable model are the gravitational force (\vec{F}_g), the force of drag (\vec{F}_d) and the Archimedes principle (\vec{F}_l). Each rod is further assumed to be a cylinder. For rod n the model thus becomes

$$\vec{F}_g = m\vec{g} \quad (11)$$

$$F_{d|n,a,x} = -C_D r \rho \int_0^{L/2} v_{a,x}(l)^2 \frac{2l}{L} dl \quad (12)$$

$$\vec{v}_a(l) = \vec{r}_n - \frac{2l}{L} \vec{b}_n \times \frac{\vec{b}_n}{L} \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{v}_c(l) = \vec{r}_n + \frac{2l}{L} \vec{b}_n \times \frac{\vec{b}_n}{L} \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{F}_l = -\rho \pi L r^2 \vec{g} \quad (15)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient for a cylinder, ρ the density of the fluid, r the radius of the cable and L the length of the rod.

The factor $\frac{2l}{L}$ in the integral part is there to compensate the lever effect when the force F_d is applied to the end of the rod. Fig.5 illustrates the depth of the end of the cable at steady-state as a function of the speed of the boat. As the figure illustrates, the cable will not be sufficiently submerged unless the speed is severely limited.

At steady-state, the sum of forces will follow the equation

$$\vec{0} = \vec{F}_{c,b} + \vec{F}_d + \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_l \quad (16)$$

Where $\vec{F}_{c,b}$ is the force of the cable on the boat. This force as a function of speed is illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** The vertical impact will be a constant and the horizontal will decrease following a square law resulting from F_d .

Fig.5: Depth of the cable at steady-state as a function of speed

Fig.6: Force of the cable on the boat at steady-state as a function of speed

Fig.7 illustrates the force of the cable on the boat at steady-state as a function of the linear mass of the cable. In this case, the horizontal force is constant since the mass does not appear in the horizontal part of Eq. (16). The vertical force depends linearly on the mass. Changing the linear mass or the mass of the last rod affect the final angle of the cable as illustrated in Fig.8.

Fig.7: Force of cable on boat as a function of linear mass of the cable at constant speed

Fig.8: Depth of the cable as a function of linear mass at constant speed

Fig.9: Error in length of the rods during a simulation

As explained earlier, the model includes a tolerance to errors affected by parameters chosen for the Baumgarte stabilization technique. The errors that remain are illustrated in Fig.9. The errors can be reduced by changing coefficients of the Baumgarte stabilization. This, however, will in turn increase the computation time when using a variable-step solver. As the figure illustrates, the maximum error in length is less than one centimetre for a cable of 16 m modelled with four rods, each with a length of 4 m. For the current study the remaining errors are deemed sufficiently small. However, if the start of the simulation is very sudden, simulations may diverge. To see simulations: Fixed cable video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T7DRGq3E5x8> or Moving cable with a constant speed video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T7DRGq3E5x8>

For successful simulations, some other practical considerations are also necessary. If a fixed-step size integration method is used, e.g., fourth-order Runge-Kutta, the step size needs to be approximately 10^{-3} for convergence. Even at this step size, simulations can diverge for large accelerations. With a variable step-size, e.g., MATLAB's ODE45, the overall result will be more accurate but instead the computation time can become unreasonable with more than one second needed to compute one second of the simulations on a powerful laptop.

3. Connecting to the model of the sailboat

3.1. Model of the sailboat

The model of the sailboat considered in the study is from *Melin et al (2016)*, which in turn is a modified version of the model in *Le Bars and Jaulin (2013)*. In this model, the state of the boat is represented by x and y for the position, v for the linear speed, θ for the heading and ω for the angular speed. The model is non-holonomic, i.e., the boat will always go in the direction θ (minus the wind drift) and therefore the speed v is defined in the frame of the boat. The controllable inputs are $[\delta_s, \delta_r]$, where δ_r is the rudder angle and δ_s is the angle of the sail, which in turn is (approximately) proportional to the sheet length. Some of the states are illustrated in Fig.10.

Fig.10: States and inputs δ_s and δ_r and representation of true wind and apparent wind

The state-space formulation of the model is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{v} \\ \dot{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v \cos(\theta) + p_1 a_{tw} \cos(\psi_{tw}) \\ v \sin(\theta) + p_1 a_{tw} \sin(\psi_{tw}) \\ \omega \\ (g_s \sin(\delta_s) - g_r p_{11} \sin(\delta_r) - p_2 v^2) / p_9 \\ [(g_s (p_6 - p_7 \cos(\delta_s)) - g_r p_8 \cos(\delta_r) - p_3 \omega v) / p_{10}] \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

where g_s and g_r are the forces on the sail and on the rudder

$$g_s = p_4 a_{aw} \sin(\delta_s - \psi_{aw}) \quad (18)$$

$$g_r = p_5 v^2 \sin(\delta_r) \quad (19)$$

The force on the sail depends on the apparent wind, as shown in Fig.10.

$$\mathbf{W}_{c,aw} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{tw} \cos(\psi_{tw} - \theta) - v \\ a_{tw} \sin(\psi_{tw} - \theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_{p,aw} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{aw} \\ \psi_{aw} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |\mathbf{W}_{c,aw}| \\ \text{angle}(\mathbf{W}_{c,aw}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where a_{tw} is the true wind speed and ψ_{tw} its direction in the earth frame. a_{aw} is the apparent wind speed and ψ_{aw} the direction of the apparent wind, and these are in boat frame.

The parameters used in the present model are provided in Table 1. This model is utilized for development and evaluation of strategies for cable towing as well as for control algorithms. For the present study, the model is deemed sufficient, but naturally further refinements might be necessary in future work. The approach of control relevant modelling, however, has also proven successful in earlier studies, see, e.g., *Melin et al (2016)* and *Le Bars and Jaulin (2013)*.

Table 1: Used parameters

p1	drift coefficient	-
p2	tangential friction	kgs^{-1}
p3	angular friction	kgm
p4	sail lift	kgs^{-1}
p5	rudder lift	kgs^{-1}
p6	distance to sail	m
p7	distance to mast	m
p8	distance to rudder	m
p9	mass of boat	kg
p10	moment of inertia	kgm^2
p11	rudder break coefficient	-

3.2. Connecting the cable force

The approach of the current paper is a modified version of the approach presented in *Jaulin and Le Bars (2015)*. Towing a cable changes the behaviour of the boat and correspondingly the model must be modified. This is done by considering the forces from the cable on the boat.

3.2.1. Modifying the sailboat model

3.2.1.1. Adding drift

In order to take the effect of towing a cable into consideration, the force of the cable on the boat must be included in the model. Let α_c denote the direction of the force of the cable on the boat in earth frame, f_c the norm, \vec{v}_c the impact on the boat's movement in x, y coordinates and α_v is the direction of this drift. Then the model can be written

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{v} \\ v_{c,x} \\ v_{c,y} \\ \dot{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v \cos(\theta) + v_{c,x} + p_1 a_{tw} \cos(\psi_{tw}) \\ v \sin(\theta) + v_{c,y} + p_1 a_{tw} \sin(\psi_{tw}) \\ \omega \\ (g_s \sin(\delta_s) - g_r p_{11} \sin(\delta_r) + g_c \cos(\alpha_c - \theta) - p_2 v^2)/p_9 \\ (-(p_2 + p_{12} \sin^2(\alpha_v - \theta))(v_{c,x}|v_{c,x}|) + g_c \sin(\alpha_c - \theta) \cos(\theta + \pi/2))/p_9 \\ (-(p_2 + p_{12} \sin^2(\alpha_v - \theta))(v_{c,y}|v_{c,y}|) + g_c \sin(\alpha_c - \theta) \sin(\theta + \pi/2))/p_9 \\ (g_s(p_6 - p_7 \cos(\delta_s)) - g_r p_8 \cos(\delta_r) - p_3 \omega v)/p_{10} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

In this model, a friction coefficient due to the cable can be defined as

$$c_f = p_2 + p_{12} \sin^2(\alpha_v - \theta) \quad (23)$$

When $\alpha_v = \theta \pmod{\pi}$ the direction of the boat is the same as that of the drift and in this case c_f is equal to the tangential friction p_2 . But when $\alpha_v - \theta = \pm \pi/2$ the friction created by the drift is orthogonal to the boat and c_f is maximal.

In addition to the drift, the cable also affects the speed v of the boat. The effect of the cable is distributed between \dot{v} and v_c depending on the difference $\alpha_c - \theta$.

3.2.1.2. Changing application point of the force from the cable

The connecting point of the force from the cable may not be at the centre of inertia of the boat. In such cases, towing a cable will affect the angular acceleration. The angular acceleration formula is changed to the following when the cable is positioned on the median of the boat

$$\dot{\omega} = (g_s(p_6 - p_7 \cos(\delta_s)) - g_r p_8 \cos(\delta_r) - p_3 \omega v - p_{13} g_c \sin(\alpha_c - \theta))/p_{10} \quad (24)$$

In this model, $p_{13} g_c \sin(\alpha_c - \theta)$ is the effect of the cable on the angular acceleration. This implies that, perhaps as expected, the cable often will add to the rotational inertia of the boat. A simulation of the boat towing a cable can be seen on <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1nrbdikXr8A>.

In the simulation, the panel to the left illustrates the cable in 3-D; the middle panel shows the boat from a bird's eye view with the force from the cable and wind direction included; the right panel shows the x - (blue), y - (green) and z - (red, depth) coordinates of the end of the cable in earth-frame.

3.2.2. Simulation results

For comparison, the path taken by a boat towing a cable and the path taken by a boat without a cable is illustrated in Fig.11.

For both cases, the boat is controlled by the same control algorithm, taken from *Le Bars and Jaulin (2013)*. In the figure, it can be seen that the boat with a cable is has a longer response time and is less controllable in a straight line. Indeed, at the start of the simulation, the boat without cable follows the line accurately while the boat with cable deviates.

The boat with the cable is also slower, i.e., the time taken by the boat with the cable to reach the final point is longer than that of the boat without a cable. Also, it might appear as if the boat with a cable is more efficient when turning, but this can be explained by the slower speed. Whether this results in significant differences in practice is studied next.

Fig.11: Path taken by the boat with or without cable

4. Evaluating the model

4.1. Setup for evaluation

For the model validation, two specific goals are considered. Firstly, can the model for towing the cable with the sailboat be used for designing adequate controllers? Secondly, can the simulations predict the actual depth of the cable?

4.1.1. Validation of the model for controller design

The test procedure for evaluating the model against actual experiments can be summarized by the following steps:

- A cable with a linear mass of 130 g/m is connected to the hull of the boat.
- A pressure sensor is attached to the cable. Due to the actual pressure sensor used, the length of the cable is limited to 6 meters and the depth measurements to approximately 3 meters.
- For the tests, the boat has to reach multiple waypoints along a path while measurements are recorded. Measurements from the pressure sensor are included when the cable is attached.
- The experiment is repeated without cable.

Furthermore, the experiments can be compared to simulations. Simulations and experiments are illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**. In the figures, the red circles indicate waypoints. A waypoint is considered reached when the boat is within the red circles, i.e., the boat passes within a certain distance from the waypoint. The blue lines are simulations and the red lines are from actual experiments. The same control algorithm is used for all cases, i.e., simulations and experiments with and without cable. As can be seen from the figures, the controller works well for both cases. Also, simulations and experiments are comparable especially in the light of the simplifications made in the model, e.g., no roll is considered, and the significant disturbances present in real experiments, e.g., waves, varying wind speed and direction.

For a more detailed comparison, the path between waypoints 4 and 7 is considered since the boat has approximately the same heading in both experiments for this part of the path. In Fig.14 speed and heading of the boat and speed and direction of the wind are illustrated for the experiments with and without cable. In the figure, values at each respective waypoint n is the mean value between waypoints n and $n + 1$.

Fig.12: Towing a cable: Waypoints (red circles), path taken in simulations (blue) and in real experiment (red)

Fig.13: Same as in Fig.12 but without cable

At waypoint 4 the speed of the boat without cable is greater than the speed of the boat with cable as could be expected. However, the wind speed is also larger for the test without cable so based on this test it cannot be deduced that the cable slows the boat down. Indeed, at waypoints 5 and 6 the situation is surprising as the speed of the boat with cable is faster even though the wind speed is smaller. In summary, the paths taken by the boats during simulations are similar and observed differences in practice can be explained by variations in wind. Hence, it appears as if robustness analysis of the closed-loop system will include the effect of a, relatively light, cable on the boat. In other words, it seems that a model of the boat only is sufficient for the design and evaluation of control systems.

Fig.14: Comparison of some significant values between waypoints for the test.

4.1.2. Validation of model for cable depth prediction

In addition to control design, the model of the cable and boat is also used to predict the depth of the towed cable. For an evaluation of the ability of the model to capture this feature, the depth recorded with the pressure sensor is compared to the depth of simulations that use speed and position data from the actual experiment. To compare the experiment of the boat to a simulation with a connected cable, the GPS position data from the run is filtered and used in simulations. In the cable simulations the positions retrieved from the test sailing are used as fixed points of the cable.

Fig.15: Comparison between depth of cable at the pressure sensor level in simulation and real test

Fig.16: Comparison of depth of cable at the pressure sensor level as a function of speed between simulation and real test

Error! Reference source not found. shows three profiles of depth – measured depth (green), depth as simulated with connected rods (red) and depth for a pendulum that follows Eq. (6) (blue). The model using connected rods better describes the measurements than the pendulum. The same is also true for depth measured as a function of speed. If a mean offset is used as a quality measure, it can be noted that the model using connected rods has a mean offset of 34 cm, while the pendulum model has a mean offset of 43 cm. The significant computational advantage of the simple pendulum model thus makes it a good candidate for predicting cable depth.

5. Conclusions

5.1. Some practical lessons learned

Based on experiments with the sailboat, some practical notes have been made:

- The position of the cable just behind the keel is advantageous as the momentum is almost zero, and the effect on the angular velocity is minimal
- The cable does not seem to interfere with rudder movement.
- With little wind and a long cable the boat can get stuck.

5.2. Ensuring sufficient depth of the cable

Adding weight to the cable will increase the depth of the hydrophone at a specific speed. Other alternatives are:

- Limit the speed of the boat by sheet control or by increasing the drag of the boat.
- Mechanical measures for ensuring sufficient submersion of the cable. Such methods could for instance be attachment of controllable wing profiles that can be adjusted to increase the downward force on the cable.

5.3. Summary

Simulations and real experiments have verified that an autonomous sailboat is a viable platform for collecting marine measurements by towing a cable. Also, there does not seem to be any need to modify the control system compared to a boat without a cable: The robustness of the used control system has been shown to handle a cable of length 6-10 m with no apparent loss of performance. Furthermore, the models presented can be used for designing closed-loop systems as well as for predicting the depth of the cable.

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3D-Printing and the Maritime Construction Sector

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Abstract

This paper presents the current status of additive manufacturing, also known as 3D-printing, and its relevance for the maritime construction sector. This technology radically changes supply chains, product designs and production in comparable industries, thanks to benefits such as on-demand localized production and form freedom. However, cost-effectiveness, gaps in knowledge, high technology variance and lack of standardization limit adaptation within the maritime construction sector. Especially for large scale additive manufacturing research gaps exist in the structural area. Models for analysis of design and production are also needed to clarify the business case.

1. Introduction

3D printing, known industrially as Additive Manufacturing (AM) has rapidly revolutionized production processes and products within a great range of industries in the last few years. This is caused by specific added values such as weight reduction, free complexity, localized production and many more which is possible because of the AM process. AM is defined as the ‘process of joining materials to make parts from 3D model data, usually layer upon layer, as opposed to subtractive manufacturing and formative manufacturing methodologies.’, *ISO/ASTM (2015)*. Examples of these are drilling, CNC milling, bending, etc. which are common within the maritime construction sector. The differences between AM and the traditionally used subtractive manufacturing technologies are schematically shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Subtractive and additive manufacturing.

Although the usage of the technology is recent, the first machines and processes were developed in 1980's and the 1990's. Wohlers, a consultancy active for over 30 years with AM, predicted that the global AM market will grow to \$10 billion in 2021, *Wohlers (2014)*. 60% of the total market consists of direct parts and services, and 40% is materials and machines, *Mitchell (2012)*. A survey was also held by Wohlers among manufacturers of printers in 2014 to determine the market shares for printer sales of industrial sectors. The maritime sector falls under the category "other" which is less than 5%, while aerospace has a market share of 12%.

Next to that, AM has only reached the plateau of productivity in prototyping, according to the hype cycle analysis of Gartner. Gartner predicts that Industrial AM will reach this level of productivity in five to ten years. To reach that plateau of productivity, machines need to improve and research has to be performed. Predictions that the overall feasibility of AM will increase in the future have been

made, *Berger (2013)*. This is based this on the fact that current trends for the build rates, powder prices, labour costs and chamber volumes are beneficial for production feasibility. However, no decline in machine prices is observed for now.

All aspects mentioned above leave the impression that there is a growth potential for AM within the maritime construction sector (MCS). For that reason a basic explorative study has been performed with the goal to indicate areas of potential added value of AM within the MCS, and to assess what further research is necessary. The MCS is defined as all work related to shipbuilding, on and offshore building, repair and the required supporting eco-system for that work, thereby including suppliers. The paper covers the fundamentals of AM including terminology, opportunities and challenges and shows the relevance of this with examples. This is followed by showing the match between maritime and AM by analysing maritime design processes and supply chains. Then, the current applications of AM in the MCS are shown, followed by the research gaps and conclusions.

2. Additive Manufacturing Fundamentals

This chapter covers the fundamentals of Additive Manufacturing (AM) with examples of current applications. AM spans multiple process categories. These categories are a recent development and up to 2015 the industry lacked these structured groupings. Therefore, licensed names were coupled to processes, making it hard to distinguish what process was used and which companies could be compared. The *ISO/ASTM (2015) 52900-15* standard groups AM in seven groups. The licensed or historical processes are presented together with the ISO standard they correspond with in Table I. The general capacities and characteristics of the different processes are qualitatively described, to clarify specific AM technology compatibility within the MCS later on.

Table I: Additive manufacturing process type overview with sub-processes, terms from *ISO (2015) 52900-15* standard, adapted from *DNV-GL (2014)*

AM Process Characteristic	Powder Bed fusion	Directed Energy Deposition	Materials Extrusion	Materials Jetting	Binder Jetting	Sheet Lamination	Vat Photopolymerization
Metal	X	X			X	X	
Plastic	X		X	X	X	X	X
Composite	X	X			X		
Others		Ceramic		Wax, Photopolymer	Sand, Ceramic	Paper	Resin, Liquid photopolymer
Durability	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Low
Build Speed	Low	Medium-High	Medium	Medium	High	High	Medium
Cost	High	Medium-High	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
Post-process	Medium	High	Low	Low	Medium	High	No
Detail Precision	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Surface Roughness	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Low
Other	-	Wide performance variety	-	-	-	No heat effects	-
Licensed	EBM,	LMD-w,	FDM,	Inkjet,	3DP,	LOM,	SLA, SL,

or historical terms	SLM, SHS, SLS, DMLS, DMP, SPS, Laser Cusing	EBAM, EBDM, EBF, DMD, LENS, LBMD, DLF, LFF, LC, CMB, IFF, WAAM	FFF, FLM, PJP, Robocasting	Polyjet, MJM, Aerosoljet Thermojet DOD, DLP	LPS, DSPC	UAM, UC	Optical Fabrication, Photo-Solidification, Solid Free-From Fabrication, Solid imaging, Resin Printing, MPSL, DLP, FTI
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Important to note, the qualitative characteristic description contains a significant variety between the technologies within one category.

2.1 Opportunities and Challenges

AM has many opportunities and challenges that require introduction before using this technology. The opportunities can be split into five groups, which can then be divided between a product or supply chain opportunity, *Innovation Quarter (2016)*. This grouping is used to give an overview of the advantages of AM according to different sources. Table II shows the wide variety of added value, but also the difficulty to grasp the added value as it often is a combination of several aspects. A simplistic methodology is still lacking to grasp the overall gain and cost effectiveness, especially considering the indirect aspects within the supply chain and subjective aspects such as aesthetics.

Table II: Opportunities of additive manufacturing according to different sources¹⁻⁵

	Product	Clarification	Supply chain	Clarification
Lower costs	- Less material ⁴ - No tooling or cheaper tooling ^{1,2}	Material is only added where needed instead of subtracted. For tooling/ moulding see Fig.3.	- Less transportation ^{1,3} - Less warehousing ¹	Only base material is needed from which all desired components can be made see Fig.4.
Better Design	- Complexity for free ^{1,4} - Different materials or multimaterial ^{1,3} - Light weight ^{1,3} - Optimized/ integrated functionality ^{2,3,4,5} - Part consolidation ¹	The process operates independent of complexity, thereby facilitating light weight structures, combination of several parts in one, etc. See Fig.2,3,5,6.	- Process flexibility or agility ²	All shapes can be made with one machine. See Fig.2.
Custom-isation	- Aesthetics ¹ - Quick change of design ² - Reverse engineering ⁴	With complexity for free, aesthetics does not directly require extra work, as does a change of design.		

¹ *Innovation Quarter (2016)*

² *Mellor (2014)*

Sustain-ability	- Less waste ^{1,3} - Less fuel consumption ¹	Material and weight reduction result in less waste and fuel consumption. See Fig.4,5,6.	- Shorter supply chain ^{1,2,3}	Less transportation thanks to local production result in reduction of transport emissions see Fig.4.
Busi-ness models	- Prototyping ¹ - Small series ^{1,2,3} - Reduction of operations ⁴	Complex to produce requiring many operations, low quantity products do not increase in cost as a result of process. See Fig.3,6.	- Production on location ^{1,3,5} - Lead time reduction ^{3,4,5} - Reduction of import/export cost ⁵ - Supplier dependency risk reduction ⁵	Localized production bypasses customs, lead times are reduced and thereby downtime cost. Suppliers are no longer sole producer of a specific component. See Fig.4.

The combination of advantages result in the expectation that there is potential for this technology within the MCS, however there are several significant challenges. Challenges of AM can be split into technology and environmental challenges. These are less well documented compared to the opportunities. The categories can be seen in Table III and are adapted from the strategic research agenda, *RM-Platform (2014)*.

Table III: Challenges of additive manufacturing.

AM Technology Challenges	Clarification
Economies of scale and overall cost effectiveness	AM costs do not decrease with increasing production, also overall cost is still relatively high compared to classical production methods.
Material integrity	Since AM parts are build up in layers, material properties vary in along the direction perpendicular to the layers causing anisotropy. Also, the effects of fatigue are not well known.
Surface finish	Layers can cause rough surface or step effect.
Post-processing	To reach required material properties and surface finish, heat treatment or machining may be necessary.
Speed-accuracy trade-off	There is always a reverse correlation between speed and accuracy, <i>Frazier (2014)</i> .
Safety	Melting of plastic and metal powder brings safety issues, <i>LR (2016)</i>
AM Environment, Standards and Training Challenges	Clarification
Regulation	Class society regulation is not yet available, first goal based steps are made, <i>LR (2016)</i>
Standards	Machinery is not yet standardized, so every machine has to be certified independently.
Training and education	There is little qualified staff available.
Intellectual property (IP)	E.g. who owns the IP rights, when components are reverse engineered?

³ *RAE (2013)*

⁴ *LR (2016)*

⁵ *Wohlers (2015)*

There is a set of technological challenges for AM that are inherent to the process. AM does not benefit from economies of scale, since the costs per product do not decrease with increasing numbers. This makes it more suited for one-offs or small series than mass production. The material integrity, which has a connection with surface finish and post-processing is also a challenge; since AM uses layers to build up the material, properties vary along the direction perpendicular to the layers. The layers also result in a surface alike stairs in this direction. These two effect usually result in the need for post-processing in the form of heat treatment and/or machining. AM will always be a trade-off between speed and accuracy and will always be built up in layers with the resulting effects. However, there is still a lot of research to be done on these subjects to be able to quantify and reduce these challenges.

The second set of challenges result from the fact that AM is a relatively new technology and can be (partially) considered temporary. To rise to these challenges, close collaboration of maritime construction sector, AM machine manufacturers and regulatory bodies is required. Only then can new regulations be made on which new research and cases can be based. Standards can follow from these rules and with standards, training becomes relevant as experience is valid over time. Intellectual property also requires close cooperation between engineering and production as well as new laws for property and liability. On top of that, to enable this collaboration and standardisation, the technological challenges need to be clear.

2.2 Usages

The usage of AM consists of three types, *ISO/ASTM (2015)*. Rapid Prototyping (RP), Rapid Tooling (RT), and Rapid Manufacturing (RM). The difference between these and their application is shown in sections 2.2.1 through 2.2.3. Several examples are given of the added value of AM of these types from other industries before that potential will be translated towards the maritime construction sector.

2.2.1 Rapid Prototyping

Rapid prototyping is the application of AM for reduced production time (Rapid) of prototypes. It was the first use of AM, as prototypes are often limited in their functionality and therefore have fewer demands on strength or finish. The design freedom of AM resulted not only in faster, but also allowed more complex prototypes. The use of prototyping is the verification of the part and to provide visual support. For example, features that do not work in practice end up in the product design. A prototype can help to identify these errors in a design stage at relative low costs. Fig.2 shows an example from the medical industry clarifying the added value of RP. In the MCS, the application of rapid prototyping is similar to that in other industries. "Prototypes" can refer to the creation of models for towing tank tests, but also marketing tools. Models of ships are now often produced for clients to visualize the vessel, resulting in a clearer picture for the client.

<p data-bbox="188 1870 662 2004">Fig.2: Medical prototyping, http://mcortechtechnologies.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/UCL-CS-19012013_high.pdf, accessed 15-9-'16.</p>	<p data-bbox="865 1545 1388 1579">Added value AM, Product & Supply Chain:</p> <ul data-bbox="865 1579 1396 1736" style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexity for free (as build from 3D scan) - Small series (unique objects without extra cost) - Production on location (short lead time) <p data-bbox="865 1747 965 1780">Results:</p> <ul data-bbox="865 1780 1396 1937" style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual support and trial object, to gain better understanding of person specific complexities - One hour reduction of effective operation time.
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2.2.2 Rapid Tooling & Prototype Tooling

Rapid tooling and prototype tooling in AM focus on the production of products or tools that facilitate an operation or a process. The important difference is that the tools itself generally do not have any strict quality demands, however the product for which the tool will be used does. An example is the casting process which is certified, together with the cast end product. But whether the mould is printed or manufactured in the classical manner does not matter for certification. Especially with casting, in which mould production can be very time and cost consuming, AM can result in significant benefits, of which an example is shown in Fig.3. Depending on the type of process and the location, it can be highly effective to produce the required tool by AM.

	<p>Added Value AM, Product:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexity for free (e.g. internal flows pipes for cooling) - Optimized functions (better cooling) - Small series (moulds are for one time use only)
<p>Fig.3: Rapid tooling applied on a sand mould, http://www.stratasys.com/solutions/additive-manufacturing/tooling/~media/E1A77FC1EFBB4DC69006DF2D38E2852A.ashx, accessed 15-9-'16.</p>	<p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost reduction of 50-70 percent within the sand casting process - Lead time reduction of 30-70 percent

	<p>Added Value AM, Supply Chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production on location - Lead time reduction - Less transportation
<p>Fig.4: Rapid tooling applied in space, ISS 3D printer, http://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/station/research/experiments/1115.html, accessed 15-9-'16.</p>	<p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost reduction - Reduce downtime - Increase agility (flexibility towards problem solving)

Another example is production of tools in remote location. An example can be seen in Fig.4. The International Space Station has a 3D printer on board to be able to make custom tools at any time without sending them from earth. In maritime construction sector, moulds are used often by suppliers for parts such as propellers. Semi-series items or structural parts, like window frames in yachts, which might be profitable to produce with rapid tooling moulds as well. This would require the additional equipment to cast metal to be available in a yard as well, which is rarely the case. Therefore this usage is most suitable for suppliers.

2.2.3 Rapid Manufacturing

Rapid manufacturing (RM), also called digital direct manufacturing, is the application of producing parts directly from CAD data. ISO uses the more general term of AM for the production of parts with AM machines. In this paper, RM is used as an application type of AM for the production of parts, as suggested by *Gibson (2010)*. As parts are currently usually built using simple geometries to ensure

manufacturing is possible, rapid prototyping enables more possibilities due to more design freedom. This can add value to parts in weight reduction, increased efficiency, part consolidation or localized production, as can be seen in Fig.5 and Fig.6.

<p>Fig.5: C-919 airplane fuselage (5,2m²), http://www.3ders.org/articles/20140207-china-developing-world-largest-3d-printer--prints-6m-metal-parts-in-one-piece.html, accessed 15-9-'16.</p>	<p>Added Value AM, Product:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Light weight - Less material
	<p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 14x faster production - 10x cheaper production

<p>Fig.6: Fuel nozzle, <i>Madlinger (2014)</i>.</p>	<p>Added Value AM, Supply chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Light weight - Optimized functions - Complexity for free
	<p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 25% lighter - 5x more durable - 2x less material waste

Figs.5 and 6 show the optimization of a constructional critical component and an engine critical component. A broad range of equally critical components can be found within the maritime construction sector. However the primary added value for these components is weight reduction and that added value is of much less importance for the maritime construction sector due to the sectors nature than in aerospace causing a significant gap within the overall feasibility.

2.3 Overview

Depending on the application, different types of benefits occur. This results in cost effectiveness of AM either with respect to the product or the supply chain. However there is a difference in the product quality requirements depending on the criticality of the application. ISO has developed a classification of criticality of the parts to clarify the necessary testing, of which the definition is given in the first row of Table IV, *ISO/ASTM (2015)*. This is matched in generic sense with the criticality of usage for RP, RT and RM at the writers' discretion.

Table IV: Generalized criticality of RP, RT and RM parts with ISO definitions at the writers' discretion

Criticality \ Usage	Low: for design or prototyping	Medium: functional parts that are non-safety critical	High: highly engineered safety critical parts
Rapid Prototyping	X		
Rapid Tooling	X	X	X
Rapid Manufacturing		X	X

3. AM in Maritime Construction Sector

First, a comparison between the needs of the sector and what AM can offer is made, followed by an analysis of the effect of the AM product design and supply chain.

3.1 Additive Manufacturing Applicability in Maritime Construction Sector

The maritime construction sector handles relatively large and crude components compared to for instance aviation and automotive sectors. These components need to be compatible with current MCS related components and strong enough to endure the maritime loading cycles, *Strickland (2016)*. Based on the use in MCS, which requests high amounts of material, large scale production of up to 5x5x5 m for complete sections, and lesser importance of roughness.

These criteria can be translated to the following requirement: large parts (>0.5m), a deposition rate of several kilograms per hour and high durability related to the use for RM. Based on these criteria and Table I, the three most relevant AM processes for the maritime industry are determined. These are Direct Energy Deposition (DED), Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) and Material Extrusion (ME), *DNV-GL (2014)*. Especially DED technology is supported for large scale metal applications, *Frazier (2014)*, *ZHAI (2012)*.

DED uses an external focused thermal energy such as a laser or electron beam to fuse material that is deposited simultaneously. PBF uses an external energy source as well, but the material is deposited before adding energy in a thin layer called the powder bed, this bed is lowered and a new layer is added multiple times. Material extrusion uses internal energy from a heating element to deposit molten material from a nozzle. More information on these processes can be found in the ISO standard, the book of Gibson or Wohlers report, *ISO (2014)*, *Gibson (2010)*, *Wohlers (2014)*.

Table V shows an adaptation of an overview of the machines available on the industrial market, *Wohlers (2014)*. Only the largest machines of the three processes previously described are included in this overview. For the sake of simplicity three parameters are shown, being building envelope (LxBxH), material type and process to give an indication for the compatibility with the maritime sector.

Table V: Additive manufacturing capacities, material categories are Metal (M) or Polymer (P), *Wohlers (2014)*

Company	Model	Process	L(mm)	B(mm)	H(mm)	Material category (M,P)	Machinery Cost (k\$)
Sciaky	VX.4-300 x108x132	DED	6300	1372	1473	M	5000
CRAN-FIELD	WAAM	DED	5000	5000	5000	M	100
DMG Mori	Lasertec 65	DED/ Milling	735	650	560	M	Unknown
Concept laser	X line 2000R	PBF	800	400	500	M	1575
Stratasys	Fortus 900mc	Extru- sion	914	610	914	P	400
EU-project	Borealis	Hybrid	4500	2500	1000	M	Unknown

Focusing on the basic requirements, there is common ground between AM and the MCS components. Although the focus of this paper covers mostly the production and supply chain effects, an indication in cost difference is of importance. General consensus on shipbuilding metal construction work cost for simplistic inland ships is 2.5 [€/kg], *Hekkenberg (2014)*. PBF, one of the more expensive AM

processes is estimated at several hundred euros per kg, *Berger (2013)*. To overcome this difference, a clear AM technology specific business case is needed. However, opportunities such as weight reduction or production on location require careful consideration, therefore this business case is not as clear as in other industries.

3.2 Designing with Additive Manufacturing

The effect of AM for design is considered on different levels of detail to see where the current processes might change. First, system engineering is considered, followed by ship design and finally mechanical design.

System engineering is often approached by using the V-model, as shown in the TU Delft course, *Hopman (2015)*. This model generally considers the mission, function, systems and implementation followed by the feedback loops on each level. Considering system engineering for ships, the content of these might change on system and component level, but the process will remain the same. On component level for instance, the fuel nozzle from Fig.6 shows that a component can ensure better fulfilment of several function. Ship design is normally depicted as a spiral including steps such as general arrangement, stability and weight, *Evans (1959)*. The content of the steps of the ship design changes because of AM, but the process itself is not affected. An example from aircraft industry is the fuselage from Fig.5 in which the weight is reduced. The design problem can be described by the interaction between function, material, process and shape, *Ashby (2015)*. To make a shape, the material is subjected to a process, so it can fulfil its function. This interaction between function, material, shape and process can be visualised as seen in Fig.7. AM can change this interaction for the design if it is considered as one of the processes available for selection.

Fig.7: The central problem in mechanical design, interaction between function, material, process and shape, *Ashby (2015)*

In general, AM does not affect design processes itself, but the content. However, it can affect the performance of a component or system. Another opportunity is to combine multiple functions into one, meaning that AM should be kept in mind throughout all design processes. It was shown that AM potentially affects the design of components and systems. To realize this a better design is required; one of the benefits of AM. One of the most promising methods to facilitate this is the use of topology optimisation. Topology optimization is a mathematical approach that uses finite element methods and optimization algorithms to create a design using boundary conditions and a loads, such as can be seen in Fig.8. This method of designing generally results in organic shapes that would be hard to fabricate normally. Meaning they have to be simplified, reducing the gains from optimizing. Design freedom of AM makes it possible to reach more optimal design solutions. However, the benefits of optimizing designs is not quantitatively known so further research is needed in this area.

Fig.8: An example of topology optimization showing the design domain and the force and the resulting structure, *Laura Del Tin (2011)*

3.3 Supply chain

Three different supply chains are used as an example to clarify the effects of AM on the maritime construction sector. AM effectuates two major changes due to the AM production process and the possibility of localized production. Firstly the changes in the basic part or component production process, secondly there are the effects of localized production. Fig.9. shows those differences within the supply chain based on *Douglas and Gilbert (2014)*.

Within traditional manufacturing, material resources such as steel plates and welding wire have to be obtained. These resources are then to be actively manufactured into parts and components, via several types of machinery which have to be available. Finally, assembly can take place, *Hengst (1999)*. Compared to this is the AM process, in which independent of the process, the material resources are equal. The manufacturing and assembly are combined into one step providing the end product directly, given that there's always a certain amount of post-processing.

The effects of localized production can be clarified with the spare parts supply chain. When an essential component breaks down, replacement has to be performed a.s.a.p. as otherwise operation ability will be reduced or even stopped. For this reason spare parts are brought along or delivered if not on board. This implies possible spare parts inventory costs, delivery cost and lost revenue due to downtime. AM could provide increased spare parts flexibility without high inventory cost.

The ideal AM process used in Fig.9 is defined as zero-defect based upon the objectives of the Borealis project *Borealis (2016)*. Next to that it is assumed that the process is certified and that no testing is required for the specific parts, thereby utilizing the full potential of AM. In reality, complete implementation of AM is required before aforementioned process can be obtained. However, besides the technology and environment stated in Table II, the whole infrastructure for the use of AM has to be in place within the specific organization. This considers mainly the requirements to make use of this technology. There must be a business case, organisational readiness both on staff and structure, the supply chain for base material and knowledge considering actual operations such as design and quality control, *Mellor et al. (2014)*. These aspects have to be assessed organisation specific before implementation.

Fig.9: Traditional MCS process, AM related MCS process and local application of AM process, based on *Douglas and Gilbert (2014)*.

The processes shown above, in combination with Table II clarify that agility in problem solving can be obtained via AM. As within the maritime construction sector most projects are considered one-offs or small series production, significant benefits can be obtained in that respect.

4. Current Maritime Application

Given the advantages of Additive Manufacturing (AM), the proven benefits in other sectors and the expected effects within the maritime construction sector, as explained in Chapter 2 and 3, it is logical that the amount of initiatives for implementation are growing multi-fold. The current applications for AM within Maritime are divided into two fields for clarity. Firstly, the research activities, which are mostly focused on technology developed in a broader framework and less on valorisation. Secondly, the early adopters of the technology within the maritime sector.

4.1 Institutional Research

Due to the low technology readiness of AM fit for usage on large scale within the maritime construction sector several research institutions or departments have been initiated. These are mostly from a sector wide perspective including all relevant partners: users, regulatory bodies and technology providers, within the consortia to ensure the shortest development and implementation duration. The requirement for this was shown section 2.1. This principle of co-innovation reduces time and development cost significantly, *Beelaerts van Blokland et al. (2008)*.

- Port of Rotterdam Field lab: Started as an innovation programme to check if printing of maritime spare parts is possible, Port of Rotterdam was offered the “Field lab” status. The next steps are investing in its own WAAM 3D printer, to facilitate research in 3D printing in the Netherlands in a project called RAMLAB. The investment amounts to several million of euros, <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/ramlab/creative-power>, accessed 15-9-'16.
- Hyundai, Large Scale Key Parts: In July 2015 Hyundai Heavy Industries co. Ltd. (HHI) announced that they are following the governments focus on AM by opening an “economy innovation centre” in Ulsan. This centre aims to localize production for 165 key parts and “it is estimated that... will save Korean shipbuilders an average of nearly \$2 billion per year”, <http://www.3ders.org/articles/20150720-hyundai-heavy-industries-opens-up-3d-printing-shipbuilding-innovation-center.html>, accessed 15-9-'16.

- CSIC, Research Centre: China Shipbuilding Industry Corporation has been researching Powder Bed Fusing since 2014. The shipbuilding company's 705th Institute set up a team focussed on AM. After developing their own version of Powder Bed Fusion, they are now further expanding their research facilities in the area of AM materials in Kunming and a technology centre in Yunnan province, <http://www.seatrade-maritime.com/news/americas/chinas-breakthrough-in-3d-printing-for-shipbuilding.html>, accessed 15-9-'16.
- Singapore, Investment and Centre for 3D Printing: The government of Singapore will invest \$500 million over the course of five year in AM. The funding is part of the Future of Manufacturing programme. Nanyang Technology University has started a centre of excellence called Singapore Centre for 3D Printing. One of the key industries of this centre is Marine & Offshore, focussing on large joints, high aspect ratio structures and large scale repair. <http://www.3ders.org/articles/20130325-singapore-to-invest-500-million-in-3d-printing.html>, accessed 15-9-'16.

Next to the research facilities Joint Industry Programs (JIPs) are being started to further speed up the overall development. These JIPs are not specifically mentioned as there are many of which not all are clearly documented.

4.2 Early Adoption of Additive Manufacturing within the Maritime Construction Sector

Early adopters within the maritime construction sector have used AM technology with a higher level of readiness to apply within the maritime sector. These are mostly less critical components such as prototypes and tools.

4.2.1 Rapid Prototyping in Maritime Construction Sector

Rapid prototyping is relatively well adopted in the maritime industry. Multiple companies already use printers to create promotional models.

- Shell: Prototypes are also being built for production visualisation by Shell, <https://3dprint.com/130436/shell-3d-printed-prototyping/>, accessed 15-9-'16: "Usually you have nothing more than paper drawings to try to describe how best to do the installation work. What we've done is we've actually used a 3D printer to ensure that we did it safely".
- HSVA: Another application of rapid prototyping is making model for towing tanks. HSVA in Germany has been using a polymer extrusion printer to fabricate rudders, appendages and energy-saving devices, <http://www.ship-technology.com/features/feature3d-printing-rising-to-the-challenge-in-ship-design-4672912/>, accessed 15-9-'16.
- 10-XL: The Dutch company 10-xl focuses on making models up to 10 m for towing tanks out of reinforced polymers, <http://10-xl.nl/#2>, accessed 15-9-'16.

4.2.2 Rapid Tooling in Maritime Construction Sector

- MMT: An example of Rapid Tooling in the maritime construction sector is AM of moulds. MMT printed a mould for a drive train enclosure in about 1/3 of the normal time at a cost reduction of 60% compared to traditional fabrication, <http://www.moldmakingtechnology.com/columns/rapid-tooling-for-sand-casting>, accessed 15-9-'16.

4.2.3 Rapid Manufacturing in Maritime Construction Sector

Rapid manufacturing is being researched and used to some extent in different parts of the maritime construction sector.

- Innovation Quarter, Spare Parts: The Innovation quarter project about spare parts finished February 2016. Several spare parts have been analysed with the following conclusions on the specific potential of the spare part being: Integral life time comparison is required and per part production cost comparison is hardly ever possible and soft benefits must be factored in *Innovation Quarter (2016)*. When looking at the near future, the expectations for AM are: faster production, depending on the components from months to weeks or even days; less tooling and thereby less investment, although this is highly dependent on the application and use of machinery etc.; optimisation of design.
- Maersk and US Navy, on board spare parts: In 2012, a 3D printer was installed aboard an amphibious assault ship, the USS Essex, <https://3dprint.com/2554/uss-essex-3d-printer-navy/>, accessed 15-9-'16. This was followed by two more printers aboard the aircraft carrier USS Harry S. Truman. The printers are used to print “anything from plastic syringes to oil tank caps”, http://pilotonline.com/news/military/local/aircraft-carrier-harry-s-truman-prints-spare-unique-parts-at/article_b46b30f0-2ad4-525f-8328-34d37034450c.html, accessed 15-9-'16. In 2014, Maersk installed a polymer 3D printer aboard one of their tankers as part of an experiment to lower the costly and complex logistical operation of getting spare parts on the right place at the right time, <http://www.maersk.com/en/the-maersk-group/about-us/publications/maersk-post/2014-3/spare-parts-just-press-print>, accessed 15-9-'16.
- Tru-marine, Repair of turbochargers: Tru-marine is a company specialized in the repair of marine turbochargers. Laser cladding (a form of DED) is used to restore nozzle rings to as-new condition. This results in reduced waste, cost and delivery time with material test showing good tensile strength and microstructure, <http://www.trumarine.com/about-us/>, accessed 15-9-'16.
- Lloyds Register, Embedded Sensing: Lloyds Registers AM research includes a focus on embedded sensors during AM. The goal is to realize getting data feed from a static asset, such as during production, for certification or for monitoring service life of the final component, <http://www.lr.org/en/services/additive-manufacturing/research-and-resources/embedding-sensors-during-additive-manufacturing.aspx>, accessed 15-9-'16.

4.3 Conclusion of usages in Maritime Construction Sector

Polymer rapid prototyping and tooling are already adopted within the maritime sector. However critical components within rapid manufacturing are still in development phase. The overall consensus based upon the interests of the research facilities is that there's much to gain in that area, but it will require extensive research to overcome the challenges stated in Table II.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

Throughout this paper, it becomes clear that the available knowledge is superficial and that the true extent of the added value of additive manufacturing is largely unknown for the maritime construction sector. This is mainly due to the difficulty to quantify the effects of opportunities such as 'complexity for free'. Next to that, opportunities such as weight reduction, which is a key driver for aviation, is of much less use for the maritime construction sector.

The areas of potential added value are therefore more within prototyping, tooling, repair, (localized) production processes and overall supply chain optimization as shown by examples of 10-XL, Maersk and Tru-marine. A significant amount of research has to be performed in three key areas to overcome the knowledge gaps.

First, an in depth feasibility assessment of additive manufacturing for the maritime construction sector is needed, which should be based on a detailed cost estimation on component scale within maritime construction sector, this is to be done per type of material and process.

Secondly, the focus has to be set on rapid manufacturing for either spare parts or the overall

construction, and not so much rapid prototyping or rapid tooling, as these don't have to fulfil the requirements stated by *ISO (2014) 17923-2*. This has to ensure the structural integrity and material properties including fatigue that need to be known. Also, processes have to be certified in consultation with class society, so that adoption of this technology is as smooth as possible.

An overall implementation impact analysis considering the production process to quantify the gains within the supply chain and the changes that have to be addressed for potential implementation of additive manufacturing is required. With a sound basis, considering a maritime construction and its components, a design optimization analysis can be made to determine the effect on ships.

When feasibility is known, material integrity should be covered and overall implementation effects mapped. Overall, there is enough incentive to continue research in the area of additive manufacturing within the maritime construction sector. However, a higher level of detail is required in the three mentioned areas to come to a more decisive conclusion on the potential of additive manufacturing for the maritime construction sector.

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Measured Performance of a 50-m² Kite on a Trawler

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Abstract

This paper describes an onboard measurement campaign held in Grande-Rivière, Gaspésie, province of Québec, Canada, in October 2015, involving a 13-meter trawler equipped with a 50-square-meter kite. The aim of the campaign was the assessment of the boat performances when kite is used. To achieve this objective, in addition to the kite control system, a set of sensors has been installed. Thus data was recorded, as boat velocity, force generated by kite, fuel consumption, boat attitude, torque and rotational speed of propeller shaft, rudder angle and wind velocity. First, maneuverability tests have been done without kite, following as far as possible the ITTC guidelines. This aimed to get data to benchmark a maneuvering model based on the parametrical models of Yoshimura and Ma. A good agreement between the experimental data and the simulation is observed. Second, runs with kite in static flight have been done, with around 12 knots of true wind speed. The data post processing has allowed to estimate a lift to drag ratio around 6 of the kite and the tethers. This is consistent with other experimental data published.

Nomenclature

Roman Letter

\underline{A}	Generalized Added Mass Matrix
B	Max beam on waterline
\underline{C}	Centripetal matrix (6x6)
C_B	Hull block coefficient
C_L	Lift coefficient of the kite
C_{WP}	Water plane area coefficient
d	Draft
d_M	Draft at mid-ship
D_p	Propeller Diameter
F_i	Component of the kite force along the i-axis into the reference frame subscripted
J	Propeller advance ratio
K_Q	Torque coefficient
K_T	Thrust coefficient
L	Distance between the bow on waterline and rudder shaft
L/D	Lift to drag ratio of the kite
\underline{M}	Generalized rigid body mass matrix (6x6)
n	Rotational speed

Q	Torque
r	Yaw turning rate
R_T	Total resistance
t	Thrust deduction factor
T	Propeller thrust
u	Surge velocity
\underline{U}	Velocity vector (3x1)
\underline{V}	Generalized velocity vector (6x1)
V_a	Kite apparent wind speed
V_{WR}	Relative Wind speed at kite altitude
\underline{V}_{WR}	Relative Wind velocity vector at kite altitude
\underline{V}_{WT}	True Wind velocity vector
v	Sway velocity
w	Wake fraction

Greek Letter

β	Drift angle
β_{WR}	Relative wind angle at kite altitude (relative to ship axis)
γ	Flow rectification factor
η	Efficiency

ρ	Fluid density	P	Propeller
ρ_a	Air density during experiments	R	Rudder
ρ_w	Water density	WT	True Wind
$\underline{\Omega}$	Turning rate vector (3x1)	SSB	Shaft stuffing box
Subscript		S	Ship
APP	Appendage	w	water
H	Hull	WR	Relative Wind

K Kite

Reference Frames

\mathfrak{R}_0 is the earth fixed coordinate system, using the North East Down (NED) convention.

\mathfrak{R}_C is the current coordinate system. It is in rectilinear motion in \mathfrak{R}_0 with a constant velocity vector equal to the on-site current.

\mathfrak{R}_S is the ship coordinate axis system, rigidly fixed to the ship. It is defined with the Z-axis pointing down, the X-axis pointing forward, and the Y-axis pointing to starboard. The origin of reference frame is at mid-ship, in the intersection between the center plane of the boat and the water plane.

\mathfrak{R}_{LF} is the low frequency ship coordinate axis system. It is defined with the Z-axis always vertical pointing down, the X-axis into the boat center plane, always horizontal, pointing forward, and the Y-axis pointing to starboard.

\mathfrak{R}_{WR} is the relative wind coordinate axis system at kite altitude. It is the result of a rotation about axis Z_{LF} of angle $(\beta_{WR} - \pi)$ applied to frame \mathfrak{R}_{LF} .

\mathfrak{R}_K is the body reference frame attached to the kite, assumed as a rigid body.

1. Introduction

The use of kite to extract energy from wind is not a new idea, as it can be seen in *Loyd (1980)*. However, the current growing shortage of fossil resources and the emergence of new ecological regulations force us to reconsider options more renewable, and the use of kite is one of them. The various ways to extract energy with kites have been properly summarize in *Fagiano and Milanese (2012)* and *Cherubini et al. (2015)* give a good oversight of technologies. The current research project, undertaken by the company beyond-the-sea®, and managed in partnership with ENSTA Bretagne, aims to develop kite as auxiliary propulsion system for ships.

For this purpose, numerical models have been developed at ENSTA Bretagne, and so forces generated by kite and associated fuel savings can be predicted by *Leloup et al. (2016)*. Other models are also under development, in particular a parametrical maneuvering model to simulate the interaction between the kite and the ship. All these tools need to be validated, and experimental comparison is one of the best way to do it. In this context, a sea trial and measurement campaign has been set up in partnership with a Canadian fishing vessel and the Merinov institute. This campaign held in Grande-Rivière, Gaspésie, Province of Québec, Canada in October 2015. The fishing vessel was a 13-meter trawler usually used for fishing shrimp on the Gulf of St. Lawrence. All specifications will be given in the first part. A set of winches and sensors has been installed on board, to control the 50-square-meter kite, and measure the induced effects. All the experimental set up will be describe in the second part. Previously, ships towed by kite have been studied for the purpose of prediction of fuel savings. Naaijen and Koster in *Naaijen et al. (2006)* and *Leloup et al. (2016)* have predicted fuel saving using an average kite towing force over a closed kite loop trajectory. Nevertheless, since the kite behavior is highly dynamic, the dynamic ship motions induced by a kite must be studied. Indeed, a kite could seriously affect the maneuvering characteristics of a ship. Consequently, a dedicated tool has been developed for the beyond-the-sea® project by *Bigi et al. (2016)*. This tool consists in solving the Newton's first law of motion of the multi-body system, ship, tether and kite. In the aim of being

adapted to a wide range of ship, the maneuvering model used in this tool is based on the parametric nonlinear model of *Yoshimura and Masumoto (2012)*. This parametric maneuvering model has been identified with 12 different ships, from a fishing vessel of 26 m long to a container ship of 230 m long. Since the *Steven Paul* is only 13 m long a validation of the model with experimental data obtained during the campaign is necessary. These data come from maneuverability tests without kite that were carried out, following as far as possible the International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC) recommended procedures 7.5-04-02-01. The validation of the maneuvering model is presented and discussed with one turning circle of both directions (to starboard and to port).

In the last part, a method for computing lift and drag ratio and lift coefficient of the kite is presented. This method is specifically adapted to the available data which were acquired. Indeed, due to a lack of some information about kite orientation during flight and about the wind along the altitude, strong assumptions and estimations have to be done, leading to results which must be interpreted with caution. However, the obtained lift to drag ratios and lift coefficients make sense with other experimental works like *Dadd (2012)* one.

2. General presentation of experimental set up

2.1. Characteristic of the kite

The kite used during trials had an area of 50 m² (34 m² of projected area), with an inflatable leading edge, and 9 inflatable battens (see Fig.1). With this architecture, the kite has his own shape without any aerodynamic load, so launching and recovering procedure are easier. The mass of the deflated kite with bridles is 21 kg. Four 60-m-tethers link the kite to the boat. The two main ones, so-called front tethers, are linked to the bridle system attached on the leading edge, and resume about 80% of forces generated by kite. Their lengths are constant. The 20% remaining are taken by the back tethers, which are linked to another bridle system attached on the battens. Back tether are used to control kite flight, and for this purpose their lengths can vary. The attachment point of the tethers was located just ahead the forward bulkhead of the wheelhouse, as it can be seen in Fig.5. The mass of the 4 tethers is 2 kg.

Fig. 1: Kite used during measurement. C-shape with inflatable leading edge and battens, 50 m², 23 kg (deflated, with bridles and tethers).

For launching and recovering procedure, all tethers are wound on the same winch. For control purpose, each back tethers goes through a special pulley system, whose length is adjustable using electric winches. Each one is powered with 24 V DC, and can deliver 700W of nominal power. Optical encoders are fixed on each motor to ensure a feedback to the control system. The latter is running Windows 7, and the software controlling motors operates in LabVIEW (National Instruments). This one allows two mode of control: automatic and manual. The automatic one maintains the kite on a specified stationary position, using a small Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) attached on the kite to get a feedback on kite position and orientation. The IMU uses a wireless connection to send data to the control system. This autopilot can only ensure static flight, which means the kite can only fly on the wind window edge. It has been developed by engineers of beyond-the-sea®, but this paper does not aim to give more details about it. The manual mode allows the operator to control directly the motor, using two joysticks. The first joystick acts on the differential length between the two back tethers, and so on the direction of the kite. The second joystick is used to trim simultaneously the

length of the two back tethers, that means adjust the global angle of incidence of the kite. The kite control system is fully independent of the data acquisition system that will be described later.

2.2. Characteristics of the vessel

The trials were conducted on a 13-m fishing vessel, called Steven Paul, Table I, Figs.2 and 5, used to fish shrimp with trawl on Saint Lawrence gulf during summer season. The Steven Paul, like the majority of the fishing vessels of the area, is equipped with lateral stabilizers to reduce roll motion, and so, improve working quality of the crew. Internal structure modifications were carried out to allow the use of a towing kite, especially reinforcing the foredeck on which kite tethers were attached.

Table I: General characteristics of the fishing vessel Steven Paul

Length Overall	13.39	m
Length of waterline (trials loading conditions)	12.89	m
Length between perpendiculars	12.28	m
Beam of the hull	5.61	m
Displacement (trials loading conditions)	64	T
Displacement (full load)	90	T
Maximum Draft (trials loading conditions)	2.66	m
Draft (full load)	3.23	m
Motorization	Caterpillar 3408 - 480hp	-
Propulsion	Ducted Propeller	-
Crew for fishing operations	Captain with 2 seamen	-

Fig. 2: Steven Paul

Fig. 3: On-board picture of the kite in static flight during one of the starboard run

A Caterpillar 480 horse power engine ensures the propulsion of the vessel (model Marine 3408). At full power (during trawling operation or maximum transit speed), the fuel consumption is about 80 liters per hour. A reduction gear, with a transmission ratio of 1:4.48 transfers power to the propeller (Fig.4). The latter is a 4 blades ducted propeller, with diameter of 1.26 meter. A grid is protecting propeller from unidentified floating objects or from the fishing ropes in case of problem during trawling operation. The characteristics of the propeller are given in Table II. The rudder is a flat plate (Fig.4), 1.45 meter high, for 0.84 meter long, driven by a hydraulic actuator.

Table II: Propeller characteristics of the fishing vessel Steven Paul

Propeller Diameter	1.26	m
Number of blades	4	-
Pitch Ratio	1.015	-
Blade Area Ratio	0.55	-

Fig. 4: Steven Paul propeller and rudder

2.3. Data acquisition system

The whole data acquisition system is based on a National Instruments CompactRIO platform. It consists of 3 main parts: a set of I/O modules depending on sensor technology, a Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA, NI CRIO-9114) and a Real-Time processor (NI CRIO-9024). All I/O modules are connected to the FPGA, and the very accurate clock of the FPGA ensures a good synchronization between the channels, and precise acquisition frequencies. The Real-Time processor logs all data coming from sensor through the FPGA on a non-volatile memory. The following table gives the details of I/O modules which have been used for this campaign. All acquisition programs have been developed with LabVIEW. Raw data were all stored in a single file, using a National Instruments proprietary format (TDMS file). These files were then converted into MATLAB® format files, and all calibration procedures and data processing were done using this software.

Table III: Summary of National Instrument I/O module used for data acquisition

Module	Description	Total number of channels
2 x NI 9870	Serial Port	8
1 x NI 9411	Digital Input	6
2 x NI 9237	Bridge Analog Input	8

3. Sensors

3.1. Kinematics of the vessel

To measure motions and velocities of the boat, an IMU coupled with a GPS was set up (Xsens MTi-G-700). This Unit includes a microprocessor able to realize data fusion, based on an extended Kalman filter providing roll and pitch information. Manufacturer ensures dynamic error for roll and pitch under 1° with a 1σ RMS error of 0.1° . The acquisition frequencies of the Xsens were 50Hz for inertial sensors (gyroscope and accelerometer), 20 Hz for roll and pitch, and 5Hz for all data regarding GPS technology (position and velocity). The Xsens was directly linked to a serial port of the CompactRIO. It was fixed in the wheelhouse, just behind the forward bulkhead, a few centimeters behind the attachment point of the kite, located ahead this bulkhead.

To avoid complex and uncertain calibration procedure of magnetometers, it has been decided to use an existing on board sensor to get yaw information, based on dual antenna GPS, instead of yaw information provided by the magnetometers of the Xsens. The sensor was a Si-Tex Vector Pro, with 1σ RMS error under 0.3° . This sensor, providing the true heading of the boat regardless the boat velocity, is used by the onboard autopilot. Therefore, a serial link was done between the autopilot and the CompactRIO to recover this information. The maximum update rate of the Si-Tex Vector Pro is up to 20Hz, according to the manufacturer. However, because the information goes through the

autopilot before reaching the data acquisition system, the final update rate was 1Hz. This could not be changed during the campaign.

3.2. Engine and rudder system

A double flowmeter had been installed previously on the engine, to measure the fuel feed and fuel return, and so provide fuel consumption (Maretron M2RSP-2R-E8). This sensor is connected to the on board NMEA 2000 network. A conversion device on the NMEA2000 network provides a serial output with NMEA183 protocol. This output was connected to another serial port of the CompactRIO, and so the fuel flow was logged at 1Hz. A device measuring the torque on the propeller shaft, developed by the company UpDaq, had also been installed previously on board. A strain gauge had been stuck on the shaft and is linked to an amplifier, sending data wirelessly to a receiver in the wheelhouse. The later was connected to the acquisition system through a serial link. The torque on the shaft was logged at 20Hz. The measurement of rotational speed of the shaft propeller was carried out thank to a binary sensor, going from 0 V to 5 V each time the magnet stuck on the shaft passes nearby the sensor. The sensor was directly linked to the Digital Input module (NI 9411) of the CompactRIO system. The rotational speed of the shaft was logged at 20Hz. A rudder angle sensor was part of the autopilot system to provide feedback. This information had been retrieved using the existing serial link presented part 3.1, with a resolution of 1° , and a frequency of 1Hz.

3.3. Kite

To get force on tethers, load cells had been used during trial. A three dimension load cell (Michigan Scientific TR3D-4K) had been rigidly fixed on the foredeck, just in front the forward bulkhead of the wheelhouse. The location in \mathcal{R}_s reference frame is (3.1m, 0m, 1.7m). This load cell has a full scale load of 17,800 N for each axis, with a safe overload of 300%. The selection process of the load cell range was done using simulation tools developed by *Leloup et al. (2016)*. During measurement phases, i.e. excluding launching and recovering procedures, the front tethers of the kite were directly connected to this load cell (no idler pulleys). So, this sensor provided information of force vector generated by the kite, expressed into the load cell axis system in a first time, and into the boat axis system after post processing (the position and orientation of the load cell implantation had been of course carefully measured). Knowing the length of tethers, and considering tethers are straight, the position of the kite in the flight window can be recovered. The non-linearity error specified by manufacturer is under 0.5% of full scale, and hysteresis and repeatability errors are under 0.05% of full scale each. It was impossible on the boat to carry out a complete calibration of measurement chain, so sensibilities provided by manufacturer had been used. The global error of the chain including amplifier error and load cell implantation measurement error, was still unknown, however it seems reasonable to expect a global error under 1% of the full scale load.

Measurement of forces in back tethers was different due to the variable length of these tethers to ensure kite control. Two one dimension load cell (Futek LCM200) were installed into the pulleys system, and each one measured twice the load passing through each back tether. These load cells have a full scale load of 4,500N, with a specified non-linearity error under 0.5% of full scale, a hysteresis error under 0.5% of full scale and repeatability error under 0.1% of full scale. Here again, full calibration procedure was impossible to carry out on board, so sensibilities given on calibration certificate of each load cell has been used. The fact that measurement of back tether forces were done into a pulley circuit adds incertitude in measurement. The used pulleys were high-class ones with ball bearing design (Harken Carbo 57 mm), so it is sensible to expect limited effects, although no test in laboratory was carried out. To take all these unknown errors into account the global error in measurement has been raised to 2% of full scale. Each load cells and each axis of the 3D load cell were connected to one of the bridge analogical input of the CompactRIO system. The frequency of acquisition of all channels was 1 kHz.

3.4. Wind

Measurement of relative wind was done using an ultrasonic anemometer (LCJ Capteurs CV7) fixed at 9.01 m from the water line, and 0.3m aft the mid-ship. The update rate of the sensor is 2 Hz, with a direction resolution of 1° and wind module resolution of 0.05 m/s. The sensor was linked to one of the serial port of the CompactRIO platform, using NMEA183 protocol. The roll and pitch motion of the boat were small (maximum $\pm 1^\circ$), with averaged periods of 2.9s for pitch and 10s for roll. These motions have induced a maximum velocity at the anemometer level of 0.2 m/s, and it has been decided to neglect these effects.

Fig. 5: Side view of the Steven Paul with the waterline as it was during measurements. The marker 1 denotes the kite attachment point and so the position of the 3D load cell described part 3.3. The marker 2 shows the position of the anemometer described part 3.4. The marker 3 notes the launching mast used for launching and recovering procedure. The marker 4 shows the mid-ship of the boat and the origin of the \mathcal{R}_s reference frame. Kite size and tether length are not true to scale.

4. Comparison of a parametric maneuvering model with experimental data

4.1. Parametric nonlinear maneuvering model

Assuming the ship as a rigid body, the ship equation of motion, in the ship coordinate system \mathcal{R}_s , is written in Eq. (1) as proposed by *Perez (2006)*.

$$(\underline{\underline{M}}_S + \underline{\underline{A}}_S)\dot{\underline{V}}_S + \underline{\underline{C}}_S \underline{V}_S = \underline{F} = \underline{F}_H + \underline{F}_R + \underline{F}_P + \underline{F}_{APP} + \underline{F}_K \quad (1)$$

$\underline{\underline{M}}_S$ is the generalized mass matrix (6x6). $\underline{\underline{A}}_S$ is the generalized added mass matrix (6x6). \underline{V}_S is the generalized ship velocity vector relative to \mathcal{R}_C expressed in \mathcal{R}_S at mid-ship. $\underline{V}_S = [u_s \ v_s \ w_s \ p_s \ q_s \ r_s]^T$ is the assembly of the linear ship velocity $\underline{U}_S = [u_s \ v_s \ w_s]^T$ with the ship angular velocity $\underline{\Omega}_S = [p_s \ q_s \ r_s]^T$. $\dot{\underline{V}}_S$ is the generalized velocity time derivative. $\underline{\underline{C}}_S$ is the centripetal matrix (6x6). \underline{F} is the generalized force vector representing the forces acting on the ship. It can be decomposed into the sum of the hull, rudder,

propeller, appendages and kite contributions. In Eq. (8) the subscripts H, R, P, APP and K denote respectively the hull, the rudder, the propeller, the appendages and the kite. $\underline{F} = [X \ Y \ Z \ L \ M \ N]^T$, where the three first components of \underline{F} represent the forces and the last three components represent the moments.

Here, the kite is not considered, consequently $\underline{F}_K = \underline{0}$. Moreover, Eq. (1) is reduced to three classical maneuvering degrees of freedom (dof), surge sway and yaw. For instance, X_H is the longitudinal component of the hull force and is expressed by the following Taylor's expansion:

$$X_H = R_T(u_S) + \frac{\rho_w}{2} L d_M \| \underline{U}_S \|^2 \left(X'_{\beta\beta} \beta^2 + X'_{\beta r} \beta r' + X'_{rr} r'^2 + X'_{\beta\beta\beta\beta} \beta^4 \right) \quad (2)$$

Yoshimura and Masumoto (2012) provide a parametric formulation of the hull derivatives. Each derivative can be function of the length, width, block coefficient, trim and draft at mid-ship without considering the false-keel. The hull block coefficient denoted by C_B is calculated with the ship length between perpendiculars, the draft at mid-ship and the maximum hull beam. As example, $X'_{\beta\beta}$ is written as follows:

$$X'_{\beta\beta} = 0.185 C_B \frac{B}{L} - 0.18 \quad (3)$$

Here, the rudder model used is the nonlinear model proposed by *Soding (1998)*. On single screw ship a dissymmetry can be noticed between maneuvers with positive and negative turning rate. The presented maneuvering model takes this effect into account by using custom flow rectification factor at the rudder, for each side. Indeed the transverse flow velocity at the rudder in \mathfrak{R}_S , denoted by $v_{F,R}^{(S)}$, is expressed as follows:

$$v_{F,R}^{(S)} = -\gamma^{+,-} (v_S + x_R r_S) \quad (4)$$

Where, x_R is the longitudinal position of the rudder and $\gamma^{+,-}$ is the flow rectification factor. γ^+ is used for positive turning rate and γ^- for negative turning rate.

The thrust deduction fraction can be estimated by the method of Weingart for single-screw ship in Eq. (5), described by *Journée (1976)*. In Eq. (5), C_{WP} denotes the water plane coefficient.

$$t = w \left(1.57 - 2.30 \frac{C_B}{C_{WP}} + 1.50 C_B \right) \quad (5)$$

4.2. Resistance and power characteristics of the Steven Paul

The resistance and the power characteristics are identified with the experimental data collected during a power test. For five different quasi-steady states of engine power, the ship velocity over ground, the propeller revolution and the torque on the shaft were measured. In order to obtain the ship velocity with respect to the free surface, the current velocity \underline{U}_C is identified according to the IMO Resolution A.751 (1993) with a turning circle done just before the power test. For each steady state the experimental propeller torque coefficient is identified with the following relationship:

$$K_Q^{\text{exp}} = \eta_{SSB} \frac{\overline{Q}_{SSB}}{\rho_w n_P^2 D_P^5} \quad (6)$$

n_P is the propeller revolution per second; \overline{Q}_{SSB} is the torque measured on the propeller shaft after the propeller and the shaft stuffing box; D_P denotes the propeller diameter; η_{SSB} is the shaft stuffing box efficiency; the overbar denotes the time average.

Assuming that the Steven Paul propeller is equivalent to Kaplan 19-A of diameter 1.30 m, of pitch

ratio of 1.015, of blade area ratio of 0.55 and assuming the shaft stuffing box efficiency equals to 0.97, the following equation must be verified for each quasi-steady state of the power test:

$$K_Q^{\text{exp}} = K_Q \left(J = (1-w) \frac{\bar{u}_S}{n_P D_P} \right) \quad (7)$$

The open water torque coefficient K_Q is determined according to the regression model proposed by *Kuiper (1992)*. The wake fraction w is then determined in order to verify Eq. (7). A wake fraction of 0.39 is identified with a Bayesian optimization from *Snoek et al. (2012)*. The left hand side and the right hand side of Eq. (7) are plotted in Fig.6.

Fig. 6: Comparison between experimental data (denoted by + symbol) and model of K_Q (dashed line) as a function of the propeller advance ratio J . The solid line shows K_T and the dash-dotted line shows the propeller efficiency.

Fig. 7: Total resistance of the Steven Paul calculated with the presented method.

The very high value of wake fraction could be explained by the presence of a protection cage upstream of the propeller. This cage may drastically decrease the mean inflow velocity on the propeller disk area. According to Eq. (5), a thrust deduction factor of 0.34 is obtained. Finally, the

total resistance $R_T = \frac{(1-t)K_T}{D_P K_Q} \eta_{SSB} Q_{SSB}$ is plotted in Fig.7.

4.3. Validation of the maneuvering model

In order to validate the Steven Paul maneuvering model, one turning circle of each side has been tested. The ship motions during the maneuvers are computed using the experimental rudder angle and the experimental propeller rotational speed as inputs. The two time series at the bottom of Fig.9 represent respectively the experimental rudder angle and the propeller rotational speed. In addition, in Fig.9, ship velocity (surge and sway) and yaw turning rate are plotted. In Fig.8 the computed ship path and the measured ship path are compared. Here, the custom values of the flow rectification factor have been optimized in order to obtain the experimental turning radius, consequently, $[\gamma^+ \ \gamma^-] = [0.95 \ 0.61]$.

The transient part until $t = 10$ s and the steady part after $t = 10$ s can be distinguished. A good agreement can be noticed for the surge and sway velocity and the yaw turning rate during the steady part of the motion. Regarding the transient part of the turning circle, the decelerating of the simulated surge velocity is lower than the experiments especially on starboard. Moreover, a delay is observable in term of yaw motion in Fig.9, which is confirmed in term of ship path. Despite the observable differences, especially for the transient part, the maneuvering model can be considered as validated, according to the measurements uncertainties and the usual maneuvering validation results available in the literature *Stern et al. (2011)*.

Fig. 8: Ship path during turning circles to portside and to starboard. Dashed and solid lines denote respectively the experimental data and simulated data; triangle and circle marks denote respectively the turning circles to portside and to starboard.

Fig. 9: From the top to the bottom respectively time series of: surge and sway velocity; yaw turning rate; rudder angle; propeller revolution per second. Dashed and solid lines denote respectively the experimental data and simulated data; triangle and circle marks denote respectively the turning circles to portside and to starboard.

5. Post-processing of kite flight data

During the campaign, due to availability issues with the boat and inoperable weather, only one day of exploitable measurement was able to be achieved. During this day, runs with kite in static flight have been done, with about 12 knots of true wind speed. The aim of the following part is to process data to retrieve lift to drag ratio of the system {kite + tethers}. However, the measurement of the lift to drag ratio is largely affected by the wind intensity and direction at the altitude of the kite (as it will be shown in Eq. (11)), which is an unknown data, as there is no reliable mean to measure it. Indeed only the relative wind over the boat, at 9 m over the sea, is known (see part Fig.5). The absolute wind at the same place can be easily retrieved using speed and heading information, but the absolute wind at other

altitude can only be estimated. Indeed, altitude impacts absolute wind both in strength and direction. With no possibility of getting precise modelling of the twist of the flow along the altitude, it has been decided to neglect the effect of twist, and only take account the 2D shear stress distribution calculated using the Eq. (9), from the ITTC 2011 recommendations. Equations (8) to (10) present the process to go from relative wind velocity and boat velocity measurement to relative wind velocity for any altitude z .

$$\underline{V}_{WT}(Z_0) = \underline{V}_{WR}(Z_0) + \underline{V}_S \quad (8)$$

$$\underline{V}_{WT}(z) = \left(\frac{z}{Z_0} \right)^n \underline{V}_{WT}(Z_0) \quad (9)$$

$$\underline{V}_{WR}(z) = \underline{V}_{WT}(z) - \underline{V}_S \quad (10)$$

Where Z_0 is the altitude measurement (m), z is the altitude above sea level (m) and n is a coefficient which is equal to 1/7 (ITTC 2011). With the relative wind vector defined for any altitude, we can create a new axis system based on it. Hence the Relative Wind reference frame is defined with the X-axis along the relative wind vector at the kite altitude, the Z-axis vertical pointing down and the Y-axis completing the coordinate system to create a direct one. This reference frame is noted with the subscript WR.

Because kite position measurement was done through a 3D load cell rigidly attached to the boat, boat motions affects kite position measurement. This is visible in figure 9 where elevation angle θ of the kite, resulting from the basic transformation of Cartesian position coordinates of the kite into spherical ones, according to boat axis system, evolves in line with the pitch of the boat. To remove these effects, position coordinates of the kite have been expressed into the \mathcal{R}_{LF} axis system, independent from the boat pitch and roll motion. The transformation matrix is created from the first two Euler angles (roll and pitch) provided by the inertial measurement unit Xsens, according to *Xsens Technologies (2014)*. Result of the transformation is given in Fig.10, showing a few seconds of a starboard run with kite in static flight.

Fig. 10: Expression of kite elevation angle in the \mathcal{R}_s reference frame (dotted line) and in the \mathcal{R}_{LF} reference frame (dash-dotted line), during one of the runs with kite in static flight. The first one is in line with the pitch angle of the boat (solid red line) due to the way the measurement of kite position was done.

To process the lift to drag ratio and lift coefficient, the apparent wind on the kite needs to be known. This one is the vectorial difference between the relative wind and the kite velocity in the \mathcal{R}_{LF}

reference frame. For the specific case of static flight, with the ship moving a constant velocity, the kite velocity is theoretically zero in the low frequency ship axis system. However kite in static flight undergoes small but permanent displacement around a middle position, but these displacements are mainly sideslip motion. With the used experimental set up, the yaw orientation of the kite was not measured, so the kite velocity vector cannot be known in the \mathfrak{R}_K reference frame. To deal with this issue, it has been decided to consider the kite in perfect static flight at all times, i.e. the kite velocity in the \mathfrak{R}_{LF} reference frame is taken equal to 0. In other words, the kite is considered as continuously located on the wind window edge as defined by *Leloup et al. (2016)*, and the apparent wind vector is equal to the relative wind vector and is included in the symmetry plane of the kite assumed as a rigid body.

5.1. Lift to drag ratio estimation

From there, it becomes easy to compute lift to drag ratio by expressing kite forces in the \mathfrak{R}_{WR} reference frame. Indeed, the coordinate of the force along X_{WR} -axis is the total drag, and the projection into the (Y_{WR}, Z_{WR}) plane is the lift. The component of force along the Z_{WR} -axis is the sum of the vertical aerodynamic force generated by kite and the weight P of the kite and tethers (equals to 226 N). The latter is then subtracted to the vertical component of force to get only aerodynamic force. Finally the lift to drag ratio is achieved by processing the following equation:

$$L/D = \frac{\sqrt{Fy_{WR}^2 + (Fz_{WR} - P)^2}}{Fx_{WR}} \quad (11)$$

5.2. Lift Coefficient Estimation

The previous part has shown the identification of lift and drag component of kite force, from the measured force expressed in the relative wind axis system. From there, and with the same assumptions, lift coefficient can be processed easily using Eq. (12).

$$C_L = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_a \cdot A_k \cdot V_a^2} = \frac{\sqrt{Fy_{WR}^2 + (Fz_{WR} - P)^2}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_a \cdot A_k \cdot V_{WR}^2} \quad (12)$$

A_k is the projected kite area (34 m²), ρ_a is the density of the air, estimated to 1.22 kg·m⁻³ during the measurement day (air temperature 15°C, atmospheric pressure 1012 hPa, relative humidity 70%), V_a is the kite apparent wind speed, equal to the relative wind speed V_{RW} in case of static flight.

5.3. Results

The Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) have been processed for 3 runs with kite in static flight. Results are presented in Table IV. No kite setting was modified during or between periods, which means the global lengths of back tethers were maintained constant (no change in global angle of incidence of the kite). Only differential variations of tether lengths were done for control purpose, and to keep the kite on a static defined position. The period 2 is shown in Fig.11 and Fig.12. Results are varying a lot, but the averaged lift to drag ratio during the considered period is equal to 6.06, and the averaged lift coefficient is equal to 0.76. This seems consistent with other experimental data published like *Dadd (2012)*. Indeed, for a 3-square-meter kite with an aspect ratio of 4.9, Dadd got a lift coefficient of 0.78 and a lift to drag ratio of 6.07. To estimate drag coefficient and so lift to drag ratio of other kite with other aspect ratio, Dadd uses *Abbott and Von Doenhoff (1959)* formulas, assuming both kite are trimmed to produce same lift coefficient. Applying this method to the kite used for the present study (aspect ratio of 5.5), the expected lift to drag ratio should be 6.36.

Fig. 11: Lift to drag ratio for each point using Eq. (11) (dotted), during a 569s run with kite in static flight. The solid line is the mean of the lift to drag ratio during the considered period, and is equal to 6.06. The associated standard deviation is 2.45.

Fig. 12: Lift coefficient for each point using Eq. (12) (dotted), during a 569s run with kite in static flight. The solid line is the mean of the lift coefficient during the considered period (=0.76). The associated standard deviation is 0.26.

Table IV: Compiled results of four periods with kite in static flight

	Duration (s)	Averaged True Wind Speed (m/s)	Averaged True Wind Angle (°)*	Lift to drag ratio L/D		Lift coefficient C_L	
				Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Period 1	399	5.7	88	5.9	2.3	0.68	0.21
Period 2	569	6.1	95	6.1	2.5	0.76	0.26
Period 3	209	5.7	304	5.3	1.5	0.59	0.17

*According to boat axis; for example 90° means cross wind, starboard tack

5.4. Discussion

The averaged results of the 3 periods are close, with also a good agreement with published data, as it has been shown previously. However, the point to point data analysis in Fig.11 and Fig.12 shows extreme values of lift to drag ratio and lift coefficient that are not realistic. This demonstrates the limits of the various assumptions which have been done. One of the most important is probably the consideration of a kite velocity equal to 0 into the \mathcal{R}_{LF} reference frame, but the straight line assumption could also be a source of incertitude. The decision to disregard the twist wind flow along the altitude due to a lack of data and models could be also detrimental. Thus, a fourth period with kite in static flight has been logged, but it had to be discarded due to inconsistent data. One possible explanation is a significant difference between the wind orientation at the measurement point and the wind orientation at the kite position. This eventuality leads us to consider, for future experimental campaign, a duplication of wind measurement systems. Moreover, the installation of multiple anemometers at various altitudes could be also a good way to improve wind estimation with altitude. Another goal of the campaign was initially to benchmark the fuel savings prediction tool developed by *Leloup et al. (2016)*, using the flowmeter installed on the engine. However, due to an unexpected unavailability of the boat and unsuitable weather, it has been impossible in only one day to carry out enough measurements alternating runs with kite and then runs without kite with identical weather. Nevertheless, a comparison can be done between power supplied by the kite, and power delivered by the engine to the propeller thanks to the sensors that were installed on-board. For example for the period 2, on the engine side, the average rotation speed of the propeller shaft is 3.4 revolutions per second, and the average torque on the propeller shaft is 1800 Nm. The total power provided by the engine to the propeller is then 38000 W. On the kite side, the average propulsive force generated by the kite during the 569 s is 505 N, the average speed of the boat is 2.4 m/s, so the average power is 1212W. This leads to a kite providing 4.5% of the total power, with only 6.1 m/s of true wind speed, and in static flight condition. Extrapolation of this case to a true wind speed of 12m/s leads then to a

kite providing 17% of the total power required. However this basic estimation needs to be treated very carefully. Indeed this is only one particular case, and does not reflect all operational conditions of the boat. Moreover this estimation does not take into account the effect of kite on the drift for instance. This could induce bigger rudder angles in order to counteract the effects of kite, and so would affect fuel savings. The investigation of these possible issues would be done in a future work using in particular the manoeuvrability model summarily presented and validated in part 4.

6. Conclusion

A full scale kite experimental set up was installed on a 13-meter fishing vessel, equipped with a 50-square-meter kite. Boat motions, engine parameters, kite forces, kite positions and wind data were recorded during one day of measurements. First, maneuverability test was carried out to validate a maneuverability modelling of the boat, based on an existing parametrical modelling developed by *Yoshimura and Masumoto (2012)*. A good agreement between experimental data and parametrical modelling is shown. Secondly, multiple runs with kite in static flight were done with various durations, from 3 to 10 minutes. From data which were logged during these runs, a method for estimating lift to drag ratio and lift coefficient has been carried out. This method was computed, and showed results making sense. Thus, a lift to drag ratio about 5.9 and a lift coefficient about 0.7 could be retained (average on the 3 periods). These results are very close of the ones obtained by *Dadd (2012)* even if strong assumptions have been done to get them. These assumptions have been discussed and ameliorations in the experimental set up for future work are under consideration.

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Hydrodynamic Optimization of a Power Boat in the Cloud

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Abstract

Publically available information on the hydrodynamics of a high-performance marine vehicle is limited. If a design team intends to create a fast, and possibly unconventional, boat or ship the challenge is to produce high-quality data for its resistance, propulsion, seakeeping etc. Viscous CFD codes have reached a very high level of accuracy, yielding both reliable ranking of variants and sound absolute values. Moreover, it has become fairly easy to utilize external computational resources in – what is commonly called – the Cloud to achieve fast turn-around time. This enables designers to undertake thorough design studies economically. This paper presents how a high-fidelity viscous code including the free surface (FINE™/Marine) was combined with a parametric modeling and optimization environment (CAESES®) to run an optimization campaign for a power boat on an HPC cluster.

1. Introduction

Getting reliable data on the hydrodynamics of high-performance marine vehicles is not an easy task. This is different to standard displacement ships which were covered through model-test campaigns in the past and are nowadays studied frequently by means of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), see for example *Harries (2010)*. That does not come as a big surprise since the majority of boats and ships travel at low Froude numbers, typically below 0.3 (on the basis of ship length).

Fast boats and ships at Froude numbers well above 1.0 require high-fidelity simulations and advanced design techniques in order to reach cutting-edge performance. Viscous flow analysis including the free surface to capture wave making while adjusting for dynamic trim and sinkage is a key element. A fully-parametric model of the shape is another powerful ingredient since it reduces the degrees-of-freedom of the design space while ensuring high-quality shapes. Search and optimization strategies support the designer in understanding trade-offs and in pushing for further improvements.

However, the computational resources needed to undertake a thorough investigation on the basis of viscous CFD are often quite substantial. Luckily, there is an increasing availability of attractive High-performance Computing (HPC) offered remotely, nicely complementing local resources if the team's workstations would not yield the necessary turn-around time. In the general public externally used computer resources are frequently referred to as Cloud solutions, even if the actual resource is a specific set of hardware located in an air-conditioned room with controlled access and ensured data security.

The paper presents a combination of dedicated systems that offer all elements for a very competitive design environment: FINE™/Marine by NUMECA, <http://www.numeca.de>, CAESES® by FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS, www.caeses.com, and “bare-metal” computational resources provided by CPU 24/7, <https://www.cpu-24-7.com>. A practical example will be given for a 6 m power boat running at 18 kn so as to illustrate how the tools are brought together and applied for hydrodynamic optimization.

2. Design task and simulation-ready CAD

A small hard-chine motor boat shall be optimized for resistance at a design speed of $V = 18$ kn (33.33 km/h = 9.26 m/s) which represents a rather typical pleasure craft used for day cruising and

sports such as waterskiing. For a boat of 5 m length in the design waterline and an overall length of a bit below 6 m, this yields a Froude number of $F_{n,LDWL} = 1.32$. Assuming a displacement volume of $\nabla = 1.3 \text{ m}^3$, the volume Froude number is $F_{n,\nabla} = 2.81$. Displacement in fresh water is estimated from 1000 kg of weight for the boat and 300 kg related to the passengers (say two adults and three kids). With a beam at the transom of around 1.6 m quite a high speed coefficient of $C_V = \nabla / (g \cdot B_{\text{Transom}})^{3/2} = 2.34$ is reached, *Savitsky (1964), Savitsky and Brown (1976)*.

Fig.1 shows a parametric model of the boat's bare hull as realized within CAESES. It can be readily seen that the boat is close to the classic designs of the 1950s and 60s. The design task was deliberately chosen to represent this type of boat as a tribute to Carlo Riva who introduced the so-called *Riva Junior* as a small pleasure craft in 1966. A classic *Riva* would feature one (or two) shaft line(s), propeller(s) and rudder(s). They are omitted here in order to focus on bare hull resistance. Nota bene: The idea of this paper is not to prove that Carlo Riva should have done better in terms of hydrodynamics. Instead, the paper is meant to show that it took 50 years (1966 to 2016) to bring together and apply the Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) technology needed to go one step further. Therefore, the *Riva* serves as a means of illustrating the abstracted design task of optimizing a hard-chine hull at high speed with free sinkage and trim in a virtual towing tank campaign.

Fig.1: Parametric model of a motor boat's bare hull, showing the baseline

2.1. Parametric model

A key prerequisite for the systematic variation of geometry is a parametric model that features as few defining elements (i.e., parameters) as possible. This is because design and optimization typically scale disproportionately with the number of free variables (i.e., the parameters chosen to vary). A general rule-of-thumb says that one needs to investigate at least as many variants as the square of the degrees-of-freedom present in a system.

Harries et al. (2015) give an overview of the options that are available for variable geometry in the context of simulation-driven design. For the motor boat shown in Fig.1 a fully-parametric model is utilized. The general idea is to identify a common (two-dimensional) building pattern which can be applied throughout a prominent direction of the geometry, typically in streamline direction (as in hulls) or somewhat perpendicular to the flow (as in rudders, propeller blades etc.).

Fig.2: Building pattern for stations at different longitudinal positions

Fig.3: Longitudinal distribution of parameters in top view (upper image) and side view (lower image)

Fig.4: Superposition of building pattern and longitudinal distribution of parameters (left image) to define a set of surfaces within a fully-parametric model (right image)

Fig.2 illustrates the building pattern for the hard-chine hull: A curved segment connects the keel line with the inner position of the spray rail which follows as a straight line. From the outer position of the spray rail a curved segment goes up to the deck. Parameters to define each section are the height of the keel line, the height and beam of the inner rail, the breadth of the spray rail and the height and beam of the deck. In addition, both the curved segment of the planing surface and the freeboard are defined via parameters for hollowness, i.e., the distance from the curve's apex to a straight connecting line. As can be imagined easily, the actual parameter values change in longitudinal direction since each section is slightly different to its neighbors, see upper images in Fig.2.

Fig.3 depicts the longitudinal distributions of the input parameters for each section in top and side view, respectively. The top view shows the spray rails and the deck while the side view features the keel line, the spray rail's vertical sweep from the transom to the stem along with the deck's sheer. The three-dimensional curves are composed of the two projects in z-direction (top view) and y-direction (side view). This is illustrated in Fig.4. Each section receives its input from these longitudinal curves. Combining the building pattern and the longitudinal curves establishes a closed mathematical definition of all surfaces (called a *MetaSurface* within CAESES), see right image in Fig.4.

Fig.5: Variants generated by changing s sub-set of nine parameters

2.2. Variable geometry

The fully-parametric model enables the designer – or an automated optimization strategy – to come up with new variants within split-seconds of CPU time and, very importantly, without any need of manual work. Fig.5 depicts six representative variants as investigated during an optimization campaign (as further elaborated in section 5). Here, nine parameters were changed simultaneously.

While the topology of the model is maintained, the variants are quite distinguishable in geometry. Differences can best be seen in the overall beam, the hollowness of the (light-blue) planing surface and in the transom's deadrise. Naturally, any parameter within the model can be individually addressed and altered. For an elaboration of single parameter variations see *Harries and Abt (2016)*.

2.3. Pre-processing for simulation

A standard means to transfer the boundary representation of geometry (a so-called B-Rep) to a grid generator for viscous flow simulations is to utilize a discrete format called STL (STereoLithography). Several steps are undertaken to ensure a reliable process: Firstly, the closed-mathematical surfaces of the parametric model are subdivided into a (high) number of triangles. This is done such that the differences between the actual surfaces and their approximating triangles fall below a user-selected tolerance (Fig.6). The resulting set of tri-meshes are subsequently stitched together to yield a watertight vessel, i.e., a discrete representation without any hanging nodes, overlaps or gaps (Fig.7). Finally, the flow domain is defined, typically as a rectangular box, and created by imprinting the vessel via a Boolean subtraction (Fig.8); see *Harries and Abt (2016)* for additional material.

Fig.6 illustrates the step of converting the surfaces to tri-meshes for the bow region of the motor boat. (Side note: Here, a special treatment at the bow can be observed. In order to avoid acute angles in the discretization of the spray rail, its most forward portion was split off and combined with the lower planing surface, shown in a lighter blue, before discretization. This adds robustness when generating the volume grid.)

Fig.6: Surfaces and watertight tri-mesh approximating the surfaces

Fig.7 depicts the watertight tri-meshes of two variants featuring most prominently a modification of the maximum beam. The tolerance is set the same. The tessellation adjusts to the changes of the geometry which can be nicely seen in the bow region of the planing surface. As should be noted the different tri-meshes making up the vessel feature different colors. This allows distinguishing regions when transferring data to the grid generator, using a so-called colored STL file.

Fig.8 shows the flow domain in a side view. The domain starts upstream of the boat and extends several times the boat length downstream. Since both water and air are taken into account in the simulation, the domain also spreads above and well below the boat. A close-up shows the imprint of the hull into the flow domain. Again the different colors can be seen for different regions of the hull

(light-blue for the planing surface, dark-blue for the spray rail, silver for the freeboard and red for the deck).

Fig.7: Watertight tri-meshes for different variants

Fig.8: Flow domain in side view (left) and close-up showing the embedded hull (right)

3. High-fidelity CFD simulation

The viscous flow simulations were undertaken with NUMECA's CFD system FINE™/Marine, a system dedicated to the maritime and offshore industry. Three components make up the suite: The mesh generator HEXPRESS™, the flow solver ISIS and the flow visualization system CFView™, see Table I for details. All of the components can be launched in batch mode and controlled via Python, enabling the integration into an automated design and optimization process.

For the analysis of the hard-chine motor boat FINE™/Marine's so-called C-Wizard was put to use. The C-Wizard supports the fast set-up of resistance and seakeeping analyses typically of interest to naval architects. It takes care of the entire pre-processing on the basis of very few input data like operating speeds, drafts and weights. In this way, the designer can fully focus on hydrodynamics without explicitly having to specify the numerics. For the small motor boat at 18 kn the C-Wizard planing mode was utilized.

3.1. Pre-processing

Upon importing the computational domain into HEXPRESS™ via the colored STL file provided by CAESSES®, all the mesh settings are automatically specified by the C-Wizard. Due to the usage of certain keywords in the STL geometry (e.g. "bow," "stern," "hull" and "rail" associated with the color names) zones of different mesh density are automatically assigned, giving a fast and reliable set-up. For instance a fine mesh is placed where the flow gradients are expected to be high. For the motor boat two important regions should be highlighted: One region is near the bow and along the spray rail

where a lot of spray, splashing and possible ventilation occurs. The other region is behind the stern where flow separation leads to a completely dry stern at cruise speed.

Table I: Specifics of the CFD system FINE™/Marine

<p>HEXPRESS™ is a full hexahedral unstructured mesh generator with anisotropic mesh capability. It features body-fitted meshes with a high quality boundary layer resolution which results from an efficient inflation technique.</p>
<p>ISIS is a time accurate incompressible free surface RANS code (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes) as presented in detail by <i>Duvigneau et al. (2003)</i> and <i>Queutey and Visonneau (2007)</i>. The spatial discretization of the transport equations is accomplished by a finite volume method. The velocity field is obtained from the momentum conservation equations and the pressure field is extracted from the mass conservation constraint, or continuity equation, transformed into a pressure equation, <i>Schrooyen et al. (2014)</i>. Pressure-velocity coupling is obtained through a Rhie & Chow SIMPLE type method. No specific requirements for the topology of the cells are imposed. The grid can be completely unstructured and cells with an arbitrary number of arbitrarily-shaped faces are accepted. In the usual case of turbulent flows, additional transport equations for turbulent entities are introduced. Several turbulence models ranging from relatively simple one-equation Spalart-Almaras to advanced EARSM (Extended Algebraic Reynolds Stress) models, see <i>Duvigneau et al. (2003)</i>, are implemented. Furthermore, a DES (Detached Eddy Simulation) approach with SST as closure model near the walls is available. Free-surface flow is represented by a VOF (Volume-of-Fluid) technique with an interface capturing approach. Both non-miscible flow phases (air and water) are modelled through the use of a conservation equation for the volume fraction of phase. The free-surface location corresponds to an iso-surface with a volume fraction of 0.5. To avoid smearing of the interface, the volume fraction transport equations are discretized with a specific discretization scheme, which ensures the accuracy and sharpness of the interface, <i>Queutey and Visonneau (2007)</i>. Furthermore, the flow solver features 6 DoF-motion for the simulation of freely moving ships, <i>Leroyer and Visonneau (2005)</i>. Also, a unique adaptive grid refinement (AGR) technique coupled with automatic load balancing is implemented, which allows to refine and coarsen the numerical grid as the simulation proceeds, see <i>Wackers et al. (2010a/b, 2011, 2014)</i>. Several criteria to trigger the refinement are available such as geometrical ones for the free surface or gradient ones for the static pressure field. Finally, an overset grid method is implemented in the flow solver to allow for limitless body motions, without the constraints of deformed or sliding grids. To decrease interpolation errors in the overset interface, adaptive grid refinement can be used to automatically refine the background meshes in time and space and, hence, greatly increase computational efficiency. The solver is optimized for heavily distributed computing using domain decomposition and all features are fully compatible with each other.</p>
<p>CFView™ is a flow visualization system with highly automatable post processing that also incorporates marine specific plug-ins. Hence, high-quality visualizations of characteristic features such as wave patterns, the free surface, wetted surface as well as the calculation of forces, momentum and angles can be realized.</p>

The flow solver's Volume-of-Fluid approach demands a fine mesh perpendicular to the free surface for an accurate capturing of the waves. The anisotropic mesh option within HEXPRESS™ supports the creation of cells which are large along the free surface and very small perpendicular to it. Moreover, the initial free surface refinement is done by the C-Wizard itself (and, if needed, further refinements could be accomplished at runtime via the Adaptive Grid Refinement technique). Fig.9 gives impressions of the mesh.

Fig.9: HEXPRESS™ mesh for the hard-chine motor boat: High-quality hexahedral grid with suitable regions of refinement (e.g. around the free surface) and seamless viscous layer insertion

Finally, the viscous layers around the wetted surfaces are automatically inserted according to the requirements of the turbulence model. Here a wall function and the two-equation SST model were

applied with ideal values of y^+ around 30 for all the geometries investigated. Naturally, accurately controlling the boundary layer resolution is of vital importance when comparing variants on the basis of viscous flow simulations. The meshing technique used here gave around 2.6 million cells for each variant with only slight alterations in the cell counts. The minimum orthogonality was greater than 10° , with only a few cells being below 20° , while the inflation technique led to smooth expansion ratios. Fulfilling both of these metrics to a high degree forms the basis of stable and accurate numerical solutions.

Following the mesh generation, FINE™/Marine's tool domhydro was run to evaluate the hydrostatics of each variant. It returns an estimate for the inertia tensor based on the hull form as well as center of gravity and displacement (or draft), depending on the operating mode. The data are then transferred to the pre-processor and the simulation set-up is finalized by the C-Wizard without any need of interaction, including the definition of the vessel's speed, the degrees-of-freedom (here sinkage and trim) and the boundary conditions.

3.2. Flow analysis

When simulating boats and ships at higher speeds it is important to treat certain aspects with greater care than for standard displacement ships at lower speeds: At high Froude numbers the hydrodynamic forces greatly impact the equilibrium position, and so does the propulsion point. The latter was modeled using a wrench definition for the propulsion anchor point (i.e., the position of the propeller) as well as the thrust direction (i.e., the propeller's shaft direction with respect to the vessel's floating position at rest), Fig.10. The flow solver automatically balances the virtual thrust applied to the wrench versus the current total drag of the vessel. Hence one can account for the propulsion point's impact on the vessel position without having to actually mesh and simulate the propeller. This greatly reduces the simulation time. A second aspect common to high Froude number vessels is a numerical phenomenon known as streaking, Fig.11. It leads to non-physical mass fractions below the hull, suggesting ventilation which would not occur in reality. There are quite a few potential reasons for this, such as resolution and quality of the mesh. In FINE™/Marine a dedicated numerical correction can be activated that is applied in the boundary layer only. This fixes the mass fraction field below the hull and, consequently, delivers a physically sound numerical solution. For the optimization presented here this correction was applied to all designs.

Fig.10: Center of gravity (grey dot) and propulsion point and direction (orange vector)

The flow solver automatically returns integral values like hull forces and moments acting on the vessel for all time steps, decomposed in x-, y- and z-direction (Fig.10) as well as viscous and pressure components. All designs were run for 1500 time steps, which ensured a completely converged solution in terms of both hull forces and vessel motions. From these data the main output required for the optimization was generated, namely total resistance as the average of the last 200 iterations. In addition, plots for the wave elevation and the static pressure distribution along the hull were produced for comparison, see also Figs.13 and 14.

Fig.11: Non-physical mass fraction field (streaking) for high-speed vessel (left) vs. corrected field using streaking correction (right) (Shown by courtesy of Light Craft Design Group)

4. Simulation and optimization in the Cloud

High Performance Computing (HPC) enables to solve challenging CAE tasks and to process and centralize big data sets. In simulation-driven design a temporary shift or even the complete transition of in-house resources to an external HPC provider is increasingly seen as an attractive solution by many industries (e.g. automotive, maritime and offshore, aerospace). This is due to scalability, flexibility and agility, in particular when working on tasks of high complexity and in teams across departments or even across companies.

The simulation of large models with a very high number of grid points, design optimizations with many variants to study and multi-disciplinary problems involving several simulation tools are typical examples of applying HPC to great advantage. Importantly, since commercial solvers have become nicely scalable, applications can be parallelized, yielding an almost linear speed-up on thousands of cores with hardly any loss of performance.

4.1. Technical set-up

The environment offered by CPU 24/7 and used for the optimization of the motor boat comprises on-demand computing power, custom-made and dedicated HPC systems with a completely pre-configured, secure and easy-to-use remote CAE set-up. It is an all-inclusive package taking in the HPC instance on “bare-metal” servers, the desired CAD and CFD applications, storage, data traffic and comprehensive support.

For the motor boat loads of variants were investigated on 6x 24 Cores Intel Xeon E5-2690v3 with a total of 144 cores, 0.784 TB RAM and unlimited storage and, furthermore, on 3x 28 Cores E5-2690v4 with a total of 84 cores, 0.384 TB RAM and unlimited storage. On the 24 core machines the simulation of a single variant took about 12 hours of clock time. (An acceleration of 35.1% could be achieved on Intel Xeon E5-2690v4 when compared to Intel Xeon E5-2690v3.)

A UNIVA Grid Engine was chosen for the automatic submission of jobs, allowing a maximum utilization of available cluster resources. For configuration and monitoring a GPU-accelerated remote visualization with NVIDIA graphic cards was employed. For graphical visualizations within CAESSES[®] a NoMachine cloud server with access to 30 remote compute and remote nodes was established. This browser based access is particularly interesting in the context of CAE applications: The engineers are able to start and monitor their jobs and put them into the installed queueing engine. Moreover, it delivers a secure web-based and easy-to-use single point of access to all desktops via a standard browser, giving ready access from the designer’s computer at work (and, if desired, from the notebook at home).

4.2. Security and software aspects

Security and license management play an important role when shifting workloads to the external resources. The HPC bare-metal Cloud as provided by CPU 24/7 is characterized by a number of key security provisions, comprising highest IT and physical security, see Table II for details.

Other important requirements for HPC “as-a-service” are workload scheduling as well as availability and adaptiveness of both hard- and software. The latter can be realized by means of an intelligent license management as offered, for instance, via “NUMECA On Demand.” It combines flexible HPC resources with an on-demand license management for FINE™/Marine (and other NUMECA tools). The dynamic aspect of HPC Cloud computing creates a need for flexible, time-dependent license allocation. For small and medium-sized companies with widely fluctuating workloads on-demand models provide a good means to scale up their resources as the design task calls for.

Table II: Security provisions in the Cloud as addressed by CPU 24/7

Data Centre Security: The HPC clusters are located at an ISO 27001 certified, verifiable, high-security computing center in Berlin, Germany. The equipment in the data center conforms to the Level TIER 4 and includes redundant infrastructures, access controls, authorization concepts and video monitoring.
Server Security: Each customer is provided with a non-virtualized, customized simulation environment with access to exclusively dedicated and private bare-metal servers. The solution is not based on a shared IT infrastructure and, consequently, its use is confined to the specific client.
Network Security: Customers and their data are isolated by completely separate systems. In technical terms the connection and operation are equivalent to adding an additional business location. For communication secure industry standard and authenticated connections and protocols with basic encryption are used (e.g. SCP, SSH, SFTP).
Application and Platform Security: A well-integrated, effective patch and change management, to avoid operating faults and minimize security vulnerabilities (which can be quickly resolved), is carried out.
Data Security: Data is stored solely in the German high security data center and is handled in accordance with the Germany’s Federal Data Protection Act and the Federal Office for Information Security (BSI). Data deletion is executed according to common data deletion standards. Data media not in use any more are destroyed by appropriate means.

5. Optimization and results

5.1. Coupling FINE™/Marine and CAESES®

Two modes of coupling the software suites of FINE™/Marine and CAESES® are available: Either the grid generator and flow solver within FINE™/Marine are run in batch mode and CAESES® takes care of the process control, generating variants and executing the external codes during an optimization, or – as an alternative – CAESES® is run in batch mode to deliver the geometry, triggered and controlled by NUMECA’s FINE™/Design3D. For the optimization of the motor boat the former approach was chosen and executed on the external resources provided by CPU 24/7.

In principle, any external code can be coupled to CAESES® by using a set of input and output files that capture the entire simulation(s) that shall be performed for each variant. In order to produce all necessary in- and outputs, typically, a test run is conducted for the baseline. All necessary input files and all output files of interest are collected. They are subsequently utilized as templates within CAESES®.

For each new variant the input files are compiled, the simulations are executed and, in conclusion, selected data items from the outputs are read for assessment. For FINE™/Marine in the context of the motor boat optimization the input files are the STL-file that describes the flow domain containing the current variant, the C-Wizard text file defining both the grid generation and flow analysis and, finally, some auxiliary files providing information on the hardware to be used. The output files are CSV files (comma separated value) showing the convergence history along with data on forces and the floating position and, moreover, a VTK file (Visualization Toolkit) with the associated flow field. More details are given in *Harries and Abt (2016)*.

5.2. Optimization

Optimization is not a black-box process but, normally, comprises several steps of exploring the design space and trying to squeeze out performance as much as possible, see *Harries (2015)* for an overview. Even though a range of operating conditions could be looked at when optimizing a product, here only the performance at one condition was chosen, namely the total resistance at 18 kn for a displacement of 1.3 m³. (This is a standard approach if the simulations are complex and take quite some resources.

At the end only a handful of designs are checked for other conditions, too, as was done here for a range of speeds.)

While the parametric model for the entire hull comprises several dozens of parameters, only nine parameters were selected for the optimization (Fig.5). These free variables were the overall beam (allowed to change from 2.1 to 2.3 m), the transom's deadrise (from 12° to 16°), the rocker (from 0.13 to 0.17 m at the transom), two values for the hollowness of the planing surface and four parameters controlling the spray rail, among them the width of the spray rail at the stern (0.04 to 0.06 m). (Even though the overall length would influence performance tangibly, it was fixed here since the design task was to keep the boat a bit below 6 m.)

Apart from some quality checks on the tessellation and the domain as input to the grid generation only one inequality constraint was taken into account, namely, the displacement volume of the boat which ought to be greater than 1.25 m³ at a draft of 0.32 m, i.e., before the hull was floated into position (via domhydro) for the targeted displacement volume of 1.3 m³.

Fig.12: Screen shot showing the DesignViewer within CAESES® for a quick comparison of variants

A set of 100 variants was investigated in a first design-of-experiment (DoE), running a Sobol sequence as explained in *Harries (2015)* and elaborated in *Press et al. (2007)*. Taking the rule-of-thumb of the square of the number of free variables in order to understand the design space, $9^2 = 81 < 100$, this is slightly above the recommended minimum number of variants. Fig.12 shows a side-to-side comparison of several of these (quasi-)randomly generated boats.

Setting out from the DoE several additional optimization strategies were employed. One strategy was based on a surrogate model (or response surface approach) as provided by CAESES® via a tight

integration of Dakota by Sandia, <https://dakota.sandia.gov>. Another strategy was a deterministic local search from one of the favorable designs found during the DoE. This was done by means of a T-Search, i.e., a pattern search readily observing inequality constraints as introduced by *Hilleary (1966)*.

5.3. Selected results

While the baseline featured a total resistance of $R_T = 1572$ N several improved designs could be identified from both the exploration and the exploitation. One design from the DoE, namely DOE_13_des0045, already yielded a resistance as low as $R_T = 1476$ N which amounts to a reduction of 6.1%. The best design found, variant TSearch_des0007 produced in a T-Search run, gave a resistance of $R_T = 1461$ N. This is a further improvement of 1% when compared to the best DoE design from which the deterministic search was launched and an overall improvement of 7% over the baseline.

Fig.13 shows the front view of six variants, including the baseline, the best from the DoE and the final and best design identified. The corresponding hull lines can be seen in Fig.5. Fig.14 compares waves and pressure plots for the baseline and the best design. The best design most notably features a beamer hull and a certain hollowness of the planing surface which indicates a slight tunneling in the stern region.

Fig.13: Wave pattern around hull for different variants

Fig.14: Comparison of free surface elevation around the stern and pressure distribution over the planing surface for the baseline and the best design (TSearch_des0007)

For both the baseline and the best design a resistance-speed investigation was conducted from 10 to 20 kn. This is depicted in Fig.15. It can be nicely seen that the best design performs better from 12 to 20 kn. The better performance at 18 kn is appreciable while resistance at a speed of 20 kn is almost the same. Judging from the gradient of the resistance-speed curve it can be expected that the baseline would have a lower resistance at speeds higher than 20 kn. Changes in the trim angle are notable, too. Apparently, the baseline needs slightly larger angles (of attack) above 15 kn.

Assuming that Carlo Riva had very high maximum speeds in mind, this demonstrates how well he designed the lines of the Riva Junior. (It needs to be kept in mind, though, that the baseline does not represent the hull form exactly.) It also allows the statement that higher performance is attainable for the motor boat by means of simulation-driven design for a specific design point without sudden performance deterioration in off-design conditions.

Fig.15: Total resistance in N (left) and trim angle in degrees and (right) over speed in kn

6. Conclusions

A high-speed hard-chine motor boat was parametrically modeled within CAESES[®] and simulated for calm-water hydrodynamics with FINE[™]/Marine. An automated optimization was carried out so as to improve total resistance at a Froude number of $F_{nLDWL} = 1.32$. A resistance reduction of around 7% could be found. Since viscous free-surface simulations for planing hulls need tangible computer resources the simulation-driven design campaign was not done on local hardware typical of a design office but rather on the bare metal resources of a secure external HPC provider. The project demonstrates that the hydrodynamic optimization of a power boat in the Cloud is feasible, bearing lots of potential for smaller offices but also for larger companies.

FINE[™]/Marine's new C-Wizard was utilized for a quick and easy set-up of accurate computations. CAESES[®] was employed to build a dedicated engineering model for the motor boat as needed for optimization. Different to traditional production-centric CAD approaches the parametric model within CAESES[®] delivers shapes that are ready for simulation. CAESES[®] provides shapes in the format readily used by HEXPRESS[™] for high-end grid generation, namely STL files that feature water-tight tri-meshes, including color codes for domain boundaries. The process chain consisting of CAESES[®] and FINE[™]/Marine as run on the HPC at CPU 24/7 is both robust and agile. Different to the typical failure rates of 20 to 30% seen in traditional CAD systems when regenerating geometry for changes in the input parameters, CAESES[®] delivers water-tight flow domains for all variants. FINE[™]/Marine takes care of producing high-quality grids and offers the sophisticated flow simulation needed for the design of high-performance marine vehicles.

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Opportunities for Cost Effective Composite Solutions for Future Ships

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Abstract

Composite materials offer great freedom to develop lightweight components and structures for designers and engineers. However inherently they require a significant amount of specialist expertise during design, manufacturing and maintenance. STRUCTeam, founded in 2010, supports its clients in the development of structures made of composite material across market sectors including the marine and shipping industry. The authors will focus on presenting the tangible benefits for end users in the various segments of the marine and shipping industry using industry examples to illustrate the findings. A methodology to assess opportunities will be presented.

1. Introduction

The composites market has been expanding rapidly in the last 30 years in the aerospace, automotive, renewables, oil & gas and sports markets, but not in the commercial marine market. Other forms of transportation (aerospace, rail, automotive) have recently adopted the use of composites to increase fuel efficiency and increase payload following the global increase in fuel costs. However, due to many factors, the commercial marine market does not follow this trend.

The following chapters aim to prove the effectiveness of composites on the lifecycle costs of vessels in the commercial marine industry through an introduction to composites, the regulations with regards to composites and the costs and benefits involved with using composites in vessels.

2. Brief Introduction on Composites

2.1. Composites definition

Composite materials are a mix of fibre, typically glass or carbon fibre, with a matrix to distribute the load between the fibres, typically polyester, vinylester or epoxy. These material combinations provide a wide and highly customisable range of costs and mechanical and physical properties when combined with selection of manufacturing processes. These materials can be stacked into a laminate with fibres oriented along the load paths.

Core materials such as PVC, PET and Balsa wood can be used to increase inertia of laminates without a dramatic increase in weight. Additives can also be added to the matrix material to improve fire resistance alongside coatings for environmental resistance. The largest use of composites is in the low cost and performance sectors, such as leisure, small RIB's, cabin boats, cruising yachts and low cost workboats. Composites are also used in unregulated vessels with special requirements for example military ships.

2.2. Regulations

The level of regulation on each sector in marine is varied depending on the type and use of the vessel. The main challenge when using composites is in the highly regulated sector of mega power yachts, shipping and workboats; all regulated by IMO SOLAS (International Maritime Organisation for the Safety of Lives at Sea). IMO SOLAS specifies according to Regulation II-2/11 that ship structures are to be constructed of steel or other equivalent material, where an equivalent material is non-combustible as specified in SOLAS Regulation II-2/3.43. This becomes a challenge for lightweight materials such as composites and aluminium.

Materials which can be proved as an equivalent to steel have a chance of being accepted. However with no clear performance parameters, this leads to high cost and risk with no guarantee of approval.

3. Opportunities for Composites in the Marine Sector

3.1. Opportunities

Although there may be a challenge from regulations in certain vessel types, there are still opportunities to use composites in certain areas. Ancillary products such as railings, stairs, light columns, davits, small deck structures, walkways and balconies are not regulated by SOLAS and can be designed with other materials.

Opportunities in the ferries/cruise ship sector would benefit from the weight saving in the cabins, superstructure and internal bulkheads, leading to a higher fuel efficiency, increase in stability, which could possibly lead to a removal of ballast systems, creating more storage or cabin space which leads to an increase in capacity.

The same benefits can be seen on cargo vessels, where composites could be utilised in topside structures, accommodation blocks and cargo hatch covers. Additional benefits come from each composite component; for example, reducing the weight of the cargo hatch by 50% leads to easier crane handling and lighter motors. In addition, the anti-corrosion properties of composite lead to a better seal performance and longevity, reducing the risk of damage to cargo.

3.2. Example

3.2.1 Composite Patrol Vessel

STRUCTeam has undertaken the case study of a 60ft patrol vessel, shown in Fig. 1, operating at a max speed of 40kts, assuming a series production of 10 boats, with the aim to compare the overall costs of different composite solutions, benchmarked against an aluminium vessel.

Selecting the most suited technology for a 60' composite patrol boat is a complex challenge with high number of variables. With the help of a well-structured design process, smart engineering and novel software solutions the task can be tackled efficiently and the most feasible alternative can be found in an optimal way.

Fig.1: Typical 60ft Patrol Vessel

STRUCTeam takes into account multiple considerations when designing any product:

- What reinforcing material is to be used: glass fibres, carbon fibres or hybrid?
- What resin technology is best?
- What core material should we use? PET or PVC foam, possibly Balsa?
- What manufacturing process is preferred: infusion or prepreg?
- How many patrol boats are we planning to manufacture?
- Cost of the prototype and cost of the series products?

- Tooling and manufacturing costs?
- Estimated operation related costs of the vessels?
- Estimated maintenance cost of the vessels?
- Project timeline?

Every options influence the total project cost. Tooling cost is in direct coherence with the chosen technology. Prepreg technology requires more complex and costly solutions than infusion. In this case, raw material costs also significantly more. On the other hand you have more performance and quality, easier handling and workmanship for the boat builder. Weighing the benefits versus the drawbacks requires detailed knowledge of the manufacturing processes and the materials, also a thorough analysis of cost related to manufacturing, designing, certifying and later on operating, fueling and manning the vessel.

Fig.2: Comparison of weight vs. material costs

Fig.3: Budget costs for 30 years

As can be seen from Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the CAPEX costs are directly linked with the weight, with an increase in cost giving a larger weight saving. This weight saving is also linked with the budget costs for 30 years. With an €800,000 cost saving over 30years between the Glass/Infusion/PET foam and Carbon Prepreg/PVC foam versions.

Based on the technical and economical assessment of this project, the most viable option is to make these vessels using carbon fibre reinforced composites with PVC core and utilizing infusion process (minimizing both CAPEX and OPEX for the boat builder and the operator).

Considerations such as build time, material cost and certification and design costs would favour the aluminium option, however regarding the ability to repair the structure in case of accidental damage, the composite options offer repair strategies similar to aluminium. This needs developing together with the operator during the design and manufacture of the boat. When looking at OPEX expenditure, the costs are 5-7% higher for aluminium vessels, compared to composite versions.

4. Method to assess opportunities

The method presented above is applicable to any structure where composites are considered. The decision to use composites for Marine and Offshore structures will often be motivated by lifecycle benefits generated by composites rather than the high performance intrinsic properties of composites. This has been illustrated in the above case study with the lower fuel costs resulting in the composites options to be very attractive in the long term for the manufacture of 60' patrol boats.

5. Conclusion

Composites give a lot of freedom due to all of the variables involved in material choice and manufacturing process choice; however present large CAPEX costs in comparison to metallic designs. Composites are proved in the long-term, increasing fuel efficiency, decreasing weight and therefore increasing payload and stability. Composites also show benefits with a low requirement for maintenance and easy repairability. The advantages of composite vessels can be seen in the adopted use in high speed ferries, where the OPEX is considered the first priority and regulating organisations are writing composite specific regulations.

However, the main challenge in the large commercial marine industry is the adoption of composites in ships by the regulating organisations, specifically proving fire retardancy equal to steel.

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STRUCTeam engineers have 120 years of accumulated experience in the design of cost effective composite structures.

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Biomimetic Super-Hydrophobic Coatings for Friction Reduction

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Abstract

Motivated by the lotus leaf and its self-cleaning properties, which stems from its hydrophobic nature, we investigated the design and application of bioinspired super-hydrophobic materials for turbulent skin-friction reduction. Commonly referred to as the lotus effect, super-hydrophobic surfaces are best known for their resistance to wetting and high-contact angles, exceeding 150°. When coupled with a low surface energy material with hierarchical nano and micro scale surface roughness, these properties may be utilized to minimize frictional resistance in water flows. In this discussion, we present the design, fabrication, and evaluation of super-hydrophobic surfaces that have been shown to provide sustained skin-friction reduction in turbulent flows.

1. Introduction

Nature has provided an exhaustive source of evolutionary functional materials to be mimicked for everyday applications, *Bhushan and Jung (2011)*. One notable case relevant to the marine environment is the lotus leaf which is known for its self-cleaning properties and resistance to wetting, *Barthlott and Neinhuis (1997)*. More specifically, lotus inspired super-hydrophobic surfaces (SHSs) have been biomimetically developed for skin-friction reduction in various flow applications, *Koch et al. (2009)*, *Samaha et al. (2012)*. Exhaustively studied in small-scale laminar flows [see *Rothstein (2010)* for a review of SHS drag reduction and slip on SHSs], advances in the design and fabrication of SHSs have permitted application of these materials in more naval relevant flows.

A smooth surface can be characterized by its surface energy and the apparent contact angle (θ^*) it makes with a drop of water. When the contact angle between a low surface energy material and a droplet exceeds 150°, Fig.1a-1b, and maintains a low contact angle hysteresis [defined as the difference between the advancing (θ_A) and receding contact angles (θ_R)], the surface is classified as super-hydrophobic. A large contact angle generally signifies a reduced wetted area and an ease of relative motion between the liquid/water and the underlying solid surface. Coupling this resistance to wetting with micro (and nano) scale roughness, a SHS can retain air pockets such that an air-liquid interface is maintained (where the liquid is water), which acts to reduce the local shear stress and may provide a slip length (λ_s) of approximately 10's of *microns*. These physical properties provide a passive and potentially more efficient alternative to the traditional means of drag reduction, for example gas injection, i.e. ALDR, BDR, PCDR. Fig.1c shows a schematic representation of a SHS with an air-water interface and the associated idealized slip on the solid-liquid and air-liquid interfaces. *Golovin et al. (2016)* recently reviewed bioinspired surfaces for turbulent drag reduction and highlighted some of the differences that need to be addressed when applying SHSs in turbulent flows.

Previous SHS drag reduction studies, including but not limited to the work of *Watanabe et al. (1999)*, *Ou et al. (2004)*, *Ou and Rothstein (2005)*, *Zhao et al. (2008)*, *Woolford et al. (2009)*, and *Daniello et al. (2009)*, have shown that SHSs can reduce drag in laminar flow. However, application of such surfaces for skin-friction reduction in wall-bounded, high-Reynolds number, turbulent flows has been less successful. More specifically, SHS drag reduction has been limited to low-Reynolds number turbulent flows using small-scale, structured surfaces and large air-water interfaces, *Henoch et al.;*

(2006), *Daniello et al. (2009)*, *Park et al. (2014)*, which can be unstable or become wetted with increased turbulence; or SHSs with small roughness scales, relative to the viscous length scale of the flow, *Aljallis et al. (2013)*, *Bidkar et al. (2014)*, *Ling et al. (2016)*. Under other conditions *Zhao et al. (2008)*, *Aljallis et al. (2013)*, *Bidkar et al. (2014)*, *Hokmabad and Ghaemi (2016)* measured no change or a drag increase in the presence of a SHS. *Tian et al. (2015)* and *Zhang et al. (2015)* also measured skin-friction reduction, up to 10 and 24% respectively, in turbulent boundary layer flows. The mixed results from this brief review raises doubts about both the effectiveness and mechanisms of super-hydrophobic drag reduction in turbulent flows, and thus warrants further investigation, particularly for the application of SHSs in large-scale, high-Reynolds number flows.

A group led by the University of Michigan as part of a Multidisciplinary University Research Initiative has developed a series of sprayable super-hydrophobic coatings that can be applied over larger areas, on the order of tens of square meters or more. This development is enhancing the understanding of the physics of flows along SHSs, and the potential for friction reduction in high-Reynolds number naval or mechanical hydraulic applications. These skin-friction reducing sprayable surfaces are now being systematically designed and fabricated for specific flow types and specific flow applications.

This discussion will focus on the theory, design, and application of SHS; and efficacy of the SHSs in fully-developed turbulent channel flow. We will also briefly highlight more recent findings for the application of SHSs for drag reduction in external turbulent boundary layer flows.

2. Super-Hydrophobic Surface Design and Fabrication

Engineered SHSs, as in nature, are comprised of a low-surface energy material with an underlying surface structure, typically consisting of micro-scale geometric post and/or ridges, or random texture elements that trap air between the solid and liquid if the Cassie-Baxter state, *Cassie and Baxter (1944)* is maintained. *Cassie and Baxter (1944)* proposed that the apparent contact angle is the weighted average of the water droplet contact angle on a smooth, chemically identical surface [θ^Y as defined by *Young (1805)*] and air, as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\cos\theta^* = r_\phi \phi_s \cos\theta^Y + (1 - \phi_s) \cos\pi \quad (1)$$

Here r_ϕ is the ratio of surface area wetted by liquid water to its projected surface area and ϕ_s is the areal fraction of the surface that is wetted by water, *Choi et al. (2009)*. From this equation we conclude that a large contact angle can be achieved with a very small ϕ_s , a very large r_ϕ , or a combination of both.

In addition to achieving large apparent contact angles with water droplets, super-hydrophobic coatings can greatly reduce the hydrodynamic skin-friction of a flow by altering the no-slip boundary condition. The presence of a composite solid-liquid-air interface acts to reduce the near-wall interaction between water and the underlying solid, and thus permits a local slip length (λ_s) and an enhanced wall slip velocity (u_s). The slip length and velocity were defined by *Navier (1823)* as

$$u_s = \lambda_s \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} \quad (2)$$

where $\partial u/\partial n$ is the wall normal velocity gradient, which is directly proportional to the wall shear-stress. Altering the slip condition results in a lower energy requirement to achieve flow speed, and thus may correlate to a skin-friction reduction. A schematic of slip over a geometric SHS is shown in Fig.1c.

Hence, the key to designing a SHS that may positively interact with flowing liquid over it is to

maintain a large contact angle, with a small wetted area, and consequently, a large liquid-gas region. This increases the area over which streamwise slip may be enhanced. It is also important to note that the presence of the required roughness features needed may actually result in a drag increase if the size of the features is large compared to the viscous sublayer (defined below).

Fig.1: (a) Water repellency of a SHS used in this effort showing multiple dyed water drops on the surface and (b) a measured contact angle of 173° . (c) Slip on SHS: A schematic of the three phase interface that can form on a SHS. At the solid-liquid interface the liquid velocity matches the wall velocity at the wall, or the imposed no-slip condition. However, the velocity at the liquid-air interface can be non-zero, corresponding to a non-zero slip length.

We designed and fabricated several SHS coatings and materials that were applied in multiple flow applications. These surfaces were previously described by *Gose et al. (2016)* for channel flow and all displayed $\theta^* > 166^\circ$ and $\Delta\theta < 3^\circ$, when measured using the conventional goniometric technique. A tabulated description of these surfaces can be seen in Table I. Variations of these surfaces with very similar properties were also implemented in an external boundary layer flow.

Surface #1 was fabricated by spray coating a blend of a fluorinated polyurethane (FPU) polyol with a highly hydrophobic molecule, fluorodecyl polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (F-POSS). A 40 ml volume of the solution was sprayed onto a 1.2 m x 0.10 m stainless steel substrate using an ATD Tools 6903 high volume, low pressure spray gun with compressed air at a pressure of 140 kPa. The sample was cured at 80°C for 72 hours in an ambient environment using a silicone heating pad.

Surface #2 was fabricated by forming a solution of fast-curing superglue (SF-100, 3M) and the same F-POSS molecules as above in equal mass fractions in Asahiklin-225 at a concentration of 50 mg/mL. The morphology of this surface was altered in some cases such that the new surfaces are either rougher or smoother than the original (denoted Surface #2a and Surface #2b, respectively).

Surface #3 consisted of a blend of the fluorinated polyurethane polyol and crosslinker from Surface #1 and fluoro-functionalized silica nanoparticles. A 25 mg/mL solution of these components was formed in Vertrel XF, with 35% of the total mass of silica particles. A total of 20 mL of this solution was sonicated, and then sprayed and cured using the same procedures as for Surface #1. This surface derives its roughness from the silica nanoparticles, not the spraying process as with Surfaces #1 and all three variants of #2, and in this way the roughness was smaller compared to the other sprayed surfaces.

Fig.2: SEM micrographs of Surface #1 at two different scales

Fig.3: SEM micrographs of Surface #2, #2a (rougher) and #2b (smoother). Each reference scale bar (white line) represents 200 μm .

Fig.4: SEM micrographs of Surface #3 at two different scales

Surface #4 was formed through chemically etching aluminium sheets, rather than the spray-coated Surfaces #1 - #3. First, 200 mm x 100 mm x 3 mm (8" x 4" x 1/8") aluminium sheets were sanded

using 220 grit sandpaper to remove any surface roughness defects. Each sheet was submerged into 2.5 M hydrochloric acid for 20 minutes. The sheets were washed with deionized water and placed in a sonication bath after etching to remove any physisorbed aluminium flakes from the surface. The sheets were then boiled in deionized water for 20 minutes. The boiling of aluminium is known to generate nanostructured crystallites of aluminium oxyhydroxide (the boehmite phase) through the reaction $2Al + 6H_2O = 2AlO(OH) + 3H_2$. After boiling, the sheets are blown dry with air and placed in a vacuum oven at 80 °C with a vial of 1H,1H,2H,2H-Heptadecafluorodecyl triethoxysilane. A vacuum is pulled to less than 100 mTorr and the silane is left to react with the boehmite phase overnight. Finally, once silanized, the sheets are washed to remove any physisorbed silane. Five sheets were fabricated and tiled to cover a 1.0 m long substrate that was attached to the upper wall of the test section.

Fig.5: SEM micrographs of Surface #4 at two different scales

The commercially available coating NeverWet[®] (Ross Nanotechnology, LLC) was also fabricated and sprayed on a 1.20 m x 0.10 m substrate per manufacturer instructions. This was the seventh surface tested. First, a basecoat is sprayed once and allowed to cure for 30 minutes at ambient temperature. Next, the topcoat is applied and allowed to dry for two minutes. The application of the topcoat was repeated three additional times, per manufacturer recommendation. Then the final coating is allowed to cure for 24 hours. SEM micrographs of the NeverWet[®] surface features can be found in *Aljallis et al. (2013)*, *Zhang et al. (2015)*, and *Hokmabad and Ghaemi (2016)*.

Table I: Properties and descriptions of SHSs evaluated in the turbulent channel. Variations of these surfaces were also tested in the turbulent boundary layer facility.

Surface Number	Contact angle, θ^* (deg)	Contact angle hysteresis, $\Delta\theta^*$ (deg)	Areal fraction, ϕ_s	RMS surface roughness, S_q (μm)	Non-dimensional surface roughness range, k^+
1 (FPU + F-POSS)	163	3	0.09	18±1	2.4 – 4.9
2 (SF100 + F-POSS)	161	1	0.11	6.4±0.8	0.62 – 0.98
2a (rougher)	162	1	0.10	8.5±0.4	1.2 – 1.6
2b (smoother)	169	0.5	0.04	2.7±0.3	0.16 – 0.34
3 (FPU + f-SiO ₂)	173	2	0.02	2.2±0.2	0.11 – 0.40
4 (Etched Al)	170	1	0.03	4.7±0.7	0.47 – 1.3
NeverWet [®]	166	1	0.04	13±2	1.2 – 2.9

3. Experimental Procedure

Our group has investigated these SHSs, first in a fully-developed turbulent flow channel at the University of Michigan, and later, variations of some of these SHSs in an external turbulent boundary layer flow at the U.S. Naval Academy. In the following sections, we explain the experimental facilities and procedures for evaluating the performance of the SHSs. We discuss in detail the results from the internal flow and highlight some of the preliminary findings from the external boundary layer experiments.

3.1. Fully-Developed Turbulent Channel Flow

The fully developed channel flow facility used in this work is schematically and pictorially shown in Fig.6, and was previously described by *Gose et al. (2016)*. The test section dimensions are nominally 0.0073 m in height H , 0.10 m in width W , and 1.2 m in length L , resulting in a W/H cross-sectional ratio of $\sim 14:1$. This high aspect ratio yields a two-dimensional flow through the core of the channel, *Dean (1978)*, *Monty (2005)*, as well as yields near-wall turbulent structures and Reynolds stresses comparable to that of an external boundary layer, *Schultz and Flack (2013)*. The facility was specifically designed to provide high-fidelity pressure-drop measurements at wall-shear stress values comparable to that of marine vessels. Pressure drop measurements offer the simplest and most widely utilized method of measuring skin-friction for internal flows. Moreover, as channel flows are internal and have a confined outer length scale (channel height H or boundary layer thickness $\delta = H/2$), which is fixed by the opposing walls, scaling is no longer dependent on the spatial location. Rather, the scaling becomes solely dependent on the bulk-flow variables for the channel flow. These characteristics suggest that the use of a turbulent channel is suitable, and may even be favorable to that of an external boundary layer, for preliminary investigation of the fundamental mechanisms for drag reduction in turbulent flows.

The flow facility is coupled to a 11.2 kW centrifugal pump controlled by a variable frequency drive. The mean flow speeds obtained in the test section range from 1 to 20 ms^{-1} . The flow rate was set and measured using an ultrasonic flow meter with an accuracy of $\pm 1\%$. The flow speed was also validated using PIV analysis of the mean flow field, approximately $130H$ from the inlet of the test section. This allows for a height-based Reynolds number Re_H (based on the mean bulk velocity U_m) of up to 145,000, corresponding to a friction Reynolds number Re_τ of 3,200. A turbulence management section consisting of honeycomb and two screens were placed upstream of a two dimensional contraction with an area ratio of 30, which work in series to reduce the turbulence in the facility. The design principles of *Barlow et al. (1999)* and *Morel (1977)* were used in the design of the turbulence management components and contraction. The flow is tripped at the inlet of the test section using 50 grit, waterproof sandpaper.

The streamwise pressure was measured through a series of pressure ports, located along the lower wall of the test section, using three speed-matched differential pressure transducers. The pressure transducers have a manufacturers specified output accuracy of $\pm 0.04\%$ of the full scale range of the sensors. The streamwise pressure ports were placed in pairs, 16.67 mm on either side of the centerline, and longitudinally at $20H$, $30H$, $50H$, $70H$, $84H$, $98H$, $112H$, $126H$, $140H$, and $150H$ from the trip at the channel inlet. A development length of $30H$ was determined to be adequate for a fully-developed state; however, pressure drop measurements over the latter $100H$ of the test section were used to infer the skin-friction. First, the wall-shear stress (τ_w) was calculated using the pressure gradient, which was then used to determine the friction velocity (u_τ) and skin-friction coefficient (C_f), as shown below.

$$\tau_w = \frac{H}{2} \left| \frac{dP}{dx} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w / \rho} \quad (4)$$

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\frac{1}{2} \rho U_m^2} \quad (5)$$

In the above equations, ρ is the density of water and U_m is the mean speed at the center of the channel. We also use the conventional definitions for the viscous length scale (δ_ν) and non-dimensional roughness (k^+) as shown below, where ν is the kinematic viscosity of water and k is the RMS (k_{RMS}) or arithmetic mean roughness (k_a) of the surface.

$$\delta_\nu = \frac{\nu}{u_\tau} \quad (6)$$

$$k^+ = \frac{k}{\delta_\nu} \quad (7)$$

Fig.6: Test section schematic and image of the Skin-Friction Flow Facility (SF3)

Fig.7 presents the baseline skin-friction coefficient for a hydraulically smooth plate with a surface roughness $0.1 \mu\text{m}$. The results are in good agreement with skin-friction coefficients provided by *Dean (1978)* and *Zanoun et al. (2009)*. Figs. 8 and 9 show the measured skin-friction coefficient for one baseline lower wall and one SHS affixed to the upper wall. We can see that replacing even one wall (approximately half of the wetted area) with a SHS can greatly alter the pressure drop, and thus the skin-friction through the channel. Surfaces #1 and #2 show significant increases in friction over the

smooth wall. These surfaces also have the largest non-dimensional roughness ($k^+ \geq 1$) and largest solid-liquid area ratio at greater than 10% per unit area. Reducing these values provides a net savings in skin-friction as shown for Surfaces #3 and #4, which have a $k^+ \lesssim 1$. This logic was employed in the design and fabrication of the variations of Surface #2. Altering the spray formulation allow us to create a rougher version of Surface #2, #2a, and a smother version, #2b. These surface variations show that SHS drag reduction is highly dependent on the non-dimensional roughness of the surface and that SHSs do not necessarily abide by the idea that hydraulically smooth surfaces ($k^+ \lesssim 5$) do not inherently alter the flow. The effect of roughness is also apparent in the PIV results for the mean flow; however, this is not shown here due to space limitations.

Fig.7: The measured baseline skin-friction coefficient data plotted as a function of Re_H for fully-developed turbulent channel flow. Correlations by *Dean (1978)* and *Zanoun et al. (2009)* are shown for reference.

To investigate the effects of roughness on SHS drag reduction for the current work, we plot k^+ versus drag reduction (DR) in Fig.10. In the current work, the skin-friction was inferred from the streamwise pressure gradient measured along one hydraulically-smooth baseline and along each SHS. Therefore, the resulting skin-friction is the average of the baseline and the SHS. Consequently, a two-sided SHS test section is expected to provide twice the savings in skin-friction, as shown below.

$$DR = 2 \times \left(\frac{C_{f, \text{baseline}} - C_{f, \text{one-SHS}}}{C_{f, \text{baseline}}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Fig.10 shows that a drag increase ($DR < 0$) is measured $k^+ > 1$, while drag reduction is only achieved when $k^+ < 1$. This is in reasonable agreement with the results of *Bidkar et al. (2014)*, which first suggested that the non-dimensional roughness of a SHS must be less than one-tenth of the viscous sublayer ($0.5 \delta_v$) to achieve drag reduction in turbulent flow. Here we see that limit may be slightly higher, but also note that small non-dimensional roughness is not the only critical parameter needed to achieve SHS skin-friction savings in turbulent flow. Rather we suggest that SHS drag reduction in turbulent flow may also be highly dependent on its state of wetting, beyond that of maintaining the Cassie-Baxter state or transitioning to the Wenzel state, a state at which the near-wall flow would feel the full effect of the roughness. If the Cassie-Baxter state is maintained, the wetted features lying above the entrapped air should have a greater impact on the flow than those lying beneath the air.

That is to say, we expect that the wetted-area and the height of the wetted roughness elements should dictate drag savings or drag increases at a given flow condition. Nevertheless, we show that drag reduction significantly greater than 10% can be achieved for fully-developed turbulent flow along sprayed and chemically etched SHSs.

Fig.8: Coefficient of skin-friction plotted against height-based Reynolds number for the hydraulically-smooth baseline and each SHS, with the exception of Surfaces #2a and #2b, which are shown below. Variation in the skin-friction is due to the presence of only one SHS affixed to the upper wall of the test section. Replacing the lower baseline wall with a SHS is expected to provide approximately twice the difference shown. Correlations by *Dean (1978)* and *Zanoun et al. (2009)* are shown for reference.

3.2. External Turbulent Boundary Layer Flow

Variations of Surface #1 (denoted as SHS 1A, SHS 1D) and Surface #3 (denoted as FSIO2B) were evaluated at the U.S. Naval Academy in an external turbulent boundary layer facility with a test section measuring 2.0 m (L) x 0.2 m (W) x 0.2 m (H). An image of the recirculating water channel is shown in Fig.11. Measurements of near zero pressure gradient turbulent boundary layer flow over the SHSs are presented and compared to those for a hydraulically smooth baseline. A TSI FSA3500 two-component Laser-Doppler Velocimeter (LDV) and custom-designed beam displacer were operated in coincidence mode and used to measure the mean velocity profile along an interchangeable substrate at a test speed of 1.26 m/s, corresponding to a friction Reynolds number of about 1,500. The LDV probe volume diameter was 45 μm (approx. one wall-unit). The flow was tripped at the inlet with a 0.8 mm wire. The velocity measurements were acquired 1.5 m downstream of the wire-trip, resulting in development length of $\sim 40\delta$ (boundary layer height). The experiments were conducted over a period of approximately four to six hours. The results for the SHSs were compared directly to a hydraulically smooth baseline. When the measured quantities were non-dimensionalized using the inner variables, the results indicated a significant reduction in the near wall viscous and total stresses with little effect on the flow outside the inner layer.

Fig.9: Coefficient of skin-friction plotted against height-based Reynolds number for the hydraulically-smooth baseline and each variant of Surface #2. Variation in the skin-friction is due to the presence of only one SHS affixed to the upper wall of the test section. Replacing the lower baseline wall with a SHS is expected to provide approximately twice the difference shown. Correlations by *Dean (1978)* and *Zanoun et al. (2009)* are shown for reference.

Fig.10: Drag reduction plotted against non-dimensional roughness, k^+ .

The mean velocity profiles for the hydraulically smooth baseline and the SHSs are shown in Fig.12a for friction Reynolds number of approximately 1,500. The baseline data collapse well with the linear viscous region and the log law, using $\kappa = 0.41$ and $B = 5.0$. The mean velocity profile for the SHSs (when non-dimensionalized by the inner scales of the baseline) are offset vertically from the log law, which is likely related to the presence of the air-water interface, and thus generates an increased mean velocity. The wake and freestream flow are also shown. It is expected that the presence of larger roughness features could generate an increase in turbulent fluctuations, and in turn cause a reduction in mean velocity profile (similar to that of a rough wall); however, as the non-dimensional roughness

of SHSs is less than 1.5, this does not occur. Additionally, the SHSs have a clear increase in the mean velocity in the viscous sublayer region, and appear to have a reduced near-wall velocity gradient, i.e. a skin-friction reduction. The resolution of the current system does not appear to be adequate to extract the value of the velocity gradient; nevertheless, this will be explored further in future efforts.

Fig.11: Image of the recirculating turbulent boundary layer facility that was used in this work. The facility is located at the U.S. Naval Academy and has been used in numerous turbulent boundary layer experiments by Professors Michael Schultz and Karen Flack. The LDV system is shown on the right, while the SHS is evident in the bottom wall of the facility.

Fig.12b shows profiles of the viscous, Reynolds, and total shear stress for the baseline and SHSs, each non-dimensionalized using the smooth wall friction velocity (u_τ) for a direct comparison. The smooth wall stress profiles follow the historical trends; however, the SHSs stress profiles exhibit some deviation. First, a substantial decrease in the near-wall viscous stress results in a significant reduction in the total stress, regardless of an increased Reynolds stress at the wall. Despite these competing effects an overall reduction in the total stress at the wall of 20 to 50% is measured. The authors also note that the peak value of the Reynolds and total stresses drastically increase and move from the wall. This effect is still being investigated, is likely not only dependent on the RMS roughness of the surface, but also on the thickness of the air plastron and its mobility.

Although, we only present the results for a single SHS, we have collected data for eight SHSs with either different sized roughness features or entirely different formulations. These data have been reviewed and are currently being processed. The data for each SHS appears to have notable similarities with the data presented here. Additional data analysis and validation, as well as an error analysis is currently underway.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have designed and fabricated scalable SHSs that are capable of providing meaningful drag reduction in turbulent flow relevant to many naval applications. The surfaces were fabricated with large apparent contact angles, small contact angle hysteresis, and small non-dimensional roughness, which in turn resulted in SHSs that positively interacted with the inner region of the flow. Pressure drop measurements in an internal turbulent channel showed that a net decrease in the frictional loss of greater than 10% could be achieved when a single wall was replaced with a SHS. Moreover, turbulent boundary layer measurements over SHSs showed a net increase in the mean velocity and a 20-50% decrease in the wall viscous stress, which offset the increase in the near-wall Reynolds stress. As a result, we conclude that SHSs can be designed and applied for friction reduction and energy conservation in turbulent flows of interest to marine applications.

Fig.12: (a) Mean velocity profiles for the hydraulically smooth baseline (black circles) and SHSs at a friction Reynolds number of 1,500, non-dimensionalized by the smooth wall data. (b) Profiles of the viscous shear stress (dotted curves), Reynolds stress (dashed curves), and total shear stress (solid curves) for the hydraulically smooth baseline (black curves and circles) and the SHS, non-dimensionalized by the smooth wall data.

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From Nuclear Submarine to Sailing Trimaran Record The Globe Circumnavigation, The Ultimate Marine Challenge

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Abstract

In 2012 BANQUE POPULAIRE V a 40 m LOA sailing trimaran circumnavigated the globe non-stop and without external assistance in 45 days and 13 hours at average speed of 26.5 kn. This non-stop record at present unattainable by any engine powered vessel highlights an unexpected superiority of sail over power in this very specific but extremely fascinating context. It is interesting and significant to understand technical solutions, materials and technologies that make possible to design and build sailing vessels able to be indisputable testimony of the man limits in this extreme challenge. The paper presents the specific design aspects of the most recent boats for the circumnavigation record and shows how the latest available technical and technological resources have been exploited.

1. Introduction

For centuries, the circumnavigation of the globe was symbol and evidence of the ability to navigate, to explore and to acquire knowledge without space limits, turning the oceans from mysterious and insurmountable obstacles to way of communications and exchanges. In more recent times the non-stop round the world route has been seen as the most iconic action for the acknowledgment of skills and leadership in navigation and marine technique.

In 1960, the nuclear-powered submarine USS TRITON, Fig.1, circumnavigated the globe without stops following the same track as the first circumnavigation led by Ferdinand Magellan. This achievement was carefully prepared to confirm the leading role of the US in the global technical development. A non-stop submerged circumnavigation was considered the best flag to hoist in the incoming meeting between USA President D. Eisenhower and Soviet General Secretary Nikita Khrushchev. Triton's accomplishment coming less than two years after the transpolar expedition of the USS Nautilus, was a clear reaffirmation of U.S. technological supremacy and of nuclear power above any other means in marine propulsion.

TRITON circumnavigated the globe covering about 27,000 miles in 60 days at 18 knots average speed and for a long time this result was considered unattainable by any other marine vehicle that was not nuclear-powered. Triton's globe-girdling cruise proved invaluable to the United States. Politically, it enhanced the nation's prestige. From an operational viewpoint, the cruise demonstrated the great submerged endurance and sustained high-speed transit capabilities of the first generation of nuclear-powered submarines. Moreover, during the voyage, the submarine collected many oceanographic data.

Triton voyage came 438 years after the first circumnavigation completed by Spanish Basque navigator Juan Sebastián Elcano after Magellan's death in 1522. Circumnavigations of the following three centuries were mostly performed for exploration and discovery of unknown lands and then for military strategic reasons. Their success and always shorter travel times demonstrated the technical progress and the achievements of navigation and marine technology. The capabilities of circumnavigation by commercial or military ships were related to marine engine development. HMS Driver completed the first circumnavigation by a steam ship in 1845–1847.

At present circumnavigation is not only quite faster than Triton's one and can be performed non-stop and with no-external assistance without using nuclear power. Surprisingly, the present record is held by BANQUE POPULAIRE V a 40 m LOA sailing trimaran in 45 days and 13 hours at average speed of 26.5 kn, Fig.2.

In the last 50 years technical achievements made this type of sailing vessels widely superior to any powered craft on this route. Moreover wind energy allows them to sail without stored fuel and free from any refurbishments. This paper wants to identify and describe the technical achievements that made possible for sail to overcome powered craft in this ultimate maritime enterprise.

Fig.1: Triton nuclear submarine

Fig.2: Maxi Banque Populaire V sailing trimaran

Joshua Slocum sailed around the world single handed in 1895-1898, but the first non-stop circumnavigation was performed by Sir Robin Knox-Johnston in 313 days on Suhaili, a 33' Length over all (L_{OA}) sailing ketch, during the first Sunday Times Golden Globe Race in 1968-69. Since the early seventies the allure of circumnavigation by sail became stronger and several attempts to get shorter time records were made. New and improved technologies allowed always more challenging targets. Furthermore, sail races around the world and prizes as the Jules Verne Trophy raised worldwide media interest. In 1970 sailing vessels performances were not comparable with Triton ones, both for average speed and non-stop capabilities. Going back to the last decades of the 20th century it is possible to identify the technical improvements that allowed sailing craft at first to equalize and then to exceed Triton's record. Only after more than forty years a sailing vessel overcame Triton's performance. In 2002 Bruno Peyron and his crew needed 64 days and 8 hours to sail Orange, an 80' L_{OA} catamaran non-stop round the world. Finally, in 2004 another catamaran, Cheyenne skippered by Steve Fosset beat the Triton's record sailing in 58 days and 9 hours. In 2012 Maxi Banque Populaire V (Fig.2) a 40 m L_{OA} sailing trimaran circumnavigated the globe non-stop and without external assistance in 45 days and 13 hours at average speed of 26.5 kn. This record is still unbroken. No sailing mono-hull is able to sail non-stop around the world in so short time. The fastest mono-hull passage has been performed by Francois Gabart on Macif during the 2012 Vendée in 78 days and 2 hours. Nevertheless the multihull supremacy must be considered in the frame of safety also. Their huge form stability provides highest righting moments at low heeling angles, but does not assure against capsizing as some dramatic incidents occurred in open sea have demonstrated.

2. Courses and Races

Since when non-stop and not-assisted circumnavigation become possible a strong boost for new attempts to reduce the travel time came from Jules Verne Trophy and Vendée Globe Race. The other round the World Races as Volvo Ocean Race, formerly known as the Whitbread Round the World Race, are very famous as well, but they are not interesting in this context as done with stops, nine legs at present, with external assistance.

The Jules Verne Trophy is a prize for the fastest circumnavigation of the world by any type of sailing vessels with no restrictions on the size of the crew, provided the vessel has registered with the organization and paid an entry fee. A vessel holding the Jules Verne trophy will not necessarily hold the absolute round the world record. The trophy was first awarded in 1993 to Commodore Explorer a catamaran skippered by Bruno Peyron that sailed around the world in 79 days and 6 hours. The name of the award is a reference to the Jules Verne novel *Around the World in Eighty Days* in which Phileas Fogg traverses the planet (albeit by railroad and steamboat) in 80 days. The current

holder is the already mentioned Maxi Banque Populaire V skippered by Loick Peyron in 45 days 13 hours 42 minutes 53 seconds.

The course starting point is defined by an imaginary line between the Créac'h lighthouse on Ouessant Island, France, and the Lizard Lighthouse, UK. The boats have to circumnavigate the world leaving the capes of Good Hope, Leeuwin, and Horn to port and cross the starting line in the opposite direction. Jules Verne Trophy is awarded to the challenger who breaks the previous Jules Verne record of the round the world voyage under sail. The winner holds the trophy until such time as his/her record has been bettered. Propulsion of the boat must solely be by natural forces of the wind and of the crew. The circumnavigation must be completed non-stop and with no physical outside assistance.

Vendée Globe is a round-the-world single-handed yacht race, sailed non-stop and without assistance. The race was founded by Philippe Jeantot in 1989 and since 1992 has taken place every four years. The 2016–2017 edition is planned to start on November 6th 2016. It is the only single-handed non-stop round-the-world race in contrast to the VELUX 5 Oceans Race, which is sailed in stages. The race is a serious test of individual endurance, and is regarded by many as the ultimate in ocean racing. The race is open to 60' Loa mono-hull yachts conforming to the Open 60 class criteria. Prior to 2004, the race was also open to Open 50' boats. The Open classes are unrestricted in certain aspects, but a box rule governs parameters such as overall length, draught, appendages and stability as well as numerous other safety features. At present the Vendee Globe for singlehanded and the Jules Verne Trophy for crewed boats are the most representative of boat technical innovations.

For around the world official sailing records, there is a rule saying that the length must be at least 21,600 nautical miles calculated along the shortest possible track from the starting port and back, that does not cross land and does not go below 63°S. It is allowed to have one single waypoint to lengthen the calculated track. The equator must be crossed. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Circumnavigation> - cite note-6 Nevertheless any non-stop eastward circumnavigation that follows the most common route around the three capes is about 27000 mg long due to the search of most favourable wind strength and direction. These last factors influence the result more than sailed course reduction. The current record of 45 days 13 hours by Maxi Banque Populaire V was established sailing 29002 mg and followed an easterly route as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3: Typical circumnavigation route followed by sailing vessels

The fact that world circumnavigation is performed at present within given courses allows to compare in a fair way the different technical features and the advances in boat design and technology. A comparison with 1960 Triton's performance has to consider that Triton followed Magellan westward

route and cruised for 26723 mg, a shorter course in respect to Maxi Banque Populaire V, but in the opposite westward direction. Current sailing records are possible only eastward and in favourable period of the year. Sailing westward against the prevailing winds and currents is much more demanding. Multihulls cannot exploit their potential sailing upwind and best westward travel time is 122 days and 14 hours set by Jean Luc Van Den Heede in 2004 sailing singlehanded the mono-hull Adrien.

3. Present time

Since when circumnavigation became a challenge for marine and maritime world, the time taken to complete it represents technical advances of the field. If the combination of cruising speed and range is considered, a further highlight is given by non-stop, not-assisted and single-handed circumnavigations.

Within this context, since first years of 21st century sailing craft are superior to power ones as reported in Introduction. The gap in favour to sailing vessels has been progressively increased by following attempts to get Jules Verne Trophy. Singlehanded attempts are evidently slower but the gap between the 57 days and 13 hours, time set singlehanded in 2008 by Francis Joyon on IDEC 2, and the crewed record is less than 12 days. Credit must be given to Dame Ellen Mac Arthur. She began her attempt to break the solo record for sailing non-stop around the world on 28 November 2004. During her circumnavigation, she set records for the fastest solo voyage to the equator, past the Cape of Good Hope, past Cape Horn and back to the equator again. She crossed the finishing line near the French coast at Ushant on 7 February 2005 beating the previous record by 1 day and 8 hours.

In Fig.4 some significant mono and multihull travel time on circumnavigation are reported. They refer to non-stop circumnavigations except the Gipsy Moth IV one that had one stop. This time has been reported as considered more representative of the state of the art in the late sixties in respect to Sir Robin Knox-Johnston’s one on Suhaili, a boat quite smaller than the others, 36’ Loa only.

Fig.4: The trend of mono and multihull travel time

3. Design and Technical Improvements

New technologies, materials and more important new design concepts have progressively reduced the time to sail around the globe. In Fig.4 the trend is monotonic but significant variations can be identified. They correspond to steps in design advances and in material availability. The first big drop from seventies to eighties, evident for both mono and multihull, is due to laminated and fiber reinforced sails whose performances are quite superior than or polyester (Dacron) ones. In the same period a general improvement in construction of both hull and rig can be appreciated due to the exploitation of high modulus fiber reinforced composite and, more important, to the improvements of their reliability for such demanding application. Finally in the first year of this century the effects of canting keels for mono-hull and of dynamic stability applied to multihulls, can be appreciated.

Consideration has to be given to the progress of navigation instruments that, although not considered in this work, have had an important role for performance and safety improvements. GPS has been used since nineties and routing software is available to on board crews and shore teams. The boat positions are tracked during travel time and this represents an invaluable support for crew mood and external help in case of emergency. Beside these main features several minor technical factors that is not possible to consider in this general presentation have provided significant contribution. Last but not least available budgets thanks to media covering and worldwide interest have reached six zeros figures. Boat to shore real time communication has become common so that large number of people can follow the attempts. In the following paragraphs the main factors influencing the result of so extreme technical and human challenge are considered, in the chronological order of their apparition.

3.1. Multihull versus mono-hull, weight and form stability

No one among the peculiar characteristics of sailing vessels has enhanced technological resources or influenced hull forms as transversal stability. In any sailing vessel the connection among stability, performances and safety is immediate and inescapable. Very few problems of marine technics can be cited for having been solved in so different and at the same time effective ways, in different locations and ages. Transversal stability is the main propulsion factor for offshore sailing vessels. Only kites powered craft or prototypes designed for absolute speed record with unconventional sail plan do not rely on it. Transversal stability of sailing vessels has been obtained in different ways based on quite different concepts. It is possible to connect some technical choices to logistics and to peculiar use of sailing vessels but is difficult to deny a deep and radical separation from European approach based on weight stability, Fig.5, and more exotic solutions based on form stability developed in Australia, Far-East or in Pacific Islands, Fig.6. Available technologies have influenced the application of the basic concepts as shown in Fig.7 and 8.

Fig.5: Weight stability by inside ballast

Fig.6: Polynesian proa with outrigger for form stability

Fig.7: Lead ballast torpedo shaped set in low-est possible position

Fig.8: Sailing trimaran for offshore racing

In a sailing vessel the resulting force of the aerodynamic actions on rig and sail plan is in equilibrium with the resulting force of hydrodynamic actions on the hull. The first one generally causes an heeling moment that, due to the direction of the resultant, can be considered as the sum of a transversal and of a longitudinal component. The longitudinal heeling moment will put bow down and will be counteracted by the longitudinal stability of the boat. The transversal heeling moment must be counteracted by ship righting moment. The equilibrium between forward thrust and motion resistance, that are the components in the motion direction of the previously considered resultants, is strongly dependent from the equilibrium between the considered moments as shown in Fig.9. From this is evident how transversal stability is one of the most influencing factors of performances of any sailing craft.

Fig.9: Forces and moments on a sailing craft

The righting moment M that a vessel opposes to an heeling transversal moment is given by: $M = \Delta \times GZ$ where Δ (kg) is the displacement and GZ (m), called righting arm is the distance between the buoyancy force direction and the weight force direction that are both perpendicular to the inclined waterline as shown in Fig.10. For a given displacement to increase the righting moment it is necessary to increase the righting arm. This is possible by:

- shifting downward the Center of Gravity (CG) as shown by a typical ballast keel form reported in Fig.7;
- shifting transversally the CG by water ballast or crew weight set upwind (Fig.11) or by canting keel (Fig.15);
- shifting further offset the Center of Buoyancy (CB) of the inclined hull. This option cannot be used on monohulls over a certain extent due to the large resistance of wide hull forms. Catamarans exploit best the concept, when the upwind hull leaves the water as shown in Fig.12. GZ becomes of one order of magnitude greater than a similar mono-hull.

The effects of such actions are different according to heeling angle. CG vertical shifting will affect stability at high angles while both CG and CB transversal shift will influence low angle stability. The equilibrium between heeling and righting moments must be obtained at a reasonably small heeling angle as, generally, hull heeling induces higher motion resistance.

Fig.10: Transversal stability factors

Fig.11: CG Trasversal shifting by "living ballast"

Fig.12: Multihull extreme form stability

There are some unconventional mono-hulls designed to allow high heeling angles without resistance increase so that weight (in case of the so-called "plank on edges") and form stability (is the case of "scow") can be fully exploited as shown in Figs.13-14. To higher righting moment should correspond larger sail areas. This is impossible as the increase of righting moment is generally connected to the mentioned resistance increase and, more important, is anyway connected to conditions or features that are far from the practical use of the craft.

Fig.13: "Plank on edge" hull form

Fig.14: The "scow" hull form

It is clear that CG vertical position of a sailing vessel is always the lowest possible. CG transversal shift is widely used by small dinghies moving crew windward as shown in Fig 11. It is the so called living ballast that has to be moved from one side to the other as the boat tacks. Mono-hull for round the world racing do a very effective application of CG transversal shifting by water ballast tanks filled upwind and by canting keels Fig.15.

Fig.15: Canting keel in full action

Fig.16: Sailing trimaran capsizing in open sea

Nevertheless it is impossible to increase weight stability over certain limits and that's why mono-hull performances are and will be always lower than multi-hull ones. Both catamarans and trimarans benefit of form stability that is very high due to the distance among the hulls and consequent very large GZ as shown in Fig.13. This is the factor that has led multihulls to a steady supremacy in the Round the World performances as shown by Fig.4. The price to be paid is in terms of safety. Mono-hull offshore sailing craft can be self-righting at any angle and participants to Vendee Globe have to comply a self-righting test. Multihulls present highest GZ values at very low heeling angles, then GZ decreases and after a 90 degrees they capsize (Fig.16) and remain in stable position. Generally they do not sink as they are not-ballasted but external help is necessary to right up and save them.

The overcoming of Triton's record is due to several factors, but the most important is the skill and courage of crews that have sailed performing, but very dangerous multihulls around the world at astonishing speed in the most severe conditions.

3.2 Sail Materials

Since early 50s, polyester is the most common fiber used in sailcloth. It is commonly referred to trade name Dacron® given to the Type 52 high modulus fiber made specifically for sailcloth. Other polyester trade names include Terylene®, Tetoron®, Trevira® and Diolen®. Polyester's desirable properties include excellent resiliency, high abrasion resistance, high UV resistance, high flex strength and low cost. Low absorbency allows the fiber to dry quickly. Although polyester is still the most common cruising sailcloth fiber it has been replaced by higher modulus fibers for most racing applications.

Structural loads on sails are related to several different factors as wind speed, boat dimensions, displacement and sail size. The present vessel speed often over 20 or even 30 knots produce dramatic increase of sailing loads due to apparent wind. Such loads can be sustained without deformations that would change sail profile and reduce sail forward thrust by so called "exotic" fibers as Kevlar or carbon. Kevlar is an aramid fiber introduced by DuPont in 1971. It has become the predominant fiber in the racing sector of the sailcloth industry. It is stronger than steel for its weight and has a modulus that is five times greater than polyester. Kevlar handicaps are poor UV resistance (Kevlar loses strength roughly twice as quickly in sunlight as polyester and, when affected, the gold Kevlar fibers turn brown) and rapid loss of strength with flexing, folding and flogging.

Carbon fiber is a high modulus synthetic fiber made from an acrylic containing carbon. It is almost unaffected by UV exposure. First used successfully in the America's Cup, carbon fiber laminates provide exceptionally low stretch for their weight. Recent manufacturing advances have led to improved fiber flexibility, which translates to longer sail life in exchange for lower modulus numbers. Recently developed carbon sailcloth fabrics have paired high modulus carbon fiber with more durable aramid, Spectra, and/or Vectran fibers to achieve durability without sacrificing low stretch. Other structural fibers such as Technor or Twaron have been proposed. They have structural performances similar to Kevlar but are more suitable for sail production.

The contribution to circumnavigation performances due to sails made by high modulus fiber can be easily appreciated by the drop in travel time from 1970 to 1990, shown in Fig.4. A further increase of performances is due to a new concept in sail making, the laminated sail. They first appeared in eighties and changed the world of sail making, starting with the high performance racers of the America's Cup and, over time, working down to performance cruisers. Lamination is the most effective method of combining materials with different characteristics to maximize the advantages of each. Films such as Mylar® and PEN are extremely efficient in reducing stretch in all directions. Laminates allow fibers to be placed in a straight uninterrupted path which results in the most efficient utilization. There are many variations of laminated sailcloth but basically the structural fibers are sandwiched between two sheets of film. The load-bearing members are laid straight and there is no crimp. This takes full advantage of the fiber's high modulus in resisting stretch. Although Kevlar is the most common structural fiber used in this construction, carbon is growing in popularity. Unfortunately, the film of outer skins is not abrasion or flex resistant as a woven and does not protect the structural fibers from harmful UV rays. Although laminated sails are generally considered suitable for short-lived racing sails, both mono and multihulls involved in setting round the world records use mainly laminated sails. Several advances in sail setting and handling, that cannot be mentioned in this work for space reasons, have given further significant contributes.

3.3 High Performance Composites

The advantages of high performance reinforced composites for racing sailing boats have been known since late seventies, but their application to offshore sailing racers has been limited by the initial poor

reliability. Only in 1993 all yachts participating to the Whitbread Round the World Race were built in composite. Previously light alloy, although worse from a structural point of view, was considered preferable when severe weather conditions had to be faced. Light alloy homogeneity and resilience were considered preferable to composite intrinsic non-homogeneity and brittle behavior. Nevertheless, also due developments in composite marine technologies, the quite better specific properties of carbon and Kevlar reinforced composites have led to their general use.

The main advantages in using composites and in particular those one reinforced with carbon are light weight, high stiffness, high tensile and compressive strength. Table 1 shows the merits of composite materials when compared to steel and light alloy in terms of stiffness and strength at equal weights.

Table I: Comparison among mechanical and elastic properties of composite and metallic materials

Material	Elastic Modulus		Tensile strength		Compressive strength		Density kg/m ³	Specific Elastic Modulus (Elastic Modulus / Density)		Specific Tensile strength x 10 (Tensile strength x 10 / Density)	
	Mpa	Mpa	Mpa	Mpa	Mpa	Mpa					
Stainless Steel	190000		515		515		7800	24,36		0,66	
Titanium Ti6Al4V	110000		660		660		4400	25,00		1,50	
Light Alloy 5083 H111	70000		320		320		2700	25,93		1,19	
Fiberglass/Polyester	10000	20000	80	300	80	300	2200	4,55	9,09	0,36	1,36
Carbon fiber T700/epoxy	35000	112000	250	1100	150	700	1500	23,33	74,67	1,67	7,33
Wood	6000	10000	50	100	30	60	550	10,91	18,18	0,91	1,82

Composites present not only high structural performances, but low density too. That is why, if we compare specific properties, resulting by the ratio with density, they are the best for use in structural elements where stiffness and weight are the most important characteristics. The contribute of composite construction in terms of weight reduction is mainly felt in multihulls where very large developed surfaces and huge loads due to highest stability are present.

Composite full exploitation has been possible when advanced technology formerly developed for aerospace sector, as vacuum bagging, autoclave and infusion molding, became available in the marine field. The higher costs limit their application to racing craft and prototypes but any Round the World record attempt tried both by mono or multi-hull, relies above state of the art marine composite design and construction. Composite contribution to performance of such extreme craft is not limited to main structural elements, but since few years, also deck hardware and rig construction take benefit from their characteristics.

Improvements in composite structural design with specific consideration of fatigue and slamming experienced at high speed in rough weather have given their fundamental contribution also. The intrinsic anisotropy of fiber reinforced plastics is most interesting for very slender almost mono-dimensional elements as trimaran hulls and cross beams.

Composites get their final shape together with structural properties during molding. This removes any form constrain allowing high levels of both structural and hydrodynamic optimization. When dealing with so long course and severe conditions endurance is important as speed or even more. Recently, composite construction reliability has been improved to such extent that skippers and crews have pushed craft to the limit. This, together with composites structural performances has been one of the key factors for the most recent record achievements.

3.4 Rig Development

The option of exploiting the mast not only as a structural element to hoist the sails, but also as an aerodynamic component to improve sail efficiency has been explored on offshore sailing vessels since early eighties. Pen Duick VI (then Manureva) sported streamlined cowlings on her light alloy masts during first trials, Fig.17. Later they were removed as non practical.

Fig.17: Wing cowlings on the masts of Pen Duick VI, subsequently removed

Fig.18: A typical carbon composite wing mast on a trimaran

It has been necessary to await the diffusion of carbon composite masts to see a general diffusion of wing profiled masts on both multi and monohull used for circumnavigation, Fig.18. The mast can be rotated at different angles according apparent wind direction and dramatically improves mainsail aerodynamic coefficients.

A further improvement to sail plan efficiency is obtained by canting the mast and the whole sail plan upwind, as shown in Fig.19. The upwind canting prevents the reduction of the effective sail plan due to the heeling angle. The sail plan remains almost vertical, the projected surface is closest to the real one, the aerodynamic resultant is almost horizontal and there is no loss due to downward vertical component. The canting rig concept has been successfully applied on multihulls only as the huge beam allows higher shroud angles.

Fig.19: Groupama trimaran with mast canted upwind in perfect trim

Fig.20: Mast and shroud layout on a typical Vendee Globe racer

Monohull masts are, at present carbon composite with wing sections. The most of top performing boat masts are stayed in a particular way. To get lower compressive mast loads and to allow the wing mast to rotate, the shrouds are connected to long outrigger poles as shown in Fig.20. The benefit on mast weight is huge and on transversal stability too.

3.5 Electronics

The performances of sailing vessels considered in this work are achieved by wind and human power. Small electricity generators are present on board. They are operated by wind energy or hydrodynamic power get by water flow below the hull. Electric energy on board is necessary to operate electronic equipment. This, with continuous progress, has strongly influenced navigation, boat handling and safety. Singlehanded performances have been hardly influenced by electronics more than crewed ones, due to the strong contribute of recent auto-pilots.

Again, a detailed description of all electronic instruments used on board is out of the aim of this paper, but synthetically they could be divided into the following main groups:

- Equipment to monitor boat performance
- Equipment for navigation and detection of obstacles
- Routing aids
- Tracking systems
- Auto pilots for singlehanded boats

Very often composite structures are monitored by smart systems fitted to the main elements.

3.6 Dynamic Stability and Hydrodynamic Lift

Previously, it has been reported how static stability is a propulsion factor for sailing vessels and it has been seen how both form and weight stability are related to motion resistance. Generally speaking, higher stability higher resistance and consequent equilibrium of these factors at limited speed. This is true for any sailing vessel although much more handicapping for mono-hulls. A very significant contribute to break this loop comes from dynamic lift. Attempts to use hydrodynamic lift on sailing boats, aimed at resistance reduction, have been made since early sixties of the last century. Such efforts were generally unsuccessful or produced results of no practical use. Only when composite technologies allowed very light construction some small dinghies, first International 14 and then International Moth, achieved full hydrodynamic lift. At present they are able even to tack and jibe in foiling condition. Such craft, although experiencing a dynamic stabilization due to foil characteristics, counteract wind heeling moment by crew weight shifted upwind. Beside that, in the early eighties, the daggerboards to counteract leeway, fitted to offshore racing catamarans and trimarans, became curved so that a vertical component of their hydrodynamic resultant was significant. Increase in vessel performance was evident although, at first, not completely understood. The vertical component reduced resistance, but at the same time, contributed to transversal stability with an extra righting moment. This moment differently from the static one, increased with speed increment.

Fig.21: Forces on foil-daggerboard

Fig.22: Foil daggerboard of trimaran

The higher the speed is, the lower the resistance, due to hydrodynamic lift and the greater stability due to hydrodynamic vertical component. Theoretically the stability could increase with speed without affecting resistance. This concept appeared soon very promising in respect to the previous exploita-

tion of static stability. Dynamic lift increases with speed squared, so that theoretically, at the increase of the wind force and of the consequent speed further stability is provided and, further speed can be achieved.

Technical and practical issues as ventilation and structural aspects limit achievable speed values but the contribute given at first by curved daggerboard and subsequently by lifting surfaces connected to vertical daggerboard is meaningful. This factor has led to better performance of offshore multihulls as witnessed by Groupama and Maxi Banque Populaire V record. Finally, when the concept has been applied to the very light America's Cup catamarans has provided full hydrodynamic lift and full dynamic stability as the hulls are flying completely out of the water and no hydrostatic force is present. A similar radical attempt was made by French skipper Eric Tabarly with Paul Ricard trimaran, Fig.23, with small outriggers fitted with large foils. The aim was to get both full hydrodynamic lift and stability but it was unsuccessful due to the relatively heavy light alloy construction available at that time. A former composite application L'Hydroptere, Fig.24, got world speed record, but the vessel was not suitable for offshore passage and dramatically capsized.

Vessels for Round the World record use a less radical but more effective application provided by curved daggerboards on racing multihulls with a reduction to hydrostatic buoyancy and a significant contribute to transversal stability. Curved daggerboards started out on 60' trimarans. It then became clear that by varying the radius of the curve the amount of lift, lateral resistance and draft could be changed. It took years but the curved boards are now used on almost every racing multihull.

Fig.23: Paul Ricard trimaran with foils

Fig.24: L'Hydroptere in full hydrodynamic lift

As regard circumnavigation and Jules Verne Trophy it can be said that dynamic stability of trimarans provided by rounded daggerboards fitted to the leeway hull probably has been the most significant factor for the achievement of the recent impressive performances. Such encouraging results are due to multihull very high speed, but the concept has been considered for mono-hull also. In 2009 the Verdier/VPLP designed Open 60 "Safran" was the first mono-hull racing keelboat to use curved asymmetrical lifting foils. Then, the Verdier/VPLP designed Virbac-Paprec 3 won Barcelona Round the World Race after leading almost the whole race and was the only boat using curved foils. Very recently, Imoca 60 racing in the next Vendee Globe and even Transat 6.50, both mono-hulls, have been fitted with foils. Results are not so astonishing as in multihulls, due to the presence of ballast that is an handicap to get hydrodynamic lift, but the effect on transversal stability is evident as shown in Fig.25.

The results of the Vendee Globe that starts in November 2016 will give a clear answer about plus and minus of dynamic stability applied to mono-hulls. It is interesting to point out that dynamic stability concept exploited on round the world record craft has had a fallout on more conventional racing/cruising mono-hulls. DSS (Dynamic Stability System) is a patented system that utilizes retractable foils to reduce heel angles and provides progressive dynamic lift complementing the static stability. It has been conceived for performance mono-hulls. DSS uses a retractable foil that deploys to leeward as shown in Fig.26. The very interesting results provided by curved daggerboards, foils and DSS devices have been possible thanks to the advances in high modulus carbon composites, as

they are the only material that allows adequate structural characteristics and light weight in very thin streamlined sections.

Fig.25: Foil daggerboard effect on IMOCA 60 Multihull

Fig.26: Dynamic Stability System on Wild Oats maxi racer

4. Conclusions and predictable developments

Setting a circumnavigation record is first endurance and then speed. Beside, safety must be taken into account. The successful compromise among these three factors, endurance, speed and safety is the technical, maritime and human result achieved by circumnavigation records. It is difficult to say if and when a fall-out of this will affect or improve production sailing yachts or pleasure navigation, but surely the advance in ultimate performances are reference and motivation for improvements of a general state of the art of the field.

The progressively smaller differences of few days or even hours between one record time and the previous show the highest level of all technical and navigation aspects involved in sailing circumnavigation. Unless unexpected factors, it is difficult to predict a significant reduction of circumnavigation time by sailing vessels. A recent attempt failed and the record is standing since 2012.

Finally, it is difficult to predict if new and different propulsion systems could allow powered vessels to overcome again sailing ones.

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Efficient and Ergonomic Assembly Processes of Sailing Yachts Based on a Modular Design

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Abstract

This paper describes an approach on how the assembly processes of high individual sailing yachts can be efficiently and ergonomically improved. The potential of productivity improvements by of sailing yachts was shown with the aid of process studies. Hereby a reorganization of the entire assembly line for sailing yachts is described. It is shown which additional equipment is necessary for comfortable handling and assembly considering human ergonomics. Furthermore the way of development and the ergonomic review with the aid of a virtual reality mock-up is shown. Besides the changed layout of the assembly line and the adapted assembly processes are presented. Finally the effects of this presented approach are mentioned for a medium-sized sailing yacht and an outline of a future yard for sailing ships is given.

1. Introduction

The market of the sailing yachts is undergoing an increasing concentration led by the dominance of a few large producers. An intense competition exists within the branch, which is reflected in a struggle for the best-value for money. Furthermore the customer requirements evolve towards more individuality and variety by decreasing costs. The customer requests are diverse and differ regionally. With an overall modular manufacturing, which can depict such a variety, a producer will be able to position itself in the market with a long-term success.

The implementation requires adjustments in equipment of manufacturing and assembly as well as the processes and organizational form of the assembly. These have to cope with the modular character of the new designed yacht.

Necessary assembly systems have to be designed depending on the number and complexity of components and modules. Thus new workplaces for module erection have to be intended to fulfill the requirements of ergonomics and an aging working population. Based on the development of demographic change the available employees will decline up to 30% from now, *Destatis (2015)*. Therefore the redesigned assembly processes have to consider by an aging staff and an increasing deficit of qualified personnel, *Dombrowski (2012)*.

2. Theoretical Background

The production of sailing yachts mainly consists of two processes. The first is the production of hull and deck made by glass reinforced plastic (GRP). Therefore different production procedures are applied (e.g. RTM, hand laminating, vacuum infusion). The second process is the outfitting, including the technical systems, the equipment and furniture. While the quality of the hull and deck production depends on the selected manufacturing procedure the outfitting is influenced by the way of assembly. Technically seen the possibility of differential constructions offers the most customization possibilities, because all single parts of furniture and technical systems are assembled in the hull separately and could be individualized by customers until that. In contrast a modular design offers just adequate individualization possibilities but in addition an economy of time for the shipyard during the assembly of sailing yachts.

According to *Dombrowski (2012)*, *Schlick et al. (2010)*, *Neubert (2013)* the ergonomics of processes influence the quality and productivity and as a consequence of that the success of enterprises. So that in case of changing the assembly procedure the redesign of the workplace layout and the assembly processes themselves should be regarded as well.

3. Analysis of the current-situation

3.1 Time survey and work-sampling study

In an initial step the current situation of final assembly is recorded by detailed time analysis for different sizes of sailing yachts. Hereby the shown assembly process is recorded per cycle and segmented to the different trades. To extend the view of assembly processes a work-sampling study is executed. Hereby the percentages of value-adding processes are identified. For this purpose the observed activities during the assembly processes are classified to value-adding (e.g. assembly of furniture or technical systems), non-value-adding (e.g. rework, cleaning) and not identified (not visible, additional time) processes. The results of the surveys are shown in Fig.1. As demonstrated on Fig.1a the working time per cycle varies intensive over the considered cycles. As illustrated on Fig.1b non-value-adding processes are dominating the spreading. The shown 54% of non-value-adding processes consist mainly of reworking processes, induced by the actual way of assembly and had to be optimized as well as the working time per cycle.

a: Working time per cycle

b: Percentage of value-adding processes

Fig.1: results of initial surveys for identification of optimization potentials

3.2 Digital process simulation and evaluation of ergonomics

The ergonomics of the entire assembly process can be characterized as insufficient. A high number of observed processes are executed in forced postures. These are particularly induced by physically overload or missing space, because of a high number of workmen in the hull. In addition the assembly of deck induces a drastically reduction of the movement abilities of the workmen. By that work-related diseases are preprogrammed.

Fig.2: Simulation of assembly processes

For an objective view of the ergonomics exemplarily processes are digitized. Therefore the simulation software IC.IDO (ESI Group, France) is used. In accordance to *Schoenherr (2014)* the applied man model is generated by an anthropometric database for a German population. For a global survey different percentiles of man are used (5th, 50th, 95th percentile). The considered movements of the man model are generated with an inverse behavior of the kinematic bones. Needed 3D-data for interaction are imported via exchange format STEP. Fig.2 shows some simulated processes during the assembly.

The evaluation of ergonomics depends on a so called discomfort value, which considers the posture of human joints (e.g. knee joint, shoulder joint) and compares the posture during the assembly process with the neutral position of man on the basis of *NASA STD 3000 (1995)*. External forces or musculoskeletal impacts have not been considered. The discomfort value is divided in three sections according to the colors of traffic lights (compare to Fig.3).

Fig.3: Simulation of assembly processes and evaluation of ergonomics for 50th percentile of man model

The validation of the ergonomics has shown intense deficits during assembly processes. Major strains have been identified in the spine and the shoulder-hand-arm system. Especially the 95th percentile of man model has shown a high number of assembly processes in a non-ergonomic way.

4. Workplace design and development of auxiliaries with CAE

Based on the results of the ergonomic evaluation and the assembly process of sailing yachts the layouts of workplaces are designed to fit a modular assembly procedure. Therefore the worst ergonomic processes (e.g. pantry, bathroom) are redesigned using a virtual reality (VR) environment. This virtual mock-up saves investment costs for validation purposes. In addition to the digitized simulation the virtual reality environment allows a direct evaluation of reachability and visibility of the new workplaces. Due to the different sizes of workman the developed workplaces are equipped with height adjustments to increase the adaptability. The optimum size of working height is evaluated by anthropometric man models and test persons, who are set into the virtual scene by the aid of marker-based body tracking. Therefore adjustments in design are made instantly.

In addition the idea of adjustment of a single system to various worker is assumed in the development of a highly flexible socket for hulls. The challenge is to design a socket in which several hulls with different dimensions fit in (see in Fig.4).

An existing socket is used as basis. The entire system is separated into two subsystems. The first is the mounting system, which has to resist the weight of the yacht and be soft towards the polished surface of the GRP hull as well. The second subsystem is the running surface on top of the socket. It has to resist the load of eight men and be flexible but also robust in retrofitting.

Fig.4: Starting position for the development of a highly flexible socket for hulls

The mounting system is realized by construction of adjustable telescopic rods which are arranged pairwise on slide rails. For preservation towards the surface of the hull the endings of the rods are cover with rubber. The running surface was designed by a system of pluggable plates made of silkscreen. For validation purposes the entire socket system is valued against buckling stiffness by the aid of a rod model. Furthermore the handling and retrofitting processes are analyzed by methods-time measurement.

5. Results

By the implementation of a modular assembly procedure the entire assembly processes are redesigned. Through this the assembly of modules is taken out of the final assembly and line production. Thereof the number of required cycles can be reduced to eight instead of 14. This leads to a decrease of the entire lead time of approx. 26% as shown in Fig 5.

Fig.5: Expected effects by implementing a modular assembly procedure

Fig.6: Comparison of ergonomics in assembly of bathroom

The evaluation of the ergonomics by using adjustable workplaces shows that the discomfort value decreases in all major strained regions (spine, shoulder-arm-hand, leg-foot), as shown in Fig.6. By the aid of the new workplaces the physiological exposure can be reduced for all observed processes. The highly adjustable hull socket is shown in Fig.7. The construction is built to a prototype and is tested successfully.

Fig.7: Universal socket for hulls with mounting system and pluggable running surface

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The presented approach includes three possibilities on how the efficiency of shipyards can be improved by implementing a modular design of sailing yachts. Therefore the separation of module assembly can be assumed as the biggest driver and as a basis of redesigning the assembly processes out of the hull at adjustable workplace. Especially the execution of working processes in an ergonomic way induces a decrease of working time which depends on the prevention of additional movements. The presented simulations and ergonomic evaluation are made by an anthropometric man model of a single population. In more and more decentralized world it has to be assumed that the simulation has to be redone by using other populations.

Furthermore the level of detail in digitization of the observed processes was intentionally idealized. As already mentioned the impacts of force, gravity and musculoskeletal dependencies have not been regarded. It is assumed that the ergonomics will increase much more than evaluated by simulation system. It is expected that the use of automatic movement generation by using cameras during process observations will increase the accuracy of the simulated movements and allows a more precise view to the real ergonomic exposure.

The implementation of a modular design has many advantages in the assembly of sailing yachts. Besides the improvement of ergonomics and therefore the reduction of process time, the reduction of lead time of the entire assembly processes has to be named. Otherwise the modular design limits the customers in individualization of their sailing yachts. As long as the customers are looking for the best-value for money a modular design will enable savings in time and money in R&D and production of yachts for the shipyards. Should the customer needs towards individualization still increase, shipyards have to be aware of implementing modular design for all of their yachts.

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Designing Future Ships for Significantly Lower Energy Consumption

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Abstract

The likelihood of both increases in, and volatility of, the cost of conventional fuel in the coming decades combined with more stringent emission regulations, means that ships in the future will have to be significantly more efficient and make use of alternative sources of energy. Considering the regulatory aspect, it has been claimed that, if the IMO were to reduce international shipping's carbon dioxide emissions to those consistent with limiting anthropogenic climate change to 2 degrees of warming, then ships in 2050 would have to reduce their carbon dioxide emissions by 75-90% compared to ships in 2012. To investigate what might be the appropriate mix of technologies and operational approaches for future ship designs the "Whole Ship Model" (WSM) was developed, which is a holistic ship design tool, primarily developed at UCL, that can generate many ship design options with different design, technology and fuel combinations. The Whole Ship model can be used to explore different arrangements and uses of energy efficiency measures on container ships, bulk carriers and tankers evaluating their performance over an operating profile. This paper will initially present some results from the Whole Ship Model, evaluating the potential performance of present day ships and technologies and will then compare this to technically feasible future ship designs that use contemporary or near-term technology to achieve very high reductions in carbon dioxide emissions and energy consumption.

1. Introduction

Although there is some agreement that oil will continue to be a part of the future energy mix for shipping beyond 2030, *Grahn et al. (2013)*, *Smith et al. (2014)*, there is uncertainty as to future trends in several socio-economic factors that are pertinent to the design of ships, such as:

- oil price (as a recent, late 2014, drop in oil prices has demonstrated)
- freight rates
- environmental regulation (which is likely to increase)

1.1. Energy efficiency and Carbon Dioxide Emissions Regulation

The International Maritime Organisation (IMO) and the European Union (EU) are both taking steps to increase carbon dioxide emission regulations in shipping.

In July 2011, the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) and the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP) became mandatory for new ships only (EEDI) and all ships (SEEMP). This came into force in January 2013, *IMO Press Briefing (2011)*. The EEDI is a metric related to the potential transport work of a ship and is calculated at an operational point of 75% of the main engine's Maximum Continuous Rating (MCR) *IMO MEPC.212(63) (2012)*. For compliance the calculated EEDI has to be smaller than the required EEDI from a reference line, which is an average index value for a defined group of ships based on data from HIS Fairplay *IMO MEPC.215(63) (2012)*. This required EEDI decreases over time, so demanding increased efficiency for future newbuild ships.

In November 2014, EU-wide rules for monitoring, reporting and verification of CO₂ emissions from ships were approved, *European Council (2014)*. From January 2018 all ships over 5000 gross tonnes calling at European Union (EU) ports will have to report actual fuel consumption for each voyage,

European Commission (2013). The rationale for this regulation is that a robust system for monitoring, reporting and verification of greenhouse gas emissions from maritime transport is a prerequisite for any market-based measure, whether applied at EU level or globally, *European Commission (2013)*. The IMO has taken its own steps towards an international mandatory system for collecting ships' fuel consumption data following MEPC 69 in April 2016, *IMO Press Briefing (2016)*. However, this is still lacking much of the detail that can be found in the EU-wide rules.

1.2. Defining an Emissions Target to limit the greenhouse gas impact to 2°C for 2050

Until any further technical and operational measures to control GHG emissions are progressed, the only effective regulation is the EEDI, which is a minimum efficiency standard for new ships, however the current EEDI trajectory does not have a future reduction rate as high as that which might be required to limit global greenhouse gas emissions to those consistent with a (maximum) 2°C global warming target.

By considering an appropriate global CO₂ emissions budget, *Traut et al. (2015)* used data from the Third IMO GHG Study, *Smith et al. (2014)*, to estimate what a limit of a 2°C increase in greenhouse gas emissions above pre-industrial levels would mean for the operational efficiency of ships.

Traut et al. (2015) examined the impact of three scenarios on the operational efficiency of ships, the scenario with the lowest required reduction in ship operational efficiency (a 75% reduction in carbon dioxide emissions compared to 2012) included a 10% decrease in operational speed per decade. For the purpose of this study, where we are considering operational speed, the most stringent scenario will be assumed; a 90% reduction in carbon dioxide emissions compared to a 2012 baseline.

2. Ship Owners and Operators in 2015

To determine a baseline of what energy efficiency technologies might currently be being used, a survey of ship owners was carried out by UCL in 2015, which was also submitted to the International Maritime Organisation's Marine Environmental Protection Committee, *Rehmatulla and Calleya (2016)*. The UCL survey can be found in, *Rehmatulla and Calleya (2016)*. This survey covered 275 ship owners and operators covering around 5,000 ships and examined the take up of technical efficiency measures. This survey indicated that there is little adoption of currently available technologies even those technologies that would deliver reductions in costs, as illustrated in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Adoption of ship hydrodynamic technical efficiency measures, *Rehmatulla and Calleya (2016)*

Rehmatulla and Calleya (2016) contain graphs showing the take-up of technical energy efficiency measures in design, hydrodynamic and machinery changes. It is very clear from the survey when there is little adoption of current technologies, as illustrated by Fig.1 where the most common technologies are still only applied to less than 20% of the fleet surveyed.

The technologies that were being used in 2015 and that are later considered in combination are:

- Bulbous Bow
- Rudder Bulb (this is combined with End Plated Propeller as in *Nielsen (2012)*)
- End Plated Propeller (this is combined with Rudder Bulb as in *Nielsen (2012)*)
- Energy saving lighting
- Engine Derating
- Speed control of pumps and fans
- Common Rail Engines (included as part of baseline ship)
- Efficient Boiler (included as part of baseline ship)

3. Whole Ship Model

The Whole Ship Model (WSM) was developed by UCL as part of the Shipping in Changing Climates (SCC) project, a multi-disciplinary project investigating likely future carbon emissions from shipping and the technical and operational methods available for their reduction. The WSM is a flexible and holistic ship design tool coded in Python that allows selecting or entering a description of a single ship or fleets, and is described in technical detail by *Calleya et al (2015b)*. Fig.2 shows an overview of the inputs that the WSM can utilise. Ship design and operational assumptions can be combined in order to examine how a ship performs over an operating profile at an early design stage. The WSM can compare technologies, different design variants of the same ship specification or examine the performance of shipping fleets, depending on the preference of the designer or decision-maker.

Fig.2: Overview of Whole Ship Model, *Calleya et al. (2016)*.

Fig.3: Overview of Whole Ship Model, *Calleya et al. (2016)*

The WSM runs in an iterative design process for both design and in service operating conditions, (see Fig.3, where the effects of different technologies, operational measures, fuel types, regulations, speeds and weather are incorporated in an iterative process leading to a numerically balanced design option). The design process establishes and fixes the main characteristics of the ship (e.g. capacity and installed power). The operational assessment process uses the ship specification created by the design process and calculates its performance at different ship speeds, weather conditions and in regulatory regions like for example in Emission Control Areas (ECA). It is important to note that the WSM calculates the ship performance in a series of steady-state conditions. The use of time-domain approaches is being considered for future development to allow full voyage modelling.

3.1. Hull Design and Still Water Resistance Estimation

The hullform modelled in the WSM has a fixed monohull topology that can be modified to represent different types and sizes of ships. The hullform generator was described in some detail in *Calleya et al. (2015b)*, and represents the hullform as a series of waterplanes constructed using straight lines and curves using hyperbolic functions. Although this method does not allow precise representation of certain features such as stern bulbs and tunnel sterns, it has the advantage of being adaptable to a wide variety of merchant ship types and sizes, without requiring excessive iteration or multiple model topologies. This model can generate a representative hullform from a limited set of inputs, some of which can either be entered by the user or based on programmed guidance (such as block coefficient varying with speed). This rapidly generated hullform is sufficient to allow the estimation of the hull lightweight, righting moment, resistance, and operational cargo load, and to give a rough general arrangement of the ship. Still water resistance is based on Holtrop and Mennen (1982) and some of the components from Holtrop (1984).

3.2. Propeller Design

The propeller model uses polynomial functions to describe the Wageningen B-Screw Series of propellers, *Oosterveld and Oossnan (1975)*. In the design process the propeller is sized to match the thrust required to drive of the ship at the specified design speed. For a fixed pitch propeller, the calculated propeller efficiency curve is fixed and then used to find the efficiency of the propeller in different operational conditions. When a controllable pitch propeller is selected the pitch of the propeller is varied for different propeller revolution speeds in order to find the highest operational efficiency.

3.3. Engine and Marine System Design

The engine model selects the main and auxiliary machinery required by the ship specification. The engine model is based on the MAN Diesel & Turbo project guides, *MAN Diesel & Turbo (2013)*. For the main propulsion machinery, the model selects from 18 two-stroke engines and 6 four-stroke Diesel engines with different cylinder numbers. In the case of the auxiliary machinery, it only considers seven different four-stroke Diesel engines with several cylinder numbers.

For the main engine, the model finds engines suitable for the maximum torque and propeller speed given by the hull and propeller design process (see Fig.4). It also takes into account engine and sea margin which are also designer defined. After finding all possible candidates, the engine model selects the most fuel efficient engine and returns to the main code information such as specific fuel oil consumption, physical characteristics, number of engines and emissions. In the case of the auxiliary machinery the engine model received from the ship definition the electrical power demand on board and then searches to find the most fuel efficient machinery option, considering and engine margin and redundancy. Embedded into the engine model is the fuel database which contains twelve different fuels and their physical properties (e.g. low calorific value). For this study only HFO has been considered since the objective is to focus on the potential impact of energy efficiency measures applied to this power train only, with respect to ship performance.

Fig.4: Relevant data flow to and from the engine and marine system model

3.4. Energy Efficiency Measure Models

Efficiency Measures are a group of technologies – hydrodynamic, mechanical or electrical – and operational choices – maintenance, routing and voyage optimisation – which, either individually or as a group, have an impact on the energy demand on board. Efficiency Measures are defined in files separate from the WSM, allowing different models to be used, different model sets have been used for different projects including those produced in the Low Carbon Shipping, *Smith et al. (2010)*, ETI project, *ETI News (2013)*, Shipping in Changing Climates and more recent projects. The Efficiency Measure model passes information to WSM via a set of parameters which modify the inputs of the different parts of WSM shown in Fig.3. A detailed list of parameters and that are passed between ships and technologies were described by *Calleya et al. (2015a)*.

The WSM has in its catalogue more than 32 different technological and operational measures which can be applied to the different ship specifications. It is possible to combine up to multiple technologies and assess the impact of each measure both on each other and the overall ship. If more measures need to be combined then it is possible to create a new efficiency measure file can be created where the impacts are modelled for that particular combination.

Each model is scaled according to the ship needs and limitations (e.g. it would not be possible for a container ship to have a set of large sails installed since there is not any space available on deck) and returns to WSM the efficiency measures' impacts such as volume, mass and energy requirements. The efficiency measures are sized and costed at the design condition while the WSM evaluates their performance separately at the operational conditions, including off-design conditions. The UCL ship performance models also consider operating ship speed as an independent input that can be varied rather than being treated as an energy efficiency measure, *Calleya et al. (2012,2015a)*.

3.5. Regulatory Controls

It is important to consider the implications of regulations on ship design. Technologies and operational measures introduced purely to comply with regulations are incorporated into the WSM in a similar way to the Efficiency Measures. The WSM considers regulatory controls for the ship such as for SO_x, NO_x and CO₂ emission or ballast water treatment. It adds the technology or group of technologies defined as being required to make the ship design comply with regulations that will be in force when launched.

4. Achieving 90% Reduction in Energy Usage in 2050

In order to find a high reduction in energy use a combination of technologies were considered that had a higher reduction in energy use than those being used by ship owners in 2015. Technologies

were selected to improve upon the efficiency of ships, beyond what owners were doing in 2015. A brief explanation is given of the relevance of these technologies in this section

4.1 Resistance Reduction

The resistance of the hullform can be reduced by hydrodynamic means, such as adding (or removing) a bulbous bow or adding a stern flap, or by reducing the skin friction by air lubrication. Air Lubrication was implemented using the assumptions contained in *Mäkiharju (2012)*, which allow for the calculation of the required air flow, for Air Layer Drag Reduction, and hence compressor power based on the air cavity. The air cavity was described as having a length of 80% of the waterline length and a width proportional to the block coefficient cubed. This allows the air cavity to be sized to fit different ships. The frictional resistance of the area of the air cavity is assumed to be reduced by 80% due to the air layer compared to an average hull form, as given in *Mäkiharju (2012)*.

4.2. Improving Propulsive Efficiency

A Contra Rotating Propeller was considered as a possible future option instead of End Plated Propellers and Rudder Bulbs, which were being used in 2015. These can be implemented in several ways; by splitting the propulsion load between a conventional propeller and a pod immediately astern of it; by the use of contra-rotating gears; or by the use of hybrid electric propulsion systems. The Contra Rotating Propeller generally has a greater improvement in energy efficiency compared with other energy efficiency measures that improve propulsive efficiency (such as modifications to the propeller) but it is more mechanically complex and expensive due to the additional equipment. For a deep-sea cargo ship a system using contra-rotating gears may be the most desirable as it is relatively compact compared to some electric options and so was used in this study.

Ishikawajima-Harima Heavy Industries Co., Ltd. (IHI) retrofitted such a CRP system to a 37000 tonne deadweight bulk carrier, Juno, in 1989 and delivered another system in 1993. Since then, energy savings of 14%-15% were confirmed, SEA-Japan No.285. The most in depth study of Contra Rotating Propellers, that considered a number of sources of information, quoted a fuel consumption saving of 8% for the Maersk EEE class, *Hoorn et al. (2013)*.

4.3 Stern Flaps

A method of reducing resistance for large ships, particularly those at higher speeds, will be to reduce transom waves, *Gabor et al., 1999* and this can be achieved with stern flaps. These devices can also act to increase waterline length and effect trim, especially on small boats with planing hulls, which can experience large changes in trim due to flaps, *Gabor et al., 1999*. The most detailed available information on the performance of wedges and flaps is from a series of model tests and trials carried out for the Arleigh Burke class DDG-51 Destroyer funded by the U.S. Office of Naval Research, *Gabor et al., 1999*. The improvement is mainly found at the high end of the Froude Number range, which makes this more applicable to container ships.

4.4. Waste Heat Recovery Systems

Waste Heat Recovery System (WHRS) can be used to recover energy lost from the propulsion engine in several ways. Steam can be raised by a boiler heated by the main engine exhaust, driving turbo-alternators to generate electricity or directly providing heat to cargo etc. An Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) WHRS can be also be used to extract energy from lower temperature sources such as cooling water. Mechanical methods such as turbo compounding can be used to extract energy from the exhaust, assumed to be parallel compounding for main engines and series compounding for auxiliary engines. Although the engine exhaust is the main source of waste energy, many (if not most) vessels already use this waste heat for cargo and domestic heating or electrical generation. Thus this practice was assumed to be part of the “baseline ship” and the additional options of ORC WHRC and turbo-compounding used as future developments. The WHRS models reflect the inability of these systems

to extract power below certain main engine operating points, and additionally the effect of increased back-pressure on engine performance.

4.5. Wind Assistance (Flettner Rotors and Kites)

The lift, drag and input motor power of Flettner Rotors were calculated with reference to *Traut et al. (2014)*. The lift and drag are calculated and resolved to the direction of the ship to give a thrust. The direction of rotation of the Flettner Rotor was chosen to maximise thrust. Each Flettner Rotor was assumed to have a modest height of 13.5 m and a radius of 2.7 m. As an example of performance, with an apparent wind direction and speed of 141 degrees and 14 knots and a 15 knot ship speed a single Flettner Rotor can produce a thrust of 460 kN. The same constant wind speed and direction, which is optimistic, was used for all the calculations with Flettner Rotors in this paper.

Kites were included, but this model is under development and so were approximated as providing 5% of the thrust required for a given ship speed. This modest gain is offset by their limited impact on deadweight.

Both Flettner Rotors and Kites were assumed to be not applicable on a container ship due to limited deck space and stability. For all other ship types Flettner Rotors were placed on deck above the bulkheads and between the holds, which are normally around 30 m apart.

5. Technology Combinations for 2050 Evaluated by the Whole Ship Model

Surveying the generalised estimates of the potential of technologies to improve ship energy efficiency, those technologies with higher reduction in emissions were selected to try to achieve a 90% reduction in ship energy usage. The 2050 combination of technologies are:

- Bulbous Bow (if required)
- Contra Rotating Propeller
- Stern Flap
- Air Lubrication
- Main Engine Turbo Compounding Parallel
- Aux Turbo Compounding Series
- Organic Rankine Cycle WHRS
- Flettner Rotors
- Kites
- Engine Derating
- Speed Control of Pumps and Fans

The above technologies were evaluated by the Whole Ship Model (WSM). For comparison purposes a combination of the existing technologies used by ship owners in 2015 (given in Section 2) were also evaluated by the WSM.

Three different ship types were considered:

- 4999 TEU Container Ship with a design speed of 25.1 knots.
- 53541 dwt Panamax Bulk carrier with a design speed of 15.3 knots
- 46249 dwt Tanker with a design speed of 14.8 knots

5.1. Variation in Fuel Consumption with Ship Speed

Figs.6 to 8 show how the fuel consumption (including auxiliary and boiler fuel use) of different loaded ship and technology combinations varies with speed. The impact of operational changes, such as reducing speed, can be assessed for given technological combinations from this data. It can be seen that the reduction in fuel consumption by combining technologies without wind produces maximum

reductions in fuel consumption between 10 and 20%. This is equivalent to operating the ships approximately 2 knots slower.

Figs.6 and 8 show that the reduction in fuel consumption for combinations of 2050 Technologies (without wind technologies) is similar to the savings from using combinations of technologies that ship owners were using in 2015. This indicates some degree of flexibility in the choice of technology when combining technologies. It also illustrates that the major reductions in emissions required in the most stringent scenario (90%) are unlikely to be achieved without the use of wind assistance, speed reduction, alternative fuels, or some other high-impact approach.

Fig.6: Fuel Consumption against speed for a 4999 TEU Container Ship fitted with different technology combinations

Fig.7: Fuel Consumption against speed for a 53541 dwt Panamax Bulk fitted with different technology combinations

Fig.8: Fuel Consumption against speed for a 46249 dwt Tanker fitted with different technology combinations.

It can be seen that the 2050 combination of Technologies has a higher fuel consumption compared to the 2015 combination at lower speeds. This is in some part due to the increase in auxiliary engine specific fuel consumption due to back pressure from turbo compounding of the auxiliary engine. This increase in auxiliary fuel consumption is also exacerbated by:

- The container ship, **Error! Reference source not found.**, having more installed auxiliary power than the tanker, **Error! Reference source not found.**
- Additional installed auxiliary power for air lubrication (and Flettner Rotors when installed).
- Turbo compounding in series being effective below 65% of the rated auxiliary power.

At higher speeds the increase in recovered waste heat due to turbo compounding in series complements the additional power required for air lubrication (and Flettner Rotors when installed). Note that the last bullet point here is actually an artefact of the way the technologies have been described in the WSM, the auxiliary engines can be sized better in the WSM by considering the combination of technologies that the ship will use, the WSM can also quickly run multiple versions of the same technology.

Figs.7 and 8 include the fuel consumption reduction from wind technologies, Flettner rotors were also plotted separately due to their large contribution to reducing fuel consumption. Even though the fuel consumption from wind technologies could vary considerably based on operational conditions, the calculated fuel consumption from using Flettner rotors on the slower bulk carrier and tanker is roughly comparable to that achieved by all the other technologies combined. Note that the findings here are subject to the assumptions used and the way their performance is modelled.

5.2. Ship Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator (EEOI) based on ship activity in 2010

The Ship Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator (EEOI) was calculated based on the average weighted operational speed of ships in 2010, from the 3rd IMO Greenhouse Gas study, *Smith et al. (2014)*, and ship utilisation information that was submitted to the IMO, *Smith et al. (2015)*.

The EEOI, as defined in *IMO MEPC Circ.684 (2009)*, is a measure of the cargo carrying efficiency of a ship, in terms of CO₂ emissions (Fuel Consumption × Carbon Factor) per cargo (m_{cargo}) × distance (D) travelled for each fuel (j) over a number of voyages (i):

$$\text{Average EEOI} = \frac{\sum_i \sum_j (FC_{ij} \times CF_j)}{\sum_i (m_{cargo,i} \times D_i)}$$

The average annual EEOI for a 4999 TEU container ship in 2010 shown in Table I was calculated based upon being 68% full for a loaded voyage with an average annual speed of 16.2 knots. For a 53541 dwt Panamax Bulk, shown in Table II, this is 90% full with a 11.9 knot average annual speed and for a 46249 dwt Tanker, shown in Table III, this is 81% full with a 11.7 knot average annual speed. The carbon factor of Heavy Fuel Oil from *IMO MEPC Circ.684 (2009)*.

Table I: 4999 TEU Container Ship EEOI in 2010 based on 68% utilisation

Technologies	Median EEOI for 16.3 knots (in 2010) Percentage change	EEOI if 25.1 knot Design Speed is used Percentage change
none fitted	0.0	0.0
Combination of Technologies used in 2015	-6.2	-15.8
2050 Combination without Wind	-1.0	-20.5

Table II: 53541 dwt Panamax Bulk EEOI in 2010, based on 90% utilisation

Technologies	Median EEOI 11.9 knots (in 2010) Percentage change	EEOI if 15.3 knot Design Speed is used Percentage change
none fitted	0	0
Flettner Rotors	-16.5	-11.5
Combination of Technologies used in 2015	-5.1	-12.7
2050 Combination without Wind	-5.9	-16.8
2050 Combination with Wind	-24.8	-31.0

Table III: 46249 dwt Tanker dwt Panamax Bulk EEOI in 2010, based on 81% utilisation

Technologies	Median EEOI 11.7 knots (in 2010) Percentage change	EEOI if 14.8 knot Design Speed is used Percentage change
none fitted	0	0
Flettner Rotors	-14.6	-11.5
Combination of Technologies used in 2015	-4.9	-11.4
2050 Combination without Wind	-5.1	-14.7
2050 Combination with Wind	-25.4	-30.0

The percentage change in calculated average annual EEOI will vary in the same way as fuel consumption. Tables I to III are useful to see what the reduction in EEOI would be from technologies in operation. In Table I, due to the 2050 technologies having an increasing fuel consumption at lower speeds and that a container ship in 2010 operated well below its design speed the combination of 2050 technologies is worse than the 2015 combination. For the Panamax Bulk in Table II they are about the same. At the lower speeds that Panamax Bulk ships operated at in 2010 the reduction in EEOI due to Flettner Rotors is approximately three times the percentage reduction in EEOI from the other three technologies. At the design speed of the Panamax Bulk ship they are similar.

6. Conclusions

This paper has summarised the Whole Ship Model (WSM), a holistic and extensible model developed by UCL for the Shipping in Changing Climates (SCC) project. The WSM allows the assessment of the performance and ship impact of a range of technologies over a range of ship types, design specifications and operational conditions. In this study, a limited set of technologies have been

evaluated against a projected, highly stringent, requirement to reduce the emissions from international shipping by 90% as part of a co-ordinated attempt to limit anthropogenic climate change to 2°C of warming.

6.1 Emissions Reduction

It was found that by combining technologies without wind and speed reduction, fuel consumption may be reduced by between 10 to 20%, although this requires multiple technologies to be adopted, in contrast to the current practice where few of the presently available technologies for efficiency improvement are being widely used. Wind assistance can provide further reductions in fuel consumption, but still far short of 90%. Meeting this challenging requirement will require a combination of technologies, speed reductions and fuel decarbonisation. Given the potentially higher costs of alternative fuels and the economic impacts of changing operational speeds, technologies that are currently seen as unattractive may become more widely adopted to help offset these issues. This has been considered in the application of energy saving technologies to warships (*Pawling et al, 2016*) where even unlikely technologies such as wind assistance were found to be justifiable considering the higher cost of naval fuels and fixed operational speeds.

6.2 Future Work

In this study, technologies and ships have been combined without optimisation, but the WSM allows individual technologies and ships to be quickly designed to work better together, by changing the technology models to represent different optimisation strategies. For example, WHRS could be optimised to perform at lower engine powers to reflect reduced ship speeds or “flexible steaming”. Such optimisation may be significant for technologies such as wind assistance, where the selection and sizing of Flettner Rotors or kites has thus far been assumed to be generic, rather than optimised for the ship size and operating profile. Simple line graphs were used here as relatively few technologies and ships were examined, but the WSM can generate large datasets containing many options and *Calleya et al. (2016)* presented a web-based approach for exploring these more expansive results.

6.2 Implications for Future Regulation

This work also has important implications for the EEDI discussion ongoing at the IMO assessing the potential energy saving from technologies allows for a path for future technologies and fuels to be developed. Having smaller savings from technologies does not mean regulation needs to be reduced.

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Design Considerations for Energy Efficient Electric Powerboats

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Abstract

Electrically driven vessels have gained ground in short-sea shipping as they are more reliable and friendly to the environment. Due to this, many design concepts for all-electric boats have come to surface during the last years. The target of this work is to highlight and focus on the major design and engineering challenges for powerboats with electric propulsion. In the first part of this paper, all the major design aspects that affect the performance of a powerboat will be discussed. Emphasis will be put on electric motor and drive selection, propeller optimization and to high power battery systems. In the second part of the paper, an actual study case of a 2.3m model powerboat fitted with a 2HP BLDC electric pod will be presented. For the selected study case an end-to-end simulation of the vessel's performance (hydrostatics, CFD and electrical system study) will be provided along with the test results deriving from the actual construction and trial of the powerboat model.

1. Introduction

Electric vessels are now a rapidly growing market due to new capability, evolution of electric motor and Energy Storage Systems(ESS) technologies, and stricter legislation regarding exhaust gas emissions from internal combustion engines. Recent research has shown that the market for electric water crafts, including those on and under water, will rapidly increase during the following years. In addition there is a market for electric outboard motors that will more than triple in value as high power pure electric versions become increasingly viable. Fig.1 below depicts the marine electrical vehicle market in US Billion \$ for 2013.

Fig.1: Marine Electrical Vehicle market in the US by application sector

This paper will only focus on surface boats destined for private or touristic use. The first part of this work will cover the basic design aspects of an electric powerboat with respect to energy efficiency, environmental impact and the optimal management of the energy/propulsion chain. In this context, alternative power sources, such as high energy density battery systems and fuel cells, power conversion systems and electric propulsion motors will be discussed. In the second part of the paper, an actual study case of a 2.3m model powerboat fitted with a 2HP BLDC electric pod will be presented. For the selected study case an end-to-end simulation of the vessel's performance (hydrostatics, CFD and electrical system study) will be provided along with the test results deriving from the actual construction and trial of the powerboat model.

2. Electric powerboat design

This chapter will cover the main challenges that emerge from the choice of integrating an all-electric powertrain to a powerboat. As it is easily understood, the main design aim for a powerboat is to have a relatively light, reliable, comfortable, safe and very fast boat that in most occasions will cover small distances. By choosing to power the boat with an electric motor, most of the above mentioned checklist is ticked as the newest trends in electric machinery design indicate that the motors for electric propulsion can be light and compact, produce less noise compared to the conventional diesel/gasoline engines, very efficient ($\eta > 90\%$) and reliable. The power source for these motors can be a diesel generator, something that is mostly encountered in LNG carriers and cruise ships but rarely in pleasure crafts, high energy density battery packs, which is most common case for power boats or fuel cells. In all cases, the power is delivered to the motor through a power electronics converter, which is often called electronic speed controller (ESC). The purpose of the converter is to regulate the power that flows through the electric motor and control the speed and torque at the motor shaft. Fig.2 below shows the components for a direct, all-electric propulsion system for small crafts.

Fig.2: Basic components of the electric propulsion system of a small craft

The above mentioned topology presents many advantages for small vessels such as ease of installation, design flexibility regarding the specific needs of each customer (desired power, maximum cruise range), and low operation cost. However, the two major disadvantages of this system is the equipment arrangement problem, as batteries take a lot of space and the higher installation cost. In the subchapters below, all the components of the EPS will be discussed separately and the arrangement problem will be addressed.

2.1. Main Energy Sources

2.1.1. Diesel Generators

The main parts of a marine Diesel generator set are the Diesel prime mover, the speed governor, the synchronous machine and its exciter. The block diagram of a Diesel Generator is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3: Diesel Generator Set block diagram

This system has two closed-loop feedback control systems: a speed feedback control system and an excitation feedback control system. These two feedback loops, ensure that the synchronous generator will operate at a steady speed and generate power at a fixed electrical frequency and voltage. The produced power is controlled via appropriate regulation of the field winding current. A detailed description of a diesel generator model can be found in *Luo (2011)*.

2.1.2. Batteries

The battery systems which intend to serve as a main energy source for the propulsion motor, have big differences with conventional batteries that are used for ignition, sparking or emergency lighting, because they are designed to give power over sustained periods of time. Deep cycle batteries are used instead of SLI batteries for these applications. Traction batteries must be designed with a high ampere-hour capacity. Batteries for electric vehicles are characterized by their relatively high power-to-weight ratio, energy to weight ratio and energy density; smaller, lighter batteries reduce the weight of the vessel and improve its performance. Compared to liquid fuels, most current battery technologies have much lower specific energy; and this often impacts on the maximum range. However, metal-air batteries have high specific energy because the cathode is provided by the surrounding oxygen in the air. Rechargeable batteries used in electric ship applications include lead-acid ("flooded", Deep cycle, and VRLA), NiCd, nickel metal hydride, lithium ion, Li-ion polymer, and, less commonly, zinc-air and molten salt batteries. The amount of electricity (i.e. electric charge) stored in batteries is measured in ampere hours (Ah), with the total energy often measured in watt hours (Wh)

In order to determine the maximum range that the batteries can offer for a specific electric vessel application, the required parameters that need to be provided are: 1)Power needs(kW) 2)Battery Capacity(kWh), battery's State of Charge(%) and the vessel's resistance characteristics(N). The equation and Fig.4 below describe how the maximum range/cruising time at a specific speed are provided:

$$t_{operation} = \frac{SOC \times E_1}{E_2 + DHP(V_n)}$$

E1 is the battery's total energy rating (kWh), SOC is the State of Charge as a fraction of 100%, E2 is the absorbed power and DHP is the delivered horsepower at the motor(kW).

Fig.4: Battery Selection Process and Maximum Cruising time calculation for battery ships

2.2 Propulsion Motors

The majority of the motors that are used as propulsion engines in leisure crafts are induction motors due to low cost, high reliability and low maintenance. However, during the last five years permanent magnet motors seem to gain more ground due to their very high efficiency, compact and light design but tend to be more expensive and have smaller lifespan. Electric propulsion motors exist in the market mainly in the form of pods or outboard engines, Fig.5. Currently the outboard engines are limited to small power ratings (10-100HP) while pods extend from a few kW to several MWs.

Fig.5: a) Electric outboard motor b) electric pod for propulsion

2.3 Power converters as efficiency improving interfaces

Power converters (often also called as VFD's standing for Variable Frequency Drives) are most often used to supply electric motors in order to keep either the motor torque constant or the motor power constant, Fig.6. The goal of using VFD's is to reduce the iron (or no-load) losses of the motor which are voltage dependent, and, hence, remain constant upon connection to network. On the contrary, there is a second term of losses, the load losses (or copper losses) which depend on the operating level of the motor and the feeding current.

Fig.6: VFD torque control

If the motor operates at partially loading conditions, i.e. the load losses are smaller than the maximum ones (corresponding to the full load) it is beneficial to reduce the applied voltage in an attempt to reduce the no-load losses, too. As it has been discussed in *Mohan et al. (2003)*, the introduction of VFD's lead to significant reduction of the energy demands of the motor in terms of both active and reactive power. Thus, the power converter can be adjusted to perform both:

- Optimized torque/power-speed control
- Optimized loss control

Therefore, the converter can trace the operating point of the motor via measuring the input current which affects the load losses (they are proportional to the square value of the current magnitude) and adjust the applied voltage so that the iron losses are equal to the load losses.

3. Case study: the construction and testing of an all-electric powerboat model

In this chapter, the construction and testing process of a battery powerboat is described as it was created to race in the Hydrocontest 2016 competition, flagship event of the Hydros Foundation, an international student competition dedicated to naval energy efficiency which is hosted annually by Hydros Foundation in Lausanne, CH. The design and construction was done by the students of the school of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering. The project that was chosen to be implemented is that of a 2.2m planing monohull. In the subchapters below the design, calculation and construction processes will be presented. Also, the test results for the vessel, for the runs made in Lake Geneva will be presented.

3.1 Hydrostatics and main loading conditions

In this chapter, the main hydrostatic characteristics for the hull of the vessel are calculated. In addition, Full Load Departure is presented. AVEVA Marine has been selected for the entire process. Fig.7 depicts the vessel’s hull. The main dimensions of the hull are listed in Table 1. Fig.8 shows the sectional area curves for various drafts.

Fig.7: NTUA planing boat bare hull

Table 1: Main dimensions of Oceanos hull

Length Overall	2.310 m
Length W.L.	1.95 m
Breadth	0.543 m
Depth	0.245 m
Design Draft	0.11 m
Displacement at Load Draft	51 kg
Lightship Weight	10.89 kg
Deadweight at Load Draft	40.11 kg
LCG (measured from transom)	0.79 m
Deadrise angle	19°
Maximum Beam at chine Bcmax	0.428 m

Table 2: Drafts at equilibrium angle (Full Load Condition)

Draft at LCF	0.111 m
Draft at AP	0.109 m
Draft at FP	0.114 m
Mean draft at midships	0.111 m

In this subchapter Full Load Conditions (hull, rudder, batteries, controller, electronics, servos, and two 10kg loads representing the cargo of the vessel) characteristics are presented. Moreover, this scenario is checked for stability in terms of GZ curves. AVEVA Hydrostatics & Hydrodynamics has been selected for the relative calculations. The present condition is referred to Lightship and the two 10 kg loads.

Fig.8: Longitudinal, vertical center of buoyancy coordinates, longitudinal center of flotation coordinate of Oceanos hull as function of draft

Fig.9: Block, prismatic, midship section and waterplane area coefficient as function of draft

Table 3: Hydrostatics at equilibrium angle (Full Load Condition).

Trim by the bow	0.005 m
KG	0.061 m
FSC	0.000 m
KGf	0.061 m
GMt	0.299 m
BMt	0.264 m
BMI	4.350 m
Waterplane area	0.81 m ²
LCG	0.788 m
LCB	0.789 m
TCB	0.000 m
LCF	0.886 m

Table 4: Righting Level (GZ) curve (Full Load Condition).

Heel to Stbd	GZ	Slope	Trim
0°	0.0000 m	0.2989 m/rad	0.004 m
5°	0.0269 m	0.3094 m/rad	0.002 m
10°	0.0549 m	0.3185 m/rad	-0.000 m
15°	0.0732 m	0.2364 m/rad	0.003 m
20°	0.1001 m	0.2313 m/rad	-0.003 m
25°	0.1093 m	0.1862 m/rad	0.001 m
30°	0.1235 m	0.1523 m/rad	-0.000 m
35°	0.1343 m	0.1044 m/rad	-0.006 m
40°	0.1411 m	0.0645 m/rad	-0.013 m

Fig.10: GZ- heel curve of Oceanos hull (Full Load condition)

3.2 Resistance Prediction

The present chapter contains numerical results and diagrams related to resistance of the bare hull. Two methods have been selected for the estimations, the towing tank method and an empirical approach based on Savitsky method. In this subchapter resistance values are the result of towing tank tests at the towing tank of NTUA Laboratory of Naval and Marine hydrodynamics. The results are aimed to a specific displacement and longitudinal value of the center of gravity at various speeds, fresh water conditions. Towing resistance, trim and heave of the hull were extracted from experiments and a prediction of effective horse power is made.

Fig.11: Towing tank resistance as function of speed of Oceanos hull

Table 5: Towing tank resistance and trim of Oceanos hull as function of speed.

Vspeed	Resistance	trim
2.002 m/s	2.936 kp	0.86°
2.505 m/s	4.572 kp	2.46°
2.999 m/s	5.141 kp	2.77°
3.500 m/s	5.674 kp	2.95°
4.007 m/s	6.296 kp	3.42°
4.508 m/s	6.845 kp	4.13°
4.783 m/s	6.969 kp	4.43°
5.079 m/s	7.025 kp	4.65°
5.245 m/s	7.075 kp	4.62°

Savitsky empirical approach remains until today a solid basis for resistance estimation of planning hulls. In order to compare the extracted results of the method with those of the towing tank's one, the same condition (fresh water, variation of speed, displacement) have been used. Table 12 shows the comparison between the two methods.

Table 6: Comparison between resistance values of Savitsky method and Towing Tank tests

Vspeed(m/s)	Rtowing test	Rsavitsky
2.002 m/s	2.936 kp	4.230 kp
2.505 m/s	4.572 kp	4.941 kp
2.999 m/s	5.141 kp	5.656 kp
3.500 m/s	5.674 kp	6.170 kp
4.007 m/s	6.296 kp	6.552 kp
4.508 m/s	6.845 kp	6.834 kp
4.783 m/s	6.969 kp	6.935 kp

Fig.12: Comparison between resistance values of Savitsky method and Towing Tank tests

Numeca Computational Fluid Dynamics software was also used to enable quick efficient simulation, in order to evaluate the above results for a given speed. The same condition (fresh water, variation of speed, displacement) has been used. Fig.13 shows the mesh has been made for the simulation and Fig.14 the representation of the CFD simulation.

Fig.13: Mesh Generation

Fig.14: CFD snapshot for $V=5$ m/s

3.3 Electrical System & Propulsion

The electric propulsion scheme that was implemented is the one that was proposed in chapter 2 for powerboats. As a main power source a 48V, 20Ah LiMn battery was used, which was connect to a 1kW DC/AC converter (Electronic Speed Controller) with a 60A fuse in between. The speed controller was directly connected to a 1.4kW Electric Pod which was mounted below the vessel's hull. Directly attached to the motor shaft a 1kW, 230mm diameter, two bladed adjustable pitch propeller was installed. The propeller characteristics from pitch = 120mm to 178mm are depicted in Fig.15.

The final vessel that was constructed based on this system and these parameters can be found in Figs.16 and 17.

Fig.15: Propeller open water characteristics, x marks efficiency, ● is K_t and ■ is $10.K_q$

Fig.16: Constructed Vessel

Fig.17: Vessel trial at Lac Lemman, Lausanne

3.4 Trials and Results

The vessel trials we conducted in the school's towing tanks and at open water in Lac Lemman in Switzerland. During each phase of the trial the vessel's batteries were fully charged. In order to be controlled, as an input to the ESC a 2.4 GHz digital receiver was connected. The receiver's signals were separated in two channels one for thruster operation and one for maneuvering. The thruster signal was a 4-20 mA signal with 10 mA being idle, 4 mA full backwards and 20 mA full forward. The same philosophy was applied to the signal that controlled the servo motor of the rudder.

There were three test scenarios: a) a small course drag race with the propeller pitch being set in 147mm to determine maximum speed and steady state current b) a small course drag race with the propeller pitch being set in 178mm for the same reason as a. and c) a long distance race course with medium cruising speed to determine the energy efficiency of the boat.

- During the first case the boat began to plan at 3 m/s and reached instantaneously a speed of 6m/s and then reached steady state speed of 4.7 m/s. The current that the motor was absorbing was 28 A and the electronics with the use of an external cooling system maintained a steady temperature of 50° C.
- During the second case the boat began to plan at 3 m/s and reached instantaneously a speed of 7 m/s but steady state speed was reduced at 4 m/s. The current that the motor was absorbing was 33A and the electronics with the use of an external cooling system maintained a steady temperature of 56° C with a rising trend. Also the boat stopped several times unexpectedly, probably because the motor could not provide the sufficient torque to the propeller.
- During the energy efficiency trial the boat did not plan and maintained a steady speed of 1.8m/s for two consecutive hours. The current that the battery was providing was 9 A which finally reached 14 A as the battery was totally discharged. The vessel was able to run for 2hours with some stops to prevent overheating. The temperature rose up to 70° C where it was manually stopped for less than a minute only for safety reasons. The energy consumption for 14km distance was 1 kWh which is equivalent to 82 g oil. (1 t Oil Equivalent is approximately 11 MWh)

In the figures below the data from the converter's black box show the results of the first study case.

Fig.17: Motor Current during accelerations and steady state for 0-100% of power with P=147mm

Fig.18: Controller temperature.

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Index by Authors

Albert	458	Halliday	141	Roberts	262
Almeter	32	Harries	458	Romano	164
Aloniati	523	Hashimoto	283	Roncin	443
Andrews	47,62	Hassani	247	Sahoo	62
Atlar		Hekkenberg	152,225	Savio	202,247
Autret	415	Hildebrandt	458	Sayers	271
Auzins	342	Hill	141	Schrader	187
Avala	62	Jochum	443	Schreiner	131
Bakirtzoglou	523	Johannesson	236	Schultz	477
Barros	477	Kajihama	380	Sellier	473
Begovic	491	Katayama	380	Selvik	247
Behrel	443	Konstantinou	523	Sender	504
Benatmane		Kourmpelis	523	Silberschmidt	236
Bergsma	428	Kramer	202	Smith	510
Bertesago	172	Kumagai	262	Soncini	7
Bertorello	491	Le Poole	225	Spathis	523
Bertram	10,271	Leroux	443	Spiraj	523
Beuss	504	Li	108	Steen	202,247
Bigi	443	Liu	108	Stenzel	131
Blanca	62	Lyridis	523	Stübing	131
Boogaard	225	Mascellaro	25	Suarez	510
Borusevitch	94	Meissner	504	Sverchkov	94
Brede	355	Mino	283	Tachikawa	380
Brinkmann	131	Monteiro	386	Taen	152
Calleya	510	Montel	443	Takahashi	262
Cannavacciuolo	331	Morais	297	Tasker	236
Ceccio	477	Murai	262	Themelakis	523
Coats	77	Murphy	77	Thill	317
Dahl	415	Nagel	355	Toda	283
Danese	297	Nême	443	Trincas	94
Deniz	193	Okada	380	Tsarsitalidis	523
Eggers	366	Okazaki	380	Tuteja	477
Eggert	504	Otheguy	152	Tzanetos	523
Eimanis	342	Overbeek	225	Valenti	115
Eriksson	415	Pappas	236	Waldie	297
Etienne	164	Parlier	443	Waller	415
Fach	311	Paternoster	331	Weymouth	401
Feys	225	Pawling	510	Wulf	355
Fountouli	523	Perlin	477	Xiao	108
Friebe	415	Prousalidis	523	Yebra	217
Gaspar	386	Pruyn	428	Zalm	428
Golovin	477	Pullin	141	Zincir	193
Gose	477	Pustoshny	94		
Grelon	443	Rahman	283		
Grigoropoulos	523	Ravina	115,172		
Halliday	141	Reyer	458		
Harries	458	Riley	77		

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